

Document Title	DOI	Abstract	Author Keywords	PDF Link	Accepted	Declined	Justificativa
Design and Practice of Blended Teaching Model of Engineering Professional Courses based on Outcome-based Education	10.1109 /ICET59358. 2023.10424121	In the context of engineering education, to improve the practical engineering skills of engineering students, the teaching ideas and implementation methods of the curriculum are designed based on Outcome-based Education. A blended teaching approach was used to design the implementation process to achieve the curriculum objectives. In this paper, we explain the process of blended teaching from the two aspects of basic knowledge and competency training. Active learning of basic knowledge is implemented based on a three-step blended teaching model before, after, and during classes. It adopts the project-driven learning approach of the flipped classroom model and cultivates students' ability to solve complex engineering problems through collaborative group and intra-group mutual assessment. Based on the original objective assessment of the curriculum and under the current teaching model, we design a diversified evaluation approach to comprehensively assess the effectiveness of student competence achievement. Practice has shown that project-based inquiry-based teaching methods based on the flipped classroom model can promote learning outcomes for students and increase their interest in learning. It avoids the blind and aimless theoretical learning process of the student and improves the practical ability of the student. The methods and means of instruction of teachers have been further extended, and the ability of students to learn independently has been improved.	Curriculum Teaching Reform; Blended Learning;Project-based inquiry learning; Outcome-based Education; Flipped classroom	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10424121	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não fala sobre engenharia de software
Improving Teamwork in Software Engineering Projects in Higher Education	10.1109 /FIE58773. 2023.10343476	In computing science (CS) education, software programming and software engineering subjects are parts of core CS subjects where students learn various programming languages and software development life cycle (SDLC). With the aim of equipping students with the necessary project skills and experiences essential for workplaces, Institutes of Higher Learning (IHL) have increasingly adopted the educational practice of bringing real-world team-based projects in the curriculum. Such software projects commonly support the use of Agile process practices, which place more emphasis on communications and teamwork among students in a team, stakeholders and industry customers. This could be manageable for small scale projects where student teams are in their learning journey with active and continuous communications with customers, while developing the necessary cohesion within the team to facilitate incremental deliverables of their software products. However, teamwork remains a bottleneck that is difficult to be consistently realized among members in group projects. It is not easy to motivate and measure all team members working towards the common goals or complete project tasks on time. As such, this paper proposes the Weekly Team Assessment (WTA) framework to continuously encourage teamwork throughout the software project development duration. We also propose the settings of dedicated leadership and constructive feedback iteratively in the WTA framework. The proposed methods have been applied and evaluated through the experiments in two software engineering modules, Professional Software Development and Team Project, involving 50 sophomore CS students who are divided into control group and experimental group equally. Experiment results are analyzed and discussed in this paper. Positive outcomes are observed from the experiment where about 72% of participants appreciate the proposed methods in improving their teamwork in group projects. The degree of effectiveness of the proposed methods is further evaluated from three aspects in the experiment.	Teamwork;software engineering education;team projects;software development life cycle;higher education	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10343476	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
SEE_ME: Software Engineering Education Methodology Exploration	10.1109/TALE. 2015.7386014	Software Engineering is a primary subject in many computer science departments of universities worldwide. Its purpose is to help students understand and apply both disciplined and systematic methods to software development. Due to the ubiquity and visibility of software in the modern world, the study, education and research into software engineering and its practice have retained a high level of interest. Distinct in nature from other computer science courses, this discipline borrows from and is influenced by other fields such as, systems analysis, design, management, quality control, and communication. In this paper, the practices and methodologies used, developed, and evaluated in the Software Engineering Education (SEE) will be outlined. Further improvements have been planned through the Software Engineering Education Methodology Exploration (SEE_ME) project.	Software engineering; software engineering education;whole person education;software development process	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7386014	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não aborda colaboração ou soft skills

Impact of outcome-based education on software engineering teaching: A case study	10.1109/TALE.2017.8252344	This paper investigates the impact of outcome-based education (OBE) on students' learning achievement from a software engineering (SE) program. It is not easy to transform an SE curriculum from traditional knowledge-based education (KBE) method to OBE method since it requires us to identify the outcomes clearly and map the outcomes with the expected capabilities of students. We first give a briefing on our SE program and outline the curriculum, then investigate the impact of OBE in two selected courses in SE program, with the completion of one course being the prerequisite for admission into the other one. Experimental results show that OBE can greatly improve the learning effectiveness of students and teaching quality.	Outcome-based education; Software Engineering; Information Technology curriculum	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8252344	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não aborda colaboração ou soft skills
Scrumming with Educators: Cross-Departmental Collaboration for a Summer Software Engineering Capstone	10.1109/LaTiCE.2015.13	This paper describes the design of a 10-week summer software engineering capstone course that provides a service learning opportunity through cross-departmental collaboration. The projects for this course centered on developing software products to support education faculty in their work in the greater university area. This paper will also discuss how Scrum was implemented over a 10-week summer semester, the outcomes and challenges of cross-departmental collaboration, the types of projects created for education faculty, and the advantages of connecting software engineering capstone courses with education faculty.	software engineering education;interdisciplinary collaboration;educational technology;service learning	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7126244	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	nã tem avaliação
SETAP: Software engineering teamwork assessment and prediction using machine learning	10.1109/FIE.2014.7044199	Effective teaching of teamwork skills in local and globally distributed Software Engineering (SE) teams is recognized as an important part of the education of current and future software engineers. Effective methods for assessment and early prediction of learning effectiveness in SE teamwork are not only a critical part of teaching but also of value in industrial training and project management. This paper presents a novel analytical approach to the assessment and, most importantly, the prediction of learning outcomes in SE teamwork based on data from our joint software engineering class concurrently taught at San Francisco State University (SFSU), Florida Atlantic University (FAU) and Fulda University, Germany (Fulda). Our approach focuses on assessment and prediction of SE teamwork in terms of ability of student teams to apply best SE processes and develop SE products. It differs from existing work in the following aspects: a) it develops and uses only objective and quantitative measures of team activity from multiple sources, such as statistics of student time use, software engineering tool use, and instructor observations; b) it leverages powerful machine learning (ML) techniques applied to team activity measurements to identify quantitative and objective factors which can assess and predict learning of software engineering teamwork skills at the team level. In this paper we provide the following contributions: a) we present in detail for the first time the full team activity measurement data set we developed, consisting of over 40 objective and quantitative measures extracted from student teams working on class projects; b) we present a ML framework which applies the Random Forest (RF) algorithm to the team activity measurements and team outcomes, focusing on predicting teams that are likely to fail; c) we describe in detail our now fully implemented and operational data processing pipeline, consisting of data collection methods from multiple sources, ML training database creation, and ML analysis subsystems; and finally d) we present very preliminary results of ML analysis results based on the data from our joint software engineering classes in Fall 2012, and Spring 2013, with the data from 17 student teams. While our ML training database is currently small, it continuously grows. Our preliminary results, verified with two independent accuracy measures, show that RF is able to predict SE Process and SE Product team performance in intuitively explainable manner.	Assessment;Software Engineering Teamwork; Machine Learning;Education	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7044199	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

Exploring Peer Evaluation Methods in Group Projects of Software Engineering Education	10.1109 /FIE61694. 2024.10893587	This Innovative Practice category full paper proposes an innovative approach to enhance peer evaluations in group-based learning. It aims at enhancing the overall peer assessment experience for students in software engineering education. In the software industry, it is all about teamwork for software development projects. There is a need to nurture students to work collaboratively in group-based learning. The collaborative milieu inherent in group projects has long been acknowledged within the sphere of software engineering education. In our university, students are cultivated the effective teamwork within the purview of CSC2101 - Professional Software Development and Team Projects (PSD & TP1), an undergraduate course in the domain of software engineering. The terrain of software group projects still presents its own array of obstacles, such as unequal contributions, internal conflicts, peer evaluation mechanism, etc. This paper first discusses the limitations of the current peer evaluation methods in this course. Next, the proposed methodology is presented that embodies four key elements: transparency, anonymity, structured assessment, and qualitative feedback. The implementation details of the proposed approaches are then described consisting of the following features and mechanisms: online platform, anonymous profiles, public results, and structured evaluation forms. The rationales for the proposed peer evaluation techniques are discussed. The experiment studies are conducted involving 40 students in our university. It includes numerous characteristics of the peer evaluation experience in order to gain a full picture of existing peer evaluation approaches within software engineering education. The survey results show a generally positive mentality toward the proposed features.	Group-based learning;peer assessment;peer evaluation approaches;software engineering education	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10893587	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Teaching and learning software project management: A hands-on approach	10.1109/FIE. 2014.7044331	Education invariably aims at developing competencies, technical as well as non-technical ones. As a consequence, there is also a need for methods that can be used to assess the quality of education faithfully. One possible approach is an assessment of whether intended learning outcomes are achieved, i.e. an investigation if the target audience possesses the desired competencies. Assessment of competencies, however, is tricky since competencies are often only vaguely defined. This paper presents SECAT, an approach to assess competencies, and particularly those needed for proper software engineering. To that end, SECAT builds on Rauner's approach for competency assessment in vocational education. Rauner's approach uses nine competency criteria, which are further refined by suitable issues that indicate to which extent a competency is, or should be, present. The main contribution of this paper lies in the adaptation and enhancement of this framework in order to make it useable in software engineering education. Adaptation and enhancements encompass issues such as team and individual assessments, integration of multiple perspectives from various groups of stakeholders, and product- and process-orientation. The paper also presents first insights from using SECAT in a pilot university course in software engineering.	software engineering; software engineering education;assessment and evaluation approaches; quality of teaching and learning;didactical approaches;evaluation of didactical approaches; competence-orientation; SECAT	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7044331	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração ou soft skills
Bridging the gap between ABET outcomes and industry expectations — A case study on software engineering course	10.1109/MITE. 2014.7020273	The role of ABET accreditation system is quite significant in providing guidance towards program and course design. The program outcomes encompassing through knowledge, skill and attitude play an important role towards competency development of the students. To improve the employability quotient of these fresh graduates, the alignment of respective outcomes along with the base lined expectations of IT industry is needed. In this context Software Engineering (SE) plays an important role in the transformation journey of the graduates to become entry level developers. It also helps to bridge the gap between academia and IT industry so that these new hires are productive as soon as possible. In this paper, the expectations of an IT industry from the new hires is described in conjunction with ABET educational outcomes highlighting pedagogical aspects that enable students develop these abilities. SE course is used as vehicle and an approach is presented integrating software code of ethics (recommended by ACM - IEEE), SE principles, pedagogical aspects and assessment instruments. Subsequently experiences from our corporate learning environment are highlighted.	Engineering Education; Outcome based education; Pedagogy;Bloom's taxonomy	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7020273	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Hints on Designing and Running Project-based Exams for a Software Engineering Course	10.1145 /3524487. 3527355	In this paper, we share our experience in designing and running a project-based exam for a Software Engineering course at the undergraduate level. We underline the teaching objectives and content of the course which aim to prepare students for the industrial environment, e.g., various design perspectives on the project, software quality assurance and evaluation, tools for development and software quality assessment, project management and team work. We present our project-based exam and summarize hints on its design, organization, and evaluation. Project examples are also introduced.	Software engineering; education;software engineering course;project; project-based course	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9853559	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração ou soft skills

An Exploration of Curriculum Teaching Reform in the Electromagnetic Field Course Based on the Idea of Engineering Education Professional Certification	10.1109/PIERS-Spring46901.2019.9017557	Engineering education professional certification is an important starting point for improving the quality of engineering education in China. According to the requirements of engineering education certification for the major of electronic and information engineering, we have decomposed the teaching objective of the electromagnetic field course and discussed the reform of teaching methods and examination methods. The teaching reform will effectively mobilize the enthusiasm of students, improve students' learning interest, cultivate students' engineering practice ability, and strengthen the teaching effect. It will promote the engineering education certification of the major of electronic and information engineering in our school.		https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9017557	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração ou soft skills
Leveraging Peer-Assessment in Project-Based Software Engineering Courses	10.1109/CSEET62301.2024.10663031	Higher educational institutions seek to improve the quality and the productivity of the educational process. The current attitude is toward involving students in the learning and evaluation process. Peer review has been proven to be one of the most effective tactics to attain this in software engineering disciplines wherein project-based courses are substantial to afford high quality competencies. A few studies in literature empirically studied the impact of peer review in project-based software engineering courses. In this work, we attempt to provide more insights by implementing peer assessment in one of the project-based courses offered by the Department of Software Engineering at the Hashemite University, Jordan, that is "Object-Oriented Software Development". In this paper, we investigate the validity of peer assessment by examining how well students in this course evaluate their peers and how the strength of students affects their assessment. The work also embeds a rubric that comprises key criteria to assess software system modelling. The results of the study reveal promising signs of using peer assessment in project-based software engineering courses.	peer-assessment;peer evaluation;peer-review; software engineering education;UML;rubric; project-based courses	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10663031	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração ou soft skills
From Explaining How Random Forest Classifier Predicts Learning of Software Engineering Teamwork to Guidance for Educators	10.1109/FIE.2018.8659102	This Research Full Paper builds on our previous research in Software Engineering (SE) Teamwork Assessment and Prediction project (SETAP) where we used Random Forest (RF) classifier to predict with over 70% accuracy the student learning effectiveness in software engineering teamwork based on 115 objective and quantitative Team Activity Measures (TAM). These TAM measures have been obtained from monitoring and measuring activities of 74 student teams during the creation of their final class project in a joint software engineering classes which ran concurrently at three universities (San Francisco State University, Fulda University and Florida Atlantic University) over the period of four years and, together with team outcomes, have been collected in publicly available SETAP database. In this paper, we provide much deeper analysis of how and why RF made its decisions, namely we address the explainability of our RF classification. We also provide in-depth analysis of differences in grading and behavior of local and global student teams (composed of students from multiple schools). We then use these insights to provide concrete and practical guidance to educators teaching SE teamwork in local and global classroom setting.	Assessment;Machine Learning;software engineering teamwork education;Random Forest; explainability;global software engineering	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8659102	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração ou soft skills
From an International Classroom to a Distributed Work Environment: Student Perspectives on Global Software Engineering	10.1109/TALE.2018.8615225	Global software engineering is an established field and software engineering educators must teach the software developers of tomorrow, who will work in distributed work environments, how to deal with temporal, geographical and sociocultural differences. This paper highlights several issues in software engineering teaching, as well as practicalities of software development, from the perspective of a group of students belonging to various cultural backgrounds.	multicultural instruction; global software engineering; software development process	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8615225	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração ou soft skills
Assessment and Feedback Under Disruptive Circumstances in Trans-National Education	10.1109/TALE48869.2020.9368427	The COVID-19 pandemic outbreak and the lock-down and social distancing strategies adopted to contain it have drastically affected our daily lives and the routine businesses. Provision of educational services in a continuous and useful manner in such circumstances is a massive challenge and requires innovative methods. Effective assessment and feedback play a pivotal role in traditional teaching and learning approaches and it is of even more vital importance in disruptive conditions. This paper discusses different assessment and feedback techniques in the online delivery of higher education courses in lockdown scenarios. The effectiveness of these approaches is evaluated through qualitative and quantitative study of student and staff feedback for an engineering course being delivered as part of a transnational education (TNE) program. In the light of the results, recommendations are made to improve the assessment and feedback activities in disruptive circumstances.	COVID-19;Higher education; Assessment and Feedback; Online teaching;Disruptive circumstances;Transnational education	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9368427	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração ou soft skills

Learning Experiences and Analysis in Professional Software Development Subject	10.1109 /TALE54877. 2022.00123	Software Engineering or professional software development (PSD) course is an important subject in Computing Science of higher education. It teaches the theory knowledge on software development life cycle (SDLC). The students will also be taught to use appropriate quality assurance techniques, continuous integration, continuous development, software version control, and appropriate configuration management techniques, etc. In the curriculum of the joint degree programme of University of Glasgow and Singapore Institute of Technology, the PSD course which teaches theory of SDLC is offered concurrently with another course named Team Projects that students work in groups for software companies on real software development projects. During the learning journey in the courses of PSD and Team Projects, students have undergone different thoughts and experiences. In this paper, analyses are conducted to provide views and opinions regarding the learning journey for both courses. Limitations of the current learning methods are discussed in this paper, together with the proposed ideas to boost the learning effectiveness of PSD and Team Projects to benefit the next student cohorts.	Learning effectiveness; Professional Software Development; Team Projects; learning journey; higher education	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10148289	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração ou soft skills
Teaching Generic Competences in Software Engineering via E-Learning – An Evaluation	10.1109 /TALE48869. 2020.9368446	It is challenging to represent the discipline 'Software Engineering' in higher education. Software development projects imply a complexity on several sectors and therefore require different skills. In addition to the professional competences, generic competences also play an important role. This paper deals with the training of generic competences in higher education with the help of an e-learning module, which was first established in summer semester 2019 and is available to the students as learning content in a Moodle course. In addition, data was collected in the summer term 2019 and the didactic setting was adapted and improved on the basis of this knowledge. So the changes in summer semester 2020 could be evaluated again. In this paper the data of 2019 and 2020 are compared in order to be able to assess the effectiveness of the changes of the didactical setting of the e-learning concept and, if necessary, to make further targeted improvements.	e-learning; generic competences; software engineering; higher education	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9368446	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração ou soft skills
Massive open online courses in software engineering education	10.1109/FIE. 2017.8190588	Despite the popularity of MOOCs in providing opportunities for socialization, collaboration, and professional improvement, there has been little research exploring them in the context of Software Engineering Education (SEE). The purpose of this study is to provide a better understanding of practices and challenges when developing academic software engineering MOOCs. To this end, we research (i) how MOOCs in SEE are designed and (ii) what learning design considerations educators and learning designers have when developing SEE-related MOOCs. To address the first research question, a systematic mapping is performed to outline the current landscape. The second research question is answered by analyzing and reflecting on practical experiences acquired during the design of a MOOC on Agile Software Development. The design of the course was based on the Pedagogical Design Pattern Framework for MOOCs, an approach to design for learning that was defined in our previous studies. For this course, two environments were considered: (a) course-time on the Tim Tec MOOC platform for deeper engagement with active learning activities, such as Project-based learning; (b) a Facebook group as a social and collaborative learning space, including scenarios based on problem-based learning to activate prior knowledge. Some of the pedagogical strategies adopted to motivate self-regulated learning included self-introduction video, diary, diagnostic self-assessments, development of small projects alone and in pairs. Our findings provide evidence that there are still several technological and pedagogical challenges that need to be addressed so as to enhance the MOOCs learning experience for SEE. Technological issues identified include the development of tools and educational games, which should be integrated into MOOCs, and the use of learning analytics to support motivation, user experience, and more active learning in specific topics, such as Project Management, Agile Methods, and Requirements Engineering. In turn, the most significant and needed improvement to the pedagogical aspects is a re-thinking of the virtual moment in the MOOC platform so as to optimize it through activities that promote active learning and contextualized assessments.	MOOCs; Software Engineering Education; Agile Software Development; Lifelong Learning; Learning Design; Design Patterns	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8190588	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não avalia colab
Content and Temporal Analysis of Communications to Predict Task Cohesion in Software Development Global Teams	10.1109 /ICGSEW. 2016.24	This dissertation proposal describes a study of interaction-based measures and their ability to predict cohesion within global software development projects. Messages were collected from six software development projects that involved students from different countries. The similarities and quantities of such interactions will be computed and analyzed. The tested measures will be analyzed at individual and group level. Similarly, content features based on communication categories, found in virtual learning teams, will be used to improve the identification of task cohesion level. Finally, temporal interaction similarity measures will be calculated to assess its prediction capabilities in a global setting.	Teamwork; Collaboration; Virtual teams	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7579488	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	

Educating Reflective Systems Developers at Scale: Towards “productive feedback” in a semi-capstone large-scale software engineering course	10.1109 /FIE56618. 2022.9962726	Feedback is critical in education. This Innovative Practice Full Paper reports lessons learned from improving the quality of feedback in a semi-capstone software engineering course, with particular focus on how to deliver productive feedback in large scale during project work. The bachelor-level introduction to software engineering course is taken by about 500 students from eight study programs, organised into 72 project teams. The course aims to educate reflective systems developers. The teaching staff includes 29 teaching assistants as supervisor and product owners for teams. Project teams get feedback on seven deliverables as part of formative portfolio assessment. Students expressed frustration on feedback not being aligned, that they got critique on topics not stated in assignments and that teaching assistants were reluctant to discuss the feedback. This article provides a description of the course design, an assessment of the quality of feedback and lessons learned from three main changes: Revising assignments and rubrics, reorganising the teaching staff and increasing training of teaching assistants. In discussing the changes, we draw on a survey to students with 142 respondents, a survey to teaching assistants with 18 respondents, meeting minutes from a student reference group and experience reports from teaching assistants as well as literature and own experience. The article concludes with three actionable lessons learned for large-scale semi-capstone courses.	software engineering education;training;bachelor; project work;teamwork;agile development methods; scrum;experience report; capstone education	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9962726	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração ou soft skills
Integrating computer security into the undergraduate software engineering classes: Lessons learned	10.1109/TALE. 2014.7062570	We present our initial findings from our attempts to integrate computer security topics in our undergraduate software engineering courses. Previously, both computer security and software engineering were taught separately, with very little integration between the two. However, this could result in non-functional requirements such as security becoming low priority for students when learning software engineering. Our attempt to integrate computer security into the software engineering course have shown that students benefit when these topics are presented side-by-side, together with practical examples of how to identify and address common security risks.	computer security;teaching software engineering	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7062570	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração ou soft skills
Using the random forest classifier to assess and predict student learning of Software Engineering Teamwork	10.1109/FIE. 2016.7757406	The overall goal of our Software Engineering Teamwork Assessment and Prediction (SETAP) project is to develop effective machine-learning-based methods for assessment and early prediction of student learning effectiveness in software engineering teamwork. Specifically, we use the Random Forest (RF) machine learning (ML) method to predict the effectiveness of software engineering teamwork learning based on data collected during student team project development. These data include over 100 objective and quantitative Team Activity Measures (TAM) obtained from monitoring and measuring activities of student teams during the creation of their final class project in our joint software engineering classes which ran concurrently at San Francisco State University (SFSU), Fulda University (Fulda) and Florida Atlantic University (FAU). In this paper we provide the first RF analysis results done at SFSU on our full data set covering four years of our joint SE classes. These data include 74 student teams with over 380 students, totaling over 30000 discrete data points. These data are grouped into 11 time intervals, each measuring important phases of project development during the class (e.g. early requirement gathering and design, development, testing and delivery). We briefly elaborate on the methods of data collection and describe the data itself. We then show prediction results of the RF analysis applied to this full data set. Results show that we are able to detect student teams who are bound to fail or need attention in early class time with good (about 70%) accuracy. Moreover, the variable importance analysis shows that the features (TAM measures) with high predictive power make intuitive sense, such as late delivery/late responses, time used to help each other, and surprisingly statistics on commit messages to the code repository, etc. In summary, we believe we demonstrate the viability of using ML on objective and quantitative team activity measures to predict student learning of software engineering teamwork, and point to easy-to-measure factors that can be used to guide educators and software engineering managers to implement early intervention for teams bound to fail. Details about the project and the complete ML training database are downloadable from the project web site.	Assessment;software engineering teamwork; machine learning;education	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7757406	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

Impact of using Agile Methods in Software Engineering Education: A Case Study	10.1109/CoDIT.2019.8820377	Agile methods have proved their applicability and efficiency in software development. Advantages of using agile methods include short development life-cycle times; multidisciplinary development teams; continuous evolution, immediacy, and reduced cost of change. Although some universities started including these methods in their curriculum, courses on practical practices for Agile methods at the undergraduate and graduate levels are still few. In this paper, an investigation is conducted to evaluate the impact of teaching practical agile methods in web engineering course on the learning outcomes of the software engineering students. This case study started by conducting a real-life business simulation inside a computer lab. Then, a questionnaire was prepared and disseminated in order to obtain the feedback on the students' perception on this teaching method. Afterward, the questionnaire results were analyzed and assessments for students were done to find out the impact of this educational technique on students' performance.	Web Engineering;Software Engineering Education;Agile methods;Scrum;XP	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8820377	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração ou soft skills
Research on the Teaching Reform of Managing the Software Process Course	10.1109/ICAIE50891.2020.00062	In view of the problems existing in the teaching of software process management, combined with the standard requirements of engineering education certification and the cases of the implementation of relevant courses in foreign high-level universities, this paper puts forward the reform measures for the practical teaching of this course. It is suggested that the practical teaching of the course should adopt the way of integrating the cases with appropriate difficulty and scale with the course projects, forming the students into the corresponding project team to complete the practical teaching of the course in the scene of the software development company, reforming the corresponding course assessment and evaluation mode, so that the students can complement each other and really learn something. We should realize the teaching goal of software engineering specialty in the new era, and train qualified software professionals.	component;managing the software process;teaching model;case project;reform in education	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9262562	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração ou soft skills
Exploration of Method to Improve the Teaching Effect of Course "Operating System"	10.1109/ICET55642.2022.9944467	Operating system is a strategic technology and a foundational software in information technology field, but it is really not easy to teach and learn this course well. To solve the problem, a method of online and offline hybrid teaching is adopted, while giving full play to the role of probing into technical topics and students' sharing in class. By the four stages of this process, before, during and after class and at ordinary times, students change gradually from knowing to being able to express, then to mastering, and finally to broadening their cognition and creative application. This makes a beneficial practical exploration on the improvement of the teaching effect of Operating System course.	operating system;hybrid teaching;MOOC;OBE;flipped classroom;mind map;group learning	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9944467	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração ou soft skills
Using Focus to Personalise Learning and Feedback in Software Engineering Education	10.1109/ICSE-SEET58685.2023.00033	Learning can be greatly enhanced by effective feedback. Traditional assessment approaches in higher education often result in feedback being used to justify marks awarded, which is often disregarded once the assessment is complete. In this paper, we explore the idea of incorporating a focus mechanism to connect feedback between assessment tasks and units, discuss how this can be applied to enhance software engineering education, and present results from several staff focus groups exploring the idea. The focus groups discussed the model, its application within software engineering units, and its limitations, with staff helping co-create the enhancements to the model through discussing experiences/sharing opinions/providing insights on assessment within their units. Results indicate that staff believe that the changes will benefit their teaching and highlighted several opportunities for this initiative to encourage students to have a more holistic view of their studies. The main challenges identified were staff workload and complexity for students which must be addressed in implementing this idea.	Assessment;Rubrics;Formative Feedback	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10172718	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração ou soft skills
Mining Software Engineering Team Project Work Logs to Generate Formative Assessment	10.1109/APSECW.2017.19	Supporting students in software engineering team project can be a challenge. Team leaders and supervisors may at times find it difficult to monitor students' progress and contribution. Students may either be falling behind or not contributing properly to the team. This paper describes a proposed solution that generate formative assessment feedback automatically using text data mining techniques. Various text similarity and machine learning techniques were explored and experimented to identify a suitable model for assessing student's performance and generating feedback. Utilising the students' individual weekly logs and the team's project plan, the proposed solution experimented on different text similarity techniques to match work done against work planned. The calculated similarity score and other extracted features are then applied to different machine learning algorithms, with the root mean-squared error used as the evaluation metric to identify the most suitable model. With this proposed solution, formative feedback generated can be used by team leaders and supervisors to identify team problems early on, and provide the students with necessary support. The students themselves can also reflect on their performance and address them earlier in the project phase than later.	Automatic Assessment;Machine Learning;Text Analysis	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8312528	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração ou soft skills

TROFOS - Agile Project Management Platform for Software Engineering Education	10.1109/TALE62452.2024.10834343	In recent years, knowledge of Agile project management principles has become increasingly important due to its prominence in the software engineering space. Industry across the globe uses Agile project management principles such as Scrum and Kanban for tracking and managing projects. In spite of this importance, the academic space is devoid of a suitable platform to allow students to develop mastery in Agile while in school. In this paper, we propose the implementation of an Agile project management platform designed specifically for academic settings. The platform, named TROFOS, aims to provide students with an experience of industry's leading platforms, such as Jira while incorporating academic-specific features such as retrospective and faculty feedback. Ultimately, TROFOS seeks to enhance project management skills among students and improve the overall quality of academic projects. We have implemented this platform, and students have used it for different projects—both course projects and final year projects. We have conducted an extensive survey evaluation of the platform using the standard UTAUT model. A survey was constructed to find out, whether TROFOS helps with software engineering education, how well users are adapting to and accepting TROFOS if they have previously been used to other tools, and how we can improve in each of the 4 areas (performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, and facilitating conditions) to make TROFOS more widely accepted by its target users in the future. The survey revealed that TROFOS meets various design objectives very well.	Software Engineering; Database Applications; Computer Uses in Education; Project Management; DevOps	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10834343	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração ou soft skills
A model and evaluation method of learning motivation in the education and training of professional engineers	10.1109/TALE.2016.7851813	The automotive industry, including DENSO CORPORATION, needs to educate and train professional engineers who can cope with changes undergoing in the recent business environments. We also aim at fostering self-motivating ability for professional engineers in education and training curriculums. However, fostering and evaluating the motivation are difficult. This paper proposes a learning model and its evaluation method of a motivational education curriculum for professional engineers. We structured the learning model based on a model for motivational design, and applied the model to prototype courses. To improve self-training ability of trainees, we introduced a pre-learning program. We conducted a survey to the trainees, and evaluated the improvement of their learning motivation during the education and training course.	Engineering Education; Learning Motivation; Training in Corporation; the ARCS model; Flipped Classroom	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7851813	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Pode ser que tenha uma forma pra adaptar
Peer Instruction in Online Synchronous Software Engineering - Findings from fine-grained clicker data	10.1109/FIE49875.2021.9637353	In this Research Full paper, we present the results of a replication study in a semester-long, sophomore-level software engineering course utilizing Peer Instruction (PI). PI is an active learning pedagogy with roots in STEM Education. In this study, we examine the relationship between student response data from in-class PI correctness and students' performance on quizzes and exams. We worked with a fully remote, synchronous course offered over Zoom. The study we replicated was with an honors cohort of students with a diversity of undergraduate majors, while we focused on a non-honors course containing computing-related majors. Our intervention design included a flipped-classroom approach for each class session with required readings, reading quizzes, followed by PI in class using online breakout rooms for peer discussion. Our course modules were heavily based on industry practices and knowledge from the workforce, across several varied modules that encompass the complete software development lifecycle, and were as follows: Software Process Models (SPM), Software Architecture (SA), Databases (DB), User Interface/user Experience (UI/UX), Software Testing (ST), and Continuous Integration (CI). Our data points for analysis with fine-grained PI student response data were two-fold: scores from weekly online quizzes, and a summative final exam, administered online through a course management system (CMS), at different points during the semester after the PI sessions. The online quizzes and the online exam were timed, closed book/notes, and conducted during class periods. We analyzed and classified individual student responses before and after each question in each module and attempted to create response patterns for each module. We correlated these response patterns with exam and quiz scores using ANOVA techniques, on a variety of questions including Parson's problems. We report overall correctness on each type of vote, track student response patterns from in-class to quizzes and the exam, and quantify absolute percentages of students that demonstrate longer-term learning from the PI process. Our results show that 58% of students exhibited cognitive gains across all modules during PI sessions. Students who learn in class from PI perform well on the quizzes and the final exam, indicating persistence of the knowledge gained during PI several weeks after the actual sessions. We also found that those who fail to learn from the PI process in the class perform worse on quizzes and the final exam. Our results were consistent across all modules. More significantly, we found PI to be an effective way to teach our software engineering course based on student learning before and after PI, in a completely virtual environment, a result unique to our study. Based on our results, we discuss the implications for software engineering education, both in-person and virtual.	Software Engineering Education; Peer Instruction; Active Learning; Online courses; Virtual Instruction; Cognitive gains using Peer Instruction; Fine-grained data analysis; student response data	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9637353	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração ou soft skills

Authentic Individual Assessment for Team-based Software Engineering Projects		In order to give students an authentic learning experience and better prepare them for the life-long learning required in contemporary workplaces, educational institutions increasingly use project-based learning in teams. However, this poses the challenge of developing authentic and equitable assessment criteria that reflect individual contributions in a team-work setting without jeopardizing project outcomes. We present a novel and innovative portfolio-based assessment framework that focuses on qualitative outcomes and ensures that the level of achievement reflects a student's competency across each of the defined learning dimensions, including professional behaviour, teamwork, process and relevant contributions towards project deliverables. In this paper, we present the main motivation behind devising and introducing the framework and also reflect on the educational outcomes and challenges of implementing the framework in the context of two final year Software Engineering project units.	Software Engineering Projects;Individual Assessment;Grading Rubrics	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9291894	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração ou soft skills
Strategies and Implications of Peer Assessment in Software Engineering Education	10.1109/FIE61694.2024.10892827	This Innovative Practice category full paper describes the strategy of peer evaluation approach. Effective team management is pivotal in the success of any collaborative project, particularly in the domain of learning Software Engineering or Professional Software Development courses. Peer evaluations are commonly used methods to motivate group-based learning. This paper addresses the significance of team management and peer evaluations in the context of two Computing Science (CS) courses offered: Professional Software Development (PSD) and Team Project (TP). The main contributions of this paper are to provide nuanced insights into the challenges and opportunities inherent in collaborative endeavors, emphasizing effective motivation, encouragement, and resolution strategies for tackling teamwork issues within group projects. This study scrutinizes the intricate dimensions of teamwork in Software Engineering education. A central aspect of the paper involves a comprehensive analysis of peer evaluation methodologies, intending to shed light on practical implications for educators and learners. The findings underscore the importance of leveraging these insights to cultivate a conducive learning environment, motivating students to actively participate in collaborative endeavors. The proposed peer evaluations approaches are presented as a combination of the existing quantitative assessment approach and newly qualitative feedback mechanisms. It incorporates these elements: weekly peer review, emotion rating & thoughts, release of feedback, and a centralized dashboard. In the study, 31 CS Sophomore students taking the CSC2101 - PSD and TP1 course participate to evaluation experiments, where positive results are obtained. The collective findings and evaluations contribute to the ongoing refinement of collaborative learning experiences within the dynamic landscape of Software Engineering education.	Peer evaluation;team project;group-based software development;software engineering education	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10892827	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Lessons from a failed flipped classroom: The hacked computer science teacher	10.1109/TALE.2015.7386008	Teaching in higher education can be rewarding, but also stressful. Different teaching approaches and paradigms may mean that teachers are constantly trying to improve the learning experience for their students — a good thing; but perhaps are not succeeding — a bad thing. This paper is essentially a story centring around a teaching experience I had over the course of a single semester. Motivated by a desire to improve the interactivity in a computer science class, I designed and implemented an initiative to facilitate student interaction and teamwork: a flipped classroom. The initiative was not as successful as hoped for, and so I drew on reflexivity and autoethnography to help understand and learn from the experience.	Teaching;Software Engineering;Computer Science;Flipped Classroom;Autoethnography;Reflection	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7386008	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração ou soft skills
Exploration and Practice of Hybrid Teaching Mode Under MOOC Environment: Taking "Database System Principle" as an Example	10.1109/ITME.2018.00117	As a new approach of online education, large open online course (Mu Class, MOOC) has been introduced for the higher education system, which has large impact on the construction courses related to database. By reforming traditional teaching concepts and teaching methods, new demands arise in the current era. "Database System Principles" is one of the core subjects in the field of computer science. Taking the "Database System Principles" course as an example, this paper analyzes the necessity of the hybrid teaching mode. It discusses the project-based hybrid teaching model construction and teaching system in the MOOC environment, introducing the detailed design of offline teaching activities and the evaluation mechanism based on process assessment. Practice shows that the hybrid teaching mode in the MOOC environment effectively improves the quality of teaching, which is extensively favored by students. Additionally, some other teaching methods to improve the teaching effect are also discussed in this paper.	Database system principle;MOOC Teaching;hybrid Teaching;Flipping classroom	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8589349	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração ou soft skills

Toward Increasing Collaboration Awareness in Software Engineering Teams	10.1109/FIE.2018.8659198	This Research Full Paper investigates collaborative personality traits in undergraduate software engineering teams. Online tools, such as Slack.com, provide team engagement and project management. While metrics can be defined for team and individual performance, it is difficult to measure collaboration and its impacts. Specifically, the forms of collaboration that lead to a successful software product should have associated metrics that correlate with individual performance, peer assessments, and project outcomes. Given the difficulty of assembling teams that best exemplify collaborative personality traits, it may be more beneficial for team members to recognize these traits so that their positive aspects can be exploited toward a successful product outcome. We employ IBM Watson™ Personality Insights service to analyze team Slack.com posts collected from forty students across ten teams and two semesters of the capstone class. We correlate thirteen traits recognized for influencing collaboration with team grades, Sprint meeting check-in quality, and peer evaluations. The correlations show that each trait is related to at least one performance metric during at least one of the Sprints. We discuss the potential meaning of different traits emerging at different times during the semester and how that can inform strategies for software developer collaboration awareness and reward.	Collaboration;software engineering;capstone projects;personality traits	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8659198	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Research on Curriculum Practice Teaching Reform of Information System Engineering Based on CDIO	10.1109/ITEI55021.2021.00076	Information system engineering is an engineering discipline that comprehensively uses computer technology and engineering management principles and methods to realize the definition, design, development, testing, deployment, and operation and maintenance of specific function information system projects in accordance with user needs, budgets and schedules. Combining the CDIO's engineering practice teaching mode, aiming at the current situation that the form and content of the practice teaching of information system engineering courses are separated from actual engineering projects, a CDIO-based course practice teaching mode is proposed. The model was practiced with the life cycle of the information system engineering project as the carrier, and the results showed that the reform measures can better solve the above problems, and at the same time can improve students' independent learning and independent practice ability to a certain extent.	CDIO;information system engineering;practical teaching	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9752746	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	nao fala em colaboração ou soft skill
Teaching and learning software project management: A hands-on approach	10.1109/FIE.2015.7344412	Project management is an essential activity across several areas, including Software Engineering. Through good management it is possible to achieve deadlines, budgets goals and mainly delivering a product that meets customer expectations. Project management activity encompasses: measurement and metrics; estimation; risk analysis; schedules; tracking and control. Considering the importance of managing projects, it is necessary that courses related to Information Technology and Computer Science present to students concepts, techniques and methodology necessary to cover all project management activities. Software project management courses aim at preparing students to apply management techniques required to plan, organize, monitor and control software projects. In a nutshell, software project management focuses on process, problem and people. In this paper we proposed an approach to teaching and learning of software project management using practical activities. The intention of this work is to provide the experience of applying theoretical concepts in practical activities. The teaching and learning approach, applied since 2006 in a Computer Science course, is based on teamwork. Each team is divided into groups assuming different roles of software process development. We have set four groups, each one assuming a different role (manager; software quality assurance; analyst and designer; programmer). The team must be conducted across the software process by its manager. We use four projects, each group is in charge of managing a different project. In this paper we present the proposed approach (based on hands on activities for project management); we summarize the lessons learned by applying the approach since 2006; we present a qualitative analysis from data collect along the application.	Learning Project Management;Practical Activities;Teaching Methodology;Teamwork	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7344412	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

Learning CS Subjects of Professional Software Development and Team Projects	10.1109 /TALE54877. 2022.00020	Professional Software Development (PSD) course is about the emerging profession of software engineering which involves developing, deploying, testing, and maintaining software. Currently, the Bachelor of Science with Honours in Computing Science (CS) joint degree programme of University of Glasgow (UofG) and Singapore Institute of Technology (SIT) carries out both PSD and Team Projects (TP) courses concurrently, where students are expected to apply the theory learnt from PSD to real-world projects in TP. TP is a practical project continuation from knowledge learnt in the PSD course. Both PSD and TP last two trimesters in parallel. This paper analyses the advantages and disadvantages of the current learning methods in PSD and TP. It is possible that there is still room for improvement in the current system. To further analyse the current learning system, a comparison of how the Software Engineering course is taught in other universities is also performed, from where ideas and methodology are proposed. The proposed methodology is analyzed and discussed from the suggestions or feedback of the CS students who have gone through both PSD and TP courses. The purposes are to improve the learning effectiveness of both PSD and TP courses.	Professional Software Development;Project-based Learning;Software Engineering;Software Development Life Cycle	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10148501	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não fala em colaboração ou soft skill
Unreined Students or Not: Modes of Freedom in a Project-Based Software Engineering Course	10.1109 /CSEET49119. 2020.9206193	Software engineering courses include practical and theoretical elements that give many options for pedagogical combinations among them. In this paper, we report on two different pedagogical approaches for an undergraduate, introductory project-based software engineering course with more than 500 students working in collaborative scrum teams. We call one approach 'Every Student is an Innovator', and the other 'No Student Left Behind'. This SE course has been long-running, with stable learning objectives and content. However, from one year to another, we radically changed the pedagogical approach of the course along several dimensions, among them the technical framework, software tools, project topic, mentor roles, assessment form and frequency, feedback and degree of student innovativeness. We report on the perceived challenges, detailed changes, the anticipated effects on the course learning outcomes. The results showed that innovativeness and fun need freedom and flexibility with processes and technology. However, strict design requirements and systematic guidance ensure fulfillment of learning objectives. Analyzing student and staff feedback, we find that both approaches lead to students using more time than intended and worrying about unknown assessment criteria.	Software Engineering Education;Project-based Software Engineering; Software Innovation; Continuous Integration; Continuous Assessment; Technology Support	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9206193	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem metricas
Converting an Undergrad-Lab to an Interactive E-Learning Experience That Enables Student Teamwork	10.1109 /FIE49875. 2021.9637206	This Innovative Practice Work in Progress Paper presents a comprehensive approach to convert an undergrad hands-on electronics lab to an e-learning experience. Special care was taken to make the format interactive as well as to encourage teamwork between students. The conversion was made to conform with the social distancing measures implemented as a response to the COVID-19 pandemic. Instead of relying on pre-recorded lessons, the lab was offered through live video sessions. Multiple cameras were used to make it easy for students to follow the instructor performing the experiment. Students worked together in teams they had chosen at the beginning of the semester throughout the entire course, giving team members the opportunity to get to know each other or strengthen existing bonds. During the live sessions, the teams were repeatedly sent to breakout rooms to discuss and vote on questions related to the execution of the experiments and the measurement results. The votes, which were carried out using the Moodle learning management system (LMS), were then discussed in the plenary, and the course of the experiment was adjusted accordingly. Using data of student participation from the LMS and the results of a detailed survey, the success of the implemented measures can be proven empirically. 88.2 % of students found that the interactive elements helped them to stay concentrated during the live sessions. 79.6 % agreed that the breakout rooms improved cooperation within their team and 72.8 % plan to stay in touch with their team members.	COVID-19;distance learning; electronics lab;teamwork; undergrad education;video conference software	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9637206	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Blended learning in software engineering education: The application lifecycle management experience with computer-supported collaborative learning	10.1109/ICL. 2015.7318104	Software engineering education (SEE) process simulates the main professional software lifecycle processes such as analysis, design, construction and maintenance (see SWEBok, ITIL, etc.). The necessity of meeting both educational needs and requirements from industry explains that using Supported Collaborative Learning (CSCL) techniques in software engineering (SE) should be based on professional tools or on similar to them. The main purpose of this work is to fill the gap between the SEE needs and the current trends in CSCL development. We generalize world experience and suggest the framework of using industry approved methods and tools. We compare CSCL tools and the other collaborative services; analyze the teaching experience of several SE courses supported by different collaborative methods and collaborative web-services. Special attention is paid to formative feedback implementation. Following achieved result we suppose that using best practices from SE will enrich CSCL methodology and tools not only for SE field, but also for other areas of knowledge.	blended learning; collaborative learning; software engineering; education;SE;SEE;CSCL	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7318104	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

An Approach to Using Existing Online Education Tools to Support Practical Education on MOOCs	10.1109 /COMPSAC. 2016.49	MOOCs are popular for online education because of its convenience and excellent educational resources. At present, MOOCs just provide very limited online practical environments such as online tests, quizzes and online judge etc., but they have not provided students with some dynamic and operable online practical environments, such as interactive education tools etc. Online education tools can satisfy the needs of online practicing, mainly because of its abundance, interactivity and convenience, but MOOCs have not made full use of these online tools yet. The paper proposes an approach to using existing online education tools to support practical education on MOOCs by two enhancements: educational resources development and real-time collaborative learning. The key to the approach is operation reuse, which involves recording, optimizing and replaying user operations on existing online educations tools. Based on the approach, we develop an education platform called Smart Web Tutor. Case study is performed to analyze user experience, and the results show that our approach contributes to students' learning, especially for real-time collaborative learning. Also, some suggestions from students are inspiring to further increase the utility and user experience of our approach and education platform.	Online education tools; MOOC;collaborative learning;educational resources	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7552093	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Using GitHub Analytics to Assess the Quality of Collaboration in Software Engineering Teams	10.1109 /FIE61694. 2024.10892887	This research-to-practice full paper investigates using team process analytics from GitHub to support team management. Effective teamwork is essential in higher education learning and workplace success. The role of educators in supporting proper team functioning includes helping students learn how to participate actively and communicate effectively in meetings, delegate work fairly, manage high-quality work throughput, and resolve conflicts if problems arise. Problems often emerge when team members have differing visions or individuals do not contribute equally to the work output. These problems are exacerbated in large classes involving many teams. Detecting these potential issues in teams and helping students work through them is important for team success. In software engineering projects, monitoring individual contributions can begin with mining activities on programming platforms such as GitHub, which makes much of the individual contributions more visible and quantifiable. In this work, we propose a framework for fairly assessing teamwork and present the development of team analytics to assist educators in detecting potential issues in team collaboration. We describe a pilot study involving this tool in the context of a software engineering capstone course with 104 students split into 22 teams managed by 4 teaching assistants. Our results show that the reports offer value in guiding the evaluation process and identifying where problems may be, but do not replace the actual repository analysis where needed. We discuss the potential value of using this tool to improve collaboration.	Capstone assessment; collaboration assessment; collaboration analytics; GitHub metrics;GitHub assessments;pull request metrics	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10892887	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Supporting Real Demands in Software Engineering with a Four Steps Project-Based Learning Approach	10.1109/ICSE-SEET52601. 2021.00014	Project-based learning (PBL) is a student-centered and learn-by-doing approach that organizes learning around projects. While entrepreneurship and PBL in SE education are thrilling research topics, there seems to be very little work focusing on the pros and cons of involving external stakeholders to support real demands in software engineering education. Working on real projects also supports students to acquire leadership skills, such as communication, project management, and teamwork. This paper describes a case study integrating students from different Software Engineering programs and involving external stakeholders, underpinned by PBL concepts. We present how this study was designed and implemented in a large institution, in four steps, summarized as follows: (I) requirements gathering and design; (II) information system development and implementation; (III) integration tests and deployment process; (IV) support and maintenance activities. The study had the participation of 59 students from a professional technical course in step one, working in teams, and 10 undergraduate students from a Bachelor's program in Information Systems in the following steps, working in pairs. Overall, the feedback from stakeholders and students exceeded expectations, although it increased the workload of teachers. We were able to distill a new set of lessons learned, and we expect that at least some of them will be useful for anyone implementing a similar course. As a consequence of this study, we plan to institutionally formalize the PBL course improvement process by defining specific outcomes and measurements.	Project-Based Learning;PBL; Software Engineering Education;External Stakeholders	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9402166	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não avalia

OBE-Based Reform for Software Project Management Curriculum	10.1109/ICCSE.2019.8845362	OBE (Outcome-based education) is a comprehensive method that distinctly defines what students should achieve, and then organizes the curriculum, teaching activities and assessment to ensure the prospective outcomes. Based on OBE, this paper introduces the teaching objectives, graduation requirements and supporting indicator points of software project management curriculum. In order to achieve these graduation requirements, this paper proposes some reform ideas, such as Teacher-centered is changed to Student-centered and project-driven, scenario animation show, teaching rhythms, cases study and team work practice etc. We hope that these reforms will be helpful in promoting students to meet their graduation requirements.	Engineering Education Professional Certificate; Outcome-based Education; Teaching Reform; Graduation Requirements	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8845362	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração ou soft skills
Measurement Models for Group-Peer Assessment of Project-Based Learning in Software Engineering	10.1109/ISCSET58624.2024.10808114	Over two decades we have been developing and testing alternative frameworks for Group-Peer-Assessment (GP A) in software engineering education. The focus lies on skills assessed through observation of students' behavior and/or examination of the results of project assignments. Assessment for such instructional types is not covered satisfactorily by traditional approaches. Assessment at the group as well as individual level must be able to cope with multiple quality criteria on scales of various types, and multiple assessors responsible for assessing distinct quality aspects. We offer two-parameter scoring models for GP A, by which individual student scores are derived from a group score and mutual peer ratings. The two parameters are: (1) a constraint on the spread of student scores and (2) the relative impact of peer ratings. GP A imposes no artificial restrictions on group size, type or number of quality criteria, or other context-specific aspects of GP A. We briefly describe our experience with GP A for software engineering courses at a university in the UK.	Bounded scales; group score; group spread; grades; peer assessments; peer impact; ratings; scale operations; scores; scoring rule; student contribution; student score	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10808114	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração ou soft skills
The effect of online assessments and feedback practices on civil engineering students' learning	10.1109/WEFF-GEDC54384.2022.9996246	The move to online teaching and learning at higher institutions because of the Covid-19 pandemic in the year 2020 challenged engineering programs to change how they have been conducting their assessments. Before Covid, this process was done to check whether module outcomes are achieved and provide a grade for the student. Nowadays continuous assessments are used instead of summative assessments and civil engineering schools must now re-think the whole purpose of the assessment process. This paper reports on a study which was designed to find out if assessments given to engineering students are improving and enhancing their understanding and promote better learning. Our important goal as engineering lecturers is to prepare students for a professional life through assessment, teaching and learning. The study focused on the small number of students who study civil engineering technology at the University of Johannesburg. Assessment within the engineering discipline is ordinarily orientated towards illustrating competence in particular assignments utilizing only conventional or traditional assessment methods such as tests and exams. This work aimed to assist students to increase their learning potential from assessments and lecturers to provide constructive assessment feedback. The main research question was to find out the extent that students learn from assessment and feedback in the Theory of Structures module under civil engineering technology. The vehicles that were used to collect data includes lecture observations, questionnaires, and interviews. The research data collection was conducted over few weeks of the second semester with first year students doing Theory of Structures. Three types of data were collected from this study. The first was a semester test results and feedback. After the test, focus group interviews were conducted to students' feedback on the test process and they also gave details about how they found questions and solutions. The third instrument of data collection was the use of questionnaires in the form of online surveys. The analysis of data started by documenting the results obtained from the interviews, and online questionnaires. The audio recordings from interviews were transcribed using Otter software. The transcribed text was then merged with findings from questionnaires and analyzed using open coding by Quirkos software. The study showed that more work still needs to be done to educate students about the importance of assessment as the findings showed that there are students who still focus on grades during assessment and not real learning. Nowadays feedback is even more important since most students are using blended or online learning which requires support and guidance from the lecturer. Although the focus was on small size of sample or few participants compared to the faculty of engineering student population, the study still managed to provide findings that will be applied to improve assessment and feedback practices.	student assessment; feedback; engineering education	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9996246	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	fora da engenharia de software

Application of the SPOC Teaching Mode in Courses of Computer Network in the Post-MOOC Period	10.1109/ITME.2016.0104	SPOC (Small Private Online Course) is a kind of typical course form in Post-MOOC Era. It upgrades the learning effect by decreasing the size of students scale and limiting course enrollment requirements. It is a perfect subsequent development and beyond for MOOC. This article firstly analyses the characteristics of the MOOC and SPOC, then we construct teaching model of computer foundation courses based on SPOC, and put it into practice. Finally, we analyze the teaching effect. Results show that through practice courses the students give high evaluation on the degrees of awareness, participation and satisfaction based on SPOC. The scope of the new model is that it will gradually break the traditional pattern of cramming education.	SPOC;teaching mode;post-MOOC	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7976518	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração ou soft skills
Flipping an engineering mathematics classroom for a large undergraduate class	10.1109/TALE.2014.7062574	Although flipping classroom is not a new idea in education, implementing flipped class is somewhat a new trend. Flipping classrooms involve students in using their textbooks, online materials, and other useful resources before coming to class. Consequently, students can spend valuable class meetings on problem-solving activities instead of lectures. Positive feedback from utilizing the flipped classroom techniques has been reported in several papers. This article presents an attempt to implement the flipped classroom for a large introductory engineering class in multivariable calculus at King Mongkut's Institute of Technology Ladkrabang. The results from implementing the flipped classroom both quantitatively and qualitatively showed a higher performance and more positive feedback when compared to those obtained from this class taught by the same instructor using the traditional classroom format in the previous year.	flipped classroom; engineering mathematics; large classroom	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7062574	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração ou soft skills
WIP Teaching Engineers to Sketch: Impacts of Feedback from an Intelligent Tutoring Software on Engineers' Sketching Skill Development	10.1109/FIE56618.2022.9962419	This Research Work In Progress Paper examines empirical evidence on the impacts of feedback from an intelligent tutoring software on sketching skill development. Sketching is a vital skill for engineering design, but sketching is only taught limitedly in engineering education. Teaching sketching usually involves one-on-one feedback which limits its application in large classrooms. To meet the demands of feedback for sketching instruction, SketchTivity was developed as an intelligent tutoring software. SketchTivity provides immediate personalized feedback on sketching freehand practice. The current study examines the effectiveness of the feedback of SketchTivity by comparing students practicing with the feedback and without. Students were evaluated on their motivation for practicing sketching, the development of their skills, and their perceptions of the software. This work in progress paper examines preliminary analysis in all three of these areas.	sketching;formative assessment;feedback; intelligent tutoring system	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9962419	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração ou soft skills
Facilitating Entrepreneurial Experiences through a Software Engineering Project Course	10.1109/ICSE-SEET.2019.00012	Skills and competencies in entrepreneurship, such as the ability to generate innovative ideas and the courage to engage with stakeholders and society, have gained importance in engineering curricula. In this case study paper, we report on how we have integrated entrepreneurial experiences into a software engineering project course and made the creation of value and reflection on the application of a structured process the heart and soul of the course. Based on current research on entrepreneurship education as well as the definition of entrepreneurial competencies used by the European Union, we show how the learning objectives, the teaching moments, the integration of external stakeholders, and the assessment work together to create an entrepreneurial environment in which students are encouraged and rewarded to work in an entrepreneurial way. Based on data from reflection reports, course evaluations, and interviews we discuss the pros and cons of our approach and how the student perception and expectations often run counter to the motivations of the course design. We thus contribute guidance for other teachers based on our own experiences in relation to the findings of our peers.	Entrepreneurship;Software Engineering Education; Project Courses	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8802115	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não avalia colab ou soft skill
Scalable Team-Based Software Engineering Education via Automated Systems	10.1109/LWMOOCS.2018.8534590	Team projects are essential in modern software engineering education. Students collaboratively build a piece of software that addresses practical issues, through which they practice both technical skills and soft skills, in a setting that resembles the real working environment. However, team projects are complex. Previous studies have explored various design spaces, such as team formation [1], project selection [2], team coaching [3], and student evaluation [4]; while others have reported experience regarding the design, organization, teaching, and evolution of a project-based software engineering curriculum [5,6,7,8]. The complexity of team projects explains why we rarely see large-scale software engineering courses with a team project. In this paper, we try to address the scalability issue of software engineering projects and lay out our blueprint for enabling the learning of software engineering with a team project via MOOCs.	Software engineering; Measurement;Education; Teamwork;Scalability; Telemetry;Tools	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8534590	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	nao avalia

Investigation and Analysis of Online Teaching in Higher Vocational Colleges during the COVID-19 Epidemic	10.1109/ICJET51873.2021.9419577	Affected by the COVID-19 epidemic in 2020, responding to the call of "Ensuring learning uninterrupted when classes are disrupted" by the Ministry of Education, schools at all levels and types in China had launched online teaching. This paper takes 210 teachers and 3952 students in a local higher vocational college in Anhui Province as the research objects, and investigates from two perspectives of online teaching and learning. The results show that there were some problems in online teaching, such as network jam, interference in home learning and lack of learning monitoring, however, timely online training, abundant online resources, convenient live broadcast tools and stable teaching platform had ensured the orderly development of the online teaching. Teachers and students were highly satisfied with online teaching. In the post-epidemic era, online teaching will be integrated with offline teaching, which become "normalized". Therefore, this research proposes that it is necessary to make more in-depth exploration and efforts in strengthening network technology support and guarantee, improving teachers' and students' information literacy, enhancing teachers' informatization resources construction ability and teaching design ability, and so on.	epidemic prevention and control;online teaching;online learning;teaching platform	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9419577	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração ou soft skill
Deploying Team-Based Learning at Undergraduate Software Engineering Courses	10.1109/SECM.2017.2	Education methods for millennials must accommodate their expectations and behaviors. Active learning methodologies seem to be adequate for this requirement. In particular, in this paper, we discuss the design and deployment of Team-Based Learning (TBL) in two undergraduate Software Engineering courses. TBL is a type of Active Learning Methodology that makes extensive use of small groups to accommodate learning and empower students with the learning responsibilities in the classroom. This paper describes our concerns and the decisions we made when designing two TBL courses at ORT University. Furthermore, we evaluated the results of our deployment and compared them with published results. Our results are aligned with the expectations inferred from the literature. Students had a positive perception of the methodology and the learning outcomes.	Software Engineering Education;Team-Based Learning;Active Learning	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7964616	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração ou soft skill
The Group Expert Evaluation in Electrical Engineering Education	10.1109/ICEPE.2018.8559787	While dealing with the identification of sensitive items in the domain of electrical engineering education, it is beneficial to use a group expert evaluation, highly skilled specialists being involved. Group expert evaluations allow obtaining reliable results mainly in the case of well-chosen specialists, providing consistency for their findings. The here presented study is devoted to the features of group expert evaluation in the field of electrical engineering education, processed with the help of universal statistical software. In our evaluation have been included professors and tutors in electrical engineering education being with Universities from Romania and Ukraine. The method for the group expert evaluation was based on their competence and expertise; additionally, data consistency analysis has involved calculation of a number of mathematical indexes. We have processed answers professionally selected, also considering their numerical score for a proper quantitative evaluation. We have mainly considered the average value of the sub-questions, while taking or not into account the competence (scientific degree) of the experts.	group expert evaluation; higher education;evaluation; competence of experts; universal statistical software; electrical engineering education	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8559787	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração ou soft skill
FAST learning: A new didactic method in software engineering	10.1109/EDUCON.2015.7096084	A new didactic method is proposed and described, called FAST, which is an acronym from Follow Accomplishments of Senior Teams, to attract to the discipline students in low level courses and reduce attrition rates. In essence, the method relies on bringing software engineering student teams from senior project courses, who have accomplished some significant results in their classes, to demonstrate and showcase their projects in introductory courses in software engineering and in other STEM disciplines. Students in lower level courses, with assistance of instructor, then analyze the projects specifications, designs, and implementations, and find out about the principles and specific details of software development on a real case study, which is available at hand. Then, depending on each project's scope, an instructor in a lower level course may choose one of the techniques, such as a demo, exercise, assignment, or even experiment, to enforce learning and motivate the students to increase their chances of staying in the degree program or even switching to the software engineering program from other majors. Typical software projects involved in the first edition of FAST learning were on robotics, wireless sensor networks, microcontrollers, data acquisition and control, and others. These activities definitely engaged students in lower level courses and caused significant excitement about prospects of learning in higher level courses and pursuing careers in software engineering.	software engineering education;engineering pedagogy;project-based learning;teamwork	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7096084	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração ou soft skill

Managing Students in Hybrid Software Project Classes	10.1109 /FIE61694. 2024.10893150	This innovative practice paper describes the authors' experiences introducing active learning methodologies into a hybrid undergraduate software engineering project course. On our campus hybrid courses have both in-person and online students participating in a single course taught by the same instructor. The project team adapted the face-to-face class activities to accommodate the idiosyncrasies of an online course delivery environment. Using active learning and authentic assessment techniques, the authors sought to improve the levels of engagement exhibited by online students. The students in this course learn to use agile software engineering practices to deliver incremental software prototypes. The online and in-person students were surveyed at the conclusion of their course to measure their perceived levels of engagement with course activities. Data was collected from two recent offerings of this course. The results suggest that the neither the in-person or online students were not significantly different from one another on most survey responses or most performance measures.	project-based learning; authentic assessment;hybrid instruction;project management	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10893150	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração ou soft skill
Assessment and development of transversal competences based on student's autonomous learning	10.1109 /EDUCON. 2016.7474597	The development of transversal competences is widely recognized as one of the key elements in Engineering Education. It is essential to complement the technical training of engineers with other soft skills like self-motivation, communication or teamwork due to their great importance in the student's learning process as well as in the student's career. Thus, it is necessary to work up in resources and technologies focused in the assessment and development of transversal skills. Moreover, as the EHEA context emphasizes the autonomous learning of students, these resources and technologies should be focused in the student side. This paper presents the definition of a theoretical model of transversal skills. Also, it is introduced an ecosystem of resources and technologies that allow engineering students the self-assessment and the self-development of their transversal competences. Right now, the validation of these outcomes is starting to be conducted with engineering students from different universities.	Transversal competences; Soft skills;360 evaluation; Recommendation systems; Online courses	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7474597	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem software engineer
Enhancing Engineering Education with Wikispaces	10.1109 /ICTEED. 2017.8585652	Wikispaces platform was used to support teambased projects and evaluate individual student work. This study was conducted for a Software Engineering course taught to third year Computer Science and Engineering students. Wikispaces Classroom enabled collaboration via sharing and editing wikis within a team and viewing other team wiki pages. Teams were formed and a unique project was assigned to each team at the beginning of the semester. Individual tasks and team work tasks were assigned by the instructor. Wikispaces enabled the instructor to create project wikis for each team. Wikispaces tracked individual members of a team by recording revision history for all project wiki pages that they had updated. This enabled the instructor to grade individual student work. Analysis of the metrics from Wikispaces and Google Analytics and responses to a questionnaire revealed that the students were engaged with the website. Majority of the students revealed that they had gained team work experience. They approved of the grades assigned based on individual tasks. Most of them agreed that the team project wikis were useful. The survey revealed that there was some sort of collaboration among students via viewing wiki pages of others in order to complete their tasks and sharing project wiki pages.	Wikispaces);Collaboration; Software Engineering; Assessment	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8585652	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Skill-Based Group Allocation of Students for Project-Based Learning Courses Using Genetic Algorithm: Weighted Penalty Model	10.1109/TALE. 2018.8615127	Project-based learning (PBL) is an important component of the practical based assessment of software engineering courses. The success of PBL relies on team composition where all necessary skills to execute the project is needed. Conventionally, facilitators assign the students to the group randomly which results in biased groups where all the necessary skills to complete the project lacks in some of the groups. Most computational tools solve the group assignment problem (GAP) by assigning students to relevant groups based on some general criterion. However, there is a need for a system which allows taking skill preference as a parameter in a limited or unevenly distributed skill set. The system needs to have more or less same strength with the presence of all the skills required to complete the project. In this paper, a method is proposed that uses the canonical genetic algorithm to generate evenly balanced groups by minimizing the intergroup difference. We have employed penalty function to rank the skills and incur a penalty for the non-presence of required skills for proof of concept. Due to unavailability of benchmark datasets, we have used the real data of software engineering courses of our university where good results have been observed.	project-based learning; penalty function;genetic algorithm;group assignment problem;skill set	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8615127	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não é aberto, nao tem colab

Software Metrics Classification for Agile Scrum Process: A Literature Review	10.1109/ISRITI.2018.8864244	Software metrics play an important role to measure every attributes and project success in software development context. In the scrum process, there are several events performed on each sprint in order to monitor team performance. Conducting an objective performance measurement in the agile process meet some challenges due to the differences in team preferences and project complexity. This paper discusses the software measurement metrics and their fundamental role in scrum software development life cycle. We review software metrics on scrum context based on 13 selected literatures. Software metrics are grouped by measurement objectives and scrum events goal. We discuss 34 software metrics distributed in scrum events; sprint planning, daily scrum meetings, sprint review and sprint retrospective. Then, we perform a unique classification and provide a set of recommendation software metrics to implement scrum based on entire project management perspectives to conduct a proper performance measurement.	Agile development process; project management; software metrics;scrum development process;scrum framework	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8864244	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
A Case of Implementation of an iPeer Software Tool to Assess and Develop Engineering Students Teamwork Capabilities in a Large Class Environment	10.1109/WEF-GEDC49885.2020.9293667	Due to the growing administrative challenges and addressing the need for creating an efficient large class learning environment, a peer review approach is introduced as a part of the Engineering Management module's teamwork assessment. The module is compulsory to all engineering disciplines and has an annual class size of ±1000 students in the University of Pretoria. As a result, the workload of academic staff has concurrently become unfeasible, especially concerning the student assessment and feedback. Furthermore, the industry feedback has indicated that the current system is not successfully producing the employability capabilities needed in the real world in terms of teamwork. This competency gap between students' actual teamwork skills and the skills required by the industry further sparked the need to revisit the teaching, learning and assessment practices of teamwork. Hence the technology-assisted peer review provided a solution to maintain the workload and the prospective to work smarter. This paper aspires to advance a better understanding regards the utilisation of peer review and its educational value in a large class size environment as the existing literature currently focus on small class size applications. This is an interactive mix methods study with a multiphase concurrent interdependent design. The emphasis is in the considerations of practical reality as the instructors in the high education institutions under the pressure of growing class sizes are in constant need of useful tools and new practical knowledge to better operate in their environment. The convenience sample includes 826 students forming 166 teams. After the completion, it became apparent that the peer review has a positive impact on students' self-awareness and that it can be used for assessment for a teamwork evaluation with certain limitations. This paper argues that the peer review, however, does not provide a 'quick fix' automatically improving students' teamwork capabilities but rather only assists in highlighting the problem areas when used in isolation. To enable actual cognitive learning and skills development, a more systematic approach involving curriculum development is required where teamwork skills are developed gradually through different modules from first to last year.	teamwork;team development;collaborative learning;peer assessment; large class	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9293667	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem software engineer

Evaluation of the quality of teaching and learning for 1st year engineering programmes – an initial contribution	10.1109 /CISPEE. 2018.8593473	A system for evaluating the quality of teaching and learning implemented at the University of Aveiro, Portugal, is briefly described. Data for five modules on the 1st year engineering programmes was collected (using questionnaires and reports filled in by students and teachers) and analysed using quantitative and qualitative approaches. The “strengths” and “weaknesses” emerging from the data were discussed. Both teachers and students showed a reflective attitude by focusing on their different roles in the teaching and learning processes. Students identified two main sets of strengths, related to material resources associated with the modules and the type of assessment, but also related to their attitudes (interest and motivation). The assessment methods, in particular the number of assessment elements, were identified as strengths by both groups (students and teachers). Teachers also identified the alignment of the modules as a strength. The weaknesses identified by students were related to their attitudes (attendance and punctuality, and the reduced number of times they contacted the teachers outside the timetabled slots) and to the teachers (their lack of/or limited support, feedback and availability). Students answering questions on the teachers’ competencies perceived those as strengths, including their pedagogical competencies. Such competencies may not have been put into practice adequately, as students did not feel supported properly by teachers in the learning process. Teachers identified the use of teacher-centred strategies and passive and deductive teaching approaches as weaknesses. However, the data analysed did not show any evidence of shifting the teaching and learning approach from teacher-centred to student-centred. The authors believe that there are several possible reasons that shape the resistance to more active learning approaches to learning and teaching: teachers are often overwhelmed by the workload associated with implementing student-centred strategies and active and inductive teaching approaches; what is verbalised and what is implemented by teachers often differs. This may indicate a “single-loop learning” approach, focused on the quality of teaching, without linking it to that of learning. Additionally, career progression often ignores completely the performance of academics as teachers, focusing on research performance. To improve the quality of teaching and learning, and academic success of students, while reducing dropout rates for 1st year engineering students, additional strategies are needed. Those include adopting student-centred teaching and learning approaches. Thus, higher education teachers should be supported and given adequate pedagogical training and resources. Simultaneously, teachers implementing such approaches to teaching and learning need to be encouraged and rewarded by their institutions.	quality;evaluation;teaching and learning;student-centred approaches;quantitative; qualitative;engineering education	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8593473	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não é engenharia de software
A Grading Schema for Reinforcing Teamwork Quality in a Capstone Course	10.1109/ICSE-Companion. 2019.00112	We teach a capstone course on software engineering where students work in teams during one semester in a real world setting. By the end of each of the three iterations, students get a grade that takes into account several aspects including peer assessment. In the past, students with low commitment used to get only a slightly lower grade because peer assessment's weight was very low. Last semester we added a new grading rule: if the peer assessment is lower than a threshold, then such a grade would be final for the affected student(s). In this work we aim to show the effectiveness of this rule for promoting teamwork quality by recording the progression of peer assessments along the semester. We found that peer assessment decreases and is more disperse in the second iteration, but significantly improves in the third iteration. Our results suggest that the new rule is effective for improving teamwork by making students more responsible for their teammates' grades sooner in the project, when there is still time for improvement.	peer assessment;capstone course	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8802860	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não fala em engenharia de software
Experiences and insights from using Github Classroom to support Project-Based Courses	10.1109 /SEENG53126. 2021.00013	This work presents an approach for using GitHub classroom as a shared, structured, and persistent repository to support project-based courses at the Software Engineering Undergraduate program at PUC Minas, in Brazil. We discuss the needs of the different stakeholders that guided the development of the approach. Results on the perceptions of professors and students show that the approach brings benefits. Besides the lessons learned, we present insights on improving the education of the next generation of software engineers by employing metrics to monitor skill development, verifying student work portfolios, and employing tooling support in project-based courses.	project-based courses; GitHub;teamwork	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9474647	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

Agile Iteration Reviews in a Project Course: A key to Improved Feedback and Assessment Practice	10.1109 /SEENG53126. 2021.00011	Agile development is increasingly taught at universities worldwide. Project courses are redesigned in order to better fit these methods, both with respect to content taught and how courses are organised. This position paper builds on experience with reviews as a feedback practice in a bachelor level project course. Reviews are a key element in agile development, but there has been little discussion in the software engineering education literature on the role of such reviews in improving feedback and assessment. Through examples of course improvement work in a course with about 140 students in 24 teams, we show how review practices are tailored to better comply with principles of good feedback practice which intend to empower students and help self-regulate learning. We argue that reviews can provide formative assessment and improve the learning outcome. Finally, we conclude with five lessons learned from three years of continuous improvement.	software engineering education;capstone course; agile software development; Scrum;self-regulated learning.	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9474641	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração
Work-in-progress: Engineering and project-based learning as the focus of technology education in Colombian high schools	10.1109/ICL. 2014.7017893	In the recent years technology education has gained importance worldwide. Colombian government has included it in the basic and secondary schools curriculum, but the current teaching-learning strategies and the resources used for technology class have proven to be insufficient. This paper presents a case study for implementing Project-Based learning in a Colombian high school, using Open source Hardware and Software. First, a set of technological competencies are defined for technology class, based on the suggestions of the Ministry of National Education. Then, a project for designing an irrigation system for the school orchard is presented, which will engage students to develop the selected technological competencies. Subsequently, a set of didactic tools for the project are presented, including an electronic platform for the control of the water flux in the irrigation system. The project will be implemented during the following months, and through diagnostic and summative assessment it is expected to measure the improvement of the technological competencies in students.	automation;electronics platform;high school;irrigation system;project-based learning;technology education	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7017893	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração
Not Just a Matter of Style: Does Aesthetics Have a Place in Software Engineering Curriculum?	10.1109 /SEENG59157. 2023.00006	Aesthetic designations of code matter in how software engineers work together. Our empirical fieldwork finds that aesthetic designations are frequently used to informally assess code in the industry (i.e., code being called "beautiful," "elegant," "ugly," "messy," etc.). In this position paper, we build on our empirical fieldwork in the industry to describe the preliminary findings of a survey on students' aesthetic attitudes toward code. To understand how aesthetics is covered in software engineering courses, we surveyed 52 B.S. and 25 M.S. software engineering students about their attitudes on how "beauty" in code manifests. Our early findings suggest that 75% of undergraduate and 86% of graduate students believe that one should always strive to write "beautiful" code. Further, 98% of graduate and 85% of undergraduate students are aware that aesthetics is an aspect of software quality. While it may be inefficient to formalize aesthetic considerations in pedagogy, we argue that aesthetic aspects of code should be made explicit in teaching code-writing skills.	aesthetics;collaborative learning;code assessment; soft skills;software engineering education	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10190474	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração
Learning analytics trends and challenges in engineering education: SNOLA special session	10.1109 /EDUCON. 2018.8363493	SNOLA is a Thematic Network of Excellence recognized by the Spanish Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness composed of the main Spanish researchers in the field of learning analytics. This network emerged in 2013 focusing mainly on the technology underlying learning analytics development, but also interested on the integration of other views and disciplines that give the network a wider scope. During these years, SNOLA has carry out numerous actions with the goal of promoting the collaboration on this field, the diffusion of knowledge and initiatives, the collection of resources and the provision of broad support. Remarkable examples of these efforts have been LASI Spain events, workshops at TEEM conferences or the numerous webinars. In this case, the EDUCON 2018 has given us the opportunity to organize this special session where 5 papers have been selected for presentation.	Learning Analytics;E-learning systems	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8363493	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não consegui entrar pra ver se avalia

Skill-Based Group Allocation of Students for Project-Based Learning Courses Using Genetic Algorithm: Weightless Penalty Model	10.1109/TALE.2018.8615338	In software engineering courses, project-based learning (PBL) is an essential counterpart for assessment. PBL requires a good spread of students based on their individual skills, this pushes for a successful outcome. Traditionally, the students are assigned to the group randomly by facilitators. In group assignment problem (GAP) students need to be placed in the appropriate groups encapsulating on general and specific criterions where possible to provide diversity. However, the need for a system arises where the assignment of students to groups require not only students to be based on certain criteria but also takes into account specific constraints. Constraints allow taking parameter such as skill preference in an unevenly or limited distributed skill set. For successful completion of projects, there is a need for groups that share same strength. In this paper, a generic method is proposed that uses the genetic algorithm to generate evenly balanced groups. We have employed weightless penalty function to rank the preference of certain constraints based on skills and incur a penalty if they are not satisfied. Since the benchmark datasets are unavailable, data collected from software engineering courses of our University is made available and its utilization with the proposed method is shown.	project-based learning; penalty function;genetic algorithm;group assignment problem;skill set;weightless	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8615338	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração
Several issues and possible solutions in compulsory project-based course	10.1109/FIE.2014.7044177	In 2009, a 12-week-long project-based course Optoelectronic Instrument Experiments (OIE) was launched at the School of Opto-Electronics, Beijing Institute of Technology. During the classes, the students are assigned to teams and each team chooses one project to implement in twelve weeks. Through the mini simulative "Cycle of Professional Practice", students will learn how to integrate the knowledge and techniques they have learned previously, and use different kinds of components and devices to construct an optoelectronic instrument. The main difference from the other project-based courses is that the OIE course is compulsory, which means every student must take this course. Here comes the problem. Young students usually are rebellious somehow. They would be enthusing about what they choose to do, while would be reluctant to even the same thing if they were arranged to do it. Moreover, students from China are good at theoretical knowledge but lack of initiative. Most of them prefer working alone to being a team member. These are stereotypes but also partly truth. Inactivity with repellent mood and initial resistance to team-based approaches became the biggest barrier in obligatory project-based courses. Aiming to solve those issues, several approaches were tried out during the OIE course design and the progresses, including the design of based projects, aptitude digging process and teamwork pedagogy, which seemed promising and inspiring in both stimulating students' enthusiasm and encouraging their team spirits. In this paper, we will give the detail of our tryout and analyses. The OIE course has been carried out for five academic years by now. Surveys conducted among the students who have taken the course and analyses are also included.	Project-base learning; Compulsory course; Teamwork;Aptitude digging	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7044177	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem metricas
Re-Engineering Higher Education by Models Suitable for COVID-19 and Students with Disabilities	10.1109/ICCSE51940.2021.9569451	Thanks to computers and the internet, since the rise of COVID-19, different methods of online teaching have replaced the face-to-face teaching; however there has not been a viable method of assessment that is fully capable of replacing in class assessments. It is hard, if not impossible, to maintain the integrity of the exams, when conducted remotely. Even prior to the COVID attack, arranging and conducting exams for students, who depend on Students Accessibility Services (SAS), were becoming cumbersome and a burden for universities and instructors. If there were no exams required, as an assessment tool, both the abovementioned issues, would not be a problem. In this paper a few theoretical common solutions to both the issues mentioned above is theorized, proposing elimination or reduction of the exams, as major assessment tool for undergraduate students. The model in which all the exams are eliminated is referred to as Stress-free, and the one with reduced exams is called Stress-less model. Implementing the models discussed in this paper, demand an overhaul of the entire higher education system.	Stress-free Education;Stress-less Education;Re-Engineering Education	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9569451	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração

Improving Grading Outcomes in Software Engineering Projects Through Automated Contributions Summaries	10.1109/ICSE-SEET58685.2023.00030	Teaming is a key aspect of most professional software engineering positions, and consequently, team-based learning (TBL) features heavily in many undergraduate computer science (CS) and software engineering programs. However, while TBL offers many pedagogical benefits, it is not without challenges. One such challenge is assessment, as the course teaching staff must be able to accurately identify individual students' contributions to both encourage and reward participation. In this paper, we study improvements to grading practises in the context of a CS1.5 introductory software engineering course, where assessing individual students' contributions to weekly lab assignments is done manually by teaching assistants (TAs). We explore the impact of presenting TAs with automated summaries of individual student contributions to their team's GitHub repository. To do so, we propose a novel algorithm, and implement a tool based off of it, AutoVCS. We measure the impact on grading metrics in terms of grading speed, grading consistency, and TA satisfaction. We evaluate our algorithm, as implemented in AutoVCS, in a controlled experimental study on Java-based lab assignments from a recent offering of NC State University's CS1.5 course. We find our automated summaries help TAs grade more consistently and provides students with more actionable feedback. Although TAs grade no faster using automated summaries, they nonetheless strongly prefer grading with the support of them than without. We conclude with recommendations for future work to explore improving consistency in contribution grading for student software engineering teams.	grading consistency;program analysis;software engineering teams	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10172639	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração
Technological developments that mediate the learning of engineers in their interaction with patients	10.1109/EDUNINE57531.2023.10102899	The objective of this article is to demonstrate how the experience of engineering students engaging directly with users, in this case patients with Parkinson's disease, in brigades and on Saturdays in Motion allows them to understand the problem and convert it to software technical requirements, with a direct impact on their engineering learning process; which is not just about data and numbers, but with human beings and all the complexity that this entails. The criterion beyond the professional competence itself by direct experience and rotation of tasks in the brigades, evidence the technical requirements of usability and the persistence of data, which makes the difference between an appropriate application or a big failure.	Parkinson disease;brigades; contextualized education in engineering;engineering and health;neurodegenerative disease	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10102899	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração
Innovations in Higher Education: MOODLE in Azerbaijan Universities	10.1109/UBMYK48245.2019.8965535	Aim of this study to describe innovations in higher education institutions and a way that they are applied in teaching and learning process in Azerbaijani universities. Nowadays knowledge and technology have a significant role in teaching and learning process in higher education. The changing scene of higher education institutions are requiring new technological implementation, new innovations and new approaches both in teaching and learning. The innovative teaching is one of the ways to enhance the quality of education. The use of innovations in higher education has a great impact in development of education and student accomplishments. Development and implementation of the ICT in education has brought many new opportunities and innovations, which are supported by the different teaching and learning platforms in higher education. This study is completed by retrieving information through a mixture of qualitative (literature review) and quantitative (survey questionnaires, focus group) methods to provide considerable evidence of the needs of Teaching and Learning in Azerbaijani Universities and MOODLE platform developed in Azerbaijani universities. Study was conducted online, and it was completed by 345 respondents from 8 partner and one non-partner universities in Azerbaijan. The link to the survey was sent out to partner universities by email and shared through social media.	innovation;teaching;learning; higher education institutions; ICT;learning management systems	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8965535	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração

Enhanced Student Engagement through Teamwork	10.1109 /FIE49875. 2021.9637476	In this Innovative Practice Full Paper we present an approach where we coupled several proven pedagogical practices to enhance student engagement during the time of remote/hybrid instruction due to the COVID-19 pandemic. One of these approaches was team-based learning throughout the entire semester which aided in student motivation. A second practice implemented was game-based learning to drive student engagement and excitement. This game-based learning approach used a semester-long scoring system which allowed students to compete for bonus points both on an individual and team basis. This enabled students to practice their teaming skills. Lastly, there was a major focus on diversity & inclusion in addition to teamwork in the course. Students were arranged into teams in an optimized manner by the CATME software. The optimization constraints were chosen using best practices for diversity in race & ethnicity, gender, skill levels, and leadership philosophy, while also considering students with similar schedules for availability purposes. The course also contained instructional modules on effective teamwork as well as contributions in the field of electrical engineering by underrepresented minorities. This paper details the innovative coupling of these practices and how they fit into the course's overall plan. Classroom activity and student perceptions associated with these practices were assessed via structured classroom observation using the COPUS protocol and collection of survey/focus group data, respectively. Assessment results are discussed, along with challenges encountered in this electromagnetics course in the hybrid/remote learning environment.	motivation;team-based learning;gamification;diversity inclusion	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9637476	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração
Enrichment of Problem Solving Skills Among Engineering Students through Cooperative Problem Based Learning	10.1109/WEFF. 2017.8467109	Cooperative Problem Based Learning (CPBL) has been implemented in several engineering institutions. Research has proven this methodology to significantly improve, among others, students' creativity, communication skills, life-long learning, and problem solving skills. However, the enrichment processes of the skills are less reported. This paper demonstrates how the enrichment of problem solving skills among engineering student undergoing CPBL happens. The research uses qualitative approach through semi-structured interviews and reviews of students' reflections. The result is demonstrated by the development of Problem Solving Skills Enhancement Model.	Cooperative Problem Based Learning (CPBL);Problem Solving Skills;Problem Solving Skills Enhancement Model	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8467109	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Ranking task activity in teaching software engineering	10.1109 /EDUCON. 2016.7474678	In this research, we investigate the possibility of applying ranking task activity in teaching and learning software engineering courses. We introduce three types of ranking tasks, conceptual-, contextual- and sequential ranking questions, which cover most core topics such as requirement analysis, architecture design and quality validation in the course. We have also done experiments on a group of students to see if ranking tasks could increase their conceptual knowledge in specific areas. Assessments were given in order to evaluate the effectiveness of this activity, showing an obvious increase in complex conceptual understanding.	Ranking Task;Software Engineering;Just-in-time Teaching	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7474678	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração
DevOpsEnvy: An Education Support System for DevOps	10.1109 /CSEET. 2017.17	As an emerging approach to support fast delivery of software features with reliable quality, DevOps attracts more and more practitioners and shows the potential to become one of the mainstream approach for software development and operation. Many universities begin to offer DevOps related courses to the students majored in software engineering and computer science. However, as a critical part of a DevOps course, the project practicing using DevOps might cast big challenges for teachers, compared to traditional project practicing. For example, the more frequent than ever delivery in DevOps practicing will inevitably increase the workload vastly for teachers to conduct effective evaluation. In this paper, we introduce a web based system (DevOpsEnvy) to support the management and monitoring of student teams practicing DevOps. By integrating several popular open source tools, this system provides students with features such as group management, project status monitoring and student performance data analysis, etc. Meanwhile, DevOpsEnvy system also provides teachers with sufficient evidence to perform evaluation. Our preliminary trial in Nanjing University revealed several advantages of DevOpsEnvy system.	DevOps;Education Support System;Project Management;Software Engineering	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8166681	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração
Interdisciplinary Software Projects as an Active Methodology to Practice for the Profession	10.1109/SECM. 2017.8	This paper presents the experience of designing, implementing and evaluating a first semester project-based course for the software engineering bachelors undergraduate curriculum at PUC-MG in Brazil in 2016. We present an overview of the motivation behind the curriculum and the challenges and restrictions considering the generation of students who are going to follow it. The methodology of the course, the selection of the projects, the composition of teams, the work that the students must deliver, the questions that usually arise during the project implementation, and the lessons learned from the perspective of the students and professors are presented. We concluded that although it is a challenge for first year students, the learning experience with the project-based course motivates their learning.	project-based course; teamwork;collaboration; interdisciplinary	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7964619	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração

Adapting a Software Acquisition Curriculum to Instruct Supply Chain Risk Management in a Project-Based Software Development Course	10.1109 /SEENG53126. 2021.00014	Project-Based Instruction has become a de-facto standard in many software engineering curricula. It engages the learner in critical thinking, fosters introspection, improves retention, and enables generalization of concepts to new engineering situations. However, as projects often focus on software construction, students tend to adopt third-party technologies without critical reflection. Such insufficient supply chain risk management (SCRM) throughout the project then threatens learning success, as students struggle to recover from inadequacies and vulnerabilities in the adopted technology. We therefore propose a capstone-style course structure to deliver an industry-realistic, project-based, and teamwork-centric software development approach. Using an existing SCRM curriculum, we add acquisition planning, bidding, and monitoring activities to an existing course design and assess learning outcomes.	software engineering education;supply chain risk management;SCRM; software acquisition;team management;project-based learning	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9474643	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração
Evaluation of Developing Educational Chatbots Based on the Seven Principles for Good Teaching	10.1109/TALE. 2018.8615175	The use of chatbot, in general, is gaining popularity in several sectors. However, in the education field, chatbot as a learning tool to improve the teaching is still in its infancy. The course team developed several chatbot prototypes using Agile Software Development. This study evaluated the educational appropriateness of chatbot using Chickering and Gamson's Seven Principles for Good Teaching to improve the delivery of a group assessment in higher education. Findings showed that the use of chatbot addressed five principles in enhancing the traditional course teaching.	teaching principle;agile framework;chatbot;crime investigation;higher education	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8615175	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração
A Statistical Study of Female Students in a Software Engineering Class: Preparedness	10.1109 /FIE61694. 2024.10893315	his is a research-to-practice full paper. Several research studies indicate that women who have opted into a computing career path must regularly contend with negative stereotypes about their technical abilities. These stereotypes are often cited as contributing factors to the underrepresentation of women in computing. To counter these stereotypes and enhance female participation in computer science, numerous interventions have been designed. However, most existing research tends to rely on anecdotal evidence and questionnaires to study these stereotypes. In contrast, our study collected data from over 900 students over a span of eight years and adopted a comprehensive quantitative approach to examine these stereotypes about female students. We utilized pre-class GitHub contribution metrics to evaluate students' programming experience and an array of in-class grading items to measure students' performance. Additionally, we mined the project repositories' git logs to gain insights into students' contributions to team projects. Our investigation began by probing whether there was a notable difference in the technical backgrounds or preparedness between female and male students. The results indicated that males tended to be better prepared. Next, we explored potential disparities in class performance between the two genders. Our findings revealed that males and females each excelled in different areas. We were also interested in discerning if female and male students contributed equally to team projects; our analysis affirmed that the contributions were comparable between the two groups. If allowed to choose their teammates, we examined whether they showed a preference for single-gender teams or mixed-gender teams. Our conclusions indicated no marked preference. This paper aims to augment the body of research on computing education by assisting educators in gaining a better understanding of female students in the class. Moreover, it tests the stereotypes by comparing them with empirical results.	Software Engineering Education;Gender Study; Statistical Study;Quantitative Study;GitHub	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10893315	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração

Face-to-Face and On-line Physics Teaching on Engineering Courses: Strategy Effectiveness Measurements	10.1109 /CISPEE47794. 2021.9507204	Due to the recent global events, in this case, the Covid-19 pandemic, a new challenge arises at all levels. Higher education was one of the most affected areas. This communication presents the use of interactive simulation software in on-line Physics education. This resource is directed towards Engineering courses which are offered at Instituto Superior de Transportes e Comunicações (ISUTC) a private institution of higher education in Mozambique. In the field of Physics, it was necessary to move from face-to-face teaching to on-line teaching. This discipline is divided into two semesters as Physics I and Physics II, with their components, in theory, problems and laboratory. To implement the laboratory classes, a search on the web was done and a virtual lab model was selected, which made use of interactive simulation experiments. In the first semester, the laboratory experiments were selected based on the criteria that they exist in laboratory work in a face-to-face system. In the second semester it was possible to develop totally new laboratory experiments. The conventional Physics teaching laboratory, LabFis, was reinvented as a virtual laboratory. Using a platform of open access, the lab guides were prepared for the different experiments. The student is guided to use the simulations to get an effective learning. To measure the effectiveness of this strategy on the on-line system, an analysis was done of the assessment results of three groups of fifty students of different Engineering courses. A comparison was established from the results in Physics I and Physics II. The assessment results compared are of the year 2019, and the year 2020. The average of students' assessments is used as an indicator of effectiveness of the adopted strategy. In general, it was observed an improvement on this indicator. After an uncertain start, the students were motivated and they welcomed these changes. They adapted satisfactorily to the new paradigm.	Physics education;online teaching;virtual laboratory; strategy effectiveness	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9507204	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração
Teaching High-Frequency Circuit Design in Online Environment	10.23919 /MIPRO52101. 2021.9596897	COVID-19 pandemic has affected engineering education worldwide with most departments opting to switch to an online (remote) mode of instruction. At our institution, the switch happened in a matter of weeks which presented significant problems in teaching the fourth year Microwave Circuit Design courses. These courses were originally designed with a "studio" component where much of the design and experimentation happened during the so-called lab hours. Experimentation was very dependent on access to specialized and very expensive equipment, most importantly to VNA-s (vector network analyzers) and TDR oscilloscopes (time-domain reflectometry). Several compromises were made for online instruction: a) reduction of teaching material to essential components, b) use of inexpensive instrumentation, c) redesign of labs for off-line work, and d) reduction in the size of teams to two members instead of three. While the first may be advisable in any circumstances, the last two were driven primarily by logistical or organizational considerations. We report on how our "studio" environment was transformed into online "lab" assignments and how this affected course content. Key aspect of it is the development of affordable instrumentation that students can purchase themselves. This includes VNA-s and software-defined radios which are utilized as spectrum analyzers. We describe the initial uses of such instrumentation in our courses, their pros and cons, and the remaining issues. These developments have the potential to fundamentally change how we teach these and similar courses and we expect that many of the ideas being implemented will carry over into face-to-face instruction.	engineering education; microwave circuits;project-based learning;microwave measurements;teamwork	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9596897	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração
CareerVio: A Platform for Personalized Collaborative and Gamified Software Engineering MOOCs	10.1109 /JCSSE54890. 2022.9836240	Software engineer is one of the highest in-demand manpower jobs in the world. As the prolonged COVID19 pandemic crisis, more and more people throughout the world became unemployed. There arises an incoming demand for reskilling and career shifting to software engineer. Online learning through MOOCs is, therefore, a viable and practical solution. However, reskilling to be a software engineer requires specific platform support that is able to develop both technical and non-technical skills, including management, communication, and teamwork, that traditional MOOCs cannot fulfill the challenges. This research aims to augment the traditional MOOCs with the additional use of personalization, collaboration, and gamification theory in the name of "CareerVio MOOCs Platform". The distinct supports and services provided by the platform comprise team composition, team recomposition, team learning, and team assessments. CareerVio enables learners to master the necessary skills required in software engineer career, enhances the interaction between learners, and allows them to take what they have learned off the page and put it into practice.	MOOCs;collaboration; personalization;software engineering;gamification; CareerVio	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9836240	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não avalia

<p>EVAL IQ: Intelligent Educational Assessment and Recommendation Platform</p>	<p>10.1109 /ICTBIG64922. 2024.10911676</p>	<p>EVAL IQ is an innovative educational assessment platform designed to simplify the evaluation process for both educators and learners. It offers separate portals tailored to each group's needs. Teachers can manage student data, create, and organize courses, design questions, and assess performance using automated scoring and in-depth analytics. The platform also includes a feedback system to facilitate continuous improvement. For students, EVAL IQ provides an easy-to-use interface for completing assessments, meeting deadlines, and providing feedback. Built with modern technology, EVAL IQ ensures efficient, transparent, and effective educational assessments, enhancing the overall teaching and learning experience.</p>	<p>Educational Assessment Platform;Automated Scoring; Machine Learning in Education;Random Forest Classifier;Course Recommendations;Student Feedback System;Online Examination System; Personalized Learning;E- Learning Solutions; Educational Technology; Feedback Mechanisms</p>	<p>https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10911676</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<p>não foca em colaboração</p>
<p>Telecommunications Engineering at Macquarie University: Modernisation and Vision</p>	<p>10.1109/TALE. 2018.8615229</p>	<p>The Telecommunications Engineering degree at Macquarie is undergoing renewal, simultaneously with a transformation in pedagogy by the School of Engineering and also a change in curriculum structure by Macquarie University. This work-in-progress paper reports a study of the effect of changes in Telecommunications Engineering education. These include updated technical content imparted through an educational approach which includes project-based learning (PBL), project ownership, replacement of traditional lectures, virtual laboratories and an emphasis on software tools and programming skills.</p>	<p>project-based learning; telecoms education principles;virtual laboratories; interactive lectures</p>	<p>https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8615229</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<p>não é de engenharia de software</p>
<p>Motivation of Computer Science Students at Universities Organized around Small Groups</p>	<p>10.1109 /EDUCON. 2019.8725059</p>	<p>The academic performance of students is affected by the academic context, their aptitudes and their motivation. The latter is particularly important in Engineering disciplines because the contents to be learnt are especially complex and many students end up having a low performance that leads them to absenteeism and drop out. The European Higher Education Area (EHEA) provides several recommendations related to the academic context (ongoing assessment, mentoring processes and active learning methods among others) that seem to have a positive impact on the students' motivation. However, these cannot always be implemented due to the high number of students per class existing at many Universities. This contribution presents an empirical case study performed with 149 Computer Science students of a University organized around small groups and innovative educational methodologies. The benefits and outcomes of this academic conditions, as well as their impact in the students' motivation, are analyzed and discussed.</p>	<p>Motivation;Engineering; Computer Science;Software Engineering;Active learning; Project Based Learning</p>	<p>https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8725059</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<p>duplicado</p>
<p>Motivation of Computer Science Students at Universities Organized around Small Groups</p>	<p>10.1109 /EDUCON. 2019.8725074</p>	<p>The academic performance of students is affected by the academic context, their aptitudes and their motivation. The latter is particularly important in Engineering disciplines because the contents to be learnt are especially complex and many students end up having a low performance that leads them to absenteeism and drop out. The European Higher Education Area (EHEA) provides several recommendations related to the academic context (ongoing assessment, mentoring processes and active learning methods among others) that seem to have a positive impact on the students' motivation. However, these cannot always be implemented due to the high number of students per class existing at many Universities. This contribution presents an empirical case study performed with 149 Computer Science students of a University organized around small groups and innovative educational methodologies. The benefits and outcomes of this academic conditions, as well as their impact in the students' motivation, are analyzed and discussed.</p>	<p>Motivation;Engineering; Computer Science;Software Engineering;Active learning; Project Based Learning</p>	<p>https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8725074</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<p>duplicado</p>
<p>An Integrated Approach to the Requirements Engineering and Process Modelling Teaching</p>	<p>10.1109 /CSEET. 2016.23</p>	<p>One of the most important knowledge area on Software Engineering is Requirements Engineering and know properly related techniques and methods is crucial to a software practitioners. This article aims to present a method adopted to teach Requirements Engineering and Process Modelling on Software Engineering undergraduate course. It was developed a method to integrate two disciplines and improve learning of both. This method was used during two semesters, with 95 students involved. The reaching of teaching method was analyzed in two ways: grades and feedback on technical report analysis, in both were applied some statistical techniques in order to get better conclusions. The teaching methodology using shows good results, but it is important gather more data in order to provide more assured conclusions.</p>	<p>Software Engineering; Requirements Engineering; Process Modelling;Active Learning;PBL</p>	<p>https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7474481</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<p>não foca em colaboração</p>

Metrics in Agile Project Courses		We believe that software engineering should be taught in a hands-on way such as through a project-based capstone course where students apply the learned concepts in a real setting. However, such a teaching format can be challenging and time-consuming for instructors. In this paper we explain how we selected and introduced a set of metrics to improve the manageability of our large multi-project capstone course. We regularly run such a course with over 100 students developing applications in 10-12 parallel projects over the course of one semester. Our approach focuses on measuring the success of three key workflows, namely Merge Management, Continuous Integration and Continuous Delivery. We show how these metrics help the instructors to keep track of the progress of multiple projects running at the same time, enabling them to identify and react to problems early.	agile software engineering; capstone course;project management;metrics; continuous integration; continuous delivery	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7883316	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Guiding Principles for Assessing Software Engineering Teams	10.1109 /FIE61694. 2024.10893426	This research-to-practice full paper presents guiding principles for developing assessments based on our experience in teaching the software engineering capstone course over the last twelve years. Software engineering courses are central to computer science and engineering programs. To provide students with an authentic learning experience, teams of students work on realistic projects that help them apply theoretical concepts to develop practical skills. Challenges arise with increasing class sizes and limited teaching resources. Despite these constraints, educators must intentionally design assessments that align with learning theories that promote deeper learning opportunities and support lifelong learning. In this work, we report on our experience designing and adapting the assessments used in our software engineering capstone course over the past twelve years. We reflect on our approach by aligning the evaluation strategies to learning theories such as behaviorism, constructivism, and social constructivism. This research-to-practice paper discusses the practical implications behind different assessment strategies in the face of large class sizes and presents guiding principles for developing assessments for software engineering team projects.	Capstone project;authentic assessments;behaviorism; constructivism;social constructivism;large classes	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10893426	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração
Towards an Approach to Prevent Social Loafing in Software Development Teams	10.1109/ESEM. 2017.37	[Background] A high-functioning team is a decisive factor for a successful software development project. However building such a team is not easy. Among many issues and obstacles encountered by teams, social loafing is a common but difficult one to tackle. [Aim] We intend to construct an approach to effectively prevent social loafing behaviors in software development teams. [Method] We built one social loafing prevention approach based on existing literature and survey instruments. It has been applied in an educational context with 2nd-year computer science students working on software development projects in teams. [Results] The approach starts with increasing team members' awareness of social loafing. Team Expectations Agreement (TEA) is then used to help the team to write down the terms that explicitly prevent social loafing. During the project, a small survey instrument is used to track regularly if the specified terms are followed by the team members. At the end of a period, the presence/absence of social loafing is assessed by the team using another short survey. How to interpret the results of the surveys is explained as part of the presented approach. [Conclusions] This approach has potential to improve team-work skills of students, which is not adequately addressed in higher education programs. Meanwhile it can be adapted in professional software development environments to prevent social loafing and improve teamwork. The next step of our study will be using the collected data to evaluate the proposed approach, and formulating a set of recommendations to use the approach in the professional software development context.	teamwork;social loafing; Team Expectations Agreement	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8170110	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	fora da educação
Designing Framework for Evaluating Community of Practice for Software Engineering Project Management	10.1109 /RIVF60135. 2023.10471839	In this paper, we identify major components assessed in the evaluation of the community of practice (CoP) formed for project management in software engineering classroom environment. Given the components, we also design sample questions for the assessment questionnaire used for students' survey.	community of practice; software engineering;project management;classroom environment;assessment; long-term strategy;short-term strategy	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10471839	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem educação

<p>A Cross-Discipline Technopreneurship Course: Student Perceived Benefits and Considerations</p>	<p>10.1109 /FIE61694. 2024.10893424</p>	<p>This innovative practice full paper describes the development and implementation of a cross-discipline techno-preneurship course, highlighting best practice, the benefits of the course perceived by students and further considerations. The course is offered at a large prestigious UK university in a department where electronic, electrical engineering and computer science courses are taught, and is mandatory for the electrical and electronic engineering students and elective for computer engineering students, who are in their third year of study as part of combined bachelor's and master's degree programs. It emphasizes teamwork, problem identification, problem solving, and creativity. This course uniquely integrates engineering skills with entrepreneurship, using a project-based learning approach requiring students to work in teams to develop a pitch, business plan, technical feasibility study, and a working prototype. These have been shown to be the most predominant methods to assess technopreneurship courses. However, the course is set apart by the focus on real-world world problems and fostering connections between students and the local start-up ecosystem. A key strength of the course is to improve students professional skills, which has been shown to be desired by employers in industry. In this work, we outline the course structure, intended learning outcomes, assessment, schedule of teaching, and present findings gained from teaching the course. Therefore, it is easily replicable by other practitioners. We detail how this builds upon previous practices to further the aims of the course to increase links with the local start-up ecosystem and improve students professional skills. The results of an online questionnaire proposed by the University optionally completed by students at the end of the course in the 2022/23 and 2023/24 academic years, revealed that students do perceive the benefit of the course as a way to develop their professional skills, such as public speaking, teamwork, and writing skills. Furthermore, the students appreciated the course structure and felt well-informed about the assessment. The results also revealed that the students rated the course highly for overall quality. The work produced by the teams confirmed our hypothesis that the hardware and/or software nature of their prototype/product appears to be disconnected from the makeup of students from the two different program backgrounds enrolled on the course. For instance, a team of only electronic engineering students still had a highly important software component that was vital for their final product. However, even more interestingly, the success of each team would appear to be based upon the team dynamics, which was monitored by the academic instructor in chard of the course throughout the entirety of the course and was a part of the assessment. Teams that demonstrated good levels of teamwork, overall tended to do better in the course than teams, which did not.</p>	<p>computing engineering; electrical engineering; entrepreneurship;innovation; problem solving</p>	<p>https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10893424</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/></p>	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>	<p>não é de engenharia de software</p>
<p>An industry-mentored undergraduate software engineering project</p>	<p>10.1109/FIE. 2014.7044180</p>	<p>Software design lifecycle application to a real world project is a critical skill required by the undergraduate computer engineer. Interaction with the local professional software development community is also an equally important opportunity that should be provided. This fosters growth of both technical and soft skills, and exposes the student to standards and working practices in providing quality software solutions for customers. This paper describes the structure of a group-based software development project that integrates industry mentors in the learning and assessment processes. Industry liaisons are given a forum to elucidate some of the industry's requirements of students in terms of knowledge of software design and industrial standards; students gain better understanding of some of the processes which take place in an actual industrial setting; and university curriculum gains industry relevance. The impact of this project is yet to be fully assessed. Assessment can be determined from two aspects: (1) in terms of the benefit to the student (effectiveness of learning objectives achieved, and motivation gained from project based learning and group work) and (2) the impact of providing industry led mentorship.</p>	<p>Industries;Computers; Software engineering; Education;Standards; Software design</p>	<p>https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7044180</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/></p>	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>	<p>não sei se tem avaliação</p>

Aligning the learning Experience in a Project-Based Course: lessons learned from the Redesign of a Programming Lab	10.1145/3528231.3528358	In teaching and training the next generation of software engineers, programming labs with students working together in small groups provide the opportunity to obtain hands-on experience for software projects involving multiple developers. However, more than other types of courses, programming labs face some challenges in providing a similar learning outcome for all students. Based on feedback and own experience from various iterations of the programming lab at TU Dortmund University, we identified that the learning experience varies significantly due to heterogeneous prior knowledge, experience levels, and personality traits of both students and tutors. In this experience report, we present our approach towards aligning the learning experience by applying three different didactic improvements based on well-studied concepts: (1) the idea of worked-out examples is transferred to teaching the software development process by providing a small software application with all corresponding artefacts like diagrams, program code and documentation, focusing on their relationships and development activities. (2) Goal-oriented and structured learning is used to define learning outcomes for every group meeting as a common ground, while audience response systems are utilized to motivate the attendance and allow students to self-reflect on their knowledge and competence level. (3) We harmonize the role of tutors by holding dedicated teaching workshops for tutors' responsibilities in the programming lab. The different approaches are evaluated based on surveys for students and tutors over three iterations of the programming lab at TU Dortmund University. Both sides' positive responses and feedback resulted in an enumeration of lessons learned as recommendations and support for other similar courses.	learning outcomes;audience response system;worked-out examples;tutoring; programming lab;software engineering	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9814915	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração
Integrated E-project collaborative management system: Empirical study for problem-based learning project	10.1109/ICITEED.2017.8250457	Traditional way of teaching is teacher-centered, which encourage the learning environment that the student will only recognize, memorize and learn the content of the class. This is a one-way communication teaching from lecturer to students [5]. Therefore, this way of learning limits students' solving problem skills and their abilities to learn by themselves. This will lead to difficulty situation when students have to manage and solve real problems. This method of learning also obstructs students to develop teamwork skills. Thus this research will explore teaching process by using the project-based management system to develop a team management program. Also, 'Collaborative Management' system will use for tracking student's learning behaviors and to support instructional learning by using 'Problem Based Learning (PBL)'. The results of this study show factors effecting teamwork efficiency and indicate skills that students need to study effectively based on the problem-based learning framework (PBL) as a guideline for developing effective skills in effective learning environment.	Problem-Based Learning (PBL);Problem- Based Learning by Project Based; Collaboration Group; Collaborative Management System;Self-Assessment; Peer Evaluation	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8250457	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Electronic Circuit Education Innovation: Take Low-pass Filter Teaching as an Example	10.1109/IGARSS46834.2022.9883320	In recent years, the educational innovation of electronic information courses has attracted widespread attention. This article combines the emergence of new educational concepts and teaching methods to propose a four-in-one educational method of "theory-simulation-experiment-innovation". Practical teaching proves that the four-in-one teaching method helps to improve the teaching quality of electronic circuits.	educational innovation;low-pass filter;four-in-one teaching	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9883320	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração
Improving programming education through gameful	978-1-4673-8633-3	In this paper we present a newly developed online learning platform which introduces gamification elements into software engineering education. Starting from assumptions based on cognitive load theory we present the design of an online gamification-based training system to be used in software engineering contexts. Students can voluntarily solve challenges for which they may earn credits. These small problems serve as assessments; the approach follows the assessment for learning paradigm in that assessments provide formative feedback to enhance the learning experience. The combination of formative assessment and gamification is new to software engineering education. We describe system design as well as the different types of challenges in detail. We also provide several examples for actual challenges used in an object-oriented programming introduction using Java.	earning;cognitive load theory; gamification;object-oriented programming;assessment for learning;Java;online web-based self-assessment Introduction (Heading 1)	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7474653	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração

Teaching Conceptual Modeling in Online Courses: Coping with the Need for Individual Feedback to Modeling Exercises	10.1109 /CSEET. 2017.30	Educational approaches for computer science proposing the use of complete online courses or traditional courses employing some kind of online material have received much attention recently. The integration of online materials into traditional courses or the replacement of entire courses offer huge possibilities, including increased teaching quality and better study and work alignment. However, researchers and teachers also identified some drawbacks of using online material, including the lack of interaction between students and teachers, and the need to discuss and provide feedback of the students' exercise results. A solution for providing such feedback are automated assessment tools which can generate feedback. However, these tools are not applicable in all situations, e.g. for providing feedback to conceptual modeling exercises. In this paper, we report on the design and implementation of an online course for teaching conceptual modeling. In this course, we use explicitly ambiguous exercises and sketch multiple solutions in brief whiteboard-style videos, thus enabling students to assess their own solutions. Evaluation results show that the proposed approach is able to fulfill students' educational needs.	computer science education; conceptual modeling;online courses	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8166694	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração
Engagement Contexts of Software Engineering Education Projects	10.1109 /EAEEIE54893. 2022.9820379	The inclusion of a capstone project has become a core component of many software engineering and computing related courses. There is general agreement that a substantial final year project provides an opportunity for students to demonstrate breadth and depth of acquired knowledge alongside industry-oriented skills and independent working. Traditionally, capstone projects are academic-proposed individual projects, in which students work from a project outline with one or more academic supervisors. Although useful to demonstrate the application of knowledge, such projects lack key activities that have been cited as beneficial to student experience and career-readiness, specifically working with others in a team and with external clients. In our study we provided a range of projects for students in a final year, compulsory capstone Software Engineering project module which forms a major requirement of the overall degree. The students were required to select a project which could be individual or team-based and where the origin of the project could be academic-proposed, student-proposed, community-based or industry-supported. Students then completed these projects with a mixture of academic supervision and, where appropriate, input from the community group or industrial partner who had proposed it. After completion, a mixed-method approach was used to evaluate student experience and satisfaction. The initial findings indicate that students who chose a team-based project and specifically those who took projects proposed for a real-world user (community or industry) were more satisfied with their experience and agreed to a greater extent that they had developed new skills. Within this group, those who chose the community projects expressed the highest levels of satisfaction, feeling rewarded that their contribution was to a project for social good. These initial findings validate the beneficial approach of involving external partners such as community groups in team-based capstone projects.	software engineering education;collaborative learning;project-based learning;capstone course; community engagement	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9820379	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem métrica
Pilot experience applying an active learning methodology in a software engineering classroom	10.1109 /EDUCON. 2018.8363331	Software Engineering I is a mandatory subject for undergraduate students that is taught in the second semester of the 2nd year of the Degree in Computer Sciences at the University of Salamanca (Spain). This degree exists since 1989 but it has transformed over time according to the education law changes in Spain and Europe. Software Engineering I is the first subject related to the area of software engineering that is taught in the degree. The novelty of the concepts and the need to develop abstract thinking to acquire the different competences of the subject, implies a handicap to teach the subject. The final grades obtained by the students in the subject are fairly low compared with other subjects in the degree. Moreover, the attendance to the face-to-face classes is continuously reduced throughout the semester, which affects to the continuous assessment. Some initiatives have been applied during previous school years but a global change of the subject is necessary. In order to increase the success rate of the subject and to achieve that students are involved in the learning process, authors have implemented an active learning methodology based on team working. Furthermore, two instruments have defined to measure the impact of the changes and evaluate the pilot.	active learning;software engineering;team work; quantitative analysis;learning styles;project-based learning	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8363331	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

Implementation of Active Learning Methods in Mechanical Engineering Education to Enhance Students' Performance	10.1109/COMPASAC.2016.12	In an effort to enhance active learning in the subject of internal combustion engines, we introduced the combined use of concept mapping and online course module techniques as a part of the course. For the purpose of this study, we used an experimental design that involves a single instructor teaching the topic of introduction to the internal combustion engines (IICE) in a given semester. Students were randomly allocated to experimental (n = 77) and control groups (n = 74). The experimental group was subjected to concept mapping strategy and the use of an online course module in addition to traditional teaching (lecture method). The control group was taught using a traditional teaching method. Results revealed that students in the experimental group had significantly higher scores than those of the control group. The performance of the students was analyzed at different levels of Bloom's taxonomy. Our results are consistent with the findings from other researches that students' performance improves by the use of active learning methods. Students reacted positively to this newly presented methodology.	Active learning;Concept mapping;Introduction to internal combustion engines	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7552215	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração
Educational Software Product: Investigating the Need for a New Software Methodology	10.1109/ICCIT-144147971.2020.9213755	Developing software needs art in addition to the scientific knowledge. Graduation project is a compulsory course requires the students to develop a software product. Students are using the traditional software development methodologies typically designed for software oriented for business (business software), therefore it is not suitable for software developed to fulfill requirements of academic subject (educational software). These two types of software are different in many perspectives. In educational software, the purpose is to satisfy pedagogical and educational purpose. This sharp variance caused many difficulties such as loss of time, cost and quality commitment and missing the correct guidance that helps the students later in the industry. In this paper, we are targeting to identify, clarify, explore, and highlight the variances between educational and business software. To achieve this target, a comparison based on software life cycle and project knowledge areas has been prepared between educational and business software. The results that have been extracted from the comparisons proved the difficulties of using tradition methodologies to develop educational software. Finally, recommendations to develop especial methodology for educational software have been stated.	Software;Education;and Methodology	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9213755	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração
Measure Students' Contribution in Web Programming Projects by Exploring Source Code Repository	10.1109/ICS51289.2020.00099	Large scale software systems are usually developed by multiple teams. Communication and collaboration skills are required as essential skills of qualified developers in the modern environment, in addition to the technical hard skills of software engineering. Therefore, group projects are included in almost courses to train students' professional skills and teamwork abilities. However, in their group projects, most of the students are only required to accomplish functional requirements with limited awareness about the quality of the software. This issue seriously affects the development speed, since it is difficult for team members to read others' code during the development process. Hence, we propose a quality-driven assessment system for group projects with the capability of checking the coding style after each submission and providing immediate feedback to help student teams maintain the code quality for their group projects. Besides, to objectively assess the contribution of all students in group projects, we propose a set of repository mining metrics including two major categories of productivity and quality. A case study about the usage of the system and the proposed contribution evaluation metrics are introduced to illustrate the feasibility of our approach.	Group Project;Continuous Integration;Automation;Code Quality	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9359031	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Assessing teamwork skills and knowledge	10.1109/ISECon.2014.6891052	This paper discusses the importance of assessing teamwork professional skills, in the science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) disciplines. There is a difficulty in assessing teamwork skills in an educational setting. The main objective of this research is to propose an assessment framework and rubric for facilitating the assessment of teamwork skills. In this paper, learning outcome areas for teamwork skills and knowledge are first defined and then assessment tools for the identified learning outcome areas are introduced. In addition, an assessment rubric is proposed based on the framework of the Model of Domain Learning (MDL) and to apply aspects of the literature found in accordance with the learning outcome areas of teamwork. The assessment rubric will be tested in different course levels in the STEM disciplines at different colleges.	Assessment;Teamwork; Model of Domain Learning; STEM	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=6891052	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem métricas

Virtual Teams and Employability in Global Software Engineering Education	10.1109 /ICGSE. 2015.21	Universities face many challenges when creating opportunities for student experiences of global software engineering. We provide a model for introducing global software engineering into the computing curriculum. Our model is based on a three year collaboration between Robert Gordon University, UK and the International Institute for IT Bangalore, India. We provide evidence based on student feedback from three cohorts of virtual team who never met face to face. We found potential employers were supportive of global software engineering in university curricula. We identify four key principles for global software engineering student projects: reconcile contrasting assessment demands between institutions, create a detailed joint timetable to reconcile teaching calendars, provide a project management framework to support phased delivery and carefully manage project scope.	Global Software Engineering Education;Virtual Teams; Student Projects	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7224489	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração
Exploring perspectives and experiences of diverse learners' acceptance of online educational engineering games as learning tools in the classroom	10.1109 /FIE44824. 2020.9273886	This Research Full paper focuses on perceptions and experiences of freshman and sophomore engineering students when playing an online serious engineering game that was designed to improve engineering intuition and knowledge of statics. Use of serious educational engineering games has increased in engineering education to help students increase technical competencies in engineering disciplines. However, few have investigated how these engineering games are experienced by the students; how games influence students' perceptions of learning, or how these factors may lead to inequitable perspectives among diverse populations of students. Purpose/Hypothesis: The purpose of this study was to explore the perceptions, appeal, and opinions about the efficacy of educational online games among a diverse population of students in an engineering mechanics statics course. It was hypothesized that compared to majority groups (e.g., men, White), women of color who are engineering students would experience less connections to the online educational game in terms of ease of use and level of frustration while playing. It is believed that these discordant views may negatively influence the game's appeal and efficacy towards learning engineering in this population of students. Design/Method: The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) is expanded in this study, where the perspectives of women of colour (Latinx, Asian and African American) engineering students are explored. The research approach employed in this study is a mixed-method sequential exploratory design, where students first played the online engineering educational game, then completed a questionnaire, followed by participation in a focus group. Responses were initially analyzed through open and magnitude coding approaches to understand whether students thought these educational games reflected their personal culture. Results: Preliminary results indicate that though the majority of the students were receptive to using the online engineering software for their engineering education, merely a few intimated that they would use this software for engineering exam or technical job interview preparation. A level-one categorical analysis identified a few themes that comprised unintended preservation of inequality in favor of students who enjoyed contest-based education and game technology. Competition-based valuation of presumed mastery of course content fostered anxiety and intimidation among students, which caused some to "game the game" instead of studying the material, to meet grade goals. Some students indicated that they spent more time (than necessary) to learn the goals of the game than engineering content itself, suggesting a need to better integrate course material while minimizing cognitive effort in learning to navigate the game. Conclusions: Preliminary results indicate that engineering software's design and the way is coupled with course grading and assessment of learning outcomes, affect student perceptions of the technology's acceptance, usefulness, and ease of use as a "learning tool." Students were found to have different expectations of serious games juxtaposed software/apps designed for entertainment. Conclusions also indicate that acceptance of inquiry-based educational games in a classroom among diverse populations of students should clearly articulate and connect the game goals/objectives with class curriculum content. Findings also indicate that a multifaceted schema of tools, such as feedback on game challenges, and explanations for predictions of the game should be included in game/app designs.	Engineering Education; Online Games;Technology Acceptance Model	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9273886	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração

Work in Progress: Task-centric Holistic Teaching Approach to Teaching Programming with Java	10.1109/EDUCON45650.2020.9125168	The academia-industry gap in computer science persists since last two decades at least. Industry expects that computer science graduates possess not only profound technical knowledge and skills but also transferable skills such as communication and collaboration in team, problem-solving ability. Students need to learn those skills during their university studies to be competitive in the market after their graduation. This paper first examines the skill gap between graduates and industry expectations, and the existing didactic approaches in computer science education. The authors then present how the Java programming course has been taught using the task-centric holistic agile teaching approach T-CHAT to enhance both technical skills and transferable skills in students. The learning process is described with learning activities and assessments that are constructively aligned with the intended learning outcomes of the course. This is work in progress, so evaluation of the course is planned for future work.	Computer science education; Problem-based learning; Project-based learning; Research-based learning; Perceptual learning	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9125168	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não avalia
Best Practice Guidelines for Technology Enhanced E-Learning	10.1109/DeSE.2016.33	This paper discusses effective teaching techniques for online courses. We present and summarise our experience of online teaching techniques that are currently adopted in our teaching. Our approach consists of five main principles: online resources, course structure, course participation technique, student-centred interaction for learning, and online assessments. We believe student-centred interactions will enhance their learning experience much more effective when studying online courses. However, there are difficulties for online professors to facilitate such interactions and to make assessments. We propose a number of key teaching strategies to support student learning by using online technology. They are based on guidelines on effective teaching techniques, content preparation & management, course structuring, existing standards, assessment, and evaluation.	e-learning;guidelines; assessments;classroom; effective-learning;online teacher	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7930646	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração
Team Maturity in Software Engineering Teams	10.1109/ESEM.2017.36	Background: In Software Engineering (SE) the term maturity is often linked to the work process and product quality. In many cases, team maturity is seen as a backdrop to the process of SE, and sometimes as something that is known to exist, but which cannot be understood, neither measured accurately nor even dimension its value. Aim: In this article, we seek to understand the concept of mature teams in the context of SE, from the perspective of the software engineers themselves. Methods: We performed an exploratory qualitative research, collecting data from 26 practitioners, from 6 companies in 4 cities in Brazil. Data was analyzed using coding techniques from qualitative research. Results: Our findings pointed out three major dimensions of the concept of Team Maturity - Learning, Relationship and Technical Maturity - which, when kept in balance, can enhance the collective productivity, product quality and also the customer satisfaction. Conclusions: These results extend our current understanding of maturity of SE teams, shedding light on aspects that have been little explored so far in this field. The proposed model can serve as a guide for teams to enhance their approach of teamwork and for future research in this area.	team maturity;software engineering team;software development;teamwork; human aspects;qualitative research	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8170109	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
A suggested strategy for teamwork teaching in undergraduate engineering programmes particularly in China	10.1109/FIE.2014.7044077	Teamwork has been considered as an important learning outcome for engineering graduates. A pilot study on teamwork training was conducted in a joint degree programme between a leading British university and a top Chinese university in 2011. A supplementary experiment in the module "Personal Development Plan" was carried out using a large sample (624 students) to compare different methods for forming groups, taking into account both team and academic performance. For the first time this work has attempted to introduce some tests and checks in the group project of a technical module. This paper reports the new findings from the supplementary experiments in the Personal Development Plan module and the technical module. An improved strategy for teamwork teaching in undergraduate engineering programmes, particularly in China, is now suggested: students would learn teamwork skills in the PDP module in the first year of the university; attend selective workshops for the practical instruction to transfer knowledge into action; and complete some technical coursework in groups in senior technical modules.	teamwork;engineering education;China;technical module;improved mechanism	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7044077	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não é engenharia de software

Internet of Things: A Project Based Engineering Course	10.1109/MITE.2017.00021	Project based learning with its emphasis on both conceptual and practical aspect is getting a lot of attention, recently, within the engineering academic circles. Project based learning leads to better participation from students because of the self study activities involved. It fosters communication, lateral thinking, team work, project management, cost analysis and problem solving skills of the students. At BMS College of Engineering, the recent paradigm shift in learning has led to more courses being offered with project based approach. 'Internet of Things' is still in its nascent stages and BMS with a flair for adopting the latest trends in technology in their curriculum, wanted to include it as part of their undergraduate program. This paper analyzes advantages and challenges in offering this course in the undergraduate level. The analyses include the steps taken, feedback, outcome and other assessment carried out as part of this activity.	MOOC;Self Study;Internet of Things;Project based Learning;Engineering Education	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8596696	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não é engenharia de software
Did our Course Design on Software Architecture meet our Student's Learning Expectations?	10.1109/FIE44824.2020.9274014	This Innovative Practice Full Paper discusses our course design on software architecture to meet the learning expectations of two groups of software engineers. Software engineers with working experiences frequently find themselves the need to upskill in their lifelong learning journey. Their learning expectations are shaped not just by their need to know but also other learning characteristics such as their working experiences. In many cases, we design courses based on the required learning outcomes and assessment criteria. In this paper, we wish to find out whether our course design on software architecture has met the learning expectations of our students over eight years. Our study data involves two groups of software engineers to upskill in two courses (1) software engineering practitioners taking a public software architecture design course (2) postgraduate students taking a Master's level software engineering programme. We explain how we evolve the course design based on their students' feedback after each run of the courses. Although the feedback of each run show encouraging results, we discover gaps in our design when we cumulatively analyze the trends of their learning expectations with their qualitative comments over the years. Our design is able to consistently meet some but not all the learning expectations that recur over the years and we discuss the reasons for this outcome and potential further interventions. We hope this discussion and trend analysis process can help course designers to improve their course design.	software engineering; learning expectations; software architecture;adult learner	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9274014	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração
Applying PBL in project management education: A case study of an undergraduate course	10.1109/FIE.2015.7344232	The Software Engineering sector has been demanding an education model that targets real market practices more and more exactly. This includes bearing in mind that, in the market, a software project is subject to numerous restrictions of time, budget and other resources required for its development. In this context, this article describes the application of a learning methodology based on problems, called xPBL. This methodology consists of elements that enable a learning environment to be built that in its essence is practical and contains real learning, and that ensure that this is supported by processes that make it possible to evaluate the effectiveness of the PBL approach from various perspectives: namely, the student's, the teacher's and that of the methodological approach itself. Based on this case study, evidence of the applicability of xPBL is demonstrated as is how the behavior should be understood of all stakeholders involved in the process of teaching and learning in one of the most complex disciplines of Software Engineering.	PBL;Project Management; Software Engineering Education	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7344232	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração
Study of the graduates' perspectives on the quality assessment of two engineering programs at a Peruvian university	10.1109/EDUNINE48860.2020.9149496	The importance of knowing the viewpoints of engineering graduates from the University of Science and Humanities (UCH), located in Lima, Peru, is crucial to make continuous improvements in the curricula of its two programs, electronic and systems engineering. Hence, in this study, a survey was carried out to find out the perspectives about the content learned in their classes as well as the characteristics and the quality of the methodology followed in them. In addition to this, they were asked about the quality of the administrative services at the university. The results of our study show a general contentment as to how the programs are being currently handled. However, there are some details that need to be corrected in order to reach an optimal point in which future graduates are completely satisfied with both engineering programs.	quality assessment; engineering programs; graduates' perspectives	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9149496	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração

"Think Before You Scrum" - An Experience Report on Daily Scrums to Aid Reflection	10.1109 /CSEET62301. 2024.10663017	Project-based software engineering courses often incorporate industry practices, e.g., the "Daily Scrum" (i.e., daily stand-ups). While the main purpose of the Daily Scrum is to discuss progress and blockers, we can also utilize them as an educational tool to facilitate student engagement and reflection since reflection is a crucial aspect of experience-based learning. This paper seeks to enhance reflective practices in software engineering project courses through a pre-meeting check-in add-on to the Daily Scrum. We also aim to assess if this increases self-reflection and consequently impacts student engagement and performance. To this end, we adapted the Daily Scrum in a software engineering project course with a pre-meeting semi-guided self-reflection on a student's work. This was supported by a bespoke online tool. Effects of the reflection were analyzed from the student perspective using surveys, application usage data, formal assessment data, and observations from teaching staff. From our experiences, we observed the pre-meeting check-in was beneficial in enhancing student self-reflectivity. Quantitative data, supported by qualitative evidence from student feedback, also suggested positive effects on student engagement and performance. Students who used pre-meeting check-ins reported increased self-reflection and showed greater levels of improvement in assessed performance. Based on our experiences we recommend incorporating regular individual self-reflection sessions in software engineering project courses.	Software engineering project courses;student reflection; stand-up meetings;daily Scrum	https://ieeexplore. iee. org/stamp/stamp.jsp? arnumber=1066 3017	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração
The Daily Smirk: A Preliminary Prototype for Continuous Peer Assessment of Team- based Projects	10.1109 /CSEET58097. 2023.00014	Team-based projects are common in many software engineering classes, but come with a host of well-known problems such as social loafing, free-riding, and undesirable team dynamics. To counter these issues, many instructors use peer assessment. Unfortunately, current peer assessment approaches exhibit several limitations, including a typically time-consuming evaluation process, feedback being too infrequent or too late to make a difference for the project, and student ratings being unreliable. In this paper, we introduce the Daily Smirk, a preliminary prototype of a new peer assessment tool that is based on three primary design decisions: (1) peer assessment is continuous throughout the project, (2) assessment is through a lightweight smiley-based rating system, and (3) assessment is normalized around a neutral state so that additional feedback is only needed for outlier ratings. We elaborate on the design of the Daily Smirk and its primary functionality, and report on a preliminary evaluation in a software design course with three team-based projects.	Software Engineering Education;Team-based Projects;Peer Assessment	https://ieeexplore. iee. org/stamp/stamp.jsp? arnumber=1022 9351	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração
A proposal for technology- based software engineering curriculum development	10.1109/ICEED. 2016.7856078	A group of software engineering educators, has embarked on a project to implement and support the creation and adaptation of a common set of teaching material and strategies for software engineering education at the undergraduate level of education. The outcome of this project is a framework, in the form of a repository of best practice software engineering teaching modules, assessment artifacts, and case projects that are founded on a set of program outcomes for undergraduate education in software engineering. The philosophy of the research is that the availability of shared pedagogical material that have been developed in a collaborative manner will advance the learning goals, and promote the adoption of teaching strategies that are in the students' best interest.	software engineering; curriculum;course;program outcome;educational research;pedagogy	https://ieeexplore. iee. org/stamp/stamp.jsp? arnumber=7856 078	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração
Using LAMS to support engineering student learning: Two case studies	10.1109 /EDUCON. 2017.7942859	The use of LAMS platform is shown to support learning of engineering students. Two case studies are presented. The first one corresponds to a teaching innovation project; in development; which aims to design and implement a blended course oriented to learning basic mechanical elements for Mechanics Engineering career. The second one is to support a course of programming language for students of several careers on engineering. Both case studies use the concepts of Learning Designs. In the second case, three experiments were performed. The experimental groups were 18, 13 and 12 students, and the control groups were of the 132, 150 and 150 students. The main conclusion is that the learning designs can improve the scores of the students that follows the learning sequences.	component;Learning Designs;mecanical engineering;programming language course;LAMS	https://ieeexplore. iee. org/stamp/stamp.jsp? arnumber=7942 859	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração

xPBL: A methodology for managing PBL when teaching computing	10.1109/FIE.2014.7044178	In order to exploit the benefits of PBL and mitigate the risk of failure when implementing it, the NEXT (iNnovative Educational experience in Technology) research group has been working on methods and tools focused on managing the PBL approach as applied to Computing. In this context, this article proposes a teaching and learning methodology based on PBL, called xPBL, consisting of elements that reinforce PBL principles, namely: real and relevant problems; a practical environment; an innovative and flexible curriculum; an authentic assessment process; close monitoring by technical tutors and process tutors, and finally, professional practitioners as teachers and tutors. Based on these elements, the paper describes the design of a PBL approach for a Design course, grounded on acquired knowledge of Design content and past PBL experiences in Software Engineering courses. This approach provides an insightful guide to implementing PBL from xPBL methodology, and provides instruments based on management techniques such as 5W2H (what, why, who, when, where, how and how much) and the production of artifacts to support the conception process of courses based on PBL.	PBL;Teaching and Learning Methodology;Management Processes;Design Course	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7044178	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração
Revolutionising Control System Engineering Education with Active Learning Strategies	10.1109/INDICON59947.2023.10440787	The paper presents a perspective on effectively implementing active learning in a control system engineering course via project based learning (PBL). The incorporation of Project based learning in control system engineering course equips students with problem solving ability, higher order thinking, leadership, time management, teamwork abilities & deeper understanding of control system concepts. Through PBL, students are engaged in interactive and immersive learning experiences. Furthermore teachers take on the role of facilitators, fostering hands-on learning and building meaningful connections with their students. The course project introduces students to the integration of hardware and software in the area of control system engineering, allowing them to gain familiarity with hardware testing and software coding for future opportunities in embedded design. Lastly, formative assessments are administered to the students and documented.	Control System Engineering; Project Based Learning; Micro Controller;Active learning	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10440787	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não fala sobre engenharia de software
Collective Intelligence Education	10.1109/ICEDEG.2018.8372324	Education continually maintains challenges evidenced by an evolution since its origins. The process of learning in education must be conceived in a decentralized and collaboration context of day-to-day, in addition, the rapid and deep technological transformation carried out at the end of the 20th century and the beginning of the 21st century, especially in the Information and Communications Technologies (ICT), confronts universities with greater pressure to demonstrate the effectiveness of their educational efforts and improvement of the teaching/learning environment. Collective intelligence (CI) is an emerging field that already has a significant impact in many areas and it will have great implications for education, not only from the side of new methodologies but also as a challenge for education, which is currently more focused on the individual than in the collective. This article proposes a model of Collective Intelligence Education with ICT, combining two strategies: the management of ideas and assessment in real time, in class. A collaborative platform called FABRICIUS has been created; it supports these two elements to encourage collaboration, empowerment and student engagement in the learning process. This research proposes a list of metrics to measure individual and collective performance of a course. Findings of 11 trials in Europe and Latin America show the efficiency of the model. Finally, the necessity of connecting university management and innovation in this field is discussed.	Collective Intelligence;Higher Education;ICT";Education; Tools;Collective intelligence; Modeling;Collaboration; Measurement;Proposals	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8372324	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não é de engenharia de software
Software Radio Challenge "LaLiga" for Modern Wireless System Education	10.1109/FIE43999.2019.9028424	This Innovative Practice Full Paper presents our methodology and tools for introducing competition in the electrical engineering curriculum. Our focus is on the education of advanced wireless communications technologies and systems. We leverage software radio technologies and open-source software frameworks to design hands-on laboratory exercises and a grading system based on competition. The motivation behind this is to potentiate creativity while unleashing the boundaries of traditional hands-on laboratories. The students form teams and use the open-source software radio framework ALOE and a partially defined protocol that implements a simplified version of the long-term evolution (LTE) standard in software. The proposed student challenge follows the Spanish soccer league format LaLiga, which consists of weekly matches and accumulative scores. The students are tasked to build an optimized transmitter and receiver following the LTE standard guidelines. The evaluation metric is link performance. The students learn how to (1) assess the feasibility, key challenges and costs for meeting the requirements of wireless communications systems, (2) analyze alternative radio design options and argue about their benefits and drawbacks, and (3) develop strategies and solutions to software radio engineering problems. We discuss our experiences and lessons learned with focus on the suitability of the proposed teaching methodology and evaluation process. Whereas the methodology is well perceived by the students, our analysis shows that the competitive scoring mechanism needs further adjustments.	Software-defined radio (SDR);project-based learning (PLB);competitive learning; long-term evolution (LTE)	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9028424	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração

Effective Use of Facebook's Social Learning Group as a Course Management System for Undergraduate Engineering Courses	10.1109 /TALE48000. 2019.9225930	A Course Management System (CMS) is a software system designed to aid instructors in teaching, as well as, facilitate students in learning. Many commercial CMSs with different arrays of features exist, ranging from expensive university-wide implementations, to free platforms for individual faculty accounts. We seek to find inexpensive or free CMS platforms feasible for usage in undergraduate engineering courses in the Global South. With that objective, firstly, we explore different CMSs to identify key components of an effective CMS in the context of university courses operating with both traditional classroom meetups as well as virtual supplements. Secondly, we consider the free social networking service Facebook's new feature of Social Learning Group as a possible CMS and conduct semester-long experiments in several undergraduate courses. We provide results and share insights on the strengths and challenges of Facebook Group as a CMS and as an alternative to prohibitively costly platforms.	course management tools; social networks;developing countries	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9225930	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração
Game Elements in a Software Engineering Study Group: A Case Study	10.1109/ICSE-SEET.2017.8	This paper presents a case study of a gamified learning experience, designed with a guiding gamification framework, for a software engineering study group. The group was formed to evaluate the learning experience in a laboratory-like setting, and the results are intended to inform the design process. Grounded-theory procedures were used to analyze qualitative data about students' perceptions of the gamified experience. Students reported positive effects such as improved content comprehension, retention, and recap. They also highlighted a positive change in the study dynamics, especially due to the practical application of concepts, the game-like experience and a reduced amount of time for studying. The latter, however, was associated with a specific type of challenge proposed as part of the gamified structure. The other type of challenge, actually, made them face difficulties related to a lack of time. They also did not progress to higher levels of evolution proposed in the gamified structure. These are indicative of the need to improve the learning experience. These improvements, also discussed in this paper, will be evaluated in real settings in future work.	Software Engineering Education;Gamification; Grounded-Theory	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7964341	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração
Engagement In a Virtual Learning on Two Social Networks Of An Engineering course using the Social Network Analysis- An approach using a case study	10.1109 /CCECE47787. 2020.9255723	This study aims to investigate learning engagements in two social networks-blog and Facebook, used for engineering course as a scale-up handle to examine the students 'participation in learning. The research question it used is finding the extent of student's engagement on the formal and the informal virtual learning sites. Engineering students' class' social network sites were used for the class activity and dataset was built from their interactions which further provides the social network analysis and statistical tool data to analyze metrics and properties. Collaborated groups were created by social network analysis. It investigated the connections of participants and unveiled network structure of participants' interactions. It found that a structured network such as Facebook are better suitable for learning interactions than a slapdash structured social network site. The study also found that students are more inclined to the former than the blog. The results provide an enlightenment and prior step to choosing appropriate sites should learning be situated on social network sites supplement to laboratory's introductory.	social network learning;social network analysis;online engineering learning;online learning engagement	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9255723	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não é de engenharia de software
A Comparative Analysis of Agile Teamwork Quality Models	10.23919 /SoftCOM52868 .2021.9559062	[Background] The literature reports multiple models (or instruments) for measuring Teamwork Quality (TWQ) for Agile Software Development However, these models have different constructs and measures, and there is a lack of empirical evidence comparing them. [Goal] This study fills this gap by analyzing if two agile TWQ models yields equivalent results. [Method] First, we mapped the models' variables given their definitions. Then, we collected data using both a BN model (Baysean Network model), TWQ-BN, and Structural Equation Modeling, TWQ-SEM, by interviewing 162 team members from two software development companies. We analyzed the collected data by applying the Bland-Altman method. [Results] We obtained enough evidence to conclude that the results for Communication, Coordination, Cohesion and Mutual Support are not equivalent. Conversely, we did not have enough evidence to claim that the models do not agree for measuring Effort and Balance of member contribution. [Conclusions] The results of this study detail how two state-of-the-art agile TWQ compare in terms of their measures as well as potential research areas for further investigation.	Teamwork;Agile Software Development;Baysean Networks;Structural Equation Modeling	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9559062	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem metrica

Gauging influence in software development teams	10.1109/FIE.2015.7344106	Agile software development teams are generally small, focused groups that require highly motivated members operating in a high-trust environment. Through interactive communication and collaborative work, team members can influence project outcomes both directly and indirectly. One method to examine influence is in terms of communication and control flow among team members when sharing a communication medium and artifact development tools. There currently exist several approaches for characterizing team communication using social network analysis. However, these approaches require modification to be applicable for measuring control flow influence in small teams. In this paper, we discuss the methodology and results of an influence study in which we analyze data generated by student teams in a capstone Software Engineering course. We develop three metrics to measure direct and indirect influence among team members, taking into account the temporal order of interactions and the small size of the teams studied. We correlate the influence metrics with grades, existing participation metrics, and team evaluation scores. The results suggest that our influence metrics correlate to a team member's perceived role on the team, measures of team communication and levels of task performance. This suggests that instructors can recognize the levels of influence exerted by team members by examining team communication and control flow, allowing for mediation prior to product development milestones.	Computer science education; agile software development; collaborative work;social network analysis;centrality	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7344106	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Sentiment Analysis on Conversations in Collaborative Active Learning as an Early Predictor of Performance	10.1109/FIE44824.2020.9274119	This full research paper studies affective states in students' verbal conversations in an introductory Computer Science class (CS1) as they work in teams and discuss course content. Research on the cognitive process suggests that social constructs are an essential part of the learning process. This highlights the importance of teamwork in engineering education. Besides cognitive and social constructs, performance evaluation methods are key components of successful team experience. However, measuring students' individual performance in low-stake teams is a challenge since the main goal of these teams is social construction of knowledge rather than final artifact production. On the other hand, in low-stake teams the small contribution of teamwork to students' grade might cause students not to collaborate as expected. We study affective metrics of sentiment and subjectivity in collaborative conversations in low-stake teams to identify the correlation between students' affective states and their performance in CS1 course. The novelty of this research is its focus on students' verbal conversations in class and how to identify and operationalize affect as a metric that is related to individual performance. We record students' conversation during low-stake teamwork in multiple sessions throughout the semester. By applying Natural Language Processing (NLP) algorithms, sentiment classes and subjectivity scores are extracted from their speech. The result of this study shows a positive correlation between students' performance and their positive sentiment as well as the level of subjectivity in speech. The outcome of this research has the potential to serve as a performance predictor in earlier stages of the semester to provide timely feedback to students and enables instructors to make interventions that can lead to student success.	Active learning;CS1;verbal conversation;Natural Language Processing (NLP); sentiment analysis;affective domain;student performance	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9274119	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração
The Impact of Moodle LMS Integration on Group Discussions to Support Collaborative Learning	10.1109/JCSSE61278.2024.10613717	This study examines the implementation of collaborative learning in Basic Physics education through the utilization of Moodle Learning Management System (LMS). The investigation focuses on the impact of LMS integration on group discussions and problem-solving activities. Methods involved the random formation of 17 groups, consisting of 51 students, who engaged in both face-to-face and LMS-supported discussions. Group assessments were conducted, comparing pre-LMS and post-LMS usage scores, using two-tailed t-test analysis to determine differences in student performance. Results indicate that the incorporation of Moodle LMS in the collaborative learning process positively influenced group discussions and problem-solving outcomes, as evidenced by significant differences between pre-LMS and post-LMS scores. These findings highlight the potential of LMS integration to enhance collaborative learning experiences and improve student engagement in Basic Physics education.	basic physics education; collaborative learning;group discussion;learning management system;Moodle	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10613717	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Software startup within a university – producing industry-ready graduates	10.1109/ICSE-SEET58685.2023.00014	Previous research has demonstrated that preparing students for life in software engineering is not a trivial task. Authentic learning experiences are challenging to provide, and there are gaps between what students have done at the university and what they are expected to master when getting into the industry after graduation. To address this challenge, we present a novel way of teaching industry-relevant skills in a university-led internal software startup called Software Development Academy (SDA). In addition to describing the SDA concept in detail, we have investigated what educational aspects characterise SDA and how it compares to capstone projects. The questions are answered based on 15 semi-structured interviews with alumni of SDA. Working with production-quality software and having a wide range of responsibilities were perceived as the most integral aspects of SDA and provided students with a comprehensive skill set for the future.	software engineering education;internal startup	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10172604	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração

Applying Scrum project management in ECE curriculum	10.1109/FIE.2016.7757568	Scrum is a cyclical project management technique whereby members of a development team work together to define product development strategies in pursuit of a common objective in an adaptable and incremental manner. We have found that Scrum is a promising approach for exposing students to project management of undergraduate engineering projects. But, the technique is not used often in undergraduate education, and it is virtually unknown outside of software engineering circles. We are experimenting with using Scrum in projects across several years of undergraduate engineering education. Our goal is to gradually expose students to project management in order to make their project experiences and learning more efficient and effective. We report on successful initial implementations in freshman courses and senior capstone design courses. Obstacles include expanding practice across all four years, accommodating a diverse student population, and overcoming a lack of experience in assessing Scrum project management.	engineering curriculum; engineering management; electrical engineering; freshman; design projects; capstone projects; Scrum	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7757568	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração
Gamifying the learning of design patterns in software engineering education	10.1109/EDUCON.2016.7474534	In this contribution a process and a way for a standardized documentation are proposed for the creation of gamified and competency-based learning activities. Furthermore the application of the process and its documentation is described by using an exemplary learning activity which was created, implemented and evaluated. The findings indicate, that the use of gamification design elements for learning a design pattern can be effective and successful and can lead to an increase in learning motivation.	Gamification; Learning; Software Engineering; Design Patterns; Competences	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7474534	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração
Reforming Assessment: Challenges Beyond Design	10.1109/ICSE-SEET52601.2021.00017	Promoting evidence-based assessment practices at scale across different disciplines is a challenge. Feedback, although powerful for affecting change in students is not always adequately implemented. An assessment framework based on strong formative feedback and other evidence-based educational practices was designed to give capstone project students an authentic learning experience, and was deployed across all our Software Engineering capstone project units involving more than 700 students and app. 30 academic staff members per teaching period. The scale of our setting raised the question about consistent and faithful implementation of the framework and its guiding principles, essential for achieving the assessment framework outcomes and equitability for students. In this study, we explore the challenges of implementing assessment practice at scale and report on our findings and support strategies in order to facilitate consistent engagement of teaching staff. The findings of our study form the building blocks of a decision-making framework to guide the implementation of ongoing pedagogical innovations at scale.	Formative Feedback; Teaching Evaluation; Fidelity of Implementation; Team Project-based Assessment and Framework	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9402179	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração
Testing and Evaluation of a Model for Optimizing the Process of Information Interaction of Users with Distributed Digital Learning Resources Based on the Chatbot Software	10.1109/TELE58910.2023.10184364	The main features of information interaction in the information and educational environment are considered. The transformation of the traditional structure of interaction between the participants of the teaching and learning process and digital learning resources is presented. It is proposed to include an additional component of the chatbot in this scheme. To illustrate the proposed model the DFD methodology is used. The chatbot presented in this study was beta tested in a web development technologies course. The results of testing the functionality within the framework of the proposed model are shown. Assessment results for the experimental and control groups are presented.	interaction; digital learning resources; functional structure; DFD; chatbot; experiment; evaluation; beta testing	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10184364	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração
Collaborative knowledge transfer via Wiki: A project based learning approach in software engineering	10.1109/ICL.2014.7017785	Due to the high complexity and numerous abstract processes in the subject Software Engineering (SWE), both, challenges in teaching and in learning arise. The teaching of Software Engineering is attempted by a new didactic approach to convey a deeper understanding of the complexity and the processes of Software Engineering in the context of the course. The approach complements the classical ex-cathedra lecture with a seminar and a project phase, whereby the direct application of theoretical knowledge is achieved in real-world situations. In addition to the consolidation of factual knowledge, transferable skills, such as presentation, communication and teamwork skills, can be encouraged. The approach focuses on self-studying as well as collaborative learning. The knowledge gained from team working is multiplied by the Wiki and spread over the whole semester.	collaborative; self-studying; Wiki; Moodle; knowledge acquisition; knowledge transfer; knowledge platform; knowledge assessment; competencies; course evaluation; Software Engineering	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7017785	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	analisar novamente

A Framework to Support the Delivery and Assessment of Practical-Based Concepts on Online Learning	10.1109 /ICCSCE58721. 2023.10237129	In recent times, the shift towards online-based teaching and learning has become increasingly prevalent. This transition has been facilitated by the emergence of various platforms, such as E-learning, MS Teams, and Google Classroom. While these platforms are well-suited for delivering and assessing theory-based courses, they present challenges when it comes to practical-based courses. The delivery and assessment of practical skills and concepts require access to appropriate tools and supervision from educators during implementation. To evaluate learners' practical knowledge, activity-based assessments can be employed. This assessment method involves observing and tracking learners' progress, considering factors such as the time taken to complete an activity and the accuracy of their attempts. However, existing online platforms for teaching and learning lack the necessary features to effectively handle the delivery and assessment of practical skills. Therefore, there is a pressing need for a mechanism that can adapt these platforms to accommodate the requirements of practical-based concepts. This paper proposes a framework designed to integrate tools for online practices, thereby facilitating the delivery of practical-based concepts through online platforms. Additionally, the framework will leverage the data generated during the online learning process to gain insights into learners' behavior and knowledge levels. By implementing this proposed framework, educators can bridge the gap between theory and practice in online learning environments. It enables the seamless delivery and assessment of practical skills, fostering a more comprehensive educational experience for learners.	E-learning;Practical-based concepts;Virtual Programming Lab; Knowledge Extraction.	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10237129	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração
Students' Reflective Learning in the Prototyping Process in STEM Education	10.1109 /TALE56641. 2023.10398238	This paper aims to present and discuss a study that we conducted to probe into junior secondary students' learning experiences in the prototyping process in STEM education, particularly their reflective experiences. In the course of developing their prototypes, the participants (N=75) were required to engage in reflecting on their learning process at the beginning, mid, and end, using the same open-ended questionnaire. Grounded theory analysis was employed to analyze the qualitative data collected through the questionnaire. In addition to unveiling their desirable learning experiences in the prototyping process, this research also revealed the challenges and difficulties they encountered, the corresponding support they needed, and the reflective changes they experienced. The findings showed that integrating reflective learning into the prototyping process is instrumental in understanding students' learning experiences in STEM education.	reflective learning; prototyping;project-based learning;group-based learning;design education	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10398238	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração
The effects of team gender composition in capstone software development projects	10.1109 /SCCC57464. 2022.10000331	Women are greatly underrepresented in software engineering programs. Thus, few women enter the software development industry, and even fewer stay for a long time. The roles assumed by most of those that do stay evolve over time, becoming more managerial and less technical. Some companies prefer not to hire women, since some stereotypes suggest that they may be less productive, more troublesome or that they may eventually drop out due to personal issues. In this paper, we aim to prove that women are at least as productive as men when addressing technical work. Moreover, we also intend to show that including more women in development teams positively impacts workplace climate. To address this issue we conducted a case study where we analyzed the impact of counting on different number of women in 53 development teams in a software engineering capstone course over 5 years. University capstone courses are final courses that resemble industrial work. We found that both women and men perform similarly, but teams that have women have less outliers. These results suggest that it may be convenient to include women as part of software development teams whenever possible. We hypothesize that frequent women dropout may be in part due to the lack of recognition of the benefits of including them in software development teams.	software development; teamwork;women in computer science	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10000331	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração

Adapting Pedagogical Frameworks to Online Learning: Simulating the Tutor Role with LLMs and the QUILT Model	10.1109 /ICAC64487. 2024.10851139	This paper presents SoloScholar, a novel asynchronous online learning platform designed to deliver personalized education to large undergraduate student groups by integrating established pedagogical frameworks with Large Language Models (LLMs). Leveraging Bloom's Revised Taxonomy, learners are categorized into beginner, intermediate, and advanced levels to personalize the educational content. The platform employs the Questioning and Understanding to Improve Learning and Thinking (QUILT) model to structure tutorial sessions and simulate the teaching role of a tutor at a Higher Education Institute (HEI). To generate contextually relevant and cognitively appropriate questions, carefully crafted prompts are fed into LLMs, synthesizing information from reliable knowledge sources. The efficacy of SoloScholar was evaluated through a dual assessment approach: a technical evaluation using the Retrieval Augmented Generation Assessment (RAGAS) framework and a human evaluation involving academic experts. The technical evaluation demonstrated high scores in answer relevancy and context utilization across all learning levels. Similarly, quantitative responses from academic experts indicated strong satisfaction with the quality and appropriateness of the generated content. The findings underscore the potential of integrating LLMs with pedagogical models to enhance personalization in online education. SoloScholar effectively addresses challenges associated with large-group teaching by providing adaptive learning experiences that cater to diverse cognitive needs.	online learning;higher education;teaching techniques;AI in education; personalized learning;large group teaching	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10851139	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração
Efficient Assessment Methods for Improving the Programme Outcomes of Undergraduate - Information Technology Programme in India	10.1109/MITE. 2016.075	Recently, most of the engineering educational institutions are assessing their degree programmes for improving their curriculum design, teaching methodologies, assessment and evaluation process. There are clear guidelines prescribed by the Government accreditation bodies of each country for defining, assessing various graduate Programme Outcomes (POs). There are two ways to assess the POs such as direct and indirect assessment. Direct assessment of the programme outcomes includes various curricular components such as continuous assessment, final examination, assignments and projects etc. In general, indirect assessment of the programme outcomes includes various survey components. We have followed the National Board of Accreditation (NBA) body of India, for defining and assessing our Information Technology (IT) programme outcomes. This paper includes the efficient strategies that we have practiced in our programme for improving the POs of undergraduate IT programme. We have grouped POs into three major categories such as knowledge, skill and attitude. Along with NBA guidelines for assessing the graduate degree programme, we have considered few other assessment components such as co-curricular and extra-curricular activities. In this paper, we have discussed the IT programme outcomes of the past three batches of students and their improvements year-by-year. From the results, it is evident that the strategies improved the entire POs of IT programme at our institution.	Programme Outcomes Assessment;IT Programme Assessment;Indirect Assessment Methods; Outcome Based Education	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8049109	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração
Product-based Learning using CES EduPack in Undergraduate Engineering Courses	10.1109 /EDUCON4565 0.2020.9125301	The present paper describes the outcomes of the application of Product-Based Learning for the development of one of the competencies needed for Material Technology-related Engineering programs: the competence of correct selection of materials and manufacturing processes in the product design stage. Several undergraduate courses, from different Engineering programs, were selected for the application of the methodology using the available software CES EduPack® in order to evaluate this competence. The proposed methodology consisted in designing an assessment involving the selection of materials and manufacturing processes and applying such assessment to students enrolled in the selected courses which incorporate the development of a product. The assessment was applied before prior knowledge of CES EduPack and then after using the software within the product design procedure. Results were compared in order to evaluate the improvement of the competence of selecting materials and manufacturing processes.	Educational Innovation; Higher education;Product-Based Learning;Materials and process selection; Competencies;Design process	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9125301	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração
Design of advanced active and autonomous learning system for computing education — A3 learning system	10.1109/TALE. 2015.7386020	In this paper, we propose an advanced active autonomous learning system (A3 learning system), an educational system based on the use of information and communications technology devices. The A3 learning system comprises active learning (AL), project/problem-based learning (PBL), and mastery learning (ML). In concrete terms, foundational learning in the software/hardware information fields and PBL from the software design stage to the system implementation stage were conducted using AL and two methods, respectively, by individual students and a group. Furthermore, the Progress Report on Generic Skills test was conducted to evaluate the educational benefits of the proposed system.	A3 learning system;computer education;active learning; problem/project based learning;mastery learning	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7386020	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração

Do students like the flipped classroom? An investigation of student reaction to a flipped undergraduate IT course	10.1109/FIE.2014.7044070	The flipped classroom pedagogy has achieved significant mention in academic circles in recent years. "Flipping" involves the reinvention of a traditional course so that students engage with learning materials via recorded lectures and interactive exercises prior to attending class and then use class time for more interactive activities. Proper implementation of a flipped classroom is difficult to gauge, but combines successful techniques for distance education with constructivist learning theory in the classroom. While flipped classrooms are not a novel concept, technological advances and increased comfort with distance learning have made the tools to produce and consume course materials more pervasive. Flipped classroom experiments have had both positive and less-positive results and are generally measured by a significant improvement in learning outcomes. This study, however, analyzes the opinions of students in a flipped sophomore-level information technology course by using a combination of surveys and reflective statements. The author demonstrates that at the outset students are new - and somewhat receptive - to the concept of the flipped classroom. By the conclusion of the course satisfaction with the pedagogy is significant. Finally, student feedback is provided in an effort to inform instructors in the development of their own flipped classrooms.	flipped classroom;inverted classroom;active learning;constructivism	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7044070	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração
Surviving the Unforeseen – Teaching IT and Engineering Students During COVID-19 Outbreak	10.1109/FIE56618.2022.9962383	In this Full Paper on Innovative Practise, we sum up our teaching experience during the COVID-19 pandemic. We focus on several courses taught at the Department of Computer Systems. The main technique to cope with COVID-19 restrictions in higher education is to use online teaching solutions. The first step was to make the traditional lectures available online through recordings enabling students to attend lectures as needed. Yet, for several courses, a quick reconfiguration was required for laboratory exercises as COVID restrictions were established in the middle of the study semester. Thereby, an irreplaceable solution was to use remote laboratories. One of the main concerns was how to set up the online environment within days and weeks and not in months. In addition to remote laboratories, we propose an online teaching and custom assessment setup that to the best of our knowledge has not been used before. For example, instead of using Proctorio for online assessment, we propose a two-stage, licence-free, online examination setup. The proof of concept was carried out with more than 200 students.	COVID-19;teaching;online;laboratories;examination	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9962383	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração
Insights into the Applications of Bayesian Networks in Software Engineering	10.23919/SoftCOM62040.2024.10721646	[Context] Bayesian networks (BNs) have been employed as a promising technique for combining existing project data with expert knowledge to support decision-making and help solve various software engineering (SE) problems. Existing secondary studies have addressed BNs in specific contexts. However, no tertiary study has been conducted to identify and catalog individual secondary studies, synthesizing the existing evidence on applying BNs in SE (BN4SE) from a broader perspective. [Objective] This paper aims to synthesize and analyze the secondary studies published on BN4SE to provide insights and opportunities for researchers and practitioners. [Method] We conducted a tertiary study following the guidelines available in the SE literature. [Results] We identified seven secondary studies addressing BNs in SE: one dedicated to software effort prediction, two to software quality prediction, one to software project management, one to requirements engineering, one to software testing, and one to several problems as it targeted the broader SE field. New research opportunities may arise from challenging aspects of BN application, such as the definition of probabilities, use of expert knowledge, use of models in practice, tool support, data availability issues, and rationale for model construction. [Conclusion] Despite the significant number of available primary studies and the relevance of BNs for the SE area, the number of secondary studies on the topic is very limited. This sheds light on a range of opportunities for the maturation of the field, e.g., the application of BNs in underexplored areas, methodological approaches for exploiting expert knowledge in data-constrained scenarios, and guidelines for detailed model construction and reporting.	Bayesian Networks;Software Engineering;Tertiary Study	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10721646	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração

<p>Improving Computing Education through a Holistic Learning Framework: A Focus Group Study</p>	<p>10.1109 /TALE56641. 2023.10398342</p>	<p>Developing computing education curricula and methods that align with university-wide learning objectives can be challenging. The goal is to ensure that students are engaged and have agency over their learning and that the curriculum is designed to enhance their formative growth to prepare them for the industry. To address this challenge, it is important to understand the underlying motives and learning patterns of both the course structure and the individual students. The Task-Oriented Portfolio Assessment (TOPA) model, along with software tools, enhances student success in computing education. TOPA employs frequent formative feedback, delayed summative grading, and outcomes-based assessment, fostering ongoing dialogue between students and staff. Recent changes introduce focus into the model, enhancing formative feedback and learning outcomes. Focus directs student attention and guides tutor feedback, addressing the challenge of understanding course structures and individual student motivations. In this paper, we describe progress through staff focus groups in a university computing department. Findings from sessions with course directors and team members identify key learning objectives, course themes, and skills. We explore course infrastructure, unit sequencing, and their alignment with the graduate course and unit learning outcomes. We also conceptualize tracking student progress and achievements across units through assessments and feedback. Results suggest that incorporating a focus framework with traceability techniques encourages students to see course units as interconnected, improving course completion and graduate employability. Challenges include rubric support, feedback consistency, and potential resistance from tutors or students. Further research is needed to validate effectiveness across institutions.</p>	<p>Formative Feedback; Assessment; Learning Outcomes; Constructive Alignment</p>	<p>https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10398342</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<p>não foca em colaboração</p>
<p>Use of Geographic Information Systems (GIS) in higher education: practical geomatics applications with Quantum GIS software</p>	<p>10.1109 /SIIE56031. 2022.9982364</p>	<p>Educational systems have undergone a great evolution over time, adapting to the needs of society and students at all times. In this context, an important advance is the increase in the different possibilities of the teaching-learning process provided by Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs). ICTs integrated with the Project Based Learning (PBL) methodology allow students to develop their potential to solve real-world problems while increasing their learning capacity. This paper presents two PBL methodologies to be performed in higher education, using open-source Quantum Geographic Information System (QGIS) software as an ICT tool. Each PBL methodology presents its potential use as geoinformation technology for forest management and energy resource assessment, respectively. The PBL methodologies allowed the students to acquire knowledge in the use of one of the most demanded software in geomatics applications. The results showed a high quality of the delivered exercises, and a good personal evaluation of the proposed methodologies and a high qualification by the students.</p>	<p>GIS; Geomatics; QGIS; ICT; Geoprocessing; Open Source; Forest engineer; Energy engineering; PBL</p>	<p>https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9982364</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<p>não foca em colaboração</p>
<p>Does Self-Efficacy Correlate with Positive Emotion and Academic Performance in Collaborative Learning?</p>	<p>10.1109 /FIE49875. 2021.9637471</p>	<p>This full research paper studies the correlation of self-efficacy in computer science as well as learning and social skills with students' academic performance and their emotions in collaborative learning environments. Self-efficacy is an essential part of social cognitive theory and provides the foundation for analyzing human thoughts, motivations, and actions. Studies show that students' successful performance and accomplishment are directly affected by the level of self-efficacy. Therefore, analyzing self-efficacy in engineering education is important since it can impact the learning process in academic settings as well as provide a metric to track for improvement. Social cognitive theories also emphasize that students' interaction with each other affects their learning process and how they perform in educational settings. In previous work [5], we analyzed students' conversations in low-stake teams in an introductory programming course (CS1) and observed a strong positive correlation between students' positive emotions while interacting with each other with their performance in the course. In this study, we focus on the correlation of self-efficacy with learner's emotion and performance. We measure students' self-efficacy with a standard instrument called "Student Attitudes Toward STEM (S-STEM) Survey". For this purpose, we asked the participants to self-report on a 5-point Likert-scaled survey including 20 questions. These 20 questions are grouped into 2 main categories of computer science and learning/social skills. Students' emotions were extracted from their speeches in teams by applying natural language processing (NLP) methods. The result of data analysis shows a statistically significant correlation between overall self-efficacy and performance in the course and positive emotions during the teamwork. We further investigate which category of self-efficacy questions most correlate with students' performance. The result shows self-efficacy in interpersonal skills and learning ability most impact students' performance.</p>	<p>self-efficacy; social skill; computer science; emotion mining; sentiment analysis; NLP; collaborative active learning</p>	<p>https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9637471</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<p>não tem engenharia de software</p>

Combining Quantitative and Qualitative Studies in Empirical Software Engineering Research	10.1109/ICSE-C.2017.163	This technical briefing provides an overview of how quantitative empirical research methods can be combined with qualitative ones generating the family of empirical software engineering approaches known as mixed-methods. The ultimate aim of such mixed-methods is supporting cause-effect claims combining multiple data types, sources and analyses that provide software practitioners and academicians solid rationale and practical value to research results. This briefing offers lessons we learned in instrumenting and executing mixed-methods approaches for the benefit of the goal above.	Empirical Software Engineering;Quantitative Methods;Qualitative Methods;Grounded Theory	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7965402	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração
Towards the Development of Qualities of Online Programming Teachers Instrument	10.1109/TALE56641.2023.10398412	This paper reports the initial findings of the first part of the two-part study which investigated the qualities of online programming teachers. The first part was a qualitative design that employed a grounded theory approach. Ten students were interviewed about the qualities of teachers they like and dislike. Another group of students (n = 58) were asked the same question using an open-ended questionnaire. Thematic analysis of the data collected from two sets of participants revealed that desirable characteristics of teachers were mainly attributed to their delivery skills. The personality of teachers is another aspect of their desirability or undesirability. Thus, the initial attributes of qualities of good online programming teachers are mainly attributed to their extrinsic (e.g., delivery skills) and intrinsic (e.g., personality) qualities. The plan for further research is also discussed.	online education;distance learning;delivery skills; distance education	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10398412	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração
Changing the Assessment Process in Mathematics for Students in Engineering	10.23919/MIPRO48935.2020.9245353	Mathematical subjects studied in the Faculty of Computer Science and Engineering at Burgas Free University are focused on acquiring fundamental knowledge and developing essential skills required for future engineers. This paper looks into changing the process of assessment of students' achievements in mathematics from closed-book exams to diversification of tasks and expected outcomes. Three aspects of assessing the mathematical knowledge in engineering programs are considered: the importance of identifying the entry level, blended learning and creating students' portfolios with MatLab. The experience of the authors in using the tools of blended learning and the use of a software environment are presented. Some emerging problems in the educational process that need to be faced are outlined.	mathematical knowledge assessment;blended learning;students';portfolios	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9245353	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração
Empowering Software Engineering Students: The Role of Gamification in Promoting Learning Independence	10.1109/ICVEE63912.2024.10823948	The role of learning media greatly supports the learning process, increasing motivation and interest in the process. Learning media can also be a place to improve competence optimally through bootcamp training menus and the like with more specific training objectives. The main objective of this study is to develop a gamification-based website to enhance students' preparedness for their Final Competency Test by tackling challenges in comprehending programming absent practical experience. The learning method implemented in this website is case-based learning that integrates dynamic coding activities. The research method uses the Plomp approach with 3 main stages, namely preliminary research, prototyping, and assessment stage. The trial of the gamification website began with media and content validation followed by small group testing and large group testing. Validation by media and material experts led to the execution of small group trials (95.7%) and large group trials (91.7%), producing exceptionally positive outcomes. The results of the small group test with 12 respondents produced a very suitable value with a score of 95.7 and the large group test with 27 respondents produced a score of 91.7% with very suitable criteria. This indicates that the web-based platform is highly viable for assisting vocational students in acquiring software development skills, enhancing their preparedness for practical IT positions such as software developers and system analysts. Subsequent study involved the incorporation of gamification, such as computer-supported collaborative learning.	gamification;learning independence;case-based learning;software engineering;final competency test	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10823948	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração
Practical laboratory classes to improve engagement and achievement amongst engineering students taking first-year mathematics	10.1109/FIE.2016.7757667	We describe the planning, delivery, and assessment of laboratory classes offered as part of two first-year mathematics courses for engineering students. The laboratory classes, which use practical examples inspired by second-, third- and fourth-year engineering courses, were designed to illustrate the relevance of mathematics to engineering. Once these classes were introduced the percentage of engaged students increased by up to a third, leading to similar improvements in pass rates and median marks.	engineering;mathematics; problem-based learning;21st century learning	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7757667	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração

Modelling online assessment in management subjects through educational data mining	10.1109 /ICODSE. 2017.8285881	Educational data mining(EDM) has been used widely to investigate data that come from a learning process, including blended learning. This study explores educational data from a Learning Course Management System (LMS) and academic data in two courses of Management Study Program, Faculty of Economics at Maranatha Christian University, which are Change Management (CM) in undergraduate program and Creative Leadership (CL) in master degree program as case studies. The main aim of this research is to provide feedback for the learning process through the LMS in order to improve students' achievement. EDM methods used are association rule mining and J48 classification. The results of association rule mining are two sets of interesting rules for the CM course and three sets of rules for CL course. Using J48 classification, two J48 pruned trees are obtained for each course. Based on those results, some suggestions are proposed to enhance the LMS and to encourage students' involvement in blended learning.	blended learning;educational data mining;association rules;J48 classification	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8285881	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração
WIP: Implementing Project Based Learning: Some Challenges from a Requirements Engineering Perspective	10.1109/FIE. 2018.8659307	Project based learning (PBL) is gaining increasing traction among educational development, scholars and practitioners. The dominant argument suggests that by engaging in real world projects and research, students can acquire valuable critical thinking, team work, problem-solving, and improved communication skills. The aim of this work-in-progress paper is to investigate the effects of PBL on student performance in a requirements engineering (RE) course. Students were divided into 5 project groups; each group carried out a RE project that addresses a real-world problem. The project deliverable for each group is a complete software requirements specification (SRS) document; a user interface design; and software development project management plan. Following the completion of the project, structured feedback was elicited from the students via questionnaires. The results were combined with the final student grades to evaluate the effect of PBL on their combined performance. Preliminary results show that PBL can benefit RE courses, especially by enhancing students performance. Yet, certain challenges, e.g., stakeholders engagement and team cohesion, must be addressed before these benefits can be fully realized.	Stakeholders;Software; Requirements engineering; Project management; Problem-solving;Training	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8659307	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Towards a Paradigm Change in Group and Peer Assessment in Software Engineering Education	10.1109 /CSEET49119. 2020.9206197	Conventional approaches to group and peer assessment are invariably based on highly questionable assumptions about educational measurement and how to weight and aggregate multiple scores into an overall judgement of outcome and performance. In this paper, we propose an alternative approach based on a sound theory of educational scoring and rating. Our approach is particularly relevant for software engineering education, where group projects with multiple types of outcomes are used to assess individual students. We will also demonstrate our novel approach by means of two software tools and compare them with other tools based on conventional approaches. Throughout, we will focus on explaining the reasons for and benefits of adopting our paradigm changing approach to group-peer marking.	group-peer marking;peer assessment;educational judgement;bounded scale; arithmetic mean;quasi-arithmetic mean;scoring rules;scoring models;scoring theory	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9206197	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração
Evolving FinTech 512 'Software Engineering For Financial Technology'	10.1109 /SEENG59157. 2023.00008	The Duke FinTech Master's program requires introductions to programming and software engineering as part of its core requirements. This paper presents the project-based software engineering course offered by the program and the process by which it has been refined over the course of four semesters to support entry into the development of financial technology. As part of a growing program, enrollment in this core course has grown from 8 to over 100 students per semester, primarily graduate students with backgrounds in finance and economics. We identify lessons learned by the students and the course staff.	Education;Software engineering	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10190454	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração

Assessing the use of open source microcontroller board for teaching engine sensing and communication in automotive laboratory	10.1109/FIE. 2017.8190738	Open source microcontroller (MCU) boards have made significant inroads towards classroom teaching over the last decade. Many programs have already switched from the traditional educational boards to, for example Arduino products, due to their low costs, easy to use, flexibility, and wide adoption in both consumer and industrial applications. However, comparing with their commercial counterparts, open source boards still lack rigorous and well-designed teaching, especially lab materials to have a seamless integration with existing curricular. Engine systems and controls is a core course in automotive engineering (AET) program that teaches students the theory and application of on-board diagnostics and monitoring system. The course has an intense lab component. Despite the consensus that AET curriculum needs more mechatronics material to reflect the critical roles that electrical, electronics, computing, communications, controls and software technologies play in today's vehicles, we find that nationwide, the lab facility of automotive programs are still heavily mechanical. We believe open source MCU boards are the ideal tool to develop new educational equipment and materials to transform automotive labs and to bridge the gap between classroom and industry knowledge base. In this work-in-progress paper we first introduce the Arduino shields for engine sensing and communication that we have designed at the request of, and in collaboration with AET faculty. We then present the assessment plan to evaluate the boards' effectiveness in helping students understand fundamental mechatronics concepts and practices, and their impact on students' learning experience for engineering design in a multi-disciplinary team.	Engines;Sensors;Automotive engineering;Microcontrollers; Education;Mechatronics; Tools	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8190738	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração
Apply VR and Simulation-Based Learning for Logistics and Warehouse Design Education	10.1109/EDUCON4633 2.2021.9453870	The current Logistics management courses here in Taiwan, are mainly divided into theoretical concepts, or system practice learning, but no matter what the existing model of the curriculum, most students' ability is still out of the expectations for the employers of the logistics industries. Furthermore, the students' learning effectiveness is not directly proportional to the course hours and their learning time, the major gap between the school and work area of Logistics management is still exist. Therefore, the theme of this study is to apply problem-based learning (PBL) and simulation-based learning (SBL) as the spirit of the design of Logistics management teaching plan and the compilation of teaching cases, and to evaluate the effectiveness of these courses design methods by the pre and post questionnaires, where the course were carried out with 45 students (into 10 groups) equipped with flexsim simulation software and VR headsets to design themselves-defined warehousing plan. The survey results show positive response from the students and provide insides for the teacher to keep on enhance the following course design.	warehousing simulation; logistics management; simulation-based learning; problem-based learning	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9453870	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração
Using Modular Strategies and Outcome-Based Education for Improving an Embedded Systems Design Laboratory	10.1109/FIE44824. 2020.9274196	This Research to Practice Full Paper presents how modular design techniques aided by an Outcome-Based educational framework, can be incorporated in an Embedded Systems Design laboratory to improve student learning. Teaching embedded systems design concepts and enhancing students' skills in this area are important tasks for universities in order to provide an up to date education. To achieve this, the laboratory objective, content, pedagogical methods, and assessment activities were aligned using an Outcome-Based educational framework to ensure proper student learning. The modular approach was applied to pedagogical methods through the design of a set of progressive laboratory experiments and six electronic educational modules. Using this approach effective laboratory experiments that promoted better student learning, in the area of embedded systems design, were developed. As a result, the overall laboratory student performance was improved and therefore the proposed methodology was validated.	Embedded systems education;Outcome-based education;Modular design	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9274196	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração
Improving independent learning and communication skills of students in last year of Engineering degrees through the use of Project-Based Learning methodologies	10.1109/TAE. 2014.6900149	Integration of Project-Based Learning (PBL) methodology within the framework of an Antennas course, in the last year of Telecommunications Engineering degree, is presented. PBL methodology is aimed to be used as a tool to improve students criticism and active learning as well as their social and communication skills. By means of using PBL methodologies and collaborative learning techniques, faculty wants to improve students teamwork skills, and encourage a more deep and autonomous learning approach. Concurrently with the development of the projects a promotion of certain dissemination activities to train students communication skills is made in order to improve their expertise and made them more competent to start their work career. Final survey results shown the effectivity of PBL methodology regarding a deep learning approach and the improvement of communication and social skills of students.	PBL;Project-Based Learning; Social skills;Engineering; Antennas	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=6900149	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	nao fala sobre engenharia de software

Applying Task-centric Holistic Teaching Approach in Education of Industrial Cyber Physical Systems	10.1109 /ICPS48405. 2020.9274773	In order to meet the increasing demand for industrial cyber physical systems, highly qualified professionals are required who possess both excellent professional knowledge and skills as well as soft skills. The interdisciplinarity of industrial cyber physical systems makes teaching the necessary skill challenging. The approach known from the education of software engineering, in which students form a team to develop a software product, is not sufficient. There is also a lack of soft skills, which are often seen as key success factors for engineering projects. To close the existing gaps in education of industrial cyber-physical systems engineering, the task-centric holistic agile teaching approach (T-CHAT) is proposed. This approach will be implemented in a newly developed curriculum for industrial cyber physical systems at the ITMO University St. Petersburg, Russia. It focuses on teaching of both technical and soft skills.	Agile teaching;Industrial Cyber-Physical Systems; Education of Industrial Cyber-Physical Systems Engineering;Perceptual learning;Problem-based learning;Project-based learning;Research-based learning	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9274773	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração
Active Project-Driven Learning Method for Taking the Teaching Reform of Android Programming	10.1109 /CSEI50228. 2020.9142484	In view of the characteristics of IoT engineering talents training, Android program design and teaching objectives, this paper proposes to use the active "project-driven" teaching method in the teaching of Android programming, which helps to improve students' interest in learning, and focus on training and improving IoT students Android program development capabilities. Based on the Active Project-Driven Learning Method, the Android curriculum reform has fully mobilized the enthusiasm and initiative of students in practical teaching. Students can master the overall process of project design and accumulate valuable project experience in learning, which helps to create strong conditions for employment. Project grouping operations can also cultivate students' awareness of teamwork and enhance their ability to communicate and collaboration. Teaching practice has proved that based on job-driven project-driven teaching. Android has achieved good teaching results with feasibility and promotion. A new idea has put forward for the teaching of Android programming course, which is the reference to the teaching of other practical courses of IOT engineering major.	android;teaching reform; project-driven;IoT	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9142484	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração
Implementing of Project-Based and Skill Assessment Pedagogy in Mechatronics Course	10.1109/REM. 2018.8421771	This paper describes the implementation of a project-based learning (PjBL) approach in mechatronics course for the first-year engineering students at ENSGSI (Ecole Nationale Supérieure en Génie des Systèmes et de l'Innovation) in France. The pedagogy is designed to meet the education plan in forming future innovation engineers. The adopted educational model combines classroom, PjBL and skill-based assessment. The project prototypes are realized using FabLab equipment and Arduino kits. The student skills are assessed by a self-evaluation, a written exam, and a project jury evaluation. Individual competencies of each student are assessed at the beginning of the course and then compared to his/her competencies at the end of the course. The results show how the PjBL with various skill assessments can be applied and how they can improve learning efficiency and student attitudes. The feedback from students is positive, which encourage us to adopt and pursue this pedagogy.	Curriculum development; Mechatronics;Engineering education;Project-based learning;Skill-based assessment	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8421771	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração
Research on the Education System of Practice Base for Professional Master	10.1109 /CIET55102. 2022.9779029	Professional master education is oriented by professional practice and aims to cultivate high-level application-oriented talents with strong professional ability. Practice base is an important carrier of professional postgraduate practice education. The teaching system of practice base is an important factor to guarantee the teaching quality of engineering master. Based on the progressive thinking, this paper puts forward three stages of practical teaching system, namely "practice basis management", "practice mode management" and "practice process management", and explores the implementation of the integration of industry and education. The practice mode management of "case teaching", "school project practice", "innovation competition practice" and "enterprise project practice" is constructed. It has proved that the implementation of practice mode management improves students' practical ability and innovation ability, and meets the needs of economic and social talent development.	professional master's degree;practical teaching system;industry-education integration;progressive system;Practice ability	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9779029	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração

An Experience	10.1109/MITE.2016.029	The paper emphasizes the need for teaching and learning mathematically intensive theory subjects using very powerful software tools. Under Electrical Engineering discipline, there are subjects like Signals & systems, Control Systems, Digital Signal/Image Processing etc. where teachers need to spend a considerable amount of time in classroom, teaching the mathematical concepts, ending up with very low level of learning by students. Learners find it very complex and unrelated as mere lecturing doesn't help them in effective interpretation of the information conveyed. There are many such software tools available nowadays having a powerful graphical data flow programming environment with a rich set of library functions and tools sets in simulation and real time mode. Such tools can simplify the teaching and learning of subjects with intense mathematical background in lesser time for the students from non-electronics stream. Here we present the efforts of teachers in learning and teaching, Signal acquisition, processing and analysis techniques for sixth semester students of Automation and Robotics in a much effective manner, using LabVIEW tool. The processed data can be presented from the tool using measurement graphs, indicators, animations, tabulated data, automated calculations, physical interpretation, visualization effects etc., thus enabling the learner with better understanding of concepts. Here we present the results of extensive use of tool to teach and learn different signal processing and analysis techniques used for biomedical signals along with the experience shared by teachers and students undergoing the activity. Course projects implemented by students after undergoing the proposed activity helped teachers to know the accelerated process of learning of the basic concepts of signal processing by students.	Electrical Engineering discipline;Signals and Systems;Digital signal Processing;Signal acquisition;Automation & Robotics;LabVIEW Tool	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8049063	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração
Comprehensive Critical Thinking Problem Solving Assessment Framework for Engineering Students	10.1109/WEFF.2017.8467176	This paper proposed a framework to assess Critical Thinking Problem Solving (CTPS) among Computer and Communication Systems Engineering students. Currently, CTPS is assessed using generic rubric that can be interpreted differently. The proposed framework consists of in-class oral, facilitation and report assessment methods that tackle the limitation of current assessment practice. After three assessments are performed throughout the semester, the total score is the accumulation of the three assessment scores. The study was implemented at Faculty of Engineering, UPM in Semester 12016/2017 which involves 41 undergraduate students, ranging from second to final years students in 7 high taxonomy level courses. From the conducted study, the proposed CTPS assessment method is comprehensive covering the oral, facilitation and report aspect. However, the proposed framework is difficult to be conducted for large classroom due to the time constraint but the data obtained in the study can be used to propose an efficient and reliable rubric for CTPS assessment.	Critical Thinking Skills;oral assessment;facilitation assessment;report assessment	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8467176	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração
Collaborative Learning : A Case Study on Information Security and Auditing Management Course	10.1109/ICONAT53423.2022.9726091	Collaborative Learning is a process of constructing knowledge through interaction with peers. In general, Collaborative learning is an instructional method involving and interaction between learners, it also involving cooperation and interaction between learners with software support. In specific, Collaborative learning is a computer mediated communication as a mode of course delivery. With the tremendous invention of smart devices in recent years, mere lecture is not sufficient to fulfil the needs and expectations of the learners. Incorporating Active Learning Strategies (ALS) with the teaching methodologies is needed in the curriculum. This study aims to explore the activity Collaborative Learning in an elective course among undergraduate students in the Information Technology. The participants included in this study are 176 students in the Information Technology branch from Thiagarajar College of Engineering. Collaborative learning is assessed by four methods of assessment: Individual, Group, Formative and Summative. At the end of the course feedback questionnaire is designed for the Collaborative Learning activity. Two control groups are created: one group with collaborative learning activity implementation and the other group without collaborative learning activity implementation. Three research questions are framed in order to know the implications of the activity. From the assessment and feedback we come to the conclusion "Collaborative Learning" works well. By incorporating Collaborative learning in the curriculum, Course Outcomes are also attained to the maximum level when compared to the previous batch of students.	Collaborative Learning;Active Learning Strategies;Rubrics; Assessment	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9726091	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	revisaar

Effectiveness of tablet learning in online courses at University of the South Pacific	10.1109/APWCCSE.2015.7476229	In recent years, technology has become the game changer in the world of higher education. The handheld mobile devices are emerging as one of the most promising technologies and tools to support learning and venture into new pedagogies. This provides uncharted opportunities for educationists and facilitators to make learning pervasive and boost lifelong learning. Mobile devices like tablet computers have proven to be effective in accelerating student engagement, enhancing focus and supporting teacher interaction. To evaluate the effectiveness of tablet learning in a higher education institution, a study was conducted on a sample of 10 students who were picked on voluntarily basis from a seven weeks online course. The attitude of students to the new technological device was analysed. The study also considered the quality of tasks and assessments produced by the students and their success rate. The results of this study showed that students have a positive attitude towards tablet learning and there was an agreement that the mobile device was a good learning tool for the online courses. Interestingly, there was no significant difference noted with the success rates and the grades of the two groups.	effectiveness;tablet learning; online;Pacific	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7476229	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração
Effectiveness of Peer Review in Teaching and Learning User Centered Conceptual Design Among Large Cohorts of Information Technology Students	10.1109/ICSE-SEET52601.2021.00016	Conceptual design often sets the direction of the development of a product. Educating Software Engineering and Information Technology (IT) students to consider the needs of users during the conceptual design stage is important. The assessment of conceptual design is a time consuming process. When budgets are limited, financial resources are inadequately allocated to allow staff to spend quality time assessing the conceptual design artifacts of large classes. We present a methodology to teach, capture and evaluate conceptual design artifacts for large classes. In two separate studies, two groups of over 185 undergraduate IT students reviewed their peers' design artifacts using a comprehensive rubric. Their reviews were later checked by two researchers using the same rubric. It was found that not only were the student-peers' reviews close to the researchers' reviews, it was possible to give students valuable and timely feedback and scaffold them to reflect, an essential characteristic for professional competence. In addition, we found that assessment by staff was not feasible due to inadequate resources. We conclude that for large classes, conceptual design artifacts can be evaluated and valuable feedback provided in a timely manner by peers with the guidance of a comprehensive rubric.	conceptual design assessment;peer review; reflective practice;persona; software engineering education;information technology education	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9402167	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração
Enhancing Student Learning Through Mobile Learning Groups	10.1109/TALE48869.2020.9368416	With the advent of mobile phones, particularly smartphones, there has been consideration interest in mobile e-learning. In particular, mobile phones provide an effective channel to complement existing channels to enhance the student learning experience. Coupled with artificial intelligence (e.g., chatbot), more innovative learning functions can be provided. In this paper, we make two contributions to the aforementioned development. First, we present an innovative AI5 model with five important learning elements: Inception, Interest, Instruction, Information and Inspiration, to facilitate mobile collaborative learning. Second, we present a mobile app prototype for students to form mobile learning groups. In each learning group, students can interact with one another and with a chatbot. Furthermore, the mobile app can facilitate the sharing of open educational resources.	mobile learning;e-learning;AI; chatbot;OER	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9368416	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração
Learning tools in Electronic Engineering. Content Curation and Personal Learning Environments	10.1109/TAEE46915.2020.9163747	The results of several teaching innovation projects are presented. Students of Electronic Engineering have been involved in these projects where Personal Learning Environments and Content Curation have been used as an improvement tool for the acquisition of ICT competence and learning technical content related to the different subjects.	Personal Learning Environment;PLE;informal learning;training innovation; content Curation;university education	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9163747	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração
Supporting young students to learn computer programming in an early schooling	10.1109/ICCVA.2015.7351898	The deployments of technology across the global toward efficient learning environment are growing rapidly. In United Kingdom educational system, the government is investing 1.1 million pounds in primary and secondary school for early programming lessoning starting from age five upwards. The ideology behind this innovation is to make younger generation linked to innovation and digital industries and improve the pace with the most successful education system in the world. In this paper, an assessment-driven educational programming tutoring system for young students is described in a high-level overview (which provides an abstract design of the main components of the proposed system), as well as a detailed discussion of some of the existing tutoring programming tools for kids. The intention will be to develop this given proposed design fully functional and then evaluate it in different primary schools from the UK and other Middle East countries. One of our main intended aims of this study would be to offer a suitable educational programming system that could ease the process of teaching and learning programming for kids in primary schooling.	Technology and Education; Coding;young students; Teaching and Learning; Computer programming; Programming tutoring systems for kids;Adaptive software	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7351898	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração

Teacher's Assistant Application	10.1109 /ICEST55168. 2022.9828475	With the start of the online teaching due to the COVID restrictions, the dynamics of the classes changed, and the Internet applications took a big swing in the education process. Before the COVID pandemic, teachers were forced to learn how to use web tools to deliver more productive teaching to pupils. But despite all the efforts of teachers and institutions to invest in quality online education, we are all witnesses that online instruction does not achieve the same effect as the teaching with a physical presence. We conducted several surveys in secondary and primary schools in the local area. The results lead to the conclusion that the attention of pupils and the quality of teaching is reduced compared to education with a physical presence. Teachers use paper notebooks, online teaching tools, online meeting scheduling tools, online assessment tools, and online homework tools from different sources. Surveys with teachers have also shown that they have difficulty dealing with inconsistent tools, paper records and most of the various software they use in their online teaching. This paper will examine the possibilities of the existing online applications for the above-mentioned teacher's needs. Following our survey results, we're creating an online tool that puts all the essential needs together, such as - keeping pupils' attention during classes, digitizing the teacher-led record section, quickly and easily assessing pupils, managing homeworks, working in groups on projects and automation of the previously listed processes. The main focus of this paper will be on our innovative application that will contribute to the work process of the teachers.	online lecturing;online application;online education; primary and secondary education	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9828475	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração
Designing An Overseas Experiential Course in Data Science	10.1109 /TALE56641. 2023.10398363	Unprecedented demand for data science professionals in the industry has led to many educational institutions launching new data science courses. It is however imperative that students of data science programmes learn through execution of real-world, authentic projects on top of acquiring foundational knowledge on the basics of data science. In the process of working on authentic, real-world projects, students not only create new knowledge but also learn to solve open, sophisticated, and ill-structured problems in an inter-disciplinary fashion. In this paper, we detailed our approach to design a data science curriculum premised on learners solving authentic data science problems sourced from an overseas project sponsor. The course consists of a local component in which students acquire requisite knowledge on data analytics through classroom-based learning and an overseas component where students were on-site with the overseas project sponsor. To evaluate the design of our course curriculum and uncover its potential benefits, we surveyed the project sponsor representatives and tasked our students with the submission of a personal reflection. Quantitative and qualitative analysis of the survey and reflections respectively revealed the sponsors' high satisfaction with the students' output and the students' perception that the course has enriched their learning. The results also indicated that the students attributed teamwork, communications, mentoring and data processing skills as key factors integral to successful project outcomes. In all, we have developed an experiential, project based and applied data science program in an overseas context offered to students from different disciplines which yields promising student learning outcomes.	curriculum design; experiential learning; analytics;data science; machine learning;multi-disciplinary	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10398363	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração
Agile approaches towards Global Software Engineering	10.1109 /ICRITO. 2015.7359249	Global Software Engineering (GSE) is emerging trend in today's industry. The Software development industry is investigating the use of Agile development methodologies in distributed environment due to its benefits of better communication and coordination, improved productivity and quality. Global Software Engineering is continually achieving momentum from past four years. In last decade, the exceptional progress has been determined. New strategy models that are the acquainted from time with time in order to stay pace with third-dimensional requests of the business. New programming framework advancement standards are discovering the spot in the professional that Agile approaches towards Software System Development, use principally based Development and component based Development. As point of all the system models is same, i.e., to urge quality item, scale back time of improvement, efficiency change and decrease in cost. Still, no single strategy model is finished in itself. Programming framework business is moving towards. Deft programming framework Development. Programming framework improvement of spry systems to have the gotten the attention of programming framework architects and analysts around the world. Examination venture is all things considered rare. Coordinated programming advancement framework regardless of its own oddity is a significant space of examination at interims framework designing of programming order.	Global Software Engineering (GSE);Global Software Development (GSD);agile approaches	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7359249	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração

Objectives and Key Results in Software Teams: Challenges	10.1145/3639477.3639747	Building software, like building almost anything, requires people to understand a common goal and work together towards it. In large software companies, a VP or Director will have an idea or goal and it is often the job of middle management to distill that lofty, general idea into manageable, finite units of work. How do organizations do this hard work of setting and measuring progress towards goals? To understand this question, we undertook a mixed methods approach to studying goal setting, management dissemination of goals, goal tracking and ultimately software delivery at a large multi-national software company. Semi-structured interviews with 47 participants were analyzed and used to develop a survey which was deployed to a multi-national organization of over 4,000 engineers. The 512 responses were analyzed using thematic analysis, linear regressions and hypothesis testing, and found that tracking, measuring and setting goals is hard work, regardless of tools used. Middle management seems to be a critical component of the translation of lofty goals to actionable work items. In addition, attitudes and beliefs of engineers are critical to the success of any goal setting framework. Based on this research, we make recommendations on how to improve the goal setting and OKR process in software organizations: invest in the data pipeline, increase transparency, improve communication, promote learning communities, and a structured roll out of OKRs.	Objectives and Key Results; Software Development; Organizational behavior; Goal Setting; Mixed methods	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10554723	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não foca em colaboração
Augmented Reality for Programming Teaching: An Exploratory Study	10.1109/EDUCON54358.2023.10125256	The growing adoption of instructional technology in education has been driven by its contribution to society's development. Our study aimed to examine the use of Augmented Reality (AR) in teaching Python programming principles. The study consisted of three phases: a systematic review of AR using the PRISMA statement, the development of a mobile AR application called "EDUpy," and the evaluation of EDUpy through two experiences with undergraduate students enrolled in different course units. The study found 30 studies in literature focused on the introduction of AR in educational contexts, ranging from kindergarten to higher education. Additionally, 57 students were enrolled in the experiences and the results showed that EDUpy was suitable in terms of user experience and effective in achieving students' learning goals. Further research is necessary to determine the impact of the application on students' soft skills, such as creativity, engagement, motivation, teamwork, and self-learning.	Augmented reality; Python; programming; software engineering education	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10125256	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
Teaching Software Construction at Scale with Mastery Learning: A Case Study	10.1109/ICSE-SEET.2019.00027	Mastery Learning involves delineating learning units and assessing each unit individually and repeatedly until a student obtains success. Mastery Learning has been shown to help students better identify and grasp fundamental concepts. We applied Mastery Learning in a second-year software construction course with roughly 450 students. We delineated 23 topics, and administered either a written or verbal quiz to assess each topic. We built a quiz auto-grading, analysis, visualization, and feedback system to help cope with the scale of the class. By the end of the semester we had administered over 12K quizzes. We found evidence that students grasped both fundamental concepts and advanced concepts better than in prior semesters. Because we made two changes at once (introducing videos and Mastery Learning) it is difficult to isolate whether the Mastery Learning Approach was solely responsible, but assessment results suggest that the repeatable micro-quizzes were instrumental in these gains. Auto-grading and extensive data collection allowed a depth of analysis that afforded us invaluable and lasting pedagogical insights.	Software Engineering Education; Software Construction Education; Mastery Learning	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8802099	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
Requirements engineering education using role-play training	10.1109/TALE.2016.7851799	This paper proposes a new method for use in requirements engineering education at universities. The method is based on two components: (1) group-work role-play training to elicit customer's real requirements; (2) a software agent to play the role of a domain expert supplying business knowledge to learners. Learners who have had no previous practical experience in defining requirements may follow a recommended procedure in order to elicit requirements. We have implemented two types of role-play training - with and without software agents' support. Twelve undergraduate students from the School of Computer Science at the Tokyo University of Technology participated in an experimental assessment of these two types of role-play training. The results of a subsequent questionnaire survey and portfolio evaluation of the goal model diagrams developed by the students showed that their requirements modeling skill levels had improved. However, because some students may have had no prior business experience, each role-play scenario needs to be carefully designed so that all necessary information regarding the strategy or vision in the problem domain is clearly laid out.	requirements engineering; KAOS; goal modeling	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7851799	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	fora da engenharia de software

Automatic Programming Assessment System for a Computer Science Bridge Course - An Experience Report	10.1109/APSEC57359.2022.00074	RWTH Aachen University in Germany offers a bridge course that introduces students of a variety of study programs to the basics of imperative programming. Due to the high number of students and limited availability of tutors, it is hard to provide instant individual feedback to all students, to notice how difficult the tasks are for the students, and to reliably monitor their progression during the course. This motivated us to use an Automatic Program Assessment System (APAS) to provide instant formative feedback to students and to systematically assess the course's tasks. In this paper, we present our study in which we investigated (1) if the use of our APAS influences the students' perceived difficulty of the programming tasks, (2) whether the use of our APAS increases the students' progression speed, and (3) if the number of automated assessments triggered by the students can serve as an indicator of a task's perceived difficulty. The results did not allow us to identify any meaningful differences between the study and control group with regards to the perceived difficulty and the progression speed. We found that the number of automated assessments can serve as a rough indicator for the task's perceived difficulty. We also found initial indication that the use of the automated assessment helps to ensure that the students complete the tasks in full and as intended by the teachers and might improve code quality. This needs to be further investigated in future work.	Automatic Programming Assessment System;study	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10043348	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
Hackathon as a Project Based Teaching Tool : Employing Programming Challenge in the Class	10.1109/ICAICT.2018.8747149	Project Based Learning (PBL) develops student knowledge and skills through solving authentic, engaging and complex challenge in a fixed time span. Academic literature reports its application over a wide variety of disciplines, having both immediate and long-lasting positive effect on team working, project management, and creativity when applying technical skills. We aim to enhance student learning in software engineering. 80% of student respondents up to the date feel that programming assignments that last longer than a week overlap with other subjects enough to draw dedication away. While it unquestionably develops transferable skills, such as time management, it also might not necessarily be good through introductory courses, where students face completely new material. As a result, our aim is to employ "hackathon" - a gathering, where programmers collaboratively code in an extreme manner over 12 to 24 hours - as a teaching tool. While there is a precedent of hackathon being used at University level, it was employed to substitute classic approach via excluding lecturing and lab work completely. Current paper presents research design and relevant discussion on measuring and validating learning outcomes when blending hackathon into traditional programming class as one of the components, not a substitute to other types of classes.	Project Based Learning (PBL);Hackathon	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8747149	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
The Effects of a Dynamic Repertory Grid for Peer Assessment: Peer Assessment of Computer Software Application Certificate Practice	10.1109/IIAI-AAI.2016.253	This study developed a novel peer assessment system from the approach of knowledge engineering. Gathering information from experts, a dynamic repertory grid was created as a peer assessment form to be used in a computer skills class taught in a vocational school. This form is dynamic in that it allows student reviewers to select personalized assessment criteria from a bank of items, causing students to reflect on the purpose of the assignment being reviewed and how to best characterize the performance of the student completing the assignment as well as providing ample feedback for students. The results compared the performance of the students using the proposed system with that of the ones using conventional approaches, and found that those who applied the proposed approach learned better and made significant improvement.	peer assessment;computer skill;knowledge engineering; learning achievement	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7557631	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
Digital Technologies in Technical Education	10.1109/TELE62556.2024.10605696	Usually technical disciplines such as mathematical analysis, algebra, analytical geometry, electrical engineering and others cause students difficulties in studying and do not arouse interest. Modern digital technologies can improve the performance and motivate students. The paper considers the use of new teaching methods, modern digital technologies, the use of student preferences. It is shown that these techniques contribute to improving the quality of the educational process and develop students' digital literacy.	digital technologies; interactive education; mathematical calculation systems;interactive online whiteboard	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10605696	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software

Student-facing Learning Analytics Dashboard: Profiles of Student Use	10.1109 /FIE56618. 2022.9962531	<p>Student-facing learning analytics dashboards (LADs) provide visualizations of course-related information to help students understand and personalize their educational practices. As such, they can be viewed as a meta-cognitive tool that enables awareness, self-reflection and sensemaking of academic performance. While student-facing LADs are becoming a standard feature in educational software, questions have been raised about students' willingness to adopt LADs and their ability to interpret feedback provided by student-facing LADs. The extent to which student-facing LADs can broadly improve educational outcomes depends, in part, on students' ability to readily incorporate LAD usage in their educational workflows. This study investigates the use of a student-facing LAD, My Learning Analytics (MyLA), over the span of one semester in a university introductory science course. MyLA draws data from the campus learning management system (Canvas) and displays three visualizations designed to provide students with actionable information. Adoption and use of MyLA was voluntary. As an exploratory study of MyLA's use in an introductory science course, this work addresses three research questions: i) What are the characteristics of students that use MyLA?, ii) How do students make use of MyLA in their coursework?, and iii) What patterns of use are exhibited by more frequent MyLA users? The results indicate that given the opportunity to use a student-facing LAD, 33% of students made repeated use of the tool. Demographic data (e.g., gender, domestic/international student) did not predict MyLA usage but significant differences in mean cumulative GPA were found between non-MyLA users and MyLA users. Broad patterns of MyLA use were aligned with major assessments in the course (e.g., MyLA was used more often around exam dates) and the grade distribution view was the most commonly accessed. Among the most highly active MyLA users, two distinct profiles were identified: aware and sensemakers. Aware users made use of the dashboard on more than 12 distinct days across the course, primarily around exam dates, and stated that they accessed the dashboard to compare their performance with others. Sensemakers made frequent use of all three MyLA views multiple times over the semester to monitor their own progress, compare their grades to others, and check what materials other students had viewed. LADs such as MyLA allow students to leverage what they already know about course assessment in their interpretation of the data presented, easing adoption and deployment of a student-facing LAD in higher education. As MyLA does not require that students have any additional training to interpret the visualizations they provide, LADs can readily be employed by students in introductory computing and engineering courses to provide them with feedback to help them plan for, monitor, and evaluate their academic progress.</p>	learning analytics dashboard; student-facing learning analytics dashboard; self-regulated learning; course level micro-learning analytics	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9962531	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colaboração
Design Principles for Generating and Presenting Automated Formative Feedback on Code Quality Using Software Metrics	10.1145 /3639474. 3640051	<p>Code quality and maintainability are among under-emphasized and often neglected topics in the curriculum of software engineering (SE) in higher education. This neglect tends to overlook research findings that demonstrate SE students' programming submissions most often exhibit severe code quality issues, which are frequently left unaddressed by the students. Furthermore, it can result in the software engineering curriculum becoming indifferent to the essential requirements of the software development industry, where code quality and maintainability play a crucial role in the software's cost throughout its life cycle. Therefore, SE students in higher education should be trained to master the knowledge and skills of writing high-quality code. One possible approach to improving students' understanding of code quality issues is to provide automatically generated formative feedback about the code quality aspects of their programming submissions throughout the code development process. However, while there are tools available for generating automated feedback on the code quality aspects of programming submissions, they often lack a set of theory-driven design principles to underpin the content and presentation of their provided feedback. This lack of theoretical foundation makes it difficult to follow a systematic approach to designing and developing such tools, reasoning about their quality, and evaluating the effectiveness of their generated feedback. To address this lack, this study provides nine contextualized design principles for generating automated formative feedback on code quality. These design principles are rooted in solid educational constructs about feedback and learning dashboards, and empirically validated and contextualized by two focus group sessions consisting of 8 senior SE students and 2 teachers. This approach has resulted in a set of contextualized design principles. These design principles can be used to guide the implementation of tools that provide automated feedback on code quality using software metrics.</p>	Programming education; undergraduate education; design principles; code quality; formative feedback; automated feedback	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10554701			<input type="checkbox"/>

Engineering Human Body for Systematic and Computational Thinking	10.1109 /FIE58773. 2023.10342946	This Research to Practice Work-in-Progress paper discusses a next-generation learning system for K-12 students to educate them on scientific concepts surrounding the human body. Specifically, our gamified learning system is designed to make learning more fun, engaging, and effective through game and experiment elements that align with science and math learning standards. It will also increase systematic problem-solving and algorithmic reasoning for K-12 students. Since the human body can be thought of as a combination of interacting systems, the game also introduces students to computational thinking by introducing internal body functions. To achieve these goals, this project has two components. First, an educational virtual reality game will be built according to the natural human body structure. During the game process, students will experience the same as the human body functions, travel along the blood circulation, help with the heartbeat, and participate in oxygen exchange. While students are playing the game, our gamified adaptive learning system tracks and controls the student's learning progress. As the AI component collects student data and uses this information, our system adjusts game content and addresses possible learner issues to refine the learning curriculum for a faster and more effective learning experience. Second, a series of hands-on activities will be conducted based on the functions of the human body (e.g., developing an artificial heart and experiencing how the heart works). Through this project, an attractive and efficient next-generation learning system will be developed and used to expose K-12 students to this learning system. The education of students will be accomplished in different dimensions through games and hands-on practice, respectively. Additionally, compared to traditional learning methods, our learning system not only increases students' interest in learning but also makes it more personalized compared to the conventional learning process. Likewise, we will refer to the results of self-efficacy surveys administered to students and teachers separately to test their perceptions of their abilities and the new system.	Gamification;Educational Software;Learning Technology;Computational Thinking;Systematic Thinking	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10342946	<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-between;"> <div style="width: 40%; background-color: #00FF00; text-align: center;"><input type="checkbox"/></div> <div style="width: 40%; background-color: #FF0000; text-align: center;"><input checked="" type="checkbox"/></div> </div>	não tem colab		
Inspectors Academy : Pedagogical Design for Requirements Inspection Training	10.1109 /RE48521. 2020.00032	The core aim of requirements inspection is to ensure the high quality of already elicited requirements in the Software Requirements Specification. Teaching requirements inspection to novices is challenging, as inspecting requirements needs several skills as well as knowledge of the product and process that is hard to achieve in a classroom environment. Published studies about pedagogical design specifically for teaching requirements inspection are scarce. Our objective is to present the design and evaluation of a postgraduate course for requirements inspection training. We conducted an empirical study with 138 postgraduate students, teamed up in 34 groups to conduct requirements inspection. We performed qualitative analysis on the data collected from students' reflection reports to assess the effects of the pedagogical design in terms of benefits and challenges. We also quantitatively analyze the correlation between the students' performance in conducting inspections and their ability of writing specifications. From the analysis of students' reflections, several themes emerged such as their difficulty of working with limited information, but also revealed the benefits of learning teamwork and writing good requirements. This qualitative analysis also provides recommendations for improving the related activities. The results revealed a moderate positive correlation between the performance in writing specification and inspection.	Requirements Inspection; Requirements Engineering Education and Training; Empirical Study	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9218174				
A Meta-Summary of Challenges in Building Products with ML Components – Collecting Experiences from 4758+ Practitioners	10.1109 /CAIN58948. 2023.00034	Incorporating machine learning (ML) components into software products raises new software-engineering challenges and exacerbates existing ones. Many researchers have invested significant effort in understanding the challenges of industry practitioners working on building products with ML components, through interviews and surveys with practitioners. With the intention to aggregate and present their collective findings, we conduct a meta-summary study: We collect 50 relevant papers that together interacted with over 4758 practitioners using guidelines for systematic literature reviews. We then collected, grouped, and organized the over 500 mentions of challenges within those papers. We highlight the most commonly reported challenges and hope this meta-summary will be a useful resource for the research community to prioritize research and education in this field.	SE4ML;Software Engineering for Machine Learning;SLR;Meta Summary;ML in Production	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10164747				

Quality Assessment for Large-Scale Industrial Software Systems: Experience Report at Alibaba	10.1109/APSEC48747.2019.00028	To assure high software quality for large-scale industrial software systems, traditional approaches of software quality assurance, such as software testing and performance engineering, have been widely used within Alibaba, the world's largest retailer, and one of the largest Internet companies in the world. However, there still exists a high demand for software quality assessment to achieve high sustainability of business growth and engineering culture in Alibaba. To address this issue, we develop an industrial solution for software quality assessment by following the GQM paradigm in an industrial setting. Moreover, we integrate multiple assessment methods into our solution, ranging from metric selection to rating aggregation. Our solution has been implemented, deployed, and adopted at Alibaba: (1) used by Alibaba's Business Platform Unit to continually monitor the quality for 60+ core software systems; (2) used by Alibaba's R&D Efficiency Unit to support group-wide quality-aware code search and automatic code inspection. This paper presents our proposed industrial solution, including its techniques and industrial adoption, along with the lessons learned during the development and deployment of our solution.	software quality assessment; software quality model; experience report	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8945717	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
Can Pre-class GitHub Contributions Predict Success by Student Teams?	10.1145/3510456.3514144	Over one million teachers, students, and schools around the world use GitHub to reach their learning goals. GitHub promotes team-work, and group or team projects are a necessary element of the software-engineering curriculum. Past studies on GitHub have explored how to integrate GitHub into teaching and how to mine information from GitHub to help students. To our knowledge, we are the first to study the previous contributions of students to GitHub in order to characterize student teams that perform well on team projects, compared to student teams that did not perform so well. We identify factors such as the number of public commits, number of repositories, and size of repositories in certain languages that are associated with the quality of team projects. We discuss the implications of this from the point of view of an educator and a student.	Applied computing → Collaborative learning	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9794264	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	nao avalia
Work in progress: Starter-project for first semester students to survey their engineering studies	10.1109/EDUCON.2015.7095941	To give students studying Electrical or Mechanical Engineering at the Bonn-Rhein-Sieg University of Applied Sciences a smoother beginning, three weeks in the first semester are used for project-based learning and self-learning exercises. The project-based learning part is used to do short-term projects (1 to 3 days) to motivate all the different subjects (mathematics, computer sciences, microcontrollers, principles of electrical engineering, measurement engineering and others) engineering students have to study during their time at the university and show the connection between these subjects. Short-term projects allow an insight into the real world of engineering, improve the student motivation, and enable students to develop soft skills. If projects like this are done in the beginning of the study it also helps them tremendously to connect to their fellow students. Further, there is the intention to prepare a situation where students "feel like engineers". This paper presents a three full-day (organised on three days with four weeks gaps in between) course in the winter term 2014 using LEGO Mindstorm robot kits to give students an easy access to programming, algorithms, sensor technology, robotics and much more.	project-based learning;self-learning exercises;motivation of first year students	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7095941	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Teaching Generic Competences in Software Engineering via E-Learning	10.1109/TALE48000.2019.9225916	The discipline 'Software Engineering' is difficult to represent in higher education, because of the complexity of software development projects and the variety of skills required. In addition to specialist skills (professional competences), generic competences are increasingly becoming the focus of education. This paper deals with the training of generic competences in the software engineering module. For this purpose, an existing didactic concept was enhanced by ELearning with the help of a Moodle course.	E-Learning;Generic Competences;Software Engineering	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9225916	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
Tech Startup Learning Activities: A Formative Evaluation		The Tech Startup model is an approach where students in Software Engineering and Entrepreneurship courses form interdisciplinary teams to create businesses based on software products. The model combines Agile software development with compatible practices from Lean Startup to foster collaboration on real technology startup businesses (tech startups). This paper introduces learning activities for use in the Tech Startup model intended to improve adherence to Agile and Lean Startup methodologies. This study describes a formative evaluation of the learning activities used for: project ideation, project planning, iterative delivery & feedback, and teamwork assessment. The study synthesizes responses to a questionnaire with feedback from three focus groups at the conclusion of an academic term. Based on our findings and observations, we report suggestions for encouraging innovative project ideas from Software Engineering students as well as approaches to holding students accountable for adhering to Agile practices.	Entrepreneurship;Agile software development;Lean startup;Slicing pie	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8442125	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

The Effects of Information Technology and E-Learning Systems on Translation Pedagogy and Productivity of EFL Learners	10.1109/3ICT.2019.8910326	This study addresses the increasing demands for reliable translation services due to the advent of the electronic text, the prolific production of texts in different disciplines, the increasing communication among individuals from different languages and cultures, and the unprecedented development of new technologies, software and applications (referred to as CAT tools). Human translation cannot address these increasing demands of customers and businesses. Hence, this study assumes that translation technologies and machine translation systems can be usefully integrated into translation classrooms for improving learners' performance and translation quality. An experimental study was carried out where 20 Level-6 students, who are attending one translation course in Prince Sattam Bin Abdulaziz University, volunteered to participate in an optional legal translation course. Participants were divided into 2 groups: an experimental group whose instruction was supported by CAT tools, and a control group who were taught using only conventional teaching methods. Results showed that there was a statistically significant difference among CAT users and nonusers in favor of the experimental group ($p < .05$). It can be concluded then that translation systems and software can be usefully used for improving EFL students' translation skills. The integration of CAT tools into the learning environment not only support the practical and professional skills that well-qualify graduates for the translation industry, but it also creates an environment that enables them to acquire different skills in some related disciplines such as assessment of translation techniques, interaction between humans and the machine, and text analysis. The study suggested that translation instructors should adopt blended learning models where they integrate translation technology with conventional teaching methods. Educational institutions are also recommended to provide professional training for instructors on the use of language software and translation systems.	CAT;information technology; e-learning;SDL Trados Studios translation technologies	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8910326	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Exploratory Data Analysis of Artificial Intelligence Integration in Philippine Engineering Programs Offered by State Universities and Colleges: A Preliminary Assessment	10.1109/SIEDS61124.2024.10534634	Artificial Intelligence (AI) has become a disruptive element in modern engineering and consequently led to the reshaping of industry demands and educational frameworks worldwide. Recognizing the potential impact of AI on the engineering sector, there is indeed a growing need to evaluate how well current educational programs are integrating these advancements. This study therefore focused on assessing the extent of AI integration within the curricula of engineering programs offered by Philippine State Universities and Colleges (SUCs) with the objective to identify their current capabilities and gaps on AI integration. To achieve this goal, the methodology employed three phases: Data Collection, Data Analysis, and Insight Generation. Initially, the Data Collection phase involved the creation of a tabular data from 78 publicly accessible SUC websites which contained the engineering program descriptions, objectives, courses and their respective descriptions. When specific course descriptions were unavailable, standard definitions provided by the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) were utilized. The Data Analysis phase involved the normalization and preprocessing of text data to establish two distinct corpora based on constructed dataset and were subsequently analyzed for AI-related keywords using 1-gram and 2-gram models. Implementation of the last phase revealed a significant but partial integration of AI competencies in the engineering curricula. Keywords such as "learn", "teamwork", "ICT", "R", "data", "statistic", "software", and "communication" suggested foundational AI skills are being incorporated within the engineering curricula. However, the absence of advanced AI terms like "machine learning" and "neural networks" highlighted a gap in preparing students for more sophisticated AI roles. This analysis indicated that while some foundational aspects of AI are introduced, a more comprehensive approach is needed for full integration. To address this, this work proposes to: (i) extend engineering programs to include core AI courses, (ii) integrate AI-focused courses into existing tracks, or (iii) offer AI courses as summer modules. Collectively, the findings of this study underlined the need for curriculum adjustments to better align engineering programs with the evolving demands of the current technology landscape, thereby enhancing the global competitiveness of Filipino engineering graduates.	Data analysis;Neural networks;Machine learning; Data collection;Software; Teamwork;Information and communication technology	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10534634	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem metrica
Assignments	10.1109/EDUCON.2015.7095955	An assignment analysis was carried out according to Bloom's taxonomy for basic and advanced Engineering Graphics courses. Assignments for the first basic course cover the first three levels of Bloom's taxonomy: remembering, understanding and applying, with some elements of creativity. Assignments for the advanced course cover the upper three levels of Bloom's taxonomy: analysing, evaluating and creating. To stimulate student interest in purposeful learning it is essential to strike a balance between student engagement and the courses' learning outcomes as determined by the curriculum. To achieve these goals the following course structure possibilities were analysed: creative elements in assignments; continuous and formative assessment with two-phase feedback; premium grading points; and external motivators.	Engineering Graphics; Bloom's taxonomy; assignment;assessment; feedback	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7095955	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software

Design and Development of a Serious Game for the Teaching of Requirements Elicitation and Analysis	10.1109 /TALE48000. 2019.9225987	Requirements elicitation and analysis is one of the topics covered in Software Engineering, Requirements Engineering (RE) and other subjects belonging to the group, which are usually taught to the undergraduate computer science students. Requirements elicitation and analysis are crucial to the software development as mistakes made at this stage will negatively impact the subsequent stages of development. Thus, it is important to ensure students' firm understanding of the topic. One way to improve their understanding is by improving their interest and engagement in the topic. Taking advantage of younger generation's inclination towards games, means to increase students' interest and understanding of the topic using serious games were proposed. However, most of the existing games thus far are not focusing on the requirements elicitation and analysis in detail and are limited to only one real-life scenario per game. This research therefore attempted to address the gap by designing and developing a digital serious game for requirements elicitation and analysis topic that aims to improve students' understanding of the topic by applying the knowledge gained from lectures to a number of real-life scenarios provided in the game. The content of the game was designed based on the learning objectives to be attained and its overall design and development followed the ADDIE model comprising analysis, design, development, implementation and evaluation phases. This paper however focuses on the design and development phases of the game. A pilot test was performed at the end of the development phase where the game's usability and its ability to attain the learning objectives of the topic were assessed. However, the test only covered the first level of the game. Analysis performed on the test results showed that while most of the assessed learning objectives were satisfactorily attained, rooms for improvement with regards to game usability were seen, particularly on the difficulty and navigability.	gamification;software engineering;requirements engineering;educational game	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9225987	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
Engineering the future: transversal skills in Engineering Doctoral Education	10.1109 /CISPEE47794. 2021.9507210	Over the last decade there has been a significant increase in doctoral students and researchers in Engineering. Entry-level skills for these academic positions are often mostly technical and frequently associated with profiles that thrive in analytical and frequently solitary tasks in laboratorial environments. However, success in doctoral programs and research careers is highly dependent on competencies that are both intrapersonal (e.g. time management, self-regulation, emotional intelligence, resilience) and interpersonal (e.g. teamworking, communication, negotiation, etc). Since the recruitment of doctoral graduates has changed significantly due to the decrease in open positions in research and professorship at universities, the transition from academia to industry has been gaining more attention from the Engineering Education community. Despite this, many studies point out that the competencies developed in Portuguese doctoral programs do not motivate nor prepare PhD graduates for a career outside academia and also don't match industry requirements in terms of competencies needed to thrive in such environments. In response, assessment reports and policy papers have been highlighting the need to rethink doctoral programs curricula in order to prepare engineering graduates for their future careers both in academia and industry. The basis for this has been advocated in the development of a specific skill set of transversal competencies. With this study, we intended to identify the transversal skills clusters that result from engineering doctoral education literature, make engineering researchers and managers aware of the importance of transversal skills, identify potential gaps in the literature and avenues for future research. In order to have a broad overview of the transversal competencies of PhD candidates in engineering, a preliminary bibliometric analysis of 2756 papers published in the last two decades was conducted using VOSviewer. The results show evidence of literature clusters related to 1) necessary skills for successfully concluding the PhD program; 2) the shift from the academic world to the labor market; 3) interpersonal competencies. In the discussion of the results, the authors: 1) advocate the emergency for HEIs to develop institutional strategies that contemplate formal opportunities to develop transversal skills during the doctoral path and ensure employability prospects for PhD candidates; b) propose the use of a framework of competencies for PhD candidates in engineering that may orientate the implementation of such institutional strategies and also help candidates to transfer such skills to industry/business in the transition from academia to industry.	doctoral education; engineering;soft skills; transversal competencies; transition to industry; VOSviewer	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9507210	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software

Learning Parallel Programming Through Programming Challenges	10.1109 /FIE44824. 2020.9274009	This research full paper describes the use of challenges to teach parallel programming, regardless of teaching methodology (traditional, Problem-Based Learning and others) or programming-contest support systems. We verify how challenges contribute to the learning of parallel programming, considering technical and motivational aspects. Studies demonstrate the potential of using programming contests as educational resources at the end of courses, encouraging students to practice and learn more about parallel programming. However, there are no proposals exploring programming challenges as part of the learning process, since the beginning of the course. This paper presents four different experiments applying challenges to teach parallel programming for undergraduate and graduate students. We evaluated different teaching/learning methodologies, contexts, educational resources (including programming marathon systems), and groups of students. Considering all the experiments, almost 250 students participated and were evaluated. We developed and applied 58 challenges to analyze theoretical and practical knowledge about parallel programming. Different metrics were used to evaluate the students during the experiments: theoretical assessments, source-code quality, program output correctness, and students receptivity/motivation to learning from challenges. Results from experiments show scores of up to 96% of learning on technical aspects and up to 83% on student satisfaction. Challenges stimulated the development of high-quality parallel solutions and promoted a healthy environment among students, where the lightly-competitive context contributed to create a collaborative atmosphere. The use of programming marathon systems as an educational tool is not imperative. The use of challenges for the students' learning, not on their classification, showed that it is possible to teach parallel programming, maintaining students focused and motivated.	Teaching;Learning;Parallel Programming;Challenges; Contests	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9274009	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem es e colab
The DevOps Lab Platform for Managing Diversified Projects in Educating Agile Software Engineering	10.1109/FIE. 2018.8658817	This Research Work-in-Progress paper presents the design of a Software Engineering (SE) course to support project-based practical training. Group projects, especially projects from industry partners, are deemed to be necessary for students to gain hands-on experiences. With projects from the real world, students learn not only practical engineering solutions, but also the context, constraints, and social aspects of SE. For a course having over 100 students with different interests and experiences, it is desired to provide diversified choices of projects to stimulate enthusiasm for learning. However, management and evaluation of diversified projects are challenging. Following the Agile principles, we need to continuously track progress and activities of each group, to provide quick feedback of deliveries, and to periodically evaluate students' performance. Therefore, we built a DevOps platform based on GitLab version control and continuous integration framework. Commits to GitLab code repositories automatically trigger build, testing, and analysis functions (which provide both qualitative and quantitative feedback to the students). This system has been in operations since 2014 for an undergraduate SE course, with over 500 students participating in over 130 project teams in total. The preliminary research showed promising results in improving SE education.	Software;Tools;Task analysis;Industries;Testing; Education;Collaboration	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8658817	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não avalia
ICTs for Education: An Inclusive Approach to Addressing Challenges Faced by Roma Communities in Europe	10.23919 /MIPRO. 2019.8757108	Despite the fact that education is a basic human right, children and youth from marginalized communities often, lack access to quality education programs. Applying ICTs as a tool to education, rather than the solution, has great potential to narrow existing education gaps, while conveying skills and competences necessary for economic and social survival in today's connected and digitalized societies. Roma are Europe's largest ethnic minority group, and despite multiple efforts to improve the living conditions of Roma people, the majority of Roma households continues to live in deep poverty, is subject to social exclusion and discrimination. Moreover, four out of five students from Roma communities, lack basic cognitive skills and competences. This paper introduces the Head in the Clouds Project (HIC), an innovative learning program based on self-organized learning environments, the use of state of the art IT devices and the innovative learning approach MINIMAX while shedding light on the use of ICTs in marginalized communities. Particularly it discusses potential long-term impacts of ICT enabled self-organized learning environments on creating more inclusive educational programs and societies, and the potential contribution of inclusive and IT supported learning environments towards the achievement of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).	Technology Enhanced Learning;Computer-Supported Collaborative Learning;Digital Learning; Self-Organized Learning Environments;Inclusive Societies;Roma Minority Group;Sustainable Development Goals;ICTs	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8757108	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab

Developing Higher Education – Post-Pandemic – Influenced by AI	10.1109 /FIE58773. 2023.10343215	The impact of the recent pandemic on Higher Education has been widely discussed in terms of the effects on students and the loss of the normal educational experience, accompanied by discussions of how to return to normality. However, in this paper the authors challenge the reality of that previous so-called normality and propose a number of changes to academic practices to take advantage of the opportunities offered by this break in existing practice. Additionally, new developments in AI technology, particularly in chatbots, present significant challenges to existing assessment practices, which were already under challenge from existing research. This also presents significant opportunities to introduce new, academically focused and effective assessment practices and instruments, taken from existing research, to improve the quality of evaluation of student learning in higher education. So, this paper has two main considerations: the development of better student engagement models to enhance cohort effects in the student experience; and the introduction of improved assessment practices and instruments from existing research, in particular focusing on student ownership of evaluation models. It discusses a number of existing research outputs, several of them produced by the authors, and some current initiatives, and looks at the pros and cons of each, in terms of effectiveness and staff and student responses. It has been widely reported that the student experience across a wide range of subjects, and in the whole range of higher education institutions, has been very badly affected by lockdowns and other changes brought about by the pandemic. In the engineering/computing community the authors have experienced first-hand the changes occasioned during this period, and have seen students become isolated, disaffected, anti-social and, in many cases, disengaged from their studies. It can be argued that one key criterion of the student experience that online delivery of learning does not support well is cohort-formation, and that developing entry-level cohort-based learning experiences, both online and face-to-face, offers a route more effective student engagement and retention. The authors discuss a number of such initiatives reported in existing research, and also describe a new initiative being developed at their own institution, based on early immersion in advanced technologies to spark interest and creativity, and thence engagement, in entry-level technology students. With regard to assessment and evaluation practices, there is a huge body of existing research questioning the widely used examination and coursework processes, arguing that these are only retained for administrative and cost efficiencies, not for any academic benefit. The recent release of ChatGPT by OpenAI has added considerable flame to the fire of essay-mills, code-farms, and bespoke thesis-writing, which has supported students cheating in assessment processes for many years. The authors take this opportunity to reconsider assessment practices, in the light of many successful models reported in the existing research, and to develop a new model of assessment, where students take responsibility for the ownership and evaluation of their own learning, mediated by academic processes.	Assessment;AI;Cohort building;student engagement	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10343215	<input type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software		
Guide to teach Lean Startup methodology to software engineering students using a serious game	10.1109 /ENC53357. 2021.9534827	In the last decade, Lean Startup has become an emerging methodology for teaching entrepreneurship to Software Engineering and Computer Science students. However, for most students, it is difficult to understand the key concepts of this methodology and put them into practice successfully. An approach to solve this problem is the use of serious games as a support tool that foster positive attitudes such as motivation, engagement and participation leading to effective learning. Besides, simulating real-life situations within an academic environment still remains a challenge. This article proposes a guide as support to teachers that aims to teach Lean Startup methodology using a serious game. The guide provides a set of recommendations, best practices and re-sources that contribute to improve the understanding of the key concepts of Lean Startup. The guide was evaluated by a group of Lean Startup experts. The results confirm the usefulness of the guide and the positive effects on learning from the experts' perspective.	Serious games;Lean Startup; Process improvement; Software Engineering; Serious games assessment	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9534827			<input type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	espanhol
Work-in-progress: A workflow for programming learning on remote version control repositories	10.1109 /EDUCON5253 7.2022.9766559	This paper shows how a teaching innovation project is being developed using GitHub to support laboratory and autonomous programming assignments/tasks as part of the Industrial Engineering course at the University of Almería. A Github organization has been created where not only assignment instructions are given but also where students can collaborate by engaging in real-time teamwork activities focused on problem-based learning while working in a professional programming environment. The students' work can be easily controlled and monitored using the commit tracking system, thus facilitating the assessment of large groups.	programming learning; teamwork;remote collaboration	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9766559					<input type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

An Analytical Study Towards the UAE Universities Smart Education Innovated Approaches	10.1109/HPCC-SmartCity-DSS.2017.26	The world has become a global village and technology has a strong influence in every aspect of our daily lives and the fourth industrial revolution that will alter the way we live and learn. This inter-connectivity brings a need for greater engagement, experience and efficiency. Catch a sign on a day in a life of a student and how connectivity and technology helps enrich his/her daily activities. This research aims to study the beneficiary of adopting Smart Education technology among United Arab Emirates (UAE) Universities. This type of education is becoming a dominant in academia especially within universities around the globe. Since it was introduced, it demonstrates a significant change in educational instructional methods. The objective of this research is to investigate Smart Education instruments such as its significance and demands. This research used different tools for assessment. Surveys and interviews were conducted to group of universities learners and educators within the higher education system in the UAE. The outcome of the research has shown a significant support towards the usage of the Smart tools and technologies. The survey has also indicated that 72% of the participants preferred the technology approach within their curriculum. The research highlighted that there is a great impact of using the Smart technology tools. In the Future, the authors would like to investigate the risk of adopting such educational approach.	Cloud Education; Education Technology; E-learning; Mobile Learning; Smart Education; University Education	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8291929	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
Measures for Predicting Task Cohesion in a Global Collaborative Learning Environment	10.1109/ICGSEW.2016.23	This paper describes a study that compared a number of interaction-based measures and their ability to predict cohesion within global software development projects. Messages were collected from three software development projects that involved students from two different countries. The similarities and quantities of such interactions were then analyzed and compared. Results from this analysis show a statistically significant correlation of linguistic characteristics (LSM) and Information Exchange Similarity with Task cohesion, when controlled by culture. In addition, the study found that quantity-based metrics had higher correlations with students' perceptions of their group's cohesiveness than similarity-based measures. More specifically, a word-based measure called Information Exchange Rate had a significant relationship to cohesion. Group rate measures were also tested, but only low significant correlations were found. These results suggest that measures based on quantity of interactions tend to be better predictors of cohesion within distributed learning teams.	Teamwork;Collaboration; Virtual groups	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7579482	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Exploring the Usage of Mobile Phones in the Assessment Process: A Case Study	10.1109/MIPRO60963.2024.10569715	Technology is changing how students learn in the 21st century significantly. Integrating mobile devices in teaching, learning, and assessment processes has emerged as an important strategy for improving teaching methodologies and students' learning. However, adopting mobile devices presents several challenges, including understanding the students' performance, impact on time, and efficiency in the assessment process. This study explores this area with an empirical study of using mobile devices and compares the results to those using traditional desktop computers. In the educational environment, we investigated students' effective use while interacting with mobile and desktop versions of the Second Introductory programming summative assessment. Multinational/multi-institutional research involved a comparative analysis between two student groups undertaking identical tasks on mobile phones and desktop computers. Our results suggest that the students' results are not affected significantly by using the mobile version of the assessment application. These results highlight the usability of mobile devices as a flexible and effective tool for various educational applications, strengthening their role in the modern learning environment.	computer science education; improving teaching methodologies;assessment process;controlled experiment;object-oriented programming	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10569715	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
Researching and supporting student note-taking: Building a multimedia note-taking app	10.1109/TALE.2015.7386015	In late 2014 collaborative research was undertaken between colleagues in the departments of Computer Science, International Communications, the Centre for English language Education (CELE), and the Language Centre at a global higher education institution (HEI-A), located partly in mainland China. This research aims to explore student note-taking habits, especially in the context of more multimedia-intense content. As part of this, student note-taking habits have been observed and studied, and a software application is being developed which will support student multimedia note-taking, and facilitate research into note-taking habits. An interesting aspect of this project has been the inclusion of HEI-A undergraduate computer science students as software developers. This paper outlines some findings of our research in terms of defining student note-taking habits, describes some of the issues we faced during the first stages of the project and gives a short description on how this application could be used for teaching and research purposes in the future.	Apps;Note-taking;Note-making;Digital Technology in the Classroom;Learning and Teaching Research	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7386015	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab

The Role of Source Code Vocabulary in Programming Teaching and Learning	10.1109 /FIE44824. 2020.9274137	This full paper, categorized as Research-to-Practice, presents an investigation on the role of source code vocabulary in introductory programming learning practices. According to software engineering literature, source code vocabulary is a fundamental aspect of software quality as it contributes to software readability and eases maintenance and evolution tasks. Furthermore, some studies show that identifier naming and comments in the code tend to use terms that reflect the software problem domain specification and can be used, for instance, to localize feature. In this paper, we build upon this knowledge of software engineering and investigate how we can take advantage of it in computer science education, specially on the teaching of programming. We conducted a twofold empirical study in an introductory programming course to investigate: (1) How to give automated feedback about identifier naming, aiming to improve software readability, and (2) To what extent source code vocabulary reflects problem specification comprehension, which is crucial to effective programming problem-solving. In the first study, we found that 51.7% of the students improved their source code vocabulary, after receiving such feedback. In the second study, the results showed that students tend to manage to better comprehend the programming problem being solved when their code identifier names are connected to the related description. It is a promising indicative that we can use this information to assess the problem requirements comprehension, which is a fundamental step in the programming problem-solving cycle. The main contribution of this paper is to shed light on the source code vocabulary and promote its role in the programming teaching and learning scenario. We present some evidence that students' source code vocabulary is a rich information source about their understanding and we can use it to produce formative feedback.	computing education; automated assessment; source code vocabulary quality	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9274137	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Applying a Traditional Software Development Process to Drive Projects in Higher Education	10.1109/SEAA. 2019.00054	As institutions of higher education attempt to professionalize their curricula, we observe the emergence of learning experiences that simulate industrial software projects and stronger focus on the skill set desired by the industry. A common practice to address that need is to introduce a capstone unit where students complete large assignments in teams and consolidate previously acquired concepts and skills. Increasingly, such projects are supported by a given software development methodology in order to familiarize students with these processes and facilitate implementation. While the growing prevalence of Agile methods in the industry is reflected in a proliferation of studies of their use in academic contexts, the application of traditional approaches does not capture much attention in research. This experience report discusses the introduction of a Waterfall model to support student teams developing Artificial Conversational Entities for an industrial client. The course structure and accompanying methods, adaptations of the process, lessons learned and recommendations for academics wishing to use a traditional method as part of a university class are presented. Our study shows that such an approach yields promising results for complex and state-of-the-art projects and practices associated with it enforce students' software-engineering skills.	software and its engineering, software creation and management, software development process management, software development methods, waterfall model	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8906735	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
Support peer assessment processes in online problem-based learning	10.1109 /EDUCON. 2016.7474598	Problem Based Learning (PBL) is proposed as one of the most well-known alternatives to traditional lectures in modeling engineering graduates to become independent workers, critical thinkers, problem solver, lifelong learners, and team worker. In the past decades much has been reported about how to support online PBL, but much less attention has been given to support assessment in an online PBL. Recently, the authors of this paper have developed a domain-specific modeling language approach and an associated web-based PBL application to support the development and delivery of online PBL modules in a cost-effective and flexible manner. In this paper, the authors emphasize to support peer assessment in an online PBL. Through using a peer assessment example, the authors present how to support teachers, who may not have a comprehensive technical knowledge, to specify a peer assessment process as a segment of a PBL script, a graphical representation of a PBL strategy. Then the PBL application can transform a PBL script that including the peer assessment into a formal model represented in an international e-learning technical standard IMS-Learning Design (IMS-LD). Finally, such a formal model can be executed in any IMS-LD compatible run-time environment. We have demonstrated the technical feasibility of this approach through specifying and transforming the example peer assessment script.	Peer assessment; Problem-based learning (PBL); learning design; IMS-LD; domain-specific modeling language	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7474598	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software

Student's Access Patterns of a Moodle-based Course Management System: A Case Study of a Large Entry Level Programming Class	10.1109 /TALE48000. 2019.9225914	With the wide adoption of Course Management Systems (CMSs) and their availability on different types of devices, students can access their course content anytime, anywhere and stay up to date with their modules on a frequent basis. The continued growth in the volume of data allows us to apply learning analytics strategies to understand patterns of access and students' online behavior. Our aim is to analyze the use of online materials in a Moodle-based CMS by students to identify their usage patterns. To do this, we systematically collected and analyzed students' access of the course materials related to two coursework assessments in a large programming course for entry level students across two years. Our results indicate that students' access of the course materials significantly impact on their assignment scores. There are also differences in students' access based on their gender and STEM/Non-STEM backgrounds. Based on our results, we derive suggestions for how to improve the learning experience of students in CMSs.	Course Management System;CSI;Programming; Mobile Devices;Learning Analytics;STEM Non-STEM	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9225914	<div style="background-color: #00FF00; width: 100%; height: 100%; display: flex; align-items: center; justify-content: center;"> <input data-bbox="1733 145 1765 167" type="checkbox"/> </div> <div style="background-color: #FF0000; width: 100%; height: 100%; display: flex; align-items: center; justify-content: center;"> <input checked="" data-bbox="1877 145 1908 167" type="checkbox"/> </div>	não tem engenharia de software	
Assessment of a Hybrid Software Development Process for Student Projects: A Controlled Experiment	10.1109/ICSE-SEET52601. 2021.00039	In recent years, a vivid interest in hybrid development methods has been observed as practitioners combine various approaches to software creation to improve productivity, product quality, and adaptability of the process to react to change. Scientific papers on the subject proliferate, however evaluation of the effectiveness of hybrid methods in academic contexts has yet to follow. The work presented investigates if introducing a hybrid approach for student projects brings added value as compared to iterative and sequential development. A controlled experiment was carried out among Bachelor students of a French engineering school to assess the impacts of a given development method on the success of student computing undertakings. Its three dimensions were examined via a set of metrics: product quality, team productivity as well as human factors (teamwork quality & learning outcomes). Several patterns were observed, which can provide a starting point for educators and researchers wishing to tailor or design a software development process for academic needs.	hybrid software development; hybrid method;software process;iterative;sequential; student projects;education	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9402199		<div style="background-color: #00FF00; width: 100%; height: 100%; display: flex; align-items: center; justify-content: center;"> <input checked="" data-bbox="1733 403 1765 426" type="checkbox"/> </div> <div style="background-color: #FF0000; width: 100%; height: 100%; display: flex; align-items: center; justify-content: center;"> <input data-bbox="1877 403 1908 426" type="checkbox"/> </div>	chance experimento
Use of a Physical Water Pipe Network Competition in Applied Civil Engineering Students' Learning	10.1109 /EDUCON. 2019.8725039	The issues of scale and complexity make it difficult to design physical problem-based exercises to enhance student learning in the discipline of water and environmental engineering. Thus, learning problems are mostly restricted to those investigated using standard laboratory setups or computer software applications. This paper presents the use of the Aqualibrium competition, a physical hydraulics problem, in enhancing the understanding of water distribution system operation for civil and environmental engineering students. The competition was open for enrollment of civil engineering undergraduate students who have completed or were at the time enrolled in the CIVL 400 (Water Resources Engineering) course at UAE University. In this paper, the competition delivery is explained in details, including aspects of team building, motivation, and timing. Data were collected on the academic performance of participating students and their feedback on their experience in the competition. Results show that the students participating in the competition while enrolled in the course were more enthusiastic about the competition and had better organization and teamwork. Students who had completed the CIVL 400 course had difficulties organizing meetings, which resulted in insufficient practice ahead of the competition. Student feedback results also show that while the competition encouraged self-learning, it left the students confused about the interactive principles of pipe network hydraulics.	Aqualibrium;problem-based learning;collaborative learning;self-learning;student competition	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8725039			<div style="background-color: #00FF00; width: 100%; height: 100%; display: flex; align-items: center; justify-content: center;"> <input data-bbox="1733 662 1765 684" type="checkbox"/> </div> <div style="background-color: #FF0000; width: 100%; height: 100%; display: flex; align-items: center; justify-content: center;"> <input checked="" data-bbox="1877 662 1908 684" type="checkbox"/> </div>

Moving on from the Software Engineers' Gambit: An Approach to Support the Defense of Software Effort Estimates	10.1109 /ICSE48619. 2023.00068	Pressure for higher productivity and faster delivery is increasingly pervading software organizations. This can lead software engineers to act like chess players playing a gambit—making sacrifices of their technically sound estimates, thus submitting their teams to time pressure. In turn, time pressure can have varied detrimental effects, such as poor product quality and emotional distress, decreasing productivity, which leads to more time pressure and delays: a hard-to-stop vicious cycle. This reveals a need for moving on from the more passive strategy of yielding to pressure to a more active one of defending software estimates. Therefore, we propose an approach to support software estimators in acquiring knowledge on how to carry out such defense, by introducing negotiation principles encapsulated in a set of defense lenses, presented through a digital simulation. We evaluated the proposed approach through a controlled experiment with software practitioners from different companies. We collected data on participants' attitudes, subjective norms, perceived behavioral control, and intentions to perform the defense of their estimates in light of the Theory of Planned Behavior. We employed a frequentist and a bayesian approach to data analysis. Results show improved scores among experimental group participants after engaging with the digital simulation and learning about the lenses. They were also more inclined to choose a defense action when facing pressure scenarios than a control group exposed to questions to reflect on the reasons and outcomes of pressure over estimates. Qualitative evidence reveals that practitioners perceived the set of lenses as useful in their current work environments. Collectively, these results show the effectiveness of the proposed approach and its perceived relevance for the industry, despite the low amount of time required to engage with it.	Software Effort Estimation; Negotiation;Behavioral Software Engineering; Defense of Estimates	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10172562	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
Work-in-Progress: An agile approach to formative assessment in higher education	10.1109 /EDUCON4633 2.2021.9454060	Formative assessment is part of a learning process in which the teacher continuously monitors students' learning and provides feedback intended to let students themselves reflect upon what they have learned and where they need to focus more attention. The underlying goal of formative assessment is to lift the students to a higher metacognitive level where they can monitor and guide their learning while simultaneously improving their learning outcomes. However, many courses are planned before the semester starts and may not include methods to continuously improve the teaching. With continuous monitoring and assessment, the philosophy behind formative assessment has some similarities to the agile methodology often employed in software- and product development. This paper presents an agile framework for formative assessment in engineering courses.By taking the viewpoint of "Knowledge as a product", this focus ensures: (1) that the students increase their knowledge through sprints and demonstrate it often, and (2), that the methods of teaching and learning are continuously improved through feedback from the students so that the teacher can adapt and improve to enable learning, all supported by formative assessment. Additionally, the agile approach to formative assessment has the potential to improve the non-technical professional skills of students.	formative assessment; feedback;agile learning	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9454060	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab e es
Model of a Centralized System for Quality Assurance in Higher Education	10.1109 /IS48319. 2020.9199951	Quality assurance in higher education is a task that is invariably the focus of the authorities. Quality standards place increasingly higher demands on educational institutions. Quality assurance procedures are cumbersome, they require a large amount of information to be collected by the higher education staff, information which is subject to verification by experts from the evaluating institution. The use of a centralized software system for external quality evaluation will unify the accreditation procedures and will attribute to their optimization. This article proposes a formal generalized net model of a centralized system for quality assurance in higher education. It aims to outline principles, guidelines, models and processes that guide the creation of specific software applications. The model described is based on our experience in creating and using the COMPASS stand-alone application for (self)assessment and accreditation in higher education.	quality assurance;external quality assurance;quality of higher education; accreditation	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9199951	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
Engineering Gender-Inclusivity into Software: Ten Teams' Tales from the Trenches		Although the need for gender-inclusivity in software is gaining attention among SE researchers and SE practitioners, and at least one method (GenderMag) has been published to help, little has been reported on how to make such methods work in real-world settings. Real-world teams are ever-mindful of the practicalities of adding new methods on top of their existing processes. For example, how can they keep the time costs viable? How can they maximize impacts of using it? What about controversies that can arise in talking about gender? To find out how software teams "in the trenches" handle these and similar questions, we collected the GenderMag-based processes of 10 real-world software teams-more than 50 people-for periods ranging from 5 months to 3.5 years. We present these teams' insights and experiences in the form of 9 practices, 2 potential pitfalls, and 2 open issues, so as to provide their insights to other real-world software teams trying to engineer gender-inclusivity into their software products.	Inclusive software;software engineering practices; GenderMag	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9283992	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab e avaliação

DIVE: Make Online Learning Diversified	10.1109 /TALE54877. 2022.00085	As university courses move online due to the pandemic, resources for face-to-face teaching become ineffective or unusable. Especially for computer science courses requiring a complicated setup, students may not be able to access the computer labs nor receive immediate guidance. To help students dive into a discovery-enriched curriculum without getting lost, we successfully developed effective courseware for various online courses and workshops to provide a diversified, interactive, versatile, and engaging (DIVE) virtual learning environment. By integrating and enhancing tools such as interactive notebook, docker, and git, students can easily reproduce the environment in a web browser, share GPU resources, interact with the lecture materials, submit lab assignments for auto-grading, collaborate on group projects with proper version control, and receive instant automated feedback as well as detailed guidance from instructors.	Courseware;Computer science;Electronic learning; Pandemics;Conferences; Education;Graphics processing units	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10148306	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Identifying Success Criteria for Sustainable AI-based Online Laboratory Courseware System	10.1109 /EDUCON5253 7.2022.9766563	The great transformation of e-learning during the Covid-19 pandemic has led to the emergence of new learning tools and virtual learning environments through Internet. Despite many advantages of e-Learning courseware systems such as availability, flexibility and accessibility, students of some sectors such as engineering, science and technology are facing several limitations in conducting their practical works remotely through online platform for laboratory experiments. The specific objective of this study was to come up with an updated success criteria and list of requirements that should be considered for developing a sustainable artificial intelligence-based online laboratory courseware system. Data for this study were collected using online questionnaire distributed to a group of e-Learning experts. NVivo software was used to analyze experts' comments on how to construct the online laboratory courseware systems. This research revealed 16 basic design and development criteria for the online laboratory courseware system, which are distributed into eight sub-branches and organized into four primary aspects. These findings suggest that in general 30 accurate indicators for the design of an effective laboratory learning system (LLS) for engineering, science and technology sectors dealing with content management, assessment, accessibility and usability as well as the adoption of artificial intelligence techniques.	Online laboratory; courseware;e-learning; criteria;artificial intelligence; Covid-19.	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9766563	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Teaching entrepreneurship in computer science: Lessons learned	10.1109/FIE. 2017.8190664	Many Computer Science departments are offering courses in Entrepreneurship. Views vary widely on the purpose, appropriateness and value of this as a topic area for students majoring in Computer Science - hence the title of this paper. We begin by exploring the meaning of the term, and review representative examples of Entrepreneurship programs in different Computer Science departments, looking at their stated goals and outcomes. We then describe our own experience designing and teaching a new, two-part, yearlong course on "Software Entrepreneurship" at Brandeis University, we extensively explore important lessons learned from this experience. Our program includes two interlocking courses, one focused on the "discovery stage" and one focused on the "delivery stage". We briefly describe the structure, learning objectives and overall flow of the courses. We then examine, in turn, a series of common challenges and our solutions and innovations in each: a) forming well-functioning student teams; b) choosing the appropriate size of teams; c) catalyzing innovation in the student teams; d) encouraging positive team dynamics and dealing with crises; e) defining the final deliverable; and f) deploying outside experts and g) assessments at the end of the course. To get a handle on the effectiveness of our approach we present a selection of student written reflections on their experience, how they felt it impacted them, and to what extent they see entrepreneurship in their own future. We conclude by identifying two broad areas for future work and study.	entrepreneurship;computer science education;software engineering;pedagogy; assessment	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8190664	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab

Meta-heuristic approaches to tackle Skill Based Group allocation in Project Based Learning Courses	10.1109/CEC.2019.8789987	In the arena of software engineering, Project Based Learning (PBL) is one of the fundamental components of practical based assessment. PBL involves team formation where necessary skills are needed to execute the project. Traditionally, the teams were randomly allocated based on individual preferences. To cab on this issue, preference based model needs few refinements such as skills needs to be identified by the facilitator while the students provide the necessary skill data. This way, students get assigned based on their skill rather than just random allocation. In a worst case scenario for random allocation, a team can end up with a very strong team having high skills or vice versa where a team has all of its members with limited skill or few skills are missing. The group created by skill preference would allow each group to more or less have the same strength and nearly all skills would be present in a group. In this paper, a method is extended from its original to cater for other state-of-the-art optimization techniques rather than just genetic algorithm to find a method that can suit small or large dataset. The objective function takes into account the differences between the total skill set of each group with the average total skill set needed for each group and the missing skill penalty of each group is added. Missing skill penalty is incurred due to not satisfying all the constraints such as non-presence of all the skills in a group. The skill rating allows better selection of members in a software engineering course. The results discussed in this paper are from 5 courses of one university.	Project Based Learning; particle swarm optimization; genetic algorithm;skill based; invasive weed optimization; firefly algorithm	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8789987	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Improving Multidisciplinary Understanding Through Interdisciplinary Project-based Learning in a First-Year Orientation Course	10.1109/FIE44824.2020.9274096	This is an Innovate Practice Full Paper. Creating modern systems with tightly integrated sub-systems relies heavily on multidisciplinary cooperation. Establishing an early value for other areas of expertise is crucial to encouraging later collaborations. This paper discusses a new first-term orientation course in Electrical and Computer Engineering at Oregon State University that is primarily taken by students pursuing a degree in Electrical and Computer Engineering. This course emphasizes collaboration and the importance of a multidisciplinary approach in engineering. The 10-week course contains engineering skills, tools, and concepts from three disciplines of engineering: Computer Science, Electrical & Computer Engineering, and Mechanical Engineering. Materials focus on how each discipline supports the other disciplines in modern engineering. Students attend one, one-hour lecture and two, two-hour labs per week. The lecture covers general engineering concepts including engineering process, design, and tools/skills. Student engineers work in teams of three, with each student focusing on a different engineering discipline. Teams design, implement, and improve on a competitive robotic project. Assessment using student surveys shows a 13% higher self-reported ability to recognize and avoid personal and engineering discipline bias from students enrolled in the new course when compared to students in the traditional course. This higher assessment value has a confidence interval of p=.005 using a two-tail T-test. Using student surveys and assignments, additional preliminary improvements were seen in student's ability to identify the need of another engineer/engineering profession to complete a portion of a project and understanding of other majors.	lab;first year;multidisciplinary; self-efficacy;interdisciplinary; collaborative	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9274096	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Comparing Team Evaluation Software (Team+ and CATME)	10.1109/FIE56618.2022.9962624	The first-year program at Michigan Technological University emphasizes an active, collaborative learning environment. Students are grouped into teams of 3-5 students to work on class activities and projects. The success of this program relies on the students learning to work together and numerous activities in the class are designed to help build these teamwork skills. For example, teams are expected to build a team contract at the beginning of the semester and provide formative and summative feedback to each team member in the form of peer evaluations. In the Fall of 2021, four faculty members at Michigan Technological University evaluated two different teaming systems designed to help enhance these teamwork skills: CATME and Team+. A total of 402 students, in 19 sections of our first-year engineering course participated in this study. Sections were randomly assigned to using either the CATME or Team+ tool. Eight sections (170 students) used the CATME tool and eleven sections (232 students) used Team+. We have historically used the CATME team tool in our courses for peer evaluation. Comparing peer evaluation results with Team+ is one metric we used to measure how our first-year engineering populations responded to this new teaming software. Additionally, we evaluated the impact both of these tools had on team connectedness and satisfaction as well as participation levels in team development activities throughout the semester. This paper will summarize these overall quantitative metrics as well as the reflections from students and faculty on both teaming systems.	team development;first-year experience	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9962624	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	chance

On combining gamification theory and ABET criteria for teaching and learning engineering	10.1109/FIE.2015.7344111	The main contribution of this paper is the introduction of a continuous improvement cycle for devising teaching scenarios and conducting learning experiences in engineering. The proposed cycle consists of seven steps on which gamification theory and ABET criteria are combined. It arose from the adaptation of a gamification design framework, commonly used in industry, into the specific context of high quality education in engineering. It is formulated at high level. Consequently, it should be useful for practitioners having different requirements and expectations. A developed practice, following the proposed cycle, is presented, discussed and evaluated. In particular, the proposal is applied and exemplified, in a scenario for teaching introductory concepts of computer programming in a first-year course. A digital game was used within a gamified learning experience, as a teaching tool. However, the learning process does not rely solely on the use of the game by itself. Moreover, the devised scenario has a purpose beyond edutainment: contributing to achievement of student outcomes, under a continuous improvement approach, according to ABET. A quantitative and qualitative evaluation of the developed practice was performed. A positive impact on students' emotional engagement and behavior was observed as a result of the evaluation process.	gamification;ABET criteria; teaching;learning;continuous improvement;student outcomes	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7344111	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Collaboration leads to success: A study of the effects of using pair-programming teaching technique on student performance in a Middle Eastern society	10.1109/TALE.2015.7386009	In pair-programming, two developers share a computer to work together on developing one piece of code. To test Pair-programming effects on student performance in a Middle Eastern society where some interaction restrictions are found, we devised an experiment that was carried out over an entire academic year consists of two semesters. The experiment targeted two sections per semester of an advanced computer programming course. The students of one of the sections worked in pairs during the lab sessions, applying pair-programming rules and techniques. The other section had students who worked individually, as it is the norm in most programming labs. Through this experiment we revealed that pair-programming has the potential to increase the students' confidence, their enjoyment of the course, and improved the course's completion rate. In addition, the students in the pair-programming section showed that they were able to individually produce code of better quality than the students in the traditional section.	Pair-programming;Extreme Programming;Agile; Computing Education; Teaching/Learning Methodologies	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7386009	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem avaliar
An Empirical Study on the Impact of Pre-recorded Lectures on Students' Performance in Integral Calculus	10.1109/TALE.2018.8615360	E-learning has become an alternative to traditional classroom learning as information technologies continue to develop at a rather fast pace nowadays. Instructional materials are being made available online with the promise of offering online collaborative learning and discussion as well. Among these e-learning paraphernalia, video-based learning has gained momentum as classroom instructional material especially in mathematics lectures where students are often faced with the difficulty in splitting their attention between trying to understand the content of the lecture and writing down detailed notes. In this study, technology-enhanced video lectures were introduced in Integral calculus. The influence of using video clips as an instructional material to enhance the performance and learning of students was evaluated based from three settings: (1) a classroom setup with live lecture only, (2) a classroom setup with pre-recorded lecture only, and (3) a classroom setup with live lecture and pre-recorded lecture. Analysis includes Paired Samples T-test and ANOVA. Results revealed the significant positive influences of video lectures in the improvement of student performances after comparison of pre-test and posttest scores. Students in the Lecture and Video Group gained the highest posttest scores. Post hoc analysis showed that there is significant difference between the three learning settings.	educational technology; integral calculus;learning mathematics;live lecture;pre-recorded lecture;student performance	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8615360	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Measuring software engineering competencies	10.1109/EDUCON.2015.7096081	Measuring competencies may serve as a feedback mechanism as well as a judgment device for a lecturer. As measuring every competency from a catalogue of competencies is not very viable, the to-be-measured competencies are grouped in competency profiles. Further, assessment practices are shown and applied to a course in a study program. A discussion of useful practices concludes this contribution.	Competency Profiles; Assessment Practices; Evaluation of Didactical Methods	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7096081	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab

Metrics Driven Research Collaboration: Focusing on Common Project Goals Continuously	10.1109/SER-IP.2017..6	Research collaborations provide opportunities for both practitioners and researchers: practitioners need solutions for difficult business challenges and researchers are looking for hard problems to solve and publish. Nevertheless, research collaborations carry the risk that practitioners focus on quick solutions too much and that researchers tackle theoretical problems, resulting in products which do not fulfill the project requirements. In this paper we introduce an approach extending the ideas of agile and lean software development. It helps practitioners and researchers keep track of their common research collaboration goal: a scientifically enriched software product which fulfills the needs of the practitioner's business model. This approach gives first-class status to application-oriented metrics that measure progress and success of a research collaboration continuously. Those metrics are derived from the collaboration requirements and help to focus on a commonly defined goal. An appropriate tool set evaluates and visualizes those metrics with minimal effort, and all participants will be pushed to focus on their tasks with appropriate effort. Thus project status, challenges and progress are transparent to all research collaboration members at any time.	Research Best Practices; Research Collaboration Management; Metrics; Lean Software Development	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7964364	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	bom
Developing and evaluating active learning classroom experiences with tablet PCs and slate devices: Half-day tutorial	10.1109/FIE.2014.7043987	Tablet PCs use their inherent ability to accept electronic ink (e-ink) and touch gesture input to enable users to interact with the device in a more natural way. This is especially important in learning environments where the user needs to focus on subject material rather than on the device used to record or store the subject information. Using Tablet PCs and slate devices, instructors are able to increase their effectiveness by making more dynamic presentations and by incorporating active exercises into their classroom environments. Tablet PCs also enable better and more natural note-taking by students and easier after-class review of course material and notes. Further, Tablet PCs facilitate better interaction with persons participating in classroom sessions from remote locations since they easily involve students exchanging visual descriptions of concepts with the instructor and the rest of the class. Several software packages are available to support the pedagogical needs of the university classroom as well as typical group collaborative environments. Classroom Presenter, DyKnow, WriteOn, LectureTools, and MS OneNote with the Interactive Classroom and Math Add in are examples of some of the packages that provide excellent classroom capabilities. These packages allow for a highly interactive environment with both teacher-student and student-student bi-direction real-time interaction. See www.ee.vt.edu/~igtront/tabletpc/ to download tablet PC software. Electronic textbook frameworks like VText are being developed to allow students to have an electronic textbook on their tablet or slate devices. This workshop will also explore the use of these frameworks and how they may be used to enhance student learning practices. In this hands-on tutorial faculty will receive an introduction to the use of Classroom Presenter, OneNote, Interactive Classroom, VText, VectorPad, LectureTools, and PDF Annotator. We will provide sufficient instruction for faculty to have a basic competency with the technology. Most importantly, we will show faculty various pedagogical practices that we have found helpful in using these technology tools in the classroom over the past seven years. Active learning exercises for various disciplines will be emphasized. Faculty will be tasked with developing short active learning exercises starting from the development of goals for the exercise, through the desired student interaction, and ending with the exercise assessment and improvement strategy. These active learning exercises will be targeted to students who are expected to be in the classroom as well as those who may be taking the course at extended campus locations. Exercises will be determined by the individual faculty member's disciplinary interests.	engagement;tablet PC; electronic ink;evaluation; active learning	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7043987	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Data Governance Education: Preparing Systems Engineering Students for Current Organizational Needs	10.1109/AmiTIC62658.2024.10747618	This study details the design and implementation of a Data Governance course using the ADDIE model and the Brightspace platform. The course aimed to develop data management competencies in systems engineering students through a blend of face-to-face and virtual scenarios and a participatory team-based methodology. Various instructional resources such as videos, readings, images, hypertext, and gamification tools catered to different learning styles, enriching the educational experience. International lectures and collaborative activities, like conceptual map creation, provided a global and practical perspective essential for understanding data governance. Continuous assessment, guided by Quality Matters™ Rubric Standards, ensured learning quality and facilitated course improvements. The Universidad Cooperativa de Colombia's Competency Evaluation System aligned evaluation activities with national and international standards. The Data Governance course successfully met its objectives, equipping students with the necessary tools and knowledge to address data management challenges in organizations. The course's structured instructional design and diverse resources were key to its success, underscoring the importance of adapting education to current needs in systems engineering.	Data Governance; Instructional Design; Blended Learning; Competency Development	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10747618	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software

Authentic Assessment of Programme Learning Outcomes in Infocomm Technology	10.1109 /TALE56641. 2023.10398340	This paper focuses on the assessment of Programme Learning Outcomes (PLOs) in the context of Infocomm Technology (ICT) programmes, aiming to align these outcomes with industry expectations. Traditionally, PLOs are assessed internally through assignments and examinations, but to ensure graduates' future employability, it is crucial to incorporate authentic assessments conducted by the industry. To achieve this, our ICT programs at Singapore Institute of Technology (SIT) adopt an Applied Learning pedagogy, integrating industry placements and projects. By allowing industry professionals to directly observe and evaluate students' performances, trust is established in SIT's assessment of PLO attainment. These evaluations provide valuable feedback on students' progress towards industry-related PLOs, enabling the refinement and realignment of educational programmes to meet industry expectations. This collaborative process fosters mutual trust between academia and industry, ensuring ongoing, authentic evaluations of PLO attainment levels. The work makes the case that feedback on PLO attainment is of great importance to universities as it informs the relevance of specific PLOs to industry, and allows for continuous improvement in curriculum design. Through active collaboration between academia and industry, competent graduates who meet industry expectations can be produced, enhancing educational outcomes. This paper emphasizes the significance of authentic assessments conducted by industry partners and analyses six years of data from this process.	Industries;Education; Collaboration	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10398340	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Relax, It's a Game: Utilising Gamification in Learning Agile Scrum Software Development	10.1109/CIG. 2019.8848104	Agile software development is a collective term for collaborative working based on a set values and principles, which has become the de facto approach for the software industry, resulting in it being an essential part of the Software Engineering (SE) curricula for many computing degree courses. One of the most popular Agile software development approaches is Scrum which is widely adopted by the software industry and university curricula. Learning Agile Scrum is imperative for students not just as the part of the SE module but for use in the development of their final software project during the course. Teaching the Agile Scrum approach in a way that students can effectively employ in their final project requires the use of some additional practical aid, which is always a challenging task for teaching staff. Employing commercial tools may not be suitable due to additional financial cost, time and learning curve for students. This paper proposes an easy and effective Game-Based Learning (GBL) approach for Agile Scrum using Trello. Trello is a web-based app with no learning curve used to design any project in a collaborative environment. It is not a Scrum tool, nevertheless its features can be transmuted into a Scrum tool to be used to develop projects. Using this Trello-based gaming activity, students can learn the Agile Scrum approach as a game not as a complex methodology. This proposed GBL approach has been used for two undergraduate courses for the last four years, demonstrating constant improvement for both courses in their learning and assessment whilst comparing it with the traditional teaching approach for Agile Scrum.	Scrum (Software development);Software;Task analysis;Tools;Games; Education;Collaboration	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8848104	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não avalia
Investigates the Impact of AI-generated Code Tools on Software Readability Code Quality Factor	10.1109 /ACIT62805. 2024.10876897	Artificial Intelligence (AI) has made great strides in various industries, including software development, with tools such as ChatGPT changing the way code is written, maintained and developed. This study investigates the impact of AI-generated code on software quality, focusing on readability, code clarity, complexity, and documentation. Comparing AI-generated code with open-source code from GitHub for three tasks of varying difficulty (easy, medium, and hard), we evaluated key metrics such as cyclomatic complexity (CC), code lines, comment density, code-to-code ratio, and variable names. The results revealed that although both AI-generated and human-generated code can be concise and efficient, code generated by AI tools shows a greater focus on documentation more clearly. AI-generated code especially in complex tasks showed improved readability due to higher comment density and the use of clear variable names. These results show that AI tools such as ChatGPT can enhance code quality, especially in the software industry where readability and comprehensibility are critical.	Readability;AI-Tools;Code Quality;Software development;ChatGPT	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10876897	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab

A Constructionism-Based Integrated Learning Framework to Promoting 21st Century Learners of IT School	10.1109/GWS.2018.8686524	Owing to the significance of 21st-century education, students need to be ready with specific essential skills and competence. Moreover, Thailand is moving forward to Thailand 4.0 in which technology plays a vital role in this transition. In an educational context, students' learning has struggled in the existing curriculums. Students learn each subject independently, while the learning activity does not promote them for innovative and critical thinking; meanwhile, the assignments/projects have not emerged from the industrial application. Furthermore, the instruction of each subject does not present the relationship between them; therefore, the students could not integrate what they learned to construct innovation meaningfully. Based on this perspective, this study endeavor to propose an integrated learning framework for faculty/school of IT to promote students' constructionism, innovative thinking, and 21st-century skills that relate to modern industry. The proposed program designed to integrate instruction and learning across IT disciplines where students could develop novel ideas in the meantime. Industrial issues are used to drive the instructional design and learning activities. Consequently, more meaningful learning and assessment can be improved, while the students' essential skills are equipped. To validate the proposed framework, a focus group with strongly-relevant experts has been conducted online. The findings show the model has been highly accepted on computer disciplines and industrial applications, pedagogy and learning activities, assessments and 21st-century skills dimensions. Moreover, the experts have pointed out that the proposed model not only help preparing the students in IT disciplines for Thailand 4.0 industry but also help utilizing faculty resource effectively.	integrated learning; constructionism;21st century learner;computer Education; engineering education; information technology	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8686524	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Exploring relationship between thinking and learning styles an experimental study towards improving learning of theoretical courses in engineering	10.1109/ICCCI.2015.7218092	Improving student's consistent learning becomes a challenge. In order to improve the learning activities among controlled group of engineering students, a customized instructional intervention was provided using MOODLE educational software. However, many students scored 'below average' in learning performance assessments. This gave the conclusion that mere usage of technology, pedagogy and content knowledge alone doesn't improve the students' learning skill. Hence, the psychological aspect of an individual learner was considered. In this research work, an attempt has been made to identify learners thinking and learning styles in order to map an appropriate learning technology. The overall objective of our hypothesis is to explore the relationship between thinking and learning style.	Brain Dominance;Thinking Style;Learning Style; Cognitive process;Data Analysis;Technologies for Learning	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7218092	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Identifying Student Team Leaders and Social Loafers in a First-Year Engineering Cornerstone Robotics Design Project	10.1109 /FIE43999.2019.9028610	This research to practice work-in-progress paper discusses the potential use of team formation survey responses to predict the development of leaders and social loafers in a first-year engineering team design project. At a large Midwestern university, a robotics cornerstone design project is offered. This project-based and collaborative learning project involves teams designing an autonomous robot. The teams are self-driven and must utilize time and project management skills. To create the teams of four, a team formation survey is administered to the students via the CATME team formation software. Students self-identify levels of prior experience with robotics and technical skills, and levels of preference about leadership, ideas, and details. The instructional staff does not impose specific roles upon team members, but teams are formed so that each team can complete all elements. Anecdotally, this model has allowed for the emergence of both leaders and social loafers within the groups. Students who exhibit leadership qualities keep their teammates on task and schedule, maintain communication and participation, and ensure teammates get help when needed. Students who exhibit characteristics of social loafing, a term used in social psychology, put forth fewer ideas and less effort, require more direction to complete tasks, and do not communicate as well with the team. The absence of leadership or the presence of social loafing can hinder a team's performance and detract from the student experience. Thus, the instructional staff is interested in identifying potential leaders and social loafers on teams early so that appropriate guidance can be given to improve the experience. Throughout the project, students also complete peer evaluations and submit weekly timesheets. This work-in-progress paper presents a methodological plan for analyzing these data to determine if a correlation can be found from specific responses on the team formation survey to student team performance.	first-year engineering; teamwork;leadership;social loafing;mixed methods research	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9028610	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software

Active Learning Explored in Open Elective Course: Internet of Things (IoT)	10.1109/T4E.2016.012	There has been a tremendous change in the processing, networking and communication since last live decades, giving rise to a new research era which includes Internet of things (IoT) that helps to connect different devices, sensors and people. The research thinking in IoT is bringing a change in the life style of the society. As many of the developing countries are involved in construction of smart cities, there arises a need to educate current generation engineers to get knowledge of IoT. To cater this, an open elective IoT has been introduced at eighth semester by Computer Science & Engineering Under Graduate (UG) program for circuit branch students. This paper discusses the challenges and experiences of introducing IoT as an open elective course. The first challenge in offering this course is identifying the content of the course, at what level the course needs to be introduced, since both hardware and software components are involved in IoT. Second challenge is involving students in learning process as it is not only theory based and different knowledge level students are part of this course. To address these challenges we followed activity based approach for teaching and learning this course. Various real-world problems are identified, and assigned to different teams consisting of four students. Outcome based evaluation is followed to assess the group activity. The author's observations indicate that the activity based learning addresses graduate attributes of UG program, such as Design/Development of solutions, Modern tool usage, Engineer and society and Life-long learning. The average attainment of the mentioned graduate attributes is 79.18% for the course in continuous internal assessment.	IoT projects;Smart city; Arduino;Raspberry Pi;Django framework	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7814787	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	nao tem colab
How can we find out what makes a good requirements engineer in the age of digitalization?	10.1109/EDUCON.2017.7942853	Good requirements are commonly viewed as a key success factor for IT (and non-IT) projects, but still there seems to be insufficient insight into which competences requirements engineers need to have these days. Digitalization is likely to pose new challenges to requirements engineering. Chances are that digitalization will change the competences that are necessary for successful requirements engineering. This paper proposes a research design that will be used for clarifying which competences requirements engineers need nowadays and how these competences change due to digitalization. To that end, qualitative and quantitative research methods will be combined for developing a comprehensive competence profile for requirements engineering on a scientific basis. The resulting competence profile constitutes a starting point for devising competence-oriented learning settings. Thus, our research contributes to a better understanding of competences for requirements engineering and improves education of future requirements engineers, in particular for coping with challenges posed by digitalization.	requirements engineering; competence;competence profile;digitalization; education;didactics	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7942853	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
Evidence-based re-design of an introductory course "programming in C"	10.1109/FIE.2016.7757492	This paper describes the step-wise re-design of a traditional introductory programming course into a blended learning course. By combining lectures with an online programming environment, short instructional videos, and Tutorial-worksheets, we intend to increase student learning and help students develop the ability to write software. To ensure a successful revision of the course, student learning is closely monitored. The course is changed in separate steps spread over several semesters. By administering a German translation of the SCS1 Assessment at each step, the effects of the changes to the course can be analyzed. The translation of the SCS1 and the data gathering process are described and preliminary data on student learning in the course are shown.	Programming profession; Videos;Software;Electronic learning;Electronic mail	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7757492	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Investigating the Potential of VR in Language Education: A Study of Cybersickness and Presence Metrics	10.1109/ICEIT61397.2024.10540709	This study highlights the vital importance of assessing the Simulator Sickness Questionnaire and presence measures as virtual reality (VR) incorporation into language teaching gains popularity. To address user discomfort, which prevents efficient learning in VR environments, the measurement of SSQ becomes crucial. Additionally, evaluating presence metrics is essential to determine the level of engagement and immersion, both crucial for rich language learning experiences. This paper designs a VR-based Chinese language application and proposes a thorough test technique aimed at systematically analyzing SSQ and presence measures. Subjective tests and data analysis were carried out to highlight the significance of addressing user discomfort in VR language education. The results of this study shed light on the difficulties posed by user discomfort in VR language learning and offer insightful advice on how to improve VR language learning applications. Furthermore, the outcome of the research explores "VR-based language education," "inclusive language learning platforms," and "cross-cultural communication," highlighting the potential for VR to facilitate language learning across diverse cultural backgrounds. Overall, the analysis results contribute to the enrichment of language learning experiences in the virtual realm and underscore the need for continued exploration and improvement in this field.	Virtual Reality (VR); Language education; Simulator Sickness Questionnaire (SSQ); presence metrics;VR-based Chinese language education	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10540709	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab

The Use of Tcad Simulations in Semiconductor Devices Teaching	10.1109 /TREET50959. 2020.9189752	Semiconductor devices have come a long way since the invention of the point contact transistor in 1947. These tiny devices transform and shape our lives and will continue to do so in ways we have yet to discover. Skills and knowledge in semiconductor devices are therefore essential for the development of a more sustainable world. Nevertheless, the ways we teach semiconductor devices are still rooted in 20th century textbooks and methods. Learning methods and materials therefore need to be updated so that students learn in ways that are appropriate for the global, dynamic and transnational environments in which they will work. Our methodology relied on using modern Technology CAD (TCAD) device simulations to revolutionize the teaching of semiconductor devices. Based on student responses, we believe that our methodology will enhance student employability and encourage student understanding of advanced semiconductor concepts, which are required for managing the global sustainability challenges. We demonstrate how the application of state-of-the art simulation and visualization CAD tools can be used to teach undergraduate students how to understand the basic principles of key electronic devices. We provide examples of teaching materials and assessment exercises that were used to assist student learning of semiconductor devices within a transnational education (TNE) programmed. Moreover, we believe that exposing students to modern industry software tools will help embed skills development and employability.	TCAD;simulations; Sentaurus;teaching	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9189752	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
QuESo a quality model for open source software ecosystems		Open source software has witnessed an exponential growth in the last two decades and it is playing an increasingly important role in many companies and organizations leading to the formation of open source software ecosystems. In this paper we present a quality model that will allow the evaluation of those ecosystems in terms of their relevant quality characteristics such as health or activeness. To design this quality model we started by analysing the quality measures found during the execution of a systematic literature review on open source software ecosystems and, then, we classified and reorganized the set of measures in order to build a solid quality model.	Quality Model;Software Ecosystem;Quality Measures;Open Source Software	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7293864	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
Hardware-software synergy for profiling an interdisciplinary computer science engineers	10.1109 /EDUCON. 2015.7096049	Courses of computer science undergraduate studies are usually classified in two main groups: core and elective courses. The former are mandatory and students must pass them all so they can achieve Bachelor degree. The number of the latter is usually several times greater than the number that a student should select. This challenges the student which elective courses to select. Some elective courses have prerequisites, so the student has to pass other (elective) course(s), while for many others the student can be enrolled in without any prerequisites. The main dilemma for the student is whether to enroll in either more tightly coupled elective courses, or more loosely coupled elective courses. Choosing the former, the student will be directed in more specific areas of computer science. However, there are students that would like to learn broad areas of computer science. This paper focuses on the emerged group of students that select interdisciplinary courses. The experience presented in this paper shows that these students enroll into three completely divergent courses: Microprocessors and Microcontrollers, Software Architecture and Design and Human-Computer Interaction. The paper presents the examples of interdisciplinary projects completed by these students. These complex projects are proposed in the Human Computer Interaction course for the students that have already successfully taken the Microprocessors and Microcontrollers and/or Software Architecture and Design courses. Some students have accepted the challenges to work on the interdisciplinary projects, which resulted in defining and finishing various diploma theses that integrate knowledge areas of two or even all of the three courses.	interdisciplinary;computer science;HCI;hardware;design patterns	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7096049	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
Applying Additive Manufacturing to Engineering Education	10.1109 /TELECOM596 29. 2023.10409762	This paper outlines the incorporation of education and training in digital fabrication and material processing within a master's engineering program, involving a group of 20 students. The program utilized additive manufacturing, specifically 3D printing, to provide students with practical knowledge in part design, manufacturing, and performance assessment. The study focused on fused deposition modeling (FDM) for the fabrication of a robotic arm, where students evaluated the performance of its components. The installation of drive motors and provision of relevant software were also integral parts of the study. A survey conducted before and after the course aimed to track the learning experience and obtain feedback from participating students. The findings showed that incorporating digital production, self-directed learning, and peer collaboration had a notable positive effect on engagement and learning outcomes.	digital manufacturing; engineering education;design innovation;additive manufacturing	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10409762	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software

Teaching Devices and Controls for Computer Engineering and Systems Students using Arduino and MATLAB/Simulink	10.1109/ICCA.2018.8444192	Devices and Controls is a core course for Computer Engineering and Systems students at the Institute of Technology, University of Washington, Tacoma. As the only control course of the CES curriculum, it has been designed to bridge the gap between system theories and engineering design/applications. It uses software and hardware tools available for control education including Arduino Mega 2560, MATLAB and the Simulink Support Package for Arduino Hardware. In addition to four-hour lectures in the classroom, students also take two-hour lab each week, and complete a small course project by the end of quarter. In Autumn 2017, both the course evaluation and the ABET indirect assessment results show that students are satisfied with their learning experience, and in particular, the hands-on experience obtained from labs and the project.	Matlab;Control systems; Education;Hardware; Software packages;Tools	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8444192	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
20 Years of EPICS at Butler University: Experiences and Lessons Learned	10.1109 /FIE58773.2023.10343064	This research-to-practice full paper discusses experiences and lessons learned from our EPICS@BUTLER (Engineering Projects in Community Service at Butler) program. The program, housed within the department of Computer Science and Software Engineering, is part of a college of Liberal Arts and Sciences and serves a diverse population of students with multi-disciplinary backgrounds. The EPICS curriculum is driven by a team-based service-learning pedagogical model. EPICS teams learn how to work together effectively while addressing the immediate IT needs of our non-profit partner clients, navigating their budgetary restrictions, and coping with any lack of existing IT infrastructure. During the 2020/2021 academic year, we launched an empirical study to review and assess EPICS@BUTLER. The study's main goal was to learn from the past 20 years of running the EPICS program by soliciting input from all parties involved. We aimed to improve and expand our service-learning model within an LAS context. More specifically, this study included surveying alumni and current undergraduate students in order to understand the successes and areas of potential improvement within our program. In addition, we conducted one-on-one interviews with our community non-profit partners as well as volunteer team mentors to assess the program's effectiveness and community impact. Based on the empirical data we gathered and analyzed, we discuss how the existing curriculum is effective at providing fulfilling experiences which help our alumni secure jobs after graduation. In addition, we found that the practice of allowing supervised teams to navigate their own EPICS projects helps them improve their professional maturity and interpersonal skills. In summary, this paper discusses an empirical study and aims to leverage the results gathered from our surveys and interviews in order to present a plan for continuous improvement and modernization of our on-going EPICS program. In closing, our paper describes a concise roadmap and offers practical recommendations for implementing a similar EPICS program at other potentially interested academic institutions.	Service-Learning;EPICS; Software Engineering;Course assessment;Teamwork	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10343064	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	chance
Social-Communication Web Technologies in the Higher Education as Means of Knowledge Transfer	10.1109/STC-CSIT.2019.8929753	The presented research deals with an expert scientific and pedagogical assessment of the factors of the transition from information and communication technology Web 2.0 to Web 3.0, which is decisive for the author's stated more global task of scientific research, namely, the computerization effect of the knowledge essence in terms of scientific and pedagogical conditions, their distribution, generation and effective assimilation by participants. In this context, the pedagogical trend is clearly followed - the development of "machine pedagogy" as the theory and practice of knowledge acquisition by computers and computer-based network entities. As modern and common platforms where one can observe the emergence of new trends, the author highlights wikis, blogs and forums as existing tools for network sharing of knowledge and types of professional competence with the maximum possible involvement of target groups of professional-oriented higher education institution, which is a prerequisite for reforming and development of new standards of higher education in Ukraine.	computer-based communications;computer-based training;knowledge-based society;web technologies;social networking communications; e-learning;virtual learning classes	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8929753	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não avalia

Metaverse to Enhance Experimental Learning in Higher Education	10.1109 /ICITR64794. 2024.10857777	The rapid growth of technology has resulted in innovative methods to improve education, and traditional learning has evolved. The purpose of this study is to explore how the education sector can utilise the ecosystem of the metaverse to improve 21st-century skills. It emphasises critical thinking, problem-solving, and collaborative information exchange in immersive and interactive learning spaces. The concept of the Metaverse was first introduced in American writer Neal Stephenson's science fiction novel Snow Crash in 1992. In Snow Crash, the characters build into symbols and interact in the Metaverse, a three-dimensional (3D) virtual world. [1] The metaverse refers to a virtual reality existing beyond reality. It is a compound word of "meta," meaning transcendence and virtuality, and "universe," meaning world and universe. The term "digitized earth" refers to a new world created by digital media like smartphones and the internet. The metaverse is a collection of developing virtual and expanded reality technologies that will provide a more vivid experience than the current internet. [2] The study aims to discover the possibility of using the metaverse to achieve experiential learning in education, to facilitate learning by fostering learners' cognitive, behavioural, and sociocultural engagement with the subject matter in the metaverse, and to explore the readiness of learners, teachers, and stakeholders to integrate this innovative system into the higher education. The literature review forms the basis for developing the methodology's conceptual framework and the hypotheses. This systematic investigation incorporates a mixed research approach, including quantitative and qualitative approaches to develop a model for education ecosystems to create a simulated education platform for a complex subject. A list of questions was given to selected students to find out whether students find out where metaverse has enhanced students' experimental learning and its effect on their learning distributed approach was used as the quantitative approach. Participant observations and focus group interviews have been used as the qualitative approaches. Thematic analysis has been incorporated to analyse qualitative data.	Metaverse;Experiential Learning;Digital Education; 21st century skills	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10857777	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	só porque quero ler
An event detection approach for identifying learning evidence in collaborative virtual environments	10.1109/CEEC. 2016.7835886	3D virtual environments support collaborative learning through connecting users in real-time allowing them to accomplish learning tasks together, in addition they enhance the students' exploration, engagement, and interactivity. However, collecting learning evidence to evaluate students in these environments has many difficulties. Therefore, the intention of this paper is to describe our approach for assessing student's learning within collaborative groups in 3D virtual worlds (VWs). It combines a computational mechanism that integrates software agents and natural agents (users) with an ontology approach that supports the identification of learning evidence from collaborative activities that mimics classroom observation. The software agents track the users and collects different actions, clicks, and events to evaluate the quantity of interactions, while the natural agents perform peer evaluations of the students to assess the quality of their performance. The aim is that such a computational model can support more in-depth assessment of learning activities in 3D spaces.	E-learning;3D Virtual Worlds; Assessment;Collaborative Learning;Learning Evidence; Software Agents;Natural Agents;Ontology	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7835886	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não avalia
Virtual Field Trip of the Central Heating and Chiller Plant as an Instructional Tool for Thermodynamics Education	10.1109 /FIE58773. 2023.10343206	This work in progress introduces a framework for developing a virtual tour of the central heating and chiller plant (the Plant) at a university in the US Midwest for teaching and learning Thermodynamics at the campus. Traditionally, this theory-heavy and abstract course is taught using textbooks, lectures, problem solving, and some laboratory experiments. The majority of course content lacks the tangible connections between engineering devices and systems in a close real-world application, making the course challenging and uninteresting for many students. In this project, 360-degree panoramic photos and proper authoring software are employed to render an immersive virtual environment of the Plant that students can visit at any time and from anywhere. The virtual field trip would provide students with tangible insights into thermodynamic and heat transfer processes from over 25 main engineering equipment, devices, and systems at the Plant. Among them are boilers, chillers, a steam turbine, heat exchangers, cooling towers, blowers, and economizers. The follow-up quizzes and assessments are designed to contribute to the course learning outcomes, such as an understanding of phase transitions, thermodynamic properties of steam, and thermal efficiencies of engineering devices. The virtual immersive experiences can help students enhance their learning experiences and engagement in the course's materials without the costs and dangers inherent in a physical tour of the Plant facility. A preliminary result of the virtual tour's evaluation with a group of students and faculty is also included to provide inputs to the next phase of the project.	virtual field trip;360-degree panoramic images;immersive education;Thermodynamics education;mechanical engineering education	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10343206	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software

Personalized Adaptation of Learning Environments	10.1109 /CAOL46282. 2019.9019525	This work is devoted to the development of personalized training systems. A major problem in learning environments is applying the same approach to all students: teaching materials, time for their mastering, and a training program that is designed in the same way for everyone. Although, each student is individual has his own skills, ability to assimilate the material, his preferences and other. Recently, recommendation systems, of which the system of personalized learning is a part, have become widespread in the learning environment. On the one hand, this shift is due to mathematical approaches, such as machine learning and data mining, that are used in such systems while, on the other hand, the requirements of technological standards "validated" by the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C). According to this symbiosis of mathematical methods and advanced technologies, it is possible to implement a system that has several advantages: identifying current skill levels, building individual learning trajectories, tracking progress, and recommending relevant learning material. The conducted research demonstrates how to make learning environment more adaptive to the users according to their knowledge base, behavior, preferences, and abilities. In this research, a model of a learning ecosystem based on the knowledge and skills annotations is presented. This model is a general model of the all life learning. Second, this thesis focuses on the creation of tools for personalized assessment, recommendation, and advising.	personalized learning; adaptive learning;learning environment;Semantic Web; recommendation system; academic advising	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9019525	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
EmoSociograms: An Open-Source Psychometric Tool for the Assessment of Social and Emotional Competencies of Students	10.1109 /FIE58773. 2023.10343023	The positive impact of the development of social and emotional competencies of students is well documented, with benefits being evident in various aspects at individual and classroom level. Based on these findings, multiple social and emotional training programs have been created and combined with methodologies for their proper implementation within classrooms. However, the development of relevant tools to assess these competencies has not followed a similar pace. The few assessment techniques currently available require extensive expertise from teachers in the area of social and emotional training, making accurate and efficient assessments difficult to achieve. To address this issue and improve the assessment process, we introduce the EmoSociograms psychometric tool, an open-source software designed for easy application by teachers in both in-person and online classrooms. We detail the main components and functionalities of EmoSociograms, along with an evaluation based on its usage in primary and secondary education schools.	psychometric tool;emotional intelligence;school climate; sociometry;sociogram;social and emotional learning	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10343023	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Work-in-Progress— Domain Usefulness Experience (DUX) for LIVE-Tutor Development	10.1109 /TALE54877. 2022.00144	Usefulness is defined as the combination of usability with utility, and can be evaluated in the same ways as usability. A novel set of heuristics for the evaluation of usefulness is applied to a recently minted software domain definition: LIVE-Tutor. These usefulness heuristics are derived and validated according to a slightly modified version of a prescribed methodology for generating domain specific usability heuristics. These modifications, such as pairing associated development guidelines with the heuristic set to define the domain in terms of "how" to best produce applications for it, are suggested enhancements for this and other methodologies. We conducted a pilot user study to evaluate a prototype application built for the target domain by applying the first iteration results. A set of general usability heuristics was used as a control group to compare with the experimental set. This study included an added innovation: integration of evaluation tasks into the application interface to facilitate capture, logging, and reporting of results for immediate analysis. Other session analytics (such as learning-gain) were likewise generated from data logged to the application database, in order to ascertain the pedagogical utility of the application.	HCI;UX;ITS;Heuristic Evaluation;STEM Education; Immersive Learning;Guided Inquiry	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10148514	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
A Case Study in Class User Interface Design of Problem-Based Learning Modeling (UIDPBL)	10.1109 /ECTIDAMTNC ON51128. 2021.9425750	Problem-Based Learning (PBL) is a student oriented learning method that using real-life practical problems to start the learning process in order to encourage problem solving skills. In User Interface Design course, the teaching and learning are not only focus on the theoretical knowledge but also focus on motivating students in soft skills. Therefore, this research purposes a Class User Interface Design of Problem-Based Learning Modeling (UIDPBL) in order to promote the 21st century of 4Cs skills - communication, collaboration, creativity, and critical thinking skills. The proposed model applies the PBL concept to the class User Interface Design. The study is evaluated by both summative assessment and formative assessment. The student learning out come as the final grading and student feedback from a questionnaire at the end of the UIDPBL cycle are taken into account. The results presented that our proposed model, UIDPBL, is able to encourage students to gain the 21st century of 4Cs skills.	Problem-based Learning; Communication skills; Collaboration skills;Creative skills;Critical thinking skills	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9425750	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	quero ler

How Far Are We? The Triumphs and Trials of Generative AI in Learning Software Engineering	10.1145/3597503.3639201	Conversational Generative AI (convo-genAI) is revolutionizing Software Engineering (SE) as engineers and academics embrace this technology in their work. However, there is a gap in understanding the current potential and pitfalls of this technology, specifically in supporting students in SE tasks. In this work, we evaluate through a between-subjects study (N=22) the effectiveness of ChatGPT, a convo-genAI platform, in assisting students in SE tasks. Our study did not find statistical differences in participants' productivity or self-efficacy when using ChatGPT as compared to traditional resources, but we found significantly increased frustration levels. Our study also revealed 5 distinct faults arising from violations of Human-AI interaction guidelines, which led to 7 different (negative) consequences on participants.	Empirical Study;Software Engineering;Generative AI; ChatGPT	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10549015	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
A Novel Software Reliability Growth Model of Safety-critical Software Considering Fault Severity Classification	10.1109/ICSR48664.2019.8987594	The safety-critical software of Reactor Protection System (RPS) plays a significant role for the safe operation of the nuclear power plant (NPP). However, it also brings challenges both to the reliability analysis of the RPS and to the Probabilistic Risk Assessment of the NPPs. The reliability analysis of safety-critical software is also expected by the nuclear regulation agencies and the software development groups for test evaluation and optimization. The detected faults during the software test process are regarded to have close connection with the software reliability and there have been hundreds of test-based software reliability models. Due to the particularity of its function, the safety-critical software of an NPP is especially sensitive to the faults with higher severity levels which should be paid special attention to. Severity levels of faults are commonly taken into account during software reliability modelling. In this paper, a novel software reliability growth model considering actual severity data was built based on a non-homogeneous Poisson process. Ratio of fatal faults with highest severity level to all accumulated faults was modelled with logistic curve. Then the mean value functions of both fatal and general faults were derived. A belief factor was employed to describe the trend of severity classification. In the end, the test data of a practical project was used to verify this model. The analysis results showed that this model had better prediction effect than Goel-Okumoto model and Inflection S-shaped model even when limited test data were collected. This novel model can be used as a helpful tool to evaluate both the reliability and the release time of the safety-critical software of an NPP.	software reliability growth model;safety-critical software;non-homogeneous Poisson process;fault severity classification;logistic curve	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8987594	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
Enhancing Teaching Methods on Embedded Systems with Project-Based Learning	10.1109/TALE.2018.8615221	Automation engineering departments must continuously develop their laboratories and pedagogical tools to provide their students with effective study plans. While acquiring state-of-the-art equipment can be financially demanding, an effort is made at the Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU) in Trondheim to provide the students with a hands-on sustainable experience. A strategy that consists of adopting low-cost commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) components for learning purposes is selected. This combines both industry-standard automation controllers, such as Programmable Logic Controller (PLC) technology, as well as novel microcontrollers designed for use in embedded systems education. Specifically, the micro: bit microcontroller based on the nRF51822 system-on-chip (SoC) and designed by the British Broadcasting Corporation (BBC) is adopted. This choice is supported by an agreement between NTNU and the Norwegian company Nordic Semiconductor, which produces the nRF51822 SoC. This paper proposes a novel organisation of the embedded systems module for the engineering cybernetics education curriculum. Students are engaged in both a series of theoretical lectures as well as practical and highly-involving laboratory group projects. The course organisation and main topics as well as result analysis of student surveys are discussed. The survey results indicate that the course organisation and topics are effective for the students.	embedded systems; education;programming; micro:bit	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8615221	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab

Towards a consensus of expected Student-Advisor responsibilities in Engineering Capstone Projects	10.1109/EDUCON54358. 2023.10125274	To deal with the complexity of today's engineering demands, leading universities intend to investigate educational advances and facilities to provide students a creative academic experience that integrates disciplinary knowledge and student transition to the world of the competitive job environment. By tackling a challenging design problem, the capstone project (CP) harnesses creative learning and transfer hands-on abilities into the industrial environment. Effective coaching on the understanding of course objectives aids both advisors and students to properly plan their tasks in CP design. Students and advisors must have a shared understanding of their roles and responsibilities, as well as the extent of independence anticipated from students. This study identifies specific areas in the capstone project that require direct advisor mentoring, aside with other areas in which students are anticipated to work independently, through a questionnaire survey consisting of 206 participants from both segments: advisors and final year engineering students. The survey results outline the discrepancies and consensus of perceptions amongst both segments, provide insights about current CP delivery, and highlight potential modifications that may be considered for improving the delivery of the capstone project where optimum levels of knowledge and skills are obtained by students. The results of this study serve as basis for guiding faculty members about finding the right balance of mentorship and students' independence, as students progress throughout different stages of their final year design capstone projects.	Education;Student Role; Advisor Role;Senior Project; Graduation Project;Capstone Project	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10125274	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Gamifying the Escape from the Engineering Method Prison	10.1109/ICE. 2018.8436340	Software Engineering is an engineering discipline but lacks a solid theoretical foundation. One effort in remedying this situation has been the SEMAT Essence specification. Essence consists of a language for modeling Software Engineering (SE) practices and methods and a kernel containing what its authors describe as being elements that are present in every software development project. In practice, it is a method agnostic project management tool for SE Projects. Using the language of the specification, Essence can be used to model any software development method or practice. Thus, the specification can potentially be applied to any software development context, making it a powerful tool. However, due to the manual work and the learning process involved in modeling practices with Essence, its initial adoption can be tasking for development teams. Due to the importance of project management in SE projects, new project management tools such as Essence are valuable, and facilitating their adoption is consequently important. To tackle this issue in the case of Essence, we present a game-based approach to teaching the use Essence. In this paper, we gamify the learning process by means of an innovative board game. The game is empirically validated in a study involving students from the IT faculty of University of Jyväskylä (n=61). Based on the results, we report the effectiveness of the game-based approach to teaching both Essence and SE project work.	software engineering practices;SEMAT;essence; software engineering methods;project management;serious game; game-based learning	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8436340	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
Developing a Language Learning Application OER	10.1109/TALE. 2018.8615424	University of Nottingham Ningbo China (UNNC) was the first Sino-foreign higher education institution (SmEI) to be established in Mainland China, and has been host to a number of student-staff project partnerships, including in the successful development of Open Education Resources (OERs). This paper reports on the completion of the first phase of an anticipated 2-year student-staff project to develop a language learning application as an OER. It explains the history and context of UNNC and the project, and discusses some of the software engineering processes completed to date. The work completed so far is described and reflected upon, and the future work and impact discussed.	open educational resources (OERs);higher education; Sino-foreign higher education;student experience;Students as partners	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8615424	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Requirements engineering education using expert system and role-play training	10.1109/TALE. 2014.7062566	In this paper, we propose a method for use in requirements engineering education in a university, and based on 3 principles. (1) A type of expert system, which accumulates business domain knowledge related to the customer's business field, and answers learners' question on behalf of the customer is necessary. (2) Group-work role-play training is essential to elicit customer's real requirements and analyze them from various points of view. (3) A software agent system to monitor learner's behavior during role-play training, and act as an advisor in giving timely advice to learners is necessary. Learners who have no practical experience in defining requirements may follow a recommended procedure to elicit requirements and analyze them. In order to confirm the effectiveness of the proposed method, we have implemented an exercise for corporate workers and fourth undergraduate students. Requirements modeling skill level of the students was increased to the same skill levels of the corporate workers by using proposed method. The students got to understand the importance of the requirements and get them into shape.	requirements engineering education;role-play training; KAOS	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7062566	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colaboração

An investigation of the team knowledge and team performance of the Chinese engineering students in a senior technical module	10.1109/FIE.2014.7044078	Teamwork is a very important attribute for future engineers. China graduates a large number of engineering graduates every year, so it is necessary to investigate the teamwork knowledge and performance level of the Chinese engineering students, and work out a better mechanism of teamwork teaching for them. This work investigates the team knowledge and team performance of the Chinese engineering students in a Year 3 senior technical module — Software Engineering, in which teamwork skills are one of the course objectives. The test results demonstrated that the declarative knowledge of the Year 3 students on team working increased through the years of learning but it was not successfully transferred into action, the skill based outcome. It was found that the participation rate for teamwork training in the technical module was low, and students focused more on the technical production. It was suggested to include the peer rating of team citizenship with a certain percentage (5–10%) in the final coursework mark, and also a certain percentage for individual contribution (5–10%). This will switch the product oriented to both teamwork and product oriented, and the individual contribution assessment will prevent social loafing and hitchhiking.	Teamwork;technical module; Chinese students;Team Knowledge;Communication Skills	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7044078	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Defining a Software Maintainability Dataset: Collecting	10.1109/ICSME46990.2020.00035	Before controlling the quality of software systems, we need to assess it. In the case of maintainability, this often happens with manual expert reviews. Current automatic approaches have received criticism because their results often do not reflect the opinion of experts or are biased towards a small group of experts. We use the judgments of a significantly larger expert group to create a robust maintainability dataset. In a large scale survey, 70 professionals assessed code from 9 open and closed source Java projects with a combined size of 1.4 million source lines of code. The assessment covers an overall judgment as well as an assessment of several subdimensions of maintainability. Among these subdimensions, we present evidence that understandability is valued the most by the experts. Our analysis also reveals that disagreement between evaluators occurs frequently. Significant dissent was detected in 17% of the cases. To overcome these differences, we present a method to determine a consensus, i.e. the most probable true label. The resulting dataset contains the consensus of the experts for more than 500 Java classes. This corpus can be used to learn precise and practical classifiers for software maintainability.	Software Maintenance; Software Quality;Machine Learning;Software Measurement	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9240684	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
Application of Digital Technologies in Teaching Chinese Garden and Architecture	10.1109/TALE48000.2019.9225886	There are many types of components of Chinese ancient buildings and their structures are complex. The traditional teaching in the aspect of presenting ancient buildings is mainly based on two-dimensional static pictures, which cannot fully present the form of components and the detail connection between components. As a result, the course is boring to learn and the teaching effect is not ideal. The application of digital technology alleviates this problem to some extent, but in spite of the great varieties of digital software, there hasn't been any reasonable application scheme to make it better serve the course teaching. From the perspective of students, this paper chose the software which was the easiest for students to master and combined it with virtual technology. Then on this basis, aiming at teaching obstacles, different teaching strategies were made. Students were invited to test on different teaching methods. Through examinations and questionnaire survey, using SPSS software to analyze test results and survey results, this paper studied the effect of different teaching strategies, based on reasonably come to the digital technology application strategies.	landscape architecture historical preservation; architecture education;virtual reality;digital technology; pedagogical strategy	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9225886	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
Automated Measurement of Competencies and Generation of Feedback in Object-Oriented Programming Courses	10.1109/EDUCON45650.2020.9125323	To overcome the shortage of computer specialists, there is an increased need for correspondent study and training offers, in particular for learning programming. The automated assessment of solutions to programming tasks could relieve teachers of time-consuming corrections and provide individual feedback even in online courses without any personal teacher. The e-assessment system JACK has been successfully applied for more than 12 years up to now, e.g., in a CS1 lecture. However, there are only few solid research results on competencies and competence models for object-oriented programming (OOP), which could be used as a foundation for high-quality feedback.In a joint research project of research projects at two universities, we aim to empirically define competencies for OOP using a mixed-methods approach. In a first step, we performed a qualitative content analysis of source code (sample solutions and students' solutions) and as a result identified a set of suitable competency components that forms the core of further investigations. Semi-structured interviews with learners will be used to identify difficulties and misconceptions of the learners and to adapt the set of competency components. Based on that we will use Item Response Theory (IRT) to develop an automatically evaluable test instrument for the implementation of abstract data types. We will further develop empirically founded and competency-based feedback that can be used in e-assessment systems and MOOCs.	computer science education; object oriented programming; educational technology; electronic learning	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9125323	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab

Scalable Learning Environments for Teaching Cybersecurity Hands-on	10.1109 /FIE49875. 2021.9637180	This Innovative Practice full paper describes a technical innovation for scalable teaching of cybersecurity hands-on classes using interactive learning environments. Hands-on experience significantly improves the practical skills of learners. However, the preparation and delivery of hands-on classes usually do not scale. Teaching even small groups of students requires a substantial effort to prepare the class environment and practical assignments. Further issues are associated with teaching large classes, providing feedback, and analyzing learning gains. We present our research effort and practical experience in designing and using learning environments that scale up hands-on cybersecurity classes. The environments support virtual networks with full-fledged operating systems and devices that emulate realworld systems. The classes are organized as simultaneous training sessions with cybersecurity assignments and learners' assessment. For big classes, with the goal of developing learners' skills and providing formative assessment, we run the environment locally, either in a computer lab or at learners' own desktops or laptops. For classes that exercise the developed skills and feature summative assessment, we use an on-premises cloud environment. Our approach is unique in supporting both types of deployment. The environment is described as code using open and standard formats, defining individual hosts and their networking, configuration of the hosts, and tasks that the students have to solve. The environment can be repeatedly created for different classes on a massive scale or for each student on-demand. Moreover, the approach enables learning analytics and educational data mining of learners' interactions with the environment. These analyses inform the instructor about the student's progress during the class and enable the learner to reflect on a finished training. Thanks to this, we can improve the student class experience and motivation for further learning. Using the presented environments KYPO Cyber Range Platform and Cyber Sandbox Creator, we delivered the classes on-site or remotely for various target groups of learners (K-12, university students, and professional learners). The learners value the realistic nature of the environments that enable exercising theoretical concepts and tools. The instructors value time-efficiency when preparing and deploying the hands-on activities. Engineering and computing educators can freely use our software, which we have released under an open-source license. We also provide detailed documentation and exemplary hands-on training to help other educators adopt our teaching innovations and enable sharing of reusable components within the community.	cybersecurity education; interactive learning environment;sandbox;virtual machines;cyber range; educational data mining; learning analytics;learning technology	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9637180	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
Facilitating learning and startup formation in experience-based courses—A team-centered model	10.1109 /EDUCON4633 2.2021.9454040	Context: This full research paper presents an experience-based course designed around a semester-long external Innovation Bootcamp. Objective: We evaluated the impact of the Innovation Bootcamp on students' learning and startup formations, measuring how it affected students' perceived challenges related to technical skills, soft skills, project management, and startup-formation mindsets. Method: We conducted design-based research comprising questionnaires, interviews, and focus groups with students and stakeholders participating in the Innovation Bootcamp. In total, 44 students answered the questionnaires conducted before and after the Innovation Bootcamps in both academic years. In the second year, 12 students answered the Berkeley Innovation Index questionnaire to measure their innovation mindsets. We also conducted four individual interviews (student cohort 1), four focus group interviews (student cohort 2), and six individual interviews with stakeholders participating in the Innovation Bootcamp in both years. Results: We found that perceptions of challenges regarding soft and project-management skills declined, while perceptions of challenges regarding technical skills did not vary during the course. Students exhibited increased motivation to engage in startup formation following close collaboration with external stakeholders only after developing their first minimum viable product. Contribution: The study's outcomes contribute to validating a new team-centered model that facilitates startup formation in experience-based courses. We also intend to help educators and researchers adopt Innovation Bootcamps in experience-based, software engineering-focused courses.	experience-based course; interdisciplinary course;soft skills;technical skills;project management;bootcamp; external stakeholders	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9454040	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

Gamification in Higher Education Database Courses	10.1109 /MIPRO60963. 2024.10569628	Universities are trying to adapt the education process for students, who may benefit from different approaches to learning. Gamification is an example; it may provide an opportunity for practical testing of the acquired knowledge and valuable feedback on their weaknesses and strengths. With an element of competition, it may further boost students' enthusiasm for learning and their self-confidence. Researchers proposed many ways to implement gamification in the education process. This paper proposes a newly developed information system and gamification model combined with the previously developed Automated Programming Assessment System (APAS) for evaluating SQL solutions at Algebra University. During learning, APAS contributes by providing rich and immediate feedback to students. The first goal is to enhance student engagement during the academic year, and the second goal is to help students who need to reenroll in the course due to their previous failure. To increase their chances, they need to prepare more whenever they are willing to learn, often physically outside the university. The proposed system is used at Algebra University in the Introduction to Databases course with the aim of empowering students, but the benefits could also be significant for the university, which is interested in minimizing the student dropout rate.	gamification;APAS; assessment;automatic evaluation;feedback;partial marks;computer science education;educational method	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10569628	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Classifying Composition of Software Development Team Using Machine Learning Techniques	10.1109 /CENIM56801. 2022.10037407	Software development projects still reportedly have high failure rates. The ineffective composition of the software team has been recognized as the main aspect of the failure of the software project. In this study, a classification model of the composition of an effective software development team was developed. The model developed consists of three predictor variables: personality, role, and gender. Outcome variables to determine team effectiveness are seen in the quality of the team. To measure the quality of the team, two metrics were used: team development level assessment and team dysfunction assessment. The techniques used for classification are logistic regression and decision trees. The experimental results show that the best method is produced by a decision tree with the highest accuracy value of 70%. Therefore, the results conclude that the use of the decision tree method can determine an effective team as software development team.	Team composition;Logistic Regression;Decision Tree Capacity Building	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10037407	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Exploring the Effectiveness and Efficiency of Electronic Testing Methods in Iraqi Higher Education Institutions: An Empirical Investigation	10.1109 /EECSI63442. 2024.10776380	In Iraqi institutions, online education has emerged as an innovative way to conduct examinations and assessments in the wake of the COVID-19 outbreak. The purpose of this study is to gain a deeper understanding of the wider connotations of online evaluation techniques by examining the implementation of digital exams at a technical establishment in Iraq. For the purpose of evaluating their reactions to digital exams, two groups of 532 educators and 5,268 students were analyzed using descriptive statistics and inferential analysis. It appears that a large percentage of teachers (84%) and students (68%) believe the online exams fail to recognize top performers, which results in incorrect results. The online examination system was also viewed favorably by only 20 percent of educators and only 60 percent of pupils. According to the Lakeland Triple Rank Test, both sets of groups provided feedback within the mid-weight range of 1.76-2.54, indicating less disparity and more uniformity among educators. To boost evaluation reliability, a blend of traditional and digital learning methods was suggested to address the widespread dissatisfaction with digital examinations in technical education. For Iraq's technical instruction to be effective and trustworthy, robust infrastructure and extended training are necessary.	Electronic Testing;E-learning;COVID-19 Impact; Higher Education;Technical Education;Assessment Reliability;Blended Learning	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10776380	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab

An Architecture Model of Recommender System for Pedagogical Design Patterns	10.1109 /FIE49875. 2021.9637342	This work in progress research-to-practice paper proposes an architecture model for active learning design pattern retrieval based on the concept of conversational recommender systems (C-RS). In earlier work, we proposed an object-based pedagogical design pattern model to generate abstraction of multiple unique implementations of collaborative active learning practices. This model helped in formalizing the problem-solution pairs that the educators face in collaborative active learning such as students' engagement in teams and class activities, social skill improvement, and assessment issues. Based on this model multiple patterns in different categories were developed through a systematic pattern development cycle combined with deductive elicitation methods and workshops. In this study, we propose an architectural model for an interactive pattern recommendation system. We use NLP models to extract the context of the problem that each pattern addresses. The extracted aspects are combined with the dimensions of each pattern based on attributes of the developed pattern model. The proposed architectural model is based on the model, view controller (MVC) pattern. In this model, the user interacts with the system through the 'view' layer. The 'model' layer stores the pattern language in the form of a graph in which each node of the graph represents one pattern, and the edges denote the relationship between the patterns. The 'controller' handles text analysis by NLP algorithms based on user input. One of the main features of our object-based design pattern model is its emphasis on team attributes by which different dimensions of collaboration in engineering education are addressed. The implementation of the developed architectural model would enable the instructors to identify possible solutions to the pedagogical challenges they face in teaching engineering classes where teamwork is an integrated part of the learning process.	Pedagogical design patterns; MVC pattern;Software Architecture;Recommender systems;NLP;Active learning; Collaborative learning	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9637342	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	nao avalia
Sail Car—An EPS@ISEP 2019 Project	10.1109 /EDUCON4565 0.2020.9125314	This paper provides an overview of the development of a Sail Car within the European Project Semester (EPS), the international multidisciplinary engineering capstone programme offered by the Instituto Superior de Engenharia do Porto (ISEP). The main goal of EPS@ISEP is to offer a project-based educational experience to develop teamwork, communication, interpersonal and problem-solving skills in an international and multidisciplinary set up. The Sail Car team consisted of six Erasmus students, who participated in EPS@ISEP during the spring of 2019. The objective of the project was to design and develop a wind-powered, easy to drive land sailing vehicle. First, the team researched existing commercial solutions and considered the marketing, ethics and sustainability dimensions of the project. Next, based on these studies, specified the full set of requirements, designed the Sailo solution and procured the components and materials required to build a real size proof-of-concept prototype. Finally, the team assembled and tested successfully the prototype. At the end of the semester, the team considered EPS@ISEP a mind-opening opportunity.	Project-based learning; Diversity in Engineering Education;Active and Collaborative Learning; Student-Centred Learning Environments;Land sailing; Wind-propelled; Sustainability;European Project Semester	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9125314	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não avalia
Fuzzy assessment model for operative groups in virtual educational forums	10.1109/SAL. 2015.7237173	This research consisted in applying the Fuzzy COPPE-Cosenza Hierarchy Model to assess student's and group's performance, using virtual discussion forum to achieve an educational task. The work brings up concepts from Pichon-Rivière's Operative Groups technique. It uses the software CQMsg - Messages Classifier and Qualifier for messages assessment and it applies, for the first time in education, COPPE-Cosenza Fuzzy Hierarchy Model, which has been successful in other areas. After analysis, results suggest that COPPE-Cosenza Fuzzy Hierarchy Model may support formative assessment for educational operative groups using a virtual discussion forum.	forum;fuzzy;assessment; educational;Brazil	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7237173	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
SWitCH: A Reskilling Program in Information Technology	10.1109 /EDUCON4565 0.2020.9125338	There has been an increasing demand for Information and Communication Technology (ICT) specialists, namely software engineers. The two-year SWitCH program was created to lower current unemployment rates, help on fulfilling the existing demand for software engineers from ICT companies and promote the reskilling of existing graduate students to the ICT area. This program consists of a one-year academic post-graduation program followed by a one-year paid internship. This paper introduces the SWitCH program, the current approach and post-graduation methodology, its comparison with similar approaches and its results so far.	STEM;information technology (IT);information and communication technology (ICT);reskilling program;post-graduation	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9125338	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não avalia
Design and implementation of a module in Smart Systems how to train engineering students in collaboration	10.1109/TALE. 2014.7062589	Effective collaboration between engineers from different branches of engineering, such as computer and electronics engineering is a skill that requires training. Most engineers, do to some degree master this skill. Doing it effectively and as an integral part of ones work is not easy. In order to better prepare engineering students for their professional career, a module in Smart Systems is designed. This modules offers, in addition to the technical learning objectives, also to give the students training in effective collaboration with their peers from other disciplines.	Engineering education;cross-discipline;project work	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7062589	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software

Distance learning method for modern youth promotion and involvement in independent scientific researches	10.1109/DSMP.2016.7583557	New information, telecommunication technologies contribute to the optimization in the management of studies. This paper is devoted to the implementation of innovative approaches to improving the curriculum of higher education. The method of finding and attracting students including girls for scientific and practical work through and their participation at team competitions and joint Interuniversity scientific-practical projects are proposed. This work has considered a problem of distance education and involvement in her adaptive learning system. Improving scientific literacy of students by finding innovative solutions to address the problems of projects are proposed. Simplify the process of obtaining a scientific career for interuniversity projects participants. The questions of mathematical models of processes of distance education (remote training) are highlighted in this article. Creation of the integrated net oriented informational-educational environment is based on them. The indicated questions are actual in connection with implantation of technologies of distance learning and inextricably related with didactic and methodological aspects of the educational process.	information technology;data mining;Interuniversity scientific-practical projects; distance learning;distance education;e-learning; information and communications technology; electronic textbook;virtual learning environment; integrated net oriented informational-educational environment;scientific career; interuniversity projects participants	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7583557	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Design of Intelligent Evaluation System of Environment Art Work Coordination for Education and Teaching Process	10.1109/ACAIT60137.2023.10528480	In order to solve the problem of insufficient coordination of knowledge points in environment art works caused by low efficiency and strong randomness of automatic paper generation in the traditional environment art work online examination system, an environment art work coordination intelligent paper generation and evaluation system based on knowledge graph and improved genetic algorithm is proposed. First of all, a method based on exam point knowledge graph is used for the retrieval of multiple keywords. Then, an improved genetic algorithm is used to automatically generate test papers and optimize knowledge points. Finally, conduct test question management and online exam module design to achieve coordination intelligent evaluation of online examination and environment art works. In the three experiments of generating paper, the maximum number of program iterations and maximum time of generating paper of the improved genetic paper generation algorithm are 137 and 43 seconds, respectively. The average success rate of this algorithm for paper generation is 96.19%, which is higher than that of the particle swarm algorithm. In addition, the paper generation time of the improved genetic paper generation algorithm is shorter. It shows that the improved algorithm has higher efficiency and quality, and the algorithm has stronger superiority. Based on this algorithm, it can realize automatic paper generation and coordination in the online examination of environmental art work, and meet the requirements of software system design.	environment art work; coordination intelligent evaluation;automatic paper generation;improved genetic algorithm;online examination	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10528480	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
Exploring LLM Tools Through the Eyes of Industry Experts and Novice Programmers	10.1109/CONISOFT63288.2024.00048	At present, Large Language Models (LLM) and Generative AI models have emerged and impacted industry and society. LLMs are Artificial intelligence (AI) systems designed to understand and generate human language. The rise in popularity of LLM-based systems has motivated research into their use in education, including code generation tools, automated feedback systems, and support for student software projects. The release of ChatGPT™ marked a significant milestone, providing an accessible tool for IA interaction. ChatGPT™ has gained popularity among students, not only in software areas. This study analyzes the perspectives of software engineering students and software engineers on using LLM tools such as ChatGPT™ for software development projects. In this study, we use a questionnaire to analyze different viewpoints and graphics to show the experiment results between these groups. The findings of this study are expected to provide valuable contributions to the understanding of how LLM tools are perceived in the context of software development and their potential implications for educational practices and industry standards.	Programming Education; Generative AI;Large Language Models;Software Engineering	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10795589	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
Teaching Robotics to Undergraduate Computer Science Students: A different approach	10.1109/FIE43999.2019.9028456	This paper explores a novel structure for a course, which we call "Multi-Semester, Multi-Cohort". The course structure is framed around a long-term vision across multiple semesters, with different groups of students each semester. We know that the vision is ambitious and that it will take more than one semester to achieve. As a result, the students working on the project will be different every semester. While this model can be used in a variety of applied disciplines, the course in this instance is in Robotics. This model has some very interesting benefits but raises unique challenges. In this paper we will explain our motivation for using this structure, details of the curriculum and pedagogical approach to it, including admission criteria, course schedule, scaffolding, assessment and report on our experiences, including what went well and what we need to improve.	computer science education; course design;projects; teams;robotics	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9028456	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software

Enterprise architecture of Colombian Higher Education	10.1109/FIE.2015.7344353	Colombian Higher Education Enterprise Architecture is a framework for managing the system-of-systems lifecycle of Higher Education Programs. With this framework is possible to model scenarios about the government as a regulator of Higher Education services, the educational institutions as providers of higher education services and the different business and social sectors, and individual citizens as clients of higher education services. Under this perspective all the stakeholders can participate in the planning, development, transfer, use and control of all the products and services lifecycles of higher education in order to prioritize improvement alternatives and measure progress when it is moving towards excellence in training processes, research, innovation, development and knowledge transfer. CHE2A is a supportive environment for the management of higher education as a public service, which hosts the vision of "Global Coalition Intelligent Network Services (-GIUNC-) to analyze and evaluate systematic, systemic and logistically, the characteristics of processes, outputs and outcomes and risks through key factors such as those proposed by the — GIUNC- itself, Registry of Qualification established by the Ministry of Education of Colombia or other similar factors established by national or international entities, from which, the stakeholders in the Higher Education services, interpret, evaluate, argue, propose, define, plan, implement and measure strategies, tactics and actions for improvement, innovation and development higher education programs. CHE2A is a knowledge management system that is enriched by the experience of organizations and supports innovation in higher education toward a high performance service. The approach set CHE2A does not advocate specific tools, methods or practices, but promotes a new way of thinking, to solve the great challenges of the interactions of technology, power, politics and economics made involves the general study design, complexity and systems engineering. Although these systems often exhibit behaviors systems of complex systems, however, not all complex problems fall within the scope of systems of systems. This article presents the context, perspective and use of CHE2A through its models ontological, epistemological, methodological and regulatory that allow navigate the life cycles of products and services offered by higher education institutions and all those entities benefiting from this results achieved.	Enterprise Architecture;Agile Methods;Simulation;Serious Play;Maturity Models;Quality Assurance	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7344353	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
Impact of Electronic Learning in Rural Universities: A Case of WSU Ibika Campus	10.1109/EDUNINE5367.2.2022.9782318	Electronic learning has become the backbone of institutions of higher learning even those located in rural areas. This research evaluated the impact of electronic learning in rural universities in teaching and learning. The research focused on the usage of e-learning tools, factors that hinder successful usage, and the effects of e-learning in a rural environment. Walter Sisulu University (WSU) was used as the case study in this research. WSU Ibika campus being a campus located in the rural and remote area of Butterworth faces challenges such as shortage of water, poor ICT infrastructure, and poor service delivery. The research adopted a quantitative approach to conduct this research study. A closed-ended questionnaire instrument was used to collect the data. The results showed that the majority of students used learning management systems to conduct assessments while few students used them to access study material and conduct group discussions.	Electronic learning;Higher Learning;Learning Management System;Rural Universities	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9782318	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Distributed Software Development with One Hand Tied Behind the Back: A Course Unit to Experience the Role of Communication in GSD	10.1109/ICGSEW.2016.13	Software development consists to a large extent of human-based processes with continuously increasing demands regarding interdisciplinary team work. Understanding the dynamics of software teams can be seen as highly important to successful project execution. Hence, for future project managers, knowledge about non-technical processes in teams is significant. In this paper, we present a course unit that provides an environment in which students can learn and experience the role of different communication patterns in distributed agile software development. In particular, students gain awareness about the importance of communication by experiencing the impact of limitations of communication channels and the effects on collaboration and team performance. The course unit presented uses the controlled experiment instrument to provide the basic organization of a small software project carried out in virtual teams. We provide a detailed design of the course unit to allow for implementation in further courses. Furthermore, we provide experiences obtained from implementing this course unit with 16 graduate students. We observed students struggling with technical aspects and team coordination in general, while not realizing the importance of communication channels (or their absence). Furthermore, we could show the students that lacking communication protocols impact team coordination and performance regardless of the communication channels used.	experimentation; communication;distributed software development;agile software development	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7579481	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não avalia

Software design for the evaluation of competency based learning in engineering careers Ontological approach for modeling	10.23919 /CISTI49556. 2020.9140954	Nowadays, in engineering careers, it is necessary to carry out activities that allow evaluation of the training process based on professional skills. This implies generating mechanisms that enable the assessment of learning based on quantitative and qualitative criteria from which competence levels of learning are defined. In this sense, it is necessary to arbitrate the means to determine performance of students before real or simulated activities of the future professional context. In this work, authors propose an ontological model as part of the design of a software. It involves the definition of the evaluation activities for the learning process based on competencies in engineering careers, such as definition of level of domain indicators, criteria and evidence determination, weights and scores specification, which accredit professional performance and stimulate the necessary feedback to complete this process. In this way, authors seek to collaborate with professors, academic management staff and other university actors who want to improve the quality of learning through new educational paradigms such as learning by competencies, since carrying out an appropriate evaluation is a task pending in education in general, and in the training of engineers in particular, mainly because of its complexity.	ontology;e-learning;ontology network;professional competencies;curriculum	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9140954	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
An UML class recommender system for software design	10.1109 /AICCSA. 2016.7945659	Recommendation systems provide suggestions for items that are potentially interesting for a user in a given context. The provided recommendations are extracted generally from a huge amount of data collected from several sources of information. Thus a recommendation system requires firstly a pre-treatment step to prepare the data and secondly the application of some techniques such as data mining techniques to handle and extract the knowledge to be recommended to the user from the data. Our contribution consists on proposing a Recommendation System for Software Engineering (RSSE). This system recommends UML classes in the design phase of UML classes diagrams. Our RSSE is composed by two main phases: an off-line phase in which we use a clustering algorithm to partition UML classes collected from several UML classes diagrams based on the semantic relations existing between their characteristics. We have defined a metric that measures the similarity between UML classes. The second is an online phase in which we use the obtained clusters of UML classes to propose suggestions to the user based on elements added to his UML classes diagram under construction. The proposed system is then experimentally evaluated by using a UML classes corpus collected from several UML classes diagrams. The experimental evaluation shows very encouraging ratio of useful recommendations.	pedagogical design patterns; assessment of collaborative activities;e-learning;CSCW; WfMS/ LMS	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7945659	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Approach based on the patterns for assessment of collaborative activities in e-learning	10.1109/ISKO-Maghreb. 2014.7033464	In this paper, we propose an approach based on the patterns designed to assessment of collaborative activities in e-learning. In fact, we used the design patterns in several levels of our approach in order to reach a solution that will define, model and execute of assessment scenarios. Then, through the experience accumulated in the modeling and execution levels of assessment processes, we can enrich the basis patterns to the upper level. Furthermore, in the literature, few methods are used for assessing the individual contribution of the learner in collective or collaborative work. Therefore, our proposal is based mainly around of this problematic, this allows us to lead a systematic approach to design assessment methods in e-learning for assessing individuals in the group or team and therefore this should lead to the assessment of group or team itself as a learning entity.	pedagogical design patterns; assessment of collaborative activities;e-learning;CSCW; WfMS/ LMS	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7033464	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es
A game-based learning system to disseminate kanban concept in engineering context: A case study from risk-based inspection project	10.1109/IEEM. 2017.8290301	Engineering activities (e.g. design, analysis, and assessment) are characterized as knowledge works, which have intangible output/input and processes, as well as invisible work-in-process (WIP). Due to its invisibility, WIP in engineering projects has not received adequate attention, which hinders engineering companies from capturing the challenges associated with WIP management and optimization. The kanban concept has been proven to enable the management and optimization of WIP in the manufacturing industry. This concept has not been prominent in engineering type of activities and projects, due to the belief that it is applicable only to repetitive and physical production. This manuscript proposes the utilization of game-based learning to disseminate the importance of managing and optimizing WIP by applying the kanban concept in engineering projects. A game is developed to serve this purpose. A project related to risk-based inspection (RBI) is selected as the case study for developing the game.	Knowledge work;game-based learning;serious game;lean;kanban; engineering project	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8290301	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab

Piloting of a Computer Science Content Knowledge Test for 10th Grade Students*	10.1109/EDUCON60312.2024.10578675	New (interdisciplinary) Computer Science (CS) subjects in K-12 education have been introduced in recent years. Most of them have educational plans derived from CS Frameworks such as the K-12 CS Framework. To some extent the educational plans have the same core topic areas: data and coding (including data compression and data structures), algorithms (involving variables and software projects), computers and networks (covering topics like logic tables and data transmission) and information society and data security (consisting of collection and processing of personal data and asymmetric encryption). Various Computer Science assessment tests such as the SCS1, MG-CSCI, PSIV1 and the Fairy Assessment have been developed for different age groups. These tests mostly include computational thinking, programming or topics that could be categorized in the first two core topic areas data and coding and algorithms. Hence, the research desideratum was to develop a test specifically for measuring the four core topic areas. These core topic areas are part of the educational plan of the new interdisciplinary subject IMP (Informatics, Mathematics, Physics) for secondary schools in Germany. The test was piloted with 156 (m = 117, f = 37, o = 2) 10th grade students, approximately aged 16 at the end of the lower secondary level. We used the Item-Response-Theory (IRT) to validate the test. This work in progress paper presents translated items and the psychometric evaluation of the piloted test. The contribution for both researchers and educators in the CS education research field is the set of items of the research-based CS test in the four core topic areas for 10th grade students that includes item sets for the areas computers and networks and information society and data security.	Programming;Education; Instruments;Assessment tools	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10578675	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
Working with Industry: Stories of Successful and Failed Research-Industry Collaborations on Empirical Software Engineering	10.1109/CESI.2017.3	The software engineering industry should be the laboratory of much, perhaps most, of the empirical software engineering research. Not only would this create a more realistic context and higher external validity of the empirical research, it would also ease the result transfer and make the results more convincing for the industry. Unfortunately, this is currently not the case. About 90% of software engineering experiments are, for example, conducted with students instead of software professionals as subjects. One reason for the lack of industry studies may be that an efficient and sustainable give-and-take-based collaboration between research and industry can be difficult to establish. The collaborations are frequently fragile, end before the research is completed, and lead to a waste of resources for both the researchers and the industrial partners. This paper presents stories and lessons learned from failed and successful research-industry collaborations. It has a focus on experience with the use of non-traditional collaboration types, such as payment to get industry participation in experiments, trade-based collaboration, lightweight collaborations at industry venues, and network-based collaborations. It is argued that empirical software engineering research should more often consider the use of alternative types of research-industry collaborations than those traditionally chosen.	collaboration;lessons learned;empirical studies	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7968168	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	educação
Social Identity in Software Development	10.1109/CHASE.2019.00033	An agile approach has become very popular over the last decade, which requires good communication and teamwork within teams as well as with outside stakeholders. Therefore, social interaction is central for a software development team to be successful. Such social interactions form social identities and social structures in both teams and organizations. This study investigates possible effects that the social identity of individuals may have on the effectiveness of software development through seven in-depth interviews. The qualitative data from interviews were analyzed and summarized using summative content analysis, and the seven individuals also answered a questionnaire on social identity taken from social psychology research. The qualitative result shows that aspects of social identity affect software developers' behavior, and that we need to build cross-functional stable teams over time also from a pure social identity perspective in addition to the product related aspects to avoid a decreased effectiveness. However, we did not see clear connections to our operationalization of effectiveness in this study, and the quantitative analysis was also inconclusive, but we see value in our suggested method when investigating social identity in software development.	programming;social identity; collective self esteem; effectiveness	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8816974	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	chance

Multi-sector Collaboration for Students of different levels to Learn Digital Technology Skills using Competency Assessment from Learning to Create pieces with a 3D printers for Young Innovators Case Study: MogroWittayakom School	10.1109/iSTEM-Ed62750.2024.10663179	This article is the result of collaboration across various associations to create learning spaces for students in compulsory and optional education as well as living skills. This article provides an example of learning digital technology skills through collaboration, starting with the establishment of an innovation room, followed by instructional activities to explore assessment methods for competency in creating works using a 3D printer tailored for young innovators. By employing rubric-based technology tailored to real-world conditions, it aims to fulfill teachers' expectations for student outcomes. This approach helps students understand and apply a rubric to evaluate and improve their own creations. The demographic involves 20 high school students from MogroWittayakom, selected through purposive sampling. The students participated in a practical performance test, receiving step-by-step training over two days, totaling 12 hours. Upon completing the instruction, students designed and fabricated their projects using Tinkercad software, which were then printed with a 3D printer. The instructor evaluated the students using a rubric-based competency assessment with three scoring levels. The results showed that all 20 participants achieved a high competency level as per the rubric, validating the hypothesis with 100% of the participants meeting the performance criteria.	competency;young innovators;rubric; MogroWittayakom School; collaborative	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10663179	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Evaluation and assessment of effects on exploring mutation testing in programming courses	10.1109/FIE.2015.7344051	Mutation analysis is a testing strategy that consists of using supporting tools to seed artificial faults in the original code of a software under test, generating faulty programs ("mutants") that are supposed to produce incorrect outputs. Novice programmers suffer of a wide range of deficits due to defective training processes. We argue that the incorporation of experiences on mutation testing in programming courses adds valuable knowledge to the learning process. In this paper we evaluate the effects of using mutation testing to improve the learning process of students in programming courses. We present results of experiments and analysis involving undergraduate students. These experiments are the continuation of a previous work in which we raise empirical evidences that the adequate incorporation of mutation testing in programming courses contributes to form an effective environment that fosters learning. To do so, we provide a mutation testing tool to promote the practice of mutation testing by novice programmers. Through practical experiences and several analysis survey we measured the effects of using the mutation testing criterion to teach programming. In addition, we collected the opinion of senior students who already knew mutation testing concepts about their opinion on the usage of mutation concepts to teach novice programmers. Our findings reveal that the effective use of mutation analysis concepts contributes to the learning process, making students see the code as a product under development that is the result of a careful manual coding process which they need for measuring and predicting the effect of each command. The main contributions discussed in this paper are: (1) presenting results of an empirical analysis involving undergraduate students, thus giving us preliminary evidence on the effects of the novel practice; (2) exposing possible practices to explore mutation testing in programming classes, highlighting the limitations and strengths of such strategy; and (3) a mutation testing tool for educational purposes.	mutation testing;experimental study;computer-aided instruction	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7344051	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Speculative Analysis for Quality Assessment of Code Comments	10.1109/ICSE-Companion52605.2021.00132	Previous studies have shown that high-quality code comments assist developers in program comprehension and maintenance tasks. However, the semi-structured nature of comments, unclear conventions for writing good comments, and the lack of quality assessment tools for all aspects of comments make their evaluation and maintenance a non-trivial problem. To achieve high-quality comments, we need a deeper understanding of code comment characteristics and the practices developers follow. In this thesis, we approach the problem of assessing comment quality from three different perspectives: what developers ask about commenting practices, what they write in comments, and how researchers support them in assessing comment quality. Our preliminary findings show that developers embed various kinds of information in class comments across programming languages. Still, they face problems in locating relevant guidelines to write consistent and informative comments, verifying the adherence of their comments to the guidelines, and evaluating the overall state of comment quality. To help developers and researchers in building comment quality assessment tools, we provide: (i) an empirically validated taxonomy of comment convention-related questions from various community forums, (ii) an empirically validated taxonomy of comment information types from various programming languages, (iii) a language-independent approach to automatically identify the information types, and (iv) a comment quality taxonomy prepared from a systematic literature review.	code comments;mining developer sources;developer information needs;comment quality assessment	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9402522	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab

A Machine Learning Approach to Predict Same-Day Discharge after Angiography Procedures	10.1109 /EMBC53108. 2024.10782577	Discharging patients from the hospital to care at home on the same day has been demonstrated to be as safe as overnight stays. The correct selection of patients who may undergo same-day discharge (SDD) is a significant challenge due to the large volume of variables that must be considered. This paper proposes a machine-learning approach to predict SDD after angiography procedures. Data from 3227 patients scheduled for angiography procedures, including information about geographical location, demographic characteristics, pre-existing diseases, and clinical procedure type, were used to train and test machine learning algorithms, such as logistic regression (LR), K-Nearest Neighbor, Naive Bayes, Multilayer Perceptron, and Support Vector Machine (SVM). The target was to predict patients with or without same-day discharge after they received an angiography procedure. Performance metrics, such as accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, learning time, and inference time, were computed for each algorithm. The algorithms with the best performance were LR and SVM, with an F1-score of 0.800 and 0.806, respectively. LR had better behavior than SVM concerning learning and inference time.	angiography procedures; machine learning;same-day discharge	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10782577	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Retracted: An Empirical Study of English Writing Teaching Based on Dynamic Assessment	10.1109 /ICSCSE. 2016.0059	English writing teaching process design directly affect the students' writing level upgrade, this paper presents a dynamic assessment of the English writing teaching mode, in order to verify the superiority of the teaching mode, the design of the teaching experiment based on the experimental class and the control class of different teaching modes, using the social science statistical software of SPSS and statistical theory and empirical based on dynamic assessment of English teaching. The empirical results show that the dynamic assessment model has a good effect on the teaching of English writing, and value of promoting.		https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7825072	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Automatic, Configurable and Partial Assessment of Student SQL Queries with Joins and Groupings	10.23919 /MIPRO52101. 2021.9596680	Many papers exist that research semiautomated or fully-automated assessment of SQL queries in the context of high education, as this approach promises less load on teachers, more consistent assessment across all students and faster feedback to students. Instead of assessment process that results either in all or none marks awarded for a query, high education standards are more in favor of providing partial marks. This, and the fact that there should be an easy way for a teacher to customize assessment rules to adapt them to institution standards, makes assessment process more complex so many currently available tools fall short. This paper presents a newly developed fully-automated assessment model and an information system that implements it system and explores the possibilities of using it for partial assessment in higher education. This assessment model is designed to support complex joins and groupings, making it more applicable for real students' assignments and resulting queries. Students also get the immediate results and a list of found issues with their queries, which is very important for them in process of learning. In this paper, built system is compared with manual assessments of the same student queries and its shows promising results, even for very complex joins and groupings.	SQL;assessment;fully automated;partial marks; configurable assessment process;join;group by;higher education	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9596680	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab es
Automatic Document Classification using Deep Feature Selection and Knowledge Transfer	10.1109 /IRASET48871. 2020.9092256	Documents in an ERP system flow from different sources (customer, supplier, etc.) and can have different layouts, sizes and subjects (invoices, delivery forms, checks, etc.). The classification of these documents is usually done manually before being saved in the ERP system or processed by an Optical Character Recognition (OCR) engine. In this paper, we investigate using different deep convolutional neural networks (CNN) to extract deep features from images of scanned documents. The extracted features are further processed using various machine learning classifiers such as Logistic Regression (LR), K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Support Vector Machine (SVM) and Gaussian Naive Bayes (GNB). Different metrics were used (accuracy, precision, etc.) and examined to compare all models performances, while cross-validation approach at different folds sizes (4, 6, 8 and 10) was used to assess their generalization ability. The effect of dimensionality reduction techniques on overall performances was also explored. The best classification rate was 96.1%, which was achieved by combining LR and the VGG19 model. This very good performance despite the small dataset used (200 images) can allow using this approach in an ERP system as a preprocessing step in document manipulation for ERP users.	ERP;document classification; deep feature selection; machine learning;transfer learning	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9092256	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab

WIP: ChatVis: Enhancing Academic Team Collaboration through WhatsApp Chat Analytics	10.1109 /FIE61694. 2024.10893414	This work in progress research paper describes the development and utilization of ChatVis, a novel tool designed to enhance collaboration and teamwork, key learning outcomes emphasized in engineering and computing curricula by industry employers and accrediting bodies such as the Accreditation Board for Engineering and Technology (ABET). Instructors implement project-based learning to help students develop these skills, often using communication platforms like WhatsApp, Slack, and Discord. Despite the availability of tools supporting teamwork and collaborative learning, a truly non-invasive method for collecting and evaluating interaction and team dynamics remains elusive. ChatVis addresses this gap by enabling instructors to assess team dynamics and individual contributions effectively without disrupting student workflow. Deployed in a C Programming course at a university in Mexico, ChatVis involved 33 students in a mini project, significantly improving student interaction, communication, and engagement. Instructors were able to visualize and provide targeted feedback on student engagement and team dynamics, thereby enhancing the quality of student work. Future work will extend this preliminary study with a comprehensive analysis aimed at determining the statistical significance and broader impacts of ChatVis.	Software Engineering Education;Team Dynamics Quantification;WhatsApp Communication Analysis	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10893414	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Improving Fuzzy Analogy Based Software Development Effort Estimation	10.1109 /APSEC. 2014.46	Analogy-based estimation has recently emerged as a promising technique and a viable alternative to other conventional estimation methods. One of the most important research areas for analogy-based cost estimation is how to predict the effort of software projects when they are described by mixed numerical and categorical data. To address this issue, we have proposed, in an earlier work, a new approach called fuzzy analogy combining the key features of fuzzy logic and analogy-based reasoning. However, fuzzy analogy may only be used when the possible values of the categorical attributes are derived from a numerical domain. The current study aims to extend our former approach to correctly handle categorical data. To this end, the fuzzy k-modes algorithm is used with two initialization techniques. The performance of the proposed approach was compared with that of classical analogy using the International Software Benchmarking Standards Group (ISBSG) dataset. The obtained results show significant improvement in estimation accuracy.	software effort estimation; case-based reasoning;fuzzy logic;fuzzy clustering;mixed dataset	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7091317	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
Novel Machine Learning Approach for Automatic Employees' Soft Skills Assessment: Group Collaboration Analysis Case Study	10.1109 /ICDS53782. 2021.9626760	Machine Learning (ML) based assessment of soft skills is a challenging domain in social computing. In today's enterprises, soft skills are regarded as one of the most crucial components for success. Based on data obtained from internal organizational sources, we evaluated the viability of utilizing ML to assess Group Communication Analysis (GSA) skills. We leveraged Latent Semantic Analysis (LSA) to understand and learn cognitive phenomena extracted from the communication extracted from the issue tracker of several popular open-source projects, with a specific input representation that allows the model to look for contextual cues in consecutive utterances. We looked at the data of 1520 engineers from three open-source software development projects that worked on an internal line of business operational systems. The ML models revealed five interpersonal and intrapersonal socio-cognitive GSA metrics in 10583 utterances and procedures, which were integrated into five clusters that assign socially engaged employee roles. Because there has not been any research on assessing employees' Soft Skills utilizing ML, our proposed method is a first in this field, relying on internal organizational datasets to obtain reliable Soft Skills assessment evaluation.	Machine Learning;HRTech; Soft Skills Assessment; People Analytics	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9626760	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Open source as an innovative approach in computer science education A systematic review of advantages and challenges	10.1109/MITE. 2015.7375330	This paper presents the results of a systematic literature review (SLR) of the advantages and challenges of using open source (OS) in computer science education. The review highlights an innovative approach of requesting students of computer science to become active members of existing OS communities as part of their curriculum. The acquisition of a wide range of skills, increasing student motivation, support for contextual learning and student-centered courses as well as the availability of a wealth of data to inform and support decision-making by educators are the main advantages as identified by the SLR. Similarly, high barriers to entry in OS projects, difficulties related to student support, assessments, grouping of students and choice of an adequate OS project are the potential challenges. In this paper, the advantages and challenges of using OS in an existing framework of a course design and delivery have been discussed in detail. In particular, the potential impact of OS in computer science education curriculum has been explored from the perspective of education providers.	Open source;computer science;computer science education;open academy; ICT;ICT skills	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7375330	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab

Technical projects with social commitment for teaching-learning intervention in STEM students	10.1109 /EDUCON4565 0.2020.9125176	We present a teaching methodology based on active learning that faces new social challenges to obtain better levels of students' motivation and promote their social responsibility. It consists of a project-based learning core that organizes students in teams to design and manufacture autonomy-oriented products capable of assisting people in a dependency situation. We mainly combine open-source software and low-cost machines to make the products. The first experience was implemented in a subject shared by all the 2nd year engineering degrees during the 2018-19 academic year. We programmed a series of short oral presentations to (i) improve students' time management skills, and (ii) receive periodical feedback across the whole semester. Herein, we report the results from the self-assessment and peer evaluation surveys of the first year of this experience. Peer evaluation was incorporated into the subject's final score. Results showed that our methodology could positively influence students' self-perception of their acquired soft-skills and technical knowledge. The high quality of the deliverables, together with the outstanding final ratings and success rates achieved, seem to be related to the extraordinary levels of students' motivation after this experience.	Project-Based Learning; Social-Based Learning; motivation;open-source;self-assessment;peer assessment	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9125176	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
CNN-DBN: Quality Assessment and Optimization of Content-Based Image Retrieval Services	10.1109 /ICSESS52187. 2021.9522341	The quality assessment of image retrieval services can master the quality of retrieval results in real-time, and provide valuable information for users. Therefore, the quality assessment of image retrieval, especially content-based image retrieval(CBIR) services, has attracted the attention of researchers. However, the traditional quality assessment approach of CBIR services had some problems, for example, they ignored the high-level semantics information of the image, used shallow learning models, etc. To address these problems, this paper proposes a quality assessment approach of image retrieval, namely CNN-DBN, it extracts image features by Convolutional Neural Network(CNN) and establishes a quality assessment model using Deep Belief Network(DBN). Based on the quality assessment results, this paper proposes a scheme to optimize the quality of CBIR. To evaluate the performance of this approach, design a set of experiments to verify the performance and practicability of the proposed approach. To a certain extent, it can evaluate the quality of image retrieval and optimize the quality of retrieval results, demonstrate the importance of image retrieval quality assessment for users.	image retrieval;quality assessment;convolution neural network;depth belief network;optimization	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9522341	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
Training App Developers in a Software Studio The Business Nano Challenge Experience	10.1145 /3639474. 3640070	Developing technical (hard) skills and non-technical (soft) skills in students who want to succeed in the mobile application (apps) development market is not trivial. It represents a considerable challenge for educational institutions. A partnership between Pontifícia Universidade Católica do Paraná (PUCPR), and Apple was established to achieve this goal through a software development studio. The environment uses the Challenge Based Learning (CBL) methodology to enable students to develop apps that can succeed in such a competitive market. One of the challenges is the Business Nano Challenge (BNC), a short challenge that focuses not only on the development skills but also on the business aspects. The main goal of this paper is to analyze the results of applying the BNC. Due to the characteristics of the project, the case study research method was chosen. It was carried out using semi-structured interviews with the studio participants. The data was analyzed qualitatively with the support of the Atlas.ti tool. The results show that, during the BNC, the students developed and practiced soft and hard skills, covering the entire app development process, from design to publishing. They also practiced tasks related to publishing the app, such as market search, project design, marketing, advertising, financial resources management, monetization, and post-publication as metrics analysis, monitoring, and optimizing the mobile app. It was possible to identify that the students developed fundamental competencies for the mobile application development market, including technical and non-technical skills and a business vision, essential to succeed in this area.	Software Studio;Business Nano Challenge;Software Engineering Education; Mobile App Development; Challenge Based Learning	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10554729	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Modern E-Learning based Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) as a Part of Teaching Process	10.1109 /ICICT50816. 2021.9358547	All sectors of our society are undergoing modernization, and education is no exception. Schools are slowly beginning to realize that teaching can be simplified with modern technologies that save us time as well as money. One of the main tasks of this article is to clarify the terms related to electronic technologies and their use in the teaching process. These technologies are used mainly in the distance form of study, which requires greater independence and activity of students in the teaching process itself. It is precisely when it comes to distance learning that the word e-learning is most used. The task of every school is to offer the best possible education for its students, and this can only be done with the help of modern achievements.	Information and communications technology (ICT);electronic educational materials;interactive system; distance learning	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9358547	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software

Integrating Site Reliability Engineering Principles with DevSecOps for Enhanced Security Posture	10.1109 /ICISAA62385. 2024.10828869	Organizations have more difficulties in today's digitally-driven environment protecting their software systems against cyberattacks while preserving dependability and effectiveness. In order to improve the security posture of software development and operations, this article investigates the combination of DevSecOps and Site Reliability Engineering (SRE) concepts. While DevSecOps extends DevOps methods to integrate security across the development lifecycle, SRE focuses on automation, scalability, and dependability. Combining these approaches allows firms to create a comprehensive strategy that puts efficiency, security, and dependability first. This article presents practical advice for implementation and provides insights into the synergies between SRE and DevSecOps through a thorough literature study, theoretical framework building, and methodological analysis. The outcomes demonstrate how combining SRE ideas with DevSecOps techniques may have a revolutionary impact by encouraging teamwork, automation, and continuous development. In today's changing digital world, this integrated strategy ultimately helps enterprises to lower the risk of cyber attacks, increase overall system resilience, and proactively detect and remediate security vulnerabilities.	Site Reliability Engineering (SRE);DevSecOps;Security posture;Software development;Cyber threats	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10828869	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Inclusion in computing and engineering education: Perceptions and learning in diagram-based e-learning classes with blind and sighted learners	10.1109/FIE. 2017.8190513	E-learning is a modality of education that has been growing all over the world. However, in computing and engineering education programs, the frequent use of graphical representations creates obstacles to the inclusion of visually impaired learners. Besides, many of the strategies and tools used in traditional lectures are not appropriated in e-learning lectures because of the distance among participants. In this context, this paper presents an evaluation of learners' perceptions during e-learning lectures on software requirements specification using UML/SysML use case models, as well as their associated learning assessment. Visually impaired and sighted learners attended online lectures in real-time with spatial distance. Participants used an external remote communication tool and some features of Model2gether to communicate and coordinate lecture activities. Model2gether was also used for collaborative real-time interaction with use case models. Learners responded a pre-survey and were interviewed prior to the lectures. After the lectures, learning assessment was twofold: by group work and an exam. Their perceptions were gathered through a post-survey and an interview. The quantitative data was statistically analyzed. The results indicate that, with appropriate tool support, it is possible to include visually impaired learners in e-learning activities based on graphical representations. Moreover, the post-survey indicates that the learners did not recognize their colleagues are sighted or not while collaborating using Model2gether.	Unified modeling language; Collaboration;Tools; Computational modeling; Integrated circuit modeling; Libraries;Electronic learning	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8190513	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Artificial Neural Network for STEM-ED in Power Transformer Failure Investigation Based on Power Utility Practice	10.1109/iSTEM-Ed59413. 2023.10305793	This research explores the creation of an educational resource that utilizes STEM principles specifically for teaching computer programming in the field of electrical engineering. The fault analysis simulation program in the research tool integrates the Key Gas and Duval Triangle methods, along with a user-friendly Graphical User Interface. 15 students registered in the computer programming course consisted of the sampling group. The instructional tool had an average score of 4.17 out of 5 famous people which is the highest possible score, in the quality evaluation accomplished by 5 experts. The prepared teaching set satisfied the standard criteria utilizing Meguigans' theory with an effectiveness of 1.1 out of 1. The findings indicated a significant impact on learning performance from the initial assessment to the final assessment, with a significant level of 0.05. Electrical engineering education can be provided effectively with this recently developed teaching and learning tool.	neural network;key gas method;duval triangle method;total dissolved combustible gas;power transformer	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10305793	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software

Team performance assessment and improvement in an agile methodology framework	10.1109/CLEI56649.2022.9959959	Improving the performance of work teams is a key issue for any organization because it has a direct impact on the productivity and quality involved in the generation of its products and/or in the provision of the services it offers. The performance of a team can be increased through improvements in the performance of each of its members or the team as a whole. There are several mechanisms to try to achieve performance improvements, however, for a correct orientation of possible actions, it is necessary to evaluate the current performance of the team and each of its members to highlight possible weaknesses or opportunities for improvement. An improvement process is by nature continuous, changes are incorporated gradually and at the same time, the achievements must be reinforced. Agile methods are closely aligned with improvement performance of teams. For instance, Scrum establishes Retrospective Meetings which are exclusively dedicated to continuous improvement of teamwork. This paper proposes a model for assessment and improvement of team performance within an agile methodological framework. In addition, a support tool that implements the model is presented. The model and its tool have been developed and refined through its application for more than a decade in two software engineering subjects. In these subjects, we apply the Project-Based Learning (PBL) teaching method, according to this the students work as a team throughout the subject in a software development project. Although our proposal has been generated in the academic field, we think that it can also be applied and be useful in an industrial context.	Teamwork;high-performance teams;performance assesment;agile methods.	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9959959	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não avalia
Anomaly Detection for Early Warning in Object-oriented Programming Course	10.1109/TALE52509.2021.9678677	As one mainstream of current software development, Object-oriented programming has become one key course for undergraduate students in Computer Science. Since Object-oriented concepts are difficult to understand for students, small programming exercises are used to train and help the students, and the study performance is evaluated based on the quality of the submitted source code. The common practice of code assessment in programming courses is checking whether the submitted projects pass carefully-designed test cases. However, even some projects pass all test cases, they may have bad software design and do not use the knowledge of Object-oriented programming well, especially in the early stage of courses. Therefore, we propose an anomaly detection approach for early warning in Object-oriented programming courses, which can automatically find the abnormal application of Object-oriented knowledge. In our approach, we conduct static analysis on the code submitted by students. Typical Object-oriented metrics are extracted, and students are divided into two groups by K-means clustering: being good at Object-oriented knowledge or not, and finally detect anomalous students based on the distance from cluster centers. We evaluate our approach on the realistic data sets collected from our Object-oriented programming course, and experimental results show the effectiveness of our method.	Object-oriented Programming;Anomaly Detection;Early Warning; Code Assessment	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9678677	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
Moving from managing enrollment to predicting student success	10.1109/FIE.2017.8190665	We describe the construction and assessment of a plan to foster student success in Computer Science (CS) in response to continued enrollment growth. We examined cross correlations of grades from student transcripts from the past four years to determine what patterns of grades in early classes were indicative of future success. The resulting statistics and visualizations showed that students generally did better in the first class than subsequent classes, suggesting that C grades in the first class might indicate difficulty. We also examined students enrolled in the pre-capstone software engineering course. The analysis showed that no graduating CS major had received a C in both first two programming courses. We examined the data to be sure that the proposal would not diminish the participation of members of underrepresented groups disproportionately. As a result, the CS faculty approved a change in prerequisite for the third course to require that student receive an A or a B in at least one of the first two courses. GPA data was also analyzed and found to be a poor predictor of success in computer science, demonstrating that our previous approach to limiting enrollment was inferior. This new approach has advantages over the previous GPA-based plan, but enrollment management plans risk making college harder for at risk students to succeed in CS. The biggest limitation of this plan is that it is expected to make only a small change in CS enrollment.	enrollment management; retention;Computer Science	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8190665	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software

Semantic Waves: A Strategy for Algorithmic Skills in K-12 Computer Science Education	10.1109 /EDUCON6031 2. 2024.10578899	The objective of this study is to develop and empirically evaluate an educational model that enhances algorithmic thinking - a key element of computational literacy - through the application with the concept of so called semantic waves for advancing K-12 students' digital proficiency. The concept of a semantic wave refers to the process of moving between abstract, theoretical knowledge and concrete, practical examples to create deeper understanding and learning. Considering this, our proposed model in the field of algorithmic thinking is intended to support pre-service computer science teachers and educators in designing instructional processes that are easy to implement and facilitate swift planning and reflection for K-12 computer science education. Initial results indicate promising outcomes but also suggested areas for enhancement. This research furthermore delves into refining the model through the incorporation of notional machines and the computational action approach for improving the training of future computer science teachers and students for the challenges of digital transformation.	Training;Computational modeling;Semantics; Refining;Reflection;Computer science education;Planning	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10578899	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
Using GitHub in the classroom - a collaborative learning experience	10.1109 /SIITME. 2015.7342358	The most important skills employers are looking for in engineering are creativity, ability to work in teams and critical thinking. However the most used teaching methods at universities, based on individual assignments or group projects while do address the creativity, fall back on the critical thinking and even in team work skill. Collaborative learning was long suggested as a good alternative for enhancing these skills and recent evolution in social coding sites and collaborative software development give a new opportunity to employ such teaching method. This paper presents the results of a collaborative learning experiment carried out by using GitHub in laboratory assignments, where the main focus was on the direct interaction of the students on each other's learning process. Results were analyzed in comparison with traditional methods and also perspectives of enhancing the learning experience in the vision of current workforce requirements.	collaborative learning;version control;social coding;GitHub	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7342358	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	nao avalia
A comparative study of languages for model-based systems-of-systems engineering (MBSSE)	10.1109/WAC. 2014.6936160	Teaching model-based systems engineering has become more challenging as research and development has shifted from systems to include systems-of-systems (SoSs). SoSs involve primarily combination of hardware and software, as well as humans and organizations. The need to teach model-based system-of-systems engineering has thus raised the need to determine what the most suitable language for modeling and teaching SoSs is. We developed a new course format, in which groups jointly reverse-engineer and model Web-based information systems in two different modeling languages, UML and OPM, and then individually assess their peers' projects. The goal of this study was to compare UML with OPM as two candidates. We developed and evaluated an online peer assessment tool which students used. About 130 undergraduate students in groups of six divided into teams of three modeled 23 systems in both UML and OPM. They then evaluated, compared, and ranked the clarity & understandability and the completeness of the four models of two systems that their peers had constructed. Findings demonstrate that neither the order of the models assessment nor the assessor gender affected the grading, indicating assessment reliability. We found significant differences in model clarity and understandability in favor of OPM and no differences in completeness between OPM and UML models. These findings validate our approach of teaching both conceptual modeling languages and using peer assessment in large-scale project-based undergraduate information systems engineering courses.	Unified Modeling Language (UML);Object-Process Methodology (OPM);model-based systems engineering (MBSE);model-based systems-of-systems engineering (MBSSE); conceive-design-integrate-operate (CDIO);large scale assessment;project-based learning (PBL);systems engineering education	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=6936160	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
Artificial Intelligence in the Assessment Process of MOOCs using a cloud-computing ecosystem	10.1109 /TALE52509. 2021.9678911	This research shows a flow of open, flexible, and adaptable computational processes to implement a learning assessment solution incorporated into a low-cost Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) platform. It considers the selection of questions made by an Artificial Intelligence (AI) engine, which receives suggestions and decisions from teachers, and which the student receives, as a virtual questionnaire in a mobile application, personalizing their learning needs in real-time. The AI is based on a forecasting engine, hosted on the remote Amazon Web Services (AWS) server, the Learning Management System (LMS) controls the assessments and the Course Management System (CMS) controls the process. This computational ecosystem is a solution that reduces the cost and the need for technical support when implementing a technology related to Machine Learning and visualization for any time and place in the LMS - CMS code. To facilitate learning portability, this ecosystem is described from three ecosystem environments, LMS-CMS (Open EDX), remote server (AWS), and an application for interfaces and server communication created in Unity3D. In these environments, ten patterns interact through various micro-services to respond to the consumption mode between the Open EDX Front End and the mobile application. Fragmentation into patterns makes this research reusable and adaptable for future online learning contexts.	MOOCs;artificial intelligence; assessment;pattern;AWS; OpenEDX	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9678911	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab

Experience Report from a Graduate ML Production Systems Course	10.1109 /eIT60633. 2024.10609876	There is a dearth of coursework on designing and implementing services that incorporate machine learning models in university curricula despite the growing industry demand. We describe the design of a course titled "ML Production Systems" which covers the implementation, deployment, monitoring, and updating of machine learning models as part of user-facing web services. The course is designed around a semester-long project to implement and deploy a home sale price prediction service. The course is a required course in a Master's in Machine Learning program and graduate Machine Learning Engineering certificate program. The course was taught in an online synchronous format to twenty-nine students in Fall 2023; fifteen of the students had more than one year of professional experience as software engineers, while the remaining fourteen students were accelerated Master's students. Analysis of open-ended written student feedback indicated that students in both groups had a positive experience and found the course to be valuable. Assessment of learning outcome achievements with a final exam and project completion rates indicated that nearly all of the students successfully achieved the learning outcomes. No statistically-significant differences in achievement between the working professionals and accelerated Master's students were detected. We believe that this course and its successful delivery will serve as a blueprint for other faculty who may want to implement similar courses.	machine learning;web services;computer science education	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10609876	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
Assessing Soft Skills Development in Informatics Students Through Project-Based Learning and Agile Frameworks	10.1109 /ICACIT62963. 2024.10788614	In the current dynamic and competitive job market, influenced by the rapid growth of Artificial Intelligence, Soft skills have become increasingly valuable. Similarly, today's informatics labor sector requires collaboration, ethics, and adaptability. However, traditional education often prioritizes technical skills over others. Thus, the present study aims to assess the development of soft skills in informatics students using the Project Based Learning (PBL) methodology within the context of Agile frameworks: Scrum and Kanban. A mixed-method study was designed using both quantitative and qualitative approaches. Student outcomes based on ICACIT accreditation criteria were utilized to quantitatively assess soft skills, focusing on indicators such as teamwork, communication, professionalism, and ethics. A perception survey was conducted to qualitatively gather data on students' experiences in developing soft skills. The results indicate a positive academic performance, with achievement levels exceeding 70%. Students also reported favorable perceptions of acquiring soft skills, and there was a significant correlation between quantitative and qualitative findings. Lastly, the assessment shows that implementing PBL within agile frameworks positively impacted informatics students, especially in communication and teamwork skills.	Agile;assessment; informatics;PBL;soft skills; student outcomes	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10788614	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Metacognitive Scaffolding to Support Students in Learning Authoring System Subject	10.1109 /LaTICE. 2015.23	Authoring System is one of the computer-based subjects that expose students with creative activities using an authoring tool such as Adobe Flash software to produce multimedia applications. The demonstrations and hands-on activities among students while learning this subject are fundamental. Therefore, the guidance from the instructors through the use of metacognitive scaffolding may ease their difficulties, as this type of guidance supports students in understanding the best possible strategy to accomplish difficult tasks and thus, develop their thinking. In this study, students were scaffolded by the instructor through the use of mechanisms of metacognitive scaffolding. This guidance was delivered through the discussion on the Facebook group page, in which each prompted mechanism of metacognitive scaffolding from the instructor was coded accordingly. In addition, to demonstrate the effectiveness, students were given a pre and post test assessment. This study was carried out for seven weeks. The sample of the study was composed of twenty master students from the Educational Technology program. The quantitative analysis reveals that students' performance in learning Authoring System subject increase after receiving metacognitive scaffolding from their instructor.	metacognition;metacognitive scaffolding;metacognitive strategies;learning performance	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7126237	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
Using the SEMAT Kernel for Software Process Assessment and Practices Implementation in an Software Process Improvement Initiative	10.1109/SCCC. 2018.8705227	Software process improvement (SPI) initiatives are based upon an appropriate assessment of the actual state or maturity of processes and a concrete model to guide engineers in the next steps to move from the actual state to an improved one. In the context of an SPI initiative at the Chilean National Customs Service, we used the SEMAT Kernel to assess software processes and to guide the implementation of practices for their improvement. We present in this paper our experience using the SEMAT Kernel. We also present a description of several lessons learned in this experience.	software process improvement semat kernel	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8705227	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab

Technology Enabled Learning (TEL) to Improve Pronunciation in the Students of Professional Courses -- A Study	10.1109/T4E.2015.17	This study seeks to assess the efficacy of technology enabled learning (TEL) to teach pronunciation to undergraduate students pursuing first year Engineering programme using 'Pronunciation Power' software in the English Language Communication Skills Lab (ELCS). The students were exposed to supra segmental features of the language through authentic tasks such as inspirational speeches, interviews, debates etc. Interestingly the findings revealed that TEL helped the students improve their accent, intonation and style of speaking better than the teacher given inputs. The performance of the students has been examined using the speech analysis software in addition to the assessment of oral presentations made by the students in the ELCS Lab.	pronunciation;supra segmental features;speech analysis;pronunciation power software	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7395630	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Effective team onboarding in Agile software development: techniques and goals	10.1109/ESEM.2019.8870189	Context: It is not uncommon for a new team member to join an existing Agile software development team, even after development has started. This new team member faces a number of challenges before they are integrated into the team and can contribute productively to team progress. Ideally, each newcomer should be supported in this transition through an effective team onboarding program, although prior evidence suggests that this is challenging for many organisations. Objective: We seek to understand how Agile teams address the challenge of team onboarding in order to inform future onboarding design. Method: We conducted an interview survey of eleven participants from eight organisations to investigate what onboarding activities are common across Agile software development teams. We also identify common goals of onboarding from a synthesis of literature. A repertory grid instrument is used to map the contributions of onboarding techniques to onboarding goals. Results: Our study reveals that a broad range of team onboarding techniques, both formal and informal, are used in practice. It also shows that particular techniques that have high contributions to a given goal or set of goals. Conclusions: In presenting a set of onboarding goals to consider and an evidence-based mechanism for selecting techniques to achieve the desired goals it is expected that this study will contribute to better-informed onboarding design and planning. An increase in practitioner awareness of the options for supporting new team members is also an expected outcome.	Agile teams;onboarding; software engineering	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8870189	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem avaliação
The Impact Of Integrated Tutorials in Supporting First Year Student Progression In Engineering	10.1109/FIE.2018.8658976	In this full paper we describe an innovative practice regarding the design and introduction of compulsory, small-group, holistic tutorials into our core first year engineering courses. Instead of traditional tutorials which seek to reinforce lecture content or provide guided help with assignments or test revision, these tutorials specifically focus on connecting topics between all courses a student is currently taking. They also aim to clearly demonstrate the value of a cohesive body of knowledge, instead of rote-learning of facts from individual areas. Tutorials are accompanied by practical demonstrations, and collaborative, guided discussions. The inclusion of these tutorials, along with other minor changes to the course content, has shown marked improvements in students' grades, retention, student evaluations and, most importantly, a change in many students' perception of the value of a coherent body of knowledge separate to that necessary to perform well in assessments. Such tutorials appear to have positively affected the retention rate of engineering students in our degree programme.	integrated tutorials;student retention;holistic pedagogy in engineering	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8658976	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab

Analysis of Software Vulnerabilities Introduced in Programming Submissions Across Curriculum at Two Higher Education Institutions	10.1109 /FIE61694. 2024.10893015	This full research paper describes the analysis of common software vulnerabilities that are introduced by students enrolled in four-year computing and cybersecurity majors from two different higher education institutions in Georgia. As the demand for secure coding education continues to grow, pedagogical improvements need to be made in identifying key software vulnerabilities students commit during code development (from the first programming course to the exit senior design capstone) which in turn can be analyzed to inform the pedagogical interventions focused at preparing students with skill sets for writing secure code and entering the professional workforce. While code security is emphasized throughout the computing curriculum, this research is focused on training individuals to be aware of common vulnerabilities and tailoring programming concept knowledge that has been shown to have a positive effect on code security. Existing research has mainly focused on developing vulnerability analysis tools rather than collecting data (and subsequently analyzing) regarding the types of vulnerabilities produced by students at their institutions. In this paper, we analyzed student code across different courses and reported the types of vulnerabilities produced by students in their assignment submission code from two different higher education institutions across different levels of the four-year curriculum. The reported vulnerabilities are grouped by CWE-ID, which is a standard and common way to categorize and identify software vulnerabilities. The resulting CWE-IDs are then grouped per student submission and per semester (across curriculum levels) to discover the common types of software vulnerabilities committed across cross sections of students. Our results from the analysis of vulnerabilities (ranging from CS1 courses to capstone courses) are organized around the following research questions: 1) What are the most common software vulnerabilities produced by computing majors at different levels through the computing curriculum?; and 2) Do these vulnerabilities persist throughout their curriculum as they advance into higher-level courses? We report that students commonly make mistakes related to variable usage, null pointer checks, hard-coding sensitive information, and improperly validating input. Vulnerabilities such as CWE-489 ("Active Debug Code") and CWE-215 ("Insertion of Sensitive Information Into Debugging Code") tend to persist across multiple course levels and may need to be focused in the computing curriculum. The number of vulnerabilities introduced in assignment code increases as course complexity increases. We also find that vulnerabilities produced by students have little overlap with what software vulnerability researchers commonly study, potentially leading to a mismatch in priority for secure coding topics. Our findings have implications for computer science and cybersecurity curriculum design and delivery.	Computing skills;Computer science;Engineering curriculum;Undergraduate	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10893015	<div style="background-color: #00FF00; width: 100%; height: 100%; display: flex; align-items: center; justify-content: center;"> <input type="checkbox"/> </div>	<div style="background-color: #FF0000; width: 100%; height: 100%; display: flex; align-items: center; justify-content: center;"> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> </div>	não tem colab
Implementation of cyber-blog system to improving concept understanding in algorithm for students	10.1109 /ICSTech. 2015.7407785	The purpose of this research is to improve students' mastery of concept understanding in the algorithm learning by implemented a system of cyber-blog. Cyber-blog is web-based software that combines the functions of web and blog in the form of a video or computer simulations sourced from the Internet or from the researcher itself. This study use Quasi Experimental Design. Quasi-Experimental Design is a method of research that aims to determine whether there is a result of a treatment in a subject and compared with subjects who did not receive treatment. Subjects were students in Vocational High School, Department of Software Engineering in Bandung. Data were collected by using a student concept mastery test and field notes and will be developed a special computer-based media in the learning algorithm which is considered difficult. Analysis of data is using analytical tests to student mastery concept test and Linkert scale (5, 4, 2, and 1) to yield the percentage of students in learning achievement. The purpose of designing, building and using cyber-blog system in this algorithm learning is expected to increase students' mastery of the understanding the concept. Most of the students gave positive responses regarding the learning that using cyber-blog system. This is demonstrated by the acquisition of a percentage of the questionnaire amounted to 70.83%.	concept mastery;quasi-experimental design;cyber-blog;algorithm	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7407785			<div style="background-color: #00FF00; width: 100%; height: 100%; display: flex; align-items: center; justify-content: center;"> <input type="checkbox"/> </div>

Education Application Usability Assessments: Comparison Between Blackboard and Canvas Based on App Reviews	10.1109 /MobiSecServ5 8080. 2023.10328998	A Learning Management System, or LMS, is a software that helps educators and students increase and improve their educational involvement and learning. Two excellent examples are Canvas and Blackboard. Different course materials are organized and readily accessible by LMS, which incorporates social learning engagement. This research aims to assess the usability of the two learning management systems, compare the usability of Blackboard and Canvas based on student satisfaction, and calculate the usability scores of the two leaning management tools. Reviews of apps are crucial for understanding user input. To evaluate the usability of software, we analyze app reviews to categorize the usability issues based on prior research in usability engineering. Apps stakeholders are students, teachers, and system administrators. In this study, we investigate the issues with the Blackboard and Canvas mobile apps for education. We group them according to Jacob Neilson's heuristics [14]; ten general guidelines for creating user interfaces. Because they are more comparable to general rules of thumb than precise usability requirements, they are known as "heuristics." Breaking down app reviews using Natural Language Processing (NLP), also sometimes referred to as text preparation, is an essential process that involves getting text data ready for analysis. Text cleaning is the process of removing noise and unimportant material from text data so that it can be more effectively examined. In fact, the annotator would find it easier to connect the review with the right heuristic [13].	Usability;Human-Computer Interaction;Learning Management Systems;User Reviews;Mobile Application Platform	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10328998	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Software cost estimation for global software development a systematic map and review study		Software cost estimation plays a central role in the success of software project management in the context of global software development (GSD). The importance of mastering software cost estimation may appear to be obvious. However, as regards the issue of customer satisfaction, end-users are often unsatisfied with software project management results. In this paper, a systematic mapping study (SMS) is carried out with the aim of summarising software cost estimation in the context of GSD research by answering nine mapping questions. A total, of 16 articles were selected and classified according to nine criteria: publication source, publication year, research type, research approach, contribution type, software cost estimation techniques, software cost estimation activity, cost drivers and cost estimation performances for GSD projects. The results show that the interest in estimating software cost for GSD projects has increased in recent years and reveal that conferences are the most frequently targeted publications. Most software cost estimation for GSD research has focused on theory. The dominant contribution type of software cost estimation for GSD research is that of models, while the predominant activity was identified as being software development cost. Identifying empirical solutions to address software cost estimation for GSD is a promising direction for researchers.	Systematic Mapping Study; Software Cost Estimation; Global Software Development	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7320354	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
The Effectiveness of Integrating Geometer's Sketchpad Software in Phase-Based Geometric Learning	10.1109/TALE. 2018.8615366	The aim of this study was to study the effect of learning activities based on the van Hiele's phases of learning geometry in the environment of GSP software on students' geometric thinking. A quasi-experimental design was employed in which participants were assigned to either the treatment or the control groups. Ten students, five from each group, were randomly chosen for interviews in order to identify the early levels of their geometric thinking. The items used in these interviews were the items contained in the van Hiele's Geometry Test (vHGT). Students in both groups were found to have achieved a good van Hiele first level of thinking in the preinterview. In the post-interview, students were asked for their views whether a square was a parallelogram, and whether a square was a rhombus. However, for both of these items, almost all the students in the control group provided inaccurate answers. Meanwhile, three students in the treatment group agreed and provided clear justifications for those items. This finding indicates that activities in geometry topics based on the van Hiele's phases of learning geometry and aided with GSP software can be applied to the students in order to enhance their geometric thinking levels.	van Hiele's model;geometric thinking;Geometer's Sketchpad (GSP)	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8615366	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software

Impacts of Augmented Reality in Legal Studies: Students' Reflections	10.1109 /ITT51279. 2020.9320872	The use of augmented reality (AR) in education is relatively new particularly for legal studies. Yet, its use and application may benefit students of law schools not only in helping them to be more interactive in the learning process, but also engaging them in a more experiential education whereby students' learning motivation can be improved. Scarcity of past research and literature on the application of AR in legal studies has led to this study to be carried out primarily to bridge the gaps in the existing literature. Based on the above premises, this article focuses on exploring the impacts of AR in the context of legal studies from the perspective of the students. By employing a pure qualitative methodology, this article engaged with a case study method, whereby one of the law schools of a higher learning institution in Malaysia has been chosen. Survey data from the Google Form was exported for the purpose of analysis in the computer-aided qualitative analysis software (CAQDAS) ATLAS.ti version 8.4. In order to make data ready for analysis, codes were built using a purely inductive approach. It was found that the application of AR has had a significant impact on students of law school particularly within the domains of active learning, unique learning and helpfulness for their studies. The implication for the study is better understanding of the impacts of AR in legal studies among law students. Hopefully, the paper would shed light into the body of literature of technological studies, AR and virtual reality, particularly within the context of higher education.	augmented reality;legal studies;reflections;ATLAS.ti; impact study	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9320872	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
A Design Analysis of A Web-Based 2D Virtual Laboratory Application for Phlebotomy Learning	10.1109 /ICSTE63875. 2024.00019	Digital transformation has changed the education sector, switching from traditional learning methods to a flexible digital setup through e-learning. In line with this, the primary goal of this study is to determine the prior knowledge of 1st-year medical technology students regarding the concepts of phlebotomy and also to administer a pre-test to find the lessons that need more reinforcement for the proposed web application. The pre-test contained 15 questions from the six foundational phlebotomy lessons. Initial results have shown that students have prior knowledge regarding phlebotomy, and the results of the pre-test assessment show an average score of 9 out of 15. Moreover, the lessons Introduction to Phlebotomy and Anatomy and Physiology of the Circulatory System need more supplemental learning support in the proposed e-learning web application as students only scored 56.67% and 23.33% of correct answers, respectively, the lowest out of all. Based on the initial findings, the proposed system for this study is an innovative web-based platform that aims to transform phlebotomy education to provide immersive learning experiences for medical technology students.	e-Learning;Web Application; Virtual Laboratory;Medical Technology;Phlebotomy	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10840329	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Experience with AOAB methodology in mobile computing module	10.1109 /OSSCOM. 2015.7372683	This paper describes a case study of how Agent Oriented Agile Based (AOAB) development methodology was implemented in mobile computing module to create game as a part of the module assessment requirements. Games can be used in higher education in many ways to increase students participation, enable variation in how lectures are taught and to increase students interest when they create their own game. We provide a new game development methodology and integrated with mobile computing module. The experience described in this paper is based on the feedback from the module staff member, students feedback, final student report and finally module evaluation report by students. The evaluation shows that the students who used AOAB methodology provide a better result rather than groups who used Agile game development methodology in game creation. Finally, we describe the benefit of using game in higher education and how we could enhance students progress in their study.	Agile methodology;Game development methodology; Adaptive development model;Predictive development model;Multi Agent Software Engineering (MaSE);Agent Oriented Agile Based (AOAB)	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7372683	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
Improving Outcomes for a Masters Capstone IT Project	10.1109/TALE. 2018.8615268	Capstone project courses are a significant learning experience that encompasses student previous knowledge with the added challenge of completing a full development process from idea to final product. This paper is a case study that describes the issues and changes to our Masters of IT capstone project in the last 4 years. Being a 2-year conversion degree adds to the challenge due to limited time exposure to IT and software development. As students are mostly driven by assessment criteria, changes on how project progress is assessed were key to improve students' behaviour in terms of team work, consistent effort and resilience. Successful changes and lessons learned can be seen as recommendations for other academics looking to update or improve their postgraduate project offerings.	project course;milestones; team work;assessment	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8615268	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software

Grading 600+ Students: A Case Study on Peer and Self Grading	10.1109/ICSE-SEET52601.2021.00031	Grading large classes has become a challenging and expensive task for many universities. The Delft University of Technology (TU Delft), located in the Netherlands, has observed a large increase in student numbers over the past few years. Given the large growth of the student population, grading all the submissions results in high costs. We made use of self and peer grading in the 2018-2019 edition of our software testing course. Students worked in teams of two, and self and peer graded three assignments in our course. We ended up with 906 self and peer graded submissions, which we compared to 248 submissions that were graded by our TAs. In this paper, we report on the differences we observed between self, peer, and TA grading. Our findings show that: (i) self grades tend to be 8-10% higher than peer grades on average, (ii) peer grades seem to be a good approximator of TA grades; in cases where self and peer grade differ significantly, the TA grade seems to lie in between, and (iii) the gender and the nationality of the student do not seem to affect self and peer grading.	computer science education; peer grading;self grading	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9402176	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Software Architectures for Implementing Achievement Badges - Practical Experiences	10.1109/LaTiCE.2014.16	There are multiple commercial and non-commercial products available to integrate gamification aspects to existing services. Some of these are platform dependent whilst others are more general purpose. Commercial systems come with some problems - for example, lack of control and privacy issues. To avoid these problems, we created two iterations of badge systems and tested both of them on large courses (ca. 300 students each). In this paper, we present these systems and evaluate their merits and flaws. Based on our experiences, we present design principles on how to implement badge systems to existing online learning environments.	gamification;achievement badges;automated assessment;system design	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=6821826	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Gamification-Based Learning Media in Object-Oriented Programming Subjects to Increase Learning Motivation of VHS Students	10.1109/ICEEIE52663.2021.9616970	The results of observations and interviews of learning media for Object-Oriented Programming subjects at Vocational high school (VHS) Malang City indicate a lack of innovation in the learning media used. Therefore, it is necessary to innovate learning media that can be accessed anywhere, anytime, and build engagement with students to foster student learning motivation. The concept of gamification in combining learning and games can be one of the best innovations to maximize the process. This development research uses the ADDIE (Analyze, Design, Development, Implementation, Evaluation) model. The results showed that the product developed according to the learning media expert was stated in a very valid category. The material expert's assessment stated that it was in a valid category. In the feasibility test, the test results on the small group test subjects stated that the development results were in a very feasible category and the large group obtained a very feasible category as well. Measurement of students' learning motivation in small groups, got the "Good" category. In the large group, the score for measuring learning motivation was obtained in the motivation category at the "Good" level.	Learning media;Gamification; OOP;Motivation to learn	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9616970	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Designing for Real People: Teaching Agility through User-Centric Service Design	10.1109/ICSE-SEET58685.2023.00007	We present the design and evolution of a project-based course – Designing for Real People – that aims to teach agile software development through an unwavering focus on the user, rather than emphasizing the processes and tools often associated with a method like Scrum. This module is the result of a fruitful collaboration between a Computer Science Department, bringing knowledge and skills in the software engineering aspects, and the Service Design group of a neighbouring Art College, with expertise in user research and user experience design. We present the details of the current structure, content and assessment strategies developed for the module, as well as the principles behind its design. The core theme of the course is gathering and responding to feedback, and so here we present how this has been applied to the design of the module itself, with lessons learned, and improvements made over time. By reflecting on our own work, we aim to provide recommendations that may aid others considering how to teach these topics.	education;agile development; service design	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10172896	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Analysis Of The Level Of Thinking On Vocational High School Students 1 Jabon Sidoarjo Using Rasch Modeling	10.1109/ICVVEE63912.2024.10823988	In the era of Industrial Revolution 4.0, technological advances have brought significant changes in various aspects of life, including education. Assessment management in Vocational High Schools (SMK) is critical to measure students' level of thinking. Rasch modeling allows analysis of student learning outcomes to assess their critical and analytical thinking abilities. The results of this research are expected to provide insight into the distribution of students' levels of thinking and provide recommendations for more comprehensive and fair assessment methods. The method used was one group pre-test post-test, which was applied to 30 students at Vocational High School 1 Jabon Sidoarjo. The reliability in Cronbach alpha was found to be 0.82, which means the questions were in an outstanding category. Some students answered questions by guessing. It is recommended that interactive PowerPoint media be used under ten pages so that the learning process can be effective and get feedback.	evaluation learning; instructional media;level of thinking;powerpoint; vocational school	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10823988	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software

Using Augmented Reality and Mobile Technologies to Train Automotive Technicians	10.1109/TALE.2018.8615272	Despite decades of research exploring augmented reality in a variety of contexts, there have been very few studies exploring the use of commercially available components and a software development kit that is user-friendly for novices. Nearly all previous research has focused on applications that require extensive programming knowledge and experience. This trend makes the utilization of research findings in real-life settings impossible for those without in-depth training in computer science. In this paper, we report the results of an experiment with automotive technician trainees comparing a mobile application built with a user-friendly commercially available software development kit to a non-augmented computer-based manual. Results indicated that the augmented reality application enabled trainees to locate parts more quickly and accurately than when using the computer-based manual. These encouraging results are part of a larger study exploring the costs and potential benefits of augmented reality and mobile technologies in automotive technician training.	augmented reality; automotive technicians; mobile technology;mobile learning;training	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8615272	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
A team-approach to putting learner-centered principles to practice in a large course on Human-Computer Interaction	10.1109/FIE.2016.7757576	We present a case study on how a team of instructors put learner-centered principles into practice in a large undergraduate course on Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) that was run in 4 parallel groups of about 50 students. The course stands on the crossroads between software engineering, business, and research in so far as student-teams apply human-centered design techniques to develop mobile apps, test them with real end-users, read research papers and regularly reflect upon their experience. As a proof of the course-concept, selected results from formative and summative assessments are presented. The summative results show that students rated the course as one of the best of the 87 computer science courses run in the summer term of 2015 at the University of Vienna. The primary goal of this paper is to provide instructors intrigued by learner-centered approaches with ideas for their own practice. In particular, this paper is of interest to those who teach Human-Computer Interaction and to those who seek inspiration on mapping their course to the 14 learner-centered principles.	Learner-centered principles; project-based learning; human-computer interaction; formative and summative assessment;student-centered learning	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7757576	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Testing Machine Learning Systems in Industry: An Empirical Study	10.1145/3510457.3513036	Machine learning becomes increasingly prevalent and integrated into a wide range of software systems. These systems, named ML systems, must be adequately tested to gain confidence that they behave correctly. Although many research efforts have been devoted to testing technologies for ML systems, the industrial teams are faced with new challenges on testing the ML systems in real-world settings. To absorb inspirations from the industry on the problems in ML testing, we conducted an empirical study including a survey with 87 responses and interviews with 7 senior ML practitioners from well-known IT companies. Our study uncovers significant industrial concerns on major testing activities, i.e., test data collection, test execution, and test result analysis, and also the good practices and open challenges from the perspective of the industry. (1) Test data collection is conducted in different ways on ML model, data, and code and faced with different challenges. (2) Test execution in ML systems suffers from two major problems: entanglement among the components and the regression on model performance. (3) Test result analysis centers on quantitative methods, e.g., metric-based evaluation, and is combined with some qualitative methods based on practitioners' experience. Based on our findings, we highlight the research opportunities and also provide some implications for practitioners.	machine learning;software testing;survey	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9793981	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Characterizing Social Network E-Assessment in Collaborative Complex Learning Resources	10.1109/CISIS.2014.36	In previous research we proposed a new type of learning resource named Collaborative Complex Learning Resource (CC-LR) in support for teaching and learning by the virtualization of live collaborative sessions, with the aim to leverage the knowledge elicited during the collaboration and produce interactive and attractive resources to be played by engineering learners. We claimed this type of pedagogically and technologically augmented learning resources is able to overcome endemic problems found in collaborative learning of on-line courses, such as lack of authentic interactivity, user empowerment, social identity and challenge, thus having a positive effect in learner engagement. In order to enhance further learning engagement we endowed CC-LR with a multifold cognitive e-assessment approach that provided effective awareness and constructive feedback to learners from the live collaborative interaction amongst group members. In this paper we extend our e-assessment approach with innovative indicators from analyzing and representing the social network interaction from the live collaboration. These new indicators are integrated into our multi-fold assessment model to produce an efficient and personalized assessment feedback to ultimately enhance and improve the collaborative learning experience with CC-LRs.	Collaborative learning; collaborative complex learning resources;cognitive and social e-assessment; networking interaction;social network analysis	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=6915525	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software

Analysing and Improving Mathematical Formulation of Webavalia: A Self and Peer Assessment Tool	10.1109 /EDUCON4565 0.2020.9125101	Recently, Problem-based learning has been increasingly used, and with those practices, self and peer evaluation tasks have gained more importance. This method of learning assists learners in the acquisition of skills and competencies. In order to support self and peer evaluation tasks, there are some different software offers in the market. The ease use of them is demanded since these tasks are an important part of evaluation. With the literature emphasis on the importance of assessment and critical spirit, it arises the possibility to implement formulas to increase the efficiency on the methodology applied and satisfaction of students and teachers. This paper introduces formulation problems about marks weighting in self and peer evaluation. It presents the advantages and disadvantages of different solutions for the formulation and suggestions of adapting them among tools, feedback surveys, and teacher's methods of evaluation. It is also expected that the formulation, which was implemented in the software tool WEBAVALIA, has a great impact on feedback, improving user experience, and both efficiency and flexibility.	mathematical models;marks; self-evaluation;peer evaluation;e-assessment; algorithm optimization	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9125101	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Remote laboratory networks behavior in the light of the self-organization processes	10.1109 /EDUCON. 2015.7096055	It is increasingly common practice to use remote laboratories as teaching/learning tools, opening a new pedagogical approach and changing the essence, in many cases, of the teaching process (the latest example is MOOC). This expansion of the theoretical applications into a "community of practices" enables the movement of the student's experiences from a "classroom only" environment into remote laboratory networks. The student is introduced into virtual environment, hosted by the Internet, thus him/her is exposed to the uncontrollable, non-linear and unpredictable behaviour (the intrinsic properties of any complex system). These phenomena require the addition to the analysis of the pedagogic effect of the remote laboratory networks, of an analysis of the self-organization process and of its results, just as in the case of complex communication systems. The reason for this approach is that remote laboratory networks are a very small part of the existing complex communication systems, such as the WEB or the Internet. Thus the above complex systems will reproduce, at a different scale, their behaviour. Since the study of "complex systems" is still in its very early stages, by this paper the authors only intended to present the first results of an assessment conducted on an existing group of remote laboratory networks. Only after the principles they are governed by are determined, as revealed by the study, we will be able to discuss their further evolution.	Remote laboratory;Complex systems;Community of practices;Positive feedback; Negative feedback	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7096055	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Towards a Set of Factors to Identify the Success in Scrum Project Delivery: A Systematic Literature Review	10.1109 /CONISOFT. 2019.00023	Agile-based software development is increasingly being adopted by software professionals, as it guarantees the early development of high-quality software and software products. One of the most popular agile methods is Scrum, which is a methodology that involves an iterative, incremental and empirical process. In addition, it is designed to add value, focus, clarity, and transparency to the activities and products of a project. Agile methods have been criticized and defended, and research has shown that accommodating change can be a factor in both success and failure. Although Scrum is a light and easy to understand process, its adoption is sometimes difficult. To gather a set of factors to identify success during a Sprint implementation, a systematic review of the literature is carried out in which we find several factors that help to achieve the success of a Sprint; these are classified into four groups: personnel, project, product, and organization. The results represent a basis for companies seeking to improve the implementation of Scrum.	component;Scrum;Scrum management;Sprint;Sprint management;success; systematic literature review; software development	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9105491	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	nao tem educacao
Automotive Perception Software Development: An Empirical Investigation into Data, Annotation, and Ecosystem Challenges	10.1109 /CAIN58948. 2023.00011	Software that contains machine learning algorithms is an integral part of automotive perception, for example, in driving automation systems. The development of such software, specifically the training and validation of the machine learning components, requires large annotated datasets. An industry of data and annotation services has emerged to serve the development of such data-intensive automotive software components. Wide-spread difficulties to specify data and annotation needs challenge collaborations between OEMs (Original Equipment Manufacturers) and their suppliers of software components, data, and annotations. This paper investigates the reasons for these difficulties for practitioners in the Swedish automotive industry to arrive at clear specifications for data and annotations. The results from an interview study show that a lack of effective metrics for data quality aspects, ambiguities in the way of working, unclear definitions of annotation quality, and deficits in the business ecosystems are causes for the difficulty in deriving the specifications. We provide a list of recommendations that can mitigate challenges when deriving specifications and we propose future research opportunities to overcome these challenges. Our work contributes towards the on-going research on accountability of machine learning as applied to complex software systems, especially for high-stake applications such as automated driving.	accountability;annotations; data;ecosystems;machine learning;requirements specification	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10164771	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem educacao

Competence and Confidence through Technology Enhanced Language Learning-The Impact of Technology Among Rural and Semi-Urban Undergraduates of Engineering in India: A Study	10.1109/ICALT.2019.00084	The present study is an assessment of the efficacy of technology enhanced language learning (TELL) in teaching English to undergraduates pursuing third year of Engineering program using specific modules based on 'Internet and Smart Phone' in the Advanced English Communication Skills Lab (AECS). After a pilot study, students were divided into two groups and a group of them were deliberately asked to use internet both in their computers and smart phones whereas others were exposed to designed software in the lab. They were given authentic tasks such as watching selected documentaries, presentations on selected CEOs of pioneering technical firms along with selected successful entrepreneurs of India. Consequently, students were asked to read and write case studies and assessed through presentations, group discussions and mock interviews. Remarkably, the outcomes revealed that TELL facilitated the target students of rural and semi urban areas significantly in enhancing their language competence, and, therefore, confidence more effectively than the other group of students who used designed software in the lab.	Technology enhanced learning;language competence;English language lab;rural and semi-rural students	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8820814	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Global Software Development Education: A Commercial Perspective from a Case Study	10.1109/ICGSE.2014.20	Universities are starting to offer courses in Global Software Development (GSD) as a way to prepare future practitioners for challenges found in organizational settings. Companies also provide GSD training especially to new recruits who might lack skills in how to effectively communicate with people from different cultures and different first languages. However this training is costly and not necessarily tailored to the specific needs of the organization or individual practitioner. With a focus on GSD education, we have developed a training framework based on simulation that addresses different kinds of GSD problems. The framework allows course leaders to design training scenarios to fit their precise needs for improved communication and cultural awareness. This paper presents a market-focused study aimed at discovering the requirements for a commercial GSD education tool. We studied the market options, identified key stakeholders, and conducted interviews with senior managers from three multinational companies. The study helped us to gain a deeper understanding of current training trends, needs and gaps according to key stakeholders. Finally, outcomes provided us with directions for future tool development. Results indicate that industry find cultural differences a more pressing problem than linguistic differences. Although industry tends to use traditional (classroom based) training methods for raising cultural awareness, they perceive that interaction simulation is a viable alternative. Performance and potential cost savings are key drivers for commercialising prototype tools. Conducting market-focussed research can help to ensure our future research is relevant, and meets the needs of industry.	global software development; distributed software development;training; education;market;commercial	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=6915268	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
A Hackathon Methodology for Undergraduate Course Projects	10.1109/FIE.2018.8659264	In this innovative practice full paper we present a methodology for organizing a hackathon as a learning instrument within the scope of an undergraduate course. Hackathons are short events (1 to 3 days), where participants motivated by a common challenge gather into groups to build a software or hardware prototype. Studies show that learning is one of the main motivators of hackathon participants. Researchers are also pointing out the importance of hackathons as an informal learning approach for college students. The acquisition of knowledge comes as a result of the practice itself and with participants learning from one another. This motivated us to bring that practice to the classroom, by offering an undergraduate course where students develop their semester project within a hackathon. In an attempt to systematize the steps, compress and optimize the time allocated for the ideation phase of hackathon projects, we propose a methodology for hackathons in an educational setting. The approach combines concepts from Challenge-based Learning and Design Thinking in a sequence of activities that streamlines the ideation process with regular deliveries in short time frames. This results in objective discussions and quick decision taking, fastly arriving at a project idea where students apply what they learned over the semester. We applied our approach in an Internet of Things undergraduate course within the scope of a semester project developed in an authentic 24-hour hackathon that took place in a maker space. This article details the methodology and presents a mixed methods study to analyze the students' perception on using this set of practices and techniques.	hackathons;experiential learning;self-regulated learning;project-based learning	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8659264	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	nao avalia

An Exploratory Study of Students' Learning Performance In Flipped Classroom Using Decision Tree and Regression	10.1109 /ICoMET48670. 2020.9074083	Flipped Classroom model is one of the most effective and influential approaches that follow a student-centered approach. It may enhance students' learning skills and creates a motivational level by conducting learning activities in pre-class and post-class sessions. The main purpose of this research is to demonstrate how a combined, teaching and machine learning approach can be useful in evaluating student learning outcomes by analyzing their learning performance. Furthermore, this can help the instructor to counsel students whose performance is lagging during the semester. To perform predictive analysis and classification, we have implemented linear regression and decision tree classifier that helps the instructor to predict and classify students learning outcomes based on their overall performance before final exams.	Flipped Classroom;Machine Learning;Predictive Analysis; Regression;Decision Tree	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9074083	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
Distance Learning Organizational Aspects on Analog Electronics Based on Moodle Platform	10.1109 /ET50336. 2020.9238280	This paper describes the distance learning organizational aspects on analog electronics course based on Learning Management System (LMS) Moodle. By using the Moodle platform, the developed course provides to the students, regardless of location and time, access to all necessary learning materials, including homework, self-assessment tests, electronic circuits and communication tools. Moreover, in the learning process, the students have opportunity to access assessments and feedback messages, which increases their engagement and motivation. In the Moodle environment the teachers have a constant global view of student progress and have a variety of tools, such as video conferencing for discussions, sending feedback messages for homework, obtaining statistics and performing additional verifications of the separate academic groups. The analysis of the student evaluation results showed that the use of the distance learning course can increase the effectiveness of the training and create skills, such as using computer-aided design systems, information technologies and teamwork.	distance learning;e-learning; learning management systems;Moodle;analog circuits	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9238280	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Cohesive Group Emotion Recognition using Deep Learning	10.1109/SNPD-Winter57765. 2023.10466291	Emotions are pivotal in shaping social dynamics and interactions. An in-depth grasp of the emotions within a group setting can offer valuable insights into group cohesion and the overall emotional atmosphere, thereby bolstering effective communication, teamwork, and collaboration. This study introduces an innovative methodology designed to predict the collective emotions of a group exclusively from an image. Leveraging advanced deep learning techniques, our approach transcends previous methods that treat groups as homogeneous entities. Instead, it acknowledges the diverse spectrum of emotions within a group, capturing the distinct emotional expressions of each individual. To facilitate this, we harnessed cutting-edge deep learning techniques encompassing face detection and pre-trained emotion recognition models. A custom dataset was meticulously curated through web-scraping, manual photography, and Google's FEC (Facial Emotion Comparison) dataset. Our research entailed the utilization of models such as YOLOv3, HaarCascade, and SSD for precise face detection in images. Subsequently, we employed pre-trained DeepFace and FER models to predict seven distinct emotions for each individual featured in the image. Comprehensive evaluations encompassed metrics such as cross-entropy losses among emotions and sample analyses, culminating in an impressive top-3 accuracy rate of approximately 90%. These findings underscore the effectiveness of deep learning in accurately predicting emotions from group images, thereby enhancing communication and collaboration across diverse contexts. This research signifies a substantial breakthrough by pioneering an approach that deconstructs group images to individuate emotional recognition, yielding a more nuanced comprehension of group dynamics and promoting improved social interactions.	Deep learning;Computer Vision;Pre-trained models; Emotion Recognition;Object detection;DeepFace;FER (Facial Emotion Recognition);YOLOv3; HaarCascade;SSD	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10466291	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
A Java Program for Automatic Team Allocation in Project-Based Coursework	10.1109/TALE. 2018.8615274	Universities around the world require project-based subjects and effective team allocation. Team allocation is a very time-consuming task in complex project-based coursework subjects. This gives rise to the need of automated team allocation software, which can help the subject coordinator quickly allocate students into optimal or sub-optimal teams based on a set of predetermined criteria. This paper details our team allocation software, which was developed in Java in 2012 for the project-based engineering projects and was actually implemented in two annual project-based subjects in the University of Wollongong in the years 2013 through 2017. The actual use of our developed team allocation software shows that this software is able to find, in a very short time, the solutions highly compliant to the team allocation criteria selected using a simple algorithm. Our developed software reduces significantly the time required to form student teams, compared to manual allocations.	Apache Tomcat;engineering project work;Java software; team allocation	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8615274	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software

An unbalanced data classification method based on improved SMOTE	10.1109/ICBASE59196.2023.10303096	With the continuous development of modern industry, product quality control standards have become increasingly stringent. The classification of product quality characteristics is of paramount importance to product quality control. It is necessary to improve classification methods specifically for imbalanced data to solve the issue of data imbalance in the classification of product quality characteristics. The Synthetic Minority Over-Sampling Technique (SMOTE) is a mature algorithm capable of effectively classifying imbalanced data and is widely applied to various classification problems. However, its performance in handling class overlap and noise issues leaves room for improvement, and these issues are often prevalent in the classification of product quality characteristics. This paper proposes an improved data sampling classification algorithm based on KNN under-sampling and DBSCAN methods to enhance the SMOTE algorithm. We first employ the KNN algorithm to remove part of the majority class data in class overlap regions, then introduce DBSCAN to eliminate noise within the sample data. Lastly, we apply SMOTE for over-sampling to balance the data. We compare common imbalanced data classification methods and our improved KD-SMOTE algorithm using a decision tree classifier on five groups of public UCI datasets. Experimental results indicate that our method improves AUC and other metrics, providing a significant enhancement over existing algorithms. This method better caters to the needs of product quality characteristic classification.	SMOTE;DBSCAN; Classification of unbalanced data	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10303096	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
A tool for assessing ethical awareness and reasoning development of engineering students	10.1109/ICL.2014.7017869	Due to the importance of ethics in the professional practice, a great effort has been undertaken by the academia to prepare students with the necessary ethical skills. However, the big challenge has been to assess the development of those skills. The aim of this work is to create an assessment tool that enables: (1) evaluation of development of ethical skills in students at different stages, called acclimation, competency and proficiency; and (2) interpretation of the learning gains in relation to interest, knowledge and strategic processing.	ethics;assessment; engineering education	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7017869	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Design of an Online Laboratory Authoring Tool	10.1109/FIE44824.2020.9274018	This Innovative Practice full paper presents a software system which purpose is to be used to compose online laboratory experiences. Online Laboratories have improved their reliability and interoperability thanks to innovative developments proposed in recent years. New companies in this area have proposed novel interaction mechanisms such as the inclusion of immersive graphic user interfaces as well as the possibilities for access laboratory experiments as a service, having the alternative of just paying for the laboratory services demanded, for an specific class or for individual users. In terms of technology it is now possible to have multiple laboratory instances running from a single laboratory infrastructure or laboratory station. In terms of standardization, big efforts have been made by the Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE) and the community of Online Laboratories to release in 2019 the first standard 18762019 - IEEE Standard for Networked Smart Learning Objects for Online Laboratories. The software system presented in this work uses a set of available resources including virtual laboratories (simulation based), local laboratory equipment, remote laboratories, laboratory activities, assessment definition and learning content (text, audio, video, etc). The system provides to the users a friendly set of tools to compose their laboratory experiences, following the IEEE 1876-2019 standard definition. The output composed laboratory experiment is saved as a Smart Laboratory Learning Object (SLLO) including mechanisms to be self-adaptable according to variables such as laboratory activities difficulty level, user previous results on the same or similar laboratory activities, and user expertise in the topic (determined based on information retrieved from the Learning Management System LMS).	Engineering Education; Online Laboratory Experiments Composer; Online Laboratory Management System; Smart Adaptive Remote Laboratory; Smart laboratory Learning Objects; Learning Engineering; STEM; xAPI	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9274018	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software

Revisiting the Impact of Classification Techniques on the Performance of Defect Prediction Models	10.1109/ICSE.2015.91	Defect prediction models help software quality assurance teams to effectively allocate their limited resources to the most defect-prone software modules. A variety of classification techniques have been used to build defect prediction models ranging from simple (e.g., Logistic regression) to advanced techniques (e.g., Multivariate Adaptive Regression Splines (MARS)). Surprisingly, recent research on the NASA dataset suggests that the performance of a defect prediction model is not significantly impacted by the classification technique that is used to train it. However, the dataset that is used in the prior study is both: (a) noisy, i.e., Contains erroneous entries and (b) biased, i.e., Only contains software developed in one setting. Hence, we set out to replicate this prior study in two experimental settings. First, we apply the replicated procedure to the same (known-to-be noisy) NASA dataset, where we derive similar results to the prior study, i.e., The impact that classification techniques have appear to be minimal. Next, we apply the replicated procedure to two new datasets: (a) the cleaned version of the NASA dataset and (b) the PROMISE dataset, which contains open source software developed in a variety of settings (e.g., Apache, GNU). The results in these new datasets show a clear, statistically distinct separation of groups of techniques, i.e., The choice of classification technique has an impact on the performance of defect prediction models. Indeed, contrary to earlier research, our results suggest that some classification techniques tend to produce defect prediction models that outperform others.	Defect Prediction; Classification Techniques	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7194626	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
AP-Coach: formative feedback generation for learning introductory programming concepts	10.1109/TALE54877.2022.00060	In this work, we aim to improve code writing skill in Python-based introductory programming courses for first-year university students. In such courses, students as novice programmers would benefit from personalised and formative feedback to: 1) quickly identify issues in their computational thinking process or coding techniques, and 2) know how to proceed when facing a certain problem. Due to the large number of students, it is impractical for instructors to manually assess all the work of each student to provide tailored feedback. We design and implement Automatic Programming Coach (AP-Coach), a web-based tool for automatically generating formative feedback for exercises on basic programming concepts. AP-Coach combines software engineering techniques (code similarity measures based on abstract syntax trees, and unit testing), and AI techniques (machine translation) in a novel manner to provide relevant feedback. We report promising results for AP-Coach in the following aspects: 1) quantitative evaluation of code similarity computation and machine translation, 2) qualitative evaluation of the perceived quality and usability of auto-generated feedback, and 3) experience of a selected group of computing students using the system.	learning programming; formative feedback; machine translation; code similarity	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10148382	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
The Development of a Visual Novel Role-Playing Game [VN RPG] as an Open Educational Resource [OER] for Philippine Literature Educators Administering the "Noli Me Tangere" Module	10.1109/HNICEM54116.2021.9731836	Many scholars saw opportunities of using digital interactive video games as a learning tool during the pandemic. However, it was indeed complex for educators, especially those who teach history-driven novels to prepare lesson plans for classes not only to get the learning outcomes but also to produce high technology materials such as video games. Given the predicament, this study aims to measure the effectiveness of the developed video game named 'Touch Me Not' under the genre Visual Novel Role-Playing Game (VN RPG) as an Open Education Resource (OER) to educators who teach the novel, Noli Me Tangere or Touch Me Not. To accomplish the proposed objective, the Understanding by Design (UbD) approach was analyzed through the administered survey questionnaire, pre-test, and post-test. The findings show that using the 'Touch Me Not' VN RPG to complement the standard class modules had a more significant effect on the educators' performance. Thus, it proved that using VN RPG is an effective complementary pedagogical tool in teaching history-driven classes.	Visual Novel Role-Playing Game [VN RPG]; Pedagogical Tools; Learning Companion; History-Driven Literature Classes; Open Educational Resource [OER]; Serious Games; Noli Me Tangere	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9731836	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
On computational thinking as a universal skill: A review of the latest research on this ability	10.1109/EDUCON.2018.8363437	In recent years we are witnessing movements around the world to bring computer programming to schools. Lots of these initiatives, however, have been conceived to address the shortage of professionals in the technology sector, an approach that is encouraged by the software industry. On the contrary, this article argues that the focus should shift towards computational thinking, an ability that goes far beyond computer science or technology, fostering fundamental skills for the citizens of the twenty-first century. In this paper we summarize the findings of recent investigations that study computational thinking from different perspectives, explaining what this new skill is made of, presenting outcomes of school interventions showing relationships between the development of this ability and improvements in different subjects and soft skills, presenting technologies to foster its development, and reviewing tools that support educators in the assessment of this skill.	computational thinking; programming; skills; computer science education; digital literacy	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8363437	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab

The education of students about ISO/IEC 29110 software engineering standards and their implementations in very small entities	10.1109/IHTC.2017.8058208	Worldwide, a large majority of organizations developing software are entities having up to 25 people. Since most published software engineering standards had been developed by and for large organizations, most Very Small Entities (VSEs) did not have the expertise to adapt or tailor those software engineering standards to meet their needs. The ISO/IEC 29110 series of standards and guides was specifically developed for VSEs developing software. Many countries that had not participated to international standard development, decided to join the ISO working group mandated to develop the ISO/IEC 29110 series. Since the ISO/IEC 29110 engineering and management guides are easily understandable and freely available, it has greatly helped their adoption. More than 17 countries, such as Colombia, Brazil, Haiti, Jordan, Malaysia, Mexico, Peru and Thailand are teaching ISO/IEC 29110. ISO/IEC 29110 has been used by many students to develop their first products. Many countries have adopted ISO/IEC 29110 as a national standard. A few countries are helping their VSEs in the adoption, implementation and certification activities with government programs. Low cost independent certification and assessment schemes allow VSEs to demonstrate recognition of their competences to local and international customers and partners.	Very Small Entities;ISO/IEC 29110;management and engineering guide;education; standard	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8058208	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
A Hands-on Education Framework for Cybersecurity	10.1109/FIE58773.2023.10343268	Businesses lose millions of dollars to cybersecurity breaches. To combat these attacks, qualified cybersecurity professionals are needed; however, the trend of unfilled cybersecurity jobs continue to grow. Finding effective learning models to teach cybersecurity concepts, which are often abstract and highly technical, has been problematic. It is hypothesized that the learning experience, efficacy of the approach, and skills proficiency of the student will improve through combining student-centered active learning models. This paper presents and evaluates a novel approach, the Project-Guided Learning (PGL) model, to address some limitations of existing learning models for teaching cybersecurity concepts. Students are given a project to research the construction and development of an optical fingerprint reader using a Raspberry Pi and the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) Biometric Image Software (NBIS). Evaluation of the PGL framework conducted through quantitative analysis of pre/post survey results and assessment data gathered over multiple years suggests this is an effective learning model for teaching cybersecurity.	cybersecurity;active learning models;project;raspberrypi; fingerprint;biometric;pgl;pbl; gicl;student-centered	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10343268	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
A Systematic Literature Review of Assessment Tools for Programming Assignments	10.1109/CSEET.2016.48	The benefits of using assessment tools for programming assignments have been widely discussed in computing education. However, as both researchers and instructors are unaware of the characteristics of existing tools, they are either not used or are reimplemented. This paper presents the results of a study conducted to collect and evaluate evidence about tools that assist in the assessment of programming assignments. To achieve our goal, we performed a systematic literature review since it provides an objective procedure for identifying the quantity of existing research related to a research question. The results identified subjects in the development of new assessment tools that researchers could better investigate and characteristics of assessment tools that could help instructors make selections for their programming courses.	Assessment tools; Programming assignments; Mapping study	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7474479	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Privacy Engineering for Protection of Personal Identifiable Information	10.1109/ICCED60214.2023.10425182	The usage of data driven systems requires a serious concern on how users' data privacy or specifically their Personal Identifiable Information (PII) are being handled. Privacy Engineering (PE) discipline needs to be cultivated among Computing students and software developers. Presently, data privacy discussion in Security courses and Software houses emphasis the enforcement of complying to data privacy legal acts. The technological aspects represented by PE, among others involve Privacy by Design (PbD) and Privacy Control Assessment tools are seldom taught. Thus, there is a gap between Privacy Engineering and Software Engineering, particularly in Malaysia. This work aims to give initial exposure to undergraduate students' understanding and implementing privacy engineering in software development. A prototype of a mobile application is developed to demonstrate basic implementation of deidentification as part of PE, for an application that holds users' PII.	Privacy Engineering; Personal Identifiable Information;Privacy Enhancing Tools; Deidentification	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10425182	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
The Importance of Institutional Support in Maintaining Academic Rigor in E-Learning Assessment	10.1109/ICTCS.2019.8923111	This paper reports on the perceptions of a group of academics regarding the role of higher education institutions in dealing with cheating when completing on-line assessments. A thematic approach to data collection and analysis was utilized. The findings showed there was an ad-hoc approach to the issue of academic integrity and dealing with cheating. While institutional policies did exist concerns were expressed as to their overall effectiveness. Additionally, faculty were not provided with sufficient training in the use of detection methods and the use of available systems and processes to ensure academic rigour in relation to cheating in on-line assessments. The findings have implications for institutions in the development and implementation of academic misconduct policies.	online;faculty;students; cheating;tools;plagiarism	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8923111	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software

arPcTECHture – a gamified educational 3D virtual world for introductory concepts in computer architecture	10.1109 /EDUCON5253 7.2022.9766679	Gamified assessments have been mainly implemented for STEM education, focusing on motivational objectives and performance evaluation of teaching-learning processes. This paper presents a gamified educational 3D virtual world developed to provide a complementary tool for teaching software engineering students the fundamental concepts of computer hardware. The research design follows the needs identified across a focus group, but the prototype may also serve as support for K-12 with technical specializations. A beta-test has concluded that the learning outcome is improved when a gamification framework is provided. The engagement level has been assessed among engineering students, validating the prototype as a new complementary method for an Applied Informatics laboratory.	Gamification;serious game; computer hardware architecture;user experience assessment	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9766679	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Facing the Challenges of Teaching Requirements Engineering		This paper reports on our experience of teaching Requirements Engineering for undergraduate students. It is well known, the obstacles educators have in teaching requirements engineering. These obstacles are related to the very nature of requirements engineering: a multidisciplinary field that deals with both computer science and social sciences concepts. Teaching requirements engineering just with problems descriptions, as a basis for the construction of requirements specifications or requirements models, misses the point. Educators should also provide students with ways of gathering client information. However, to be effective in this regard, there is the need that students interact with clients. Our pedagogical strategy is designed to tackle these challenges. Notwithstanding, we need to have feedback about the strategy, which lead to the design of an assessment to gauge the efficacy of our pedagogical strategy. We, describe the strategy, stress its novelty in facing the challenges, and provide assessment results over 3 semesters.	Requirements elicitation; requirements engineering education;creativity; pedagogic strategy.	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7883333	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
Integration of Computational Techniques in the Teaching of Physics of Electronic Devices: A Practical and Applied Perspective	10.1109 /EDUCON6031 2. 2024.10578826	For a long time, theoretical classes have been the fundamental element of teaching in Physics of Electronic Devices courses. These classes focus on general principles and physical laws that govern device behavior, such as band theory and electrical current models, in relation to device parameters. However, a significant change has been introduced in the educational approach, incorporating computational techniques, particularly the finite element method, for the design and analysis of electronic devices such as diodes, transistors, and other components. This change introduced to the Physics of Electronic Devices program offers students a unique opportunity to more realistically understand the behavior of devices based on their geometric and structural characteristics and the environment in which they operate. Students can now model devices such as the diode, Schottky diode, and MOSFET using finite element software, applying the physical laws that govern the dynamics of carriers, such as the Poisson equation, carrier transport equations, and the continuity equation. This more practical and applied approach allows students to acquire skills highly in demand in the semiconductor industry, where similar programs are used in the design of new devices. Additionally, assessment strategies will be implemented to measure and improve learning outcomes in this new educational approach. Continuous evaluation will be essential to adapt and refine the program.	electronic devices;finite element method;meshing; Poisson equation;continuity equation	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10578826	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Learning from Mistakes: An Empirical Study of Elicitation Interviews Performed by Novices	10.1109/RE. 2018.00027	[Context] Interviews are the most widely used elicitation technique in requirements engineering. However, conducting effective requirements elicitation interviews is challenging, due to the combination of technical and soft skills that requirements analysts often acquire after a long period of professional practice. Empirical evidence about training the novices on conducting effective requirements elicitation interviews is scarce. [Objectives] We present a list of most common mistakes that novices make in requirements elicitation interviews. The objective is to assist the educators in teaching interviewing skills to student analysts. [Research Method] We conducted an empirical study involving role-playing and authentic assessment with 110 students, teamed up in 28 groups, to conduct interviews with a customer. One re-researcher made observation notes during the interview while two researchers reviewed the recordings. We qualitatively analyzed the data to identify the themes and classify the mistakes. [Results and conclusion] We identified 34 unique mistakes classified into 7 high level themes. We also give examples of the mistakes made by the novices in each theme, to assist the educationists and trainers. Our research design is a novel combination of well-known pedagogical approaches described in sufficient details to make it re-peatable for future requirements engineering education and training research.	Requirements Elicitation Techniques, Interviews, Requirements Engineering Education	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8491134	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem avaliar

Designing a Multi-disciplinary Group Project for Computer Science and Engineering Students	10.1109 /EDUCON. 2019.8725147	This paper describes the design of a group-based project that combines both the hardware and software disciplines of our Computer Science (CS) and Computer Engineering (CE) undergraduates. The goals for the multi-disciplinary design project (MDP) are to provide our 3rd year undergraduates with the opportunities to apply the theoretical knowledge acquired from their early years to solving a practical problem, foster a continuous improvement mindset, and experience the benefits and challenges of working collaboratively in a large team. This requires the formulation of a suitably complex problem that can integrate the skill sets from both the CE and CS programmes. It also requires suitable assessment strategies that can evaluate the students at the individual level, at the group level and at the inter-group level. This paper shares our pedagogical considerations in designing the project module, our experience gleaned from conducting the module over the last five years and some results of a recent online survey conducted to gather students' feedback on their experience of MDP.	multi-disciplinary; collaborative;group-based; design	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8725147	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es
Mining Twitter Messages for Software Evolution	10.1109/ICSE-C.2017.65	Twitter is a widely used social network. Previous research showed that users engage in Twitter to communicate about software applications via short messages, referred to as tweets, and that some of these tweets are relevant for software evolution. However, a manual analysis is impractical due to the large number of tweets - in the range of thousands per day for popular apps. In this work we present ALERTme, an approach to automatically classify, group and rank tweets about software applications. We apply machine learning techniques for automatically classifying tweets requesting improvements, topic modeling for grouping semantically related tweets and a weighted function for ranking tweets according to their relevance for software evolution. We ran our approach on 68,108 tweets from three different software applications and compared the results against practitioners' assessments. Our results are promising and could help incorporate short, informal user feedback with social components into the software evolution process.	user feedback;software evolution;text mining	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7965331	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
Continuous Validation for Data Analytics Systems		From a future history of 2025: Continuous development is common for build/test (continuous integration) and operations (devOps). This trend continues through the lifecycle, into what we call 'devUsage': continuous usage validation. In addition to ensuring systems meet user needs, organisations continuously validate their legal and ethical use. The rise of end-user programming and multi-sided platforms exacerbate validation challenges. A separate trend is the specialisation of software engineering for technical domains, including data analytics. This domain has specific validation challenges. We must validate the accuracy of statistical models, but also whether they have illegal or unethical biases. Usage needs addressed by machine learning are sometimes not specifiable in the traditional sense, and statistical models are often 'black boxes'. We describe future research to investigate solutions to these devUsage challenges for data analytics systems. We will adapt risk management and governance frameworks previously used for software product qualities, use social network communities for input from aligned stakeholder groups, and perform cross-validation using autonomic experimentation, cyber-physical data streams, and online discursive feedback.	software validation; continuous development; devOps;machine learning; data analytics;ethics; governance	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7883399	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
Managing IT Projects and Evaluating their Cost and Complexity: State of the Problem	10.1109 /SUMMA50634. 2020.9280649	According to statistics, about a quarter of all started software projects are completed on time, a quarter are canceled, and about half of all projects are completed over budget or late. Existing methods and software products for estimating the time and cost of software development projects are often not suitable for evaluating the project at an early stage, where the wrong project deadlines and budget are most often set. Within the framework of this research, the task is to investigate the existing approaches to estimating the cost and labor intensity, as well as to propose an author's approach taking into account the shortcomings of existing methods. This will improve the quality of information systems development by reducing the number of delays in completing tasks, as well as by minimizing possible costs over the budget allocated for the project. This will also help to minimize costs in the decision-making process during the project.	Risk management;cost and labor intensity assessment; project management methodologies;software development projects	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9280649	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
Implementing Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion in Accreditation	10.1109 /ICACIT56139. 2022.10041468	Many people enjoy the advantages of digital transformation. However, recent technical advancements, applications, and tools reflect the deficits of society regarding diversity, equality, and inclusion across disciplines and organizations. Fortunately, these three elements may become part of accreditation criteria and processes for engineering, computing, and other programs. Moreover, accreditation bodies, higher education institutions, and educators need to become ready to implement these new criteria. This work addresses the meaning of the three concepts in the context of accreditation. It also emphasizes the potential benefits for technical professions, future engineers, and ICACIT. Therefore, it becomes crucial to outline measures that support the integration of diversity, equity, and inclusion in higher education study programs and global accreditation agencies.	Engineering and computing curricula;accreditation; diversity;equity;inclusion; assessment;ICACIT;higher education	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10041468	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab

Social Networks during Software Ecosystems' Death	10.1109 /SESoS59159. 2023.00007	Software Ecosystems (SECO) depend on platforms that serve as environments for developers' interaction. The SECO may die when the organization that owns the platform does not support the synergy between organizational goals and developers' expectations. The death results in the suspension of vital activities, such as code development and maintenance, impacting developers who lose work, learning, and experience gained. On the other hand, the responsible corporation loses resources invested in SECO. These signs indicate a SECO death is an important event for the community and should be analyzed. This paper reports a GitHub (GH) study focusing on three web SECOs: AngularJS, PhantomJS, and MomentJS. We analyze metrics based on developer community engagement and collaboration to understand what happens in these SECOs before, during, and after the platform's death. From the search questions, we found some directions: Users' recruitment and permanence: Without management and engagement, communities get out of SECOS a few years after your entry, so methods to control and organize the community are needed. Community relationships: The community needs engagement to strengthen and maintain your relationships. Some types of programs are useful methods to engage and encourage users to collaborate between them.	software ecosystem;death platform;death ecosystem	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10190619	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	ouro
Deep Learning for Violence Detection in Surveillance: The Role of Transfer Learning and Pre-Trained Models	10.1109 /ACIT58888. 2023.10453685	In recent years, the use of CCTV footage for proactive crime prevention has surged, particularly in public places like airports, train stations, and malls. However, the efficacy of these surveillance systems becomes questionable for their substantial reliance on human resources which may lead to erroneous or delayed responses. This research takes a comprehensive approach for violence detection which was previously limited to binary classification, by categorizing violence into four distinct classes: abuse, arson, assault, and fight. It employs transfer learning combined with computer vision techniques for violence detection and classification in video footages. The study compares the performance of four pre-trained neural networks, namely DenseNet121, VGG16, MobileNet, and Xception. The dataset created for this research is compiled from three datasets available on Kaggle. The results reveal that the Xception model performed comparatively better achieving the highest AUC score of 98.39%, while the VGG16 model attained the lowest AUC score of 96%. In addition to the AUC score, precision, recall, and f1-score are employed as performance metrics. Transfer learning with convolutional neural networks (CNN) significantly reduced computational requirements and time. Automating the detection and categorization of violent behavior through the employed approach has the potential to reduce the risk of fatalities and injuries in public areas. It also improves the speed and accuracy of threat detection, enabling swift preventive actions by authorities.	Violence Categorization; Computer Vision;Deep Learning;Transfer Learning; Pre-trained Models	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10453685	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Experiences with remote labs in electrical drive	10.1109 /RTUCON. 2014.6998192	A remote environment proposed in the paper enables the study electrical drives via the Web. The active learning concept of the distance education and the set of Internet-based laboratory works open the possibility to learn Basic and Advanced Courses of Electrical Drive providing a lot of benefits for both the learners and the faculty. The remote labs for the bachelor and master students are presented. Reporting and assessment procedures along with the analysis of the results obtained are discussed.	Distance learning;Electrical engineering education; Laboratories;Motor drives; Variable speed drives;Web and internet services	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=6998192	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
The use of digital technologies for the development of pre-service teachers' rhetorical skills: the experience of Ukraine	10.23919 /MIPRO55190. 2022.9803713	The authors characterize the typology of digital technologies for the development of pre-service teachers' rhetorical skills: video content (speeches of prominent speakers of the past and present, fragments of movies, theater performances, television programs, speeches of masters of the word, lectures by national and foreign teachers, reports of famous teachers), audio content (podcasts, audiobooks), rhetoric courses on educational platforms, specialized rhetoric resources, specialized software in the field of rhetoric, social communities for on-line communication. The expert assessment was conducted to identify the most effective type of digital technology in the field of rhetoric for the development of pre-service teachers' rhetorical skills. The use of video content (speeches by prominent speakers of the past and present), audio content and specialized software was found to be the most effective. The conclusions of the expert group were confirmed by the Kendall concordance coefficient and the chi-square test for estimating the probability of the result.	digital technologies;rhetorical skills;electronic educational resources;specialized software in the field of rhetoric;pre-service teacher; professional training;informal education	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9803713	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software

Neural Sentiment Analysis of User Reviews to Predict User Ratings	10.1109/UBMK.2019.8907234	The significance of user satisfaction is increasing in the competitive open source software (OSS) market. Application stores let users send their feedbacks for applications, which are in the form of user reviews or ratings. Developers are informed about bugs or any additional requirements with the help of this feedback and use it to increase the quality of the software. Moreover, potential users rely on this information as a success indicator to decide downloading the applications. Since it is usually costly to read all the reviews and evaluate their content, the ratings are taken as the base for the assessment. This makes the consistency of the contents with the ratings of the reviews important for healthy evaluation of the applications. In this study, we use recurrent neural networks to analyze the reviews automatically, and thereby predict the user ratings based on the reviews. We apply transfer learning from a huge volume, gold dataset of Amazon Customer Reviews. We evaluate the performance of our model on three mobile OSS applications in the Google Play Store and compare the predicted ratings and the original ratings of the users. Eventually, the predicted ratings have an accuracy of 87.61% compared to the original ratings of the users, which seems promising to obtain the ratings from the reviews especially if the former is absent or its consistency with the reviews is weak.	Open Source;OSS;Transfer Learning;Sentiment Analysis; Deep Learning;User Satisfaction;Software Quality	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8907234	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
Designing End-User Personas for Explainability Requirements Using Mixed Methods Research	10.1109/REW57809.2023.00028	With software systems becoming increasingly complex and opaque, explainability has become an emerging software quality aspect of our time. Raising explainability requirements for a large crowd of stakeholders can be a difficult task. At this point, it is unclear what factors have an impact on the subjective need for explanations. As researchers, we do not know whether end-users' explainability needs are specific for each system or if there are user types that have more generalized needs. Designing stakeholder personas has proven to be an effective method to elicit and communicate requirements. Indeed, personas have been established in both research and in applied scenarios such as software projects. Past work has created end-user personas for explainability requirements in the context of a specific system. The goal of this work is to design personas that do not only apply to explainability requirements of a certain software, but to explainability requirements in general. To this end, we conduct a mixed-methods user study consisting of an online survey and an interview study. Based on insights of 70 participants from the online survey, 10 of which were also interviewed, we design four end-user personas for general explainability requirements. We also validate the personas by doing use case walkthroughs with our participants. Our results indicate that it is possible to design end-user personas for general explainability requirements. These personas might be used in early software development stages to estimate end-users explainability needs before more specific requirements can be raised.	Explainability;Personas; CrowdRE;Requirements Engineering	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10260886	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
An analysis of XSS, CSRF and SQL injection in colombian software and web site development	10.1109/EATIS.2016.7520140	Software development and web applications have become fundamental in our lives. Millions of users access these applications to communicate, obtain information and perform transactions. However, these users are exposed to many risks; commonly due to the developer's lack of experience in security protocols. Although there are many researches about web security and hacking protection, there are plenty of vulnerable websites. This article focuses in analyzing 3 main hacking techniques: XSS, CSRF, and SQL Injection over a representative group of Colombian websites. Our goal is to obtain information about how Colombian companies and organizations give (or not) relevance to security; and how the final user could be affected.	CSRF;hacking;SQL Injection; software development;web security;websites;XSS	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7520140	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Automating the Evaluation of the Scalability, Flexibility, and Robustness of Collective Behaviors for Robot Swarms	10.1109/SBR/WRE6306.2024.10837963	Robot swarms are large self-organizing groups of robots that coordinate to collectively perform missions that escape their individual capabilities. In a robot swarm, the individuals operate using local perception and communication, without relying on a leader or external infrastructure for coordination. These characteristics help robot swarms achieve desirable properties, such as scalability, flexibility, and robustness. In this paper, we use recently proposed experimental protocols to evaluate these properties in various typical collective behaviors for robot swarms. We focus on demonstrating that the joint application of defined protocols can help streamline and automate evaluation and reporting processes in swarm robotics research. In our experiments, instances of robot control software for typical collective behaviors are systematically simulated and evaluated across different environmental configurations and swarm sizes. We show how automated tools can facilitate the evaluation of swarm robotics properties.	Swarm robotics;swarm performance indicators; collective behavior;system properties	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10837963	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software

Continuously Evaluated Research Projects in Collaborative Decoupled Environments		Often, research results from collaboration projects are not transferred into productive environments even though approaches are proven to work in demonstration prototypes. These demonstration prototypes are usually too fragile and error-prone to be transferred easily into productive environments. A lot of additional work is required. Inspired by the idea of an incremental delivery process, we introduce an architecture pattern, which combines the approach of <code>long{MEDIATION}</code> with microservices for the ease of integration. It enables keeping track of project goals over the course of the collaboration while every party may focus on their expert skills: researchers may focus on complex algorithms, practitioners may focus on their business goals. Through the simplified integration (intermediate) research results can be introduced into a productive environment which enables getting an early user feedback and allows for the early evaluation of different approaches. The practitioners' business model benefits throughout the full project duration.	Research Best Practices; Research Collaboration Management; Metrics; Lean Software Development; Software Architecture	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8452764	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	chance
Designing a Student Video Presentation Assignment: Considerations for Minimizing Stress	10.1109/FIE43999.2019.9028495	Oral communication has been identified as a key skill for undergraduate students to master. Presenting results from course projects is a common means to provide students with an opportunity to practice planning a presentation, making slides, and communicating results to their peers. However, with large classes, there may not be enough time to give all students an equal opportunity to present their results. In this study, students produced videos sharing results of their term design project in a senior-level required control systems course at a private STEM-focused institution in the Midwest. In addition to the videos, the traditional question and answer period that accompanies inclass presentations was replaced with an asynchronous online discussion board. This paper focuses on how an assignment can be designed to reduce additional stress caused by a new format for both faculty and students.	project based learning; technical communication; oral presentations; teamwork; videos; discussion board; undergraduate	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9028495	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Visualization of Students' Solutions as a Sequential Network	10.1109/EDUCON52537.2022.9766502	It is known that timely and personalized feedback is vital to the learning process, and because of increasing enrollment, instructors can find it harder to provide that feedback. Learning analytics presents a solution to this problem. The growth in popularity of online education systems better enables learning analytics by providing additional educational data. This work focuses on the analysis of students' incorrect short answers and their pathways to correct solutions. By considering student submissions as sequences, this work uses a dimension called "distance" which can be used to predict how far off a student's incorrect answer is from a correct one. This distance metric can be used for recognizing students who may need help, understanding which concepts students struggle with, evaluating assessment questions, and improving multiple-choice answers. This paper discusses the methods, relevant learning scenarios, and applications of the learning analytics system. It features the results and analysis of a usability test conducted on 56 faculty members.	Network; learning analytics; data visualization	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9766502	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
An assessment of a ROS class using an educational mobile robot	10.1109/IESTEC62784.2024.10820208	The Robot Operating System (ROS) is a middleware that standardizes robot programming, both in simulation and with real equipment. Despite this open-source tool being available for several years, there's still a need to enhance its utilization in robotics education across all educational levels. In this study, a ROS class is assessed among university students using a commercial educational robot. The primary objective is to measure academic emotions in learning and student performance to determine the impact of the class using the open-access tool from a GitHub repository (https://github.com/joseVarelaAldas/ROS-Crowbot). This tool is based on the roserial package, compatible with the ESP32 board. For class, CrowBot robots connected to the local wireless network via WIFI are used. The participants in this study were eight students from an electronics degree program at a higher education institution, who had no prior experience with ROS and received practical training using the educational mobile robot. For data collection on class performance, three parameters are assessed: execution time, functionality, and motivation, and to measure academic emotions, a validated self-report instrument is used. The results show an overall performance of 82.1%, and in the self-report on academic emotions, a high score in enjoyment (95%) and the lowest score in boredom (24.1%) were obtained. In conclusion, the repository provides an interesting, practical, and accessible tool for an introduction into the world of robotics using ROS.	ROS; Mobile robot; Middleware; Class assessment	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10820208	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software

Poster: Improving Formation of Student Teams: A Clustering Approach		Today's courses in engineering and other fields frequently involve projects done by teams of students. An important aspect of these team assignments is the formation of the teams. In some courses, teams select different topics to work on. Ideally, team formation would be included with topic selection, so teams could be formed from students interested in the same topics. Intuitive criteria for a team formation algorithm are that students should be assigned to (1) a topic which they have interest and (2) a team of students with similar interests in their topic. We propose an approach to meeting these criteria by mining student preferences for topics with a clustering approach and then matching them in groups to topics that suit their shared interests. Our implementation is based on hierarchical k-means clustering and a weighting formula that favors increasing overall student satisfaction and adding members until the maximum allowable team size is reached.	student team formation; bidding;clustering;peer assessment system;MOOCs	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8449473	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Digital Escape Room Project: Engaging Electronics for University Students	10.1109/TAE59541.2024.10604970	This work proposes the implementation of a project-based learning methodology for the practical part of digital electronics subjects in the first years of undergraduate studies. Through the project called Digital Escape Room, a series of challenges and exercises are developed in a modular way that the students must solve in order to create a final design in Quartus software and demonstrate it on an FPGA-based device. The implementation of this project has allowed us to see that the academic results and the satisfaction and motivation of the students have improved significantly compared to previous years.	Digital electronics;Wired systems;Quartus software; FPGA	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10604970	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
A proficient high level programming program as a way to overcome unemployment among graduates	10.1109/FIE.2015.7344188	Unemployment has been a major concern in recent years. This is particular true for young people and in the case of Portugal for youngsters with a Higher Education degree. In this paper we describe the program "Acertar o Rumo", a two years program to reconvert unemployed graduates in Engineering and Exact and Natural Science in experienced Java programmers. Particularly, we focus on the Programming courses of the program, where the two main programming paradigms, the procedural and the object-oriented, as well as principles and technologies for developing enterprise systems were taught. We describe the main methodologies and approaches followed and report the very positive results obtained with the first edition of the program till now. We finish the paper by proposing some recommendations and improvements for further editions.	Unemployment;Human resources reconversion; Computer Science Education;Programming learning	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7344188	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Machine Learning models to predict Agile Methodology adoption	10.15439/2020F214	Agile software development methodologies are used in many industries of the global economy. The Scrum framework is the predominant Agile methodology used to develop, deliver, and maintain complex software products. While the success of software projects has significantly improved while using Agile methodologies in comparison to the Waterfall methodology, a large proportion of projects continue to be challenged or fails. The primary objective of this paper is to use machine learning to develop predictive models for Scrum adoption, identifying a preliminary model with the highest prediction accuracy. The machine learning models were implemented using multiple linear regression statistical techniques. In particular, a full feature set adoption model, a transformed logarithmic adoption model, and a transformed logarithmic with omitted features adoption model were evaluated for prediction accuracy. Future research could improve upon these findings by incorporating additional model evaluation and validation techniques.	Adoption;Agile methodologies;Machine learning;Scrum	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9222987	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não avalia
Clustering The Quality Level of Lecturer Teaching Using The K-Means Method	10.1109/CITSM52892.2021.9588948	Universities require faculty who have the quality in the process of learning (PBM). Therefore, it is necessary to level the quality of teaching faculty grouping which aims to assist the academic authorities in determining the quality of teaching faculty decision. Material treated in this study were 104 faculty assessment in the form of questionnaires in the academic year 2018/2019 are sourced from the student and processed using the k-means and then implemented using rapid miner software. The results of testing the accuracy of clustering quality of faculty performance against this method is 100%. The results can be concluded from this study is very precise k-means is used to classify the level of quality of teaching faculty.	K-Means;Lecturer;PBM; questionnaire;students; clusters;data mining	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9588948	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software

Analyzing the impact of asynchronous multimedia feedback on novice computer programmers	10.1109/FIE.2015.7344103	For many engineering students, freshman programming represents one of the hardest courses for them to master. Unlike other science fields, few students are routinely exposed to programming in the K12 system. This can make the freshman programming course daunting. However, in the field of software engineering, success in this area is vital, as success in nearly all future courses requires mastery of this skillset. In the engineering field, we find that many students are visual learners. These students learn best by seeing, and they can perform very well in the classroom with the appropriate usage of teaching styles. However, when it comes to providing feedback to students on submitted assignments, the main method employed is the written comment, which is not conducive to visual learners. From a faculty member's standpoint, this makes sense, as it is the simplest form of feedback. However, written feedback is often ineffective at improving student performance, as many students simply do not read the comments because the students feel they are not relevant to their performance. This can be compounded in the freshman year, as students are still learning what is meant to be an effective college student. At higher levels, an alternative feedback mechanism, namely asynchronous multimedia feedback, has shown great promise. In lieu of written feedback, students are provided feedback for software engineering exercises through the use of a short video made via video capture. The video captures in multimedia format the instructor's perceptions and actions when grading a given assignment. The video shows, in real time, what the instructor saw, whether it is a program crashing or the successful operation of the program. Furthermore, it provides the instructor the ability to potentially fix simple blatant errors and see the instructor's debugging strategy. The article describes the pedagogical foundation for the technique, specifics of the technique used, student perceptions of the technique, and an assessment of the learning gains from using such a method in an introductory freshman programming course. In general, students are shown to prefer the technique versus traditional grading, and a statistically significant improvement in overall outcomes for the experimental course is shown to exist. A statistically significant correlation between the watching of videos and outcomes is also shown.	asynchronous feedback; video feedback;assessment; grading	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7344103	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Teaching programmable logic controllers: a hands-on and skill-building approach	10.1109/ICPS59941.2024.10640000	Programmable logic controllers (PLCs) are essential in process automation and production technology. Hence, educating students about PLCs and their usage is crucial to prepare skilled workers in relevant engineering fields. This paper proposes a multidisciplinary teaching approach combining technical and business perspectives in using PLCs. Besides such 'hard skills,' we encourage the students to become creative and learn to collaborate. We describe how our course is structured and how company visits are integrated. A student evaluation of our course is given and discussed. In general, the evaluation supports our approach.	programmable logic controller;education;business	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10640000	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Implementation of Neuroresearch Method in Self Assessment Services Development: BeeBest E-Application	10.1109/ICISS59129.2023.10291833	The neuroresearch method is a combination of qualitative and quantitative research. Neuroresearch in this study is applied to develop the BeeBest application which is based on a fundamental concept where the progress and development of a nation is based on the importance of human capital. Therefore, various efforts have been made to improve the quality of human capital itself, especially quality work life (QWL). The BeeBest application is a self-assessment-based application that is useful for increasing the QWL of its users. The research method used is the Neuroresearch Method which consists of 3 (three) stages, namely Exploratory, Explanatory, and Confirmatory Research. The results of the research show the stages of Neuroresearch which are the basis for the development of BeeBest Apps. BeeBest Apps are expected to be able to contribute to increasing the capacity and competency of human capital through self-assessment and self-intervention in a sustainable manner. QWL can be built when a person is able to see and photograph his own capacity so that he can use and utilize it productively and optimally as an effort to make a valuable contribution to his life.	BeeBest Application; Neuroresearch;Self Assessment Services	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10291833	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software

A making and gaming approach to learning about RF path loss and antenna design	10.1109 /ISECon. 2018.8340494	As part of an ongoing, longitudinal study on the use of “making” and “gaming” in the classroom, two sequential activities for learning about radio-frequency (RF) path loss and antenna design are presented. “Making” involves integration of makerspace concepts and tinkering in the curriculum, while “gaming” refers to gamified curricula; in this study we investigate the joint use of these two elements in the classroom. The RF path loss activity is modeled after ham radio “fox hunting”, where students must locate a transmitter hidden on campus; it makes use of low-cost software-defined radios, and prompts students to confront concepts including measuring signal power, frequency domain thinking, and antenna polarization. The follow-up activity challenges students to build an antenna designed to receive household gas meter readings; students must design their antennas specifically for operation in the 900 MHz band, and must give a presentation describing the theory of their antenna to their peers. A competition is held where students attempt to see which of their antennas can collect the most wireless gas meter readings over a five-minute interval. Assessment data from the broader study show that relative to a baseline offering, the treatment group developed an improvement in interest, perception, independence, and self-assessed abilities. This paper discusses the implementation of the activities, the students’ approach to solving the proposed challenges, the assessment data, lessons learned from student focus groups, and instructor observations.	Antennas;gamification; making;path loss;radios; tinkering	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8340494	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Code Saga – A Mobile Serious Game For Learning Programming	10.1109 /IoTalS53735. 2021.9628484	During this global pandemic of coronavirus, the amount of self-learning done by students has considerably increased. They cannot only rely on online classes to study as students easily lose interest in these online classes. A number of studies have shown that undergraduate students have problems grasping the introductory chapters of programming. If they cannot even understand the basics, then they might not be able to comprehend the more complex chapters. Tutors have to find a means to match their teaching methodology to the students’ interest so that the latter can be as engaged as possible. This brought about a need to devise a new method of learning for IT-related undergraduate courses. It is a well-known fact that many students show a keen interest in video games. Using video games for teaching can be an interesting way to encourage self-learning of students. The concept of integrating gameplay with educational contents is known as serious games. In this paper, a mobile serious game, Code Saga, is being proposed. The primary aim of Code Saga is to smooth out the learning process of students opting for IT courses at undergraduate level. The game has been design to cover key chapters on Programming based on the latest IEEE/ACM curriculum guidelines for undergraduate degree programs in Software Engineering. A combination of mixed gaming-approaches has been used to make the game as entertaining and educational as possible to the undergraduate students. The game includes fun assessment activities to assess the players’ understanding on various programming concepts. The game also consists of a scoring mechanism, which a tutor can use to track students’ strengths and weaknesses on specific topics. Code Saga has been tested by a group of students at the University of Mauritius and the results confirmed that most students prefer to learn programming using serious games compared to the traditional learning methods.	mobile serious game;learn programming;game based learning;coding games; undergraduate	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9628484	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
Improving e-Assessment in Collaborative and Social Learning Settings	10.1109/INCoS. 2015.76	Cognitive assessment in collaborative and social learning requires assessment processes that achieve significant effect on collaborative learning and engage learners through accountability and constructive feedback. In order to design a coherent and efficient assessment system for collaborative and social learning it is necessary to design an enriched learning experience that predisposes the feedback and awareness in the group. This research focuses on e-assessment of collaborative learning and extends it with Social Network Analysis (SNA) techniques that are able to analyze and represent social network interaction during the live collaborative sessions. The interaction data extracted from social and collaborative networking must be integrated into a general assessment system to produce an efficient and personalized awareness and feedback about the collaborative activity and the social behavior of the participants. In previous work we provided a conceptual and methodological research approach of e-assessment applications and tools that meet the mentioned requirements and goals. In this paper we provide empirical data and interpretation to validate the approach.	software infrastructure; software reuse;collaborative learning;virtualized collaborative sessions	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7312086	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	nao avalia

Using Internet of Things for Automatic Student Assessment during Laboratory Experiments	10.1109/ISC246665.2019.9071654	A Learning Management Systems (LMS) is a tool for creating, distributing, tracking, and managing various types of educational material. In a previous work, the authors proposed a framework for a future LMS enhanced by Internet of Things (IoT) capabilities. The authors outlined the expected enhancements that IoT will bring to the LMS functionalities. In this paper, the authors explain the detailed implementation of an LMS application that enables a lab instructor to assess students' performance automatically during and after lab experiments. The authors explain the implementation details of the application, including the software; hardware; and IoT devices and sensors that were used to realize the application objectives and the methods used to connect the LMS to the IoT equipment. In addition, the authors explain the experiments that were made to test the efficiency of the application, which was implemented on top of the Moodle LMS using a custom Plugin that was used to connect Moodle to the IoT tools and execute the functionalities of the application.	Learning Management System;Internet of Things; IoT in education;IoT-enhanced LMS;Lab Experiments;Automated Assessment;Students' Assessments	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9071654	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
Reliability Assessment of Target Recognition Task Based on Unmanned Aerial Vehicle Simulation System	10.1109/ICAACE61206.2024.10548822	Target recognition is a fundamental and crucial task in numerous applications of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs). Analyzing and assessing the reliability of UAVs in executing target recognition tasks plays a pivotal role in furthering the development of UAV technology. Therefore, this paper proposes a reliability analysis and assessment method for target recognition tasks based on a UAV simulation system. First, a comprehensive analysis of the software and hardware components essential for UAVs to perform target recognition tasks is involved, including sensors, flight control systems, cameras, and target recognition algorithms. Then, the impact of external interferences on UAV flight attitudes, camera imaging, and target recognition performance is investigated. Through a comparative calculation under normal conditions, the relevant indicators reflecting target recognition capabilities is established, which can be use to evaluate the reliability of UAV target recognition tasks. This approach addresses the current challenge of a lack of effective reliability metrics and assessment methods for UA V missions.	Reliability assessment; unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs);target recognition; flight attitude angle;YOLov8	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10548822	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
A process and a tool to assess vocabulary learning for Computer Science Engineers	10.1109/EDUCON.2014.6826163	The study that we are presenting in this paper has been conducted with Computer Science Engineering students. We have selected a group of volunteers to use an educational software platform called Vocabulary Notebook to acquire specific vocabulary/concepts that are taught in the subjects "Technical English" and "IT Project Management". In this study we are assessing both the usability of the tool (observing students while using it and extracting conclusions and metrics) and also observing and analyzing the methodology that students apply when it comes to organizing the concepts, by using their own categories, definitions, applying filters and doing self-assessment tests. By the end of the study we will collect this data into a survey and a questionnaire, where we will ask students for feedback about the process and tool. In addition to analyzing the results, by the end of the semester we will also compare the marks obtained by our subject students with the marks of the rest of the class.	educational technology; vocabulary;information management;engineering education;continuing education	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=6826163	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Potential implementation of subject areas in Malaysia's research assessment Co-word analysis study	10.1109/IC3e.2017.8409244	In the education environment, subject area is one of important matter since primary school to higher learning institution. Subject area exists in other developed countries for research assessment. But, apparently, some of country didn't apply the subject area in its research assessment's framework. It is important to have the subject area in the assessment's framework in order to know the development and progress of subject area. Therefore, in this study, one of mechanism used to produce potential subject area is by manipulated selected bibliometric element which called as co-words analysis. This study is focused on 20 year time span started from 1995 and 2015 for Malaysian's researcher's publication. All data were extracted from selected database, Scopus. In Scopus, data were sorted from the highest cited publication. We used a powerful tool namely as Vosviewer to help us to extract the occurrence and potential words that hidden in publication. As a result, our result produced 7 clusters of potential subject area. In this study, we performed correlation analysis between our clusters with selected ranking in order to relationship between these two variable. The analysis results gave us a valuable information that there are potential to implement the subject area in the assessment. Another valuable information from our result is the potential to combine two method in assess the assessment, which is by using the bibliometric element with human judgement. The details for our research were divided into sections.	co-words;subject area; research assessment; bibliometric mapping; research area;vosviewer	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8409244	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab

Professional Development for High School Computer Science Teachers on Data Science through a Feminist Lens	10.1109 /FIE49875. 2021.9637249	This Research-to-Practice Work in Progress paper presents a recent professional development for high school computer science teachers. The court system increasingly relies on algorithms to rate a criminal defendant's likelihood of recidivism. These algorithms utilize machine learning models tuned on biased datasets, resulting in false assessments. There are several other alerting examples of how a software engineer's personal bias affects their design and development of technology. This bias leads to poor usability of technology for underserved groups. Data science applies machine learning on massive datasets to invent new technology to improve everyday life from healthcare to consumer needs. Designing and developing data science solutions for a diverse population requires an unbiased approach. Data feminism, which emerges from the intersecting fields of data science and feminist theory, presents a methodology to solve data science problems given three principles: 1) invent new ways to represent data unknowns, 2) invent new ways to reference the material economy behind the data, 3) make dissent possible. In this paper, we present a case study on a week-long online professional development for computer science high school teachers on data science using a data feminist lens. We discuss the data science tools and technology taught during the weeklong event. We share examples of the data feminism principles and class exercises. The computer science teachers also participated in community building activities. The culminating weeklong challenge was to analyze an earthquake dataset, which included themes of socioeconomic disparity within a city. The teachers worked in teams to explore this dataset with the new data science techniques and recommend resource management solutions for a city's earthquake response. In this paper, we explore the question: how the participating computer science high school teachers incorporate data feminism into their data science pipeline? We analyze the audio transcripts collected during the week to create visual analytics on our findings. We consider the impacts of culturally responsive approaches to computer science K-12 curriculum and future professional development in this space.	Computer science;Machine learning algorithms;Visual analytics;Urban areas; Software algorithms; Earthquakes;Machine learning	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9637249	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
What is Programming? Putting all together, Part II –The Cognitive Skills associated	10.1109 /CONISOFT. 2019.00018	Programming demands a high level of intellectual work and also cognitive skills of high level order. To learn programming is not an easy task, neither to teach nor train those skills. In this paper we present, as a second part of our research, the foundations of the cognitive skills extracted from classic and specialized literature, in order to set a basis for new studies addressed on how to train cognitive skills and how to assess them. We present a survey to investigate if students and professional software developers have awareness about the implication of cognitive skills in the programming process. The survey has encouraging results.	programming;cognitive skills; assessment;teaching; learning	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9105573	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
GreenGame: Solving the climate crisis in a Game to actually take action in real life	10.1109/ISPA-BDCloud-SocialCom-SustainCom57177.2022.00039	Green Software Development (GSD) is an area in the Software Engineering field that studies the contribution of software to global warming and seeks solutions to the climate crisis. Despite the great number of research discussing GSD, most students and professionals in the software engineering field are not aware of the existence of this area, even though some of them are interested in climate change. In this context, the GreenGame (GG) was created to present to software engineering students the GSD area. GG is a board game representing a world map. The players are CEOs of multinational companies who need to invest in activities around the world. The game's goal is to decrease the global temperature, however, players must be careful as some activities can actually increase it. If the temperature increases by 4°C, the game is over for everyone. If the temperature decreases and reaches 0° C, the richest player wins. We developed the game in two iterations of development and assessment. We improved the game based on the feedback we received, however in both assessments, we also got positive feedback. As future work, we want to produce a digital version of the game.	Sustainability;Software Engineering;Game-Based Learning;Green Software Development	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10070661	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não avalia
Interventions for Software Security: Creating a Lightweight Program of Assurance Techniques for Developers	10.1109/ICSE-SEIP. 2019.00013	Though some software development teams are highly effective at delivering security, others either do not care or do not have access to security experts to teach them how. Unfortunately, these latter teams are still responsible for the security of the systems they build: systems that are ever more important to ever more people. We propose that a series of lightweight interventions, six hours of facilitated workshops delivered over three months, can improve a team's motivation to consider security and awareness of assurance techniques, changing its security culture even when no security experts are involved. The interventions were developed after an Appreciative Inquiry and Grounded Theory survey of security professionals to find out what approaches work best. They were then validated in fieldwork with a Participatory Action Research study that delivered the workshops to three development organizations. This approach has the potential to be applied by many development teams, improving the security of software worldwide.	Developer centered security, software security, software developer, intervention, action research	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8804446	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software

Extracting New Metrics from Version Control System for the Comparison of Software Developers	10.1109/SBES.2014.25	Previous studies have evaluated the work done by software developers using data extracted from version control systems (VCS). However, they have focused mostly on counting the amount of written lines of code and the number of commits, which are general information that can be obtained from these software repositories. In the present article, we innovate by considering fine-grain operations at line and file levels stored in the VCS, like additions, deletions and modifications, which allow to derive a much more detailed and rich information about the work done by developers. We also define a new set of metrics to measure such fine-grain information and present two simple approaches for comparing developers based on the proposed metrics. This helps to improve our understanding of how important and alike the developers were. A case study using data from a real software development project is described. The study showed that the metrics and the comparative approaches resulted in information that is consistent with the perception of the project manager. Furthermore, our investigation points to a great potential for future work by expanding the set of metrics and exploring new comparative approaches.	metrics;comparison of software developers;version control systems	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=6943481	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
Methodology of Alternative Efficiency Assessment in the MATLAB Application	10.1109/FarEastCon.2019.8933843	The work reveals the author's methodology for evaluating the effectiveness of investment projects of global and national economic significance level, taking into account noneconomic parameters, developed in MATLAB software. The alternative methodology is fundamentally different from the generally accepted valuation concept of valuation, which is based on the CBA method (cost-benefit analysis) and the "Cash flow" method. The basis of this methodology is taking into account noneconomic characteristics (parameters, indicators), which is particularly relevant for making an objective decision on the implementation of the estimated project of global and national economic significance level. The author's methodology is based on the mandatory accounting of the whole complex of developed non-economic parameters (indicators). At the moment, a list of 26 parameters classified into six groups is offered. Six economic parameters are also estimated. All parameters are presented in quantitative scales of clear, fuzzy sets and in qualitative scales (points). The program script in the MATLAB environment allows us to simplify the introduction of an array of source data, an array of constraints; to unify the presentation of assessment results (comparative tables, charts) and to make calculations using the programmed method models easily. The method has the potential to be modified, improved, especially in the aspect of taking into account qualitative non-economic parameters of the assessment.	non-economic parameters (indicators);alternative assessment method; MATLAB software;global significance level;national economic level.	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8933843	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Leveraging Continuous Feedback in Education to Increase C Code Quality	10.1109/CSCI58124.2022.00351	This paper presents a framework for students learning C programming. CoFee is a modular framework focusing on code security and code robustness by using state-of-the-art software analyzers. Further, error messages are supplemented by meaningful hints suited for novice students. It also follows the theory of situated learning by exposing students to typical software engineering workflows using Gitlab for version control, continuous integration and code quality reports. To check code quality CoFee supports well-established open-source tools which were tested on a purpose build test suite. Its modular architecture allows easy integration of future analyzers. The evaluation within an operating systems course shows that CoFee enhances the code quality of the students' submissions and that it is well-suited for novice students.	Automated Assessment; Continuous Integration; Version Control;Instant Feedback;Secure Programming	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=1021647	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
Empirical Assessment of Identifying Human Blood Group Based on Image Processing Assisted Deep Learning Principles	10.1109/ICSES63760.2024.10910647	This study presents an empirical assessment of identifying human blood groups using image processing assisted by deep learning principles, specifically employing a cascaded Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) and Light Gradient Boosting Machine (LightGBM). Traditional methods of blood group identification are time-consuming and prone to errors, prompting the need for automated, more efficient systems. In this work, a CNN model was initially used to extract deep features from blood sample images, followed by a LightGBM classifier for final blood group classification. A comprehensive dataset, representing all major blood groups (A, B, AB, O, and Rh types), was collected and preprocessed for training and testing. The cascaded CNN-LightGBM approach achieved an accuracy of 92.4%, significantly outperforming baseline models, including standalone CNN (88.2%) and Random Forest (83.5%). The model also demonstrated high precision (92.1%), recall (92.0%), and F1-score (92.1%). Real-world testing was conducted to validate its robustness in clinical settings. The results indicate that the proposed model is well-suited for accurate and efficient blood group identification, with low inference time, making it ideal for real-time applications. This approach has the potential to transform blood diagnostics by providing an automated, scalable, and accurate solution.	Blood Group Identification; CNN;LightGBM;Image Processing;Cascaded Model; Medical Diagnostics	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10910647	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software

Peer-Formulated Assignment Method for Experimental Projects in CS courses	10.1109/FIE.2018.8658915	New assignment methods are needed for motivating students to carry out experimental projects in computer science (CS) courses. This paper describes a study that uses the peer-formulated assignment method to improve assignment efficiency in CS experimental projects. This method requires each student or group to come up with a problem and then pick another problem from other students to solve. This exchange of problem and solution helps motivate students and leads to their enjoyable learning. Under the guidance of an instructor, students can be inspired with great interest, enhance their practical abilities, and cultivate themselves with an innovative spirit. The role of instructor is not weakened but rather becomes more important. The instructor plays a critical role in assessment. A comprehensive project consists of many design stages, which require the involvement of the instructor. This method has been applied in two CS experimental courses with comprehensive projects, namely, software engineering (SE) and digital system design (DSD). The results show that approximately a 19% improvement in passing rate and a 35% improvement in student perceptions (grade above Good) for SE course. Similar positive results can also be found for DSD course. The survey results also show that most of the students were interested in their assignment, with 81.5% positive and 14.8% no opinion. In conclusion, the peer-formulated assignment method can improve the performance of the students and has achieved a favorable level of acceptance among students.	peer-formulated assignments;undergraduate; computer science education; experimental course	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8658915	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
Design Considerations of a Flexible Computer Based Assessment System	10.1109/UBMK.2019.8907044	Nowadays, the use of computers in the field of education is becoming increasingly widespread. In this study, several Computer Based Assessment (CBA) systems including one of the popular open source software used today was examined and their deficiencies are revealed. Based on these deficiencies, a more complete web-based CBA requirements and features are identified. Based on these requirements/features, in this paper, a new novel design and reference implementation of a CBA software is introduced. The developed system analyzes questions using the item-response theory and while selecting questions based on their difficulty, it also shuffles questions linked group questions (paragraphs, etc.). The system is tested with several courses over many students and its effectiveness is reported in this paper.	computer based assessment; item-response theory; e-exam; web based software development	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8907044	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Students Online Exam Proctoring: A Case Study Using 360 Degree Security Cameras	10.1109/ETCCE51779.2020.9350872	Online courses, online exams and online certificates are conducted by various universities and Information Technology (IT) institutes worldwide. Delivery tools have been created for conducting the exams from any place. Applying this will lead saving time and travelling cost. Nowadays, due to the COVID-19 pandemic, there is a big demand on the online courses and exams. This paper introduces a new approach for exam proctoring using 360-degree security camera. Mainly, online exams' security is a major concern. Thus, a delivery tools must not only ensure the identity of a test-taker but also the overall test integrity. In this paper, the usage of the 360-degree security camera over the traditional webcam was investigated in order to enhance the exam security and to minimize the stressful restrictions. To verify this goal, a case study on a group of volunteer students within the college of computer science and engineering was made. In addition, an automated proctoring model that will eliminate the need for a real-time proctoring and remove any scheduling constraints in order to prevent cheating is proposed in this paper. The machine learning algorithms is exploited to enrich the proposed system. A secure frame work using the biometric is applied in order to ensure authentication and running the online exam smoothly.	information technology;online course;online exam	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9350872	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Assessment of the Impact of Artificial Intelligence on College Student Learning Based on the CRITIC Method	10.1109/EASCT59475.2023.10393426	This paper investigates the impact of artificial intelligence (AI) on college students' learning. It employs a questionnaire survey to collect data and establishes an evaluation index system. The survey data is visualized through charts and analyzed for correlations with students' characteristics and responses. Single-choice questions are quantified using positive values, while multiple-choice questions use a numerical accumulation approach. The survey questionnaire is divided into four key indicators: autonomous learning ability, learning motivation, learning efficiency improvement, and learning progress. These indicators are rigorously analyzed for correlation and are found to be effectively uncorrelated, forming a robust evaluation index system. The CRITIC analysis method assigns objective weights to these indicators (0.2118, 0.1924, 0.3540, and 0.2419, respectively) for each survey sample. A group decision-making model is applied to explore AI's impact on students' learning. This study offers valuable insights into the influence of AI on college students' learning experiences, providing a foundation for educational decision-making to enhance the overall education system and improve students' learning outcomes.	artificial intelligence;CRITIC evaluation analysis method; group decision-making model	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10393426	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software

Sustainable Data Analysis in Engineering: 6- Year Review Emphasizing Open-Source Tools	10.1109 /ICSCC62041. 2024.10690466	The authors' examination of quantitative data analysis tools through Evidence-Based Software Engineering (EBSE) and PRISMA flow, within a 6-year review of published journal articles, is commendable for its potential impact on sustainable engineering practices. Identifying top tools like SPSS, R, Stata, Excel, SAS, SmartPLS, MATLAB, AMOS, LISREL, and MPlus, and emphasizing their usage trends provides valuable insights for researchers and educators. However, the paper could enhance its contribution to sustainability by urging the preference for open-source tools, aligning with principles of collaboration, and minimizing environmental impact. Including an evaluation of tools' ecological footprints, such as energy consumption and waste generation, would further align with sustainable engineering goals. Additionally, considering emerging trends in sustainable data analysis tools could help researchers stay informed about evolving technologies. In summary, while the paper offers crucial insights into quantitative tools, integrating sustainability considerations, promoting open-source options, and evaluating ecological footprints could significantly enhance its relevance to sustainable engineering practices concisely.	Data Analytics;Sustainable Engineering Practice; Evidence-based Engineering; systematic literature review; meta-analysis	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10690466	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Source Code Level Word Embeddings in Aiding Semantic Test-to-Code Traceability	10.1109/SST. 2019.00016	Proper recovery of test-to-code traceability links from source code could considerably aid software maintenance. Scientific research has already shown that this can be achieved to an extent with a range of techniques relying on various information sources. This includes information retrieval which considers the natural language aspects of the source code. Latent Semantic Indexing (LSI) is widely looked upon as the mainstream technique of this approach. Techniques utilizing word embedding information however also use similar data and nowadays enjoy immense popularity in several fields of study. In this work, we present our evaluation of both LSI and word embeddings in aiding class level test-to-code traceability of 4 open source software systems, the assessment relying on naming convention information.	traceability;testing;test-to-code;word embeddings	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8823709	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
A Framework for Designing Contextualized Computing Curriculum	10.1109 /RESPECT4980 3.2020.9272497	Contextualized computing is a two-decades-old approach to providing foundations in computer science. The intent has always been to promote a diversity of approaches and to cast a wide net through which to bring under-represented groups into the field. Much of the curriculum design is ad hoc. This experience paper presents a disciplined model for curriculum design that provides a structure and methodology for integrating computing with another discipline. A framework for analysis is presented that abstracts the curriculum development process. It is grounded in 50 years of scholarship on instructional design. It extends established practice to concurrently develop goals, objectives, activities, and assessments across at least two domains. The methodology is applied in two non-traditional domains: an industry-based work-integrated learning program at a 'software as a service' company, and in an alternative high school mathematics class for students at risk. This approach is unique in its emphasis on promoting a principled framework for curriculum design. It extends traditional instructional design by applying methodologies of agile development to identify, execute, and assess instructional computing.	contextualized computing; interdisciplinary computing; computing curriculum design; high school computer science	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9272497	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
QuLog: Data-Driven Approach for Log Instruction Quality Assessment	10.1145 /3524610. 3527906	In the current IT world, developers write code while system operators run the code mostly as a black box. The connection between both worlds is typically established with log messages: the developer provides hints to the (unknown) operator, where the cause of an occurred issue is, and vice versa, the operator can report bugs during operation. To fulfil this purpose, developers write log instructions that are structured text commonly composed of a log level (e. g., "info", "error"), static text ("IP {} cannot be reached"), and dynamic variables (e.g. IP {}). However, opposed to well-adopted coding practices, there are no widely adopted guidelines on how to write log instructions with good quality properties. For example, a developer may assign a high log level (e.g., "error") for a trivial event that can confuse the operator and increase maintenance costs. Or the static text can be insufficient to hint at a specific issue. In this paper, we address the problem of log quality assessment and provide the first step towards its automation. We start with an in-depth analysis of quality log instruction properties in nine software systems and identify two quality properties: 1) correct log level assignment assessing the correctness of the log level, and 2) sufficient linguistic structure assessing the minimal richness of the static text necessary for verbose event description. Based on these findings, we developed a data-driven approach that adapts deep learning methods for each of the two properties. An extensive evaluation on large-scale open-source systems shows that our approach correctly assesses log level assignments with an accuracy of 0.88, and the sufficient linguistic structure with an F1 score of 0.99, outperforming the baselines. Our study highlights the potential of the data-driven methods in assessing log instructions quality.	log quality;deep learning;log analysis;program comprehension	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9796196	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software

Extending the SEMAT Kernel to Represent and Assess Software Architecture Evaluations	10.1109 /CLEI60451. 2023.10346125	Software architecture evaluation (SAE) is a key area in software architecture design. Some of its key challenges are describing and assessing the architecture itself, the architectural decisions, the business or mission goals, and the quality attributes; and further, the adoption itself of SAE practices. The lack of a standard representation for SAE endeavors hampers its adoption by development teams, its (semi-)automated support by tool providers, and its normative assessment by process specialists. In this paper we introduce SAEMET (Software Architecture Evaluation Method and Theory), an extension of the Essence standard proposed by SEMAT and adopted by OMG; The Essence kernel defines "things" (called Alphas) any software engineering endeavor should include, and provides an extensible representation to be used for assessing an endeavor progression. SAEMET includes five sub-alphas (Quality Attributes, Business Goals, Architecture Description, Architecture Decision, and Evaluation Adoption), and provides a complete description for each one, their progression levels, and the relationships among them. Our approach is useful for representing an already published architecture review, conducted using DCAR (Decision-Centric Architecture Review method), and assessing its suitability for actionable support of adoption, automated support, and normative assessment. Ongoing empirical evaluation of SAEMET is underway, and early results indicate it is usable and useful for guiding and auditing SAE endeavor, as well as planning courses to train teams for adopting SAE.	software architecture; software architecture evaluation;SEMAT	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10346125	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
Preliminary Results for the Automated Assessment of Driving Simulation Results for Drivers with Cognitive Decline	10.1109 /SAS51076. 2021.9530113	Aging related changes and pathology affecting cognition and the ability to drive are significant issues for individuals, their families and the general population. Ensuring that unsafe drivers have their license suspended or get the additional training they need is important for the safety of the general population. On the other hand, allowing a person to continue to drive as long as they are safe is important for the social, emotional and cognitive wellbeing of the individual. This paper presents results of a preliminary study to see if an automated assessment based on trained machine learning models can correctly classify simulator drives as safe or unsafe in comparison to expert driver assessment opinion. The results show that the machine learning is able to achieve 85% accuracy in comparison to the experts for a combined group of 47 drivers that included 20 Healthy Controls, 9 diagnosed with Lewy Body Dementia and 18 diagnosed with mild Dementia of Alzheimer's Type. This work shows the potential for automated driver simulation assessment, which could reduce the burden on clinicians regarding driver safety evaluation.	Aging Drivers;Driver Simulation;Machine Learning;Cognitive Decline; Dementia;Alzheimer's Disease	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9530113	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
GUPPIE program — A hands-on STEM learning experience for middle school students	10.1109/FIE. 2017.8190546	This paper describes the details of a theme-based and hands-on STEM learning program utilizing an underwater robot called GUPPIE. Glider for Underwater Problem-solving and Promotion of Interest in Engineering (GUPPIE) is an example of a robot with oceanographic and environmental monitoring application. GUPPIE helps students to learn about fundamentals of physics (buoyancy, gravity, drag and lift force), electronics (circuitry and power distribution), programming, building (using tools and assembly), and testing in a systematic way. In this work we analyse the effects of the hands-on activities with meaningful context on students' 1) confidence level; 2) attitude towards robotics; 3) and level of interest towards STEM careers. The survey results suggest that using robots with sensible real world applications improves young students' attitudes and interests towards robotics. Based on these results, introducing young students to topics that are not part of official school curriculum, such as programming, increases the excitement and confidence in early ages, especially for girls, and can result in pursuing STEM related subjects in higher education. Results also revealed that girls are more interested in building while boys are more attracted to programming.	Marine engineering;STEM; Active Learning;Project-based learning;Student assessment;Survey; Motivation	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8190546	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
R.ECOS - Educational Recommender Ecosystem	10.1109/JSOS. 2017.4	This paper presents R.ECOS, an approach from the Software Ecosystems (SECO) perspective to recommend Educational Resources. It defines a platform that allows services integration and other Ecosystems services, with the aim of facilitating the reuse and sharing of solutions in Recommender Systems. The development of the proposal advances on studies of our Research Group, especially in the educational area. An initial assessment of the proposal was made through an application scenario, in which the services of R.ECOS were developed to define groups of users. Additionally, services from third-party were reused. The obtained results in the application scenario point to the viability of our proposal.	Recommender Systems; Educational Resources; Clustering;Software Ecosystem	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7961693	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab

PARMA: a Platform Architecture to enable Automated, Reproducible, and Multi-party Assessments of AI Trustworthiness		As AI applications are emerging in diverse fields – e.g., industry, healthcare or finance – weaknesses and failures of such applications might bare unacceptable risks which need to be rigorously assessed, quantified and, if necessary, mitigated. One crucial component of an effective AI trustworthiness assessment and risk management are systematic evaluations of the AI application based on properly chosen and executed tests. In addition to the known requirements of providing facilities for automated and reproducible tests, an assessment platform for Trustworthy AI must support the integration of different AI models and data sets, must be extensible for AI risk specific metrics and test tools, and should facilitate collaboration between model providers, assessment tool developers and auditors. In this paper, we develop an architecture of a platform for automated, reproducible and collaborative assessments of AI applications, based on an in-depth requirements analysis that maps use cases and collaboration scenarios to technical requirements.	Technical requirements; Software testing; Systematics;Collaboration; Computer architecture;Data models;Regulation	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10669860	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não avalia
Grouping Training Samples To Increase The Validity Of Recognition Algorithm Solutions	10.1109/ELNANO54667.2022.9927020	The paper is devoted to increasing the validity of recognition algorithms by dividing training samples into subsets of their related instances and using such subsets at the stage of training recognition procedures and in the criteria for making decisions about the types of signals considered. Software tools for implementing this approach are proposed. A variant of grouping training samples is considered, which is based on dividing the samples into clusters of similar instances. A supposed possible increase in the validity of the algorithm solutions here is associated with a more detailed consideration of the dislocations of the accumulation of signals in feature spaces. The proposed system for forming a system of isolines and shape characteristics can be used in algorithms for recognizing pathological patterns in the ECG signal shape. This approach also implements the principle of data dimensionality reduction about the characteristics of the waveform, which can be used in deep learning systems. The introduction reveals the general formulation and relevance of the proposed research. Section 1 discusses general issues of problem formulation: specific types of recognized signals, features for their description, the recognition algorithm chosen for research, the procedure for assessing the validity of its solutions and assessing the initial validity of solutions for the original algorithm before grouping training samples. In Section 2, we study the grouping of training samples of the algorithm by their separate clustering according to the types of recognized signals. An assessment of its effectiveness is given. The results of the work are briefly disclosed in the general conclusions.	algorithms evaluation of solutions validity;cardiac diagnostics;cardiocycle; grouping of training samples; signal recognition algorithms	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9927020	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Ontological Framework for Constructing Hybrid Prognoses and Risk Assessment of Critical Conditions of Patients	10.1109/SmartIndustryCon57312.2023.10110768	The paper describes a cloud-based ontological framework for designing hybrid cloud software systems and services for predicting patient conditions and assessing the risk of critical conditions and events. The proposed solution is based on integrated semantic models for the formation of knowledge, documents, hypotheses and reasoned decisions in medicine. These complexes combine several types of sources for the formation of knowledge bases and various methods and approaches to solving such problems (mathematical modeling, machine learning, and knowledge engineering). For a group of diseases or a section of medicine, knowledge bases are formed about diseases that have passed the verification procedure or that doctors are ready to trust a priori. The means of declarative description of the rules of interpretation of knowledge about the dynamics of the development of diseases and numerical values from predictive models are provided.	risk assessment;forecast; declarative knowledge; framework;explanation generation;decision support system	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10110768	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
GNSS software defined receiver pseudorange error assessment	10.1109/MetroSea5217.7.2021.9611623	SDR approach, applied to the field of GNSS, allows the implementation of high customizable low-cost GNSS Software Defined receivers. These can reveal as useful tools for navigation algorithms prototyping. In the FOSS scenario the most interesting SDR appears to be GNSS-SDR. In this paper we evaluate GPS L1 pseudorange error GNSS observations acquired by SDR; for this purpose a low-cost COTS u-blox GNSS receiver has been employed as term of comparison. Preliminary results suggest that SDR pseudorange are noisier than u-blox ones and this will probably reflect in the degradation of the single point solutions.	GNSS-SDR;GNSS;GPS; SDR;low-cost;FOSS; pseudorange error assessment;open-source	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9611623	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software

FACT - Fine grained Assessment of web page Credibility	10.1109 /TENCON. 2019.8929515	With more than a trillion web pages, there is a plethora of content available for consumption. Search Engine queries invariably lead to overwhelming information, parts of it relevant and some others irrelevant. Often the information provided can be conflicting, ambiguous, and inconsistent contributing to the loss of credibility of the content. In the past, researchers have proposed approaches for credibility assessment and enumerated factors influencing the credibility of web pages. In this work, we detailed a WEBCred framework for automated genre-aware credibility assessment of web pages. We developed a tool based on the proposed framework to extract web page features instances and identify genre a web page belongs to while assessing its Genre Credibility Score (GCS). We validated our approach on 'Information Security' dataset of 8,550 URLs with 171 features across 7 genres. The supervised learning algorithm, Gradient Boosted Decision Tree classified genres with 88.75% testing accuracy over 10 fold cross-validation, an improvement over the current benchmark. We also examined our approach on 'Health' domain web pages and had comparable results. The calculated GCS correlated 69% with crowdsourced Web Of Trust (WOT) score and 13% with algorithm based Alexa ranking across 5 Information security groups. This variance in correlation states that our GCS approach aligns with human way (WOT) as compared to algorithmic way (Alexa) of web assessment in both the experiments.	Web Page;Quality;Ranking; Credibility;Genre;Automated; Framework;Information Security	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8929515	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
AIMED: Agile, Integrative and Open Method for Open Educational Resources Development	10.1109/ICALT. 2017.104	This project is inserted in the research and practice areas that support the development of educational resources, such as, serious games and training simulation, to understand how they should be planned, developed, evaluated, validated and used for the learning and assessment purposes. In this study, we have proposed and specified an agile, integrative and open method for educational resources development, named AIMED, in a holistic and multidisciplinary approach. This approach integrates the areas of simulation modeling, game design, instructional design, principles of agile development methods, project management practices and content domain. AIMED is based on integration of DevJSTA methodology, for creation of serious games, and AM-OER method, for development of open educational resources. A feasibility study was done with serious game development, which should be used and evaluated by domain experts, as well as, the methodology will be used and validated in new case studies.	education;game;method; production	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8001747	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Technology-Enhanced Self-Regulated Learning: Assessment Support Through an Evaluation Centre	10.1109 /COMPASAC. 2018.00180	Learning in universities can be characterised as self-regulated learning [1]: students have to set learning goals, apply learning strategies, assess their progress, correct their strategies and redefine goals in cyclic phases. IT-based educational tools enhance lectures and provide numerous opportunities to support students in mastering the demands of self-regulated learning (e.g., by providing quizzes). The data basis of such tools can be utilised in order to support students during the phases of (self-)assessment and correction. Additionally, teachers can benefit from fine-grained analysis of individual lectures and assessments of the student group's conduct in order to improve their lectures. Both, teachers and students directly benefit from structured feedback on individual as well as group performance. However, the information required for beneficiary feedback to students and teachers must be presented in an ordered and well-prepared fashion. Evaluation centres can offer an automated extraction of important information based on the underlying data stored by the IT-based educational tools. In this short position paper we present a prototypical evaluation centre and discuss how it can assist teachers in improving their lectures, while it provides students with required information for correct self-assessment at the same time. The proposed evaluation centre was tested in different settings and preliminary results based on subjective user feedback can be extracted.	Self regulated Learning; Audience Response Systems;AMCS;Evaluation Center	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8377805	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Qualitative Assessment of Tangible-Intangible Outcomes and Challenges of Massive Open Online Courses	10.1109 /ASET56582. 2023.10180609	Given the growing popularity of Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) due to openness to support learning needs of massive audience, we cannot overlook the fact that MOOCs also suffer from poor completion and satisfaction rate. A 2018 Columbia University's Teachers College study on edX and Coursera courses shows that MOOC Certificate programs have a completion rate of 15% or less. It might seem easier, but creating MOOCs is anything but simple and MOOCs design and research face substantial hurdles in understanding individuals' technology-mediated epistemic practices. In this study, we attempted to reconstruct the episodic memories of members of Generations Y and Z, based on their unique interaction with MOOC platforms and gathered qualitative insights. The data was collected using semi-structured interviews based on purposeful sampling, and analysed thematically in Atlas software to translate usability perceptions and challenges faced by two population groups. The findings of the study suggest that MOOCs openness be redesigned by instructional designers to include personalization, content validation and automation processes for better retention, satisfaction and completion rates.	MOOCs;platform design; Millennials;Gen Z	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10180609	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software

Distress Study Through Machine-Learning Techniques	10.1109 /BIA52594. 2022.9831227	Machine learning as a contemporary approach in research provides an opportunity to cover and process a large amount of data. This is a condition for the synthesis of reliable characteristic descriptors of distress. The process of model selection is a factor in achieving the necessary adequacy and improving the quality of results. Age is a risky reason to take into account the development of cancer. This paper analyzed classification models for predicting distress in patients with the oncological disease, segmented into three age groups. Experimental results of a study conducted on the age of the patient and assessment of distress, using three methods of machine-learning are presented.	classification;machine learning;psychooncology; distress;age;SVM;Boosted; Bagged	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9831227	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem mavaliação
A Self-adaptive Indicator Selection Approach for Solving Credit Risk Assessment	10.1109 /COMPSAC542 36.2022.00249	Credit risk assessment, which aims at identifying high-risk users, plays a critical role in financial institutions. A common method is to use the greedy strategy to generate an interpretable rule set to classify all the users into high-risk or non-risk users. During each iteration, the greedy strategy utilizes a pre-defined indicator function to evaluate which rule is the best and then adds it to the rule set. However, in reality, the indicator function is designed manually and requires much domain knowledge and expert experience. Worse still, we need to design a suitable indicator for every situation, which is tedious and time-consuming work. This motivates us to propose a self-adaptive indicator that can be adapted to different situations without too much human intervention. In this paper, we see the indicator as a weighted sum of several sub-indicators. By tuning the weights, the indicator can be adapted to different situations automatically. That is, we transform this indicator selection problem into a weights tuning problem. To find the best weight of self-adaptive indicators, machine learning methods and black-box optimization are utilized. The experimental results demonstrated that our self-adaptive indicator can select a better rule set to identify more high-risk users compared to the human-defined indicator.	indicator selection;black-box optimization;machine learning;credit risk assessment	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9842539	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
A Community-based Computational and Engineering Sciences Initiative toward National Development (COESIND)	10.1109 /FIE43999. 2019.9028640	In this Innovative Practice Full Paper, we propose to establish a community-based learning initiative, which integrates recruitment, advisement, and retention programs with hands-on activities that supplement core curriculum for cohorts of students in the STEM fields - from recruiting through graduation and placement into the workforce. This initiative is designed in three phases: the pilot phase, the alliance phase, and the backbone phase. This project is aimed at the pilot phase; however, its focus does not end when the piloting is over, but rather, it is intended to integrate with other pilot programs into building regional alliances. Through the regional alliances, this proposed pilot initiative is planned to become part of the national backbone program, which aims at producing well-prepared, underrepresented graduates into the STEM-related workforce. Because the percentage of women and minorities (African-American, Hispanics, and Native Americans) in STEM-related workforce is so small, the COESIND program is designed to broaden the participation of these groups. To do so, a community of the eight campuses of Chattahoochee Technical College, the five campuses of Georgia-Perimeter College, the Girls, Inc. of Greater Atlanta, Georgia, Young Women's Christian Association (YWCA) of Greater Atlanta, and three area high schools in Cobb County, all in the metropolitan area of Atlanta, Georgia, will participate in the COESIND program. A Kennesaw State University (KSU) CS mentorship program, The Girls, Inc.'s summer camps have consistently attracted several girls over the years (Google IgniteCS). These institutions, collectively, have a significantly large population of African-American (A-A), Hispanics, and Girls/Women. Faculty from the College of Computing and Software Engineering (CCSE) and College of Engineering at KSU, located in Kennesaw, Georgia, will lead the proposed program. KSU, which recently merged with Southern Polytechnic State University (SPSU), located in Marietta, Georgia, now has a student population of 5,000 in these two Colleges. Moreover, KSU was recently classified as an R2 institution. The University also offers an array of STEM programs and has been ranked 7th among institutions that offer online courses and, at the time the merger, SPSU was ranked among the top three producers of African-American engineering technology graduates in the nation. With its prior implementations of two NSF-LSAMP programs, among other undergraduate-level student training, KSU is qualified to lead such an initiative. Our focus on Computing and Engineering sub-disciplines, among the many STEM-fields, is intentional: To focus on programs and activities where computing and engineering technologies are deployed as tools to solving real-world problems. In this paper, we will describe the motivation of the project and the detailed implementation plan of the pilot phase. The assessment plan along with the measurable outcomes, are summarized in the paper as well.	STEM-related workforce; community-based learning; under-representatives;hands-on experiences;Internet of Things (IoT)	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9028640	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software

Exploring the Relationship Between Collaborative Discourse, Programming Actions, and Cybersecurity and Computational Thinking Knowledge	10.1109 /TALE48869. 2020.9368459	Computational thinking (CT) skills are necessary for solving the real-world problems of today and are therefore being incorporated into K-12 curricula. Cybersecurity is of similar importance; however, it can be difficult for young learners to grasp the required concepts and use them to construct meaningful algorithms. We discuss our approach that combines a hands-on robotics platform with a block-based programming environment to facilitate the learning and application of cybersecurity and CT concepts. Throughout a week-long intervention, high school students were introduced to cybersecurity and CT and given the opportunity to apply this knowledge in a collaborative setting to solve security problems on the robotics platform with instructor and peer support. A series of competitions between groups of students further motivated students to translate their learned concepts to practice, often leading to breakthroughs as students incorporated new algorithms into their existing projects to counteract previous security flaws. We present evidence of the learning behaviors of several such groups through mixed-method case studies integrating data collected from learning performance, collaborative discourse, and analysis of program development. We discuss the impact of this approach on cybersecurity and CT learning and then present future directions for this work.	K-12 STEM education; educational robotics; cybersecurity;computational thinking;collaboration	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9368459	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Dentalcariesdetectionsystem Using R-CNN Algorithm	10.1109 /ICIE59379. 2023.10165754	One of the most prevalent chronic illnesses, dental caries, is brought on by developing bacteria, affects people of all ages. Currently restorative fillings are frequently utilised to treat dental cavities, although these treatments frequently fail. Meanwhile, numerous researchers have advanced a novel viewpoint that each case of caries needs to be handled separately after learning how caries risk varies among groups utilising the caries risk assessment. Deep learning approaches have produced exceptional diagnostic results radiology is the subject. The current study's objectives were to detect caries lesions, recognize distinct radiographic extensions on panoramic films using deep learning algorithms, and compare the results to those of skilled dentists. Methods: Three experienced dentists assessed 1160 dental panoramic films in total. The circles used to mark each caries lesion on the films were combined to form the reference dataset. On dental panoramic radiographs, deep learning approaches were able to recognise and classify caries lesions in a manner that was comparable to that of expert dentists. It is important to investigate the effects of using these expert neural networks for deciding how to diagnose diseases and therapy.	Caries detection/ diagnosis/preventative;Deep learning;CNN;R-CNN;MLP; Gan's	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10165754	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Students' Use and Non-Use of GAI tools in Revising Penetration Testing Reports	10.1109 /TALE62452. 2024.10834334	Penetration testing reports document cybersecurity vulnerabilities discovered and recommendations to remediate them. Thus, the reports need to be written clearly and structured for replication of test results, decision-making and action by a company's senior management, IT management and IT technical staff. This study aims to explore students' decision to use or not use genAI tools by examining their perceptions on using genAI tools, reasons for the use or non-use of genAI to revise their drafts for clarity and conciseness, cohesion and coherence, relevance to the audience, and professionalism and tone, their learning outcomes and the usefulness of the workshop. The students participated in a three-hour workshop embedded in a regular module delivered via zoom. During the workshop, the students were given the option to use or not use any genAI tools to help them perform the revision tasks in the workshop. The students performed the revision tasks in lab group teams and uploaded their revised drafts to the discussion forum in the learning management system for further feedback by the faculty. There was no advance support to students regarding any genAI tool as the aim of the study was to explore the above-mentioned aspects of their current use or non-use of genAI tools. They responded to an online survey at the end of the workshop. The findings revealed that the students were positive about the benefits of using genAI in helping them revise their penetration testing reports. This awareness, however, did not sway some students who chose not to use genAI tools as they wanted to understand and perform the task using their own thinking process. The genAI users mainly used ChatGPT and Copilot to perform the revision tasks. They found these tools helpful in assisting them to generate ideas, structure the report and perform the four revision tasks. Furthermore, they used these tools even though they were aware that moderate levels of editing on genAI's output were required. The findings also showed that both groups of students mentioned similar learning outcomes from the workshop. However, the emphasis in the learning outcomes mentioned differed for both groups. This reflects that the critical elements in writing pedagogy with or without genAI tools might be students' content and language proficiencies besides the ownership of their writing process.	student perceptions;level of use of genAI tools; penetration testing reports; revising;learning outcomes	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10834334	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software

Classification of Motor Unit Action Potential Using Transfer Learning for the Diagnosis of Neuromuscular Diseases	10.1109 /ICSS54381. 2022.9782209	In the assessment of neuromuscular illnesses, the motor unit action potentials (MUPs) in an electromyographic (EMG) signal are an important information source. Many methodologies in the time and frequency domains have been employed for quantitative research of EMG data since recent improvements in software EMG technology. The use of several feature extraction methods to describe MUP morphology is investigated in this article. Single classifier characteristics were used to investigate classification algorithms. To predict the class label for each MUAP, a distance weighted K-nearest neighbour (KNN) classifier was applied (Myopathic, Neuropathic, or Normal). The proposed techniques perform brilliantly in terms of overall classification accuracy, according to an exhaustive analysis of the clinical EMG database for the categorization of neuromuscular disorders.	Motor unit action potentials (MUPs);Electromyographic (EMG) signal;Distance weightedK-nearest neighborhood (KNN) classifier	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9782209	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem engenharia de software
Representation of abstract concepts: Differences across computing disciplines	10.1109/FIE. 2015.7344411	Computer Science has evolved towards a discipline with different branches. Software is designed, produced and linked taking into account different viewpoints. This process typically involves multidisciplinary teams: Front End Developers, (OO)Programmers, Database Engineers. Software developers, who were educated in different computing disciplines, meet on the shop floor, where they link together software that was designed from different viewpoints. In this paper, the emphasis is on human characteristics, rather than on the formal properties of programming and modeling languages. Do the involved computing practitioners refer to the same concepts when they use the same words? A preliminary version of this study [1] addressed the assessment of differences in mental representations of abstract entities involved in programming and modeling. In this extended version we report the results of an experiment, designed to compare mental representations of abstract concepts with mental models described in the literature. We point at differences between groups of students, enrolled in different computing curricula, and explore possible explanations.	computer science education; engineering education research;human factors	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7344411	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	não tem colab
Research on Evaluation Model of System Optimization Using Statistical Metrology and Coefficient Variation Method	10.1109 /ICCASIT53235 .2021.9633706	With the rapid development of society, the healthy and sustainable higher education system is particularly important. As the level of higher education varies in different countries, it is therefore necessary to assess the health of the higher education system comprehensively, in order to make up for its deficiencies. The aim of this contribution is to establish a series of models for assessment, as well as put forward specific policy recommendations to help improve the education index of designated countries or regions. In this work, we collect plenty of data related to higher education. Based on Principal Component Analysis (PCA), we select 20 second-level indicators out of 36 initial indicators. Then, we divide these 20 indicators into 5 groups and construct a three-level evaluation index system to get Higher Education Evaluation Index (HEEI). Next, we determined weight of each indicator using both the Entropy Weight Method (EWM) and Coefficient Variation Method (CVM). And then we set three levels for the HEEI through K-means algorithm to establish the Higher Education Evaluation Model.	Higher Education System; Assessment of Education; EWM	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9633706	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem ES
Estrangement between Classes: Test Coverage-Based Assessment of Coupling Strength between Pairs of Classes	10.1109 /QUATIC. 2014.13	This work discusses a new metric, Estrangement Between Classes (EBC), that is derived by executing tests. This metric is based on the statement coverage of tests and provides assessment of the strength of associations between classes. We demonstrate with an illustrative example of the popular Apache Email component that this new metric can provide additional information in reverse engineered class diagrams by highlighting missing associations in these diagrams, the strength of existing associations and utility classes. It can also be effective in indicating the important design elements in cases of over-engineered or dead code. The proposed metric can be potentially used in the context of agile methods of software development during refactoring and program maintenance as comprehension aid. Since EBC is based on tests, no additional effort is required by developers who follow the Test-Driven approach or generally develop tests.	Coupling metrics;dynamic metrics;test coverage; software design;agile methods;UML	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=6984092	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem ES

Towards a Normalized Trustworthiness Approach to Enhance Security in On-Line Assessment	10.1109/CISIS.2014.22	This paper proposes an approach to enhance information security in on-line assessment based on a normalized trustworthiness model. Among collaborative e-Learning drawbacks which are not completely solved, we have investigated information security requirements in on-line assessment (e-assessment). To the best of our knowledge, security requirements cannot be reached with technology alone, therefore, new models such as trustworthiness approaches can complete technological solutions and support e-assessment requirements for e-Learning. Although trustworthiness models can be defined and included as a service in e-assessment security frameworks, there are multiple factors related to trustworthiness which cannot be managed without normalization. Among these factors we discuss trustworthiness multiple sources, different data source formats, measure techniques and other trustworthiness factors such as rules, evolution or context. Hence, in this paper, we justify why trustworthiness normalization is needed and a normalized trustworthiness model is proposed by reviewing existing normalization procedures for trustworthy values applied to e-assessments. Eventually, we examine the potential of our normalized trustworthiness model in a real online collaborative learning course.	trustworthiness; normalization; e-assessment; information security; collaborative learning	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=6915510	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem ES
Engaging undergraduate students in a biomedical research project: a virtual collaboration across institutes under the pandemic environment	10.1109/FIE49875.2021.9637452	In this work-in-progress (innovative practices) paper, we introduced a biomedical engineering research project to students in our primarily undergraduate institute (PUI) where sources and research activities are limited. Here, we present the motivation, background, best practices, initial assessment, and future work. Through virtual collaboration with a research institute, the project helped engage students in research activity, broaden the current scope of our project-based pedagogy, and address the typical challenges in online learning. In this semester-long project, a group of seven students from two schools developed a highly coupled Simulink model that captured the behaviors of the human cardiovascular system. The model aimed to study the aging effect of the aorta on cardiac power and blood pressure. Regarding the project design, we introduced the concept from the software engineering, i.e., "Agile Principle" and "Minimal Viable Product". Students started to develop a working model of one component (i.e., O2 and CO2 exchange model in the tissue) from the entire system. Through multiple iterations, the model was debugged, expanded, and polished. We recognized the critical role of communication in the virtual space. Besides routine team meetings on Zoom, we also mentored students with model debugging time through the Slack platform. Students developed their professional skills through weekly learning journals where ideas, reflection, confusion can be shared with faculty. The preliminary assessment indicates positive impacts, such as growth mindset, time management, and more career options.	Project-based Learning; Undergraduate Research; Virtual Space Collaboration	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9637452	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem ES
Teaching Database Querying in the Cloud	10.1109/FIE43999.2019.9028440	Cloud-based resources for students to create and query databases can be leveraged in a traditional database curriculum as well as in updated curriculum to support data science. This paper describes processes to apply for a Google Cloud Platform grant for educators, to establish student accounts, build a SQL database in the cloud and connect to it, and also use SQL to query a big data platform for millions of records in open source data sets. These freely available, industrial strength resources can be used for teaching SQL and database creation, as well as for introducing more advanced topics such as physical design, performance comparison, and data warehouse creation and population. Associated learning objectives, assignments, and assessment of student learning and perspectives are presented.	database education; SQL querying; data warehouse design; columnar databases; physical database design	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9028440	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es
CONAN: Diagnosing Batch Failures for Cloud Systems	10.1109/ICSE-SEIP58684.2023.00018	Failure diagnosis is critical to the maintenance of large-scale cloud systems, which has attracted tremendous attention from academia and industry over the last decade. In this paper, we focus on diagnosing batch failures, which occur to a batch of instances of the same subject (e.g., API requests, VMs, nodes, etc.), resulting in degraded service availability and performance. Manual investigation over a large volume of high-dimensional telemetry data (e.g., logs, traces, and metrics) is labor-intensive and time-consuming, like finding a needle in a haystack. Meanwhile, existing proposed approaches are usually tailored for specific scenarios, which hinders their applications in diverse scenarios. According to our experience with Azure and Microsoft 365 – two world-leading cloud systems, when batch failures happen, the procedure of finding the root cause can be abstracted as looking for contrast patterns by comparing two groups of instances, such as failed vs. succeeded, slow vs. normal, or during vs. before an anomaly. We thus propose CONAN, an efficient and flexible framework that can automatically extract contrast patterns from contextual data. CONAN has been successfully integrated into multiple diagnostic tools for various products, which proves its usefulness in diagnosing real-world batch failures.	Diagnosis; Incident; Cloud Systems; Contrast Pattern	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10172587	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es

A Named Entity Recognition Based Approach for Privacy Requirements Engineering	10.1109 /REW53955. 2021.00072	The presence of experts, such as a data protection officer (DPO) and a privacy engineer is essential in Privacy Requirements Engineering. This task is carried out in various forms including threat modeling and privacy impact assessment. The knowledge required for performing privacy threat modeling can be a serious challenge for a novice privacy engineer. We aim to bridge this gap by developing an automated approach via machine learning that is able to detect privacy-related entities in the user stories. The relevant entities include (1) the Data Subject, (2) the Processing, and (3) the Personal Data entities. We use a state-of-the-art Named Entity Recognition (NER) model along with contextual embedding techniques. We argue that an automated approach can assist agile teams in performing privacy requirements engineering techniques such as threat modeling, which requires a holistic understanding of how personally identifiable information is used in a system. In comparison to other domain-specific NER models, our approach achieves a reasonably good performance in terms of precision and recall.	privacy requirements engineering;named entity recognition;user stories;agile development	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9582331	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es
AI Integrated Administration tool design with ML Technology for Smart Education System	10.1109 /ICACITE60783 .2024.10616455	Artificial intelligence (AI) is increasingly the solution for higher education institutions wanting streamlined administrative operations in a time when technological change and new introductions are fast-paced. This paper takes a look at the prospective changes brought about by an AI-powered administration vis-à-vis the rise of technological advances in a higher education context, from operations and the use of resources to mechanisms for decision-making specifically in Cagayan State University, Carig Campus. AI adoption could revolutionize the traditional administrative job workflows within universities and colleges, helping it provide solutions to complex challenges for the whole world's university and college ecosystem. AI also allows institutions to automate the running of routine administrative operations, such as student enrollment, course scheduling, and financial management, among others. For instance, the automation process of some selected routine administrative operations-comprising a very wide list of activities, such as student enrollment, course scheduling, and many others-can be implemented in institutions that use AI algorithms. More so, AI-powered analytic tools help in the optimization of resource allocation in higher education institutions. AI systems can give actionable insights into trends in enrollment, performance metrics of their student body, and demographics of students. The data-driven approach, therefore, allows institutions to be efficient in resource allocation and predictive future demands that will best fit in the students' and stakeholders' educational programs for evolution. Besides, artificial intelligence-based decision support systems offer real-time intelligence to the administrators in the process of making informed decisions.	Artificial Intelligence;Higher Education;Administration; Operations;Streamline; Technological Advances	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10616455	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es
Secure Codacity with Evolution: Visualizing Security Vulnerability Evolution of Software Systems	10.1109 /ICTer51097. 2020.9325429	The analysis of large-scale software and finding security vulnerabilities while its evolving is difficult without using supplementary tools, because of the size and complexity of today's systems. However just by looking at a report, doesn't transmit the overall picture of the system in terms of security vulnerabilities and its evolution throughout the project lifecycle. Software visualization is a program comprehension technique used in the context of the present and explores large amounts of information precisely. For the analysis of security vulnerabilities of complex software systems, Secure Codacity with Evolution is an interactive 3D visualization tool that can be utilized. Its studies techniques and methods are used for graphically illustrating security aspects and the evolution of software. The Main goal of the proposed Framework defined as uplift, simplify, and clarify the mental representation that a software engineer has of a software system and its evolution in terms of its security. Static code was visualised based on a city metaphor, which represents classes as buildings and packages as districts of a city. Identified Vulnerabilities were represented in a different color according to the severity. To visualize a number of different aspects, A large variety of options were given. Users can evaluate the evolution of the security vulnerabilities of a system on several versions using Matrices provided which will help users go get an overall understanding about security vulnerabilities varies with different versions of software. This framework was implemented using SonarQube for software vulnerability detection and ThreeJs for implementing the City Metaphor. The evaluation results evidently show that our framework surpasses the existing tools in terms of accuracy, efficiency and usability.	3D software visualization; Vulnerability Evolution;Re-engineering;Vulnerability Analysis;3D graphics;human-computer interaction	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9325429	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es

The TESI Project: An Adaptive Personalized System for Creating Expression Tools in Social Inclusion of Disadvantage Learners	10.1109/CIST.2018.8596475	This paper deals with an Adaptive Personalized System for Creating Expression Tools in Social Inclusion of Learners with Verbal Communication Disabilities. The European Union (EU) project TESI - Tools of Expression for Social Inclusion (TESI), focuses on social integration of people with verbal communication disorders at risk of social isolation. It is intended to conceptualize and develop social competences (SC) related to personal, social and professional development of people with verbal communication disorders through the creation of an adaptive, affordable and easy-to-use software solution. To develop and put into practice the TESI Project, international partners from different backgrounds, specialties and educational levels, work closely with 9 associated partners. The description of this research project, now in its initial stage, allows us to reflect on the role of this technology-based solution in supporting disadvantaged learners, examine the TESI conceptual model and software system and the process of validation it through a pilot study.	Mobile learning;software mobile computing;ICT support;social inclusion;disadvantage learners	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8596475	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es
Post-Pandemic Hybrid Work in Software Companies: Findings from an Industrial Case Study		Context. Software professionals learned from their experience during the pandemic that most of their work can be done remotely, and now software companies are expected to adopt hybrid work models to avoid the resignation of talented professionals who require more flexibility and work-life balance. However, hybrid work is a spectrum of flexible work arrangements, and currently, there are no well-established hybrid work configurations to be followed in the post-pandemic period. Goal. We investigated how software engineers are experiencing the post-pandemic hybrid work landscape, aiming to understand the factors that influence their choices between remote and in-office work. Method. We explored a large South American company by collecting quantitative and qualitative data from 545 software professionals who are currently navigating diverse hybrid work arrangements tailored to their individual and team requirements. Findings. Our study revealed an array of factors that significantly impact hybrid work within the software industry, including individual preferences, work-life balance, commute time, social interactions, productivity, and more. Team dynamics, project demands, client expectations, and organizational strategies also play an important role in shaping the complex landscape of hybrid work configurations in software engineering. Conclusions. In summary, the success of hybrid work models depends on balancing individual preferences, team dynamics, and organizational strategies. Our study demonstrated that, at present, there is no one-size-fits-all individuals approach to hybrid work in the software industry. CCS CONCEPTS • Social and professional topics	software professionals;hybrid work;post-pandemic;case study	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10556484	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Unintended Consequences when the Engineering Design Team is Noninclusive: An Exploration of the Literature	10.1109/EDUCON5253.2022.9766789	Accessibility and equity have become increasingly important in recent years. Inclusive Engineering Design is an approach to design that “enables and draws from the full range of human diversity” [1]. Through showcasing a number of examples, this paper demonstrated the need for engineers to embrace inclusive design principles in all fields of engineering. The examples used in the paper centre around Urban Planning and Housing, Unconscious Bias in Artificial Intelligence and Automotive Engineering – testing the car design. Urban Planning compared a housing development in Brazil with that of one in Vienna. The one in Brazil was a re-housing design project that took no input from the residents that were to be relocated from the favelas, resulting in their lives being upended. Vienna’s housing project was co-designed with the residents to ensure a better quality of life for all. Section III on Unconscious Bias in Artificial Intelligence showcased a range of examples where lack of diversity on the design team had a detrimental effect on people. People of colour were labelled as gorillas by Google’s photo application; gender classification worked best on white males and worst on darker females; criminal risk assessment software rated black defendants as 77% more likely of committing a future violent crime and cardiovascular disease (CVD) was not being captured in women using AI, as CVD presents differently in males and females [2]. Test dummies in Automotive Engineering have traditionally been designed using dimensions and physique of a male body. Because a woman’s body is biologically different to that of a man, women are therefore 17% more likely to die in a car crash than a man and 47% more likely to be seriously injured. Pregnant women and the older generation are even worse. Underrepresented groups in engineering, such as females, people of colour and those with disabilities continue to be affected by the design choices that were and are being made by engineers worldwide. This paper highlights why design methodologies need to change to be more inclusive. While the consequences of the designs showcased in the paper are unintended, they still have a resonating impact that goes beyond their intended use.	Engineering;inclusive design;design team;bias;gender bias	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9766789	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es

Performance comparison of visualization-based malware detection and classification techniques	10.1109/ICET56601.2022.10004652	Cybercriminals use malware or malicious software to cause harm to the victim. Malware is a continuous source of concern for security teams. Malware analysis techniques, including static, dynamic, hybrid, and memory analysis, are used to comprehend the behavior and its impact. The aforementioned malware analysis techniques require domain knowledge to extract the artifacts from suspicious files, which is not always possible. A visualization approach, in which malware files are transformed into images, is one of the recently used techniques by researchers for malware detection and classification. In this paper, we apply four widely used techniques based on the visualization using a new dataset of memory dump files of malware families and benign classes. These visualization techniques include a histogram of oriented gradients (HOG) with multilayer perceptron (MLP), convolutional neural network (CNN) with pretrained weight of visual geometry group 16 (VGG), Transfer learning of VGG16 with support vector machine (SVM), and integration of global image descriptor (GIST) and HOG with SVM. Among the selected techniques, CNN with a pretrained weight of VGG16 outperformed the other techniques in terms of accuracy, precision, recall, and f1-score. Apart from the performance metrics, the results of selected techniques are also analyzed in terms of computational cost and memory utilization.	Machine Learning;Deep Learning;Static Analysis; Dynamic Analysis;Memory Analysis	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10004652	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Problem Patterns in Study Processes and Recommended Remedies for Students	10.1109/GECon62014.2024.10734031	In many computer science related bachelor degree programs - as well as in the entire area of science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM) - in Germany, students are known to struggle in various ways, quite often right from the early stages of their studies. If unattended, these initially struggling students will eventually drop out, more or less frustrated and without a degree. However, as lecturers, we do see positive potential in many of these struggling students. We are convinced that we could save many of them from dropping out early, if we were able to provide them with the appropriate support. As our cohorts are very heterogeneous, we need to tailor this support to different needs. Therefore, we need to identify typical problem patterns as well as their root causes. To achieve this, we analyze student behavior in our students' cohorts, based on information that we gather through learning analytics on student activity data, by quantitative surveys, as well as from qualitative interviews with students and alumni, and from workshops with students and student tutors. From these insights, we develop a model of typical stages and behavioral patterns in first-semester students, that we can use both in counseling and as a basis for developing teaching interventions that support struggling students appropriately for their individual needs.	Heterogeneity;self reflection; student experience;student development	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10734031	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es
Rebooting the System and Building New Futures: Supporting Women's Comeback in IT		Despite the slow growth in the number of women in the IT sector, there has been a notable increase in the technology events and communities explicitly aimed at women. Recognizing the diverse nature of women interested in entering or remaining in the IT field, it is crucial to understand the factors driving them. This study addresses the need to understand the diverse motivations of women seeking to enter or continue their careers in IT. By analyzing online survey data $(N=513)$ of Finnish women career-changers, our research explores the distinct motivational factors that attract career changers compared to retraining those already working in the IT industry. We also investigate the influence of 'Women in Tech' programs and communities in supporting these career transitions. Findings indicate varied motivational drivers between the two groups, underscoring the importance of tailored attraction and retention strategies. The study also reveals the significant role of 'Women in Tech' kind of initiatives in offering essential support and resources for women navigating their way into the IT field. Overall, our attraction and retention theory of women in the IT sector can assist educational providers and companies in better understanding career-changers and women in technology and, in that way, support the work to bring women back into the IT industry after decades of underrepresentation in the field. CCS CONCEPTS •Social and professional topics \rightarrow Information science education; Computer and information systems training; Software engineering education; Gender;•Human-centered computing \rightarrow Empirical studies in ubiquitous and mobile computing;•Information systems \rightarrow Mobile information processing systems. ACM Reference Format: Sonja M. Hyrynsalmi. 2024. Rebooting the System and Building New Futures: Supporting Women's Comeback in IT. In 2024 ACM/IEEE Workshop on Gender Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion in Software Engineering (GE@ICSE '24), April 20, 2024, Lisbon, Portugal. ACM, New York, NY, USA, 8 pages. https://doi.org/10.1145/3643785.3648485	Software Engineering Communities;Career-Change;Women in STEM; Gender bias;Talent attraction;Talent retention	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10647146	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Machine Learning in Cyber Security Analytics using NSL-KDD Dataset	10.1109 /TAAI54685. 2021.00057	Classification is the procedure to recognize, understand, as well as group ideas and objects into given categories. Classification techniques adopt training data patterns to predict the likelihood that subsequent data will classify into one of the given categories. Classification techniques utilize a variety of algorithms to classify future datasets through training data patterns. In current society, many network attacks continue to carry out various types of attacks. This work performs data pre-processing and uses Python with machine learning algorithms to analyze the NSL-KDD data set. We use various machine learning methods, such as decision trees, random forests, Naive Bayes, KNN, Gradient Boosted Trees, and SVM to analyze the confusion matrix and predict the accuracy. We also draw the ROC curve and the AUC area. We calculate the ACC accuracy and make a simple assessment of the quality of different algorithms. Test results show that through data pre-processing, machine learning algorithms can be performed with extremely high accuracy.	Python;Cyber security; Machine learning; Classification;NSL-KDD	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9778058	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es
Development of an Algorithm for Automated Assessment of Technical Condition of a Highvoltage Circuit Breaker	10.1109 /RPA59835. 2023.10319825	Automation of processes in the power industry — is a set of software and hardware tools that ensure the normal operation of equipment and monitoring of the power system.	Analytical models; Automation;Machine learning algorithms;Circuit breakers; Data models;Mathematical models;Software;Power systems;Integrated circuit modeling;Task analysis	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10319825	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es, colab
TaintSQL: Dynamically Tracking Fine-Grained Implicit Flows for SQL Statements	10.1109 /ISSRE55969. 2022.00012	To address software engineering tasks such as security risk assessment, software change government, and access control in database applications, taint analysis approaches for SQL statements have been commonly adopted for tracking information flows in these applications. However, existing taint analysis approaches cannot track implicit flows (i.e., control dependencies between sources and sinks) for SQL statements, facing the challenges of native/unmanaged code and database management system (DBMS) complexity. To address these challenges, in this paper, we propose TaintSQL, a cell-level dynamic taint analysis (DTA) framework (maintaining a taint tag for each table cell) to track fine-grained implicit flows for SQL statements. Our TaintSQL framework includes two novel techniques, namely MutalF and MocklF. MutalF aims to track implicit flows with causal relationships, whereas MocklF aims to dynamically track implicit flows at runtime. We implement the two techniques of TaintSQL and evaluate them on a set of test subjects to assess their effectiveness and efficiency. The evaluation results show that both techniques effectively track fine-grained implicit flows for SQL statements with reasonable runtime overhead. The F1 scores of MutalF and MocklF are 96.2% and 97.9%, respectively. We also conduct an industrial study of MutalF in an international IT company (which serves over 1 billion global users and 80 million merchants). The positive feedback from the software engineers also demonstrates the practicability of the TaintSQL framework and the MutalF technique in industrial settings.	implicit flow;taint analysis; SQL statement	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9978977	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Predicting Risk Matrix in Software Development Projects using BERT and K-Means	10.23919 /EECSI56542. 2022.9946637	This study aimed to create a risk matrix model for a software development project with 60,000 datasets from the Stack Overflow Question on Kaggle.com. BERT has been used for sentence embedding techniques to represent entire sentences and their semantic information as vectors, K-Means has been used to group sentences and calculate the frequency of occurrence so that the probability is expressed in the vertical direction, and TextBlob estimates the severity of the impact with sentiment analysis represented in the horizontal direction. Validation with BERT on the cluster formed by K-Means by creating a classification text with 86% accuracy results with 30 epochs. The proposed risk matrix formation model is a novelty that can be integrated into the risk management framework. The model determines risk priorities, especially in software development projects.	BERT;k-means;risk matrix; stack overflow	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9946637	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Development of a joule metric information-measurement system for instant assessment of oral mucosa state	10.1109 /SIBIRCON56155. 2022.10017046	The aim of the research was to develop an information-measurement system for instant assessment of oral mucosa state and to carry out experimental tests on electrochemical parameters of saliva. An information-measuring system consisting of a four-electrode flow-type sensor, a measuring unit and a personal computer with software implementing an algorithm for processing and statistical evaluation of the obtained data was proposed. In the course of the research, the optimal parameters of the input effects were determined. Depending on the oral mucosa condition, the patients were divided into two groups: 1st - control group of patients with a healthy oral mucosa (n1=25); 2nd – research group of patients with inflammatory diseases of the oral mucosa (n2=25). The age of the patients ranged from 19 to 24 years old. On average, the value of the Q parameter in inflammation is 2.5 times higher than the average value of this indicator in patients with healthy mucosa due to the activation of biological processes that affect the electrochemical properties of saliva.	oral mucosa;oral mucosal lesions;stomatitis;oral candidiasis;electrochemical parameters;electrochemical information-measurement systems;sensor	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10017046	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es

A quality model for the systematic assessment of requirements traceability	10.1109/RE.2015.7320420	Traceability is an important quality of software requirements and allows to describe and follow their life throughout a development project. The importance of traceable requirements is reflected by the fact that requirements standards, safety regulations, and maturity models explicitly demand for it. In practice, traceability is created and maintained by humans, which make mistakes. In result, existing traces are potentially of dubious quality but serve as the foundation for high impact development decisions. We found in previous studies that practitioners miss clear guidance on how to systematically assess the quality of existing traces. In this paper, we review the elements involved in establishing traceability in a development project and derive a quality model that specifies per element the acceptable state (Traceability Gate) and unacceptable deviations (Traceability Problem) from this state. We describe and formally define how both, the acceptable states and the unacceptable deviations can be detected in order to enable practitioners to systematically assess their project's traceability. We evaluated the proposed model through an expert survey. The participating experts considered the quality model to be complete and attested that its quality criteria are of high relevance. We further found that the experts weight the occurrence of different traceability problems with different criticality. This information can be used to quantify the impact of traceability problems and to prioritize the assessment of traceability elements.	requirements traceability; traceability problem classes; problem dependencies; assessment;inspection	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7320420	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Web-Based Performance Evaluation System Platform Using Rule-Based Algorithm	10.1109/ICIEE55102.2022.9778996	The project endeavored to design and develop a Web-based Performance Evaluation System with integration of rule-based algorithm that will analyze the performance of each reviewee based on the scores from their examination. The algorithm automatically provides suggested reading materials based on the result of the assessment. With this, the system will help the reviewees assess their own performance. The system was developed using Agile Methodology Model of Software Development. The software produced was tested using Alpha and Beta software tastings. The FURPS model was used to assess the software quality as perceived by the selected group of respondents. The system was found to be functional, meeting the designed functional requirements specifications.	performance evaluation; review center;electronics engineering;FURPS	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9778996	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es
Information System for Ergonomic Assessment of a Perspective Maneuverable Aircraft Cockpit	10.1109/APEIE52976.2021.9647651	The article is devoted to the ergonomic assessment of the crew workplaces of a promising maneuverable aircraft using the information system developed for these purposes. The assessment is based on a variety of human-machine-environment ergonomic indicators. The article provides description of the main groups of ergonomic indicators, discusses methods for the indicators assessment. The article discusses the use of an information system consisting of a database containing information on the ergonomic parameters of the developed workplaces of the crew of a promising maneuverable aircraft, and software for processing this information. The structure of the database is considered, methods of obtaining an integral ergonomic estimate are described. The analytical hierarchy process method is used as a method for obtaining an integral ergonomic assessment of the crew's workplaces; the article provides a general scheme of the method. The paper provides a general description of approaches to the design of the logical and physical structure of various database parts.	cockpit;workplace;ergonomic indicators;ergonomic assessment;database; method of analytical hierarchies	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9647651	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es
Experiments with personal ownership of quality at the University of Texas at El Paso	10.1109/FIE.2015.7344079	The lack of commitment to create quality work is a long-standing problem in education, and it is a direct negative driver of student performance, disturbing students' ability to: apply imparted concepts, build team quality work, and foster industry's economy. The quality of delivered work is poor mainly because students do not spend needed time and effort to review their own work; e.g., research papers, group projects, and assignments. At the University of Texas at El Paso (UTEP), experimental developments targeted students' commitment to create quality work, creating infrastructure to conduct personal reviews for different types of work products, and teaching students to conduct effective personal reviews of their own work. A partial implementation of check lists, review processes, and teaching material has been used in courses at UTEP. The work to be developed includes measuring time distributions of effort (time to build the product vs. time to correct the product), recording the defects injected in products, creating checklists based on the recorded defects, creating a process to review products, and defining a defect log. The goal is to create a habit within students to create quality work by using personal reviews to improve the quality of submitted work.	Quality;Personal Review; CMMI;Personal Software Process (PSP)	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7344079	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Designing and Developing a Resource Center for Primary and Secondary Computing Education Researchers	10.1109 /FIE44824. 2020.9274252	This full research paper considers the resources needed to meet the research and evaluation needs of the many efforts to incorporate computing education throughout primary and secondary schools. In order to support these efforts, we developed csedresearch.org, a site designed to serve as a resource center for primary and secondary computing education research. We first considered criteria and recommendations for resource centers previously established by others. We provide a general description of the purpose of the csedresearch.org as well as a description of how we used quantitative and qualitative methods over numerous phases of development (pre-concept/research, concept, alpha, and beta, launch) to ensure that it meets the needs of potential users. We discuss how the current product compares against the general criteria for resource centers, its original intentions and expectations, and how it has fared through the phases of development one normally expects from a digital resource center. As the resource center evolves, we continue to seek feedback and resources to further meet the needs of the community. We also discuss the data that is being collected and could be collected to further benefit the community to define not only what educational practices work best overall, but what works best for particular demographic groups, including underrepresented groups in computing. And finally, we are faced with the challenge for maintaining the information so that remains robust and current.	Education;Software;Testing; Interviews;Instruments; Computer science;Buildings	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9274252	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Automated IoT-Based Performance Assessments Through Activity Recognition and Semantic Evaluation in Smart Learning Environments	10.1109 /ICCAD60883. 2024.10553999	In this paper, we utilize internet-of-things and semantic technologies to automate the assessment of socio-technical behaviors in engineering students in a circuits laboratory setting. Socio-technical learning objectives in engineering courses, such as the ability to make ethically informed judgments and the proactive observance of safety procedures, are challenging to assess for many reasons, among them being that their assessment can be time consuming to administer and can be subjective. In this work, we propose a novel framework that includes perception and data aggregation layers that utilize both sensor and video monitoring approaches to perform activity recognition, an ontology schema for representing and relating the data, and a semantic query layer that reasons out the desired performance evaluation. Finally, our work presents conclusive data supporting the advantages of using IoT and semantic technologies in automating the assessment of socio-technical learning outcomes in engineering courses.	activity recognition; automated assessment; internet of things;semantic reasoning;knowledge-based; socio-technical student outcomes;smart learning environment	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10553999	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Design of Portable Industrial Automation Education Training Kit Compatible for IR 4.0	10.1109 /ICSPC47137. 2019.9068090	A myriad of existing education training kits are easily accessible, however lacks practicality as they require a large space to operate. This calls for a more portable and smaller training kit to facilitate the teaching and learning experiences. It is also necessary to ensure that the new design meets the requirement of the fourth Industrial Revolution besides assisting teaching and learning. A study was conducted using the results of students undertaking Industrial Automation Course in UNITEN. The data was obtained from assessment results when only simulation software was used, and simulation software is complimented by a training kit. The results indicated 1.6% and 18.0% increment in the number of students obtaining A+ respectively. This shows that students who are exposed to both simulation and also sensors and actuators wiring learnt better compared to the control group. Ultimately, this paper presents the development of a portable programmable logic controller (PLC)-based training kit for industrial automation course. This portable PLC training kit is only 470 × 370 × 270 mm in dimension, which is equivalent to a cabin size baggage, and weigh below 10 kg, making it the most suitable to teach smart sensor application for IR 4.0.	PLC Trainer;Portability; Intelligent Sensor;Teaching and Learning;Industrial Automation Training kit	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9068090	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Assessment of the quality of students training for IT-departments	10.1109 /IVForum. 2017.8246043	The task of high schools students target preparation for divisions of industrial enterprises information technologies is considered in the paper. The expediency of interdisciplinary project student group creation for realization of innovative projects is shown. The application of the DEA methodology for assessing the effectiveness of mastering competencies and the requirements of professional standards is described.	system analysis;education; training quality assessment; project management	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8246043	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es

KIAAA: An AI Assistant for Teaching Programming in the Field of Automation	10.1109 /INDIN51400. 2023.10218157	Especially in highly interdisciplinary fields such as automation engineering, contemporary programming education with tailored assignments and individual feedback is a major challenge for educational institutions due to the increasing number of students per teacher and the ever-increasing demand for computer science professionals. To address this gap, we present "KIAAA" an AI Assistant for Automation Engineering Teaching, a work-in-progress approach for an integrated, customized, and AI-based learning support system for automation and programming courses based on instructor-defined course objectives. Thereby in the KIAAA system, the individual knowledge level of the students is determined and individually tailored virtual learning scenarios are generated based on the knowledge and learning profile of the students. These are iteratively adapted based on the answers given. To achieve this, KIAAA uses several AI components, a hybrid rule-based scenario generation component, a Help-DKT-based cognitive model, and a solution assessor that uses a combination of traditional code analysis methods and AI-based analyses methods for automated programming task assessment. These components are the main parts of KIAAA to generate customized programming scenarios as well as visualization and simulation based on a modern game and physics engine.	intelligent tutoring system;ai-based adaptive task generation;automated programming task assessment	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10218157	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Utilizing Unsupervised kNN on Customer Risk Assessment for Banking	10.1109 /ICSTE57415. 2022.00022	Facing the rise of anti-money laundering and anticapital terrorism, financial institutions spend a lot of money and time every year to conduct Know Your Customer (KYC) verification for customers. Therefore, we devise an approach to carefully handle the tasks of data processing. Specifically, we choose to adopt instance-based learning in this work to consider each target customer one at a time. Also, we separate all the data features into profile and transaction ones. Based on the concept that customers of similar profiles tend to have similar transaction behaviors, we calculate the outlier score of each customer. Only when a suspicious customer having a high outlier score is determined, further actions of manual screening should be taken. Moreover, our approach is explainable as statistics of the corresponding profile and transaction features are reported. With these carefully designed means, our approach helps to significantly improve and speed up the whole KYC process.	anomaly detection;customer risk assessment;instance-based learning;k-nearest neighbors;know your customer	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10071299	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es
Ordinal scales and feedbacks in educational process of computer control of electrical technology	10.1109 /RTUCON. 2016.7763151	This paper provides the education technique for students of Computer Control of Electrical Technology specialty of Riga Technical University. This method is used for creation of the ordinal scales, grouping and evaluation of students work during the whole semester in software-oriented subjects. The special website is developed to organize data collection, data analysis and feedback from students. It is successfully used during the last eight years and allows controlling and objectively evaluating students' results by multiple criteria.	education;ordinal scales; multi-criteria decision making;assessment	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7763151	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Employing git in the classroom	10.1109 /WCCAIS. 2014.6916568	Git is a well established, well received source version control system for the software development community and beyond. In an effort to better expose my students to the purpose and process of version control, I introduced Git as a mechanism to both disseminate in-class exercises and worked solutions as well as facilitate the submission of continuous assessment. I document in this paper my experience of the experiment and describe the steps required to marshal free third party services to support the tasks undertaken by students and lecturer.	course management;version control;learning management system	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=6916568	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Automatic Rule Generation of Fuzzy Systems: A Comparative Assessment on Software Defect Prediction	10.1109/UBMK. 2018.8566479	Fuzzy rule base systems are expert systems rely on fuzzy set theory. Here the knowledge of human expert is transferred to the artificial model via fuzzy rules. Therefore, preciseness, completeness and coverage of fuzzy rules in a fuzzy system is vital for the accuracy and plausibility of fuzzy reasoning. However, in such cases where the human expert is unable to supply the rules sufficiently, data-based automatic rule generation methods attract attention. In this study, 2 linear and 2 evolutionary approaches of automatic fuzzy rule generation methods are investigated. The investigated linear solutions contain Wang-Mendel Method and E2E-HFS, while MOGUL and IVTURS-FARC are the selected evolutionary approaches. Wang-Mendel and MOGUL is commonly considered as basic methods of the group they belong to. IVTURS-FARC is distinguished with its ability to handle interval valued fuzzy sets. Among the rest of the algorithms, E2E-HFS is unique with its weak dependency to data. Because it only use some simple properties of corresponding input variable. In order to compare the completeness and the accuracy of automatically generated fuzzy rules, several experiments are performed on different software defect prediction datasets, and the classification performance of resulting fuzzy systems is evaluated. Provided results show that even if training of evolutionary approaches seem to be more precise, similar accuracy can be achieved by linear approaches, and they perform better regarding the experiments on unseen data.	Fuzzy Inference Systems; Fuzzy Rule Generation; Evolutionary Rule Learning; Software Defect Prediction	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8566479	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Impact of Agile Scrum Methodology on Team's Productivity and Client Satisfaction – A Case Study	10.1109 /ICAC3N53548. 2021.9725505	Customer satisfaction is the primary goal of any software service provider in the long run. A small team dedicated to a short sprint handles a variety of challenges while providing deliverables to the client in agile software development. The customer, on the other hand, makes numerous decisions to get a design that meets market standard. In Agile software development, changes are organized into user stories for the sprint, developed in iterations and are reviewed by customers on regular intervals. Under the supervision of Scrum master, the teams work in back-to-back sprints to meet the sprints goals. Agile helps to deliver the end product in line to the client requirements but team might feel stressed out in the end-to-end process. This research paper presents the performance analysis of Agile Scrum methodology towards critical project parameters of Customer satisfaction and Team's productivity.	Customer satisfaction;Team Productivity;Agile;Scrum Methodology;Scrum master; User stories	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9725505	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Design and Development of a Network Learning Platform Based on the Big Data Concept	10.1109/EITT. 2018.00030	With the continuous development of information technology, the use of network learning platforms has become a new way for students' self-study. Combining network technology and multimedia technology, online learning platforms create a "virtual" learning environment, provide high-quality learning resources and enable prompter learning evaluations for students. However, through an examination of the literature and practical experience of applying some MOOCs, Cloud Classes and other learning platforms, it is clear that the online learning platform still has some shortcomings. For example, the collecting and storing of data about students' learning processes can result in a single type of information, indirect presentation, incomprehensive evaluation mechanisms, and lack of prediction of learning development. The development of the Big Data concept and technology is changing the way of learning, and the process evaluation mechanism needs to be established and improved urgently. Under the Big Data concept, this study has analyzed the demands of students' online learning and evaluation, and used software engineering methods to design and develop the network learning platform. The platform is integrated with many functions, such as announcement management, resource sharing, homework management, online discussion, group collaboration, online exams, Q&A, and learning diagnosis, so as to provide an excellent environment for students' learning, and to collect data through the learning process to provide evidence for process evaluation. The functions of the platform were tested, were basically found to have achieved the expected goals, and will be put into use.	Network learning platform; Big Data;Process evaluation; Learning diagnosis;B/S architecture	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8719421	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Managing Soft Skills Development in Technological Innovation Project Teams: An Experience Report in the Automotive Industry	10.1109 /FIE58773. 2023.10343417	This Research Full Paper reports an experience related to the Training Program 4.0 to encourage technological innovation focused on developing professional skills, especially soft skills, in undergraduate and graduate students. As the primary motivation for this program, the constant technological evolution and consequent demand for continuing education of information technology professionals stand out. Also, considering the complexity of problems solved with technology and an increasingly demanding market, computing education has been transforming, focusing on technical skills, such as cloud technologies and AI, and non-technical skills, such as self-initiative, communication, and collaboration. In this context, continuing education initiatives through teaching and learning approaches centered on practice are beneficial for forming professional skills. This study describes an experience of one of the units of the Training Program 4.0 focused on innovation for the automotive sector, based on the report and discussion of three projects. As a main contribution, the report proposes a PBL process for innovation projects, transforming it into a PBL training that can be planned, executed, monitored, and continuously improved. Using an appropriate assessment model makes it possible to manage soft skills throughout the projects, carrying out necessary interventions. To present evidence of the use of the proposed PBL Process, the results of the projects are discussed, showing how Soft skills can be managed in the context of innovation projects or other educational contexts, such as courses or disciplines.	Continuous Education; Problem-Based Learning; PBL;Competencies development;Soft Skills;IT Project	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10343417	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	chance
AI-Powered Conceptual Model for Scrum Framework	10.1109 /ICCI58132. 2023.10273881	Scrum is an incremental, interactive agile framework widely used to develop practical problems; the Scrum team focuses on achieving a common goal each cycle, "Sprint Goal" instead of the traditional sequential technique for delivering products. Although many organizations are adopting Scrum, it is still following the traditional manual approaches. Even though many tools are available in the market to facilitate project management and Scrum master tasks, the support is still limited and lacks the utilization of Artificial Intelligence science. This study focuses on integrating the Scrum framework with Artificial Intelligence to build a predicting model that can assist project management "in particular the Scrum master" to predict the achievement of the Scrum Team per Sprint using Story Points; this prediction is built based on several factors that can affect the burndown charts per Sprint.	Agile;Artificial Intelligence; Scrum Master;Story Points	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10273881	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Supporting the Assessment of Collaborative Design Activities in Multi-tabletop Classrooms	10.1109/APCASE.2015.54	The present study describes a proposed multitable top system for supporting collaborative database design activities in the classroom. Additionally, two experiments were conducted to evaluate students' and teachers' perceptions of the proposed system potential on aspects of group work assessment such as: ease of grading individuals as well as groups, equality of students' participation, and, capability to accurately reflect individual contributions. Ten educators and 22 students from a Computer Science program participated in the experiments. The findings of this work show that the use of the proposed system impacted positively on the educators' perception about the ease of grading individuals and groups. In addition, distinguishing users in collaborative group work is key for decreasing social-loafing. The results suggest that the proposed system does have potential to support a better group work assessment.	Collaboration;Atmospheric measurements;Particle measurements;Databases; Education;Computers;Data visualization	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7287031	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es
Secure Mobile Application for Uniform Resource Locator (URL) Phishing Detection based on Deep Learning	10.1109/ICONNIC59854.2023.10467246	As time progresses, there is growth in the population of internet users, resulting in a rise in digital threats. Among these dangers, the prominence of phishing attacks has become a significant cause for concern due to their increasing frequency. The latest report from the Anti-Phishing Working Group (APWG) stated that phishing attacks continued to increase from the third quarter of 2022 to the fourth quarter of 2022. This research contributes to reducing phishing attacks by providing convenience to the public in detecting phishing URLs through a secure mobile application. This study is the first to develop a secure mobile application for detecting phishing URLs using a deep learning-based detection method with the architecture of long short-term memory (LSTM) and gated recurrent unit (GRU). The application is developed using the secure software development lifecycle (SSDLC) agile scrum methodology. This method was selected due to the requirement for rapid and sustainable app development with potential threat mitigation. Threat mitigation is carried out through risk analysis, threat modeling, secure coding, and security testing. Based on the test results, the developed mobile application successfully mitigated 85.7% of potential threats, demonstrated robust security in its program codes, and exhibited 98.1% precision in detecting phishing URLs.	application security;deep learning;phising;secure software development lifecycle	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10467246	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es
Classification of High-risk Sleep Apnea with Arrhythmia Using Heterogeneous Ensemble Learning from Wearable Accelerometer	10.1109/BIBM62325.2024.10822586	Sleep apnea poses a greater risk in arrhythmia patients. However, most sleep apnea studies have focused on healthy or sleep-disordered breathing subjects. In addition, it is not practical to use in everyday life by utilizing complex home-based portable devices that can obtain various biomedical signals for the classification of sleep apnea. In this study, a classification framework for sleep apnea was proposed for arrhythmia patients who are at high risk for sleep apnea. In particular, only accelerometers that can consider breathing patterns related to sleep apnea were used. In accelerometer signals, the normal breathing pattern of high-risk groups often resembles the sleep apnea pattern. To improve the classification performance for high-risk sleep apnea, this similar pattern was defined as the gray-zone, and a clear normal breathing and sleep apnea pattern was defined as the ideal group. We used a novel heterogeneous framework that combines (i) the feature generation method of statistics, relationship, and crest factor and (ii) the stacking ensemble method of support vector machine, multilayer perceptron, and logistic regression to classify sleep apnea pattern between ideal and gray-zone group. As a result, the proposed method obtained 0.71 ± 0.02 and 0.71 ± 0.01 of the F1-score in the ideal and grayzone group, respectively. The overall performance was higher than that of baseline models. The proposed ensemble learning framework could potentially be embedded in wearable devices to provide sleep quality assessment services to high-risk sleep apnea patients anytime, anywhere.	Sleep apnea;arrhythmia; heterogeneous ensemble learning;accelerometer signals	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10822586	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es
Personas in O2O Mobile Healthcare: A Method for Identifying and Creating User Groups	10.1109/ICEBE.2016.026	Persona is a useful technique to obtain a group of target users that share common behavioral characteristics. However, persona analysis in mobile healthcare system is particularly difficult due to the complexity, ad hoc and multi-scenario nature of healthcare processes. In this paper, a personas method is proposed for the identification and creation of user groups in mobile healthcare. The approach utilizes sequence alignment, clustering technique to identify user groups. Then based on the behaviors of the user groups, we perfect the personas by constructing a decision tree of multiple user attributes. The approach is demonstrated in a case study of mobile medical appointment. The result shows that the method overcomes some drawbacks of current methods, and it is less subjective, more efficient, and less reliant on specialized expertise.	personas;user groups; healthcare process;sequence similarity;cluster analysis; decision tree	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7809907	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es

Growing small businesses using software system for intellectual analysis of financial performance	10.1109 /TCSET. 2018.8336190	The purpose of this research is to develop a software product aimed to provide end-user assessment of financial sustainability of the company and based on it deliver practical recommendations for business development. For breaking businesses up on the structural and functional groups were used Lloyd's algorithm, DB S CAN and fastDBSCAN. The best breakdown is based on collective ratings; The rule of a classification as a decision tree C4.5.	Financial analysis; Information technology;Data mining;cluster analysis; classification;collective ratings	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8336190	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem clab
Assessment Transformation in the Age of AI: Moving Beyond the Influence of Generative Tools	10.1109 /MSCC62288. 2024.10697011	This paper meticulously examines the escalating impact of AI Generative Tools on academic assessments and suggests renovating strategies to uphold the integrity of educational evaluations. With the increasing prevalence of AI-assisted cheating, traditional assessment methods encounter unprecedented challenges, prompting a fundamental shift in educational practices. The paper navigates the proliferation of AI Generative Tools, inspecting their diverse forms and motivations while addressing the ethical dilemmas arising from their integration into academic settings. Recognizing the constraints of current plagiarism detection tools, the paper explores innovative approaches to mitigate AI influence, emphasizing educational awareness programs, unambiguous academic integrity policies, and advancements in detection technologies. Advocating a departure from conventional assessment paradigms, the paper proposes the adoption of randomized questions, live assessments, and competency-based evaluations. Additionally, it recommends collaborative and authentic assessments to foster teamwork, communication, and the real-world application of knowledge. The paper delves into the necessity for updated policies, underscoring the enforcement of academic integrity and highlighting the significance of faculty development programs to empower educators in addressing AI-assisted cheating. The conclusion underscores the imperative for educational institutions to adapt proactively, providing practical insights and issuing a call to action in response to the dynamic challenges posed by AI.	ChatGPT;Assessment methodologies;Evaluation strategies;Academic integrity; Artificial intelligence (AI)	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10697011	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Where is it? Tracing the Vulnerability-Relevant Files from Vulnerability Reports	10.1145 /3597503. 3639202	With the widely usage of open-source software, supply-chain-based vulnerability attacks, including SolarWind and Log4Shell, have posed significant risks to software security. Currently, people rely on vulnerability advisory databases or commercial software bill of materials (SBOM) to defend against potential risks. Unfortunately, these datasets do not provide finer-grained file-level vulnerability information, compromising their effectiveness. Previous works have not adequately addressed this issue, and mainstream vulnerability detection methods have their drawbacks that hinder resolving this gap. Driven by the real needs, we propose a framework that can trace the vulnerability-relevant file for each disclosed vulnerability. Our approach uses NVD descriptions with metadata as the inputs, and employs a series of strategies with a LLM model, search engine, heuristic-based text matching method and a deep learning classifier to recommend the most likely vulnerability-relevant file, effectively enhancing the completeness of existing NVD data. Our experiments confirm that the efficiency of the proposed framework, with CodeBERT achieving 0.92 AUC and 0.85 MAP, and our user study proves our approach can help with vulnerability-relevant file detection effectively. To the best of our knowledge, our work is the first one focusing on tracing vulnerability-relevant files, laying the groundwork of building finer-grained vulnerability-aware software bill of materials.	vulnerability-relevant file; security;software supply chain	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10548095	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es
The Framework for Political Communication Text Mining Based on Twitter	10.1109 /ICORIS50180. 2020.9320805	In recent years, social media as a medium that is widely used in communication in the community. The phenomenon of communication on social media is increasingly being used in political communication. Social networking site services like Twitter and Facebook are believed to have the potential to increase public participation in politics. Twitter is an ideal platform for voters, politicians, political parties, and political institutions to disseminate not only public information but also political opinions to the public through their networks. This research is related to the effectiveness of social media (Twitter) as a means of political communication used by the public, especially in the election of the Mayor of Makassar and other elections in Indonesia. This paper, using two methods for social media analysis on political communication. Support Vector Machine (SVM) to classify predictable words or sentences, and the K-Means method is used to classify words or sentences related to political communication. The results of this study can be used by voters, candidates, political parties, and political institutions, as information and also as a measurement aid in determining the choice of candidates.	Social Media;Twitter;SVM;K-Means;Political Communication	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9320805	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Social Impact Assessment on a Renewable Energy Project: A Case Study in Peru	10.1109/TDC-LA.2018.8511693	Some energy projects became in causes of possible social conflicts during its implantation; in this way and in order to prevent social conflicts, it should conduct a social impact assessment (SIA) before developing an energy project. In this work, we conducted a social impact assessment on a renewable energy project in Lima, Peru, by applying of the grey systems theory. In the case study, four stakeholder groups and five evaluation criteria, for SIA, were identified. Consequently, the results showed that the energy project would have a positive social impact from the point of the view affected population. In addition, the criterion more valuated by population under analysis, was the impact on the research. Moreover, the method applied in this study showed interesting results that could help to authorities from university under study and local authorities to make the best decision about the energy project. In addition, the method could be used to assess social impact from other type of energy projects.	Social impact assessment; Grey systems theory;Energy project	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8511693	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es
Are CISQ Reliability Measures Practical? A Research Perspective	10.1109/ICSTW.2017.7	The Object Management Group (OMG), which is driven by industry, proposes an operational standard for measuring reliability by providing specifications for 29 reliability measures. The goal of this article is to systematically assess whether (1) the provided measurement specifications are suitable to be implemented in a static testing tool used in practice and (2) the measures are suitable for capturing reliability issues in software. Therefore, we implemented the CISQ measures (CISQ is the consortium responsible for driving the quality related topics of the OMG) for Java in our quality measurement tool after defining assumptions resulting from the language independent and at some point imprecise specifications. In format of a case study, the CISQ-based measurement tool has then been applied on several versions of the open source project HSQLDB. The results show that CISQ measures properties that are vital for fulfilling reliability requirements. In the course of the case study, the engineers of HSQLDB fixed a number of issues identified by our tooling as they were considered to be critical. While a number of rule violations are considered to be still problematic, they could not be fixed since the engineers did not have the code ownership. In these cases, they proposed improvement suggestions to the responsible teams.	software quality;code quality; CISQ;reliability	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7899024	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Young technology entrepreneurship enhancement based on an alternative approach of project-based learning	10.1109/EDUCON.2017.7942872	It has been noticed [1] that graduates, from a technology-oriented curriculum of studies, have developed the appropriate theoretical knowledge background and present the required hard skills. However, they lack of entrepreneurship skills and business minded orientation. Moreover, even if courses such as Management and Entrepreneurship are part of the curriculum, students view these subjects uninteresting due to a lack of practical component [1]. Young people need the opportunity to sharpen their skills so that they can quickly join the job market [2]. This paper describes an altered version of the Project Based Learning method (PBL), as a suggestion for developing entrepreneurship skill to students, based on their ideas and interests. The proposed method was used in two educational projects implemented by Applied Informatics in Business and Economy students. The assessment of hard and soft skills development was performed through written tests, interviews and 360 degrees feedback from the participants. The final results were very promising, depicting that 80% of the participants made it through the program successfully. Moreover, they felt confident enough for their knowledge and capable to start their own business. An interesting finding was that 40% of the students were already building a team to start developing their own product. They all believed that their entrepreneurial skills were developed. In addition to that, written tests showed that their hard skills have also been enhanced. Even though the economic environment of Greece is aggressive to entrepreneurship [3], a year after the projects were concluded, 20% of the participants were still trying to build their own business by developing their own product. It is the first time, to the best of the authors' knowledge, that technology and informatics are used as means to enhance entrepreneurship in Greece, starting from concept and ending to the actual promotion of an actual product (prototype).	Entrepreneurship;Soft skill development;Project Based Learning	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7942872	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem avaliar
An Autonomous Vehicle Group Formation Method based on Risk Assessment Scoring	10.1109/DASC/PiCom/CBDCom/Cy55231.2022.9927817	Forming a secure autonomous vehicle group is extremely challenging since we have to consider threats and vulnerability of autonomous vehicles. Existing studies focus on communications among risk-free autonomous vehicles, which lack metrics to measure passenger security and cargo values. This work proposes a novel autonomous vehicle group formation method. We introduce risk assessment scoring to assess passenger security and cargo values, and propose an autonomous vehicle group formation method based on it. Our vehicle group is composed of a master node, and a number of core and border ones. Finally, the extensive simulation results show that our method is better than a Connectivity Prediction-based Dynamic Clustering model and a Low-Independently clustering architecture in terms of node survival time, average change count of master nodes, and average risk assessment scoring.	autonomous vehicle group; risk assessment scoring; vehicle group formation	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9927817	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es

Research on Input-Output Index System Construction of The Power Grid Company Asset Value	10.1109 /AEMCSE5198 6.2021.00028	On the basis of asset classification of asset group, the specific category of asset input-output value collection of asset group of the Power Grid Company is determined. This paper systematically combs the company's intangible assets value evaluation method, intangible assets method and intangible assets classification. Starting from three aspects of security, reliability and economy of power grid operation, as well as the asset status and DEA method provided by various management departments of power grid, the input-output evaluation index system of asset group of The Power Grid Company is constructed.	Power grid company group assets value assessment; Intangible assets value assessment;Indicator system	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9513184	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es
Evaluating ChatGPT-driven Automated Test Generation for Personalized Programming Education	10.1109 /FLLM63129. 2024.10852510	Large Language Models (LLMs), such as ChatGPT, hold immense potential to irrevocably influence the dimension of educational technology by providing empowerment for personalized learning experiences. This paper covers the integration of ChatGPT into existing eLearning platforms toward supporting Java programming education. Using artificial intelligence-based capabilities of ChatGPT in natural language processing, our software enables instructors to generate individual module assessments tailored to a student's profile with unprecedented ease. Evaluation of the effectiveness and efficiency of the system was performed by a comprehensive review of the system, obtaining feedback from instructors and students, and analyzing test performance metrics. The evaluation showed that most teachers found the system very user friendly, with significant savings in time for test creation. Satisfaction related to personalized tests designed by ChatGPT was also adequate, and the average scores achieved on test cases set by ChatGPT were relatively high compared to those manually curated. Results underline the potential of ChatGPT-driven automated test generation for enhancing personalized programming education on eLearning platforms, making available tailored assessment, by consideration of individual needs of students, and increased learning outcomes and efficiency.	Large Language Models; ChatGPT;eLearning; Programming Education; Automated Test Generation; Personalized Learning;Java Programming;Natural Language Processing; Educational Technology; Assessment	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10852510	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es
Lessons Learned in Utilizing the SETR Process in the Procurement of TPSs on the CASS Family of Testers	10.1109 /AUTEST. 2018.8532541	Programmatic improvements can be achieved through the incorporation of "lessons learned" from preceding projects in the acquisition of Consolidated Automated Support System (CASS) Family of Testers (FoT) Operational Test Program Sets (OTPS). The application of the Systems Engineering Technical Review (SETR) process to CASS FoT OTPSs presents unique challenges. Adhering to policy and minimizing impact to total lifecycle costs (TLC) have differing goals. However, lessons can be extracted from previous CASS OTPS procurements implementing SETR while minimizing the competing effects of the two. The SETR process is NAVAIR's procedure to perform system engineering reviews for Naval Aviation products. This process has been implemented on CASS FoT OTPS procurements for a multitude of reasons including: increased risk management, ensuring product confidence, and program/project uniformity. SETR provides an assessment of the emerging design against the overall objective of promoting a well-managed development effort leading to a system that meets programmatic requirements while still providing the system performance required to support mission needs. It also offers insight into project progress while providing a layer of independent review at programmatic milestones. This paper will discuss the experience of implementing SETR on CASS FoT OTPS procurements. It will summarize some lessons learned with key areas of focus to include: obstacles, useful elements, and specific examples of implementation from recent CASS OTPS programs. The focus will be on a few key elements of SETR that are especially important for CASS OTPSs: stakeholder participation, checklist tailoring, requirements tracking, and risk management. These topics will be covered from the point of view of government acquisition, but there will be valuable insights for TPS developers. The intent is to allow future CASS FoT OTPS development projects to effectively implement SETR while minimizing the cost and schedule impacts of policy, thereby reducing TLC, and increasing speed to the fleet.	SETR;Systems Engineering; Test Program Sets; Statement of Work;Request for Proposal	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8532541	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es

One Size Does Not Fit All: A Grounded Theory and Online Survey Study of Developer Preferences for Security Warning Types		A wide range of tools exist to assist developers in creating secure software. Many of these tools, such as static analysis engines or security checkers included in compilers, use warnings to communicate security issues to developers. The effectiveness of these tools relies on developers heeding these warnings, and there are many ways in which these warnings could be displayed. Johnson et al. [46] conducted qualitative research and found that warning presentation and integration are main issues. We built on Johnson et al.'s work and examined what developers want from security warnings, including what form they should take and how they should integrate into their workflow and work context. To this end, we conducted a Grounded Theory study with 14 professional software developers and 12 computer science students as well as a focus group with 7 academic researchers to gather qualitative insights. To back up the theory developed from the qualitative research, we ran a quantitative survey with 50 professional software developers. Our results show that there is significant heterogeneity amongst developers and that no one warning type is preferred over all others. The context in which the warnings are shown is also highly relevant, indicating that it is likely to be beneficial if IDEs and other development tools become more flexible in their warning interactions with developers. Based on our findings, we provide concrete recommendations for both future research as well as how IDEs and other security tools can improve their interaction with developers.	developer security warnings; software development;code security	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9284069	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Developing Algorithms for Predicting Gene-Disease Associations	10.1109//IICCS61609.2024.10763762	It is evident that identifying gene-disease relationships is essential to elucidate disease genomics and progression as well as aiding in developing targeted therapies. This work aims at training and testing various machine learning approaches for predicting these relations, as well as considering various datasets, and their integration involving multi-omics data. The process of data collection has been carried out from Genomic, Transcriptomic, and Clinical data stored in various data repositories and then preprocessed for feature selection and fine-tuning of the model along with the development of Supervised, Unsupervised, and Integrated Models. The models were built and tested using cross-validated data sets; model efficiency was assessed with respect to accuracy, precision, recall and F1-score. The findings showed that the models from the second group of hybrids obtained a systematically higher accuracy than models from the first and subsequent groups, especially when analyzing multiple types of 'omics data at once. Similar deployments on entirely separate datasets ensured the model's reliability and portability across different contexts. Furthermore, interpretability features and visualization modules were included into the software to improve assessment and interactivity for users and scholars. This research will be beneficial for the field of genomics since it proposes tools that will help in the better understanding of disease and the identification of genes involved in particular diseases, making it possible to start the process of targeting important genes in order to develop cures for such diseases. The study results preciously highlight the significance of applying integrated strategies of data and analytic methodology to improving the accuracy of the prediction and implementing the personalized medicine concept.	Gene-disease associations; Machine learning; Bioinformatics;Genomics; Multi-omics data integration	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10763762	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Formation of IT Project Implementation Team	10.1109/CSIT49958.2020.9322005	The criteria for forming a project team and its impact on the project success are analyzed in this paper. It is noted that the team is selected for each project at the first stage of its implementation. The project team means a team of like-minded people motivated to fulfill the project. The article suggests an original procedure for forming a project team, which involves the selection of performers according to defined criteria based on weight coefficients assigned by experts. The assessment is based on the competencies acquired by graduates of IT specialties and reflected in educational and professional programs.	project team;expert evaluation;project management;competencies; educational and professional program	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9322005	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
IntelliGame in Action: An Experience Report on Gamifying JavaScript Unit Tests	10.1145/3643796.3648466	This paper investigates the integration and assessment of Intelligame, a gamification plug in initially designed for Java development, within the realm of JavaScript unit testing. We aim to verify the generalizability of Intelligame to JavaScript development and to provide valuable insights into the experiment's design. For this, we first customize Intelligame for JavaScript, and then conduct a controlled experiment involving 152 participants utilizing the Jest testing framework, and finally examine its influence on testing behavior and the overall developer experience. The findings from this study provide valuable insights for improving JavaScript testing methodologies through the incorporation of gamification.	Gamification;IDE;IntelliJ; Software Testing	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10713933	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Static analysis of source code written by novice programmers	10.1109/EDUCON.2017.7942942	In this paper we are reporting the finding on the use of a static analysis of C source code written by students learning to program. Two different tools for static code analysis were used to analyze the solutions submitted by the students on the partial exams and exams from the introductory course in programming in a three year period. We have collected, analyzed and compared most common errors reported by both tools. We further investigate if the available checks provided by these tools, often used in professional software development practices to find bugs and improve the code quality, can also help novice programmers in tracking down and resolving their problems in the code or have any other value in the process of learning programming.	staitic analysis;novice programmers;programming errors	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7942942	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
A Fault Prediction Method for Meteorological Disasters of Grid Equipment Based on Equipment Vulnerability	10.1109/EDPEE61724.2024.00024	This article aims to design an efficient fault prediction algorithm for grid equipment by combining equipment vulnerability assessment and meteorological disaster risk assessment, so as to improve the stability and safety of power grid operation. In order to achieve this goal, this article first constructs the equipment vulnerability assessment index system, and combines historical meteorological data and equipment fault records to improve the meteorological disaster risk assessment model. On this basis, a fault prediction algorithm based on historical fault data and real-time operation data is designed by using data mining and neural network technology. The performance of the model is further optimized by adjusting the parameters of the model. The experimental results show that compared with the traditional fault prediction methods, the model proposed in this article has significantly improved the prediction accuracy, real-time, F1 score and MAE. The algorithm can accurately identify the vulnerability of equipment and the risk of meteorological disasters, and provide targeted maintenance and management suggestions for power grid companies. The research results of this article provide new ideas and methods for fault prediction of grid equipment, which is helpful to improve the stability and safety of power grid operation.	Equipment vulnerability;Grid equipment;Meteorological disasters;Failure prediction	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10539742	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Comparative Case Study of Plan-Driven and Agile Approaches in Student Computing Projects	10.23919/SoftCOM50211.2020.9238196	Plan first, execute second" and "Adapt to change as you iterate" are two paradigms that are well known in software development, as they represent disparate schools of project management: traditional and agile. Despite a long-lasting debate on prominence of each, little comparative research has been reported, particularly in the context of academic projects, where all too often a no-process approach still prevails. This paper presents an experiment that was carried out during the Spring semester of the 2018-2019 academic year at two engineering schools in Europe in order to assess the impacts of a given development method on the success of student computing undertakings. A structured, metric-based assessment scheme was applied to reveal patterns associated with the use of Plan-driven, Iterative and no-process approaches on product quality, team productivity and teamwork quality facets.	software engineering;agile; software process;education; comparative study;capstone project	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9238196	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	chance
An Action Design Research on development and deployment of a computer-based group discussion support tool for achieving consensus and culture change at an educational institution	10.1109/IEEM.2015.7385871	Organisational culture change is a long and complex process that typically takes years to complete and has a very low success rate. This project addresses the problem by the proposed use of an Action Design Research Methodology to build and deploy an IT artifact named Organisational Culture Assessment Instrument-Spilter (OCAI-Spilter) to speed up cultural change while reducing failure rate. OCAI-Spilter should be able to fast-track culture change by addressing the problem of scalability and process losses encountered in most change projects involving large numbers of people. We used an iterative prototyping process to continuously refine the tool in use. We also reviewed the design principles in Action Research Design to improve the usability of the tool. New design principles and learning were derived from this process. Finally, we showed the effectiveness of the artifact by measuring the results of the tool in use through culture surveys and alignment, as well as idea generation that was administered through the tool.	Organisational culture change;Organisational Culture Assessment Instrument;action design research	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7385871	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Monitoring students' mobile app coding behavior data analysis based on IDE and browser interaction logs	10.1109/EDUCON.2014.6826202	This paper describes a case study of assessing student's coding behavior and skills in a realistic development setting. Students had to solve typical programming problems in the context of app development for the Android platform using the Eclipse IDE. Data was analyzed using IDE as well as browser interaction logs. In addition, screen recordings of the students' interaction with the IDE provide further insight. In this paper we present the first results of our ongoing work.	android;coding behaviour; alternative learning assessment;IDE interaction	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=6826202	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es

Distributed Energy Resource Benchmark Models for Distribution Impact Assessment - Update of Activities by CIGRE Working Group C6.36	10.1049/icp.2021.1481	With growing levels of distributed energy resources (DER), effective assessment and design of active distribution systems increasingly depend upon access to models that accurately represent the various DER and their controls. However, as DER technologies continue to rapidly evolve, along with the analysis needed to capture their impacts on the system, there is an increasing need for benchmark models that can serve as a common reference by distribution engineers, vendors, academia, and other industry stakeholders. This paper provides an update on the work by CIGRE Working Group C6.36: "Distributed Energy Resource Models for Impact Assessment" to identify a set of benchmark DER models for quasi-static time-series load flow (QSTS) simulations, increasingly used to evaluate active distribution system impacts and performance. These benchmark models can be used by the industry to understand and verify the performance of existing models as well as serve as a reference for further modifications and enhancements. This paper discusses the working groups proposed DER benchmark model framework, which specifies the DER benchmark model hierarchy and requirements. Additionally, initial efforts in developing benchmark models for PV systems, energy storage systems, and smart inverters are presented along with the lessons learned and future work.		https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9692860	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es
AUGGO: Augmented Reality and Marker-based Application for Learning Geometry in Elementary Schools	10.1109/CENIM51130.2020.9298003	Suitable learning media can be used to achieve learning goals. The more interactive the learning media, the learning process will be more interactive. This paper proposes a learning media named Auggo. Auggo is an Augmented Reality (AR) and marker-based application as an interactive media to learn geometry in Elementary School. To show the impact of Auggo, this research conducts a test to 14 students in elementary school as participants. The test was carried out using the Two-Group Paired Sample T-Test method with those 14 elementary school students. Participants were divided into 2 groups: 7 participants as Group A (experimental class) and 7 participants as Group B (control class). Assessment of participants showed the results of the pretest to posttest in Group A increased by 26%, while Group B only increased by 10.29%. These results indicate that the AR-based AUGGO application can help students in improving the understanding of space concept.	learning media;Augmented Reality;Geometry;Elementary School	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9298003	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Professiogram as a Tool for the Selection of an Expert	10.1109/PTEs.2018.8604225	The article discusses the use of professiograms, built on the basis of psycholinguistic analysis of speech, as a tool for assessing the professional suitability of an expert at the center for the evaluation of qualifications.	professiogram;qualification assessment;metro program;psycholinguistic speech analysis	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8604225	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
An Applied C Programming Exercise with Card Game Strategy and Analysis of Codes by a Grouping of Score and Code Metrics	10.1109/TALE48000.2019.9225853	We have proposed an applied C exercise with the subjects of card game Poker strategy. We have operated contest management server WinT and provided execution environment. Learners implement their strategies aiming efficient poker's hands of cards with estimating of remaining deck and weighted rate. In this paper, we consider a method of personalizing advice for students. For this purpose, we use the K-means method to group students, analyze the feature of each group, and consider feedback strategy. We aim to reduce the burden on teachers and TAs and provide higher quality advice by the support system automatically performing this method.	C programming exercise; card game strategy;contest style;code metrics;K-means clustering	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9225853	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Self-Adaptation of Software Services Based on User Profile	10.1109/INTERCON63140.2024.10833493	In recent years, several methods have been proposed to evaluate user experience (UX) improvements using real-time emotion detection, but the correlation between user emotions and personality traits in self-adaptive software has not been fully explored. This paper investigates the feasibility of implementing a software service that adapts based on the user's emotional and personality state. Using pre-trained models for real-time emotion detection and the BFI-2-S test for personality assessment, we conducted an experiment with 30 users on the Neo Digital Skills platform, evaluated through the User Experience Question-naire (UEQ). Our findings show that self-adaptation significantly enhances UX, with improvements in Attractiveness (from -0.81 to 1.69), Stimulation (from -0.73 to 1.78), and Novelty (from -0.62 to 2.02), indicating that personalization based on emotions and personality traits boosts user engagement, satisfaction, and innovation perceptions.	personality;self-adaptation; software as a ser-vice;user experience;user profile	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10833493	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Structuring Information about the State of the Cyber-Physical System Operator	10.1109/Inforino48376.2020.9111654	Human operator, who manages complex equipment and makes responsible decisions, is occupied an important place in the cyber-physical system. His activity is accompanied by high psycho-emotional stress, which can negatively affect performance. Therefore, in the cyber-physical system, monitoring (including remote monitoring) of the functional state of a person is necessary. This article discusses the problem of structuring heterogeneous information, which is recorded during the monitoring process and is used to assess the state of the human operator. This information can be represented by various types of data (quantitative, qualitative, interval, in the form of time series, etc.), and it should be structured to facilitate the detection of hidden patterns and relationships. The features of structuring the flow of heterogeneous data for assessing the human state are given and methods for this assessment are highlighted. Solving the problems of structuring heterogeneous data is accompanied by examples.	human operator;state assessment;monitoring; heterogeneous data; structuring;hidden patterns	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9111654	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es
A Case Study of Using Scrum for Small to Medium Software Development Project E-Voting Student Council Elections	10.1109/ICISS62896.2024.10751566	This research discusses the implementation of the Scrum methodology in the development of an internet-based e-voting application for student council elections in high schools. In Indonesia, after the amendment of the 1945 Constitution, democracy has shifted towards liberalism, where the selection of officials is based on procedural and financial considerations. The turnover rate of legislative officials has become a crucial indicator of the quality of democracy. The General Election Commission (KPU) views novice voters as a group that requires special attention. The research reveals that the social and educational environment contributes to the political behavior of students. The Scrum methodology is employed for the development of the e-voting application, enabling continuous communication and adaptability to changes. The application aims to increase student participation in general elections and provide insights to the General Election Commission. The results show that the implementation of Scrum is successful, with a focus on data management, student account management, input validation, and quick counts. The application is expected to provide effective democracy education to students and support the electoral process at the school level.	E-voting;Kanban;Scrum; Sprint	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10751566	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sen avaliar
Replication Can Improve Prior Results: A GitHub Study of Pull Request Acceptance	10.1109/ICPC.2019.00037	Crowdsourcing and data mining can be used to effectively reduce the effort associated with the partial replication and enhancement of qualitative studies. For example, in a primary study, other researchers explored factors influencing the fate of GitHub pull requests using an extensive qualitative analysis of 20 pull requests. Guided by their findings, we mapped some of their qualitative insights onto quantitative questions. To determine how well their findings generalize, we collected much more data (170 additional pull requests from 142 GitHub projects). Using crowdsourcing, that data was augmented with subjective qualitative human opinions about how pull requests extended the original issue. The crowd's answers were then combined with quantitative features and, using data mining, used to build a predictor for whether code would be merged. That predictor was far more accurate than the one built from the primary study's qualitative factors (F1=90 vs 68%), illustrating the value of a mixed-methods approach and replication to improve prior results. To test the generality of this approach, the next step in future work is to conduct other studies that extend qualitative studies with crowdsourcing and data mining.	Crowdsourcing;Github; Replication;Software Engineering	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8813275	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Nurturing Hybrid Work Literacy in Upper Secondary Schools: Selecting the Best Hybrid Work Configuration for Coding Camps	10.1109 /FIE61694. 2024.10893177	This research full paper presents findings on whether different hybrid work configurations during coding camps result in equal quality prod-ucts.- Background: Hybrid work has become the new normal way of working for many professionals, including software developers - some work from home, others from their office, and others from a combination of both. Thus, educating people on hybrid work is crucial. However, there is a lack of evidence and guidance to support educators in organizing hybrid non-conventional learning experiences, such as coding camps and hackathons. Research question: How do different hybrid work configurations impact the final product teams develop during coding camps for upper secondary school students? Methodology: We organized a hybrid coding camp at our university to teach upper secondary school students (aged 15–19) Agile-based Software Engineering practices and enhance their ability to develop high-quality software. The 180 participants (75% M; 25% F) had diverse backgrounds and little or no previous software development experience. The camp lasted 20 hours and integrated components from two baseline camps (onsite and on-line). We randomly assigned the 60 teams to two groups following different hybrid work configurations and compared the mobile apps they developed. Moreover, we compared all the apps of the hybrid coding camp to those of the baseline camps. Findings: The quality of the hybrid, onsite, and online coding is similar. The products of the two hybrid work configurations have similar quality. One configuration places slightly more emphasis on the User Interface, whereas the other concentrates slightly more on programming logic. This work has direct implications for educators, who can use both configurations without affecting the overall quality of the product.	User interfaces;Aging;Solids; Remote working;Encoding; Software;Logic;Programming profession;Software engineering;Software development management	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10893177	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Deep Learning for Self-Driving Cars: Chances and Challenges		Artificial Intelligence (AI) is revolutionizing the modern society. In the automotive industry, researchers and developers are actively pushing deep learning based approaches for autonomous driving. However, before a neural network finds its way into series production cars, it has to first undergo strict assessment concerning functional safety. The chances and challenges of incorporating deep learning for self-driving cars are presented in this paper.	Deep Learning;Functional Safety;Automotive	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8452728	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Quantum Clustering for Cybersecurity	10.1109 /QCE60285. 2024.10243	In this study, we develop a novel quantum machine learning (QML) framework to analyze cybersecurity vulnerabilities using data from the 2022 CISA Known Exploited Vulnerabilities catalog, which includes detailed information on vulnerability types, severity levels, common vulnerability scoring system (CVSS) scores, and product specifics. Our framework preprocesses this data into a quantum-compatible format, enabling clustering analysis through our advanced quantum techniques, QCSWAPK-means and QkernelK-means. These quantum algorithms demonstrate superior performance compared to state-of-the-art classical clustering techniques like k-means and spectral clustering, achieving Silhouette scores of 0.491, Davies-Bouldin indices below 0.745, and Calinski-Harabasz scores exceeding 884, indicating more distinct and well-separated clusters. Our frame-work categorizes vulnerabilities into distinct groups, reflecting varying levels of risk severity: Cluster 0, primarily consisting of critical Microsoft-related vulnerabilities; Cluster 1, featuring medium severity vulnerabilities from various enterprise software vendors and network solutions; Cluster 2, with high severity vulnerabilities from Adobe, Cisco, and Google; and Cluster 3, encompassing vulnerabilities from Microsoft and Oracle with high to medium severity. These findings highlight the potential of QML to enhance the precision of vulnerability assessments and prioritization, advancing cybersecurity practices by enabling more strategic and proactive defense mechanisms.	Quantum Machine Learning; Quantum Clustering; Cybersecurity	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10821094	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sen es
OtoFrame: A Software Solution for Keyframe Extraction in Otology Endoscopic Videos	10.1109 /ICAC61394. 2024.10718823	A novel software application to address a critical industrial challenge is developed to extract keyframes from endoscopic videos in otology. While we have existing solutions for extracting keyframes from videos, they have shown to be inadequate in addressing the unique challenges posed by endoscopic videos in otology. Conventional keyframe extraction techniques often miss crucial frames necessary for accurately diagnosing a patient's eardrum condition. The reason behind this oversight is the different perception of keyframes between conventional computer vision techniques and the standards required by medical practices. Our software, OtoFrame employs advanced image extraction techniques upon receiving an endoscopic video with its primary objective being to deliver optimal and clinically relevant eardrum images to the user for assessment. By leveraging open-source computer vision techniques and learning-based image classification methodologies, the software guarantees precise extraction of keyframes from otology endoscopic videos ensuring highly accurate results.	Keyframe Extraction;Transfer Learning;Image classification;Endoscopic video;Eardrum frames; Artificial Intelligence	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10718823	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Enziguame: An Educational Game About Enzymes and Metabolism	10.1109 /FIE58773. 2023.10343365	This paper presents a novel game to teach metabolism and enzymatic activity concepts, exploring game-based and active learning. This study is part of a larger project that aims to update primary and secondary school teachers with scientific knowledge, allowing them to include novel teaching strategies and general discussions about eating habits and health with their students. The game impact was measured by qualitative assessment of 75 teachers who used the game, and overall, the feedback was very positive. Enziguame has been developed to explore essential concepts of metabolism and enzymatic activity. A heterogeneous group of people from computing and biomedical science participated in creating the game's software, and another group worked on reviewing the pedagogic issues in the game to make it able to be used in the classroom. The computing subgroup created a game design document describing the game's features, mechanics, elements, and scenarios. The game's development was cyclic, constantly reviewing the requirements for pedagogic, content, and computing technical aspects. Our results show the strong game's evolution, which was possible through the constant feedback from teachers from middle school, high school, and university education. Now, we have Enziguame's stable final version, with several mechanics that approach the contents in a playful and didactic way. Enziguame teaches about metabolism and enzymes, and, at the same time, it tests the motor and reasoning player's capacity through its gameplay, where the player controls an enzyme and needs to lead that one to its substrates, regulating the body's metabolism. The gameplay is accompanied by the "Teacher" character, who appears occasionally and explains things to the player, like an enzyme and how it works. The game has different levels, representing distinct places of the body. Such levels allow us to explore the various kinds of enzymes and the different phases of our metabolism. Through game development and its presentation to teachers, we can conclude that using games for didactic purposes brings great benefits. The game simulates enzymatic activity in the body and explanatory texts and significantly promotes knowledge through play activity.	learning;game-based learning;enzyme activity; obesity;healthy habits	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10343365	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Ensuring the Reliability of AI Systems through Methodological Processes	10.1109 /QRS62785. 2024.00023	The strategic implementation of Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies in the industry requires extending conventional engineering disciplines to include AI-specific considerations. This allows the management and evaluation of risks associated with AI technologies, thereby unlocking their potential to improve system autonomy. Moreover, this allows to ensure a high level of confidence among stakeholders, such as regulatory authorities and clients. In this context, this paper provides an overview of the findings from the confluence.ai research program, which aims to develop methodological guidelines/ processes for engineering trustworthy AI systems. These processes are the result of collaborative efforts by a large group of experts focused on AI system trustworthiness. Data trustworthiness assessment and risk analysis are examples of these methodological processes.	AI-Systems reliability; Trustworthiness; Methodological processes; Data assessment;Risk analysis	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10684663	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Mellrak: an Ontology Driven CDSS for Symptom Assessment, Risk Assessment and Disease Analysis of Breast Cancer	10.1109 /ICSECS52883. 2021.00116	Automated approach with increased robustness and efficiency has proven its significant applications in the medical sector and offers a wide variety of growth opportunities. The paper proposes a Clinical Decision Support System (CDSS) for the Breast Cancer prediction named Mellrak for risk assessment, symptom assessment and breast cancer using the aid of Ontology and questionnaire. The risk assessment and breast cancer assessment are carried out with the help of clinical guidelines. The patient sorting using age group, weight and blood pressure to find the risk factor is performed using DL-Query that connects instances and inferred classes. This paper contains the architecture of the system and SWRL rule formation along with breast cancer stage determination through biopsy reports and mammography reports.	Ontology;Breast Cancer;Web Ontology Language (OWL); Protégé;VOWL;SWRL; BIRADS;Risk Assessment; Symptom assessment; SPARQL;DL QUERY	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9537027	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Crowdsourcing-Based Ranking Aggregation for Person Re-Identification	10.1109 /ICASSP40776. 2020.9053496	Person re-identification (re-ID) is widely applied in surveillance and criminal detection applications. The existing research focus on devising the stand-alone re-ID methods, ignoring their practical application in the multi-person collaboration scenario. To improve the search efficiency, a group of investigators are usually assigned the same task to re-identify a suspect from a shared gallery set. Due to their personalized viewpoints and search feedback operations, different investigators may obtain diverse search results of the same query target. In this case, merging different rankings and generating an improved result is of great importance. To this end, this paper proposes a crowdsourcing-based ranking aggregation to adaptively fuse multiple ranking lists for re-ID problem. The method estimates the reliability of individual investigators, with a specifically designed long tail distribution to fit the top ranking demand, and is feasible for human-machine interaction. Extensive experiments conducted on four dataset-s demonstrate the superiority of the proposed method.	Person Re-Identification; Crowdsourcing;Aggregation	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9053496	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

GPR-AI Master: GPR Data Analysis Utilizing Deep Learning and ECS for Backfill Grouting Detection in Shield Tunnels	10.1109 /PIERS62282. 2024.10617955	The quality of backfill grouting behind the shield tunnel is crucial for the structural support of the tunnel lining and tunnel excavation alignment. The actual grouting condition cannot be visually observed directly in the tunnel construction due to the presence of segmental linings. Ground-penetrating radar (GPR), due to its portability and excellent penetration of tunnel linings, is a promising method for non-destructive assessment of grouting quality. However, traditional GPR data processing suffers from subjectivity and lack of quantifiability. Therefore, utilizing artificial intelligence techniques for GPR data analysis holds significant importance. Based on experimental model data, we have developed a deep learning model using residual networks ResNet-18, enabling rapid and quantitative processing for GPR grouting thickness detection. The model's performance on the test dataset demonstrates that the deep learning model based on experimental data exhibits favorable results in the identification of grouting thickness. To address the portability of data analysis, we propose a model deployment method based on Elastic Cloud Servers. Users can access this system through an interactive interface, allowing them to directly upload GPR data and obtain visual results. The visual results include GPR raw data, grouting thickness distribution, and grouting thickness assessment. This application not only ensures the objectivity of GPR data analysis but also overcomes the closed nature of traditional data processing and transmission. Finally, we have explored and envisioned the applications of automated GPR data collection and intelligent data analysis, which hold significant reference value for the safety and automation of shield tunnel construction projects.	National Natural Science Foundation of China; State Grid Shanghai Municipal Electric Power Company;	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10617955	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Virtual reality game for safety education	10.1109 /ICALIP. 2014.7009764	Safety and health issues are important components for any industry that involves machinery operations. To control various hazards leading to occupational injuries and illnesses, one common method is safety training and education. In this study, we developed a 3D virtual reality game to enhance safety training and education. Based on the recommendations from industrial partners, a pedestal grinder and its operation were selected for this study. The pedestal grinder and the mechanical laboratory were converted to three dimensional shapes using 3D modeling software. The completed 3D models were brought into the game engine to replicate actual laboratory environment. This allows students to interact within the virtual environment and be able to operate the virtual pedestal grinder safely. The interactivity between a user and the equipment within 3D virtual environment was implemented using visual programming tool inside the game engine. A pilot study was conducted to assess the students' learning with regard to the pedestal grinder safety using three groups: lecture only, lecture with physical laboratory, and lecture with the developed 3D virtual environment. The results indicated the benefits of 3D virtual reality game over "lecture only" delivery method in enhancing students' learning. Furthermore, virtual reality game allows students to retain information as good as the "lecture with physical laboratory" delivery method.	Virtual Reality;Safety Education	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7009764	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Unveiling Hidden Patterns: Clustering Algorithms on C Code embedding	10.1109 /I2CT61223. 2024.10543306	Automatic grading can help streamline assessment by using advanced algorithms to evaluate embedded C programs swiftly and objectively. This technology ensures standardized evaluations, providing quick and objective feedback on programming proficiency, enabling educators and employers to gauge participants' skills accurately. This paper proposes leveraging the application of machine learning clustering methods on embedding of C programs that have been examined by subject matter experts (SMEs) to uncover hidden patterns in the input vectors. A variety of clustering techniques are applied at the score level to capture the patterns in the data and analyze if they lie at par with the SMEs' evaluations. Machine learning models can at best capture clusters at the questions level, i.e., it can capture similarities amongst text, but cannot comprehend the logic behind it and classify the types of errors in code solutions. K-means clustering proves to provide the best compact clusters at a question level of the chosen dataset with biased data distribution in the markings.	Automatic grading; embedding C programs; Machine learning;clustering; SMEs;similarities;score; Questions	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10543306	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Automotive A/B testing: Challenges and Lessons Learned from Practice	10.1109/SEAA51224.2020.00026	Over the past 15 years, A/B testing has been a critical tool for accurate prioritization of development efforts in online and web-facing companies. As automotive companies progress on their digitalization process, A/B testing and other experimentation techniques start to be adopted. However, specific characteristics of the automotive software industry create additional challenges to the successful adoption of A/B testing. Recently, research has been conducted to investigate the challenges and opportunities for experimentation techniques in the automotive and more generally in the embedded systems domain. However, despite the collaboration with industry, previous research was based on either hypothesized or toy scenarios in companies seeking, but not yet running experimentation. Utilizing a case study method, we investigate the challenges of adopting A/B testing in two large-scale automotive companies that are currently running or preparing for their first A/B testing. The contribution of this paper is two-fold. First, we present our main findings in terms of the challenges of real A/B testing iterations in automotive vehicles. Second, we present the current, potential solutions and lessons learned from applying A/B testing in the automotive domain.	A/B testing;Automotive Software;Case study; Challenges	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9226309	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es
Cognitive computer training in children with cognitive and learning disabilities: Two interesting case studies	10.1109/TISHW.2018.8559508	The future of healthcare is dramatically changing with technology advances acquiring an increasingly important role in vulnerable groups of people. The purpose of this study is to explore the effect of a computer-based training software on improving the cognitive functions of cognitively impaired children; a second grade student of a primary school with Simpson-Golabi-Behmel syndrome and a fourth grade student of a primary school with learning difficulties. For the purpose of this study, cognitive assessments before and after the intervention were performed by a psychologist in order to evaluate the students' cognitive status and the possible cognitive improvement of the students after the intervention. Results have shown performance improvement in variety of functions, such as Attention, Brain Speed, working Memory, Skills, Intelligence and Navigation. These findings are encouraging, as well as insightful and could have significant effects in the development of online brain software as an innovative tool for the improvement of cognitive decline.	Cognitive disabilities;learning disabilities;cognitive computer training	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8559508	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es
An evaluation method for panoramic understanding of programming by comparison with visual examples	10.1109/FIE.2015.7344104	In recent years, professionals in different fields have become able to do programming by using simplified software tools, as a consequence of this they are becoming able to understand programming in a general or "panoramic" way. This understanding is not evaluated by current programming abilities testing methods such as written paper tests or practical programming. This paper proposes a Programmed Visual Contents Comparison Method to assess programming ability, and additionally, a testing system based on this method. With this method, by comparing 2 displayed images and interactive animations produced by programming samples (a question) a subject must decide which one of the programs is more difficult to build with programming than the other, or, if the difficulty is similar for both of them. The validity of the method is confirmed by comparing the ability reported by programming teachers with the results of an experiment performed with a testing system.	Computer science education; Programming Training; Student Assessment;Graphic Design;Software Engineering	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7344104	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Developing the STEM Experience for In-Service Primary Teachers through Micro-controlling Hardware and Coding	10.1109/ITHET.2018.8424789	This paper presents the design and implementation of a technological literacy course in professional development training for a diverse group of in-service primary teachers in Hong Kong. A set of micro-controlling hardware was chosen such that not only the controlling and coding barriers are acceptable to the teachers but that their pupils can also adopt the easy-to-use hardware and software to create STEM projects in primary schools. The hands-on training seeks to broaden their technological experiences in various interfacing and sensing activities. The coding challenge is reduced by introducing visual programming, thereby allowing the learners to focus on real- world problems in the STEM disciplines. Details of the course are provided and the assessment projects by Engineering Design Process are illustrated in this paper. The quantitative evaluation of teachers in their micro-controlling experience is provided.	STEM;micro-controller; Breakout board;engineering design process;sensor	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8424789	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Strengthening study skills by using ERPsim as a new tool within the Pupils' academy of serious gaming	10.1109 /EDUCON. 2016.7474611	Companies are currently calling for more and more graduates with good management and planning skills. But, studies show that rising student numbers lead to a high dropout rate. Thus, strengthening the study skills of the students plays a key role in reducing this dropout rate and should be a key objective of every education system. In particular, universities have the power to improve the study skills of pupils at an early stage through the designed programs and measures. With the Pupils' Academy Serious Gaming, the Department of Computer Science at the Technical University of Munich (TUM) has introduced an instrument to promote the study skills. This initiative aimed primarily at pupils of upper vocational schools (UVS). In addition to the study skills, thus the ability of more application-oriented knowledge transfer objectives and playful introduction to an important enterprise software can be achieved. This paper presents the Pupils' Academy based on the online SAP ERP Simulation Game ERPsim as an example of how the enterprise software SAP ERP is successfully applied to strengthen study skills. In addition, the pupils learn how to deal with the SAP platform and train skills like decision making, analysis, strategy development, data processing and presentation. The positive impact on study skills is evidenced with the help of a self-assessment by means of an IT-based survey carried out by the participating students. These examinations include the activities related to the two study skills time management and teamwork.	study skills;online business game;didactic framework;IT-based questionnaire; ERPsim;vocational school	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7474611	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es
Improving the Identification of Hedonic Quality in User Requirements — A Controlled Experiment	10.1109/RE. 2017.49	Context and Motivation Systematically engineering a good user experience (UX) into a computer-based system under development demands that the user requirements of the system reflect all needs, including emotional, of all stakeholders. User requirements address two different types of qualities: pragmatic qualities (PQs), that address system functionality and usability, and hedonic qualities (HQs) that address the stakeholder's psychological well-being. Studies show that users tend to describe such satisfying UXes mainly with PQs, and that some users seem to believe that they are describing a HQ when they are actually describing a PQ. Question/Problem The problem is to see if classification of any user requirement as PQ-related or HQ-related is difficult, and if so, why. Principal Ideas/Results We conducted a controlled experiment in which twelve requirements-engineering and UX professionals, hereinafter called "classifiers" classified each of 105 user requirements as PQ-related or HQ-related. The experiment shows that neither (1) a classifier's involvement in the project from which the requirements came nor (2) the classifier's use of a detailed model of the qualities in addition to the standard definitions of "PQ" and "HQ" has a positive effect on the consistency of the classifier's classification with that of others. Contribution The experiment revealed that classification of user requirements is a lot harder than initially assumed.	Hedonic Quality;Pragmatic Quality;Controlled Experiment;User Experience; Project Involvement; Definitions of Pragmatic and Hedonic Qualities;Quality Model	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8048907	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
A Method of Purchase Prediction Based on User Behavior Log	10.1109 /ICDMW. 2015.179	In this paper, we propose a method to predict next-one-day-purchase behavior of "Online to Offline"(O2O) itemsbased on huge scale of user behavior log. The overall solution isdescribed in 2 parts: the feature engineering of the user behaviorlog and the ensemble of different supervised learning models. Inthe feature engineering section, besides the basic features, wefurther analyze the behavior of mobile users and propose somespecial features in O2O scenarios. Those scenarios includes thegroup-based rank, the transition rate, the centralized proportion, re-buy patterns, geohash-related features and etc. which haveimproved the model a lot in practice. Besides, group-based rankcould be easily extended to other similar business scenarios. Next, model ensemble are tuned in 2 ways: 1) blended models that aretrained randomly sampled data to enrich the diversity of thetraining data to boost the performance, 2) training individualmodel for different patterns of user-item pair, like the next-daypurchaseprediction, re-buy patterns and etc. Finally, a blendedof the above models are used to build the prediction result. Toevaluate the proposed method, we use the data provided byAli Mobile Recommendation Competition held in 2015 whichconsisted of the behavior logs of items from mobile users in onemonth from Nov. 18, 2014 to Dec.18, 2014, and predict purchasebehavior of O2O items in Dec.19, 2014. The result is evaluatedunder F1 prediction score metric and it achieve a good scores 8.64% that ranks 4th over more than 7,000 teams in the competition.	gradient boosting;model ensemble;feature engineering	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7395781	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es

Industry-University Collaboration: An Educational Program with Automotive Industry	10.1109 /TALE48000. 2019.9226013	In universities, it is well known that implement projects with Industry is beneficial for students as they develop different outcomes that will help them in their professional activities. If to this relationship between Industry-University, students from different universities of the world are added to collaborate in international engineering projects, the benefits will be greater: Students will learn ways of working from other countries, so that will help to create societies of engineers who will interact with harmony between countries and cultures. Links between students from different countries will be created to solve common engineering projects. This article is about the experiences of Tecnologico de Monterrey, Campus State of Mexico, as a member of an academic program with Automotive Industry called PACE (Partners for the Advancement of Collaborative Engineering Education). In this program, international projects were developed, making teamwork with students from different universities of the world. Students worked in multidisciplinary and multicultural teams with different time zones and languages. Videoconferencing tools were used for long-distance communication. Each year a forum was organized, where teams met to deliver progress and their finished project. Projects were related to different areas of Automotive Engineering such as design, manufacturing and production of components.	industry-university collaboration;international projects;educational innovation;long-distance collaboration	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9226013	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es
Visual Acuity Assessment Device for Mute and/or Deaf-Mute Individuals	10.1109 /HNICEM60674 .2023.10589229	This paper is introduced as an exploration of how to utilize advanced technology and computing can assist individuals who are mute and/or deaf-mute individuals. It recognizes the rapid progress in technology and computing, which opens up opportunities to address the unique needs of this particular group. The research question addressed in this paper is how we can use accurate time sign language recognition to assist people suffering from mutism and deafness to make the healthcare system more inclusive and accessible to them, especially when taking visual acuity assessments which is normally needed for acquiring eyeglasses. The system comprises a microprocessor unit and a Python-based program that is used to facilitate the visual acuity assessment properly and accurately. The keyfindings of this paper suggest that realtime sign language recognition technology can significantly improve the healthcare experience for individuals who are suffering from mutism and deafness by facilitating communication and reducing barriers to access facilities for eye health care to person with disability like person who are mute and deaf. The study also highlights the need for further research and development so as to improve the accuracy and efficiency of sign language recognition technology for people who are mute and deaf.	American Sign Language (ASL);Visual Acuity;Sign Language Recognition; Machine Learning	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10589229	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es
iProg: Getting started with Programming: Pilot experiment in two elementary schools	10.1109/SIIE. 2017.8259651	The results obtained by the elementary school students in subjects like math and Portuguese mother language have been worrisome during the last few years. There are several reasons for this, but opinions point to the student's inability to solve problems, difficulties in logical reasoning and lack of critical attitude. The Portuguese Ministry of Education proposed in 2015/2016, in extracurricular period, the Getting Started with Programming challenging in primary School activities, with the intention of promoting computational thinking competences in students. Two schools from Coimbra city opted to use Scratch software for the implementation of this project aiming to promote school success in subjects already mentioned. The project, based on the academic curriculum of 4th grade, intends to link the theoretical knowledge with the practical knowledge, promoting the characteristic values of the city of Coimbra. This project implementation resulted in different applications (computer games) created by students, covering the contents of the mentioned subjects, but concretizing these knowledge with the socio-cultural and environmental realities of the city of Coimbra. The following study demonstrates the results obtained in 5 classes in 2015-2016 and six classes in 2016-2017, according to student satisfaction and project evaluation.	Scratch;Curriculum Enrichment Activity; Satisfaction;Programming	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8259651	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es

A multi-criteria item-based collaborative filtering framework	10.1109/JCSSE.2014.6841835	Collaborative filtering methods are utilized to provide personalized recommendations for users in order to alleviate information overload problem in different domains. Traditional collaborative filtering methods operate on a user-item matrix in which each user reveal her admiration about an item based on a single criterion. However, recent studies indicate that recommender systems depending on multi-criteria can improve accuracy level of referrals. Since multi-criteria rating-based collaborative filtering systems consider users in multi-aspects of items, they are more successful at forming correlation-based user neighborhoods. Although, proposed multi-criteria user-based collaborative filtering algorithms' accuracy results are very promising, they have online scalability issues. In this paper, we propose an item-based multi-criteria collaborative filtering framework. In order to determine appropriate neighbor selection method, we compare traditional correlation approaches with multi-dimensional distance metrics. Also, we investigate accuracy performance of statistical regression-based predictions. According to real data-based experiments, it is possible to produce more accurate recommendations by utilizing multi-criteria item-based collaborative filtering algorithm instead of a single criterion rating-based algorithm.	Collaborative filtering;multi-criteria rating;item-based; accuracy;scalability	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=6841835	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	chance
Relation of Individual Time Management Practices and Time Management of Teams	10.1109/FIE44824.2020.9274203	Full research paper-Team configuration, work practices, and communication have a considerable impact on the outcomes of student software projects. This study observes 150 college students who first individually solve exercises and then carry out a class project in teams of three. All projects had the same requirements. We analyzed how students' behavior on individual pre-project exercises predict team project outcomes, investigated how students' time management practices affected other team members, and analyzed how students divided their work among peers. Our results indicate that teams consisting of only low-performing students were the most dysfunctional in terms of workload balance, whereas teams with both low-and high-performing students performed almost as well as teams consisting of only high-performing students. This suggests that teams should combine students of varying skill levels rather than allowing teams with only low performers or letting students to form teams without constraints. We also observed that individual students' poor time management practices impair their teammates' time management. This underlines the importance of encouraging good time management practices. Most teams reported that they divided tasks in a way that is beneficial for the acquisition of technical skills rather than collaboration and communication skills. Only a few teams assigned tasks so that students would have worked only on tasks they already knew and thus felt most comfortable to work with.	student project;time management;team configuration	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9274203	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Mining relationships in learning-oriented social networks	10.1109/DSAA.2015.7344877	The widespread use of computing and communications technologies has enabled the popularity of social networks oriented to learn. In this work, we study the nature and strength of associations between students using an online social network embedded in a learning management system. With datasets from two offerings of the same course, we mined the sequences of questions and answers posted by the students to identify structural properties of the social graph, patterns of collaboration among students and factors influencing the final achievements. The results show some hints to pursue and investigate deep user analytics in online social learning systems, e.g., to build accurate prediction models for the success of effectiveness of the learning tasks based on the patterns of students' participation in the platform.	Online Social Networks; Informal Learning;Social Networks Analysis	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7344877	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es
Design and Realization of Transmission and Substation Engineering Safety Training System Based on VR Technology	10.1109/AEECA62331.2024.00042	Against the background of the current large-scale construction of electric power infrastructure, the safety of transmission and substation engineering has become the focus of industry attention. In order to overcome the limitations of traditional safety training methods, this study proposes a design scheme for a safety training system based on virtual reality (VR) technology for the characteristics of transmission and substation projects. The study first analyzes the demand for safety training in power transmission and substation engineering, and then elaborates on the design method of the system architecture, including key technologies such as 3D scene modeling, interactive function development, and system integration. Through a series of experimental validation, the study finds that the system can provide an immersive learning experience, significantly improve the safety awareness and operational skills of construction personnel, and demonstrate excellent training effects in the actual operational assessment. It is finally concluded that the safety training system for power transmission and substation projects based on VR technology is of great significance for improving the level of project safety and reducing the occurrence of safety accidents, and provides a new development direction for the field of power project safety training.	virtual reality;power transmission and transformation engineering; safety training;system design;interactivity	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10898526	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es

Exploring the Assessment List for Trustworthy AI in the Context of Advanced Driver-Assistance Systems	10.1109 /SEthics52569.2021.00009	Artificial Intelligence (AI) is increasingly used in critical applications. Thus, the need for dependable AI systems is rapidly growing. In 2018, the European Commission appointed experts to a High-Level Expert Group on AI (AI-HLEG). AI- HLEG defined Trustworthy AI as 1) lawful, 2) ethical, and 3) robust and specified seven corresponding key requirements. To help development organizations, AI-HLEG recently published the Assessment List for Trustworthy AI (ALTAI). We present an illustrative case study from applying ALTAI to an ongoing development project of an Advanced Driver-Assistance System (ADAS) that relies on Machine Learning (ML). Our experience shows that ALTAI is largely applicable to ADAS development, but specific parts related to human agency and transparency can be disregarded. Moreover, bigger questions related to societal and environmental impact cannot be tackled by an ADAS supplier in isolation. We present how we plan to develop the ADAS to ensure ALTAI-compliance. Finally, we provide three recommendations for the next revision of ALTAI, i.e., life-cycle variants, domainspecific adaptations, and removed redundancy.	machine learning;ethics; functional safety;automotive software;trustworthy AI	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9474814	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
AI-Based Assistant for Determining the Required Performance Level for a Safety Function	10.1109 /IECON49645.2022.9969007	Standards such as ISO 13849 and ISO 12100 enable users to model safety related control elements with safety functions, according to a specified architecture and required performance level. In this direction, a novel Artificial Intelligence (AI)-based assistant is introduced in this paper to aid in determining the required performance level parameter by indulging the user in a dialog-based conversation regarding hazard scenarios. This will help inexperienced machinery safety personnel (e.g. mechanical engineer) to get an overview of the safety engineering aspects, before consulting with safety experts for risk assessment.	Artificial intelligence; machinery safety;performance level;safety function; chatbot	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9969007	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
A Fine-Grained Data Mining Model Based on Psychometric Data	10.1109 /ICMCCE51767.2020.00250	As social development and the pace of life gradually accelerates, psychological pressure and conflict become more and more prominent, and mental health becomes an issue of growing concern for the country and its people. In order to study the relationship between people's mental health problems and their own personal information factors, the authors use a fine-grained mining model of psychometric data. First, the model clusters the user groups by the k-means++ clustering algorithm, then uses C4.5 decision tree algorithm for classification and prediction in each group, and finally synthesizes the results of all the decision tree predictions to establish a highly accurate prediction model of mental health factors through a cyclic iterative approach.	Psychological Assessment; Data Mining;kmeans++;C4.5	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9421763	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Towards Automatic Capturing of Traceability Links by Combining Eye Tracking and Interaction Data	10.1109 /RE48521.2020.00064	Despite its numerous scientifically cited benefits, traceability is still rarely established in industrial settings. Years of research in the area have brought several different approaches to create traceability links including Information Retrieval (IR) and Machine Learning approaches. However, their accuracy and overall traceability support is not sufficient yet to be properly applied in practice. In my research, I want to investigate the usage of eye tracking and interaction data in the field of traceability. By tracking how software engineers interact with documents, where they focus on and recording gaze links between those documents, an algorithm is designed to obtain trace links between artifacts from these data. Eye tracking and interaction data have the advantage that they can be recorded in an automatic, non-intrusive way without requiring manual effort. They give detailed insight about where people focus on when working on tasks. However, software support of eye tracking is still limited, especially in the context of dynamic content such as switching between, scrolling or editing documents. Therefore, one essential step of my research is to provide software support for recording eye tracking data in dynamic document environments. By combining eye tracking data with additionally recorded metadata such as interactions, this eye tracking framework shall enable the automatic capturing of gaze links and gaze durations during software engineering tasks. The approach of using eye tracking in the context of traceability will be evaluated in several usage scenarios such as requirements coverage assessment.	software traceability;eye tracking;interaction data; trace links	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9218195	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Deep Learning Based Computer Vision Bound Fall Detection for Elderly People	10.1109 /SCOReD60679 .2023.10563480	Due to the devastating effects, such as increased mortality and morbidity, falls among the elderly are a significant health issue globally. Supporting the elderly in their daily activities is a significant problem for society because they are the age group with the largest rate of population growth. An automated fall detection system has gained popularity in the healthcare sector due to the social and financial benefits it offers. Vision-based fall detection systems have a great promise now that Smart Homes are a growing trend and there are more cameras in our everyday environments. An autonomous real-time fall detection system based on vision is given in this paper. In this research, we suggested a 3D RGB camera-based method for fall detection. Machine learning algorithms, which were trained on characteristics retrieved by a deep learning-based computer vision algorithm, are used to distinguish between occlusion, falling, and routine everyday activities. Deep learning algorithms are used to identify people in videos. Two datasets—one developed locally and the other made public—were used for the experimental validation of the suggested methodology. Several assessment metrics are computed for evaluation. This analysis demonstrated the efficacy of the suggested solution. Temporal characteristics in a video series are captured using motion history images, and spatial features are then effectively retrieved for classification using a depth-wise convolutional neural network.	Elderly;Video-based;Fall detection;Daily Activities; Artificial Intelligence;Deep learning;Machine Learning	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10563480	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Expert Mining for Evaluating Risk Indicators Scenarios	10.1109 /COMPSACW. 2014.38	To take maximum advantage of open source software (OSS), the understanding, management and mitigation of OSS adoption risks is crucial. The objective is to avoid the impact of potentially significant adverse events on the business. Bayesian networks allow the integration of open source community data and expert judgement in order to determine the value of risk indicators. The approach taken here is to ask domain experts to evaluate specific scenarios of OSS community data (or risk drivers) in terms of values of risk indicators. In this paper, we describe the structure of tactical workshops with the purpose of obtaining the domain expert evaluation. The results of this evaluation are used in the RISCOSS methodology to construct Bayesian networks that map data from community risk drivers into statistical distributions that are feeding a platform management dashboard. We describe the empirical application of the tactical workshops and the lessons learned from the workshops conducted so far.	OSS;risks;Bayesian networks;social network analysis;risk indicators;expert workshop;driver;OSS adoption	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=6903130	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Poster: Kotlin Assimilating the Android Ecosystem - An Appraisal of Diffusion and Impact on Maintainability	10.1145 /3639478. 3643071	Kotlin is a language alternative to Java, introduced in 2011. It promises to address many of Java's limitations and lead to better application maintainability. In 2017, it became a first-class language for Android development with full tool support. We mined a dataset of 2708 Android applications on which we based our study. Our empirical assessment of the diffusion of Kotlin in Android app development shows that it is now used in around 40% of projects. Kotlin adoption has a significant positive effect on code maintainability metrics and in popularity among end-users and developers. Overall, Kotlin appears to be successfully fulfilling its promise of being a better Java for Android development.	Software Maintainability; Android Development;Kotlin	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10554952	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Using Assurance Cases to assure the fulfillment of non-functional requirements of AI-based systems - Lessons learned	10.1109 /ICSTW58534. 2023.00040	While AI as a cross-sector technology is applied to more and more use cases and contexts, concerns and questions about the impact of this use on the people involved and society as a whole are increasing. Many companies want to act on these concerns and put a high emphasize on the ethical and fair use of AI in their use cases. But up to date easily applicable methods to translate ethical values, such as fairness, into technical specifications are often missing. One method to do so previously described in literature is the development of an Assurance Case. An Assurance Case presents the argument structure of how a claim ("The system is fair") can be substantiated by evidences like tests. To test the application of the method for fairness requirements in the real world and derive important insights for future use, the method was tested with the real life use case of a software product, which assigns positions in the training of doctors in hospitals. By testing the method in a real life setting, it was possible to develop it further and both, increase its usability and facilitate the focus on ethical aspects such as fairness. Fundamental questions were: Can the method of Assurance Cases be used to enhance fairness of an AI system? What is the application like in an industry context? How can one improve the method of Assurance Cases to be applicable for the assessment of fairness in AI systems? Together with developers, software and domain experts as well as AI and Open Innovation experts and researchers, the method was applied to the use case of an industry partner. Key insights are that the developed Assurance Case is of great help to the industry partner, especially when thinking about future adaptations, communication and potential regulations or required evidences to support their claim of a fair system. Based on the insights derived from testing the process, the method can be improved, enabling it to be applied more efficiently on future use cases and thus enhancing the fairness of AI systems in the long term. Based on our experience, we consider the Assurance Case framework to be helpful and useful to be able to assure fairness of AI systems.	Assurance case; fairness; practical elaboration; medical rotations	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10132168	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es
Requirements engineering: The quest for the dependent variable	10.1109/RE. 2015.7320404	Requirements engineering is a vibrant and broad research area. It covers a range of activities with different objectives. By reviewing experiments previously included in systematic literature reviews, this paper provides an overview of the dependent variables used in experimental requirements engineering research. This paper also identifies the theoretical motivation for the use of these variables in the experiments. The results show that a wide range of different variables has been applied in experiments and operationalized through both subjective assessments (e.g., subjects' perceived utility of a technique) and objective measurements (e.g., the number of defects found in a requirements specification). The theoretical basis for these variables and operationalizations are unclear in most cases. Directions for theoretical work to identify suitable dependent variables are provided.	Requirements engineering; experiments; dependent variables; frameworks; measurement; theory	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7320404	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Adjustment of Mutant Vector Elements of the Differential Evolution Method as Applied to Solving the Problem of Power Shortage Minimization of Electric Power Systems	10.1109 /SIBIRCON56155. 2022.10016950	The adequacy assessment is a topical tool for planning the progress of electric power systems and includes several important calculation steps, namely: the formation of random states, minimization of power shortages, and determination of reliability indicators. Modern software complexes use various types of models for minimizing power shortages, flow, including linear and non-linear models, as well as appropriate methods for solving problems based on these models. In current paper, differential evolution methods are used to solve nonlinear problems, and three options for adapting the known differential evolution algorithms DE, aDE and jDE to solving the problems are considered. An important part of the work is the analysis of existing and proposed options for modifying the mutation process. Which can be used in the above methods. The main changes include an additional check of compliance of mutant vectors with upper and lower constraints, and in case of their discrepancy, three options for correcting mutant vectors are considered. The experiments performed involved 3 and 7 node systems and showed the advantage of the implemented methods using the correction of the elements of mutant vectors in the form of an increase in the speed of solving problems up to 47% relative to the existing correction method. (Abstract)	heuristic algorithms; differential evolution; mutation strategy; power system reliability; minimization of power shortage; maximum allowable flow; quadratic model; adequacy assessment	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10016950	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

A KPI-based Condition Monitoring System for the Beer Brewing Process	10.1109/ETFA.2019.8869184	The process of beer brewing is very complex as it has to fulfill strict demands on the product quality as well as on the availability and the performance of the plant. As a consequence, a condition monitoring of the beer brewing process and its visualization plays an important role such that all relevant deviations are detected as early as possible by the production manager. While a general process for condition monitoring already exists, there currently exists no approach to realize this process for the domain of beer brewing. Therefore, this paper presents a condition monitoring system for the beer brewing process developed in an industrial project. This condition monitoring system is based on Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) that support the production manager in evaluating the actual state of the production processes. A set of brewery-specific KPIs are determined and discussed in the paper. In addition, software architecture and visualization of the KPIs in a brewery-specific dashboard are presented. We evaluate our concept at various beer breweries and report about lessons that we have learned.	Condition Monitoring;Key Performance Indicators; Production Systems; Microservice Architecture	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8869184	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Outsourced Products Task Allocation via Group Multirole Assignment with Considering Variance	10.1109/CSCWD57460.2023.10152644	The phenomenon of uneven product quality in software outsourcing enterprises is common. Even for products with similar functionality, the company cannot guarantee the final delivery quality. Effectively solve the stability of product quality, which is more conducive to long-term cooperation between customers and the company. Hence, this paper formalizes the Outsourced Products Task Allocation (OPTA) problem via the Environments-Classes, Agents, Roles, Groups, Objects (E-CARGO) model. Through its sub model Group Multirole Assignment (GMRA), a team with the optimal qualification value can be obtained. However, the stability of the assignment result is still not guaranteed. Therefore, this paper innovatively introduces the concept of variance and proposes the Group Multiple Role Assignment with Considering Variance (GMRACV) model to tackle this issue. And make better improvements to it, achieving a performance loss of 1% in exchange for about 32% stability. Large-scale randomized experiments show that the proposed model can effectively reduce the variance between products while maintaining the overall quality of all products. And for data with different distributions, the model can still obtain excellent results stably, which further verifies the feasibility of the model.	Outsourced Products with Stable Quality;Role- Based Collaboration (RBC);E-CARGO;Group Role Assignment (GRA);Group Multirole Assignment (GMRA);GMRA with Considering Variance (GMRACV)	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10152644	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es
Generating Team Quality Formula to Predict Product Quality in Software Engineering Project of College Students	10.1109/ICTS52701.2021.9607916	In the CHAOS report 2020 released by the Standish Group, "a good team" is an essential factor in determining the success of a project. Therefore, team quality assessment becomes significant for team management. Furthermore, it has believed that the quality of the product developed represents the quality of the development team. For this reason, it is necessary to measure the quality of the team at any point, so we can take mitigation steps to improve the quality. The study has two aims: (1) to build a team quality measurement model to prove that team quality positively correlates with product quality and (2) to produce a team quality formula to predict product quality. We conducted the study on ten teams with 57 students who attended the Software Development Workshop class. The students applied self-assessment to assess the quality of the team. In addition, software development practitioners carried out product quality assessments. The method used to obtain a relationship between the two is the Pearson correlation. We generated a team quality measurement formula using the Brute Force method. This study proves that the quality of the development team has a positive correlation with the quality of the product developed by 0.87. Meanwhile, the team quality formula can be used as a reference to predict the quality of the product developed	team quality;team quality formula;product quality; software development; capacity building	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9607916	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Data-driven Development of Digital Health Applications on the Example of Dementia Screening	10.1109/MeMeA52024.2021.9478676	Following the paradigm of precision medicine, the combination of health data and Machine Learning (ML) is promising to improve the quality of healthcare services e.g. by making diagnoses and therapeutic interventions as early and precise as possible. The implementation of this approach requires sufficient amounts of data with a high quality along the data life cycle. This goal seems recently achievable through the implementation of several national digital health strategies and the hope of a growing societal acceptance of digital health applications due to the implications of the COVID-19 pandemic. But, a collection of tools and methods is missing, which supports developers to use data as driving force of the development process. Due to the iterative nature of software application development, it allows the continuous improvement through the integration of collected digital data. We refer to this as a data-driven approach and identify steps to take and tools for its implementation. Associated challenges and opportunities of this translational approach are outlined on the example of a self-developed dementia screening application. Using our methodology, we compared multiple ML algorithms based on the data of an observational study (n=55) and achieved models with sensitivity up to 89% for unhealthy participants within this use case.	Data-driven Development; Machine Learning;Digital Psychometrics;Dementia; Mobile Screening;Ambulatory Assessment	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9478676	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

A daytime obstructive sleep apnea severity assessment framework	10.1109/EMBC.2016.7591205	Obstructive sleep apnea (OSA) is a prevalent sleep disorder characterized by repeated episodes of complete or partial blockage of the upper airway. These episodes can interfere with sound sleep and have fatal health consequences. They can also reduce the flow of oxygen to vital organs, like the brain, and lead to brain damage. In this paper, we leverage the correlation between brain damage and OSA to design a prediction framework that can assess the severity level of the OSA condition, as well as estimate the Apnea-Hypopnea Index (AHI) using only features obtained during wakefulness. Our daytime severity screening tool can enable the prioritization of patients for PSG studies based on the severity of their condition and can enable a more timely perioperative risk stratification. The proposed framework has a two-layered design that first classifies patients into coarse-grained OSA severity categories, before proceeding with the fine-grained AHI estimation within the classified category in the second layer. The performance of this framework was evaluated using the PSG's AHI scores as a gold standard. Using the proposed framework, patients can be classified into the correct severity group with 99.6% accuracy and their AHI can be estimated within an error of 4.5 events/hour, making the proposed system a promising reliable, daytime alternative for OSA severity screening.	Heart rate;Sleep apnea; Feature extraction; Biomedical monitoring; Software;Data collection	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7591205	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es
Automatically identifying focal methods under test in unit test cases	10.1109/SCAM.2015.7335402	Modern iterative and incremental software development relies on continuous testing. The knowledge of test-to-code traceability links facilitates test-driven development and improves software evolution. Previous research identified traceability links between test cases and classes under test. Though this information is helpful, a finer granularity technique can provide more useful information beyond the knowledge of the class under test. In this paper, we focus on Java classes that instantiate stateful objects and propose an automated technique for precise detection of the focal methods under test in unit test cases. Focal methods represent the core of a test scenario inside a unit test case. Their main purpose is to affect an object's state that is then checked by other inspector methods whose purpose is ancillary and needs to be identified as such. Distinguishing focal from other (non-focal) methods is hard to accomplish manually. We propose an approach to detect focal methods under test automatically. An experimental assessment with real-world software shows that our approach identifies focal methods under test in more than 85% of cases, providing a ground for precise automatic recovery of test-to-code traceability links.	Traceability;unit testing; method under test	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7335402	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
A Study on Product Recommendation System based on Deep Learning and Collaborative Filtering	10.1109/ICAECT57570.2023.10117628	This essay analyses and contrasts the literature that has already been written about various product recommendation systems and the mechanisms that underlie them. Although there are many research contributions in the literature, in this article I have critically and thoroughly examined recent research and review papers that are relevant to AI-based product recommendation systems. The present techniques are divided into groups based on the fundamental ideas included into their processes. The idea put out by the concerned writers, the experimental technique, and the performance assessment criteria are highlighted. Also noted are the researchers' assertions. The flaws that have been found are highlighted together with our results from the thorough literature study. This work is crucial for the comparison of different AI-based product recommendation systems, which is a necessary step before dealing with related problems. Following a review of the literature, I have put up a system for recommending products to users, in which the tool suggests products that a particular user would want to buy. I have gathered information about items and users by using ML algorithms. The suggested system establishes a link between the people and the products.	Artificial Intelligence; Collaborative Filtering;Deep Learning;Machine Learning; Product Recommendation Systems	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10117628	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Risk Assessment of User-Defined Security Configurations for Android Devices	10.1109/ISSRE.2016.30	The wide spreading of mobile devices, such as smartphones and tablets, and their advancing capabilities, ranging from taking photos to accessing banking accounts, make them an attractive target for attackers. This, together with the fact that users frequently store critical information in such devices and that many organizations allow employees to use their personal devices to access the enterprise information infrastructure and applications, makes security assessment a key need. This paper proposes an approach for assessing the security risk posed by user-defined configurations in Android devices. The approach is based on the analysis of the risk (impact and likelihood) of user misconfiguration to harm the device or the user. The impact and likelihood values are defined based on a Multiple-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) performed on the inputs provided by a set of security experts. A case study considering the user-defined configurations of 561 Android devices is presented, showing that the majority of the users neglect important and basic security configurations and that the proposed approach can be used in practice to characterize the security risk level of such devices.	security configuration assessment;mobile devices; security benchmarking	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7774544	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Description of Software for Comparative Analysis of Clustering Methods	10.1109/SIBIRCON56155.2022.10017038	This paper presents the structure of software for comparative analysis of clustering methods. The entire path of the software is described. It all starts with data extraction. Then the stage of data preparation. The third stage is the stage of normalizing the values. Then comes the fourth stage – the stage of division into clusters. The software uses two clustering methods, namely k-means and agglomerative clustering. The main idea of the k-means method is that the data is randomly divided into clusters, after that the middle of the masses is iteratively recalculated for at least some cluster acquired at the last step, after that the vectors are again divided into clusters in accordance with which of the new centers came out to be closer to the selected indicators. Agglomerative clustering is a type of cluster analysis. The essence of the method is as follows. Several groups are being created. Any group contains one object at the initial stage, after it finds two more similar groups. Binds groups and this process is repeated until a whole group of similar instances is formed. The fifth stage includes quality assessment. For this, the silhouette method is used. The result of the program execution is the division of data into clusters by two algorithms, as well as obtaining an estimate of the quality of clustering.	clustering;dataframe;k-means;agglomerative clustering;silhouette method	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10017038	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Decision making to calculate economic sustainability index: A case study	10.1109/DASA51403.2020.9317045	This work assesses the economic sustainability of industrial factories in Egypt based on the Analytical Hierarchical Process (AHP). The authors designed an economic sustainability index calculator (ESIC) using Unified Modelling Language (UML) and implemented the software using Visual basic of Applications (VBA) tool to the code the program. UML was used for the system analysis and design only, giving an insight to the system architecture. The manual method of calculating the economic sustainability index is included in this research and verified by using the designed ESIC. The categories of key performance indicators (KPIs) included in this work are production-based, plant-layout-based, and quality-based.	UML;Object-oriented modelling;Economic Sustainability;Economic Sustainability Index;VBA; Sustainability;AHP	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9317045	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Control Method for an Autonomous Group of Multi-Rotor Aircraft	10.1109/ICCT58878.2023.10347061	The purpose of this article is to improve the efficiency of control and monitoring of an autonomous group of multi-rotor aircraft by developing a software and hardware complex. The study is aimed at creating an intelligent system that will allow you to control a group of drones for basing, data backup, charging on-board batteries, and performance assessment. Simplicity, diversity, good design scalability, ease of control, high maneuverability of multi-rotor systems have led to their widespread use. However, this type of design is not aerodynamically stable and for this reason needs an active stabilization system that would correct the speed of rotation of the propellers in real time. The developed PAK will allow you to control a group of multi-rotor aircraft by sending various commands. The developed system will allow automatic landing of a multirotor copter on a moving platform. In the course of the work, a general method for controlling an autonomous group of multi-rotor aircraft was described, and a structural-graphic diagram of the UAV stabilization system was developed. The structure of information flows in the UAV control system has been developed. The developed models will be used to build a simulation model, as well as in the direct development of a control system. a structural-graphic diagram of the UAV stabilization system has been developed. The structure of information flows in the UAV control system has been developed. The developed models will be used to build a simulation model, as well as in the direct development of a control system. a structural-graphic diagram of the UAV stabilization system has been developed. The structure of information flows in the UAV control system has been developed. The developed models will be used to build a simulation model, as well as in the direct development of a control system.	control system;unmanned aerial vehicles;group of robots;monitoring	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10347061	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Items' difficulty level determination based on a Statics test with parameters variation	10.1109/FIE.2014.7044334	Looking for the improvement of the students' learning, the engineering school of EAFIT University is currently developing an evaluation and training system. In this system, each student has the option of doing "dynamic" exercises in a specific field of a subject. Whenever a student uses the system, an exercise is generated with different parameters and values. The mentioned system (Evaluation System) has been used in the last semesters, achieving the improvement in the students' comprehension and learning level of the Statics subject. The system under development, allows the students to train themselves in different topics of the subject and, at the same time, it allows the teachers to evaluate the learning process. Based on the fact that in the course assessments, an exam with different parameters and values is presented every time a student accesses the system, it is possible that some students present tests with different complexity levels. Therefore, the test could be considered inequitable for some people. This paper presents an analysis of the difficulty level of a test generated with the system. The test was applied to two different groups of students which are taking the course in the 2014-1 semester. The first group took a test where the items' values and parameters were not changed; and the second one, took a test where the items' values and parameters change for each student. Based on the obtained results, a statistical study is made which intends to determine the difficulty and discrimination level of each of the test items, both for the dynamics parameters test and the fixed parameters test in order to finally determine how much varies the items' difficulty due to the parameters variation. This will help to generate more equitable tests in the future for the assessment of a group of students that are taking the course.	Evaluation system;Dynamic tests;fixed tests;Statics; Statistical methods	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7044334	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es
Incorporating Prior Scientific Knowledge Into Deep Learning for Precipitation Nowcasting on Radar Images	10.1109/JCSSE53117.2021.9493821	Precipitation nowcasting aims to precisely predict the rainfall intensity in the near future that can be applied in various applications. A common approach is to simulate the complex physical processes or extrapolate the rainfall from the current stage. The existing deep learning model for this task uses an end-to-end network to forecast, but this approach has often met with limited success due to the complexities of the problem. Therefore, this paper proposes a novel hybrid model that combines the scientific method from meteorology and the deep learning method from computer science. We experimented with the model on both simulated data and radar images. Also, we have created the simulated data to imitate important features from radar images. The results show that our hybrid modeling approach outperforms all baselines on almost all datasets (both simulated and the radar data).	Deep Learning;Nowcasting; Spatial-Temporal Analysis; Physical Processes;Radar Images	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9493821	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
API Description-Based Conformance Assessment of Architectural Design Decision	10.1109/ISOSE55356.2022.00013	Microservice APIs are often designed based on Domain-Driven Design. It can be challenging to judge the quality of the relation between such a design and the implemented API, especially when facing frequent releases and changes in an API and its design models. Manual conformance assessment of this relation is time-intensive and error prone. This paper proposes a novel approach for automated conformance assessment of API designs in relation to API design decisions. Our approach aims to provide the first fully automated conformance assessment approach based solely on the code of API Descriptions such as OpenAPI. We applied and exemplified our approach for checking conformance to the patterns and practices in an API design decision for mapping links in a system's domain model to API representations. The total accuracy score (F1-measure) for decision option identification in our multi-case study for this decision is 97.22%.	API Design;ADD;Architecture Conformance Assessment; DDD;Microservice Architecture	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9912616	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
On-line Test and Fault Location of Aviation General-purpose cables based on TDR	10.1109/CVIDLICCEA56201.2022.9825377	On-line monitoring and fault location of aviation general-purpose cables are necessary to ensure the safe operation of the system. In order to solve the problems of low efficiency, poor accuracy and less test items of traditional cable on-line quality detection methods, a novel on-line test equipment suitable for complex cables is proposed. This paper mainly presents the fault location technology based on solid-state time domain reflection (TDR). The human-computer interaction software is programmed with Microsoft Visual Studio. The data processing module and signal acquisition module are proposed based on MCU. In addition, the cable fault location module, test channel switching module, interface monitoring and protection module integrated with power supply module are designed. The equipment has the characteristics of high precision, fast speed with many test points. It implements the rapid and accurate positioning of cable faults while improving the efficiency of troubleshooting with application prospect.	Aviation General-purpose Cable;On-line Test;Fault Location;TDR	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9825377	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Proposal of a Data Collection Method for Realizing Feedback in a Program Tracing Exercise System	10.1109 /TALE62452. 2024.10834347	Program tracing tasks ask about the behavior of a program, such as "the next expression to be executed" or "the value of a variable during the execution of that expression." The program tracing exercise system developed by Tomoto et al. provides an environment that enables efficient practice using program tracing tasks. This system poses questions based on the program tracing tasks in response to the learner's answers. As feedback, it displays the program's correct behavior based on the progress of the question and shows the execution results with concrete variable values based on the learner's answers. However, generating new program tracing tasks and integrating them into this system requires significant effort and time. Therefore, the authors proposed a method for automatically generating program tracing tasks from programs. This paper proposes a method for collecting the data necessary to realize feedback. This method involves tracing program execution with the debugger gdb and collecting the necessary data based on the program's structure and the learner's answers. The evaluation using programs extracted from programming exercise textbooks showed that this method can correctly collect the data necessary to provide feedback.	Program tracing task;the GNU debugger;e-learning; programming;feedback	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10834347	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Multi-channel Spatio-Temporal Causal Representation Model for Cognitive Load Assessment in Physiological Signals	10.1109 /ICME57554. 2024.10687915	Cognitive load assessment task faces a significant challenge regarding the neglect of rich spatio-temporal dependencies and causal dependencies in multi-channel physiological signals. To this end, we present a multi-channel spatio-temporal causal representations model that explicitly characterize the inherent causal structural variability and spatio-temporal dependencies within a single channel and interrelationships among multiple channels. Particularly, a causal structure is constructed by optimizing a score-based causal function under the constraint of causal Markov property. It can effectively disentangle the latent spatio-temporal feature variables into two groups: causal representation and task-irrelevant representation. Empirical evaluations on two public datasets and one in-house dataset suggest our model significantly outperforms the state-of-the-art methods.	Cognitive load;Markov blanket;causal learning; spatio-temporal dependency	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10687915	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es
Using Generative AI to Support Standardization Work – the Case of 3GPP	10.1109 /SEAA64295. 2024.00038	Standardization processes build upon consensus between partners, which depends on their ability to identify points of disagreement and resolving them. Large standardization organizations, like the 3GPP or ISO, rely on leaders of work packages who can correctly, and efficiently, identify disagreements, discuss them and reach a consensus. This task, however, is effort-, labor-intensive and costly. In this paper, we address the problem of identifying similarities, dissimilarities and discussion points using large language models. In a design science research study, we work with one of the organizations which leads several workgroups in the 3GPP standard. Our goal is to understand how well the language models can support the standardization process in becoming more cost-efficient, faster and more reliable. Our results show that generic models for text summarization correlate well with domain expert's and delegate's assessments (Pearson correlation between 0.66 and 0.98), but that there is a need for domain-specific models to provide better discussion materials for the standardization groups.	machine learning; standardization; requirements;automation	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10803398	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Introducing Undergraduates to Pattern Recognition and Machine Learning through Speech Processing	10.1109 /ICASSP. 2019.8683618	This paper describes an educational project experience that achieves a software implementation and performance analysis of a blind signal to noise ratio (SNR) estimation system for noisy speech. The system is based on a pattern recognition paradigm and no clean speech reference signal is available. It is a product of the faculty's research and funded by a government contract. The faculty's research on a real-world issue in speech processing has been converted into an undergraduate project. Assessment results show that the project is viewed very favorably by students. Target versus control group results show that the target group feels better qualified for graduate study and career options in digital signal processing.	project based learning;blind SNR estimation;pattern recognition;quantitative assessment	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8683618	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Social Aspects and How They Influence MSECO Developers	10.1109 /CHASE. 2019.00032	Mobile software ecosystem (MSECO) is a new software development paradigm for mobile technologies, having three main dimensions, namely: Technical, Business and Social. The literature has a considerable number of studies on Technical and business dimensions, but only a few studies focus on the social aspects of MSECOs. However, the literature has enough to provide evidence that the actors involved, such as developers, are crucial to an MSECO. This study aims to complement earlier studies by describing new social factors that influence developers to work in a MSECO. We conducted a systematic literature review in order to identify these new factors, and a field study in which 20 developers were interviewed to understand how these factors can influence them to join or keep participating in a MSECO. We found that developer become more rigorous to continue participating then to adopt a MSECO.	Mobile Software Ecosystem, Social Aspects, Developer's Collaboration	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8817021	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem clab

Applying the multiclass classification methods for the classification of online social network friends	10.23919 /SOFTCOM. 2017.8115508	Online social networks (OSNs) are platforms which facilitate social interactions between their users through message exchange, photo and video sharing, status updates, etc. One of the most popular OSNs is Facebook. Connections between users on Facebook are modeled through concept of friendship. Each connection between users is binary - two users either are or aren't "friends". Information about of the actual intensity or nature of their connection is not available although in real life it can vary significantly. A majority of observed network friends are acquaintances in real-life while close friends are in the minority. The goal of this paper is to demonstrate and evaluate how user interaction statistics can be utilized for effective assessment of the nature of users' real-life relationship. Using an ensemble of popular classification algorithms, we will classify ego-user's network friends into 3 groups: close friends, friends and acquaintances. As our main contribution, we will compare the efficiency of chosen algorithms and suggest the best approach for conducting this type of analysis on similar OSN communication data.	online social networks; Facebook;multiclass classification;educational data mining	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8115508	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Structural connectivity of temporal lobe structures detects temporal lobe epilepsy	10.1109 /ICBME. 2016.7890924	Temporal lobe epilepsy (TLE) is the most common form of adult epilepsy. Detection of TLE from neuroimaging data is a challenging task. In many cases, patients with findings from standard clinical examination do not show any identifiable abnormalities in magnetic resonance imaging (MRI). In this study, we propose a method to detect TLE from structural connectivity of temporal lobe structures, using an integration of diffusion tensor imaging (DTI), graph theory analysis, and machine learning tools. To this end, first, we apply probabilistic tractography to extract white matter fibers and generate weighted structural connectivity graphs of 17 TLE patients and 17 healthy control subjects. Machine learning of graph theoretical measures are then used to classify TLE patients and control subjects. Using leave-one-out cross-validation, we show that graph theory measures used in logistic regression classifiers achieve accuracy in the range of 76% to 91% for the classification of the 34 subjects into the TLE and control groups. The results suggest that machine learning of the graph theoretical metrics derived from DTI-based networks of temporal lobe regions may be used for the diagnosis of TLE patients. Such a method may improve diagnostic assessment, especially in patients without obvious abnormalities in the conventional, anatomical neuroimaging examinations.	temporal lobe epilepsy (TLE); magnetic resonance imaging (MRI);diffusion tensor imaging (DTI);probabilistic tractography;graph theory; structural connectivity network;machine learning; logistic regression classifier	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7890924	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Applying Two-rounds Collaborative Peer Review to Assess Students' Programming Assignments	10.1109 /ICEBE55470. 2022.00050	As peer code review gradually becomes a necessary skill for software developers, to adapt the mechanism of peer code review, the concept of peer review will be introduced into the course of education for students to learn the process of code review. However, most of the peer code reviews currently implemented in education are to allow students to review each other's programming work, and most of them only implement a single-round review, not a two-rounds review that is more in line with the actual software development company's use. The single-round review causes students to lack the habit and opportunity to correct their code errors, resulting in limited progress for students in peer code reviews. To improve the problems mentioned above, we propose a code-based assessment system that integrates the mechanism of the two-rounds review and modifies the original system architecture for both students and teachers. On the student side, students can revise their code and upload it, so that students can learn programming skills and code quality through code revision. On the teacher side, the new review feedback score function allows the teacher to know whether student review comments are helpful or not, and to know how well students understand the review metrics and programming concepts through the feedback scores. The teacher can also help the students to review the program so that each student can receive review comments after each round of review. Lastly, through the performance of the experimental group and the control group to analyze the impact of the two-rounds peer review on students' learning and use the UTAUT model to analyze the students' acceptance of the two-rounds review evaluation system.	peer review;code quality;peer code review system;two-rounds peer review	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10035092	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Assessment of Human Emotional Responses to AI-Composed Music: A Systematic Literature Review	10.1109/SCSE61872.2024.10550861	In the world of musical creation, the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) represents a significant paradigm shift in emotional engagement. This research investigates the human emotional responses evoked when listening to AI-composed music. Focused on figuring out the emotional impact of AI-composed music, the study explores the complex relationship between human emotional experiences and compositions crafted by AI algorithms. Through a comprehensive literature review, this paper examines existing methodologies, insights, and gaps in understanding the emotional dimensions of AI-composed music. Major findings reveal that while AI software like artificial intelligence virtual artist (AIVA) shows it can help explore emotional authenticity, ongoing doubt and preference for music made by humans highlight the need for more research. Attitudes of both listeners and music professionals toward AI-composed music are characterized by skepticism and negative perceptions, emphasizing the urgency to address reservations and investigate the unique emotional qualities of AI-composed music. Furthermore, the complex nature of music emotion recognition, influenced by factors such as music genre, cultural perspective, and age group, complicates understanding emotional responses to both human-created and AI-composed music. The paper supports the development of analytical methods, particularly through machine learning and deep learning approaches, to enhance understanding of the complexities of emotional responses and improve AI music composition. A human-experience-centered framework is proposed to address subjectivity in assessing emotional responses to music. This research aims to understand the details of emotional responses and find out if AI-composed music can really evoke emotions comparable to human-created compositions.	AI-composed music;artificial intelligence;emotional responses	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10550861	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Evaluation of Qiulin Group's Internal Control System: —Based on the Fuzzy Comprehensive Evaluation Model of Internal Control	10.1109/ICMSSE53595.2021.00010	As an important part of company management, internal control runs through all aspects of business activities. In view of the non-quantitative of the internal control evaluation system of the enterprise, this article applies the fuzzy comprehensive evaluation model of enterprise internal control, and evaluates the internal control of the group by analyzing the relevant data of Qiulin Group's financial statements. Finally, it puts forward relevant suggestions to improve the internal control of the enterprise, hoping to provide a reference for the improvement of internal control of the enterprise.	Internal Control;Influencing Factors of Enterprise Internal Control;Fuzzy Comprehensive Evaluation Model of Internal Control	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9609258	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Selective Lead Integration: Enhancing ECG Classification for Effective Cardiac Monitoring	10.1109/WF-IoT58464.2023.10539513	The advent of telehealth technology has ushered in advanced avenues for remote, non-invasive health monitoring, precipitating a surge in the development and application of remote health monitoring platforms. Such platforms are increasingly integrated with sophisticated algorithms to enable timely detection and diagnostic alerts. Prominently, electrocardiogram (ECG) monitoring systems have become pivotal in diagnosing a myriad of cardiac conditions. However, modern cardiac monitoring paradigms exhibit a deficiency in understanding the nexus between diseases and the corresponding leads. This oversight not only diminishes the diagnostic accuracy but also incurs superfluous consumption of computational resources and data bandwidth, thus challenging the efficacy and sustainability of the monitoring process. This research introduces an innovative model tailored for the concurrent multiclass classification of ECG signals by leveraging a minimal and highly correlated set of leads. A performance assessment delineates that the proposed model attains a Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) range of 92.8%-99.7% in all 23 categories using only six leads, sur-passing existing ECG classification strategies that employ 12-lead ECG signals. Furthermore, empirical results underscore that our proposed strategy, even with its reduced lead count, achieves superior accuracy for three cardiac conditions and maintains equivalent accuracy for an additional 17 conditions according to the testing data set.	ECG monitoring;Heart diseases;12-Lead signal; Multiclass classification; Lead-wise grouping;datasets	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10539513	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Early Diagnosis of Mild Cognitive Impairment Using Random Forest Feature Selection	10.1109/BIOCAS.2018.8584773	Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a neurodegenerative disease which is progressive and can be described by amyloid deposition, and neuronal atrophy. In this study, a support vector machine (SVM) approach with radial basis function (RBF) has been proposed in order to detect the Alzheimer's disease in its early stage using multiple modalities, including positron emission tomography (PET), magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), and standard neuropsychological test scores. A total number of 896 participants from the Alzheimer's Disease Neuroimaging Initiative (ADNI) were considered in this study. The proposed approach is able to classify cognitively normal control (CN) group from early mild cognitive impairment (EMCI) with an accuracy of 81.1%. In addition, the accuracy of 91.9% for CN vs. late mild cognitive impairment and accuracy of 96.2% for CN vs. AD classifications have been achieved through the proposed model.	Machine Learning;Early Mild Cognitive Impairment; Alzheimer's Disease; Multimodal Imaging	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8584773	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Vulnerability Analysis on Internet of Things (IoT) Networks using Raspberry Pi and Open Web Application Security Project (OWASP)	10.1109 /FORTEI-ICEE64706. 2024.10824490	The security of a network supports a system so that every device is in a safe condition, with secure communication, and secure access control to every asset in the IoT ecosystem. Some previous research references make the topic of discussion in this research, namely security on IoT servers. On that basis, the idea was created to conduct vulnerability analysis on the IoT network using Raspberry Pi and OWASP (Open Web Application Security Project). The application of OWASP in IoT networks has proven successful on Raspberry Pi because of its flexibility compared to Personal Computer (PC). This is evidenced when an attack on a local network server is carried out, 7 types of vulnerabilities are found and then the stages of solving solutions to vulnerabilities on the server are carried out. The highest level of vulnerability obtained is categorized as "Medium" and the lowest level obtained is categorized as "Low". So, the conclusion of this research states that the highest vulnerability is obtained in the cloud hosting network type because it is connected to the internet, and it becomes a different thing on a local network that is only connected to a local area network.	IoT;OWASP;Raspberry Pi; Vulnerability	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10824490	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
An Approach to Design a Composite Index of Economic Development and Identifying the Bounds of its Levels	10.1109/ACITT. 2019.8779918	Paper considers the task of assessment of regions' economic development level using composite index assessment technology. It is proposed to design composite index by block convolution of two groups of partial indicators. First group contains indicators measured in absolute scale. Second group consists of relative measures of dynamics. For each group we proposed own procedure for data normalization and own method for data convolution in partial composite index. The procedure for identification of intervals' bounds on the composite index's scale for each level of economic development is proposed to the aim of classification of Ukraine's regions. Presented means for identification of intervals' bounds of data grouping may be used to solve other tasks independently from the way of design of composite index and set of initial indicators. The results calculated may be used in the decision-making system as source data for further calculations, as well as a criterion for determining the socio-economic development directions.	Composite index assessment technology;regions' economic development; economic information;data normalization;convolution; bounds of the level of economic development	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8779918	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es
Student Team Formation Using SCRUM	10.1109 /FIE58773. 2023.10343197	SCRUM (Scrum) is a popular framework for developing and sustaining complex products. It is designed to be an agile methodology that emphasizes collaboration, flexibility, and customer satisfaction. At its core, Scrum is built around the concept of a small, self-organizing team of people, known as a Scrum Team. This team works together to achieve a common goal, each member taking on a specific role and responsibility. In this paper, we propose a modified Scrum Team structure as a model for student teams in academic project environments. Our modification involves identifying specific roles within the team to provide more structure and align with industry practices. By doing this, we hope to help students better understand the importance of roles and responsibilities in project management and improve their project outcomes. The proposed approach involves providing a Scrum mapping for student teams of three and four members, with each member taking on a specific role based on Scrum principles. In our proposed approach, roles will rotate after each new assignment or a set number of times, giving students the opportunity to experience different roles and responsibilities within the team. We believe this approach will provide further exposure to the popular agile design approach and help students develop critical project management skills. We implemented our modified approach in a computer engineering course with lab components focused on microcontrollers to test our modified approach. Our experience using this approach was positive, with students reporting a greater understanding of project management concepts and improved project outcomes. Finally, we believe that our modified Scrum Team structure will also aid in the assessment of ABET's student outcome 5, which focuses on teamwork, communication, and project management. By providing a clear framework for project management and emphasizing the importance of roles and responsibilities within the team, we hope to help students develop the skills they need to succeed in their future careers.	SCRUM;Effective Team; Team Forming;Team Assessment	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10343197	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es
A method for assessing computational thinking in students using source code analysis	10.1109 /ICALT55010. 2022.00050	This paper summarizes research in progress, at a national scale, that analyzes large volumes of elementary school and high school projects to assess the development of skills, attitudes, and practices that students develop when solving problems via computer programming, grounded on their understanding of fundamental concepts in computing. The approach is independent of programming languages and uses a generic abstract syntax tree and projects' metadata to calculate metrics, and establish relationships between measures, school regions, educational centers, and student groups. The research relates source code analysis using abstract syntax trees to some of the main computational thinking concepts. Preliminary results obtained using the proposed method are presented and discussed.	Code analysis;computational thinking assessment;generic abstract syntax tree	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9853800	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Be My Eye (Third Eye for Blind People)	10.1109 /ICAIT61638. 2024.10690833	As of 2023, more than 2.2 billion people worldwide are visually impaired. Among them, more than 36 million people are totally blind, meaning they cannot perceive light, and about 217 million have moderate to severe visual impairment. This group faces a variety of difficulties on a daily basis. With this paper we strive to introduce a software solution that would help the visually impaired. Advanced technologies including object detection, optical character recognition (OCR), cash identification, voice commands, and navigation aid are all integrated into our suggested solution. This article covers the software's architecture, development methodology, user-centric features, results from impact assessments and usability evaluations, and emphasis on promoting autonomy, accessibility, and empowerment. By means of a modest analysis, the research illuminates the possibility that the program could have a beneficial effect on the lives of visually impaired users, so promoting inclusivity and empowerment within the digital sphere.	Assistive Technology; Accessibility;Visually Impaired;Comprehensive Software;Object Detection; OCR;Currency Detection; Voice Controls;Navigation; Usability Testing;Impact Evaluation;Empowerment; Inclusivity	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10690833	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Accuracy and Fairness in Pupil Detection Algorithm	10.1109 /BigMM52142. 2021.00011	Despite being highly accurate, widely used multimedia analysis algorithms can suffer from bias, affecting users' trust in them. For instance, algorithms for face recognition, pedestrian detection, and image search have recently been reported to be biased. In this paper, we move the discussion on algorithmic fairness to a new domain, namely, pupil detection. We audit a widely used OpenCV algorithm for pupil detection from the perspective of fairness and accuracy. The algorithm is audited using two different datasets: a single-person image dataset (CelebA), and a group image dataset (Images of Groups). In both datasets, we found the OpenCV pupil detection algorithm to provide reasonably high accuracy but also yield statistically significant bias with respect to gender. The results provide the first empirical evidence for the existence of gender bias in pupil detection algorithms in both single person as well as group image settings. These results could have a deleterious impact on downstream multimedia applications such as identity authentication, attention assessment, and e-learning. Finally, we discuss the process of appropriately choosing the pupil detection algorithm parameters that may help reduce bias while maintaining high accuracy in various multimedia applications.	Algorithms;Accuracy; Algorithmic Fairness;Face Detection;Gaze Tracking; Computer Vision;Pupil Detection;Machine Learning; Statistical Analysis	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9643325	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
The Impact of Integrating Renewable Energy Sources on Coherency Patterns in Electrical Power Systems	10.1109 /EPECS62845. 2024.10805503	Coherency assessment is essential for wide-area protection and control of interconnected power systems. The transient response of renewable energy sources (RESs) differs from conventional generators. Therefore, the increasing penetration of RESs necessitates the analysis of hybrid power system dynamics to ensure system security and reliability during various disturbances. This paper proposes an online coherency assessment strategy based on the frequency signals acquired from phasor measurement units (PMUs) to include RESs in the analysis. Moreover, it investigates the impact of RESs on the generators' coherency patterns. Coherent groups are identified under both limited and wide-scale integration of RESs. Moreover, the system's dynamic response is investigated in the case of uniform distribution of RESs among voltage-controlled buses. The 10-machine New England power system is adopted in this study. All time-domain simulations are conducted on the DigSILENT PowerFactory software. Results demonstrate the viability and effectiveness of the proposed strategy for online coherency identification in hybrid power systems. It also reveals that integrating RESs impacts coherent groups under certain conditions.	coherency assessment; renewable energy sources; electromechanical oscillations;Kendall rank correlation coefficient	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10805503	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Gamification in Agile Development Methodology: A Systematic Literature Review	10.1109 /NETAPPS6333. 2024.10823426	Gamification is a technique that uses game mechanics and aspects to engage and inspire people to complete a task. Gamification has grown in popularity in several industries recently, including software development. The purpose of this systematic literature review (SLR) is to review the most recent findings in the field of gamification's application to agile methodology between the years 2015 and 2024. With the help of search terms like "gamification," "agile methodology," and "game mechanics," "agile development," a thorough scan of databases including the IEEE Xplore, and Scopus was carried out. Articles and studies released in English were examined. Data were extracted analysed using a spreadsheet to organize information such as study design, sample size, research setting, kinds of game mechanics used, and major findings. To combine the results from the chosen studies and discover any recurring themes or patterns, a thematic analysis method was used. The findings of this SRL points to areas for further study and contributes to understanding the benefits and best practices of using gamification in agile methodology and provides insights for practitioners and researchers in the field.	gamification;Agile methodology;Agile gamification	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10823426	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Skin Temperature Assessment During Lumbar Sympathetic Blocks by Infrared Thermography	10.1109 /EMBC46164. 2021.9629731	Complex Regional Pain Syndrome (CRPS) is a pain disorder that can be triggered by injuries or surgery affecting most often limbs. Its multifaceted pathophysiology makes its diagnosis and treatment a challenging work. To reduce pain, patients diagnosed with CRPS commonly undergo sympathetic blocks which involves the injection of a local anesthetic drug around the nerves. Currently, this procedure is guided by fluoroscopy which occasionally is considered as little accurate. For this reason, the use of infrared thermography as a technique of support has been considered. In this work, thermal images of feet soles in patients with lower limbs CRPS undergoing lumbar sympathetic blocks were recorded and evaluated. The images were analyzed by means of a computer-aided intuitive software tool developed using MATLAB. This tool provides the possibility of editing regions of interest, extracting the most important information of these regions and exporting the results data to an Excel file. Clinical Relevance— The final purpose of this work is to value the potential of infrared thermography and the analysis of its images as an intraoperative technique of support in lumbar sympathetic blocks in patients with lower limbs CRPS.	Temperature distribution; Pain;Surgery;Tools;Skin; Thermal analysis;Data mining	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9629731	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Game coding to initiate an inchoate interest in computer science in middle-school girls	10.1109 /RESPECT. 2018.8491698	Summary form only given, as follows. The complete presentation was not made available for publication as part of the conference proceedings. By the onset of middle-school a gender-based computing experiential gap arises between male and female students. This disparity, which negatively impacts computing self-efficacy in girls, also influences course selection in secondary school and may be a variable in subsequent career choice. The underlying reasons for the gender-based digital divide, which may include socially pervasive gender stereotypes and a lack of early interaction with technology, are disparate and complex. Early intervention is required to ameliorate this gender disparity before it widens in high school. In order to address this issue and garner interest in the STEM disciplines, Barry University (BU) offered a two week coding camp for underrepresented girls in the North Miami area, in June of 2016 and 2017. Female students of middle-school age, unlike their male counterparts who tend to engage in solitary pursuits, use this adolescent developmental period to hone social skills within their peer group. The camp curriculum utilized the collaborative element to introduce the girls to the fundamentals of computer science, by familiarizing students with the concepts of design, critical thinking, and social awareness via video game coding with MIT's Scratch software. Post-camp feedback from the participants, their parents, and local educators was positive with regard to the girls' interest and a desire to pursue coding further and assessment of the student learning outcomes was satisfactory.	Outreach;Gender Inclusive; Underrepresented Middle School Girls;Assessment; Gaming	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8491698	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Optimization of Key Process Parameters for Surface Mount Technology Production Line Based on Improved Proximal Policy Optimization Algorithm	10.1109 /CBASE64041. 2024.10824406	The optimization of key process parameters on the surface mount technology (SMT) production line plays a significant role in improving the product quality qualification rate. Existing research methods involve identifying the mapping relationship between key process parameters and product quality through vast amounts of historical data, and then determining the optimal process parameters through optimization algorithms. However, in actual production environments, product quality is affected by factors that cannot be easily quantified, such as the quality of solder paste and environmental conditions, resulting in continuous changes to the optimal process parameters. Therefore, when optimizing key process parameters, it is necessary to make real-time adjustments based on the actual production conditions of the production line. This paper proposes an improved Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) algorithm. Firstly, the Actor network and Critic network in the PPO algorithm are replaced with a ID-CNN-GRU-Attention network structure. Secondly, the state space, action space, and reward function are designed based on the actual operating conditions of the SMT production line. Finally, the improved PPO algorithm is evaluated from three aspects: reward return, robustness, and success rate. Compared to the Actor-Critic algorithm, the improved PPO algorithm may have some limitations in terms of robustness, but it shows significant improvements in reward return and accuracy. Specifically, the reward return is increased by 76.22% and the accuracy is improved by 26.16% compared to the Actor-Critic algorithm. When compared to the standard PPO algorithm, the improved PPO algorithm demonstrates an increase in reward return by 29.31%, a reduction in variance by 2.4%, and an improvement in accuracy by 8.66 %.	SMT;PPO;1D-CNN;GRU; Process Parameter Optimization	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10824406	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

The selection of the corporate information system for innovative project management tasks	10.1109 /EIConRus. 2017.7910807	The usage of modern methods in innovation project management is a driving force of innovation system development. To maintain cognitive economy systematic development in Russian Federation it is necessary to select the management type for innovative project: process management, project management or traditional management. The usage of enterprise information systems solves many problems that occurs in every type of management. The aim of the article is to consider and analyze the classes of enterprise information systems, their functionality in the area of innovative project management using the comparative analysis method and method of expert assessment and to suggest the software products of particular class that could be used for innovative projects management tasks.	Innovation management; enterprise information system;project management; process management;the comparative analysis method;method of expert assessment	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7910807	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Brain Age Prediction in Children Aged 0–5 Years based on T1 Magnetic Resonance Images	10.1109 /ICBEA58866. 2023.00017	Purpose: BrainAge is a biomarker used to evaluate whether the brain is developing or aging normally, and accurate prediction of brain age in children can be used to determine whether children's brain development is in a normal state. The aim of this study is to propose an accurate prediction of brain age in children aged 0–5 years based on T1 magnetic resonance images and multiple machine learning methods.Methods: Using two feature extraction methods based on radiomics first order grey scale feature extraction and Freesurfer feature extraction with five machine learning modelling methods (support vector machine regression SVR, Gaussian process regression GPR, correlation vector regression RVR, K-neighbourhood regression KNR, random forest regression RFR).Results: The best mean absolute error (MAE/days) and correlation coefficient R-squared values obtained for each method are shown below: SVR: MAE=182.27, R=0.76; GPR:MAE=85.26, R=0.96; RVR: MAE=123.97, R=0.93; KNR: MAE=162.86, R=0.81; RFR: MAE=81.83, R=0.96; where Freesurfer feature extraction method and RFR machine learning modelling method can achieve the best accuracy. This study explored the effects of different feature extraction methods and brain age prediction modelling methods on the prediction of brain age prediction accuracy, and the best accuracy of MAE=81.83 was achieved for the brain age prediction of children in the age group of 0–5 years.	BrainAge;MRI;Machine Learning;Radiomics	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10248063	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Similarity Detection Techniques for Academic Source Code Plagiarism and Collusion: A Review	10.1109 /TALE48000. 2019.9225953	Source code plagiarism and collusion are continuing problems in academia. To deal with these issues, lecturers are often aided by automated code similarity detection techniques or tools. Students' programs are filtered by these, and suspicious groups of programs are displayed to the markers for further investigation. As the detection techniques are many and varied, it can be demanding to choose the most suitable one for a particular teaching context. This paper summarises the mechanisms by which each of these techniques works, compiled from publications listed by Google Scholar and one or more of the ACM digital library, IEEE Xplore digital library, ScienceDirect, Scopus, and the references of already listed publications. The review is intended as a guideline for lecturers seeking to choose the most suitable technique, and for researchers who are seeking to understand the current trends and the possible research gaps in this topic.	source code similarity detection;plagiarism; collusion;academic integrity; programming;computing education	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9225953	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es
Topic Modelling using Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) and Analysis of Students Sentiments	10.1109 /JCSSE58229. 2023.10201965	Open-ended question responses are an unstructured data source that contains extremely useful information. The idea of obtaining information using open-ended questions is particularly popular and frequently employed in various schools and digital platforms. In the field of education, universities collect and generate vast amounts of data daily, left unused or not analysed. This demonstrates the need to develop different models to promote the use of text-based data analysis techniques. In this study, surveys with open-ended questions were used to draw out analytical insights from student views on automated personalised feedback assessments. Opened-ended questions present questions that require answers that use natural language. The human language data described in text documents is made possible by the use of various Natural Language Processing (NLP) approaches. These approaches include the Latent Semantic Analysis (LSA) and Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) that analyse open ended questions and surveys data. In this study, LDA is used for modelling topics to analyse students' sentiments on the feedback assessment given to them regarding their performance on the module. Providing automated personalised feedback to large student groups has many challenges, such as the type of communication delivery mode and the language used for feedback about their progress. This study offers an application of NLP in an education environment to provide meaningful and useful student feedback. The paper presents the steps, algorithm and findings so that practitioners can apply this model to their education setting. The findings reveal 87% of students have positive sentiments, 7% are neutral, 5% are confused by the personalised feedback forms. This informs practitioners about the value of the feedback but also areas for future work when offering feedback to students.	LDA;sentiments;NLP; modelling;assessments	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10201965	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es

System Design of Multivariate Quality Control Based HR Department Staff Training Website for Shagang Group	10.1109/ICICTA.2015.231	In order to fully motivate and mobilize the staff in Jiangsu Shagang Group to consciously participate in the training and learning, we implement the credit rewards mechanism in the training process and put forward a new flexible assessment solution for employee training exam. We design and develop for HR Department of Shagang Group a staff training website system, in which the processing procedure is simplified through the combination of computerized processing. Borrowing the upgrade mode from online game, the website is displayed in the manner of "What You See Is What You Get" and strive to achieve the principles of "Fairness, Impartiality, Openness" to fully mobilize the enthusiasm of the employees.	Website Design;Multivariate Quality Control;Incentive Mechanism;Flexible Assessment;Human Resource Management	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7473448	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
LibD: Scalable and Precise Third-Party Library Detection in Android Markets	10.1109/ICSE.2017.38	With the thriving of the mobile app markets, third-party libraries are pervasively integrated in the Android applications. Third-party libraries provide functionality such as advertisements, location services, and social networking services, making multi-functional app development much more productive. However, the spread of vulnerable or harmful third-party libraries may also hurt the entire mobile ecosystem, leading to various security problems. The Android platform suffers severely from such problems due to the way its ecosystem is constructed and maintained. Therefore, third-party Android library identification has emerged as an important problem which is the basis of many security applications such as repackaging detection and malware analysis. According to our investigation, existing work on Android library detection still requires improvement in many aspects, including accuracy and obfuscation resilience. In response to these limitations, we propose a novel approach to identifying third-party Android libraries. Our method utilizes the internal code dependencies of an Android app to detect and classify library candidates. Different from most previous methods which classify detected library candidates based on similarity comparison, our method is based on feature hashing and can better handle code whose package and method names are obfuscated. Based on this approach, we have developed a prototypical tool called LibD and evaluated it with an update-to-date and large-scale dataset. Our experimental results on 1,427,395 apps show that compared to existing tools, LibD can better handle multi-package third-party libraries in the presence of name-based obfuscation, leading to significantly improved precision without the loss of scalability.	Android;third-party library; software mining	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7985674	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
LEOPARD: Identifying Vulnerable Code for Vulnerability Assessment Through Program Metrics	10.1109/ICSE.2019.00024	Identifying potentially vulnerable locations in a code base is critical as a pre-step for effective vulnerability assessment; i.e., it can greatly help security experts put their time and effort to where it is needed most. Metric-based and pattern-based methods have been presented for identifying vulnerable code. The former relies on machine learning and cannot work well due to the severe imbalance between non-vulnerable and vulnerable code or lack of features to characterize vulnerabilities. The latter needs the prior knowledge of known vulnerabilities and can only identify similar but not new types of vulnerabilities. In this paper, we propose and implement a generic, lightweight and extensible framework, LEOPARD, to identify potentially vulnerable functions through program metrics. LEOPARD requires no prior knowledge about known vulnerabilities. It has two steps by combining two sets of systematically derived metrics. First, it uses complexity metrics to group the functions in a target application into a set of bins. Then, it uses vulnerability metrics to rank the functions in each bin and identifies the top ones as potentially vulnerable. Our experimental results on 11 real-world projects have demonstrated that, LEOPARD can cover 74.0% of vulnerable functions by identifying 20% of functions as vulnerable and outperform machine learning-based and static analysis-based techniques. We further propose three applications of LEOPARD for manual code review and fuzzing, through which we discovered 22 new bugs in real applications like PHP, radare2 and FFmpeg, and eight of them are new vulnerabilities.	Program Metric, Vulnerability, Fuzzing	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8812029	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

A survey on public awareness towards renewable energy in Turkey	10.1109 /ICRERA. 2014.7016523	The use of renewable energy sources are rapidly increasing as alternatives to conventional sources. As Turkey having a great potential of renewable sources, the consciousness of community is a very significant issue for the development in this area. A survey of renewable energy awareness is conducted in this paper; implemented on university students from multiple disciplines. In order to determine the awareness of students, a validated questionnaire was prepared The survey depended on gender, age and education parameters of 322 students studying in state/private colleges and universities in Ankara. Thus, the perspective of the undergraduate and graduate students towards renewable energy has been studied. With this study, according to the education, politics, environment and energy factors, assessments are made trying to uncover the relationships between these factors. The data obtained from study were analyzed with SPSS 15.0 statistical software package. As a result, it is clear to say that there is a gradually increasing awareness among university students and a more reliable perception in the society either. This study is especially expected to be useful in determining the renewable energy content of the curriculum for relevant educational institutions and for the development of short and medium-term energy policies for future plans in other institutions.	Renewable energy;public awareness;Turkey;opinion survey;energy situation in Turkey	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7016523	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Application of a Gravitational-Benchmark Model for Road-Transport Energy Evaluation: Simulation Results	10.1109 /CIEES55704. 2022.9990850	A systematic approach has been composed for studying the possibilities for application of an existing criterion model for informative assessment of the energy efficiency of transportation processes. Based on the proposed methodology and on six selected typical objects in the field, extensive simulation studies have been performed based on the average fuel consumption of motor vehicles. New data have been obtained for efficiency coefficient of transport processes, as the efficiency coefficient varies within the intervals (0.004... 59.7) %, (0.001...14.92) % and (0.001...3.89) % for the objects of classification groups A1, A2 and B, respectively. The performed research is the first step of the justification of the workability and the practical applicability of the criterion model.	road transport;energy efficiency;energy evaluation; simulation;gravitational benchmark	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9990850	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
User's Perspective of Smartphone Platforms Usability: An Empirical Study	10.1109/ISMS. 2014.70	Smartphones are overwhelmingly considered as one of the most viral technological advancements in handheld and mobile computing. A wide array of companies are directly or indirectly incorporating new smartphone platforms and hence continually enhancing their features to wholly new levels. However, the incorporation on the most basic 'ease of use for all' front is still seriously lagging. Although new exciting features are innovated and developed on pace, yet there remains a huge gap for adequately supplementing the usability quotient of smartphones that is presently inferior in comparison to the desktop systems. Humans with variable ages, cognitive structures, experience based mental models and perceptions of reality eye smartphones differently. This inherent heterogeneity is one of the most burdening problems in smartphone adaptability and usability phenomenon. To target this critical and highly practical usability issue, a comparative investigation of the usability evaluation for the smartphone platforms (iOS & Android) considering the needs of older people is conducted. The main purpose is to investigate the difference of performance measure of older age groups (novice, intermediate, experienced).	smartphone platforms; usability evaluation;older adults;swipe;tap;interaction gestures	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7280939	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
A Software Package «Apnea» for the Diagnosis and Treatment of Obstructive Sleep Apnea	10.1109 /EIconRus5475 0.2022.9755455	According to the international classification of sleep disorders ICSD-3, sleep disorders are grouped into 7 different groups, one of which is "Obstructive Sleep Apnea" (OSA). In order to improve the quality of sleep, a mobile application "Apnea" was developed. It helps users in self-diagnosis and treatment of snoring and OSA. This will have a positive effect on many areas of life in the future: the number of accidents due to falling asleep while driving will decrease; the working capacity of the population will increase due to the improvement of people, since inadequate sleep increases the risk of many diseases, including sudden death. The software complex analyzes many patient data: name, age, gender, height and weight of the user, neck circumference, waist circumference, patient complaints, recording of the sound phenomenon of the client's snoring, processing of user's photographs to construction of a 3D model and determine the pathology of the dentition, heart rate data processing and activity results during the day. Based on the results of the assessment, users are offered various recommendations compiled by a team of doctors to improve the quality of sleep (smart alarm clock, soothing music, breathing techniques, myofunctional exercises, recommendations for diet therapy, sleep hygiene, etc.).	obstructive sleep apnea (OSA);snoring; otorhinolaryngology;mobile application;technology; diseases;precision medicine	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9755455	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Pirus: A file storage service in cloud computing for educational use	10.1109 /EDUCON. 2014.6826128	This paper describes a file storage service for elearning platforms using object oriented logic in a cloud computing environment. The service can be used by an academic community giving users the ability to store remotely and access their personal files with no security compromises. The Learning Research Management (LRM) innovative system is introduced and a technological assessment of this system is proposed and implemented using a statistical evaluation process. The conducted process is based on the perceptions from using the system by the involved student population. This process leads to an iterative decision making phase to further improve the system.	e-learning platforms;file storage;cloud computing; Software as a Service	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=6826128	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Clustering of Data that Quantify the Degree of Impairment of the Upper Limb in Patients with Alterations of the Central Nervous System	10.1109 /CCE50788. 2020.9299168	Previous studies have considered improving the classification procedures for motor impairment of the upper limb in patients with Central Nervous System alterations. This work compares two classification methods to be able to group the SSULF scale into five classes to have a better assessment, results showed that with the K-Means more than the 95% of the control group SALM values were correctly classified in SSULF 1 and with the Fuzzy C-means the 92%, so we can assume that the K-means method did a better classification for our purpose.	clustering (unsupervised) algorithm;data classification; smoothness of movement	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9299168	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Susceptibility Evaluation Of Rain-Induced Landslides Based On Multi-Source Data: A Case Study Of Xingguo County, China	10.1109 /IGARSS52108. 2023.10281598	Landslide natural disasters (LND) have high frequency, wide distribution, and multiple occurrences, causing significant losses to personal and property safety. LNDs account for over 70% of natural geological disasters in China, often caused by precipitation. Xingguo County, Jiangxi Province, is prone to LND due to its geographical location. Rainfall-induced LNDs account for over 70% of the county's LND. In this study, a digital modeling and machine learning approach is used to evaluate the susceptibility of rain-induced landslides in Xingguo County and generate a high-precision susceptibility map. Six influence factors are selected, and four machine learning algorithms, including support vector machine (SVM), decision tree (DT), back propagation neural network (BPNN), and random forests (RF), are used for susceptibility evaluation. A rainfall-induced landslide susceptibility map is derived, and landslide points are classified into five susceptible types. The experimental results show that the BPNN model achieved the best performance. The accuracy of the models is validated using the area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (ROC), area under the curve (AUC), accuracy (ACC), and kappa coefficient. The results showed that all models performed well, but the BPNN model achieved the best performance with an AUC of 0.75, ACC of 0.67, and kappa coefficient of 0.75.	Landslide susceptibility;Rain-induced landslide;Machine learning;Xingguo county	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10281598	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es
A Semantically Enriched Goal-Oriented Referential Integrity Model in Systems of Systems Context	10.1109/ACIT. 2018.8672670	System of Systems (SoS) results from the collaboration of a set of independent socio and technical constituent systems, largely driven by stakeholders' needs and goals taking into consideration SoS high-level goals and the constituent systems-level individual goals. It's challenging to manage the satisfaction of these goals in such large and complex SoS arrangement, where links between these goals may not be clearly known or specified. Additionally, competing stakeholders' interests and goals establish a complex stakeholder environment. In this research the i* goal-oriented framework has been utilised in SoS context to identify, model and manage goals of the overall SoS and its constituent systems. This paper discusses a novel Goals Referential Integrity (GRI) model that is aimed at maintaining the integrity and consistency of both the SoS-level and the constituent systems-level goals, in an attempt to address the current challenges of managing goals in an SoS arrangement. Furthermore, an ontology-based model has been developed to (1) support the GRI model and semantically annotates goals' levels in SoS context, and (2) specify the relationships and linkages between the SoS organisation, its constituent systems, global and local goals, and strategic and policy documents. Together the GRI model and its associated ontology model form the Semantic Goal Referential Integrity (SGRI) applied in SoS context, where conflicts between goals at the SoS and the constituent systems levels can be discovered in an attempt to maintain the semantic integrity of the SoS and constituent systems goals.	Systems of Systems;Goals; Goal-Oriented Modelling;i* Framework;Goals Referential Integrity;Semantic i* Enrichment	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8672670	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Activity-Based Model Synchronization and Defects Detection for Small Teams	10.1109/QRS-C.2017.12	Software modelling deals with multiple problems such as defect detection, synchronization and authorship assessment. These problems are obviously solved by complex tools for static and manual analysis of models. But an origin of these problems is in dynamical part of software modelling process - activities of developers, that can be incrementally processed right in developers' environments. So, methods that utilize activities should be more suitable for small agile teams or in learning process. In this paper, we present novel model synchronization and real-time defects detection methods based on developers' activities, and the tool SmallTEAmsHelper, which collects developers' activities over models, detects defects at the time they arise and provides an incremental model synchronization. We also present results of SmallTEAmsHelper deployment to students of the course Principles of software engineering and collected dataset of students' activities, which will be used for future work in an area of activity-based approaches.	UML;Software modelling; Defect detection;Model synchronization;Small teams	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8004288	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Evaluation of Touch Technology for the Aging Population	10.1109/ICVR46560.2019.8994539	Optimal and effective hand function is essential for performing activities of daily living e.g., eating and dressing. Multiple advances in technology typical of our modern era overwhelmingly affect today's environment. Operating these technologies, which are necessary for performing a wide variety of basic and instrumental activities of daily living, often require perfecting new manual skills. A touchscreen is an excellent example of a modern technological application which has become prevalent in all aspects of modern life and its use requires fine motor skills to perform a range of activities such as tapping, swiping, and virtual pinching. However, traditional hand assessment tools are not able to capture the skills necessary to operate a touchscreen. The ability to assess these skills is essential for the development of appropriate treatment protocols as well as for determining technological adaptations necessary for making touchscreens accessible to all.The Touchscreen Assessment Tool (TATOO) is a software application developed to comprehensively and objectively assess the hand performance abilities necessary for operating a touchscreen. The current pilot study examined the usability of the TATOO application by individuals in two age groups: elderly individuals (over 75 years) and middle-aged adults (over 45 years). The validity of the TATOO was examined by comparing the performance of the two age groups. Additionally, the correlations between the results of the TATOO and with traditional hand assessment tools (e.g., prehension strength and dexterity) were determined for the elderly group.Usability as assessed with the System Usability Scale was very good in both age groups. Discriminative validity was demonstrated with elderly individuals demonstrating less accurate and significantly longer performance time. No correlation was found between the TATOO variables and prehension strength (grip and pinch strength) or dexterity skills.The TATOO has the potential to become an important novel supplement to the toolbox available to clinical professionals treating the elderly in the modern world. Future studies with larger samples of elderly individuals are warranted in order to establish a normative data base.	Touchscreen Assessment Tool (TATOO);hand assessment;elderly individuals;aging;usability	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8994539	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Developing Faculty Expertise in Information Assurance through Case Studies and Hands-On Experiences	10.1109/HICSS.2014.606	Though many Information Assurance (IA) educators agree that hands-on exercises and case studies improve student learning, hands-on exercises and case studies are not widely adopted due to the time needed to develop them and integrate them into curriculum. Under the support of National Science Foundation (NSF) Scholarship for Service program, we implemented two faculty development workshops to disseminate effective hands-on exercises and case studies developed through multiple previous and ongoing grants, and to develop faculty expertise in IA. This paper reports our experience of holding the faculty summer workshops on teaching information assurance through case studies and hands-on experiences. The topics presented at the workshops are briefly described and the evaluation results of the workshops are discussed. The workshops provided a valuable opportunity for IA educators to connect with each other and form collaboration in teaching and research in IA.	Conferences;Educational institutions;Cryptography; Access control; Authentication	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=6759209	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

<p>SkEye: Detecting Imminent Attacks via Analyzing Adversarial Smart Contracts</p>		<p>Smart contracts are susceptible to various vulnerabilities that can be exploited by hackers via developing adversarial contracts. Existing vulnerability detection techniques often concentrate solely on vulnerable contracts, neglecting adversarial contracts, which may weaken the effectiveness of vulnerability detection and fail to meet practical needs. In this paper, we propose SkEye, a novel technique that integrates adversarial and vulnerable contracts together to detect vulnerabilities and resulting imminent attacks. SkEye works during the stage after adversarial contracts have been deployed but before attack transactions are initiated, providing a critical time window for emergency response to mitigate potential losses. Upon deployment of a smart contract, SkEye detects whether it is adversarial, and then utilizes the probabilistic matching technique to localize victim contracts. By pairing adversarial and victim contracts, SkEye comprehensively extracts complete attack behaviors. Furthermore, SkEye leverages Large Language Model (LLM) to decide the types of vulnerabilities exploited by adversarial contracts. Our evaluation, conducted on 174 real-world adversarial contracts from 159 incidents resulting in financial losses totaling approximately \$1.36 billion, demonstrates SkEye's effectiveness in detecting vulnerabilities and imminent attacks. Compared to state-of-the-art techniques, e.g., BlockWatchdog and Slither, SkEye also reveals the superior performance. CCS CONCEPTS • Software and its engineering → Software verification and validation.</p>	<p>Smart Contract; Large Language Model; Vulnerability Detection</p>	<p>https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10764946</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<p>sem colab</p>
<p>Measurement range increment in a method for evaluating Panoramic Understanding of Programming</p>	<p>10.1109/FIE.2016.7757489</p>	<p>In a prior study we introduced the Programmed Visual Contents Comparison Method (PVCC) for assessment of programming abilities related with Panoramic Understanding of Programming (PUP). With this method, by comparing two or more output pictures produced by programming samples (a question), a student must decide which one of the programs producing them is more difficult to build with programming, or, if the difficulty is similar for all of them. This study reported also the results of a test to evaluate this method's validity performed with groups of students of diverse fields. Validity was verified by comparing the initial programming ability reported by programming professors of these groups with the test results; this confirmed that the PVCC method worked well to find programming abilities related with PUP. In this paper we propose an enhancement to the PVCC Method based on the preparation of New Questions where two or more samples displaying both input data and output pictures are shown. By adding input data to output pictures and focus strictly on the programming processes needed to obtain these pictures from the provided input data, we aim to broaden the range of discernible programming abilities related with PUP. The results of a test performed to verify the suitability of New Questions performed with professors of programming is also reported.</p>	<p>Computer science education; Programming Training; Student Assessment; Graphic Design; Software Engineering</p>	<p>https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7757489</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<p>sen colab</p>
<p>A Review of Dark Web: Trends and Future Directions</p>	<p>10.1109/COMPSAC54236.2022.00283</p>	<p>The dark web is often discussed in taboo by many who are unfamiliar with the subject. However, this paper takes a dive into the skeleton of what constructs the dark web by compiling the research of published essays. The Onion Router (TOR) and other discussed browsers are specialized web browsers that provide anonymity by going through multiple servers and encrypted networks between the host and client, hiding the IP address of both ends. This provides difficulty in terms of controlling or monitoring the dark web, leading to its popularity in criminal underworlds. In this work, we provide an overview of data mining and penetration testing tools that are being widely used to crawl and collect data. We compare the tools to provide strengths and weaknesses of the tools while providing challenges of harnessing massive data from dark web using crawlers and penetration testing tools including machine learning (ML) techniques. Despite the effort to crawl dark web has progressed, there are still rooms to advance existing approaches to combat the ever-changing landscape of the dark web.</p>	<p>Dark Web; TOR; Cybersecurity; Privacy; Web crawlers; Anonymity; Data Mining; Data Protection</p>	<p>https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9842561</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<p>sem colab</p>

Health Assessment of HV Cable Based on Data Correlation Analysis and Fuzzy Rules Joint Algorithm	10.1109 /ICPEE56418. 2022.10050323	In recent years, HV cable is increasingly considered as one of the optimal choices for power transmission and distribution in urban power grid. The monitoring data for HV cables becomes huge, and effective measures are urgently required to sort these big data and evaluate the health condition of HV cable. In this paper, an intelligent HV cable health condition evaluation method which combines correlation analysis and the fuzzy rules on the multi-source cable monitoring data was proposed. Firstly, four groups of correlation classification for data mining were carried out on 13 types of cable monitoring data collected from 22 practical HV cable routes, consequently 9 classes of characterized monitoring data were sorted through correlation analysis. Secondly, the statuses of all the cable routes routes were evaluated by making fuzzy rules according to the characterized data. Eventually, the scores indicating the health status of each cable route was obtained. The research results indicating that this joint algorithm could successfully distinguish HV cables in abnormal and severe health conditions. The data mining and classification method can be used as a good reference for inspection and maintenance schedule for HV cables.	HV cable;health assessment; correlation analysis;fuzzy rule;big data	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10050323	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
A conceptual framework and its application for project developing in mechatronics education	10.1109/TIME-E. 2014.7011622	This paper presents a conceptual framework of project developing for the final year of mechatronics students. This is a concept of preparing students with the knowledge, skills, and experience in a design of mechatronics systems on the according basis with the requirements and realities of today's industry. The project developing of the students was began with the ideological of combining mechanical, electrical, electronics, and embedded programming merge into a single interdisciplinary field. After that, virtual prototyping, this stage is the integration of aided design, programming design, and simulation design to demonstration the functionality of the virtual prototype on a computer environment. Finally, the virtual project which was verified and optimized to be used a physical prototyping. The results of the assessment panel members found that students can develop the project successfully and achieve its objectives through the application of such framework.	mechatronics education; virtual prototype;physical prototype;miniature 3-axis milling machine	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7011622	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Comparative Analysis of Predictive Analytics Models in Classification Problems	10.1109 /APSS47353. 2019.00028	Present research is devoted to the comparative analysis of the quality of classification for some methods of descriptive and predictive analytics in the case when most (or all) of independent variables are measured in quality scale with large amount of levels. In this case, some classification methods or their popular realizations calls for conversion of quality variables into systems of dummy variables. If quality scales have large amount of levels which are presented in almost equal proportions in the training set, i.e. it doesn't make sense to enlarge levels, above mentioned requirement will lead to the dramatically rise of problem dimension. As a result, researcher is faced with the curse of dimensionality. It means that, if the problem dimension rise, it'll be necessary to rise the sample size to preserve factors impact estimation accuracy. At the same time, it's not always possible to arrange appropriate growth of the training set volume. In some cases, it's limited by specific properties of the body of interest (system). If such situation appears, it'll be extremely important to evaluate the sensitivity of prediction/classification methods to the curse of dimensionality. Authors of this research focused on the four method of classification, which earn first lines in the lists of the popular methods of business analysis long ago. There are: . Two methods of classification tree building - CART and C4.5 . Logistic regression . Classification on the basis of random forest The first three are descriptive methods, which let's get interpreting (man ready) models, the fourth belongs to predictive analytics. Selection is not random. Descriptive analytics problems extremely important for the process of planning, when it's necessary to get answer on the question "What will be if ...?". Particularly, one need to get target group description for organization of marketing communication. At the same time, it is quite conceivable that utilization of interpreting (man ready) models involves loss of prediction quality in comparison with methods of predictive analytics. The current research domain is the activity of microfinancing institutions (MFIs). Traditional problem here is the potential client assessment. The main challenge, which arise in the process of above mentioned problem solution, is the constraints on the volume, composition and type of data, which is available for prediction of default or default probability assessment. Thus, it's necessary to evaluate the abilities of classification methods which were designed for work with large amount of data (it means big size of the training set and a lot of variables, from which the most important should be selected). In real practice of microfinancing organization, the most of recorded factors are measured on the qualitative scales with large amount of levels, what is the origin of the above-mentioned problems. The empirical part of the research is grounded on the data of real microfinancing organization. Some hypotheses about the reasons of default were tested as byproduct of this research.	predictive Analytics, descriptive Analytics, social media analysis, microfinance organization,	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8943805	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Extending Interaction Flow Modeling Language as a Profile for Form-making Systems	10.1109 /IKT54664. 2021.9685877	Form-making systems are used to create, store, and spread forms such as questionnaires, surveys, and online exams. In general, the constant change of requirements makes the development process of such systems more complicated and longer. In order to reduce the complexity of generating form-making systems, in this paper, we propose a UML profile based on Interaction Flow Modeling Language (IFML) standard. On top of the rich set of concepts that exists in IFML for modeling the user interface and behavior of software systems, we extend this standard to support concepts dedicated to form-making systems. As tool support, we have implemented our UML profile in Papyrus. The tool helps designers build a valid model with less effort. To assess our profile and validate its efficiency, we experiment a case study for making an exam for a course. The results show that the proposed profile can support many scenarios of using form-making systems.	Interaction Flow Modeling Language (IFML);Model-driven Engineering;IFML Extension;UML profile;Form-making Systems	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9685877	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sen colab
Towards Application of Speech Analysis in Predicting Learners' Performance	10.1109 /FIE56618. 2022.9962701	In this work in progress, we propose a model for analysis of students' verbal conversation during teamwork to predict their academic performance based on expressed emotions. Our previous studies support the link between an individual's attitude and emotional states during the cognitive process with their performance in the given context [1], [2]. Traditionally the learners' affective states were assessed by having them fill out standard surveys. More recently the researchers have been using advanced methods to extract students' emotions from their writings by using Natural Language Processing (NLP) models. These models are applied to data collected from different sources such as discussion forums, team chats, students' reflective surveys, and journals. In this research, we take one step further by recording students audio in class as they converse about the course topic in low-stake teams and extract emotions from their conversations by NLP methods. The main contributions of the proposed model are 1) the audio transcription component 2) the multi-class emotion analysis unit and 3) the performance prediction model based on input data. SpeechBrain pre-trained models with transformer language models were applied for automated transcription of audio data and converting them to embedding vectors. NLP methods were applied for sentiment analysis. Next, we formed the feature set by combining the extracted emotions with students' formative assessment grades during the semester to implement a prediction model. We further analyzed which features in the feature set have a higher impact on the students' academic performance. The early result of this research is promising as we found high accuracy in the predicted scores of the students.	Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR);emotion analysis;predictive model; academic performance;NLP	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9962701	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
MURDOC: Transforming Pixels into Perception for Camouflage Detection	10.1109 /DASC62030. 2024.10748781	The MURDOC project introduces an application to enhance trustworthiness and explainability in computer vision models, focusing on camouflage detection. It aims to address the need for transparent and interpretable AI systems in sensitive domains such as security and defense. MURDOC integrates advanced eXplainable AI techniques including off-ramps for collecting interpretable insights, attention mechanisms for high-lighting relevant features, and a user-centric image pre-processing tool within the visualization interface. This paper offers an assessment of MURDOC's potential impact on trustworthiness and explainability in camouflaged object detection tasks. It discusses and assesses the potential effectiveness of off-ramps in gathering XAI output at various model stages, such as feature maps, attention mechanisms, and activation maps. Additionally, the paper investigates how user-driven image pre-processing mechanisms may enhance the trustworthiness of the model's predictions and decisions, allowing users to modify the input and observe prediction changes. As a work in progress, the development of MURDOC shows promise in bridging the gap for transparency and interpretability in camouflage detection. The paper also discusses the challenges, future directions, and potential applications of MURDOC's capabilities in diverse domains requiring transparent and trustworthy AI systems. The source code for the version of MURDOC in this paper is available on GitHub at: https://github.com/Department-70/DASC_2024 .	Camouflage Object Detection;Trustworthiness; Transparency;Informative AI; Explainable AI;AI	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10748781	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

A preliminary study of DTI Fingerprinting on stroke analysis	10.1109/EMBC.2014.6944100	DTI (Diffusion Tensor Imaging) is a well-known MRI (Magnetic Resonance Imaging) technique which provides useful structural information about human brain. However, the quantitative measurement to physiological variation of subtypes of ischemic stroke is not available. An automatically quantitative method for DTI analysis will enhance the DTI application in clinics. In this study, we proposed a DTI Fingerprinting technology to quantitatively analyze white matter tissue, which was applied in stroke classification. The TBSS (Tract Based Spatial Statistics) method was employed to generate mask automatically. To evaluate the clustering performance of the automatic method, lesion ROI (Region of Interest) is manually drawn on the DWI images as a reference. The results from the DTI Fingerprinting were compared with those obtained from the reference ROIs. It indicates that the DTI Fingerprinting could identify different states of ischemic stroke and has promising potential to provide a more comprehensive measure of the DTI data. Further development should be carried out to improve DTI Fingerprinting technology in clinics.	Diffusion tensor imaging; Fingerprint recognition; Manuals;Lesions;Physiology; Euclidean distance	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=6944100	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Best Practices for Cultivating Innovative Thinking Skills in Innovation Competitions and Programs	10.1109 /FIE58773.2023.10343440	Engineering and computing education have always embraced student Innovation Competitions and Programs (ICPs), such as design challenges, hackathons, startup competitions, and boot camps. These programs are typically organized to increase interest in STEM fields, achieve the broader objective of forming well-rounded engineers and encourage students to bring their innovative ideas into real life. In addition, all ICPs also aim to advance students' innovative thinking skills. With the increased focus on entrepreneurship and innovation in STEM programs, many higher education institutions now organize some form of ICPs. This increased popularity of ICPs bears the questions of (i) whether ICPs achieve their intended objectives, (ii) what program components are most effective, and (iii) how to design ICPs for recruiting diverse student groups. Although these questions are highly relevant to advancing the educational benefits of ICPs, the literature lacks holistic studies focusing on the best practices of ICPs. In this paper, we present the findings of a qualitative research study to investigate ICP types and attributes that make the most impact on fostering an innovation mindset. We interviewed the organizers of ICPs to understand their objectives for organizing their events and rationales for specific program elements. Besides, we asked questions about how they promote their events, the best ways to reach out to students, team selection and forming, their assessment and judging procedures, during and after competition support, and the best practices and challenges. These interview scripts were transcribed, coded, and analyzed using qualitative data analysis software. An analysis of extracted thematic concepts was performed to identify the best practices and strategies that ICP organizers utilize to increase the Impact of their programs. The paper presents the preliminary results of this thematic analysis of the codes. Overall, findings suggest that incorporating more entrepreneurial elements, innovation training in ICPs, and effective mentoring may improve the learning outcomes related to innovative thinking skills.	student competitions;design competitions;innovation; entrepreneurship;critical thinking;extracurricular	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10343440	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Failure causes Based Wind Turbine Components Classification and Failure Propagation: For proactive maintenance implementatio	10.1109 /ICWEAA.2018.8605082	The wind turbine is a complex system that can be divided into subsystems or several independent components with many interrelationships that characterize dependencies. The maintenance cost of these machines represents a big part of the total price of the kWh (40% for offshore wind energy). New maintenance practice such as e-maintenance or proactive maintenance need accurate degradation model to avoid costly corrective maintenance. The assessment of the reliability of wind turbines has become increasingly important in recent years. Majority of existing works in the literature deal with the reliability at a component level. However, the maintenance task aims to repair all the system, which cannot be guaranteed by the knowledge of the state of a single component without the consideration of its interactions with the rest of the system. In this paper, we propose a new classification of the component of a wind turbine that consists in grouping the various components by their causes of failure. The purpose of this classification is to improve the future design of the system and to allow the performance of proactive maintenance by eliminating the cause of failure and prevent their re-occurrence.	Degradation model;fault propagation;proactive maintenance;reliability;wind turbines	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8605082	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Smart Farmer Education System for Disease Identification, Severity Assessment and Infestation Management (Brinjal)	10.1109 /ICIIS58898. 2023.10253572	The agriculture industry is one of the most significant sources of foreign exchange and employment in the Sri Lankan market. Therefore, small crops play a crucial role in ensuring the food security of the population as they are integral components of Sri Lankan cuisine. However, industry experts have identified inefficient disease and pest management as a hindrance to production. This issue requires immediate attention and proper action, which can be effectively addressed through the utilization of ICT technologies. Consequently, this research paper proposes a smart system that aims to assist farmers and agriculture professionals by providing them with farmer education, disease and infestation management tools, as well as progression level calculations. The implementation of this system aims to uplift the agriculture industry in Sri Lanka. The developed 'AI-based mobile application system for Brinjal Diseases,' which is based on analyzing the eating patterns of leafhopper damage, presents an innovative approach to identify the most significant threats to Brinjal, specifically focusing on leafhopper damage. This proposed system effectively informs various stakeholders, including the Area Agricultural Research Officer, Seed Certification and Plant Protection Center (SCPPC), Agricultural Service Center, Office of the Register of Pesticides (ROP), Plant Protection Service (PPS), as well as farmers, regarding the dispersion and prevention of brinjal diseases and pest infections.	brinjal diseases;pest control; CNN;maskR-CNN;YOLOV5; disease dispersion; crowdsourcing;image processing	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10253572	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Understanding Fairness Requirements for ML-based Software	10.1109 /RE57278. 2023.00046	Today's technologies are becoming more and more pervasive and advanced software systems can replace human beings in many different tasks. This is especially true in the case of automated decision-making systems based on machine learning (ML). Important ethical implications arise when such decision systems are used in sensitive contexts (e.g., justice or loans). The elicitation of these implications, that is, of the ethical requirements behind ML-based systems is a new challenge we must address to avoid societal risks. This is particularly urgent for fairness since this notion lacks a precise and commonly accepted definition, thus hampering its assessment. This paper aims to give a comprehensive definition of fairness, present a unified taxonomy of alternative interpretations, define a new decision tree that can guide the choice of the correct interpretation, and carry out a preliminary assessment with experiments in a real-world context.	Fairness;Non-functional Requirements;Machine Learning	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10260716	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Evaluation of the circularity of the Hungarian waste management system using LCA methodology	10.1109 /IYCE60333. 2024.10634934	Based on the analysis of the current waste composition, the share of organics in municipal solid waste, and the currently available waste treatment policy and techniques, the LCA methodology is used to evaluate the Hungarian waste management system and its circularity. The waste management system is undergoing a significant transformation as more waste streams will be separately collected in the near future. From 1st January 2024, municipal solid waste is classified into three groups: packaging waste (paper-, polymer-, and metal-based), biodegradable waste (compostable or food waste), and mixed municipal solid waste. From 1st January 2025, textiles must be collected separately and should not be part of the mixed municipal solid waste. The current waste treatment procedures focus on circular and carbon-neutral solutions. The EU is targeting to transform its economy into a circular economy. To encourage this, the EU has set targets for the 27 Member States to increase recycling and reduce landfilling, which are adopted by Hungary. Namely, 70% of packaging waste must be recycled by 2030. Moreover, 65% of municipal solid waste must be prepared for re-use or recycling and only 10% of municipal solid waste can be disposed to landfills by 2035. The remaining municipal solid waste stream is aimed to be utilized as a Waste-to-Energy (WtE) source. To achieve EU energy targets, it is necessary to expand low-carbon energy production methods to reduce the amount of waste landfilled, so expanding WtE capacity is a suitable solution to achieve better environmental performance. In addition to Waste-to-Energy, the potential of waste heat from landfill gas utilization in gas engines will be assessed as an additional carbon-neutral energy source that can be utilized either directly or through, e.g., PCM storage technology. In this study, the environmental impacts of the current Hungarian waste management system and the proposed waste management targets are compared by a holistic approach applying the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) methodology. The environmental model is created in "LCA for Experts" (GaBi) software, and the evaluation is carried out with the Environmental Footprint 3.0 impact assessment method considering Climate Change (Global Warming), Acidification, Eutrophication, Particulate Matter, Photochemical Ozone Formation, Ozone Depletion, Resource Use, Land Use, Water Use and Toxicity.	life cycle assessment;circular economy;Waste-to-Energy; waste management	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10634934	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Europa Clipper Payload Verification and Validation: Instrument Delivery into System Integration	10.1109/AERO55745.2023.10115740	NASA's Europa Clipper mission is designed to investigate the habitability of the Jovian moon Europa with a suite of 10 science instruments. The project is now past its project system integration review and in the middle of instrument deliveries to Assembly, Test, and Launch Operations (ATLO). The payload verification and validation (V&V) program is thus in the process of receiving and auditing instrument-provided verification evidence, executing the payload-level software interface testing campaign, and beginning a series of checkouts on the flight instruments in ATLO. Previous work described the set of planned verification activities that we developed to ensure consistent V&V coverage across all of the instruments, and at the instrument, payload, and ATLO levels. This paper describes the implementation of that plan, including statistics on scope of the work and its execution, adjustments/additions to the original plans, how the team managed priorities with limited resources, and other lessons learned. We first describe the payload V&V oversight of instrument-level verification item closures. We describe the assessments performed to determine V&V status at instrument deliveries, and how we managed shortfalls and workload. We then describe the software interface V&V campaigns that the payload team is executing, summarizing the verification work and resources required to perform it. Finally, we describe the V&V role in post-delivery activities for the instruments including a summary of pre-ATLO (PATLO) testing and early ATLO activities. We conclude the paper by reflecting on how the executed V&V program compared to the planned program, and what strengths and challenges the program as designed offered in the execution phase. We then briefly summarize the work remaining as the payload V&V program enters its final phases prior to launch.	Vocabulary;Databases; Instruments;System integration;Software; Planning;Teamwork	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10115740	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem avaliar
Risk management practices for information system projects in the public sector	10.1109/ICEEI.2017.8312374	Information System projects face many risks and challenges due to their complexity and technicality. Most public information system projects fail to achieve their objectives due to various factors including poor risk management. Despite continuous attention and emphasis on the importance of risk management during project implementation, risk management practices were relatively low and the risk management process has not been practiced in its entirety; it is commonly implemented only during its early phase. This paper analyzed selected risk management models that are commonly used by project managers. In general, five basic risk management processes are included and analyzed in these models, namely Risk Identification, Risk Analysis, Risk Classification, Risk Mitigation and Risk Control. This study also identified the level of basic risk management processes adopted by information system projects in a number of selected case studies.	Project Management; Information System Project; Risk Management;Risk Management Practice;Public Sector	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8312374	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Remote Usability Testing of Tour Guide Application	10.1109/ICCTEIE54047.2021.9650658	Many Indonesian people travel to visit several areas in Indonesia. Most of them require assistance with tourism information and services. Therefore, PT XYZ developed a tour guide application to facilitate travelers to find information from tourism service providers. Usability testing is essential to evaluate the application by assigning several tasks to the user. This paper presents our work in remote usability testing of the application. This test was conducted by involving 15 test participants divided into three groups based on their age ranges. These ranges are age groups of 20–29 years, 30–39 years, and 40–49 years. We measure four usability aspects, which are learnability, efficiency, error, and satisfaction. The first three aspects are performed by giving the test participant several tasks to complete. Meanwhile, the satisfaction aspect is evaluated with System Usability Scale (SUS) questionnaire. The usability testing results indicate that all user in all age range complete the tasks and the defective rate is below the average standard. For the efficiency aspect, our test shows that participants' efficient time to complete the task is 0.061 goals/sec. From the results of the SUS score, we found that this application is acceptable for all user age in range.	usability testing;system usability scale;software evaluation	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9650658	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Three Sources of Blockchain Technology Vulnerabilities - how to Deal with them?	10.1109/ICCSEA54677.2022.9936330	The authors consider the problem of ensuring the security of smart contracts. The relevance of research is associated with a growing field of threats, an increase in economic risks, and the absence or insufficiency of the necessary tools to ensure the security of smart contracts. The authors begin the study by classifying the sources of vulnerabilities in smart contracts. The authors distinguish three groups: the disadvantages and limitations of the programming languages of smart contracts, the weaknesses of the blockchain technology itself, and the penalties associated with the misunderstanding or incorrect application of accepted programming methods. The authors provide a detailed classification of the vulnerabilities of smart contracts. Further, the authors show the need to use static code analyzers of smart contracts and their automation using static code analyzers of smart contracts. The final part discusses the results of an experiment to study the effectiveness of using static analyzers to improve the security of smart contracts.	smart contract;static analysis;vulnerability sources;security audit; vulnerability templates	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9936330	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Individual Plant Detection on Post-Harvest Forest Floor Using Aerial Imagery	10.23919 /SoftCOM62040 .2024.10721958	Effectively identifying and locating plants on the forest floor is essential for successful reforestation efforts and forest health assessment. This task is challenging due to the diverse range of plants, the high variance in appearance, the limited availability of accurately labeled data, and the complexity of data collection in post-harvest forest areas. These challenges are addressed by integrating field-surveyed plant data with images captured by Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) to produce labeled training data. A custom Faster-RCNN model is trained using the aforementioned data to detect individual plants and clustered plant groups. Two different annotation approaches (unified class and distinct classes) are explored to address plant groupings and compare their performance using Mean Average Precision at 50% overlap (mAP50) and F1 score. The model trained using the unified class approach shows promise in detecting plants and plant groups larger than 0.15 square meters (F1 score: 0.44) but struggles with those smaller than 0.15 square meters. The inclusion of field-labeled data makes detection more challenging but ensures reliability. Meanwhile, the distinct class approach shows limited success. This work underscores the value of high-resolution imagery and comprehensive temporal analysis in enhancing detection accuracy and reliability.	UAV;remote sensing;plant detection;deep learning; forestry;ecosystem;direct seeding	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10721958	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Research on Design of Visual Simulation Evaluation System Oriented to Ergonomics	10.1109 /ICHCI58871. 2023.10277746	This paper addresses the need for a standardized Chinese human body model library in visual simulation evaluation tools for ergonomics analysis. The study investigates various evaluation methods such as Rapid Upper Limb Assessment (RULA), NIOSH 1981, NIOSH 1991, Snook & Ciriello 1991, among others. Using open-source component packages such as QT, OGRE, and OPENCV, an ergonomics-oriented visual simulation evaluation system is designed. The system enables visualization of scene construction, human activity design, simulation, and human-mechanical ergonomics evaluation. Leveraging the Chinese human body standard model, a human-machine activity simulation case similar to DELMIA is developed. The effectiveness and feasibility of the system design are validated by comparing the analysis results of human-machine ergonomics evaluation.	system design;visual simulation;ergonomics evaluation;RULA	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10277746	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
A Taxonomy of Banking Financial Model in Study of Computer Science	10.1109 /ICELTICs6273 0. 2024.10776283	In the dynamic aspect of banking, the ability to bank financial models accurately is paramount for strategic decision-making, risk management, and regulatory compliance. A robust financial model serves as a cornerstone for understanding the complexities of banking operations, assessing profitability, and optimizing resource allocation. However, despite the extensive research in this field, there remains a notable gap in the literature regarding certain aspects of banking financial models, especially the utilization of computer science in the field. Therefore, this paper proposes a taxonomy of the banking financial model in computer science studies. We utilized a taxonomy approach introduced by Nickerson et al. [1] with the conceptual-to-empirical (C2E) technique to construct our taxonomy for organizing and categorizing computer science fields into hierarchical groups based on shared similar objects and characteristics. Based on the result, our taxonomy advised structuring and describing banking financial models through five objects, thirteen dimensions, and 127 characteristics in which the risk assessment algorithm, data encryption, optimization algorithm, and Monte Carlo simulation are dimensions discussed more often. Furthermore, the empirical examination allows researchers to identify the utilization of integrating an optimal decision support system with uncertainty handling and software architecture in this research domain as a potential future work.	banking;computer science; financial;taxonomy	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10776283	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Real-World Bug Hunting Techniques for Advanced Real-Time IP Address Redirection	10.1109 /ICMCSI64620. 2025.10883165	This research study builds the state-of-art cyber security platform that eventually relied on the internet. It focuses on building this from high-end approaches with practical bug-hunting awareness in its aim toward effective threat detection. It continuously monitors network traffic through several algorithm models for analyzing and stopping malicious activities at real time. In doing this, it blocks and dynamically changes IP addresses in such a way that unwanted access cannot happen. Key Features: Anomaly detection through User and Entity Behavior Analytics, Security Adaptation, Automation, and Response for effective threat management, a threat intelligence feed keeping it abreast of new attack vectors, and the platform comes with deep logging for forensic investigations purposes. Predictive analytics, along with its continuous learning module, allows the detection algorithms to get optimized. Its friendly user interface promotes teamwork, data aggregation, and collective protection and, henceforth, provides the all-encompassing and flexible cybersecurity solution that can help to strengthen the businesses' defenses against constantly changing threats.	Threat Intelligence Sharing; Anonymization;Data Aggregation;Cloud Platform; Cybersecurity;Encryption; Privacy;Python	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10883165	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Sensory responses of autism via electroencephalography for Sensory Profile	10.1109 /ICCSCE. 2014.7072794	The aim of this study is to investigate the brain signals of autism children through electroencephalography (EEG) associated to physical tasks. The physical task was meant to stimulate the sensitivity correlation of sensory response of a child. A group of autism children was chosen for this study and were given by five sensory stimulations which are audio, taste, touch, visual and vestibular. The acquisition of brain signals was acquainted using EEG Neurofax 9200 and the electrode positions were using 10-20 International System placements. The preprocessing signals were analyzed using independent component analysis (ICA) using EEGLAB Software and Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT). The alpha wave was selected by level 6 decomposition and the extracted features represents the characteristic of the sensory task. The means, standard deviations and approximation entropy were extracted on the clean signals and forms into Sensory Profile (Sensory Profiling). From the overall results, the behavior of each autism children has been observed unstable emotion while running the sensory stimulation. The observation also helps to improve their learning strategy for the future work in assessment.	Electroencephalography (EEG);autism;independent component analysis (ICA); discrete wavelet transform (DWT);sensory profile (SP)	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7072794	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es
Assessment on the Optimal Dimming Level in Lighting System between Firefly Algorithm and Particle Swarm Optimization Algorithm	10.1109 /SCORed50371.2020.9250929	The lighting system is one of the main systems in the building and contributes a considerable amount of energy. Therefore, the daylight harvesting system (DHS) is vital in the lighting system for control and minimize energy consumption from artificial lighting. The main objective of the lighting system is to minimize the dimming level of the luminaires. The optimization method was used in this research to solve the problem formulation in the lighting control system. There are several benefits by using optimization methods such as energy-saving while fulfilling the standard of the average illuminance level based on the European Standard EN12464-1 for the occupancy comfort. In this research, the Firefly Algorithm (FA) and Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) algorithm were compared in order to determine the best optimization method which can solve the problem formulation in the lighting system. The simulation result for FA and PSO has been carried out using MATLAB software. Based on the results, the PSO algorithm shows high performance compared to FA method in order to minimize the dimming level.	dimming level;average illuminance;firefly algorithm; particle swarm optimization	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9250929	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es
idb: A Tool for Blackbox iOS Security Assessments	10.1145 /2897073.2897710	Smartphones and mobile apps are increasingly used to manage and store sensitive data by both corporations and individuals. In this paper, common iOS mobile application flaws are reviewed as seen in real-world applications. For each type of flaw, defenses are recommended and it is shown how the author's tool 'idb' can be used to efficiently test for a range of these application flaws. The idb tool is open source and available to the public.	Uniform resource locators; Encryption;Mobile communication;Best practices;Smart phones; Mobile applications	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7832998	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Detection and Clustering of Neutral Section Faults Using Machine Learning Techniques for SMART Railways	10.1109 /ISCM147871.2019.9004366	Fault detection and diagnosis plays an important role particularly in railways where abnormal events are detected and a detailed root causes analysis is performed to prevent similar occurrence. The current method used to detect immediate and long-term faults is through foot inspections and inspection trolleys fitted with cameras proving to be inefficient and time consuming when analyzing the data. This paper examines the smart fault detection system on the overhead wires by applying machine learning techniques for accurate assessment of the neutral section before and after failure thereby grouping the events into fault bins. Modern computational intelligence has enabled the fault diagnostic and fault detection to be accurate from the data generated and sensors. The interaction between the pantograph and contact wire will be monitored using accelerometers and non-contact infrared thermometer sensors where should there be a deviation from the normal signal spectrum it will be detected. The measured data from onsite will be conveyed to ThingSpeak for cloud computation thereby providing notifications in real-time which allows the end user to visualize, analyze and act on data online. A prototype has been built and tested which shows that the system works reasonably with data collected from sensors.	fault diagnostic;neutral section;machine learning; accelerometer;k-means;data aggregation	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9004366	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Model-Based Methods for Quality Evaluation of Cloud Services	10.1109 /DASC/PICom/ CBDCCom/Cyber SciTech. 2019.00130	The issue of less-than-100% reliability and trustworthiness of third-party controlled cloud components (e.g., IaaS and SaaS components from different vendors) may lead to laxity in the QoS guarantees offered by a service-support system S to various applications. Our goal is to assess how well the internal mechanisms of S are geared to offer a required level of service to the applications. Our external assessment of QoS provisioning involves the construction of a computational model of the actual system under test. We employ system identification technique that uses the computational model to determine the feasible resource allocation for an externally observed behavior and use it to infer the actual system parameters. Our external system assessment methodology delineates domain-knowledge of the system from the assessment process at a meta-level and hence allows re-use of the technique across different systems. We illustrate our QoS assessment method using a replicated data service case study.	Quality of Service (QoS); Model based Engineering; Cloud induced Uncertainties; Machine Intelligence Tools	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8890388	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
MESIA: Understanding and Leveraging Supplementary Nature of Method-level Comments for Automatic Comment Generation		Code comments are important for developers in program comprehension. In scenarios of comprehending and reusing a method, developers expect code comments to provide supplementary information beyond the method signature. However, the extent of such supplementary information varies a lot in different code comments. In this paper, we raise the awareness of the supplementary nature of method-level comments and propose a new metric named MESIA (Mean Supplementary Information Amount) to assess the extent of supplementary information that a code comment can provide. With the MESIA metric, we conduct experiments on a popular code-comment dataset and three common types of neural approaches to generate method-level comments. Our experimental results demonstrate the value of our proposed work with a number of findings. (1) Small-MESIA comments occupy around 20% of the dataset and mostly fall into only the WHAT comment category. (2) Being able to provide various kinds of essential information, large-MESIA comments in the dataset are difficult for existing neural approaches to generate. (3) We can improve the capability of existing neural approaches to generate large-MESIA comments by reducing the proportion of small-MESIA comments in the training set. (4) The retrained model can generate large-MESIA comments that convey essential meaningful supplementary information for methods in the small-MESIA test set, but will get a lower BLEU score in evaluation. These findings indicate that with good training data, auto-generated comments can sometimes even surpass human-written reference comments, and having no appropriate ground truth for evaluation is an issue that needs to be addressed by future work on automatic comment generation. CCS CONCEPTS • Software and its engineering → Documentation.	Code comment;Comment generation;Deep learning; Evaluation	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10556420	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Facial Recognition Development to Detect Corporate Employees Stress Level	10.1109 /TALE48000. 2019.9225909	Technology has developed so well even to the point where machines can recognize our faces. There many APIs and algorithms out there that can recognize human faces. These APIs or algorithms is called Artificial Intelligence or AI. As modern civilian life in modern society, AI has been used so many times and developed into something more. This time, we proposed an idea to recognize motions and emotions on human faces to detect their stress levels. Companies nowadays need to have something that can know how their employees are feeling or think about their work. This program works by taking an image input from mounted cameras on the office's monitor. However, before that, the program must have been trained first to recognize faces and emotions. For this, the eigenfaces algorithm is used. After the input is received, then the program will process the image received and extract the features from the images such as eyes, nose, mouth, etc. to detect if there are faces and also the emotions of the face. After that, the features extracted will be matched with the features in the database to give an output of the percentage of stress.	face stress recognition; artificial neural network; employee stress recognition; eigenfaces	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9225909	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Assessment of elbow spasticity with surface electromyography and mechanomyography based on support vector machine	10.1109/EMBC.2017.8037699	The Modified Ashworth Scale (MAS) is the gold standard in clinical for grading spasticity. However, its results greatly depend on the physician evaluations and are subjective. In this study, we investigated the feasibility of using support vector machine (SVM) to objectively assess elbow spasticity based on both surface electromyography (sEMG) and mechanomyography (MMG). sEMG signals and tri-axial accelerometer mechanomyography (ACC-MMG) signals were recorded simultaneously on patients' biceps and triceps when they extended or bended elbow passively. 39 post-stroke patients participated in the study, and were divided into four groups regarding MAS level (MAS=0, 1, 1+ or 2). The three types of features, root mean square (RMS), mean power frequency (MPF), and median frequency (MF), were calculated from sEMG and MMG signal recordings. Spearman correlation analysis was used to investigate the relationship between the features and spasticity grades. The results showed that the correlation between MAS and each of the five features (MMG-RMS of the biceps, MMG-RMS of the triceps, the EMG-RMS of the biceps, EMG-RMS of the triceps, EMG-MPF of the triceps) was significant ($p < 0.05$). The four spasticity grades were identified with SVM, and the classification accuracy of SVM with sEMG, MMG, sEMG-MMG were 70.9%, 83.3%, 91.7%, respectively. Our results suggest that using the SVM-based method with sEMG and MMG to assess elbow spasticity would be suitable for clinical management of spasticity.	Support vector machines; Elbow;Muscles;Kernel; Feature extraction; Correlation; Electromyography	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8037699	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Agile development: It's only natural	10.1109/MySec.2014.6986018	A significant number of software development methods have been published over the last 40 years that purport to be properly based on empirical, adaptive and collaborative development. All suggest, some by name, rapid development; bringing systems to production rapidly and at lower cost. The latest manifestation of these methods is Agile Development. This paper pursues the idea that in normal, everyday life people inevitably and invariably behave in this manner; empirical, adaptive and collaborative. Their behaviour is entirely based on empirical observation of the immediate circumstances and conditions, they adapt their behaviour according to these empirical observations, and they usually need to and indeed do, collaborate with others to achieve their ends. This thinking appears to be well supported in management literature, and by influential thinkers, historically. The thesis is also that every activity that people undertake can be reasonably defined as a project. Everyday activities such as going to work, visiting the supermarket, having dinner in a restaurant with friends are examples of the myriad activities undertaken by individuals, groups and families in the natural course of their lives. To achieve success in even these usual and commonplace activities requires planning, and the activities are carried out using empirical experience to adapt their behaviour as necessary, and is almost always done in cooperation and collaboration with others. The question must arise as to why Agile Development of computer software systems is still considered as a secondary, probably second-rate and even damaging and unworkable approach to software development when these development approaches are so embedded with ideas of empirical planning, adaptive project management and collaborative behaviour. They're only natural!	agile development;adaptive planning;empirical project management	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=6986018	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Using computer history as innovation for computer organization subjects	10.1109/ITHET.2015.7217966	One of the main difficulties when teaching basic subjects related with computer fundamentals and organization to computer engineering undergraduate students is to provide an applied vision close to the current real world in order to motivate and encourage them to study this subject. Learning about the basic principles about how computers work interaction between main hardware components and fundamental assembly language programming has currently become of minor interest for our students because of the use of many simplifications and abstractions that are far from the technological reality of today. In this paper, we show how a group of teachers of the Universitat Politècnica de Valencia (UPV) have included computer history as an additional activity of the Computer Organization subject. Our main objective has been to increase the student motivation and also to spread the history of computers among young people. To this end an active visit to the Museum of Informatics of the UPV is organized as a part of the contents of the subject. This activity is designed to establish and emphasize relationships between the museum collection and the topics used as representative examples for teaching. The main concern in the organization of this activity is the large number of students involved (more than 400). This paper describes how the experience has been carried out in the present and the previous academic year; the way we have made an evaluation to improve it according the students opinion and the results achieved; lessons learned and new challenges for the future.	Computers;Organizations; History;Assembly;Computer architecture;Informatics; Education	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7217966	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

An Assessment of Graph Neural Networks for Detecting Pointer and Type Errors	10.1109/ICTC55196.2022.9952665	As the number of reported vulnerabilities continues to rise, detecting vulnerabilities remains a significant research challenge. Due to the complexity of current software systems, it becomes more difficult to detect vulnerabilities quickly and precisely using conventional methods such as static program analysis or text-based pattern matching. Recently, graph neural networks (GNN) have attracted much attention in vulnerability identification because they can manage graph structures that can represent different information flows and their relationships within a program. Due to the varying types of vulnerabilities and graph topologies of a program, it is challenging to select an appropriate graph neural network model for vulnerability identification. In this paper, we compare four GNN models to detect vulnerabilities including GCN, GraphSAGE, FastGCN, and AS-GCN. To train these models, we employ eight CWEs that can be categorized into two groups pertaining to pointer and type errors. Based on our experimental results, GraphSAGE shows better performance than other models in most cases, however GCN-based models show better results for some CWEs. As a result, our comparative study can be used as an indicator to select an appropriate model in vulnerability detection using graph neural networks.	Network topology;Software systems;Graph neural networks;Topology; Information and communication technology; Complexity theory;Pattern matching	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9952665	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Supporting Feature Estimation with Risk and Effort Annotations	10.1109/SEAA.2016.24	The accuracy of effort estimates is an important factor for the success of a project. In agile projects, these estimates are often obtained through the structured group estimation process of planning poker. To increase the accuracy of such estimates, we propose to annotate user stories with symbols that highlight risk and effort drivers and thus give all team members a better understanding of a project's challenges. In this paper, we report on the results of a study that examines the effect of using risk and effort annotations on project teams' level of shared understanding, estimation accuracy and estimation bias. Our results show that the use of annotations in planning poker increases estimation accuracy.	planning poker;estimation accuracy;annotations	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7592770	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab es
A Classification Scheme for Wireless Channel Models Across the Development Life Cycle	10.1109/USNC-URSI.2019.8861912	Wireless channel models play a critical role at all stages of the development life cycle, from standards development to network deployment. Because most organized efforts to develop channel models are relatively short term and are designed mostly to support concept assessment and standards development, the distinctive needs and requirements for the channel models used at each stage of the cycle are rarely acknowledged. Here, based upon consideration of the needs and requirements for channel models across the product life cycle, we propose that such models be divided into three distinct types (I, II and III) based upon their role, generality, application, computational complexity, primary stake holders and time available to develop. We further propose that channel model development road maps be created that will allow developers concerned with particular wireless technologies and/or deployment scenarios to more effectively communicate their needs channel modelers.	channel model;propagation; development life cycle	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8861912	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Pattern-Driven Semantic System Integration	10.1109/CISIS.2015.13	This paper presents patterns to align domain models of information systems represented in UML class diagrams. The main objective is to facilitate the process of interoperating systems applying a method to perform a conceptual integration of the existent models. This method regards ontological distinctions of Object Types for enhance the accuracy of the intended semantic of the concepts.	Integration;analysis;pattern; derivation	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7185171	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
A Java EE Data Persistence Layer Model Based on Multi Persistence Technology	10.1109/ICMSS55574.2022.00009	Aiming at how to improve the execution efficiency and development efficiency of Java EE application data persistence layer, the popular JDBC, MyBatis framework and Spring Data JPA are selected as the research objects of persistence technology. Their architecture and persistence operation process are analyzed and combined with the DAO design model. A data persistence layer model integrating the three is proposed. The model relies on JDBC interface, mapper interface and repository interface to interact with database in DAO implementation class. At the same time, the selector is used to switch between different persistence technologies according to the record number of database table. The model is applied to the development of data persistence layer in the target assessment system of colleges and universities, JDBC, MyBatis and Spring Data JPA are used as development methods to compare with the model in this paper. Practice shows that this model can ensure that every persistent operation has the best execution efficiency and higher development efficiency. Keywords-JDBC, MyBatis Framework, Spring Data JPA, Java EE, Data Persistence Layer.	JDBC;MyBatis Framework; Spring Data JPA;Java EE; Data Persistence Layer	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9827642	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Learning lane change intentions through lane contentedness estimation from demonstrated driving	10.1109/ITSC.2016.7795661	To assure a safe, comfortable and especially a cooperative driving experience while driving semi, highly or even fully automated, anticipation of the driving behavior of other traffic participants is needed. Because of the amount of different traffic situations and influence factors on the task of driving, due to uncertainties in environmental sensor measurements, and as a consequence of variable and individual driving styles, probabilistic models in combination with machine learning techniques are often applied to learn driving behavior from data. In this paper, with the help of a simulator study, the driving behavior of a subject group is examined regarding their intention to change lane on highways. The simulator is set up as a partially automated driving system that takes discrete maneuver wishes as input (lane change left or lane change right). If the traffic situation permits it, the requested maneuvers is executed automatically by the system. This generates ground truth labels that are being used to train a lane change intention classifier. The results show that the approach is able to predict upcoming lane changes at an average of more than 3.5 seconds in advance.	Emotion;Affect;Machine Intelligence;IAPS;Valence; Arousal;Feature Selection; Classification	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7795661	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es
Affect detection in normal groups with the help of biological markers	10.1109/INDICON.2015.7443733	Emotion Recognition always has been one of the key areas in human machine interaction, machine learning or affective computing. Two dimensional valence arousal model has been used here. In this paper, we present how simple emotion recognition can be done by measuring nine basic non-invasive Biological markers or physiological signals including BR [Breathing], ECG [ElectroCardioGram], EMG [ElectroMyoGram], GSR [Galvanic Skin Response], HR [Heart Rate], PR [Pulse Rate], RR [Respiration Rate], and ST [Skin Temperature] on thirty healthy subjects. Pictorial emotional stimuli categorized as High Valence High Arousal [HVHA], High Valence Low Arousal [HVLVA], Low Valence High Arousal [LVHA] and Low Valence Low Arousal [LVLA] were shown using International Affective Picture System (IAPS) for approximately thirty minutes. Six features from each signal were extracted for analysis. Different types of classification algorithms like QDC [Quadratic Discriminant Classifier], kNN [k Nearest Neighbour], Naive Bayes and LDA [Linear Discriminant Analysis] were used in classification of data. Maximum accuracy around 75% for each classifier was obtained. Further improvements are required to make this more robust and to deploy commercially.	Emotion;Affect;Machine Intelligence;IAPS;Valence; Arousal;Feature Selection; Classification	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7443733	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es
Understanding the Relation between System Usability and End User Performance	10.1109/IIESEC54230.2021.9672429	Web applications have been spreading everywhere. However, this may have a number of drawbacks mostly related to usability issues. Therefore, the investigation of usability problems continues to improve these applications. In this study, usability metrics are used for web application interface evaluation. The relation between web application usability and end user performance is investigated. Many studies have evaluated interface usability in a number of sectors; however, studies on oil and gas web applications have been limited. In this study, two sessions with twelve participants were designed to obtain data directly from end users. The sessions were observation and user feedback sessions. The findings indicate a potential relation between system usability and end user performance in terms of effectiveness and satisfaction.	System usability;User Interface;End User performance;Human Factors; Oil and Gas sector;Human Computer Interaction;Web applications;Energy Informatics	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9672429	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Integrated design of Battery Energy Storage System with PV for university campus energy sustainability	10.1109/URUCON63440.2024.10850230	This document presents a real case study evaluating the optimal design for installation of a battery energy storage system (BESS) together with a photovoltaic system (PV). The selected case study was the UNIFEI campus in Itajubá-MG, Brazil, supplied by the Brazilian distribution utility CEMIG. The tariff structure in Brazil is essentially classified in two groups: group A for customers supplied in medium, high voltages, and underground systems and group B, supplied in low voltage systems. UNIFEI is supplied at 13.8 kV medium voltage level, thus classified as group A4, and with the time of use (TOU) tariff "Green Tariff", i.e. with different energy prices for peak and off-peak periods and a single price value for power demand. Therefore, based on the campus energy bills, it was developed and applied an approach using the software HOMER® - Hybrid Optimization of Multiple Energy Resources to calculate the demand power and energy size for the battery energy storage system(s) using ferrous lithium batteries mainly focusing in saving electricity generated by the PV systems during the day to supply electrical energy during peak hours at night, thus avoiding high electricity prices from the utility. Then, it was evaluated the possible technical and economic impacts. This paper contributes to the global issue on sustainable development, taking universities as living labs in energy transition.	Battery energy storage system;photovoltaic system; university campus;energy sustainability;integrated design	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10850230	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Research on multi-modal data fusion technology based on automotive spot welding process	10.1109 /AIIM60438. 2023.10441028	With the wide application of automotive welding automation, the fusion of multimodal data has become an important research direction. In this paper, a multi-modal data fusion technology based on automotive spot welding process is proposed, including management configuration service, equipment data service, database data service, data fusion service, gateway service and public class module. Through the selection of microservice framework Spring Cloud, message queue, front-end framework, and other technologies, different types of data sources are accessed, managed, processed, and stored. Experimental results show that this technology can effectively improve the efficiency of data integration, sharing and application, and provides strong technical support for the intelligent construction of automotive welding automation.	multimodal data fusion; automotive welding automation;Microservices architecture	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10441028	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
An Empirical Study of Career Planning for University Students based on SPSS Statistical Analysis	10.1109 /ITEI55021. 2021.00070	Career planning is crucial in helping students to improve their career awareness and employability. This study conducted a quantitative study with 433 questionnaires (M=208, F=225, Mage=21.6) on the situations of university students' career planning. Correlation analysis, difference analysis and cluster analysis (K-means algorithm and Pam algorithm) were used with SPSS statistics software to understand their status in four indicators—self-understanding., status assessment., career exploration and decision action.	Career planning;Correlation analysis;Difference analysis; Cluster analysis	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9752666	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es
Agent-based simulation model for identifying failure on students' project	10.1109/SMC. 2017.8123105	In learning and development, students need to be made aware of their slips and mistakes in terms of acquiring the required knowledge, skills and competencies, especially, in active learning approaches. However, assessments may not necessarily lead to an effective understanding of student's errors. Most assessors are required to measure the extent of student's accurate output in terms of exam answers or practical assessments. Areas of failure tend to be overlooked and for this reason, learners at-risk of achieving poor results can become careless when completing assessments. In the present study, we examine the following research questions: (i) How can we simulate the landscape of data on both individual and team behaviour in terms of failure in their projects? (ii) How can we develop ways of identifying at-risk students in each team and support them immediately? Therefore, in order to address this problem, this research proposes an agent-based simulation of student projects, which considers both individual and team errors. This model is created on the basis of particular characteristics of individual learners within the team. We assume that individuals working within a team are subject to recognition-primed decision making when confronted with particular problems to solve. The adjustment proposed by this model includes analysing the problem using prior knowledge and planning as well as judgements on the suitability of particular solutions. This research will be further developed to identify at-risk learners in terms of investigating the areas they want to develop to achieve their learning goals in particular subjects and especially in the software development fields.	agent-based simulation; students' project;human failure awareness; recognition-primed decision model	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8123105	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es
Optimizing Feedback Recommendation in Smart Training Framework using NLP	10.1109 /IDAP64064. 2024.10710987	This paper primary goal is to assess an item's resemblance to a ranked group of things. Our research investigates how smart training framework can employ such recommendation systems to provide feedback remarks for students' open-ended responses. In this case, it's employed to create a feedback framework that aids educators in evaluating their pupils' free-form responses. We explore various methods for assessing the semantic relatedness of two answers and use our unique metric, Faculty Assessment points (FAP), to assess the quality of semantic relatedness. Evaluating open-ended data, like natural language, is sometimes regarded as a challenging endeavour. We have developed a software infrastructure that allows us to conduct Randomized Control Trials on the ASSISTments Platform in order to assess the system's quality.	Machine Learning;NLP; Statistics;etc	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10710987	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Insider Threat Detection and its Behavior with Excessive Access Privileges	10.1109 /SSITCON62437. 2024.10796563	Insider threats, one of the most challenging cyber threats, often result in significant organizational losses. This study explores the correlation between suspicious users and job roles vulnerable to insider threats. The research highlights that users with higher access privileges are more exposed to potential insider attacks. K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) and hierarchical clustering, implemented using Weka, were employed to detect suspicious activity and group users by their roles. Based on a comparison of successive months, an overall accuracy value of 0.85 was obtained. By monitoring for suspicious changes in their cluster over time, we were able to identify 80% of insider threats with the ITAdmin job. The results revealed that many users exhibiting abnormal activities held IT admin roles, indicating that those with the highest access permissions are more prone to insider threats. This study addresses a gap in understanding the relationship between excessive access permissions and security risks.	cyber threats;access privileges;job roles;threat detection	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10796563	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Analysing Cancer Care Informatics Through The Lens of The United Nations Sustainable Development Goals - A Review and Assessment	10.1109 /CANCERCAR E. 2018.8618264	Cancer Care Informatics (CCI) and its impacts are assessed using the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The positive and negative impacts of CCI on the SDGs are considered through a literature review and expert assessment. There has not been a prior publication of such an assessment and this could contribute to more holistic governance of CCI. The paper reviews the individual SDGs along with consideration of the 17 SDGs as a whole. Whilst the relationship of CCI with the achievement of SDG3 (Good Health and Well-Being) is the obvious impact, CCI also has impacts on other underpinning targets or indicators within the SDG framework. For example, the Greenhouse Gas emissions from the electricity consumed by CCI computer systems will have a negative effect on SDG13 Climate Change. Using the SDG lens helps us to identify the other direct and indirect impacts of CCI on Sustainable Development and affords the opportunity to manage deliberately such impacts as improving equality of access, elimination of modern slavery and delivering CCI education.	Cancer Care Informatics; Sustainable Development Goals	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8618264	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab, es
Towards a symmetrical definition of QoE: An Evaluation of Emotion Semantics in Augmented Reality Training	10.1109 /QoMEX58391. 2023.10178564	The current definition of quality of experience (QoE) designates delight and annoyance as diametrically opposing indicators of the degree of fulfilment of an application, service or system user's pragmatic and hedonic needs and expectations. However, these inherited emotion terms are rarely used to describe emotions of equal amounts of arousal or opposing amounts of valence in the literature. This work assesses the significance of this asymmetry to the definition of QoE by determining the utility of emotion terms to communicate the emotion component of QoE. This was done in the context of a QoE evaluation of augmented reality training instruction formats. Correlates were sought between various measures of emotional state. This included physiological ratings, facial expressions and eye gaze. Emotional state was subjectively reported using three distinct methods: self-assessment manikin questionnaire; 2D emotion space terms; and open-ended terms. Regression analysis showed multiple significant correlations between implicit and explicit metrics, but not to the emotion terms used by the participants. This calls into question the utility of such vaguely understood terms. The use of more symmetrically opposing emotions in the definition of QoE may benefit consensual interdisciplinary communication.	quality of experience; emotion; augmented reality; procedure; training	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10178564	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es
Workload Assessment in Remote Mixed Reality Medical Procedural Training Through Physiological Signals	10.1109 /EMBC53108. 2024.10782348	Mixed reality (MR) technology has been adopted for teaching and procedural planning/guidance in medicine, but its impact on performance is not well understood. Evaluation of cognitive load during MR-augmented learning experiences could help to quantify its utility. In this study, we performed a cognitive load analysis using physiological signals, specifically pupillary diameter (PD) and heart rate variability (HRV), to assess the learning experience of students performing simulated ultrasound-guided central venous catheterization (CVC) through MR remote assistance. We evaluated the cognitive load in students performing high-precision (vessel location and needle insertion) and low-precision (guidewire and catheter insertion) portions of the US CVC procedure and compared them to the results of students learning via teleconferencing software. The mean PD after baseline correction was lower, an indicator of decreased cognitive load, during high-precision MR-guided tasks than during the lower-precision tasks (3.80 vs 7.42 px, p<0.09). The observed changes in PD suggest a positive impact on the overall teaching experience for students exposed to holographic objects during training. Heart rate variability, measured by a ratio of low to high-frequency power, showed a similar but non-significant trend. No significant differences were seen in high vs low precision task workload in the control group. Our findings provide valuable insights into the potential benefits of incorporating holographic objects into complex medical procedure training. Clinical relevance— The study demonstrates that within MR, the cognitive load during medical procedural training is reduced when providing augmented 3D models in MR that are utilized by the instructor.	cognitive load; mixed reality; pupil diameter	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10782348	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
NTIRE 2020 Challenge on Video Quality Mapping: Methods and Results	10.1109 /CVPRW50498. 2020.00246	This paper reviews the NTIRE 2020 challenge on video quality mapping (VQM), which addresses the issues of quality mapping from source video domain to target video domain. The challenge includes both a supervised track (track 1) and a weakly-supervised track (track 2) for two benchmark datasets. In particular, track 1 offers a new Internet video benchmark, requiring algorithms to learn the map from more compressed videos to less compressed videos in a supervised training manner. In track 2, algorithms are required to learn the quality mapping from one device to another when their quality varies substantially and weakly-aligned video pairs are available. For track 1, in total 7 teams competed in the final test phase, demonstrating novel and effective solutions to the problem. For track 2, some existing methods are evaluated, showing promising solutions to the weakly-supervised video quality mapping problem.	Video recording; Quality assessment; Generative adversarial networks; Target tracking; Training; Cameras; Image coding	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9150822	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Meso-Structure Quantitative Research about Coals Based on the Digital Image Processing Technology	10.1109 /ICMTMA. 2015.160	The coals of rich in cracks have low strength, large deformation and difficult to support, obtain triaxial compression test parameters by RMT-150B rock mechanics and concrete mechanical testing machine, the micro-structure of coals damage photos on coals samples fracture obtained by scanning electron microscope observations. Use the fissures information extraction software developed from MATLAB platform. This paper put forward a quantitative research idea to extract fracture morphology and the two-dimensional geometry of the coals micro-structure based on image enhancement and regional growing algorithm. At the same time, make a statistical analysis of coals samples triaxial compression fracture azimuth, width, length and other information. We obtain coals's strength and elastic modulus is lower and the presence of a large number of initial damage, with significant anisotropy and in homogeneity.	coal;region growing method; meso-structure;SEM	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7263654	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Sources of error during inertial sensing of human movement: a critical review of the fundamentals	10.1109 /MeMeA57477. 2023.10171885	Inertial assessments of human movement have potential to support diagnosis and treatment of neuromuscular disorders in healthcare settings. Despite the potential advantages, uptake and acceptance by healthcare professionals are still a challenge, as inertial measurement units are prone to measurement errors due to inherent limitations with the technology. As such, full exploitation is limited to a small group of highly qualified personnel. For usage to be more ubiquitous, standard practices for acquiring high-quality data are required and should include methods for error avoidance, detection, identification, quantification, and mitigation. In this paper, a critical review of sources of error was conducted, from which a taxonomic error classification framework was developed. From this review, it has become apparent which sources of error carry the highest risk for impacting data quality. Methods for error mitigation have been identified, along with limitations and areas for improvement. This framework is intended to serve as a useful reference for both proficient and non-proficient users to ensure all sources of error are considered when developing and interpreting IMU-based assessments. It also provides a foundation for developing standard practices to help users efficiently and reliably acquire high-quality data, which is imperative for uptake and acceptance in healthcare settings.	Clinical movement assessment;wearable sensors;measurement error; signal processing;standard practice	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10171885	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es
A Knowledge-Based Autonomous Decision-Making Method for Agents in Asymmetric Confrontation	10.1109 /CASE56687. 2023.10260346	This paper studies an asymmetric confrontation problem, i.e., multiple agents with weak capability attack a powerful target. In particular, agents' autonomous decision-making is essential in a complex and situation-change scenario. A knowledge-based autonomous decision-making method is proposed for agents to improve their decision-making ability in the confrontation. The proposed method is based on the tactical pursuit point (TPP) mechanism and each agent's current situation. Firstly, each agent conducts a situation assessment based on the available information, including situation type assessment and situation superiority assessment. Then, the TPP mechanism is utilized to generate a continuous tactical pursuit space (set of all possible tactical pursuit points). To reduce the complexity of decision-making, the tactical pursuit space is defined by a tactical pursuit basis and a decision-making vector. In addition, the decision-making vector is calculated by a designed function based on the situation assessment information. Therefore, a tactical pursuit point can be determined by the decision-making vector in the tactical pursuit space. Finally, under the guidance of the tactical pursuit point, each agent performs the attack maneuver. Simulation results show that the agents can make autonomous decisions during the confrontation. Meanwhile, multiple agents cooperate to attack a target, and the number of casualty agents is reduced.	Computer aided software engineering;Automation; Simulation;Decision making; Knowledge based systems; Complexity theory;Behavioral sciences	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10260346	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Hardware and software innovations in energy-efficient system-reliability monitoring	10.1109/DFT. 2017.8244435	Many threats that can undermine the reliability of a system can be realized at design, while others only during its online operation. As the availability of system monitoring sensors and run-time software increases in heterogeneous platforms, there is a demand for a novel platform-independent framework that can capture and deliver, in a holistic way, system level self-assessment and adaptation capabilities at run-time. In this paper, two groups from academia and one from industry present the following three contributions. First, system reliability is considered from the perspective of novel timing guardband designs for aging mitigation. Effective timing guardband models are presented from the physical to the system level, while targeting multiple wear-out mechanisms. Second, a technique for correlating complex software and micro-architectural events with power integrity loss is presented. The presented technique uses an embedded voltage noise sensor, a power-network model and a genetic algorithm for identifying workload that triggers power-network resonances which can ultimately lead to system failures. Third, the 'PRIME' cross-layer programming framework is presented that unites available sensors and dynamic-voltage and frequency scaling actuators with learning-based run-time process mapping and scheduling algorithms. Scenarios on exploring the energy efficiency and reliability of heterogeneous platforms using run-time software derived from the developed framework are also reviewed.	Aging;Timing;Degradation; Software;Monitoring; Reliability engineering	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8244435	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

A Computational Model for Improving the Accuracy of Multi-criteria Recommender Systems	10.1109/MCSoc.2017.14	Artificial neural networks are complex biologically inspired algorithms made up of highly distributed, adaptive and self-organizing structures that make them suitable for optimization problems. They are made up of a group of interconnected nodes, similar to the great networks of neurons in the human brain. So far, artificial neural networks have not been applied to user modeling in multi-criteria recommender systems. This paper presents neural networks-based user modeling technique that exploits some of the characteristics of biological neurons for improving the accuracy of multi-criteria recommendations. The study was based upon the aggregation function approach that computes the overall rating as a function of the criteria ratings. The proposed technique was evaluated using different evaluation metrics, and the empirical results of the experiments were compared with that of the single rating-based collaborative filtering and two other similarity-based modeling approaches. The two similarity-based techniques used are: the worst-case and the average similarity techniques. The results of the comparative analysis have shown that the proposed technique is more efficient than the two similarity-based techniques and the single rating collaborative filtering technique.	Recommender systems; Collaborative filtering; Multi-criteria recommendation; Artificial neural networks; Similarity	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8326613	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	chance
Predictive Analytics in Performance Appraisal Systems: Enhancing Objectivity and Fairness	10.1109/IDICAIEI61867.2024.10842916	Background & Scope: Performance evaluation systems are crucial in evaluating employee performance, providing feedback, and facilitating talent development initiatives. Conventional performance evaluation systems rely on personal opinions and are susceptible to prejudice. Utilizing data-driven predictive analytics enhances the objectivity and equity of the performance evaluation system. This study examines the potential role of predictive analytics in improving the fairness and impartiality of performance rating systems. The study investigates the potential of predictive analytics models to mitigate biases, improve accuracy, and promote objectivity in performance evaluation. Methodology: A detailed and comprehensive analysis of the literature on predictive analytics in performance management and staff development has been done to identify gaps and find untapped areas. The research integrates the data from organizations that employ predictive analytics for their employee performance evaluations, which have been included as a sample in this research for the Qualitative assessment & review. Originality: This research contributes to the current understanding of the application of predictive analytics in the organization's employee performance assessment system. It provides an in-depth analysis of the advantages, disadvantages, and methods of using predictive analytics in assessing human resource management operations for an employee's performance. Implications and Future Directions: Performance assessment systems that utilize and implement predictive analytics in the organization to improve the fairness, accuracy, and impartiality of HRM decision-making and that can examine the ethical, scalability, and long-term impacts of using and applying predictive analytics in the Organization for Performance assessment in the HRM practices.	Predictive Analytics; Performance Appraisal; Objectivity Enhancement; Fairness Improvement; HRM Operations	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10842916	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Collective Ontologies Design and Development	10.1109/CISIS.2014.82	The paper presents the research performed within the KOMET (Knowledge and content structuring via Methods of collaborative ontology design) project targeted at of a new structuring paradigm design for data and knowledge. Such approach is formed with regard to individual cognitive styles and it uses recent advances in knowledge engineering and conceptual structuring, aimed at creating new consistent and structurally holistic knowledge bases for the various areas of science and technology. Three stages of research have been done within the project. The results of these research stages described in the paper can be applied to organizing the collaborative ontology design (especially for research and learning purposes), data structuring and other group analytical work. Some implications for practice are proposed.	collective ontology design; cognitive styles	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=6915575	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es
Predictions based on Twitter — A critical view on the research process	10.1109/ICODSE.2014.7062667	Twitter data is increasingly used to make predictions about real-world events. However recently, several studies directly or indirectly questioned proposed Twitter prediction procedures. In this paper, we conduct a literature review to investigate the research processes adopted by previous Twitter prediction studies in detail. We first identify the actors involved, and then we study how they influence the different phases of the research process. We found that in Twitter prediction research up to four actors perform several sampling, filtering, classification and assessment decisions throughout the development of prediction models. If these decisions and the reasons behind them are not sufficiently documented, the developed prediction methods cannot be reproduced in future research and consequently their validity and reliability are hard to assess.	Twitter; prediction; microblog; reliability; validity	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7062667	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Measuring changes in gait and vehicle transfer ability during inpatient rehabilitation with wearable inertial sensors	10.1109 /PERCOMW. 2017.7917600	Restoration of functional independence in gait and vehicle transfer ability is a common goal of inpatient rehabilitation. Currently, ambulation changes tend to be subjectively assessed by clinicians. To investigate more precise objective assessment of progress in inpatient rehabilitation, we quantitatively assessed gait and transfer performances over the course of rehabilitation with wearable inertial sensors for 20 patients receiving inpatient rehabilitation services. Participant performance was recorded on a sequence of ambulatory tasks that closely resemble everyday activities. We developed a custom software system to process sensor signals and compute metrics that characterize ambulation performance. We quantified changes in gait and transfer ability by performing a repeated measures comparison of the metrics one week apart. Metrics showing the greatest improvement are walking speed, stride regularity, acceleration root mean square, walking smoothness, shank peak angular velocity, and shank range of motion. Wearable sensor-derived metrics can potentially provide rehabilitation therapists with additional valuable information to aid in treatment decisions.	Accelerometry;ambulatory monitoring;inertial measurement units;signal processing;wearable sensors	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7917600	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Internet of Things based Blockchain Key Management	10.1109 /ICSSIT46314. 2019.8987834	Blockchain is collection of blocks process and also Security of Account is needed for private keys. Blockchain is a based Collection of blocks. blockchain in Public Key Infrastructure is utilized and validate the entities. Analysis of current PKI for blockchain and Analysis of blockchain and discussed of wallet key management. Also proposed secure group communication. The acknowledgment should perceived as double-edged sword of software architecture in a blockchain, terms of auditability in allows to achieve benefits, strong integrity protection. also confidentiality achieve in sensitive data over network. come together with characteristics on the other hand they, also permanence, properly considered that need. for example, interaction in personal data, may result particularly critical in blockchain adoption. aslo how to works blockchain transection and different types of blockchain technologies.	Blockchain;Machine learning; Blockchain key management; Blockchain group key management;Risk assessment	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8987834	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Detection of Traumatic Brain Injury Using Single Channel Electroencephalogram in Mice	10.1109 /SPMB50085. 2020.9353651	Preclinical studies of traumatic brain injury (TBI) are often performed using a murine model of mild traumatic brain injury (mTBI) due to highly controlled settings and high reproducibility in this experimental model, compared to studies of human TBI. We have previously demonstrated persistent changes in the sleep wake cycle using a widely accepted mouse model of mTBI. The gold standard of sleep wake assessment is achieved by recording brain electroencephalogram (EEG), which not only allows for standard sleep staging but also allows further signal processing through quantitative EEG methods. Conventional methods of sleep staging require manual scoring by a trained expert. Here, a 1-D deep convolutional neural network (Deep CNN) is proposed to automatically score sleep stages and identify mTBI from a single-channel EEG signal with duration of 64 seconds by classifying the EEG signal into one of four classes: sham (control) wake, sham (control) sleep, mTBI wake, and mTBI sleep. We demonstrated that the proposed Deep CNN has the ability to learn features to classify the target classes. Deployment of the trained model on Raspberry Pi further indicates the capacity to perform classification in real time and mobile applications. Thus, the proposed system has the potential to provide a low-cost and fast method for detection of TBI in individuals.	Sleep;Manuals;Signal processing;Brain modeling; Electroencephalography; Mice;Brain injuries	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9353651	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Novel Attack Vector to Abuse AWS for Cryptojacking	10.1109 /ICAAIC60222. 2024.10575628	This study investigates cryptojacking attacks on cloud infrastructure, focusing on hacker groups and their methods from 2017 to 2024. We analyze how attackers deploy mining software and malware in the cloud, leading to performance degradation, resource consumption, and financial loss. Typically, these attacks target specific cloud resources like AWS EC2 or Lambda. Our novel approach involves using an EC2 instance as an internal command-and-control (C2) server to coordinate the provisioning of AWS ECS, Lightsail, and EKS services for mining purposes. System specifications are exfiltrated through DNS tunneling. We propose strategies and best practices for mitigating these attacks. Victims of these attacks often face significant costs, with each dollar gained by attackers resulting in nearly \$153 in electricity and compute bills.	Cryptojacking;Cloud; Blockchain;Monero;XMRig; Mining;Amazon Web Services;Miningcore	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10575628	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

A novel approach for travel package recommendation using Bayesian approach	10.1109 /ICCCCT2. 2015.7292764	Today internet has been connected to people more in the world of tourism, amusement, economics and as a trend huge number of travel firms provide online services and these services are provided by individual sectors. In the traditional approach the Tourist area season topic model is used which address the unique trait along the travel statistics. Since the user has to choose only from the available packages which fails to provide a customized travel package. Therefore Tourist Relation Area Season Topic model is enhanced by creating relationship among the users and the data are semantically classified which provides effective assessment on automatic travel group formation. The Nearest Neighbor method helps to find the neighboring places for the particular area. As the solution which is more efficient than the conventional recommended system and also satisfies the user by providing customized package. It supersedes the hybrid recommendation strategy to produce an efficient result to the travellers. The collaborative tagging which mainly works in tagging the neighboring places by predicting the value for the suggested areas and this mechanism helps to capture effective results in the real world recommender system.	Collaborative Tagging;Spatial Temporal Auto Correlation; Recommender System; Nearest Neighbor	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7292764	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es
Mathematical Modeling and Analysis of Patterns in Structured Collections of Big Data	10.1109 /ACIT58437. 2023.10275705	This paper addresses the issue of creating and applying mathematical models and methods for finding generalized solutions when working with structured collections of "big data". We reviewed the modern methodologies used to solve problems of this class. The mathematical model presented describes an ordered set of all subsets formed from a finite ordered base set of arbitrary size and data type. We explored a set of functional dependencies of five discrete input variables to work with this mathematical model. Some of these functional dependencies are derived for specific solutions with specified boundary conditions. The paper also presents examples of how the derived functional dependencies are applied in the implementation of mathematical methods using this model. This required us to conduct a comparative assessment of the search time for a solution with and without the use of these mathematical methods. Comparative graphs are demonstrated to show the rate of increase in the number of operations depending on the size of the original finite base set with and without the use of these mathematical methods. As a result of this, logical conclusions are drawn regarding the impact of mathematical methods for working with structured collections on minimizing time and computational resources.	big data;mathematical model; computational modeling;data analysis;data organization structure;ordered set of arbitrary cardinality	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10275705	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Putting away the Groceries with Precise Semantic Placements	10.1109 /CASE49997. 2022.9926691	We present a methodology for a service robot to put away the groceries in a precise and stable configuration that satisfies the desired semantic relationship of grocery and pantry objects. This task is invaluable to the motor impaired and increases the capability of contextualized service robots. We show that augmenting traditional geometric assessment with contextual knowledge of food categorization and a language association model, allows the robot to complete this task efficiently. We quantitatively validate our approach with a data set of 51 common grocery items, of which 11 objects are used for real world experiments. According to our evaluation, our method is able to successfully shelf objects next to semantically related objects 100% of the time when these relationships exist. We achieve this with an average placement precision of 3.2cm and a standard deviation of 1.1cm. We discuss remaining challenges and needed improvements for robots with these capabilities to be introduced to home environments.	Measurement;Computer aided software engineering; Automation;Service robots; Semantics;Task analysis; Older adults	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9926691	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

INGR Roadmap Systems Optimization Chapter	10.1109 /FNWF55208. 2022.00143	Fifth generation (5G) networks represent the first step from evolutionary to revolutionary networks. Use cases driving this transition for 5G networks focus on the need to support heterogeneous traffic such as enhanced Mobile Broad Band (eMBB), massive Machine-Type Communications (mMTC), and Ultra-Reliable Low-Latency Communications (URLLC). On the software and control side, 5G and beyond networks are expected to support Software-Defined Networking (SDN) and Network Function virtualization (NFV) technologies and will leverage the merging of communication and computing through the "wireless edge". With the deployment of novel applications and the expected increase in their usage and demand, the scope of innovation within future networks will be governed by: (a) limitations and boundaries of available resources; (b) limitations of the adaptability of legacy solutions (scalability and flexibility); (c) limitations of available decision making entities (network slice orchestrators and SDN controllers will not be enough); and (d) lack of intelligent management and control solutions for multi-variate optimization. Technologies are available for efficient use and self-adaptive optimization of resources using enablers such as AI-powered autonomic control loops. With ever increasing complexity expected for beyond-5G networks, there is a necessity for novel design, planning and operations paradigms. There is a need for assessment of legacy tools versus new Artificial Intelligence solutions for applicability to systems optimization, and a need for introduction of novel methods to model and study the behavior of highly complex systems developed for the realization of 5G and beyond networks. The goal of this working group (WG) is to assess complexity challenges for the 5G era and beyond, explore novel design, planning and operations techniques for networks and services, and explore intelligence sciences to create the roadmap of the IEEE Future Networks Initiative (FNI) Systems Optimization WG.	Systems Optimization;Traffic Variance;Control Variance; Service Variance; Confluence;Dependency; Complex Systems;Self-Organizing Networks;Self-X; Autonomics;Autonomic Management & Control (AMC);Emergence	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10056672	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
A Scalable Multi-factor Fault Analysis Framework for Information Systems	10.1109 /BigData52589. 2021.9671747	Information systems such as cellular networks produce large volumes of data, making the characterization of network faults a difficult task. In this work, we introduce a new fault analysis framework based on association rule mining and validate it to identify the root cause of faults in information systems. The paper describes a strategy using association rules to specifically target faults while improving runtime performance relative to the standard Apache Spark implementation. We also introduce a novel association rule filtering strategy called Cover Set filtering that prunes and merges rule sets to produce high-quality, concise and interpretable results. The proposed framework is evaluated with real-world telecommunication datasets. Comparing this framework approach with other strategies, we demonstrate a better rule diversity in general and a sufficiently compact analysis of the faults. The validation of our experimental results was conducted by telecommunications experts, who confirmed the clarity and value of the results for a quantitative assessment of cellular network failures.	Cellular networks;Runtime; Filtering;3G mobile communication;Filtering algorithms;Big Data; Handover	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9671747	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es
Advanced Safety Accident Analysis for Temperature Variation on Methanol Chemical Plant	10.1109 /ICSGRC57744. 2023.10215395	Carbon capture and utilization (CCU) is the process of capturing carbon dioxide (CO2) to be recycled for further usage. Captured CO2 can be converted to several products which is one group being alcohols, such as methanol, to use as biofuels and other alternative and renewable sources of energy. The purpose of this paper is to investigate the effect of different temperature on methanol plant due to consequence accidents analysis in Papar, Sabah, Malaysia. This work investigated the possibility of (1) to identify chemical component's mass and volume in the mixture for different temperature on methanol production and (2) to quantify the safety of methanol plant using distance and area plot threat analysis for different temperature. Based on the inherent safer concept, the increasing of the temperature will affect the plant safety. In this study, there have three plant condition which have the volume of 42 m3 and the pressure of 442 bar at outlet stream but with three different temperatures which are 220°C, 260°C, and 300°C. To model the process and determine the mass density of the mixture, mass fraction, and volume fraction, HYSYS software was utilized. ALOHA and MARPLOT tools were then used to determine the distance and area plot threat of toxicity, thermal radiation and overpressure. Results proved that Plant 1 with 220°C operating temperature has the farthest red zone distance and highest rate of fatalities (751 m and 56.6%), compare to Plant 2 and 3, coming from MeOH toxicity and MeOH BLEVE at night time, respectively. This study can be used to recommend suitable and safe location for methanol plant and its surrounding area.	Methanol chemical plant; Safety accident;Temperature variation	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10215395	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

On SORA for High-Risk UAV Operations under New EU Regulations: Perspectives for Automated Approach	10.1109 /ICUAS57906. 2023.10156517	In this paper, we investigate requirements to prepare an application for Specific Operations Risk Assessment (SORA), regulated by European Union Aviation Safety Agency (EASA) to obtain flight authorization for Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) operations and propose some perspectives to automate the approach based on our successful application. Preparation of SORA requires expert knowledge as it contains technicalities. Also, the whole process is an iterative and timeconsuming one. It is even more challenging for higher-risk operations, such as those in urban environments, near airports, and multi- and customized models for research activities. SORA process limits the potential socio-economic impacts of innovative UAV capabilities. Therefore, in this paper, we present a SORA example, review the steps and highlight challenges. Accordingly, we propose an alternative workflow, considering the same steps, while addressing the challenges and pitfalls, to shorten the whole process. Furthermore, we present a comprehensive list of preliminary technical procedures, including the pre/during/post-flight checklists, design and installation appraisal, flight logbook, operational manual, training manual, and General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), which are not explicitly instructed in SORA manual. Moreover, we propose the initial idea to create an automated SORA workflow to facilitate obtaining authorization, which is significantly helpful for operators, especially the scientific community, to conduct experimental operations.	ConOps;Design and Installation Appraisal;EASA; Flight Checklists;General Data Protection Regulation; Operational Manual;SORA; Training Manual;UAV	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10156517	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
PACED: Provenance-based Automated Container Escape Detection	10.1109 /IC2E55432. 2022.00035	The security of container-based microservices relies heavily on the isolation of operating system resources that is provided by namespaces. However, vulnerabilities exist in the isolation of containers that may be exploited by attackers to gain access to the host. These are commonly referred to as container escape attacks. While prior work has identified vulnerabilities in namespace isolation, no general container escape detection and warning system has been presented. We present Paced, a novel, realtime system to detect container-escape attacks. We define what constitutes a cross-namespace event and how such events can be used to detect a container escape attack. We develop a provenance-based approach to isolate cross-namespace events and propose a rule—privileged_flow—to detect attacks on Docker and Kubernetes environments. We evaluate our detection method on a suite of contemporary CVEs with container escape exploits, bad container configurations, and benchmarks. Paced achieves near-perfect accuracy with no false negatives. We release our implementation and datasets as free, open-source software.	provenance;container; container escape;security	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9946350	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Delivering Clinical Impact with AI: Key Challenges and Considerations	10.1109 /ICICAT62666. 2024.10923454	The field of machine learning applications in wellbeing and medication proceeds to pull in expanding intrigued and investigate consideration. There are increasingly signs of this technology's guarantee in each zone of restorative investigate. In any case, it is very exceptional to see these strategies utilized to compelling clinical arrangement. The essential deterrents and impediments of fake insights (AI) within the setting of wellbeing care are discussed in this article, together with the steps that must be taken to induce these possibly paradigm-shifting breakthroughs from lab inquire about to the patient's bedside. Essential Segment: evacuating the essential deterrents to the utilize of AI frameworks in healthcare, such as those related to profound learning itself, as well as any fundamental alterations to workflow or societal traditions. As such, careful, peer-reviewed clinical assessments carried out as a component of controlled trials have to be be respected as the gold standard for information creation. In terms of conduct, this may not always be seen as doable or fitting. Execution measurements got to speak to genuine clinical utility and have centrality for the target group of onlookers. Postmarket administration and checking are vital to preserve a adjust between the rate of advance and the probability of harm, without imperiling patients by withholding supportive innovation or uncovering them to unsafe drugs. It is significant to empower coordinate assessments of AI systems, for instance, by giving partitioned, nearby, and edifying test sets. Hence, the manufactured insights software engineer must seek for potential dangers such as dataset moving, confounder fitting, segregating inclinations, and various issues with extrapolating to a different population than the common open, in expansion to potential negative side impacts from unused computers on wellbeing results. Coordination AI investigate into convenient, clinically demonstrated, fittingly overseen, and human-beneficial stages is demonstrating to be troublesome.	Clinical Impact;Artificial Intelligence;Healthcare; Machine Learning; Challenges;Integration;Data Management;Validation; Ethical Considerations; Regulatory Compliance	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10923454	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Network risk evaluation from security metric of vulnerability detection tools	10.1109 /TENCON. 2014.7022358	Network Security is always a major concern in any organizations. To ensure that the organization network is well prevented from attackers, vulnerability assessment and penetration testing are implemented regularly. However, it is a highly time-consuming procedure to audit and analysis these testing results depending on administrator's expertise. Thus, security professionals prefer proactive-automatic vulnerability detection tools to identify vulnerabilities before they are exploited by an adversary. Although these vulnerability detection tools show that they are very useful for security professionals to audit and analysis much faster and more accurate, they have some important weaknesses as well. They only identify surface vulnerabilities and are unable to address the overall risk level of the scanned network. Also, they often use different standard for network risk level classification which habitually related to some organizations or vendors. Thus, these vulnerability detection tools are likely to, more or less, classify risk evaluation biasedly. This article presents a generic idea of "Network Risk Metric" as an unbiased risk evaluation from several vulnerability detection tools. In this paper, NetClarity (hardware-based), Nessus (software-based), and Retina (software-based) are implemented on two networks from an IT department of the Royal Thai Army (RTA). The proposed metric is applied for evaluating overall network risk from these three vulnerability detection tools. The result is a more accurate risk evaluation for each network.	Network Security;Risk Evaluation;Security Metrics; Vulnerability Detection	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7022358	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
A web-based framework using a Model-View-Controller architecture for human motion analysis	10.1109 /ENBENG. 2015.7088815	In a world with large technological advances and where technology takes a more and more essential place, the interaction between technology and health is increasingly present, particularly when one speaks of web technologies. The computerized clinical decision support systems (CDDS) are a good example of combination of web technology and health [1]. This work was part of a larger project that aimed to develop a tractable cloud-based open-source framework for human movement analysis and classification, using inverse kinematics from marker trajectories collected by means of a motion capture system. The main objective of the present work was to contribute to the development of a web-based framework for human motion analysis, throughout an interface designed under a Model-View-Controller (MVC) architecture [2]. The communication between the client and the server is based on the HyperText Transfer Protocol (HTTP) and the WebSocket standard. HTML5 is the base technology, which controls the overall layout of the front-end (user interface). Together with this technology we used Impress.js, which controls the style and layout of the web page. For a high-performance back-end, we used the Python programming language, which was responsible for the connection between the user interface and the tools of the OpenSim software (Scale and IK), as well as all the data processing. Usability and learnability assessment was assessed using the System Usability Scale [3]. The target audience for this study was chosen from two groups, which are representative of the potential end-user populations: a) Biomedical engineering students; b) Clinicians and students of physiotherapy. None of the groups had previous knowledge with the system, and before the experience, the individuals of the each groups had a 4 minutes explanation on the interface of the features and way of using. Preliminary results shown usability scores comprised between 74,2 and 84,4 respectively for groups a) and b), and learnability scores of 67,9 and 78,6 respectively for groups a) and b). With the proposed framework the users can simply upload the patient's clinical information, determine how the selected musculoskeletal model anthropometry should be modified so it best matches patients characteristics, and to what degree each model's segment (markers) should match the collected motion data during the inverse kinematics process. Finally a report is generated, where it is possible to observe a given variable, a group of variables compare, experimental and normative data, and also add comments, print, and save it in PDF. From SUS results we conclude that the interface was extremely useful, clear, and easy-to-use and learn for both groups. Also, the users are likely to recommend our framework to other.	Web framework;Human motion;Database	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7088815	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Research on Personnel Safety Risk Early Warning Technology Based on Power Infrastructure Samples	10.1109 /ICEACE60673. 2023.10442715	In response to the problems of dispersed professional knowledge, complex management system, and complex business processes in the infrastructure business control of State Grid Corporation, this article proposes a personnel safety risk warning technology based on power infrastructure samples. Firstly, preprocess the scattered infrastructure business data to form a high-quality infrastructure sample library; Next, based on the sample library, a safety risk knowledge graph for infrastructure personnel is constructed based on dynamic graphs; Finally, based on the constructed safety risk knowledge graph of infrastructure personnel, the PinSage model and DynGCN model are combined to capture the spatial structure features and time series features of the dynamic graph. The model is trained through comparative learning, and knowledge inference technology is used to predict the risk information of construction personnel, achieving rapid identification and warning of typical risk sections, providing intelligent auxiliary decision-making for the assessment of personnel behavior and facility status risks on the infrastructure site.	knowledge reasoning; infrastructure;safety risk warning	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10442715	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
AI-driven methodology for refining and clustering Agile requirements	10.1109 /IRASET60544. 2024.10548285	Refining the backlog is crucial in the Agile development process for prioritizing work, detecting and resolving problems quickly, and aligning development efforts with project objectives. With automated tools for refining and structuring the backlog, teams can operate more efficiently with a clear understanding of product requirements. In this paper, we present our automated approach for conducting requirements analysis within the Agile Methodology. This method includes the refinement of backlogs through the identification of duplicate user stories and their subsequent clustering. Our method is based on machine learning and natural language processing techniques. To implement our approach, we developed a web-based tool that selects the user stories file, groups them by actor, and applies the unsupervised k-means algorithm to create clusters. We then used word embedding with sentence transformers of BERT to evaluate the similarity rate between each pair of user stories in a cluster. The tool highlights the most similar user stories and facilitates the decision to delete or keep them. The proposed approach was evaluated on a set of case studies using different performance measures. The results demonstrated the effectiveness of our method in detecting duplicate user stories in the backlog.	Artificial intelligence;NLP; Agile methodology	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10548285	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Energy Efficiency Maximization for Secure Live Video Streaming in UAV Wireless Networks	10.1109 /VTC2024-Spring62846. 2024.10683409	Unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) have shown great potential in live video streaming applications, especially in surveillance and reconnaissance. However, ensuring high quality of service (QoS) remains a challenge due to the dynamic nature of wireless channels. In this paper, we tackle the crucial challenge of energy-efficient and secure UAV-enabled live video streaming. To maximize long-term energy efficiency, we propose a cross-layer optimization framework that coordinates the adjustment of video coding parameters, wireless resource allocation, and UAV trajectory planning. We formulate the joint optimization as a constrained Markov decision process (CMDP) to capture the complex interdependencies between video quality, energy usage, and security risks. We introduce a new performance metric that captures the trade-off between video quality and energy consumption. The core of our method is a customized first-order constrained policy optimization, which efficiently handle complex real-world constraints like UAV battery capacities and end-to-end transmission delays. Our approach achieves scalability and sample efficiency with minimal gradient information. Through extensive system modeling and simulations under various network conditions, we validate the effectiveness of the proposed method compared with existing reinforcement learning algorithms.	secure UAV video streaming; safe reinforcement learning; constrained Markov decision process;energy efficiency maximization	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10683409	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
A Fast No-Reference Screen Content Image Quality Prediction Using Convolutional Neural Networks	10.1109 /ICMEW. 2018.8551572	Image quality assessment (IQA) is an inherent research topic in image processing field for several decades. Recently, machine learning has achieved success in many multimedia tasks and can be applied in IQA. Especially, screen content images (SCIs) is greatly increasing in various applications, but the characteristics of SCIs makes it difficult to directly apply general IQA methods to predict qualities. In this paper, we propose a fast no-reference SCIs quality prediction method. First, we use the convolutional neural networks (CNNs) to predict the quality scores of each patch. Second, we present a SCIs-oriented quality aggregation algorithm for acceleration. Experimental results demonstrate that our method can achieve the high accuracy (0.957) with subjective quality scores, outperforming existing methods. Moreover, our method is computationally appealing, achieving flexible complexity performance by selecting different groups of patches.	No-reference Image Quality Assessment;Convolutional Neural Networks;Screen content images	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8551572	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Application of Success Factor Model for Green Highway Projects in Malaysia	10.1109 /ICSGRC49013. 2020.9232572	Green highway is a management concept of an expressway project during the planning, design and construction stages. This concept combines transportation and ecological sustainability which is the backbone of the transportation system, ecosystem, municipal well-being and town development. The implementation of green highway in an expressway design is a critical initiative towards the achievement of Sustainable Development Goal (SDGs). The Malaysia Green Highway Index (MyGHI) manual was introduced to support the green highway in the Malaysian context. However, MyGHI is relatively new to such endeavors and a mechanism to measure a successful green highway is still lacking. The purpose of this study is to provide an integral knowledge on the factors influencing green highway implementation and determine the level of importance for each factor. Model constructs were introduced and established from the literature concept and theory as well as from exploratory data using the qualitative approach. Transcribed interview data analysis was analysed using Nvivo, Microsoft Excel and Critically Index assessment. It was found that three factors that affect the success of green highway are innovation; construction activities; and material and resources. Twelve experts from government and private agencies participated in contributing to factors and perspectives towards multiple theories and concepts to produce the green highway model. Hence, the idea of developing a model for a green highway is valid and justified, but is limited to the expressway in the Malaysian context.	Green Highway;Success Factor Model;Malaysia; Expressway Project;Nvivo	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9232572	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Value-Mapping IT Platform Options in Global Health: A Multi-year Case of Code Rot versus the Event-Driven Outbreak Economy	10.1109/HICSS. 2016.384	This multi-year action research case study examines a global public health organization's efforts at innovation enabled by investments into an open source online IT platform. The case illustrates a core managerial challenge of balancing the tension between on-going maintenance and event-driven investments in an organization with few technology human resources internally. Using Fichman's (2004) framework for assessing real options of IT platform assessments, we identify the specific sources of value from such an investment in this organization, drawing out research and practice implications.	online collaboration community development; case study;action research; options value mapping	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7427567	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es
Intelligent integrated coking flue gas indices prediction	10.1109/SNPD. 2017.8022698	Focus on the first China domestic coking flue gas desulfurization and denitration integrated device, in order to solve the problem that the entrance parameters fluctuate and a detection lag exists due to the upstream coking workshop, which is extremely unfavorable to the optimal control of desulfurization and denitration process. An intelligent integrated prediction model of flue gas SO2 concentration, O2 content and NOx concentration was proposed: the mechanism models of SO2, NOx concentration and O2 content were established according to the principle of material balance and reaction kinetics, respectively. For the prediction error, raw data was pretreated and the auxiliary variables were determined by principal component analysis, in order to improve the training speed and generalization ability of neural network, an improved RBFNN combining optimal stopping principle and dual momentum adaptive learning rate was proposed and used to compensate the error. Based on the practical data of two 55-hole and 6-meter top charging coke ovens in the coking group, the effectiveness and superiority of proposed model and method were verified by simulation via comparison of various models.	coking flue gas;mechanism model;neural networks; integrated modeling	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8022698	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Smart Contract Vulnerabilities and Detection Methods: A Survey	10.1109 /ICCCNT61001. 2024.10724246	Smart contracts are fundamental to blockchain technology, enabling automated contract execution without intermediaries. Their widespread adoption, particularly on platforms like Ethereum, has led to significant digital asset holdings. However, the immutability of blockchain magnifies the impact of even minor errors during smart contract development, potentially resulting in substantial financial losses. Given the frequency of vulnerabilities in existing contracts, secure smart contract development is essential. This paper conducts a comprehensive review of known vulnerabilities and detection methods to guide a more secure approach to smart contract development and promote safer blockchain ecosystems.	Blockchain;Smart Contracts; Vulnerabilities	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10724246	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Overview of microwave medical applications in Europe since the beginning of the COST action TD1301 — MiMed	10.23919 /EuCAP. 2017.7928067	In the last twenty years, Microwave Imaging (MWI) has emerged as one of the most promising novel medical imaging modalities. With European researchers being at the forefront of MWI development of medical applications, the creation in 2013 of the Action network "MiMed" (Microwave MEDical) in the framework of the European cooperation in Science and Technology (COST) was welcomed with vivid enthusiasm. MiMed has polarised mostly independent research efforts into the design of several MWI devices. Such a reserve of knowledge and numerous initiatives carried by MiMed have constituted a unique opportunity for researchers to leverage existing experience and expertise to streamline the transition from simulation/phantom testing to full clinical trials and clinical adoption of MWI devices. Moreover, collaboration among participants has provided the support to overcome common challenges and bring MWI from "research bench to patient bedside", boosting the European Research Area and its excellence in a worldwide context.	medical microwave imaging; microwave thermotherapy; COST Action;research network	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7928067	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es

Predictive Analysis of Zero-Day Vulnerabilities Using Deep Neural Networks	10.1109 /ICTBIG59752. 2023.10456046	Staying one step ahead of developing threats to national security requires rapid innovation in predictive analytic approaches. This is because it is projected that the complexity of cyberthreats will continue to rise in the coming years. This paper provides a unique technique for zero-day vulnerability prediction analysis using deep neural networks (DNN). This approach was developed thanks to the characteristics of DNN. The use of historical data on anticipated weak points is at the core of our method, which was developed with the goal of providing a proactive reaction to the issues presented by elusive threats. This strategy's major purpose was to provide a proactive reaction. The recommended technique provides an all-encompassing approach and is made up of three reliable components. Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) are used for feature extraction, LSTM networks for temporal analysis, and Random Forests, or RFs, for group learning. This method, which draws on a wide variety of academic fields, provides for a complete and trustworthy prognostic analysis. These parameters include, in addition to accuracy and precision, false positive rate (FPR), mean time to detection (MTTD), area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC), recall, and F1 score.	Convolutional Neural Networks; Ensemble Learning; Feature Extraction; LSTM; Temporal Analysis; Vulnerability Data	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10456046	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es
KEWS: A KPIs-Based Evaluation Framework of Workload Simulation On Microservice System	10.1109 /CSCWD61410. 2024.10580478	Simulating the workload is an essential procedure in microservice systems as it helps augment realistic workloads whilst safeguarding user privacy. The efficacy of such simulation depends on its dynamic assessment. The straightforward and most efficient approach to this is comparing the original workload with the simulated one using Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), which capture the state of the system. Nonetheless, due to the extensive volume and complexity of KPIs, fully evaluating them is not feasible, and measuring their similarity poses a significant challenge. This paper introduces a similarity metric algorithm for KPIs, the Extended Shape-Based Distance (ESBD), which gauges similarity in both shape and intensity. Additionally, we propose a KPI-based Evaluation Framework for Workload Simulations (KEWS), comprising three modules: preprocessing, compression, and evaluation. These methodologies effectively counteract the adverse effects of KPIs' characteristics and offer a holistic evaluation. Experimental results substantiate the effectiveness of both ESBD and KEWS.	workload simulation; key performance indicators; microservice system; similarity metric	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10580478	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	se colab
Enabling simheuristics through designs for tens of variables: Costing models and online availability	10.1109/WSC. 2014.7020034	Experiments are key to characterize, model and optimize engineering systems. The use of computer models and hence computer simulations, have allowed engineers to predict the effect of dozen and sometimes hundreds of variables at a specific time in a particular system. The combinatorial explosion that results from using classical techniques to generate experimental designs, however, has hampered such capability. Many analysis tasks, such as simulation optimization and simheuristics, will be importantly enhanced with the possibility of dealing with dozens of variables at a time in a convenient manner. In previous work we identified a series strategies to this end. The objective of the present study is to propose a costing approach to compare these strategies. In addition, designs for 10, 20 or 50 variables and their assessment are made readily available online to different users interested in simulation-optimization based on experimental design, as illustrated here with 50 variables.	Software; Computational modeling; Algorithm design and analysis; Optimization; Costing; Computers; Vectors	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7020034	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Work Posture Analyses for Ergonomics Working Condition Improvement of Concrete Work Practices	10.1109 /ICAST1. 2018.8751572	The aimed of the research is to improve the working condition of concrete work practices at Politeknik Negeri Bali Indonesia. Occupational accidents in concrete construction in Indonesia have recently increased and the cause is always claimed as human error. This is true, but behind human error, there is another root cause, which is the awkward posture causes by the unsafe working condition. This research was conducted at the concrete workshop, Civil Engineering Department Politeknik Negeri Bali. As the vocational higher education, it is important to build a healthy and safe work culture for students as prospective construction industry practitioners that expected to contribute in creating healthy and safe working conditions, so that work accidents can be avoided. This stage of research focused on the analyzing of the work body posture as a basis of recommendation in creating healthy, safe, comfortable and productive working conditions. The work body posture assessment was based on the principal of RULA Software. The body posture analyses were divided into two groups, group A (arm and wrist postures analyses) and group B (neck, body, and leg postures analyses). The study found out that the most awkward postures in concrete work practices were during concrete steel reinforcement fabrication, concrete mixing, and pouring concrete. RULA analyses showed that all of the work body postures were in the high-risk category with the grand score more than 6. In conclusion, the work condition needs improvement immediately, and it is recommended to create the ergonomics working conditions by harmonizing the man-tools or man-machine interaction.	Work posture; ergonomics; working condition; concrete work	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8751572	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Xorbits: Automating Operator Tiling for Distributed Data Science	10.1109 /ICDE60146. 2024.00392	Data science pipelines commonly utilize dataframe and array operations for tasks such as data preprocessing, analysis, and machine learning. The most popular tools for these tasks are pandas and NumPy. However, these tools are limited to executing on a single node, making them unsuitable for processing large-scale data. Several systems have attempted to distribute data science applications to clusters while maintaining interfaces similar to single-node libraries, enabling data scientists to scale their workloads without significant effort. However, existing systems often struggle with processing large datasets due to Out-of-Memory (OOM) problems caused by poor data partitioning. To overcome these challenges, we develop Xorbits, a high-performance, scalable data science framework specifically designed to distribute data science workloads across clusters while retaining familiar APIs. The key differentiator of Xorbits is its ability to dynamically switch between graph construction and graph execution. Xorbits has been successfully deployed in production environments with up to 5k CPU cores. Its applications span various domains, including user behavior analysis and recommendation systems in the e-commerce sector, as well as credit assessment and risk management in the finance industry. Users can easily scale their data science workloads by simply changing the import line of their pandas and NumPy code. Our experiments demonstrate that Xorbits can effectively process very large datasets without encountering OOM or data-skewing problems. Over the fastest state-of-the-art solutions, Xorbits achieves an impressive $2.66 \times$ speedup on average. In terms of API coverage, Xorbits attains a compatibility rate of 96.7%, surpassing the fastest framework by an impressive margin of 60 percentage points. Xorbits is available at https://github.com/xorbital/xorbits .	scalable data science; dataframe;array;tiling; computation graph	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10597861	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Computer-Assisted Qualitative Data Analysis in the Healthcare Cold Chain	10.1109 /RI2C60382. 2023.10355970	Healthcare Cold Chain (HCC) involves a number of health-related stakeholders, in which procedures are needed to ensure the proper storage and distribution of health services and medical products at recommended temperatures to maintain their potency. In this study, we conduct the qualitative analysis for key issues and concerns in the HCC by using computer-assisted qualitative analysis tool called Atlas.ti program. Data are initially collected from 332 samples based on seven groups of HCC stakeholders in Thailand and then later analyzed using the content analysis by evaluating key themes of issues and concerns in the HCC. Our analysis using the Sankey diagram shows that key concerns can be classified and categorized to 9 group codes, where the top three ranks are 1) knowledge and training for key involved staffs, 2) an effectiveness of temperature control in the chain, and 3) equipment as well as storage resource, respectively. Finally, characteristics of concerns are examined for each type of stakeholders to obtain key insights in the study.	Health care Cold Chain; Qualitative Data Analysis; Atlas.ti;Mixed-Method Research	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10355970	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Focus on the Stability of Large Systems: Toward Automatic Prediction and Analysis of Vulnerability Threat Intelligence	10.1109 /DSC53577. 2021.00070	With the increase in the number of users and business volume, the business systems of Internet companies are becoming more and more complex, resulting in a surge in the number of alarms. A large number of dirty alarms add a huge workload to security operations, which indirectly pose a large number of threats to business systems. At present, most systems use the method of accessing third-party Threat Intelligence to assist operators to realize automatic handling of alarms. However, this method has lagging and accuracy problems, making this work always difficult to meet the requirements of fast and accurate. This article proposes a new method for gathering vulnerability Threat Intelligence, which can obtain vulnerability information in advance of security announcements issued by security vendors. By analyzing the vulnerability disclosure process, this method obtains vulnerability information from the original source submitted by open source mail group, of developers. We used NLP technology and XGBoost model to automatically analyze the vulnerability information, and finally generate FINTEL. The experimental result shows that this method has an accuracy of 93%, and can obtain vulnerability information 10h to 7 days before security vendors release. The scope of application covers all open source code repositories and some closed source repositories.	Machine learning algorithms; Scalability;Prediction methods;Stability analysis; Security;Surges;Research and development	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9750473	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

RUNNER: Responsible UNfair NEuron Repair for Enhancing Deep Neural Network Fairness	10.1145/3597503.3623334	Deep Neural Networks (DNNs), an emerging software technology, have achieved impressive results in a variety of fields. However, the discriminatory behaviors towards certain groups (a.k.a. unfairness) of DNN models increasingly become a social concern, especially in high-stake applications such as loan approval and criminal risk assessment. Although there has been a number of works to improve model fairness, most of them adopt an adversary to either expand the model architecture or augment training data, which introduces excessive computational overhead. Recent work diagnoses responsible unfair neurons first and fixes them with selective retraining. Unfortunately, existing diagnosis process is time-consuming due to multi-step training sample analysis, and selective retraining may cause a performance bottleneck due to indirectly adjusting unfair neurons on biased samples. In this paper, we propose Responsible UNfair NEuron Repair (RUNNER) that improves existing works in three key aspects: (1) efficiency: we design the Importance-based Neuron Diagnosis that identifies responsible unfair neurons in one step with a novel importance criterion of neurons; (2) effectiveness: we design the Neuron Stabilizing Retraining by adding a loss term that measures the activation distance of responsible unfair neurons from different subgroups in all sources; (3) generalization: we investigate the effectiveness on both structured tabular data and large-scale unstructured image data, which is often ignored in prior studies. Our extensive experiments across 5 datasets show that RUUNER can effectively and efficiently diagnose and repair the DNNs regarding unfairness. On average, our approach significantly reduces computing overhead from 341.7s to 29.65s, and achieves improved fairness up to 79.3%. Besides, RUNNER also keeps state-of-the-art results on the unstructured dataset.	Deep Learning Repair; Fairness; Model Interpretation	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10548361	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
El trabajo grupal en Matemática, su aporte al desarrollo de habilidades profesionales desde la perspectiva estudiantil	10.1109/ARGENCON.2016.7585308	Learning assessment of engineering programs is a central aspect to consider when trying to improve the training of the future engineer. A group of teachers of mathematics area started a study on the proposed assessment plan. The process of aligning the course's objectives with the desired professional profile, teaching and assessment strategies led us to incorporate as a general objective: "students should be able to work effectively in groups". This paper analyses the opinion from students of the Differential Equations course about the experience of working in groups, and the transcendence of this activity in their professional training.	Training; Silicon compounds; Instruments; Software; Silicon; Mathematics	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7585308	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Research and Application of Simulation Test Method for Precision Load Control System	10.1109/EI2.2018.8582041	Precision load control is an important part of UHV AC-DC grid system protection, and it can also be used as a precise switching device for distributed energy, micro-grid and other systems. Through the classification, grading and sub-regional management of load resources, the real-time precise control of the interrupted load of the classified users can be realized by the direct dispatching of the dispatching, which can avoid a large number of overall pull-off of the substation or the line, and reduce the social impact of the grid fault. At the lowest level, improve the defense capability of large power grids. In order to ensure the stability and reliability of the precision load control system, the Precision load control system needs to be fully verified before it is put into use. In this paper, a set of simulation test environment is developed for the characteristics of precise load control system devices and complex test systems. The test environment is based on the actual software and hardware architecture, for internal communication characteristics, research test methods, customized test case drivers, and simulation. Various operating conditions under full load operation, comprehensive verification and assessment of the functional performance of the precision load control system to ensure the stability and reliability of the precision load control system. The proposed simulation test method has certain reference significance for the simulation test of precise load control system and new energy safety and stability control system.	Precision load control; new energy; load control terminal; reliability	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8582041	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Online Joint Multi-Metric Adaptation From Frequent Sharing-Subset Mining for Person Re-Identification	10.1109 /CVPR42600. 2020.00298	Person Re-Identification (P-RID), as an instance-level recognition problem, still remains challenging in computer vision community. Many P-RID works aim to learn faithful and discriminative features/metrics from offline training data and directly use them for the unseen online testing data. However, their performance is largely limited due to the severe data shifting issue between training and testing data. Therefore, we propose an online joint multi-metric adaptation model to adapt the offline learned P-RID models for the online data by learning a series of metrics for all the sharing-subsets. Each sharing-subset is obtained from the proposed novel frequent sharing-subset mining module and contains a group of testing samples which share strong visual similarity relationships to each other. Unlike existing online P-RID methods, our model simultaneously takes both the sample-specific discriminant and the set-based visual similarity among testing samples into consideration so that the adapted multiple metrics can refine the discriminant of all the given testing samples jointly via a multi-kernel late fusion framework. Our proposed model is generally suitable to any offline learned P-RID baselines for online boosting, the performance improvement by our model is not only verified by extensive experiments on several widely-used P-RID benchmarks (CUHK03, Market1501, DukeMTMC-reID and MSMT17) and state-of-the-art P-RID baselines but also guaranteed by the provided in-depth theoretical analyses.	Testing;Measurement; Visualization;Adaptation models;Feature extraction; Data models;Training	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9156809	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Tools for Analysis of Treatment Dynamics and Outcomes for Personalized Medicine in Asthma	10.1109 /AICT59525. 2023.10313198	This paper introduces a methodology for tracking the dynamic changes in parameters related to asthma treatment. Leveraging extensive data gathered from clinical trials, blood analysis, and patient records, this study has developed sophisticated tools for visualizing and evaluating the treatment dynamics among afflicted patients, as well as appraising the effectiveness of the treatments administered. To manage and process the copious amounts of data, advanced software tools were devised, thereby enabling precise and insightful analyses. Utilizing state-of-the-art statistical models, discernible patterns and trends associated with asthma have been identified, contributing to a deeper comprehension of the dynamics of treatment response and efficacy assessment. Through a thorough examination of longitudinal patient data, intricate insights into treatment patterns, disease progression, and long-term outcomes have been uncovered. In summary, this paper conducts a comprehensive analysis of patient parameters, employing a multidimensional strategy that encompasses clinical trials, blood parameter evaluations, and patient-year data assessments. The innovative software tools, models, and data analysis techniques employed in this study facilitate a meticulous evaluation of treatment dynamics and eventual outcomes. The implications of these findings are invaluable for enhancing clinical practices and ultimately enhancing the quality of life for individuals grappling with asthma.	Asthma treatment; multidimensional approach; insightful analysis;statistical models;Recurrence Prediction	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10313198	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Satellite Communication Vulnerabilities and Threat Landscape	10.1109 /SILCON63976. 2024.10910765	Satellite communication (satcom) has become an integral part of modern society, providing essential services in various sectors such as military, aviation, maritime, and emergency response. Despite its importance, satcom systems remain vulnerable to numerous threats that could result in significant consequences. This paper examines the vulnerabilities and threat landscape associated with satellite communication. Several factors contribute to the susceptibility of satcom systems, including their reliance on radio frequency signals, which can be easily intercepted, jammed, or spoofed. Additionally, satcom equipment and infrastructure may lack adequate security features, making them easy targets for cybercriminals. Potential adversaries include state-sponsored actors, hackers, terrorists, and criminal organizations seeking financial gain or causing chaos. These groups have varying levels of motivation, resources, and expertise, enabling them to develop sophisticated attack methods. Some common satcom exploitation techniques include signal jamming, eavesdropping, hijacking, and cyberattacks targeting ground stations, satellites, or user terminals. The impact of satcom vulnerabilities varies depending on the sector but generally includes service disruptions, loss of sensitive information, safety risks, and economic losses. To address these challenges, it's crucial to implement robust security measures, such as encryption, authentication, network segmentation, regular software updates, and employee training. Furthermore, international cooperation and collaboration between public and private entities are necessary to ensure effective threat intelligence sharing and incident response.	Satellite Communication; Vulnerabilities;Eavesdropping;Cyberattacks; Exploitation Techniques; Signal Jam-ming	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10910765	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es

How to combine models? Principles and mechanisms to aggregate fuzzy cognitive maps	10.1109 /WSC60868. 2023.10408326	Fuzzy Cognitive Maps (FCMs) are graph-based simulation models commonly used to model complex systems. They are often built by participants and aggregated to compare the viewpoints of homogenous groups (e.g., anglers and ecologists) and increase the reliability of the FCM. However, the default approach for aggregation may propagate the errors of an individual participant, producing an aggregate FCM whose structure and simulation outcomes do not align with the system of interest. Alternative aggregation methods exist; however, there are no criteria to assess the quality of aggregation methods. We define nine desirable criteria for FCM aggregation algorithms and demonstrate how three existing aggregation procedures from social choice theory can aggregate FCMs and fulfill desirable criteria, enabling the assessment and comparison of FCM aggregation procedures to support modelers in selecting an aggregation algorithm. Moreover, we classify existing aggregation algorithms to provide structure to the growing body of aggregation approaches.	Biological system modeling; Aggregates;Fuzzy cognitive maps;Classification algorithms;Reliability; Complex systems	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10408326	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es
sEmoD: A Personalized Emotion Detection Using a Smart Holistic Embedded IoT System	10.1109 /COMPSAC. 2019.00125	Scientific mental health crisis analysis through smart Internet of Things (IoT) system is able to provide an overall assessment of personalized emotion state. With recent advancements in IoT technology, we developed an embedded smart IoT system (sEmoD) for emotion detection. We designed and implemented a wearable Cyber-Human System (CHS) with a low power Bluetooth communication module to collect Body Area Sensor's (BAS) data using a smartphone. This wearable IoT device is capable of collecting physiological data over an extended period of time. Experimentation and verification have been conducted on a group of test subjects with different test scenarios including a happy, depressed, stressed, and calm state of being. This study introduces the use of signal processing and machine learning techniques for sensor data analytics to detect a (potential) personalized mental health crisis. The proposed system, sEmoD, can distinguish between the different emotional crises events with a high degree of accuracy (~80%).	Emotion, Smart IoT, Heart variability, CHS, GSR, Affective Computing	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8754492	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Automation of Health Monitoring System for Elderly and COVID-19 Patients using IOT	10.1109 /ICT57861. 2023.10126306	The healthcare industry has been getting advanced scientifically and technologically through wireless-sensing devices. Automation of the healthcare system with the Internet of things has been implemented & attains accurate results. Due to the panic situation of COVID-19, this automation of health monitoring systems plays an important role in the medical sector. In this research work, an advanced IoT-based, fully automated health monitoring system has been implemented for elderly & COVID-19 patients. The proposed design is verified on the python 3.6.0 software tool. The Lack of early treatment may cause patients to get unexpected risk failure, including death. This research work monitors elderly & older COVID-19 patients monitorization remotely using IoT technologies, even in crucial conditions. Wearable IoT devices have saved healthcare workers time and effort, according to medical regulations. The following mechanism helps with early diagnosis, quarantine, and patient monitorization has been performed with 68% saving time. This investigation aims to keep physicians and researchers can be updated about elderly patients covid 19 health issues while protecting their safety and health. Temperature and pulse sensors are used to check primary patient information. If heart rate or body temperature exceeds a safe level, IOT warning devices can give an indication. The designed application has achieved a sensitivity of 98.53%, an accuracy of 98.63%, a throughput of 97.98%, and a monitoring rate of 98.21%. The employed application is very helpful to researchers and doctors for easy treatment & covid 19 prevention. The proposed IoT-based automated health monitoring application strives with present technology and better method.	Health monitoring;IoT;Covid 19;elder health assessment	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10126306	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es

Tactical Training Using Augmented Reality/Virtual Reality and Haptics	10.1109 /ICTACS62700. 2024.10840957	This study investigates the effects of these immersive technologies on military personnel's training efficacy, efficiency, and safety. Virtual reality (VR) immerses users in artificial surroundings, augmented reality (AR) superimposes digital data on the actual world, and haptics adds tactile input to improve realism. These technologies work together to create training simulations that are incredibly realistic, adaptable, and closely mimic real-world situations. Examples of these scenarios include military operations, emergency response protocols, and technical maintenance jobs. This research emphasizes the advantages of AR, VR, and haptics in military training, including higher information retention, improved skill learning, and enhanced preparation for operational difficulties. It does this by doing a thorough assessment of the available literature and case studies. By eliminating the need for live exercises and giving students practical experience in authentic settings, these immersive technologies provide a secure and affordable substitute for conventional training approaches. Furthermore, employees stationed in remote or inaccessible regions may receive training nearly anytime, anywhere, thanks to the scalability and mobility of AR and VR devices. In the future, this field of study will focus on developing increasingly complex simulation environments and on utilizing advances in machine learning and artificial intelligence to build intelligent and adaptable training systems. Furthermore, haptics, AR, and VR are being widely used by allied agencies and military groups, which has great potential for collaborative training platforms and more equitable access to excellent training materials. Incorporating immersive technology into tactical and technical training signifies a fundamental change in military readiness and education, with far-reaching effects on the 21st-century armed forces' efficacy and adaptability.	Immersive technologies; Augmented Reality;Virtual Reality;Mixed Reality; Training;Defense	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10840957	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
QoE Models for Online Video Streaming	10.1109/IUCC-CIT-DSCI-SmartCNS5518 1.2021.00020	With the rising popularity of video streaming services, Quality of Experience (QoE) acts as the crucial role in improving user's experience. Distinguished from Quality of Service (QoS), which mainly weigh the video streaming quality with network transmission performance, QoE focuses on the subjective and user-oriented assessment when users views the videos online. It is a vital issue for online streaming to ensure a user-satisfied transmission under dynamic network. This highlights the need for an accurate and feasible QoE model to balance the user experience and available transmission bandwidth. This paper summaries and analyzes existing explorations on QoE models for online video streaming, especially with the advancement on emerged learning-based models, to promote the development of this research field.	Analytical models; Computational modeling; Quality of service;Bandwidth; Streaming media;Ubiquitous computing;User experience	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=9719656	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Development of Consistent Followup and Analysis of Level of Cancer Detection Using Wearables With AI Technology	10.1109 /IC2PCT60090. 2024.10486658	Machine reading-based totally wearable 's have recently emerged as a promising approach to useful resources at the early level of most cancer detection in smart healthcare environments. However, the demanding situations springing up from the higher danger and sensitivity associated with most cancer detection have taken a toll on the improvement of these technologies. This research undertakes a sensitivity evaluation of machine studying-based totally definitely wearable's for early-degree cancer detection in clever healthcare environments. By inspecting the behavioral and predictive talents of such technologies, the research pastimes shed light on their efficacy in helping the early detection of most cancers and other cardiovascular-related illnesses. The sensitivity evaluation of this has a look at awareness of extracting meaningful styles from the affected person's baseline fitness records gathered through using devices and getting to know-based absolutely wearable's with the aid of computational modeling and information mining strategies. Numerous experiments were accomplished to assess competencies, which include individual engagement, predictive accuracy, and scalability of techniques hired in such eventualities. Effects of these experiments were grouped into classes based totally on the type of algorithms, i.e., supervised and unsupervised, and in addition, evaluated to highlight the most promising techniques for early-diploma cancer detection. Eventually, insights from the results were used to suggest a comprehensive sensitivity analysis framework that may be applied for overall performance optimization in diverse future healthcare programs.	Promising;Meaningful; Maximum;Environments; Detection;Experiments; Sensitivity;Performed	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=10486658	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Analysis, Design, and Implementation of an Autopilot for Unmanned Aircraft - UAV's Based on Fuzzy Logic	10.1109/APCASE.2015.42	The UAV (Unmanned Aerial Vehicles) they have demonstrated their enormous capabilities in military and civilian applications in recent years. They have become an indispensable tool in the field of defense, security and support for the development of a nation. Similarly, the technological development has allowed these aircraft to fly autonomously thanks to electronic control systems called autopilots. The functional architecture of the autopilot which has been presented in this paper bases its operation on fuzzy logic for complete control of the aircraft, in stability, altitude, course, direction and acceleration using the minimum possible controls, reducing the computational processing. The system presented is tested through multiple flight hours in different climatic conditions, the results are satisfactory and the system shows to be really promising. Both the hardware and software of the proposed control system are the result of teamwork of Ecuadorian researchers.	autopilot;UAV;fuzzy control; autonomous flight;fuzzy logic","Aircraft;Aircraft navigation;Aerospace control;Fuzzy logic;Sensors; Trajectory;Process control	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=7287019	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Development of a microgrid protection laboratory experiment for the study of overcurrent and undervoltage functions	10.1109/CHILECON.2017.8229640	Today, power systems face new challenges in different fields, such as economic, social, environmental and technical. In the technical field, a number of issues related to protection systems are recognized, due to the inclusion of distributed generation and microgrids, among other aspects. This paper presents a novel laboratory experience aimed at university students, with the objective of understanding the operation and limitations that traditional protection systems face today. This is part of the learning process of the Micro-grid and Distributed Generation course, of the Department of Electrical Engineering, University of Chile, where the requirement of complementing the class of electrical protections with a laboratory experience was detected. In this paper, the methodology for the design of the experience, including all its stages, is presented. A practical application to a group of students was included as part of the pre-assessment, with a view to including improvements to the laboratory guide. During the evaluation it was possible to verify the degree of difficulty that the students had, assess their performance, and receive comments after their completion. With all the information gathered, improvements for future instances of the experience in the coming semesters are proposed.	Distributed power generation; microgrids;laboratories; power system protection; relays	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8229640	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Increasing Self-Compassion in Young People through Virtual Reality	10.1109/ISMAR-Adjunct.2019.00042	Mental health conditions pose a major challenge to healthcare providers and society at large. According to the Mental Health Foundation of New Zealand, one in five people will develop a serious mood disorder, including depression, at some time in their life [2]. Early intervention can have significant positive impact on a person's prognosis, particularly important in affecting outcomes for young people [38]. Co-designed solutions to improve resilience and well-being in young people have specifically been recognised as part of the National Suicide Prevention Strategy and the New Zealand Health Strategy. Innovative interventions that support long-term change for individuals are urgently needed [10]. Self-compassion/self-criticism constitutes a protective/risk factor with regard to developing and maintaining depression [3]; particularly in young people [4]. Self-criticism is one of the major psychological factors, defined as dominant response style of negative evaluation and judgement of self to perceived failure [5]. One effective method to increase self-compassion and reduction in depression may be to address self-criticism through compassion-focused therapy [6]. Virtual Reality (VR) in Health is an emerging field. It is becoming more commonplace with the advent of affordable consumer head mounted devices, and has significant potential for the understanding, assessment and treatment of mental health problems [7]. It can provide a non-threatening, zero risk environment which allows for free exploring of different strategies [16]. We propose to take this new technology and co-design Virtual Reality scenarios with young people, which focuses on real world situations that impact the sample group most and assists them to view these experiences with a self-compassionate lens. This is achieved by being taught compassionate manners of responding to a scenario and by switching perspective. We provide an overview of an initial proof-of-concept study, propose a study in different social settings and highlight key points for discussion pertaining to technology use, data safety, privacy, and considerations for addressing depressive symptoms necessary to advance this work.	virtual reality, mental health, self compassion	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?arnumber=8951911	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Educator Experiences of Low Overhead Student Project Risk Management	10.1145/3636243.3636250	Many software-related courses at tertiary level incorporate group projects in their assessment strategy. Project goals vary according to course learning outcomes, for example, consolidating course content and preparing students for industry by providing experience in teamwork. Studies have shown that many teams experience issues that are detrimental to project goals. In this paper, we explore the use of a risk framework that has been created to support academic group projects. We invited instructors from the computer science (CS) and software engineering (SE) disciplines within our university to use the framework to support their group projects and to report on their experience. Instructors from eight courses used the framework to address different needs. Most educators found the risk framework useful but students were more indifferent or critical. An outcome of our experience is the recommendation that instructors need to ensure risk plans are implemented throughout the project and to assess risk-related activities. © 2024 Copyright held by the owner/author(s). Publication rights licensed to ACM.	computing education; software project management; student project risks; tertiary education	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85182935820&doi=10.1145%2F3636243.3636250&partnerID=40&md5=e1347f808d037906ed2984f04da16e0a	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Using Focus to Personalise Learning and Feedback in Software Engineering Education	10.1109/ICSE-SEET58685.2023.00033	Learning can be greatly enhanced by effective feedback. Traditional assessment approaches in higher education often result in feedback being used to justify marks awarded, which is often disregarded once the assessment is complete. In this paper, we explore the idea of incorporating a focus mechanism to connect feedback between assessment tasks and units, discuss how this can be applied to enhance software engineering education, and present results from several staff focus groups exploring the idea. The focus groups discussed the model, its application within software engineering units, and its limitations, with staff helping co-create the enhancements to the model through discussing experiences/sharing opinions/providing insights on assessment within their units. Results indicate that staff believe that the changes will benefit their teaching and highlighted several opportunities for this initiative to encourage students to have a more holistic view of their studies. The main challenges identified were staff workload and complexity for students which must be addressed in implementing this idea. © 2023 IEEE.	Assessment; Formative Feedback; Rubrics	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85171754917&doi=10.1109%2FICSE-SEET58685.2023.00033&partnerID=40&md5=641018da0ddaf2042ed9258d9a313485	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Engaging undergraduate students in a biomedical research project: A virtual collaboration across institutes under the pandemic environment	10.1109/FIE49875.2021.9637452	In this work-in-progress (innovative practices) paper, we introduced a biomedical engineering research project to students in our primarily undergraduate institute (PUI) where sources and research activities are limited. Here, we present the motivation, background, best practices, initial assessment, and future work. Through virtual collaboration with a research institute, the project helped engage students in research activity, broaden the current scope of our project-based pedagogy, and address the typical challenges in online learning. In this semester-long project, a group of seven students from two schools developed a highly coupled Simulink model that captured the behaviors of the human cardiovascular system. The model aimed to study the aging effect of the aorta on cardiac power and blood pressure. Regarding the project design, we introduced the concept from the software engineering, i.e., 'Agile Principle' and 'Minimal Viable Product'. Students started to develop a working model of one component (i.e., O2 and CO2 exchange model in the tissue) from the entire system. Through multiple iterations, the model was debugged, expanded, and polished. We recognized the critical role of communication in the virtual space. Besides routine team meetings on Zoom, we also mentored students with model debugging time through the Slack platform. Students developed their professional skills through weekly learning journals where ideas, reflection, confusion can be shared with faculty. The preliminary assessment indicates positive impacts, such as growth mindset, time management, and more career options. © 2021 IEEE.	Project-based Learning; Undergraduate Research; Virtual Space Collaboration	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85123829349&doi=10.1109%2FIE49875.2021.9637452&partnerID=40&md5=6fd532d4e2e2833cc41694592edba112	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem avaliar
Assessing a Multidisciplinary Group of Undergraduate Students Applying the Challenge Based Learning Methodology to Learn Mobile Development	10.1145/3422392.3422484	Assessment is an important part of the learning experience, because it helps to clarify what students regard as important, how they spend their time and how they come to see themselves as learners. Besides, assessing students using new learning methodologies, which avoid the idea of teachers as the center of knowledge and students as secondary actors, allow us to understand their advantages and disadvantages. Challenge Based Learning (CBL) is one of these proposals, created with the essential principles of which skills are expected to the 21st century. This paper presents an experience applying an assessment approach during one year to a multidisciplinary group of students, who learned how to develop mobile applications using CBL and came from different universities and courses. The main focus is to allow those students to learn to self-Assess them, understand their learning progress on ten technical topics, and share learned lessons from that experience. © 2020 ACM.	Challenge Based Learning; mobile development; multidisciplinary groups; self-Assessment	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85099352149&doi=10.1145%2F3422392.3422484&partnerID=40&md5=9d16b8d8e466f02c646cefbe93b73d58	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Metaheuristics and Software Engineering: Past, Present, and Future	10.1142/S0218194021500443	This work aims at giving an updated vision on the successful combination between Metaheuristics and Software Engineering (SE). Mostly during the 90s, varied groups of researchers dealing with search, optimization, and learning (SOL) met SE researchers, all of them looking for a quantified manner of modeling and solving problems in the software field. This paper will discuss on the construction, assessment, and exploitation tasks that help in making software programs a scientific object, subject to automatic study and control. We also want to show with several case studies how the quantification of software features and the automatic search for bugs can improve the software quality process, which eases compliance to ISO/IEEE standards. In short, we want to build intelligent automatic tools that will upgrade the quality of software products and services. Since we approach this new field as a cross-fertilization between two research domains, we then need to talk not only on metaheuristics for SE (well known by now), but also on SE for metaheuristics (not so well known nowadays). In summary, we will discuss here with three time horizons in mind: the old times [before the term search-based SE (SBSE) was used for this], the recent years on SBSE, and the many avenues for future research/development. A new body of knowledge in SOL and SE exists internationally, which is resulting in a new class of researchers able of building intelligent techniques for the benefit of software, that is, of modern societies. © 2021 World Scientific Publishing Company.	learning; metaheuristics; optimization; Search; software engineering	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85116619368&doi=10.1142%2fS0218194021500443&partnerID=40&md5=fe d8b318378429f470172c63a9aa7d55	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Asynchronous Inter-Class Project Collaboration Adaptation Method to Agile Practices in University Context	10.1016/j.procs.2024.11.084	Universities are increasingly incorporating Scrum, a popular Agile methodology, into software engineering programs. However, existing solutions (workshops, online tools) fall short in facilitating asynchronous collaboration, a critical challenge for geographically dispersed or busy student teams. This study addresses this gap by proposing an asynchronous inter-class collaboration tool as an adaptation approach to facilitate Scrum implementation in university projects. The tool mitigates common constraints like student time availability and fosters flexible collaboration by incorporating adaptive, constructivist, and collaborative learning principles with agile methodologies. An experiment was conducted with undergraduate students enrolled in software engineering and related courses at Mindanao State University Main. The students utilized the tool for inter-class projects. The tool, built upon a conceptual model for asynchronous Agile Scrum ceremonies, successfully promoted Scrum practices, particularly Sprint Planning. However, challenges related to internet connectivity and student motivation persisted. Interestingly, the tool generated a novel "Sprint Chart" that assessed team maturity in adapting Scrum practices. Valuable feedback was gathered through experiments administered to educators and students involved in the conducted sprint retrospective. The adaptation approach bridges the gap between academic and industry environments by enabling flexible collaboration and Scrum adaptation. It highlights the importance of coordination, commitment, and technological support in asynchronous settings. The inter-class collaboration approach enhances student experiences but requires addressing communication hurdles. The Sprint Chart offers a valuable assessment method for educators. Future research should explore applying the adaptation approach to various team sizes, agile methodologies, and assess long-term effectiveness. Standardized training in Agile methodologies is recommended. Addressing technological barriers and refining the tool's functionalities are crucial for wider implementation. © 2024 The Authors.	Agile Adoption; Agile in Education; Async Collab; Inter-Class Collab; Project Collab Tool; Scrum in Education	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85214986533&doi=10.1016%2fj.procs.2024.11.084&partnerID=40&md5=3f71aa094bedb26b3353ee0b68c78e63	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem avaliar

<p>Improving Teamwork in Software Engineering Projects in Higher Education</p>	<p>10.1109 /FIE58773. 2023.10343476</p>	<p>In computing science (CS) education, software programming and software engineering subjects are parts of core CS subjects where students learn various programming languages and software development life cycle (SDLC). With the aim of equipping students with the necessary project skills and experiences essential for workplaces, Institutes of Higher Learning (IHL) have increasingly adopted the educational practice of bringing real-world team-based projects in the curriculum. Such software projects commonly support the use of Agile process practices, which place more emphasis on communications and teamwork among students in a team, stakeholders and industry customers. This could be manageable for small scale projects where student teams are in their learning journey with active and continuous communications with customers, while developing the necessary cohesion within the team to facilitate incremental deliverables of their software products. However, teamwork remains a bottleneck that is difficult to be consistently realized among members in group projects. It is not easy to motivate and measure all team members working towards the common goals or complete project tasks on time. As such, this paper proposes the Weekly Team Assessment (WTA) framework to continuously encourage teamwork throughout the software project development duration. We also propose the settings of dedicated leadership and constructive feedback iteratively in the WTA framework. The proposed methods have been applied and evaluated through the experiments in two software engineering modules, Professional Software Development and Team Project, involving 50 sophomore CS students who are divided into control group and experimental group equally. Experiment results are analyzed and discussed in this paper. Positive outcomes are observed from the experiment where about 72% of participants appreciate the proposed methods in improving their teamwork in group projects. The degree of effectiveness of the proposed methods is further evaluated from three aspects in the experiment. © 2023 IEEE.</p>	<p>higher education; software development life cycle; software engineering education; team projects; Teamwork</p>	<p>https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85183018520&doi=10.1109%2FIE58773.2023.10343476&partnerID=40&md5=077b8e514d895772177c9f4f81479a8e</p>	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/></p>	<p>chance</p>
<p>Automotive software architectures: An introduction: Second edition</p>	<p>10.1007/978-3-030-65939-4</p>	<p>This book introduces the concept of software architecture as one of the cornerstones of software in modern cars. Following a historical overview of the evolution of software in modern cars and a discussion of the main challenges driving that evolution, Chapter 2 describes the main architectural styles of automotive software and their use in cars' software. Chapter 3 details this further by presenting two modern architectural styles, i.e. centralized and federated software architectures. In Chapter 4, readers will find a description of the software development processes used to develop software on the car manufacturers' side. Chapter 5 then introduces AUTOSAR - an important standard in automotive software. Chapter 6 goes beyond simple architecture and describes the detailed design process for automotive software using Simulink, helping readers to understand how detailed design links to high-level design. The new chapter 7 reports on how machine learning is exploited in automotive software e.g. for image recognition and how both on-board and off-board learning are applied. Next, Chapter 8 presents a method for assessing the quality of the architecture - ATAM (Architecture Trade-off Analysis Method) - and provides a sample assessment, while Chapter 9 presents an alternative way of assessing the architecture, namely by using quantitative measures and indicators. Subsequently Chapter 10 dives deeper into one of the specific properties discussed in Chapter 8 - safety - and details an important standard in that area, the ISO/IEC 26262 norm. Lastly, Chapter 11 presents a set of future trends that are currently emerging and have the potential to shape automotive software engineering in the coming years. This book explores the concept of software architecture for modern cars and is intended for both beginning and advanced software designers. It mainly aims at two different groups of audience - professionals working with automotive software who need to understand concepts related to automotive architectures, and students of software engineering or related fields who need to understand the specifics of automotive software to be able to construct cars or their components. Accordingly, the book also contains a wealth of real-world examples illustrating the concepts discussed and requires no prior background in the automotive domain. Compared to the first edition, besides the two new chapters 3 and 7 there are considerable updates in chapters 5 and 8 especially. © Springer Nature Switzerland AG 2021.</p>	<p>Application specific development environments; Automotive software engineering; Embedded and cyber-physical systems; Engineering applications; Software architectures; Software design</p>	<p>https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85136449558&doi=10.1007%2F978-3-030-65939-4&partnerID=40&md5=cd1a9f19ab7ab3c46257f528e9ba7f70</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/></p>	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>	<p>sem colab</p>

Unlocking inclusive education: A quality assessment of software design in applications for children with autism	10.1016/j.jss.2024.112164	Digital technologies are an essential resource for maximizing education opportunities, yet the COVID-19 pandemic has exposed learning inequities, particularly among underrepresented groups such as children with autism. In this study, we have evaluated the quality of a distinctive dataset of multiplatform software applications, encompassing both assistive and mainstream software, first-hand acquired from special education professionals and families of children with autism. Through a heuristic evaluation based on a system indicators, and an in-depth analysis, we aimed to (1) assess the quality and effectiveness of assistive technologies in supporting the education of children with autism; (2) determine the adaptability of mainstream applications to the unique educational needs of children with autism; and (3) explore the features and constraints of applications targeting children with ASD, categorized according to the needs they cover. The resulting quality ranking, organized by cognitive domains, provides insights into the engagement and effectiveness of applications supporting the learning of children with autism. Furthermore, the findings delineating the functionalities and limitations of these applications contribute to the identification of necessary software engineering best practices. These practices align with user-centered design principles and drive the development of accessible software, thereby fostering high-quality inclusive education for children with autism. © 2024 The Author(s)	Autism; Inclusive software; Quality assessment; Software engineering education	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85200806255&doi=10.1016%2fj.jss.2024.112164&partnerID=40&md5=4e9fc772a5ad83b08b3c9728616cbc59	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Factoring Expertise, Workload, and Turnover Into Code Review Recommendation	10.1109/TSE.2024.3366753	Developer turnover is inevitable on software projects and leads to knowledge loss, a reduction in productivity, and an increase in defects. Mitigation strategies to deal with turnover tend to disrupt and increase workloads for developers. In this work, we suggest that through code review recommendation we can distribute knowledge and mitigate turnover while more evenly distributing review workload. We conduct historical analyses to understand the natural concentration of review workload and the degree of knowledge spreading that is inherent in code review. Even though review workload is highly concentrated, we show that code review natural spreads knowledge thereby reducing the files at risk to turnover. Using simulation, we evaluate existing code review recommenders and develop novel recommenders to understand their impact on the level of expertise during review, the workload of reviewers, and the files at risk to turnover. Our simulations use seeded random replacement of reviewers to allow us to compare the reviewer recommenders without the confounding variation of different reviewers being replaced for each recommender. We find that prior work that assigns reviewers based on file ownership concentrates knowledge on a small group of core developers increasing the risk of knowledge loss from turnover. Recent work, WhoDo, that considers developer workload, assigns developers that are not sufficiently committed to the project and we see an increase in files at risk to turnover. We propose learning and retention aware review recommenders that when combined are effective at reducing the risk of turnover, but they unacceptably reduce the overall expertise during reviews. Combining recommenders, we develop the SofiaWL recommender that suggests experts with low active review workload when none of the files under review are known by only one developer. In contrast, when knowledge is concentrated on one developer, it sends the review to other reviewers to spread knowledge. For the projects we study, we are able to globally increase expertise during reviews, +3+3%, reduce workload concentration, -12-12%, and reduce the files at risk, -28-28%. We make our scripts and data available in our replication package [1]. Developers can optimize for a particular outcome measure based on the needs of their project, or use our GitHub bot to automatically balance the outcomes [2]. © 1976-2012 IEEE.	code ownership; Code review; expertise; knowledge distribution; recommenders; turnover; workload	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85186074295&doi=10.1109%2fTSE.2024.3366753&partnerID=40&md5=a042c44b1a6432f914238d1743ad01d3	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

TeamUp: Form Best Project Teams	10.1007/978-3-031-44668-9_29	Team formation is a critical task in many contexts such as business, sports, healthcare, research, education, and more. In the academic settings, students working in teams on group projects is proven to be a very effective learning methodology. Our software engineering course features a semester-long team project as the key component of this course. However, team assignments are complex and nontrivial tasks, necessitating a careful assessment of many different factors to ensure optimal performance of the team as well as individual participants' satisfaction. Usually a predefined set of questions are used to understand participant's capabilities and preferences, and teams are formed either manually or automatically based on the results of those questions. In this paper, we propose a generalized question definition by associating each question with three factors: multiple choice/multiple answer, similarity or diversity, and option valuation, in order to consider various types of factors, provide flexibility and capture each individual's characteristics. We then propose two team performance score functions that differentiate similarity questions from diversity questions and capture each of their team formation objectives. A heuristic team formation algorithm, TeamUp, is proposed, attempting to maximize the team performance as well as participants' preferences. Through the initial evaluation we show our proposed algorithm can perform well for different team size and type of questions. © ICST Institute for Computer Sciences, Social Informatics and Telecommunications Engineering 2023.	project-based learning; team formation; team project	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85175794179&doi=10.1007%2F978-3-031-44668-9_29&partnerID=40&md5=e7408a4e4deb0000d69cc27961dca550	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem avaliar
Strategies and Implications of Peer Assessment in Software Engineering Education	10.1109/FIE61694.2024.10892827	This Innovative Practice category full paper describes the strategy of peer evaluation approach. Effective team management is pivotal in the success of any collaborative project, particularly in the domain of learning Software Engineering or Professional Software Development courses. Peer evaluations are commonly used methods to motivate group-based learning. This paper addresses the significance of team management and peer evaluations in the context of two Computing Science (CS) courses offered: Professional Software Development (PSD) and Team Project (TP). The main contributions of this paper are to provide nuanced insights into the challenges and opportunities inherent in collaborative endeavors, emphasizing effective motivation, encouragement, and resolution strategies for tackling teamwork issues within group projects. This study scrutinizes the intricate dimensions of teamwork in Software Engineering education. A central aspect of the paper involves a comprehensive analysis of peer evaluation methodologies, intending to shed light on practical implications for educators and learners. The findings underscore the importance of leveraging these insights to cultivate a conducive learning environment, motivating students to actively participate in collaborative endeavors. The proposed peer evaluations approaches are presented as a combination of the existing quantitative assessment approach and newly qualitative feedback mechanisms. It incorporates these elements: weekly peer review, emotion rating & thoughts, release of feedback, and a centralized dashboard. In the study, 31 CS Sophomore students taking the CSC2101 - PSD and TP1 course participate to evaluation experiments, where positive results are obtained. The collective findings and evaluations contribute to the ongoing refinement of collaborative learning experiences within the dynamic landscape of Software Engineering education. © 2024 IEEE.	group-based software development; Peer evaluation; software engineering education; team project	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-105000789404&doi=10.1109%2FIE61694.2024.10892827&partnerID=40&md5=ce8d28fa05901f505234a135b525e97b	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Frequent, Timed Coding Tests for Training and Assessment of Full-Stack Web Development Skills: An Experience Report	10.1145/3408877.3432549	This experience report describes the use of frequent, timed coding tests in a project-intensive software engineering course in which students first learn full-stack web development using Ruby on Rails and then apply their skills in a team project. The goal of the skills tests was twofold: (1) to help motivate students to engage in distributed practice and, thus, gain adequate coding skills to be an effective team member during the team project and (2) to accurately assess whether students had acquired the requisite skills and, thereby, catch deficiencies early, while there was still time to address them. Regarding the first goal, although several students indicated that the tests motivated them to engage in substantial practice coding, it was ultimately inconclusive as to the extent of the tests' impact on students' distributed practice behavior and on their preparation for the project. Regarding the second goal, the skills testing approach was indeed considerably more effective than graded homework assignments for assessing coding skill and detecting struggling students early. Lessons learned from our experiences included that students had significant concerns about the strict time limit on the tests, that the tests caused a spike in mid-semester withdrawals from the course that disproportionately impacted students from underrepresented groups, and that detecting struggling students was one thing, but effectively helping them catch up was a whole other challenge. © 2021 ACM.	assessment; full-stack web development; mastery learning; skills testing; software engineering education	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85103339901&doi=10.1145%2F3408877.3432549&partnerID=40&md5=df12929f3bb10f6754050c1f5f3e0e92	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Project based learning methodology: An effective way of learning software engineering through database design and web technology project	10.16920/jeet/2021/v34i0/157182	<p>Nowadays, Project-based learning is an integral part of many professional courses in Engineering. Projectbased learning is a student-centric approach in which students learn about a course by working in groups to solve an open-ended real world problem. In our opinion, it takes students near to the real world at a very early stage. For students, it acts as a tool to learn concepts and principles, to adapt to the evolving ICT industrial requirements and challenges. The objective here is to convey our systematic teaching and learning method, based on Project- based learning, to effectively learn the principles and practices of Software Engineering. Also, it prepares students how to apply these theoretical concepts to solve the real world problems by working in a team. For more than 10 years we are conducting this activity very rigorously for Third Year Computer Engineering students. This activity incorporates applying theory of Software Engineering to develop experiential learning by developing a mini-project using Database and Web Technology. Our 7- point method for development of mini-project has continuous Assessment through critical reviews and presentations by students. We conducted survey for all batches and took their feedback to understand the role of Project Based Learning in their Professional Career. Feedback of these students helps us to update our methodology and/or course contents. Applying Database technology and getting acquainted with development of user interface is bit easy for students but applying the Software Development Life Cycle [3] learnt in Software Engineering is quite challenging. There are many skills they learn and acquire while developing mini-project like questions to be asked during field work, design strategy and analysis through modelling, teamwork[4], time management, communication skills and many more which takes them a step closer and works as a basic building block for their growth as a software professional. Our survey questionnaire gives insight of all and acts as a measuring tool. This paper addresses our 7-point method, design, our process of evaluation and challenges faced by the students and faculty during this process with the help of representative projects. © 2021, Rajarambapu Institute Of Technology. All rights reserved.</p>	Mini project; Project-based learning; Software engineering	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85099744550&doi=10.16920%2fjeet%2f2021%2fv34i0%2f157182&partnerID=40&md5=7303f87a0ce2203bacfe16474ab9a10c	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Deep learning-based method for prediction of software engineering project teamwork assessment in higher education		<p>One of the very recent applications of machine learning and deep learning is to predict student's performance for a specific task. Particularly in software engineering projects in higher educational institutions, one of the major challenges is how to improve the overall software team performance with the ultimate goal of increasing software team productivity. This problem can be termed as Software Engineering Teamwork Assessment and Prediction (SETAP). To address this, we proposed a SETAP method that uses an effective deep-learning-based method for assessment and early prediction of student learning effectiveness in software engineering teamwork. Further, we identified critical features by using feature importance, which affects the performance of the student's team. For the experimental purpose, we used the freely available dataset from the UCI data repository for student learning effectiveness in software engineering teamwork. In the proposed work, we used Feed-forward deep neural network classifier for this purpose. Deep neural networks can produce high accuracy with complex data very quickly. This made them a perfect choice for our work. To compare and evaluate the performance of the proposed prediction method with others (RF, GLM, GBM), we used accuracy percentage, sensitivity, and specificity as performance measuring benchmarks. Also, we evaluated the method on our university datasets. Results proved that the proposed method performed better than the above-mentioned state-of-the-art classifiers. © 2021 Little Lion Scientific.</p>	Deep learning; Software engineering; Stacking; Teamwork assessment	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85107071159&partnerID=40&md5=8ae8ea8722e116551a52957592072ffb	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	nao avalia

The Impact and Measurement of Today's Learning Technologies in Teaching Software Engineering Course Using Design-Based Learning and Project-Based Learning	10.1109/TE.2022.3169532	Contribution: This article demonstrates the impact of today's Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) in teaching software engineering (SE) course with design-based learning (DBL) and project-based learning (PBL). The results show a positive influence of integration of DBL and PBL in reducing industry gaps with improved student performance, engagement, and learning through designed PBL activities. Background: For an engineering graduate analysis, design, thinking, and validation of complex systems interactions is a desirable skill to support sustainability goals. A restructuring in delivery of the course through interactive lecture time and more project-based activities can improve students' engagement, performance, and overall achievement in attaining desirable program learning outcomes (LOs). Intended Outcome: The objective is to provide student learning with an experience on how to apply critical thinking and creativity to specify, design, and validate software systems by focusing on challenges faced in the software industry. Application Design: Google classroom was used to conduct interactive class and tutorial sessions, design various PBL activities, exchange information, and work in teams. Throughout the semester, all learning and practice modules of the course were linked sequentially with intermediate milestones. Findings: The results show a positive outcome in helping students in attaining the knowledge, and understanding of both theoretical and practical concepts. These findings are based on academic results, PBL activities, and two anonymous surveys. The findings of statistical analysis suggest a positive influence of DBL and PBL in SE course to meet industry challenges, expectations, and overall course and program LOs. © 1963-2012 IEEE.	Collaborative learning; design-based learning (DBL); instructional design; project-based learning (PBL); student assessment	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85129640400&doi=10.1109%2FTE.2022.3169532&partnerID=40&md5=ee5eb6ae94baabfc74a7a0268849da96	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem avaliar
WIP: Engaging Software Engineering Students in Synchronous and Asynchronous On-line Course		Many engineering educators regard experiential learning as the most effective way to train future generations of engineers. The authors have noticed higher levels of engagement when students participate in class activities than when they are simply listening to lectures. These activities may include games, discussions, group activities, and peer reviews. Covid19 restrictions forced a shift to the online delivery of all courses at our university this year. Often, activities developed for face-to-face delivery of software engineering topics cannot be used without modification in the online delivery of either synchronous or asynchronous courses. This paper describes the authors' experiences using active learning materials in an online software engineering course. Students taking this course were allowed to take it either synchronously or asynchronously. The project team critically examined existing active learning materials used for face-to-face delivery of the course and adapted them for online course delivery. The authors monitored the levels of student engagement in each group and surveyed individual students to measure their perceived level of engagement with course activities. Our initial assessment data suggest that students attending synchronous class meetings were slightly more engaged with the course materials than those who did not. Students interacting with the active learning course materials, whether synchronously or asynchronously, felt more engaged with the course than they would have with a traditional online lecture course. © American Society for Engineering Education, 2021		https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85124555537&partnerID=40&md5=e7e6d58910f85d068f6ef349288f57b0	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Software engineering teamwork data understanding using an embedded feature selection	10.23940/ijpe.21.05.p6.464472	Teamwork plays an essential role in determining the outcome of software engineering projects, especially when software is being developed by large teams in geographically distributed environments. To understand the successful development of these types of projects, it is important to assess the required teamwork skills that would help in resolving possible problems and avoiding failure. However, it is still not clear how to assess teamwork skills. In this paper, we propose an analytical framework based on a machine learning algorithm to study teamwork skills and factors that influence the success/failure of software engineering projects. For this purpose, we conduct our study on the Software Engineering Teamwork Assessment and Prediction (SETAP) dataset using a machine learning algorithm to extract the relevant features. The dataset provides quantitative data of team activity measures related to the software engineering process and the product at the different software development lifecycle phases. The results show that each of the software lifecycle phases requires different teamwork skills. The results demonstrate the efficiency of the approach; that has predicted team outcomes by accuracy score greater than 90% for process and product data. © 2021 Totem Publisher, Inc. All rights reserved.	Features selection; Gradient boosting; Machine learning; Software engineering; Teamwork	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85106633831&doi=10.23940%2Fijpe.21.05.p6.464472&partnerID=40&md5=25bf3e96a319f6a21461804a7b8a150d	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem avaliar

Sprint to Inclusion: Embedding Accessibility Sprint in a Software Engineering Course	10.1145/3641554.3701838	This experience report contributes to the expanding body of literature advocating for the inclusion of accessibility topics within core computing courses rather than restricting them to specialized electives such as human-computer interaction (HCI). We integrated an accessibility-focused sprint into a 3-credit software engineering course at a large private university in the US. Throughout the course, students progressively developed a software project in groups with a dedicated sprint designed to emphasize the importance of accessibility. This sprint included lectures on accessibility principles and hands-on accessibility testing on their own projects, followed by a sprint to fix the issues found. A survey was conducted at the end of the course to gauge their learning outcomes and perceptions of accessibility. The results demonstrate that integrating accessibility into a software engineering course not only enhances students' technical skills but also boosts their commitment to creating inclusive software. We present the accessibility interventions made, assessment instruments used and our findings in this report. We also offer key insights as takeaways for the computing education community, providing guidance for educators aiming to embed accessibility into their curriculum. © 2025 Copyright held by the owner/author(s).	Computing Education; Digital Accessibility; Project-based learning; Software Engineering	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-86000272335&doi=10.1145%2F3641554.3701838&partnerID=40&md5=5438f1c60b457f18f00f957dd16ce878	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Investigating Student Insight in Software Engineering Team Projects		Preparing software engineering students for industry jobs is a difficult task. Employers often ask for a combination of technical and soft skills. In this paper, we describe an exploratory study focused on 47 teams of 3rd year Computer Science students who were each involved in the development of a medium sized software application. We employed open coding on free-text student feedback and focused on key areas of working process, planning, challenges and lessons learned. We evaluated how student perception aligned with feedback received from mentors with industry experience, as well as with the assessment from teaching staff experienced in software engineering. We open-sourced a replication package that allows reusing, repeating or extending our investigation. We showed that the course objectives were reached, that soft skills remain an important component of team projects as well as identified several action points that can further improve education in software engineering. Copyright © 2021 by SCITEPRESS - Science and Technology Publications, Lda. All rights reserved	Empirical Study; Project; Soft Skills; Software Engineering Education; Teamwork	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85125228249&partnerID=40&md5=93ce0ed50f3e1da838ca11cb14b66d62	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem avaliar
Proceedings of the 30th European Conference on Systems, Software and Services Process Improvement, EuroSPI 2023		The proceedings contain 48 papers. The special focus in this conference is on Systems, Software and Services Process Improvement. The topics include: Trustful Model-Based Information Exchange in Collaborative Engineering; Boosting the EU-Wide Collaboration on Skills Agenda in the Automotive-Mobility Ecosystem; Automotive Data Management SPICE Assessment – Comparison of Process Assessment Models; corporate Memory – Fighting Rework with a Simple Principle and a Practical Implementation; managing Ethical Requirements Elicitation; process Improvement Based on Symptom Analysis; the New Cybersecurity Challenges and Demands for Automotive Organisations and Projects - An Insight View; an Open Software-Based Framework for Automotive Cybersecurity Testing; requirements Engineering for Cyber-Physical Products: Software Process Improvement for Intelligent Systems; A Low-Cost Environment for Teaching Fundamental Cybersecurity Concepts in CPS; gamified Focus Group for Empirical Research in Software Engineering: A Case Study; identification of the Personal Skills Using Games; identifying Key Factors to Distinguish Artificial and Human Avatars in the Metaverse: Insights from Software Practitioners; An Approach to the Instantiation of the EU AI Act: A Level of Done Derivation and a Case Study from the Automotive Domain; Investigating Sources and Effects of Bias in AI-Based Systems – Results from an MLR; quality Assurance in Low-Code Applications; towards User-Centric Design Guidelines for PaaS Systems: The Case of Home Appliances; Supporting the Growth of Electric Vehicle Market Through the E-DRIVETOUR Educational Program; Sustained Enablement of AI Ethics in Industry; exploring Metaverse-Based Digital Governance of Gambia: Obstacles, Citizen Perspectives, and Key Factors for Success; preface; an Investigation of Green Software Engineering.		https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85172081217&partnerID=40&md5=385ad31a aac6e07353d1f3de5e9e1717	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Design and implementation of a mobile augmented reality simulator for physics teaching in higher education; [Diseño e implementación de un simulador basado en realidad aumentada móvil para la enseñanza de la física en la educación superior]	10.21556 /edutec. 2022.80.2509	The benefits attributed to augmented reality (AR) in the teaching of different fields of knowledge have led to the intersection of teaching and learning modalities and methods that seek to enhance the strengths of this technology applied to education. One of the approaches intertwines augmented reality with mobile learning and simulation-based learning activities. However, how to develop these applications in order to provide a learning experience is a line that continues to be built. In this article presents the development phases of a mobile augmented reality simulator, whose formulation is based on the experience of a student group using a web simulator. In addition, evaluation results of quality augmented reality objects are presented, obtaining a positive assessment in the technical aspects, use and guide, which suggests an adequate integration of augmented reality technology with the pedagogical aspects considered in the application design. © 2022 Authors. All rights reserved.	Mobile Augmented Reality; Physics Teaching; Simulator; Software Engineering	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85140368074&doi=10.21556%2fedutec.2022.80.2509&partnerID=40&md5=07841a28e495ef310e5d7c9d6872cade	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Socially Distant Active Learning and Student Engagement in Software Engineering Courses		Often, activities developed for face-to-face delivery of software engineering topics cannot be used without modification in the online delivery of course materials. Following Covid protocols in face-to-face classes also requires modification of active learning course materials. This paper describes the authors' experiences during the past three years using active learning materials in a face-to-face software engineering course with and without social distancing. As well as their experiences teaching both synchronous and asynchronous online versions of the same course. The project team critically examined existing active learning materials used for face-to-face delivery of the course and adapted them for use in online and socially distanced face-to-face course delivery during Fall 2021. The authors monitored the levels of student engagement in each group and surveyed individual students to measure their perceived levels of engagement with course activities. Our assessment data suggests that students attending face-to-face class meetings (with or without social distancing) felt more engaged with the active learning course materials than those taking the class online. Students interacting with the active learning course materials, whether face-to-face or through Zoom breakout rooms, felt more engaged with the course materials than they would have in a traditional online lecture course. Students receiving in-person instruction tended to have fewer missing assignments and provided higher course evaluations than students completing the course activities online. © American Society for Engineering Education, 2022.		https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85138275735&partnerID=40&md5=708fa1ea62425205dbee154c59644097	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Guide to teach Lean Startup methodology to software engineering students using a serious game	10.1109 /ENC53357. 2021.9534827	In the last decade, Lean Startup has become an emerging methodology for teaching entrepreneurship to Software Engineering and Computer Science students. However, for most students, it is difficult to understand the key concepts of this methodology and put them into practice successfully. An approach to solve this problem is the use of serious games as a support tool that foster positive attitudes such as motivation, engagement and participation leading to effective learning. Besides, simulating real-life situations within an academic environment still remains a challenge. This article proposes a guide as support to teachers that aims to teach Lean Startup methodology using a serious game. The guide provides a set of recommendations, best practices and re-sources that contribute to improve the understanding of the key concepts of Lean Startup. The guide was evaluated by a group of Lean Startup experts. The results confirm the usefulness of the guide and the positive effects on learning from the experts' perspective. © 2021 IEEE.	Lean Startup; Process improvement; Serious games; Serious games assessment; Software Engineering	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85116088684&doi=10.1109%2FENC53357.2021.9534827&partnerID=40&md5=e2e7874347031df933a6c04108b369e9	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Utilization of Information Entropy in Training and Evaluation of Students' Abstraction Performance and Algorithm Efficiency in Programming	10.1109/TE.2024.3354297	Contribution: This research illuminates information entropy's efficacy as a pivotal educational tool in programming, enabling the precise quantification of algorithmic complexity and student abstraction levels for solving P problems. This approach can provide students quantitative, comparative insights into the differences between optimal and student implemented solution, and allowing educators to offer targeted feedback, thereby optimizing the learning and abstraction processes in algorithm design through deliberate practice. Background: Abstraction is considered one of the most important skills in problem solving. Many studies in programming have shown that higher abstraction capability can significantly simplify problems, reduce program complexity and improve efficiency. However, it is difficult to develop criteria to measure the level of abstraction, and there is still a lack of relevant systematic research. Research Questions: 1) How can students' abstraction ability in programming be effectively measured? 2) How to develop programming education and training methods based on the measurement of abstraction ability? Methodology: Forty-six grade 10 students participated in the experiment, divided into two groups for programming training using information-entropy-based assessment and traditional learning methods. Their level of computational thinking, algorithmic efficiency improvements, and test scores were used to measure performance and to analyze the effectiveness of the training methods. Findings: Through empirical research, this article finds that information-entropy-based assessment can reflect the differences in problem solving among students possessing varying capabilities. Information entropy can be crucial for evaluating and improving students' abstraction performance and algorithm efficiency. © 1963-2012 IEEE.	Abstraction; complexity; information entropy; programming; software engineering (SE) education	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85184826042&doi=10.1109%2FTE.2024.3354297&partnerID=40&md5=045faa1f76c74481df9198dc022457b5	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Code Saga - A Mobile Serious Game for Learning Programming	10.1109/ITeS53735.2021.9628484	During this global pandemic of coronavirus, the amount of self-learning done by students has considerably increased. They cannot only rely on online classes to study as students easily lose interest in these online classes. A number of studies have shown that undergraduate students have problems grasping the introductory chapters of programming. If they cannot even understand the basics, then they might not be able to comprehend the more complex chapters. Tutors have to find a means to match their teaching methodology to the students' interest so that the latter can be as engaged as possible. This brought about a need to devise a new method of learning for IT-related undergraduate courses. It is a well-known fact that many students show a keen interest in video games. Using video games for teaching can be an interesting way to encourage self-learning of students. The concept of integrating gameplay with educational contents is known as serious games. In this paper, a mobile serious game, Code Saga, is being proposed. The primary aim of Code Saga is to smooth out the learning process of students opting for IT courses at undergraduate level. The game has been designed to cover key chapters on Programming based on the latest IEEE/ACM curriculum guidelines for undergraduate degree programs in Software Engineering. A combination of mixed gaming-approaches has been used to make the game as entertaining and educational as possible to the undergraduate students. The game includes fun assessment activities to assess the players' understanding on various programming concepts. The game also consists of a scoring mechanism, which a tutor can use to track students' strengths and weaknesses on specific topics. Code Saga has been tested by a group of students at the University of Mauritius and the results confirmed that most students prefer to learn programming using serious games compared to the traditional learning methods. © 2021 IEEE.	coding games; game based learning; learn programming; mobile serious game; undergraduate	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85123770518&doi=10.1109%2FItS53735.2021.9628484&partnerID=40&md5=29fa0ba7d044b8265ea29a492cc62719	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Tracking Representational Flexibility Development through Speech Data Mining	10.1109/FIE44824.2020.9273818	In this work-in-progress research we exploited and investigated a virtual reality (VR) based, flexibility learning environment (FLE) in which adolescents with autism use, customize, and design an assortment of simulation games that represent and exemplify the application of forces and Newton's laws of motion. The simulation/game modeling and making tasks acted as the primers of practicing and assessing representational flexibility in solving the engineering design problems with computational thinking. The participants' participation behaviors and verbal utterances during the intervention sessions have been archived via screen and webcam recordings. The current study findings indicated that two approaches of speech or text data mining, multi-label classification and similarity index, can act as the in-situ performance assessment methods to evaluate the representational flexibility development for engineering design and computational thinking of a heterogeneous learner group. © 2020 IEEE.	educational data mining; learning by making; representational flexibility; virtual reality	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85098595235&doi=10.1109%2FIE44824.2020.9273818&partnerID=40&md5=435dbbf61dc1c1a623dd592b3059d1e8	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

<p>An Equity-minded Assessment of Belonging among Computing Students</p>		<p>Creating a Computer Science and Software Engineering Department that supports students with diverse identities and backgrounds is essential to creating a computing workforce that reflects the world at large. Inspired by the work of Metcalfe et al.'s survey conducted at the University of Illinois [1], we use the same methods to examine the state of our computing department with respect to issues of inclusive climate and student sense of belonging, which have been shown to be important for retention in STEM fields [2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8]. We use the four areas that contribute to belonging based on the work of Rainey et al. [9] along with a fifth category of learning environment in order to assess our students' sense of belonging. This paper's main focus is based on results from two surveys of California Polytechnic State University students conducted exactly one year apart (2019: n = 154, 2020: n = 122). Both surveys were sent to all computing majors in Spring quarter, the last quarter of the regular academic year. We found that 58-68% of students felt they were not typical computer scientists, which mirrors the results of the survey conducted at the University of Illinois [1], indicating that the lack of belonging is perhaps a ubiquitous problem within the field of computing. Other salient results include identifying the presence of statistically significant differences for some groups based on gender and race & ethnicity. These differences were found when looking at students' senses of their science identity and learning environment. We also found that women had a significantly greater chance of having strong interpersonal relationships within computing. The survey results are augmented by a survey of first-quarter freshmen in Fall 2019 (n = 44) and student interviews conducted in Spring 2021 (n = 15). We hope that the addition of these results explain and expand upon our main results and add insight as to how the student experience can evolve from a student's first quarter onward. These differences shine an important light on some positive trends as well as several concerning differences to be examined in our quest to create a diverse and equitable department. © American Society for Engineering Education, 2022.</p>		<p>https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85138308090&partnerID=40&md5=72f8952013cc6d7ab052a4c9492032ad</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<p>sem colab</p>
<p>Comparative Case Study of Plan-Driven and Agile Approaches in Student Computing Projects</p>	<p>10.23919/SoftCOM50211.2020.9238196</p>	<p>Plan first, execute second' and 'Adapt to change as you iterate' are two paradigms that are well known in software development, as they represent disparate schools of project management: traditional and agile. Despite a long-lasting debate on prominence of each, little comparative research has been reported, particularly in the context of academic projects, where all too often a no-process approach still prevails. This paper presents an experiment that was carried out during the Spring semester of the 2018-2019 academic year at two engineering schools in Europe in order to assess the impacts of a given development method on the success of student computing undertakings. A structured, metric-based assessment scheme was applied to reveal patterns associated with the use of Plan-driven, Iterative and no-process approaches on product quality, team productivity and teamwork quality facets. © 2020 University of Split, FESB.</p>	<p>agile; capstone project; comparative study; education; software engineering; software process</p>	<p>https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85096534399&doi=10.23919%2fSoftCOM50211.2020.9238196&partnerID=40&md5=3ef50c75bd91ca5d6e465b164205b651</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<p>sen colab</p>
<p>Effectiveness of Peer Review in Teaching and Learning User Centered Conceptual Design among Large Cohorts of Information Technology Students</p>	<p>10.1109/ICSE-SEET52601.2021.00016</p>	<p>Conceptual design often sets the direction of the development of a product. Educating Software Engineering and Information Technology (IT) students to consider the needs of users during the conceptual design stage is important. The assessment of conceptual design is a time consuming process. When budgets are limited, financial resources are inadequately allocated to allow staff to spend quality time assessing the conceptual design artifacts of large classes. We present a methodology to teach, capture and evaluate conceptual design artifacts for large classes. In two separate studies, two groups of over 185 undergraduate IT students reviewed their peers' design artifacts using a comprehensive rubric. Their reviews were later checked by two researchers using the same rubric. It was found that not only were the student-peers' reviews close to the researchers' reviews, it was possible to give students valuable and timely feedback and scaffold them to reflect, an essential characteristic for professional competence. In addition, we found that assessment by staff was not feasible due to inadequate resources. We conclude that for large classes, conceptual design artifacts can be evaluated and valuable feedback provided in a timely manner by peers with the guidance of a comprehensive rubric. © 2021 IEEE.</p>	<p>conceptual design assessment; information technology education; peer review; persona; reflective practice; software engineering education</p>	<p>https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85115636743&doi=10.1109%2fICSE-SEET52601.2021.00016&partnerID=40&md5=03100a26ce53cdab58f420f1355040f9</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<p>sem colab</p>

<p>A Machine Learning Approach for Suggesting Feedback in Textual Exercises in Large Courses</p>	<p>10.1145/3430895.3460135</p>	<p>Open-ended textual exercises facilitate the comprehension of problem-solving skills. Students can learn from their mistakes when teachers provide individual feedback. However, courses with hundreds of students cause a heavy workload for teachers: providing individual feedback is mostly a manual, repetitive, and time-consuming activity. This paper presents CoFee, a machine learning approach designed to suggest computer-aided feedback in open-ended textual exercises. The approach uses topic modeling to split student answers into text segments and language embeddings to transform these segments. It then applies clustering to group the text segments by similarity so that the same feedback can be applied to all segments within the same cluster. We implemented this approach in a reference implementation called Athene and integrated it into Artemis. We used Athene to review 17 textual exercises in two large courses at the Technical University of Munich with 2,300 registered students and 53 teachers. On average, Athene suggested feedback for 26% of the submissions. Accordingly, 85% of these suggestions were accepted by the teachers, 5% were extended with a comment and then accepted, and 10% were changed. © 2021 ACM.</p>	<p>assessment support system; automatic assessment; education; feedback; grading; interactive learning; learning; software engineering</p>	<p>https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85108123395&doi=10.1145%2F3430895.3460135&partnerID=40&md5=891c562b926299496a9ccb5e2e24e2e</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/></p>	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>	<p>sem colab</p>
<p>FORMATIVE ASSESSMENT ACTIVITIES TO ADVANCE EDUCATION: A CASE STUDY</p>	<p>10.28945/4758</p>	<p>Aim/Purpose During the education of future engineers and experts in the field of computer science and information communication technology, the achievement of learning outcomes related to different levels of cognitive ability and knowledge dimensions can be a challenge. Background Teachers need to design an appropriate set of activities for students and combine theory-based knowledge acquisition with practical training in technical skills. Including various activities for formative assessment during the course can positively affect students' motivation for learning and ensure appropriate and timely feedback that will guide students in further learning. Methodology The aim of the research presented in this paper is to propose an approach for course delivery in the field of software engineering and to determine whether the use of the approach increases student's academic achievement. Using the proposed approach, the course Process Modeling for undergraduate students was redesigned and experimental study was conducted. Course results of the students (N=82) who took the new version of the course (experimental group) were compared to the results of the students from the control group (N=66). Contribution An approach for a blended learning course in the field of software engineering was developed. This approach is based on the formative assessment activities that promote collaboration and the use of digital tools. Newly designed activities are used to encourage a greater level of acquired theoretical content and enhance the acquisition of subject-specific skills needed for practical tasks. Findings The results showed that students who participated in the formative assessment activities achieved significantly better results. They had significantly higher scores in the main components of assessment compared to the students from the control group. In addition, students from the experimental group expressed positive views about the effectiveness of the used approach. Recommendations The proposed approach has potential to increase students' motivation and academic achievements so practitioners should consider to apply it in their own context. Recommendations Researchers are encouraged to conduct additional studies to explore the effectiveness of the approach with different courses and participants as well as to provide further insights regarding its applicability and acceptance by students. Impact on Society The paper provides an approach and an example of good practice that may be beneficial for the university teachers in the field of computer science, information-communication technology, and engineering. Future Research In the future, face-to-face activities will be adapted for performance in an online environment. Future work will also include a research on the possibilities of personalization of activities in accordance with the students' characteristics. © 2021. All Rights Reserved.</p>	<p>assessment; collaborative learning; course design; digital tools; process modeling</p>	<p>https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85108215095&doi=10.28945%2F4758&partnerID=40&md5=9c177ef1022614ce6278b749155d8621</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/></p>	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>	<p>sem es</p>

Software Defect Prediction Using Optimized Cuckoo Search Based Nature-Inspired Technique	10.1007/978-981-16-1502-3_19	These days, software systems are very complex and versatile. Therefore it is essential to identify and fix the software error. Software error assessment is one of the most active areas of research in software engineering. In this research, we are introducing soft computing methods to assess software errors. Our proposed technique ts software gives errors and accurate results. In our proposed method, the error database is first extracted, which acts as an input. After that, the collected input (data) is clustered by the clustering technique. For this purpose, we use the modified C-Mean Algorithm. Therefore, the data is clustered. An efficient classification algorithm then groups clustered data. For this reason, we use a hybrid nervous system. Therefore, there are software bugs, and these errors are optimized using the MCS algorithm. Our proposed method for software error assessment is implemented on the Java platform. Performance measurement is measured by various parameters such as execution rate and execution time. Our proposed Cuckoo search based strategy is comparable to many existing strategies. Graphical representation of comparison results from our proposed strategy for identifying software proposals is one that effectively evaluates profitable strategy and reasonable reference rates. © 2021, The Author(s), under exclusive license to Springer Nature Singapore Pte Ltd.	Cuckoo search; Nature inspired algorithm; Optimization algorithm; Software defects	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85112730935&doi=10.1007%2F978-981-16-1502-3_19&partnerID=40&md5=49ae9da96f15691643163735f7f9e53a	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
UXpedite Learning Design Bridging Instructional Design and Software Engineering for Effective Augmented Reality Learning Environments	10.1097/CIN.0000000000001301	The demands of contemporary everyday contexts have accelerated the deployment and adoption of emerging technologies, such as augmented reality, to enhance the learning experience. Traditionally, AR learning environments have been designed according to established instructional design principles. Now, it has become essential to update this approach by addressing the current demands of modern teaching and learning methods (eg, face-to-face and online learning) alongside technical issues related to augmented reality (eg, virtual scenarios). Additionally, the inclusion of software engineering methodologies can contribute to increased precision in the design process. In this sense, the current research presents a blended learning design model named UXpedite Learning Design, which integrates both instructional design and software engineering design approaches to facilitate the development of AR environments. The model comprises six phases: (i) needs assessment, (ii) ideation, (iii) prototyping, (iv) development, (v) technical testing, and (vi) user evaluation. A case study was conducted to demonstrate the implementation of the proposed model in developing the Virtual-Beat application, a tool designed to teach the interpretation of human vital sign measurements. Our tests indicate that using the Virtual-Beat application leads to slightly better learning outcomes compared with conventional classroom education, as evidenced by a statistically significant difference in examination scores between the experimental group (M = 7.53) and the control group (M = 7.08), t73 = 2.96, P = .004. Additionally, the User Experience Questionnaire completed by participants who used the application yielded positive results, highlighting a favorable overall experience (M = 1.465) and excellent attractiveness (M = 1.667). However, the assessment also identified a need for improvement in user interaction control. In conclusion, the findings suggest that the UXpedite Learning Design model shows promise for creating high-quality learning environments that align with the evolving needs of higher education. © Lippincott Williams & Wilkins.	Augmented reality; Higher education; Instructional design; Interactive environments; Software engineering	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-105001185164&doi=10.1097%2FCIN.0000000000001301&partnerID=40&md5=29f0a04c19cade01185e68cfeaadfc88	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Design and development of the online career counselling: a tool for better career decision-making	10.1080/0144929X.2020.1795262	Nowadays, students experience career problems, such as the transition from university to the labour market where they need the career counselling services. Accordingly, it was attempted to design an online career counselling tool and provide services and guidance for students in career fields. This study was conducted in three parts in 2019. In the first part, the career counselling website was designed. In the second part, using the opinions of the experts (20 career counselling experts and 20 software engineering specialists), the website efficiency was assessed, and, in the third part, to conduct the online career counselling, 45 students were assigned into the online counselling, the face-to-face groups, and the control groups to compare their career decision-makings at the pretest and the post-test. The results showed that it is possible to design the online career counselling. Also, according to the results of the third part, the face-to-face and the online groups, compared with the control group, showed a significant and positive mean in the career decision-making. It can be said that the online counselling can be used besides the face-to-face counselling at those universities and educational centres that deal with students to prepare them for career fields. © 2020 Informa UK Limited, trading as Taylor & Francis Group.	career decision-making; online counselling assessment; online counselling design; Online education	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85088572928&doi=10.1080%2F0144929X.2020.1795262&partnerID=40&md5=76da5872189de6781d9cb9c8d57c624f	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

<p>Proceedings of the 30th European Conference on Systems, Software and Services Process Improvement, EuroSPI 2023</p>		<p>The proceedings contain 48 papers. The special focus in this conference is on Systems, Software and Services Process Improvement. The topics include: Trustful Model-Based Information Exchange in Collaborative Engineering; Boosting the EU-Wide Collaboration on Skills Agenda in the Automotive-Mobility Ecosystem; Automotive Data Management SPICE Assessment – Comparison of Process Assessment Models; corporate Memory – Fighting Rework with a Simple Principle and a Practical Implementation; managing Ethical Requirements Elicitation; process Improvement Based on Symptom Analysis; the New Cybersecurity Challenges and Demands for Automotive Organisations and Projects - An Insight View; an Open Software-Based Framework for Automotive Cybersecurity Testing; requirements Engineering for Cyber-Physical Products: Software Process Improvement for Intelligent Systems; A Low-Cost Environment for Teaching Fundamental Cybersecurity Concepts in CPS; gamified Focus Group for Empirical Research in Software Engineering: A Case Study; identification of the Personal Skills Using Games; identifying Key Factors to Distinguish Artificial and Human Avatars in the Metaverse: Insights from Software Practitioners; An Approach to the Instantiation of the EU AI Act: A Level of Done Derivation and a Case Study from the Automotive Domain; Investigating Sources and Effects of Bias in AI-Based Systems – Results from an MLR; quality Assurance in Low-Code Applications; towards User-Centric Design Guidelines for PaaS Systems: The Case of Home Appliances; Supporting the Growth of Electric Vehicle Market Through the E-DRIVETOUR Educational Program; Sustained Enablement of AI Ethics in Industry; exploring Metaverse-Based Digital Governance of Gambia: Obstacles, Citizen Perspectives, and Key Factors for Success; preface; an Investigation of Green Software Engineering.</p>		<p>https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85172812882&partnerID=40&md5=8faa70c69abb9636c143605515fdd4d0</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<p>sem es</p>
<p>Research on input-output index system construction of the power grid company asset value</p>	<p>10.1109/AEMCSE51986.2021.00028</p>	<p>On the basis of asset classification of asset group, the specific category of asset input-output value collection of asset group of the Power Grid Company is determined. This paper systematically combs the company's intangible assets value evaluation method, intangible assets method and intangible assets classification. Starting from three aspects of security, reliability and economy of power grid operation, as well as the asset status and DEA method provided by various management departments of power grid, the input-output evaluation index system of asset group of The Power Grid Company is constructed. © 2021 IEEE.</p>	<p>Indicator system; Intangible assets value assessment; Power grid company group assets value assessment</p>	<p>https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85114052970&doi=10.1109%2fAEMCSE51986.2021.00028&partnerID=40&md5=13e03f60aa1ccfa189126d5b9e257b52</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<p>sem colab</p>
<p>An Open-Source Online Examination System to Meet the Integrity Demands of E-Learning</p>	<p>10.3844/jcssp.2024.628.640</p>	<p>The rise of online learning platforms and the growing demand for remote education emphasize the importance of online exam-proctoring tools. Online proctoring tools presented in the literature require high internet speed and specialized hardware support, posing accessibility challenges for individuals in developing countries. This study aims to develop a solution that relies on something other than high internet speed and high-end hardware components. The proposed solution extracts data generated from keystroke logs, browser history, and applications opened during the assessment to predict online exam cheating. This data is compared to the words in the test using Term Frequency (TF) and Inverse Document Frequency (IDF) to predict cheating. To evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed solution, an experiment was conducted with sixteen undergraduate Software Engineering students divided into two groups of eight students. The groups were given 20-minute-long software engineering and database exams, each comprising 30 MCQS. These exams were conducted with the proposed proctoring tool and only one group was allowed to cheat. Results indicated that the proposed tool effectively detects cheating during exams. This approach can mitigate the digital divide, particularly for individuals lacking high-speed internet access and costly hardware. Consequently, the study proposes an inclusive solution designed to cater to users from diverse demographic backgrounds. © 2024 Abdul Wahab Muzaffar. This open-access article is distributed under a Creative Commons Attribution (CC-BY) 4.0 license.</p>	<p>E-Learning; Natural Language Processing; Online Exam; Online Exam Cheating; Proctoring</p>	<p>https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85190639283&doi=10.3844%2fjcssp.2024.628.640&partnerID=40&md5=4dcb8f5ae02f963ba59be852d4e4bfc6</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<p>sem colab</p>

Development of Android multiple representative media: Enhancing cognitive achievement and motivation of student in chemistry	10.1063/5.0110561	This research aimed to produce the valid and feasible product of android multiple representative media to be used as independent learning media for improving student's cognitive learning outcomes and motivation. Research and Development (R&D) with the ADDIE's (Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation, Evaluation) model was applied in this research. The implementation was carried out on 114 eleven-grade students of the two senior high schools in West Kalimantan, Indonesia using a simple random sampling technique. The implementation was conducted with Pre-Experiment Method One Group Pretest-Posttest Design. The data collection was conducted by using instrument test questions of cognitive learning, students' learning motivation questionnaire, and questionnaire of media quality assessment which had been validated theoretically and empirically which was developed with learning aspects, concept aspects, component aspect of multiple representatives, visual and audio aspects, and software engineering aspects. Test of Hotelling's T2 was used in this research. The results showed that android multiple representative media has valid and feasible to use in chemistry learning. The research also showed that there were significant differences in cognitive learning outcomes and student's learning motivation before and after using android multiple representative media with an increase of 19.74 and 18.39, with the percentage of effective media contribution in the amount of 46.8%. This research suggests that the use of android multiple representative media is recommended in chemistry learning at senior high school. © 2023 Author(s).		https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85151277898&doi=10.1063%2f5.0110561&partnerID=40&md5=e8ccc7fbaac4a01b333962bfcc82ce5	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Balancing the Engineering Disciplines!: An Interdisciplinary First-Year Design Project		When engineering students graduate and begin work as an engineer, they are confronted with the reality of the interdisciplinary nature of the workplace. This reality frequently extends beyond engineering disciplines and includes colleagues from other backgrounds ranging from project managers, marketing and sales, to assemblers, machinists, and technicians. Often, they are also required to follow a documented or prescribed process that may resemble an engineering design process. To better prepare students for both engineering practice and internships along the way, we developed a semester-long design project that is bound by many of these constraints. This Work in Progress paper describes the project goals and constraints, periodic checkpoints that reinforce the engineering design process, assessment methods, and project motivations with the objective of enabling others to successfully implement the design project in their course. Since its founding, Dunwoody College of Technology has prided itself on ensuring students learn in an environment that mirrors industry as closely as possible. With this history in mind, we guide interdisciplinary groups of students consisting of electrical, mechanical, and software engineering majors through the engineering design process. The project objective is to research, design, build, calibrate, and test a balance or scale with a digital readout made from simple components. Successful completion requires elements of each engineering discipline represented in the course. The course itself, Introduction to Engineering, is laid out in a manner that incrementally introduces each of the concepts required for the design. For example, the concept of forces and moments are introduced within the mechanical engineering module prior to requesting the students demonstrate their weight measurement scheme. The project was carried out with three independent sections of students participating in team sizes ranging from 2 - 3 students, with the intent of having a mix of all three disciplines when possible. Preliminary lessons learned and feedback from administering the project are presented. Additionally, resulting designs are compiled and organized into categories, with some common themes and pitfalls identified. Recommendations for future iterations that incorporate lessons learned are discussed. © American Society for Engineering Education, 2021		https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85124505459&partnerID=40&md5=74d89574c1579441d56a454f1a3693ea	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Measurement Models for Group-Peer Assessment of Project-Based Learning in Software Engineering	10.1109/ISCSET58624.2024.10808114	Over two decades we have been developing and testing alternative frameworks for Group-Peer-Assessment (GP A) in software engineering education. The focus lies on skills assessed through observation of students' behavior and/or examination of the results of project assignments. Assessment for such instructional types is not covered satisfactorily by traditional approaches. Assessment at the group as well as individual level must be able to cope with multiple quality criteria on scales of various types, and multiple assessors responsible for assessing distinct quality aspects. We offer two-parameter scoring models for GP A, by which individual student scores are derived from a group score and mutual peer ratings. The two parameters are: (1) a constraint on the spread of student scores and (2) the relative impact of peer ratings. GP A imposes no artificial restrictions on group size, type or number of quality criteria, or other context-specific aspects of GP A. We briefly describe our experience with GP A for software engineering courses at a university in the UK. © 2024 IEEE.	Bounded scales; grades; group score; group spread; peer assessments; peer impact; ratings; scale operations; scores; scoring rule; student contribution; student score	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85215499639&doi=10.1109%2fISCSET58624.2024.10808114&partnerID=40&md5=b6ee832f0ab80d685c4aff99c1bec540	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sen colab

Educating Reflective Systems Developers at Scale: Towards 'productive feedback' in a semi-capstone large-scale software engineering course	10.1109 /FIE56618. 2022.9962726	Feedback is critical in education. This Innovative Practice Full Paper reports lessons learned from improving the quality of feedback in a semi-capstone software engineering course, with particular focus on how to deliver productive feedback in large scale during project work. The bachelor-level introduction to software engineering course is taken by about 500 students from eight study programs, organised into 72 project teams. The course aims to educate reflective systems developers. The teaching staff includes 29 teaching assistants as supervisor and product owners for teams. Project teams get feedback on seven deliverables as part of formative portfolio assessment. Students expressed frustration on feedback not being aligned, that they got critique on topics not stated in assignments and that teaching assistants were reluctant to discuss the feedback. This article provides a description of the course design, an assessment of the quality of feedback and lessons learned from three main changes: Revising assignments and rubrics, reorganising the teaching staff and increasing training of teaching assistants. In discussing the changes, we draw on a survey to students with 142 respondents, a survey to teaching assistants with 18 respondents, meeting minutes from a student reference group and experience reports from teaching assistants as well as literature and own experience. The article concludes with three actionable lessons learned for large-scale semi-capstone courses. © 2022 IEEE.	agile development methods; bachelor; capstone education; experience report; project work; scrum; software engineering education; teamwork; training	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85143776799&doi=10.1109%2FIE56618.2022.9962726&partnerID=40&md5=161f185e9e85fe23bf422d89d943f814	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	chance
Analyzing Group and Individual Contributions within Group Programming: RepoRabbit Web Application	10.1145 /3502717. 3532136	In this work, we focus on developing resources for group programming and software engineering education which are important topics within Computer Science curriculums. Our goal is to help educators to be able to understand and assess their students' software projects. To achieve this goal, my advisor and I have developed a web-based application that processes student code repositories and visualizes the resulting data. In our analysis, we use coding metrics such as the number of commits made and number of lines coded (this includes insertions and deletions) along with commit frequency. From this analysis, we are able to curate specific information to help the educator answer questions about fairness, timeliness, consistency, and overall contribution from each student. In the future, we hope to make our application available for all educators. © 2022 Owner/Author.	measuring developer contribution; software engineering education; student assessment; team projects	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85134515440&doi=10.1145%2F3502717.3532136&partnerID=40&md5=c51ade7517d45b6f167c88c4863b434d	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Did our Course Design on Software Architecture meet our Student's Learning Expectations?	10.1109 /FIE44824. 2020.9274014	This Innovative Practice Full Paper discusses our course design on software architecture to meet the learning expectations of two groups of software engineers. Software engineers with working experiences frequently find themselves the need to upskill in their lifelong learning journey. Their learning expectations are shaped not just by their need to know but also other learning characteristics such as their working experiences. In many cases, we design courses based on the required learning outcomes and assessment criteria. In this paper, we wish to find out whether our course design on software architecture has met the learning expectations of our students over eight years. Our study data involves two groups of software engineers to upskill in two courses (1) software engineering practitioners taking a public software architecture design course (2) postgraduate students taking a Master's level software engineering programme. We explain how we evolve the course design based on their students' feedback after each run of the courses. Although the feedback of each run show encouraging results, we discover gaps in our design when we cumulatively analyze the trends of their learning expectations with their qualitative comments over the years. Our design is able to consistently meet some but not all the learning expectations that recur over the years and we discuss the reasons for this outcome and potential further interventions. We hope this discussion and trend analysis process can help course designers to improve their course design. © 2020 IEEE.	adult learner; learning expectations; software architecture; software engineering	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85098571338&doi=10.1109%2FIE44824.2020.9274014&partnerID=40&md5=edf768e65a43a4d8a1fb73f4eaa88810	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Machine learning based feedback on textual student answers in large courses	10.1016/j.caeai.2022.100081	<p>Many engineering disciplines require problem-solving skills, which cannot be learned by memorization alone. Open-ended textual exercises allow students to acquire these skills. Students can learn from their mistakes when instructors provide individual feedback. However, grading these exercises is often a manual, repetitive, and time-consuming activity. The number of computer science students graduating per year has steadily increased over the last decade. This rise has led to large courses that cause a heavy workload for instructors, especially if they provide individual feedback to students. This article presents CoFee, a framework to generate and suggest computer-aided feedback for textual exercises based on machine learning. CoFee utilizes a segment-based grading concept, which links feedback to text segments. CoFee automates grading based on topic modeling and an assessment knowledge repository acquired during previous assessments. A language model builds an intermediate representation of the text segments. Hierarchical clustering identifies groups of similar text segments to reduce the grading overhead. We first demonstrated the CoFee framework in a small laboratory experiment in 2019, which showed that the grading overhead could be reduced by 85%. This experiment confirmed the feasibility of automating the grading process for problem-solving exercises. We then evaluated CoFee in a large course at the Technical University of Munich from 2019 to 2021, with up to 2, 200 enrolled students per course. We collected data from 34 exercises offered in each of these courses. On average, CoFee suggested feedback for 45% of the submissions. 92% (Positive Predictive Value) of these suggestions were precise and, therefore, accepted by the instructors. © 2022 The Authors</p>	Assessment support system; Automatic assessment; Education; Feedback; Grading; Interactive learning; Learning; Software engineering	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85136131222&doi=10.1016%2Fj.caeai.2022.100081&partnerID=40&md5=20c0c5672a472fb6d844fd755a79b1	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
On the Impact of Grading on Teamwork Quality in a Software Engineering Capstone Course	10.1109/ACCESS.2023.3265302	<p>Every semester, we deliver a capstone course on software engineering where students undertake a real-world project in three iterations. By the end of each iteration, students are graded in several dimensions: software quality, project management, and peer assessment. The latter is the only grade assigned individually; therefore, students who are penalized by their teams (e.g., for being perceived as low contributors to the team effort) are not severely affected. This results in little incentive for improvement, which potentially jeopardizes the overall quality of the project outcome. Envisaging to promote team cohesion, we devised a new grading rule: if the peer assessment of a student is lower than a threshold, that would be their final grade in the iteration. This paper reports the results of studying the effectiveness of the proposed rule. We recorded peer assessments over six consecutive semesters: (1) the first three as the baseline measure; (2) the semester where we introduced the new grading rule; and (3) the following two semesters, as a contrast. When the rule was first introduced, peer assessments resulted low and heavily spread at the beginning, but they consistently improved toward the end of the semester. When the instructional team already trusted the rule and explicitly emphasized its application, peer assessments consistently grew along the semester but resulted in fewer outliers. The study results show that exposing peer assessments earlier on helps promote team reflection. They also made evident the positive impact of teamwork for producing quality products in a software engineering capstone course. © 2013 IEEE.</p>	Capstone course; software engineering education; teamwork	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85153366964&doi=10.1109%2FACCESS.2023.3265302&partnerID=40&md5=7baafbf13ae51528618c7d270f4638c	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem avaliar
Student Perspectives on the Purpose of Peer Evaluation during Group Game Development Projects	10.1145/3481282.3481294	<p>Being able to work well in a team is valued in industry and beyond. As such, many university educators strive to help their students to collaborate effectively. However, it is typically the case that more than ad-hoc experience is needed to master teamwork. Often, students need to become reflective practitioners who learn from their experiences and enact change. Self and peer evaluation can help evoke such reflection. However, the facilitating conditions for effective learning from peer evaluation during group projects in computing are not yet well-defined. This research is an initial step in identifying these conditions. In this study, students engaged in a long-term multidisciplinary software engineering project in which they produced a digital game. They completed regular exercises in which they reflected upon and wrote about their contributions to the project as well as those of their peers. Thematic analysis of 200 responses to an open-ended question about the purpose of these exercises illustrated student perspectives: giving and receiving feedback; prompting personal reflection and improvement; supporting supervision; aiding marking; informing project planning and management; exploring and reshaping group dynamics; improving project outputs; providing a system to hold group members accountable; and giving a sense of safety to raise issues without repercussion. Giving consideration to these differing perceptions will help educators to address student concerns about group projects, notably standardisation, workload efficiency, and fairness, and will lay the foundations for a model of peer evaluation which improves teamwork. © 2021 ACM.</p>	Collaborative Learning; Group Work; Peer Assessment; Peer Evaluation; Peer Rating; Peer Review; Project-based Learning; Software Development; Student Team Projects; Teamwork	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85115243503&doi=10.1145%2F3481282.3481294&partnerID=40&md5=6a1b6b7758e9bd60e94da06180ae97e4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	chance

A systematic literature review of capstone courses in software engineering	10.1016/j.infsof.2023.107191	Context: Tertiary education institutions aim to prepare their computer science and software engineering students for working life. While much of the technical principles are covered in lower-level courses, team-based capstone courses are a common way to provide students with hands-on experience and teach soft skills. Objective: This paper explores the characteristics of project-based software engineering capstone courses presented in the literature. The goal of this work is to understand the pros and cons of different approaches by synthesising the various aspects of software engineering capstone courses and related experiences. Method: In a systematic literature review for 2007–2022, we identified 127 articles describing real-world capstone courses. These articles were analysed based on their presented course characteristics and the reported course outcomes. Results: The characteristics were synthesised into a taxonomy consisting of duration, team sizes, client and project sources, project implementation, and student assessment. We found out that capstone courses generally last one semester and divide students into groups of 4–5 where they work on a project for a client. For a slight majority of courses, the clients are external to the course staff and students are often expected to produce a proof-of-concept level software product as the main end deliverable. The courses generally include various forms of student assessment both during and at the end of the course. Conclusions: This paper provides researchers and educators with a classification of characteristics of software engineering capstone courses based on previous research. We also further synthesise insights on the reported course outcomes. Our review study aims to help educators to identify various ways of organising capstones and effectively plan and deliver their own capstone courses. The characterisation also helps researchers to conduct further studies on software engineering capstones. © 2023 The Authors	Capstone; Computer science education; Project course; Software engineering education	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85151055501&doi=10.1016%2fj.infsof.2023.107191&partnerID=40&md5=f61b4ce82ec07ea1d9dcc2a48205ad3d	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Exploring the Integration of Generative AI Tools in Software Testing Education: A Case Study on ChatGPT and Copilot for Preparatory Testing Artifacts in Postgraduate Learning	10.1109/ACCESS.2025.3545882	Software testing education is important for building qualified testing professionals. To ensure that software testing graduates are ready for real-world challenges, it is necessary to integrate modern tools and technologies into the curriculum. With the emergence of Large Language Models (LLMs), their potential use in software engineering has become a focus, but their application in software testing education remains largely unexplored. This study, conducted in the Capstone Project course of a postgraduate software testing program, was carried out over two semesters with two distinct groups of students. A custom-built Travel Application limited to a web platform was used in the first semester. In the second semester, a new set of students worked with an open-source application, offering a larger-scale, multi-platform experience across web, desktop, and mobile platforms. Students initially created preparatory testing artifacts manually as a group deliverable. Following this, they were assigned an individual assignment to generate the same artifacts using LLM tools such as ChatGPT 3.5 in the first semester and Microsoft Copilot in the second. This process directly compared manually created artifacts and those generated using LLMs, leveraging AI for faster outputs. After completion, they responded to a set of assigned questions. The students' responses were assessed using an integrated methodology, including quantitative and qualitative assessments, sentiment analysis to understand emotions, and a thematic approach to extract deeper insights. The findings revealed that while LLMs can assist and augment manual testing efforts, they cannot entirely replace the need for manual testing. By incorporating innovative technology into the curriculum, this study highlights how Generative AI can support active learning, connect theoretical concepts with practical applications, and align educational practices with industry needs. © 2013 IEEE.	Capstone project; ChatGPT; generative AI; Microsoft Copilot; sentiment analysis; software testing education	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-105001239332&doi=10.1109%2fACCESS.2025.3545882&partnerID=40&md5=86a933c4b170caf390243024326fe224	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Achieving Scalability in Project Based Learning through a Low-Code platform	10.1145/3422392.3422482	Defining an adequate project for a Software Engineering course is a challenging endeavour. Such a project must simulate as faithfully as possible a real industrial project, while accounting, e.g., for: i) the natural lack of experience of the students, ii) their constraints to full-Time dedication, and iii) reasonable effort required from the instructors. Additionally, while having a real client from industry may contribute to a more realistic experience, the project itself must be challenging enough to motivate the client while still not unduly burden the students. We report on our experience and share our insights from adopting a state-of-The-Art low-code software development platform as the core technology for project-based learning-with a real client in a one-semester software engineering course. We had to handle i) a large class (200+ students), while providing ii) individual assessment iii) for students from very different backgrounds (majoring in three different topics). While we believe i) and ii) are recurrent, iii) poses a significant challenge in the establishment of a fair pedagogic context. We assess the merit of the experience taking as proxy: i) the students' individual and group performance, assessed both by the instructors and the client, and ii) the results of the course's standard institutional pedagogical survey. We have found evidence that the designed project created an even playing field for students from different backgrounds, while being manageable for the instructors and rewarding for the client. © 2020 Owner/Author.	Low-Code Platforms; Project-based Learning; Scalability; Software Engineering Education	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85099341995&doi=10.1145%2F3422392.3422482&partnerID=40&md5=6af1f4d4a0a1906707f4e957de9e9dc5	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Assessment of Collaborative Problem Solving in Engineering Students Through Hands-On Simulations	10.1109/TE.2021.3079523	Contribution: This article discusses the use of manufacturing simulation games to study collaborative problem-solving skills in engineering students. The simulation represents the mass production paradigm in which large quantities of identical products are produced. Empirical data is collected from the simulation to evaluate the skills engineering students used in solving the problem and their group effectiveness. Background: The use of simulation games to teach problem solving in design and manufacturing is an effective approach to convey concepts to students. Simulation games engage students in experiential and collaborative learning with fun elements. Research Questions: How does hands-on simulation engage students in collaborative problem solving? How does participation in collaborative problem solving affect group effectiveness? Methodology: This work presents a study of 37 university-level engineering students in the United States. Participants worked in groups completing the simulation game and responded to surveys on their various skills used. Findings: Participants utilized analytical, metacognitive, and thinking skills in their engagement, reported that the simulation games enhanced their understanding of manufacturing concepts and active collaboration improved problem-solving effectiveness. © 1963-2012 IEEE.	Collaborative problem solving; educational games; manufacturing systems; product design; simulation games	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85107204131&doi=10.1109%2FTE.2021.3079523&partnerID=40&md5=e1be2935ae40deca6d0743e76357bfa4	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es
Sustainable project-based learning methodology adaptable to technological advances for web programming	10.3390/su13158482	The fast pace of development of the Internet and the Coronavirus Disease (COVID-19) pandemic have considerably impacted the educative sector, encouraging the constant transformation of the teaching/learning strategies and more in technological areas as Educational Software Engineering. Web programming, a fundamental topic in Software Engineering and Cloud-based applications, deals with various critical challenges in education, such as learning continuous emerging technological tools, plagiarism detection, generating innovative learning environments, among others. Continual change and even more change with the current digitization becomes a challenge for teachers and students who cannot depend on traditional educational methods. The article presents a sustainable teaching/learning methodology for web programming courses in Engineering Education using project-based learning adaptable to the continuous web technological advances. The methodology has been developed and improved during 9 years, 15 groups, and 3 different universities. Our results demonstrate that the methodology is adaptable with new technologies that might arise; it also presents the advantages of avoiding plagiarism in students and a personalized induction for every specific student in the learning process. © 2021 by the authors. Licensee MDPI, Basel, Switzerland.	Programming approach; Sustainable education; Teaching experience; Teaching methodology; Web programming	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85111960377&doi=10.3390%2Fsu13158482&partnerID=40&md5=e88ef175c156d2b3f02cbc7877a927fa	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Research and Design of Intelligent Test Paper System Based on Genetic Algorithm	10.1109/ICBASE51474.2020.00068	With the mutual integration of computer technology and education, promoting the reform of education and teaching network, online examination mode has gradually become an important means of new education measurement. The online examination system has basically realized the examinee answer, check and system group, and other functions, but there is a set of performance is not high, the examination such as the imperfection of the auxiliary function, in view of the above problem, this paper analyzes the group's related theory, using genetic algorithm as a smart group volume is determined, and genetic operation process of the group to carry on the design and improvement; At the same time, the system function and framework technology are deeply analyzed, the system function framework is established, and the intelligent test system is finally realized. © 2020 IEEE.	computer technology; Genetic algorithm; intelligent test paper system	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85105381500&doi=10.1109%2fICBASE51474.2020.00068&partnerID=40&md5=0896c17fd6f283b0e7783dfa94a33f5a	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Reliability Assessment of Machine Learning Models in Hydrological Predictions Through Metamorphic Testing	10.1029/2020WR029471	The reliability of the machine learning model prediction for a given input can be assessed by comparing it against the actual output. However, in hydrological studies, machine learning models are often adopted to predict future or unknown events, where the actual outputs are unavailable. The prediction accuracy of a model, which measures its average performance across an observed data set, may not be relevant for a specific input. This study presents a method based on metamorphic testing (MT), adopted from software engineering, to assess the prediction reliability where the actual outputs are unknown. In this method, the predictions for a group of related inputs are considered consistent only if the input and output follow certain relations that are deduced from the properties of the system being modeled. For instance, the predicted runoff volume should increase in a rainfall-runoff model as the rainfall magnitude of an input increases. In this study, the MT-based method was applied to assess the predictions made by various machine learning models that were trained to predict the magnitude of flood events in Germany. Surprisingly, the prediction accuracy of a model and its ability to provide consistent predictions were found to be uncorrelated. This study further investigated the factors influencing the assessment result of a given input, such as its similarity to observed data. Overall, this research shows that MT is an effective and simple method for detecting inconsistent model predictions and is recommended when a model is employed to making predictions under new conditions. © 2021. American Geophysical Union. All Rights Reserved.		https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85115750900&doi=10.1029%2f2020WR029471&partnerID=40&md5=da1f27dadde4628301262ffbaf97b872	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Towards a Paradigm Change in Group and Peer Assessment in Software Engineering Education	10.1109/CSEET49119.2020.9206197	Conventional approaches to group and peer assessment are invariably based on highly questionable assumptions about educational measurement and how to weight and aggregate multiple scores into an overall judgement of outcome and performance. In this paper, we propose an alternative approach based on a sound theory of educational scoring and rating. Our approach is particularly relevant for software engineering education, where group projects with multiple types of outcomes are used to assess individual students. We will also demonstrate our novel approach by means of two software tools and compare them with other tools based on conventional approaches. Throughout, we will focus on explaining the reasons for and benefits of adopting our paradigm changing approach to group-peer marking. © 2020 IEEE.	arithmetic mean; bounded scale; educational judgement; group-peer marking; peer assessment; quasi-arithmetic mean; scoring models; scoring rules; scoring theory	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85097649661&doi=10.1109%2fCSEET49119.2020.9206197&partnerID=40&md5=3f464b031ede6e66b166f0d15af2fd5	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Examining Teamwork: Evaluating Individual Contributions in Collaborative Software Engineering Projects	10.1145/3641554.3701821	Collaborative learning and group projects are integral to Software Engineering (SE) education as they help prepare students for professional environments where teamwork and collective problem-solving are crucial. Accurately assessing individual contributions within the group project setting remains a significant challenge. Traditional assessment methods often fail to distinguish between individual efforts and collective achievements, particularly in team-based assignments prevalent in SE courses. This paper explores how several factors potentially affect individual participation in group programming projects. We compare metrics for evaluating individual contributions and examine the effect of group formation strategies on collaborative practices. Our data consist of the collaborative artifacts of 77 teams and peer evaluation responses from 154 students across two semesters of a graduate-level software engineering course, providing insights into several research questions, including the effectiveness of different metrics for estimating individual contributions, the distribution of programming tasks among students, and the impact of group composition on task distribution and peer evaluations. © 2025 Copyright held by the owner/author(s).	Collaboration; Empirical Evaluation; Metrics; Software Engineering; Team-based projects	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-86000248934&doi=10.1145%2f3641554.3701821&partnerID=40&md5=9a0e0e9736f950a6c30412c2dac4eb9b	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	chance

The Impact of the GQM Framework on Software Engineering Exam Outcomes	10.14569/JACSA.2024.0151063	Assessment is crucial in educational systems, particularly in Software Engineering (SE) programs, where fair and effective evaluations drive continuous improvement. The shift to student-centric methodologies has evolved assessment strategies to focus on aligning educational processes with students' developmental needs rather than merely measuring academic outputs. This paper adapts the Goal-Question-Metric (GQM) framework to enhance learning in software engineering education by linking educational goals, learning activities, and assessment methods. This approach specifies expected learning outcomes and integrates mechanisms for continuous improvement, aligning teaching strategies with student performance metrics. A systematic framework for course assessment using the GQM framework is presented, aligning assessment methods with Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs) and Student Learning Outcomes (SLOs) to ensure data-driven enhancements. To validate this approach, a template was introduced to assess the impact of a tailored GQM approach on the final exam outcomes of a software engineering course at King Abdulaziz University's Department of Computer Science. A controlled experiment was conducted over two semesters with students from the CPCS 351 course. The control group, in the first semester, completed their finals without applying GQM, while the experimental group in the following semester employed a customized GQM framework. Statistical analyses, including ANOVA and Mann-Whitney U tests, were utilized to compare exam performance between the groups. Results indicated a significant improvement in the exam scores of the experimental group, thereby validating the effectiveness of the GQM framework in boosting academic performance through structured exam preparation and execution. © (2024), (Science and Information Organization). All rights reserved.	continuous improvement; education; Goal-question-metric (GQM); learning outcomes; learning process; software engineering; statistical analysis	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-86000671582&doi=10.14569%2fJACSA.2024.0151063&partnerID=40&md5=5eda9383e0e395fa0ae70a9f3a89db3f	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Design Thinking in the Improvement of Usability of Physics Mobile Educational Application	10.1007/978-981-16-1781-2_55	This article describes the creation of a mobile application following the design thinking (DT) approach and its assessment of usability. DT is thought of as a methodology to create innovative solutions to the needs of end-users through well-established five stages. We worked with high school students, a pedagogical team, and a group of undergraduate students in software engineering. In each of the DT stages, diagrams, maps, matrices, groupings, prototypes, and simulations were elaborated that allowed us to empathize with the user, define, create, and test the creative ideas generated throughout the process (development process). To evaluate the usability of the application, the USE questionnaire (Usefulness, Satisfaction, and Ease of use) was applied to a group of students from the education career. The results indicate that it has been possible to develop an educational mobile application with a good level of usability that meets the needs of users. © 2022, The Author(s), under exclusive license to Springer Nature Singapore Pte Ltd.	Design thinking; M-learning; Mobile computing; Usability	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85115637976&doi=10.1007%2f978-981-16-1781-2_55&partnerID=40&md5=bb81ec6e3ae13f30d884e99ab2ad30d2	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Impact of software development processes on the outcomes of student computing projects: A tale of two universities	10.1016/j.infsof.2021.106787	Context: Project-based courses are more and more commonly used as an opportunity to teach students structured methods of developing software. Two well-known approaches in this area – traditional and Agile – have been successfully applied to drive academic projects. However too often the default is still to have no organizational process at all. While a large variety of software development life-cycle models exists, little guidance is available on which one to choose to fit the context of working with students. Objective: This paper assesses the impact of iterative, sequential and “hands-off” development approaches on the success of student computing projects. A structured, metric-based assessment scheme was applied to investigate team productivity, teamwork and the quality of the final product. Method: Empirical evidence was collected during a controlled experiment carried out at two engineering schools in Europe. More than 100 students at Bachelor's and Master's levels participated in the research, with varied software development and teamwork skill sets. Results: Similar patterns were observed among both sets of subjects, with iterative teams demonstrating the highest productivity and superior team cohesion but a decline in the quality of the final product. Sequential development led to a considerable improvement in the external quality characteristics of the software produced, owing to the method's stress on design activities. Conclusion: The findings of this study will be of use to educators interested in applying software development processes to student groupwork. A set of guidelines is provided for applying a structured way of working in a project-based course. © 2021 The Author(s)	Capstone project; Comparative study; Computer science education; Education; Software engineering; Student projects	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85120696494&doi=10.1016%2fj.infsof.2021.106787&partnerID=40&md5=de7f141fa3649f4deb62bb2152204513	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

<p>RUNNER: Responsible UNfair NEuron Repair for Enhancing Deep Neural Network Fairness</p>	<p>10.1145/3597503.3623334</p>	<p>Deep Neural Networks (DNNs), an emerging software technology, have achieved impressive results in a variety of fields. However, the discriminatory behaviors towards certain groups (a.k.a. unfairness) of DNN models increasingly become a social concern, especially in high-stake applications such as loan approval and criminal risk assessment. Although there has been a number of works to improve model fairness, most of them adopt an adversary to either expand the model architecture or augment training data, which introduces excessive computational overhead. Recent work diagnoses responsible unfair neurons first and fixes them with selective retraining. Unfortunately, existing diagnosis process is time-consuming due to multi-step training sample analysis, and selective retraining may cause a performance bottleneck due to indirectly adjusting unfair neurons on biased samples. In this paper, we propose Responsible UNfair NEuron Repair (RUNNER) that improves existing works in three key aspects: (1) efficiency: we design the Importance-based Neuron Diagnosis that identifies responsible unfair neurons in one step with a novel importance criterion of neurons; (2) effectiveness: we design the Neuron Stabilizing Retraining by adding a loss term that measures the activation distance of responsible unfair neurons from different subgroups in all sources; (3) generalization: we investigate the effectiveness on both structured tabular data and large-scale unstructured image data, which is often ignored in prior studies. Our extensive experiments across 5 datasets show that RUUNER can effectively and efficiently diagnose and repair the DNNs regarding unfairness. On average, our approach significantly reduces computing overhead from 341.7s to 29.65s, and achieves improved fairness up to 79.3%. Besides, RUNNER also keeps state-of-the-art results on the unstructured dataset. © 2024 IEEE Computer Society. All rights reserved.</p>	<p>Deep Learning Repair; Fairness; Model Interpretation</p>	<p>https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85185535952&doi=10.1145%2f3597503.3623334&partnerID=40&md5=041f305a67780385c6ab895bc051028c</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/></p>	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>	<p>sem colab</p>
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<p>Integrated Project Development through Combined Theory and Practices of Core Courses focusing on Software Development Skills: Integrated Learning Framework</p>	<p>10.16920/jjeet/2024/v37is2/24148</p>	<p>The National Education Policy promotes moving from the conventional content-heavy and memorization learning practice towards holistic learning/integrated learning. It imparts a creative and multidisciplinary curriculum that focuses equally on curriculum and assessment. All educational establishments assess students using written examinations, quizzes, seminars, term paper writing, and course projects. A semester typically includes 4-5 courses, and students must earn credits for these courses by scoring a good Cumulative Grade Point Average (CGPA). As course projects offer depth knowledge/holistic learning/lifelong learning of a course for the student, many courses include course projects as one of the activities in the course. If all the courses are intended to include course projects as a mandatory pedagogy, it will be difficult for students to acquire in-depth knowledge and required skills while also dealing with stress. So we are proposing an integrated learning framework by applying the theory and practices of two core courses-Software Engineering and Web Technologies to develop a web application. This integrated learning focuses on developing software development and software testing skills in computer science for undergraduate students pursuing a bachelor of engineering degree. This framework alleviated the pressure on students during placement and created job opportunities in software development. The framework consists of three important phases-The first phase includes the identification of the problem as a need for customers, writing requirements and analyzing the same. Students apply modular design principles and break down the codebase into distinct modules. This technique enhances code organization, reusability, and maintainability. The second phase focused on developing the front end by harnessing the power of Angular, a leading web framework, to craft a sleek and interactive user interface. The backend is built using Node.js, which serves as the foundation, enabling the software system to cater to high-performance server environments. These modules communicated seamlessly through well-defined APIs, facilitating the integration of various components within the application, ultimately delivering a seamless and responsive user experience. An industry expert conducted a workshop on Angular software testing workshop was conducted for students by industry experts to expose the students to designing test cases, test plans, and testing strategies. The hands-on experience on testing tools was provided during the workshop. Faculty reviews are conducted on each phase, and rubrics-based assessment is done on each phase. Approximately sixty teams created web-based applications for real-world scenarios. Positive aspects of the framework in feedback indicated that more than 87% of the students agreed that they could apply Software engineering principles and practices such as requirements management, modular design and testing in web applications. Also, more than 85% of students acquire skills from code-to-web design mastery by developing web applications in Angular Node.js and backend implementation. This framework helped to improve teamwork, presentation and communication skills. Confidence in software development improved to a greater extent. The design and implementation of the framework met the stated outcome of the courses. The student's academic performance improved by 10% compared to the previous year when students were not involved in the integrated project development. © 2024, Rajarambapu Institute Of Technology. All rights reserved.</p>	<p>Framework; learning; practices; project; skills; technology; testing; web</p>	<p>https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85193733082&doi=10.16920%2fjeet%2f2024%2fv37is2%2f24148&partnerID=40&md5=060cfbe73bdd351bae53fd9bde192e6c</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<p>sen es</p>
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Exploring Peer Evaluation Methods in Group Projects of Software Engineering Education	10.1109 /FIE61694. 2024.10893587	This Innovative Practice category full paper proposes an innovative approach to enhance peer evaluations in group-based learning. It aims at enhancing the overall peer assessment experience for students in software engineering education. In the software industry, it is all about teamwork for software development projects. There is a need to nurture students to work collaboratively in group-based learning. The collaborative milieu inherent in group projects has long been acknowledged within the sphere of software engineering education. In our university, students are cultivated the effective teamwork within the purview of CSC2101 - Professional Software Development and Team Projects (PSD & TP1), an undergraduate course in the domain of software engineering. The terrain of software group projects still presents its own array of obstacles, such as unequal contributions, internal conflicts, peer evaluation mechanism, etc. This paper first discusses the limitations of the current peer evaluation methods in this course. Next, the proposed methodology is presented that embodies four key elements: transparency, anonymity, structured assessment, and qualitative feedback. The implementation details of the proposed approaches are then described consisting of the following features and mechanisms: online platform, anonymous profiles, public results, and structured evaluation forms. The rationales for the proposed peer evaluation techniques are discussed. The experiment studies are conducted involving 40 students in our university. It includes numerous characteristics of the peer evaluation experience in order to gain a full picture of existing peer evaluation approaches within software engineering education. The survey results show a generally positive mentality toward the proposed features. © 2024 IEEE.	Group-based learning; peer assessment; peer evaluation approaches; software engineering education	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-105000741671&doi=10.1109%2FIE61694.2024.10893587&partnerID=40&md5=3f8c8de854e4086e678737d6c56604c5	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
A systematic mapping study on group work research in computing education projects	10.1016/j.jss. 2023.111795	Context: For developing students' group- and teamwork skills needed in the team-oriented work environments of the software industry, the role of project-based learning is considered central. Yet there does not appear to be a proper mapping of the current group work research in the computer science project education literature. Thus, the current state of group work research in the research area is somewhat unknown. Objective: This study aims to form an overview of how research has addressed students' group work in the field of computer science (CS) and software engineering (SE) to identify research gaps as well as suitable topics for more detailed literature reviews. Methods: A systematic mapping study was used to investigate how group work in tertiary education has been undertaken in the literature during the past decade. Results: Based on the selected papers, the most investigated group work areas were related to the assessment of groups, group formation, communication, and cooperation. The research appeared to be quite narrowly focused on a few areas. Most of the papers were experience or evaluation research. A case study using interviews or questionnaires to gather data from a single course was the most representative type of study. The papers were mainly published in scientific conferences. The use of theoretical frameworks was limited, with a focus on a few established frameworks. Tuckman's group development theory was the predominant framework, while other commonly used concepts and theories include social loafing, Kolb's learning style theory, and the Big Five personality traits model. Conclusion: Out of 7515 papers screened, 225 were deemed eligible and analyzed. We conclude a need for more focused group work research in CS/SE student projects, in which education is inspected from particular perspectives. This would create identifiable lines of research and structure the research area. Relatedly, we suggest that the underused theoretical frameworks can inspire important research: group interventions would benefit from a socially shared regulated learning perspective, explicit use of justice theories would improve theoretical understandings of group behavior, and transactional distance would help analyze how students adopt a software process. Moreover, the research area could be precipitated by novel theoretical perspectives. For practitioners, those implementing a group project course can benefit from a large amount of literature on assessment and group formation, which are issues on which the teacher must take a position. We also include a lessons-learned summary for teachers. Generally, the present results outlining the field in a structured way can facilitate research-based teaching. © 2023 The Author(s)	Group projects; Group work; PjBL; Project education; Systematic mapping study	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85165061885&doi=10.1016%2Fj.jss.2023.111795&partnerID=40&md5=6b2179515faf747a9bb978922087467f	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es

Software engineering practices for machine learning — Adoption, effects, and team assessment	10.1016/j.jss.2023.111907	Machine learning (ML) is extensively used in production-ready applications, calling for mature engineering techniques to ensure robust development, deployment and maintenance. Given the potential negative impact machine learning (ML) can have on people, society or the environment, engineering techniques that can ensure robustness against technical errors and adversarial attacks are of considerable importance. In this work, we investigate how teams of experts develop, deploy and maintain software with ML components. Moreover, we link what teams do to the effects they aim to achieve and provide means for improvement. Towards this goal, we performed a mixed-methods study with a sequential exploratory strategy. First, we performed a systematic literature review through which we mined both academic and grey literature, and compiled a catalogue of engineering practices for ML. Second, we validated this catalogue using a large-scale survey, which measured the degree of adoption of the practices and their perceived effects. Third, we ran validation interviews with practitioners to add depth to the survey results. The catalogue covers a broad range of practices for engineering software systems with ML components and for ensuring non-functional properties that fall under the umbrella of trustworthy ML, such as fairness, security or accountability. Here, we present the results of our study, which indicate, for example, that larger and more experienced teams tend to adopt more practices, but that trustworthiness practices tend to be neglected. Moreover, we show that the effects measured in our survey, such as team agility or accountability, can be predicted quite accurately from groups of practices. This allowed us to contrast the importance of the practices for these effects as well as adoption rates, revealing, for example, that widely adopted practices are, in reality, less important with respect to some effects. For instance, writing reusable scripts for data cleaning and merging is highly adopted, but has a limited impact on reproducibility. Overall, our study provides a quantitative assessment of ML engineering practices and their impact on desirable properties of software with ML components, by which we open multiple avenues for improving the adoption of useful practices. Editor's note: Open Science material was validated by the Journal of Systems and Software Open Science Board. © 2023 The Author(s)	Artificial Intelligence; Engineering practices; Machine learning; Maturity Models; Software engineering	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85179133424&doi=10.1016%2Fj.jss.2023.111907&partnerID=40&md5=6e38d78e6097c3db9de699702d42b134	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
CareerVio: A Platform for Personalized Collaborative and Gamified Software Engineering MOOCs	10.1109/JCSSE54890.2022.9836240	Software engineer is one of the highest in-demand manpower jobs in the world. As the prolonged COVID19 pandemic crisis, more and more people throughout the world became unemployed. There arises an incoming demand for reskilling and career shifting to software engineer. Online learning through MOOCs is, therefore, a viable and practical solution. However, reskilling to be a software engineer requires specific platform support that is able to develop both technical and non-technical skills, including management, communication, and teamwork, that traditional MOOCs cannot fulfill the challenges. This research aims to augment the traditional MOOCs with the additional use of personalization, collaboration, and gamification theory in the name of 'CareerVio MOOCs Platform'. The distinct supports and services provided by the platform comprise team composition, team reposition, team learning, and team assessments. CareerVio enables learners to master the necessary skills required in software engineer career, enhances the interaction between learners, and allows them to take what they have learned off the page and put it into practice. © 2022 IEEE.	CareerVio; collaboration; gamification; MOOCs; personalization; software engineering	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85136236300&doi=10.1109%2FJCSSE54890.2022.9836240&partnerID=40&md5=6cb5e05f0a8d55666b48ec3b27faa9	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem avaliar
Empowering Software Engineering Students: The Role of Gamification in Promoting Learning Independence	10.1109/ICVVE63912.2024.10823948	The role of learning media greatly supports the learning process, increasing motivation and interest in the process. Learning media can also be a place to improve competence optimally through bootcamp training menus and the like with more specific training objectives. The main objective of this study is to develop a gamification-based website to enhance students' preparedness for their Final Competency Test by tackling challenges in comprehending programming absent practical experience. The learning method implemented in this website is case-based learning that integrates dynamic coding activities. The research method uses the Plomp approach with 3 main stages, namely preliminary research, prototyping, and assessment stage. The trial of the gamification website began with media and content validation followed by small group testing and large group testing. Validation by media and material experts led to the execution of small group trials (95.7%) and large group trials (91.7%), producing exceptionally positive outcomes. The results of the small group test with 12 respondents produced a very suitable value with a score of 95.7 and the large group test with 27 respondents produced a score of 91.7% with very suitable criteria. This indicates that the web-based platform is highly viable for assisting vocational students in acquiring software development skills, enhancing their preparedness for practical IT positions such as software developers and system analysts. Subsequent study involved the incorporation of gamification, such as computer-supported collaborative learning. © 2024 IEEE.	case-based learning; final competency test; gamification; learning independence; software engineering	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85217062705&doi=10.1109%2FICVVE63912.2024.10823948&partnerID=40&md5=26853cc37a08752481d4fb078aaa27f7	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Empathy, Education, and Awareness: A VR Hackathon's Approach to Tackling Climate Change	10.3390/su16062461	Climate change education is crucial for fostering informed and engaged future generations. However, traditional pedagogies often fail to engage learners fully and provide real-world, experiential learning. This paper presents a novel approach to climate change education through a three-day virtual reality (VR) hackathon. The hackathon focused on four United Nations (UN) Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)—Quality Education, Affordable and Clean Energy, Sustainable Cities and Communities, and Climate Action. Using VR technology and game design software, engineering students worked in teams. They competed against each other in designing immersive environments that demonstrated their understanding of these SDGs and climate change. Our goal was to encourage the development of empathy, education, and awareness around these critical global issues. The hackathon also integrated authentic assessments, mirroring real-world engineering tasks and providing a more practical and relevant learning experience. Our findings suggest that this VR hackathon has significantly enhanced students' understanding of the SDGs and climate change issues, their competency with VR technologies, as well as their teamwork and problem-solving skills. This paper discusses the hackathon's design, implementation, and outcomes, highlighting the potential of such innovative approaches in tackling climate change education and awareness. © 2024 by the authors.	climate change; education; renewable energy; sustainable development; virtual reality	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85189019918&doi=10.3390%2fsu16062461&partnerID=40&md5=de4278d71c53153753f37572d05da017	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Life-cycle assessment of non-domestic building stocks: A meta-analysis of current modelling methods	10.1016/j.rser.2021.111743	Building stock models (BSMs) are essential for simulating the contributions of regional and national building sectors to climate change under different policy scenarios, and for identifying pathways to climate change mitigation. To date, BSMs have focused on the operational life-cycle impacts of domestic dwellings; there has been less emphasis either on non-domestic buildings (NDBs) or full life-cycle analysis. This paper provides a first review of the theory and practice of NDB stock modelling which considers life-cycle energy, emissions and costs. A meta-analysis of the literature was undertaken involving a structured search of relevant articles in key scientific repositories. 98 in-scope studies were identified and data collected on their aims and objectives, methodologies, data sources, system boundaries, considered impacts, representativeness, uncertainty analysis, validation and verification techniques, further research identified, model transparency and software tools employed. The review necessitated the classification of modelling methodologies. The existing 'bottom-up' and 'top-down' groups were found to be ambiguous and led to confusion. Therefore, an alternative methodology classification is proposed, considering both the modelling technique and model simulation data used. The findings of the analysis indicate that most approaches use engineering models employing archetype data. However, almost all current life-cycle models of NDB stocks are incomplete. Only one study considered the full building life-cycle and most did not include uncertainty analysis. The reproducibility of study results is poor since most do not provide sufficiently-detailed information on the models and data used. Critically, there is a lack of representative input data which limits their usefulness as evidence in policymaking. © 2021 Elsevier Ltd	Building stock modelling; Classification; Life-cycle assessment; Methodology; Non-domestic buildings; Review	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85117725896&doi=10.1016%2fj.rser.2021.111743&partnerID=40&md5=149d61c6178f02a09b9ee8a8e70bbc881	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Using Active Learning to Teach Software Engineering in Game Design Courses	10.1007/978-3-031-33338-5_9	Game developers are beginning to understand it is important to approach computer game design like how all software engineers approach projects involving large numbers of people and significant investment of time. Engineering instructors often rely on the traditional lecture model when they teach topics to a classroom of students. Students often fail to engage with the material presented by lecturers. Many engineering educators regard experiential learning as an effective way to train future generations of engineers and game developers. The authors have created two courses that focus on software engineering and game development. These courses were initially offered as traditional lecture classes to both in-person and online groups of students. This chapter describes the authors' approaches to revising these game design classes to make use of flipped classroom models that rely on active learning, role-play, and gamification to cover software engineering topics in these courses. Students learn to use Agile software engineering practices to design, implement, and test game prototypes. In-person students were surveyed to measure their perceived levels of engagement with course activities. Our assessment data suggests that students attending flipped class meetings were slightly more engaged with the course materials than those taking the class offered using lectures only. Students interacting with the active learning course materials felt better able to apply their knowledge than students in a traditional lecture course. © The Author(s), under exclusive license to Springer Nature Switzerland AG 2023.	Active learning; Agile development; Game design; Role-play; Student engagement	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85196470132&doi=10.1007%2f978-3-031-33338-5_9&partnerID=40&md5=5a9cc658e1ec1c3565bbc94641ca581e	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Designing for learning during collaborative projects online: tools and takeaways	10.1108/ILS-04-2020-0095	Purpose: In response to the evolving COVID-19 pandemic, many universities have transitioned to online instruction. With learning promising to be online, at least in part, for the near future, instructors may be thinking of providing online collaborative learning opportunities to their students who are increasingly isolated from their peers because of social distancing guidelines. This paper aims to provide design recommendations for online collaborative project-based learning exercises based on this research in a software engineering course at the university level. Design/methodology/approach: Through joint work between learning scientists, course instructors and software engineering practitioners, instructional design best practices of alignment between the context of the learners, the learning objectives, the task and the assessment are actualized in the design of collaborative programming projects for supporting learning. The design, first segments a short real-time collaborative exercise into tasks, each with a problem-solving phase where students participate in collaborative programming, and a reflection phase for reflecting on what they learned in the task. Within these phases, a role-assignment paradigm scaffolds collaboration by assigning groups of four students to four complementary roles that rotate after each task. Findings: By aligning each task with granular learning objectives, significant pre- to post-test learning from the exercise as well as each task is observed. Originality/value: The roles used in the paradigm discourage divide-and-conquer tendencies often associated with collaborative projects. By requiring students to discuss conflicting ideas to arrive at a consensus implementation, their ideas are made explicit, thus providing opportunities for clarifying misconceptions through discussion and learning from the collaboration. © 2020, Emerald Publishing Limited.	Computer-supported collaborative learning; Higher education; Instructional design; Mob programming; Online collaborative Programming; Project-based online course; Software engineering	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85087043795&doi=10.1108%2fILS-04-2020-0095&partnerID=40&md5=e7942a2fb93b7ed3dc3d3eacfc9b728f	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es
Designing for Real People: Teaching Agility through User-Centric Service Design	10.1109/ICSE-SEET58685.2023.00007	We present the design and evolution of a project-based course - Designing for Real People - that aims to teach agile software development through an unwavering focus on the user, rather than emphasising the processes and tools often associated with a method like Scrum. This module is the result of a fruitful collaboration between a Computer Science Department, bringing knowledge and skills in the software engineering aspects, and the Service Design group of a neighbouring Art College, with expertise in user research and user experience design. We present the details of the current structure, content and assessment strategies developed for the module, as well as the principles behind its design. The core theme of the course is gathering and responding to feedback, and so here we present how this has been applied to the design of the module itself, with lessons learned, and improvements made over time. By reflecting on our own work, we aim to provide recommendations that may aid others considering how to teach these topics. © 2023 IEEE.	agile development; education; service design	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85171749638&doi=10.1109%2fICSE-SEET58685.2023.00007&partnerID=40&md5=c70d0c0244b331f3c37bf42728d3ae25	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
The Potential of AI-Driven Assistants in Scaled Agile Software Development	10.3390/app14010319	Scaled agile development approaches are now used widely in modern software engineering, allowing businesses to improve teamwork, productivity, and product quality. The incorporation of artificial intelligence (AI) into scaled agile development methods (SADMs) has emerged as a potential strategy in response to the ongoing demand for simplified procedures and the increasing complexity of software projects. This paper explores the intersection of AI-driven assistants within the context of the scaled agile framework (SAFe) for large-scale software development, as it stands out as the most widely adopted framework. Our paper pursues three principal objectives: (1) an evaluation of the challenges and impediments encountered by organizations during the implementation of SADMs, (2) an assessment of the potential advantages stemming from the incorporation of AI in large-scale contexts, and (3) the compilation of aspects of SADMs that AI-driven assistants enhance. Through a comprehensive systematic literature review, we identified and described 18 distinct challenges that organizations confront. In the course of our research, we pinpointed seven benefits and five challenges associated with the implementation of AI in SADMs. These findings were systematically categorized based on their occurrence either within the development phase or the phases encompassing planning and control. Furthermore, we compiled a list of 15 different AI-driven assistants and tools, subjecting them to a more detailed examination, and employing them to address the challenges we uncovered during our research. One of the key takeaways from this paper is the exceptional versatility and effectiveness of AI-driven assistants, demonstrating their capability to tackle a broader spectrum of problems. In conclusion, this paper not only sheds light on the transformative potential of AI, but also provides invaluable insights for organizations aiming to enhance their agility and management capabilities. © 2023 by the authors.	agile; AI; artificial intelligence; assistants; large-scale; SAFe; scaled agile framework; tools	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85192354993&doi=10.3390%2fapp14010319&partnerID=40&md5=f398b473542becc3545b1057216b89e6	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

<p>Correction to: Agile meets quantum: a novel genetic algorithm model for predicting the success of quantum software development project (Automated Software Engineering, (2024), 31, 1, (34), 10.1007/s10515-024-00434-z)</p>	<p>10.1007/s10515-024-00474-5</p>	<p>In this article, the Appendix section was missed during production processing from this article and should have read as follows: Appendix A: Categories, challenges, causes and their respective best practices. (Table presented.) Categories (Khan et al. 2023) Concepts (challenges(Ch)) (Khan et al. 2023) Causes Best practices (BP) Knowledge and awarness Ch1 (Knowledge gap) C1 (Lack of domain specific knowledge) [BP1], [BP2], [BP3], [BP4], [BP8], [BP10] BP1-Foster collaboration and camaraderie through structured activities, aiming to enhance interpersonal relationships and team synergy. Ch2 (Team dynamics) C2 (Lack of market intrest) [BP2], [BP5], [BP6], [BP7], [BP9] BP2-Simplify complex quantum development concepts into digestible content to improve team comprehension and application skills. Ch3 (Quantum software development education) C3 (Limited acadamic reserch) [BP2], [BP5], [BP8], [BP10] BP3-Organize regular workshops and training sessions to raise the team's awareness and proficiency in quantum software development. C4 (Funding sources) [BP6], [BP7], [BP8], [BP9] BP4-Implement strategies and exercises designed to solidify trust and unity among team members, crucial for tackling sophisticated projects. BP5-Educate teams on the extended timelines often associated with quantum development and its potential long-term technological impact. BP6-Upgrade and refine the technological infrastructure to support the unique demands of quantum software development effectively. BP7-Increase awareness within the industry about the benefits and applications of quantum software, fostering broader acceptance and investment. BP8-Provide support and resources for executing quantum software engineering research in academic settings to push the boundaries of the field. BP9-Develop a deep understanding of how quantum software systems will interact with and affect business operations and strategies. BP10-Stay informed about and integrate domain-specific best practices to ensure excellence and relevance in quantum software development. Sustainable scaling Ch4 (Ethically aligned quantum software development) C5 (Complex technical requirements) [BP13], [BP14], [BP15], [BP16] BP11-Develop agile frameworks that incorporate ethical guidelines specifically designed for quantum software development, ensuring that products are aligned with societal values and norms. Ch5 (Agile-quantum ecosystem) C6 (Cross-disciplinary integration difficulties) [BP12], [BP15], [BP16], [BP17] BP12-Form agile teams comprising experts from various disciplines to facilitate the integration of diverse knowledge, which is crucial for the complex nature of quantum software development. C7 (Rapid pace of innovation) [BP11], [BP12], [BP13], [BP14], [BP15] BP13-Establish innovation labs that operate within the agile methodology, dedicated to exploring and rapidly prototyping with emerging quantum technologies. BP14-Implement continuous learning and development programs within agile teams to keep pace with the rapid innovation in quantum computing. BP15-Create protocols that guide the effective integration of agile practices within the quantum software development process, ensuring that agility and quantum innovation complement each other. BP16-Align quantum software development projects with Sustainable Development Goals to ensure that scaling up quantum computing capabilities does not come at the expense of environmental or social sustainability. BP17-Introduce governance structures that apply agile principles to manage the complexity and ethical considerations of quantum software projects, allowing for flexibility and adaptability in decision-making processes. Quantum-aware tools and technologies Ch6 (Classic-quantum tailoring) C8 (Right tool for right job) [BP18], [BP20], [BP24] BP18-Develop and integrate agile toolkits that are tailored for quantum software development. These should facilitate the classic-quantum tailoring process and ensure that developers have the right tools for quantum-specific tasks. Ch7 (Continuous SE infrastructure) C9 (Lack of industrial interest) [BP21], [BP23], [BP25] BP19-Implement agile practices to regularly evaluate and select quantum development tools. This iterative tool assessment should be part of the sprint reviews, ensuring continuous alignment with project needs. C10 (Limited resources) [BP19], [BP21], [BP22], [BP24] BP20-Within the agile framework, allocate resources specifically for exploring and integrating quantum technologies. This addresses the limited resources challenge by earmarking investments for quantum development. BP21-Form interest groups or committees within agile teams that focus on increasing industrial interest in quantum software development through demonstrations, publications, and industry partnerships. BP22-Designate specific agile sprints to focus on the transformation process from legacy software to quantum software. These sprints would deal with refactoring, integration, and the adoption of new quantum technologies. BP23-Conduct workshops to train agile teams on how to effectively manage the technological paradigm shift, incorporating quantum computing concepts into their existing agile practices. BP24-Develop CI/CD pipelines that are capable of supporting both classical and quantum software development, ensuring that agile practices can sustain a continuous SE infrastructure. BP25-Encourage agile teams to engage in technological foresight to anticipate and prepare for future shifts in quantum technology, integrating this into their sprint planning and backlog refinement. Standards & specifications Ch8 (Processes standardization) C11 (Varying Interpretations of Agile Methodologies) [BP29], [BP32] BP26-Develop maturity models specific to agile-quantum development to assess and guide teams on their journey towards optimized agile practices in quantum software creation. Ch9 (Optimum documentation) C12 (Rapid Evolution of Quantum Technologies) [BP27], [BP28], [BP31], [BP32], [BP34] BP27-Institute standard assessment protocols that evaluate the effectiveness of agile practices and</p>	<p>https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85211588108&doi=10.1007%2fs10515-024-00474-5&partnerID=40&md5=43e31515da1ec4a4320fa5f69ffde82d</p>	<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-between; align-items: center;"> <div style="width: 20px; height: 20px; background-color: green; border: 1px solid black; display: flex; align-items: center; justify-content: center;"> <input type="checkbox"/> </div> <div style="width: 20px; height: 20px; background-color: red; border: 1px solid black; display: flex; align-items: center; justify-content: center;"> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> </div> </div>	<p>sem colab</p>
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Code-quality evaluation scheme for assessment of student contributions to programming projects	10.1016/j.jss.2022.111273	Project-based learning is the most common approach to software engineering education, due to its emphasis on the teamwork skills essential to real-world collaborations. This study developed an automated programming assessment system (APAS) featuring a code-quality evaluation scheme to overcome difficulties in assessing the contribution of individual team members. Team participation is visualized on a weekly basis to provide insights pertaining to team dynamics, and metrics based on code quality allow the segmentation of students by level of contribution. Insights provided by the proposed system were also shown to facilitate interventions aimed at improving code quality. Empirical analysis based on submission data from 146 students (41 teams) demonstrated the feasibility of the proposed system in monitoring group-based learning projects at the university level, particularly in detecting free-riders. © 2022	Automated programming assessment system; Cooperative/collaborative learning; Programming education; Project-based learning; Quality	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85126357023&doi=10.1016%2Fj.jss.2022.111273&partnerID=40&md5=becc03f9d7161829b62a46162b7da409	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es
Diversity and Teamwork in Student Software Teams	10.1145/3593663.3593687	Diversity is becoming an increasingly relevant topic in software engineering. A higher diversity rate in professional software teams has been shown to positively influence communication, innovation, and performance. Understanding whether similar effects exist in software development teams at an educational level would be important to identify potential challenges and opportunities that might affect students at later professional stages. Therefore, in this paper we investigate the impact of diversity on key teamwork skills such as communication, collaboration, and productivity in student software development teams. In particular, we conducted several surveys on project work progress throughout an introductory software engineering course with students and their tutors regarding these teamwork metrics. We investigate how the self-assessments and the project outcomes relate to seven aspects of diversity, and find correlations between teamwork satisfaction and team diversity. We see deteriorations in certain teamwork metrics over the project timeline - independently of the team diversity. Our findings suggest that the impact of diversity on student teams may be more complex than on professional teams: diversity minorities in teams may feel frustrated more easily. Consequently, it is important to ensure that software development courses maintain motivation and decrease possible frustrations regarding teamwork. © 2023 ACM.	collaborative learning; computing education; Diversity; teamwork	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85163514843&doi=10.1145%2F3593663.3593687&partnerID=40&md5=c3af8495e51014640e0f1b913b3132a4	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem avaliar
arPcTECHture' - a gamified educational 3D virtual world for introductory concepts in computer architecture	10.1109/EDUCON5253.7.2022.9766679	Gamified assessments have been mainly implemented for STEM education, focusing on motivational objectives and performance evaluation of teaching-learning processes. This paper presents a gamified educational 3D virtual world developed to provide a complementary tool for teaching software engineering students the fundamental concepts of computer hardware. The research design follows the needs identified across a focus group, but the prototype may also serve as support for K-12 with technical specializations. A beta-test has concluded that the learning outcome is improved when a gamification framework is provided. The engagement level has been assessed among engineering students, validating the prototype as a new complementary method for an Applied Informatics laboratory. © 2022 IEEE.	computer hardware architecture; Gamification; serious game; user experience assessment	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85130484039&doi=10.1109%2FEDUCON52537.2022.9766679&partnerID=40&md5=71267bf685b69f91448ba dd57af0fbf7	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Does Interdisciplinary Creative Coding Boost Creativity? A Mixed Methods Approach	10.21427/EEWB-NV85	This study explores the influence of an interdisciplinary intervention on creative problem-solving skills. Literature deems such skills as vital for software engineering (SE) students in higher education. 39 SE students and graphic design (GD) students were randomly paired to work on an open-ended creative coding assignment in p5.js, an online JS-based Processing editor that makes it easy for novices to quickly and easily code visual webpages. Three categories were formed: the test group SE+GD (18 students), and control groups SE+SE (10) and GD+GD (11). A mixed methods approach was taken to gather and interpret results: Amabile's Consensual Assessment Technique provided a global creativity score for the finished product, the Creative Programming Problem Solving Test assessed three dimensions of the creative process (Ability, Mindset, Interaction), and 9 semi-structured follow-up interviews provided context and revealed underlying themes. The results indicate that, while the creativity of the end product initially takes a hit, the SE+GD groups' socio-interactive creativity levels increased. We also observed fixed mindsets towards creativity ("design students are more creative than we") that call for future work. © 2023 SEFI 2023 - 51st Annual Conference of the European Society for Engineering Education: Engineering Education for Sustainability, Proceedings. All Rights Reserved.	Creative Programming Problem Solving Test; Creativity; Interdisciplinarity; Software Engineering Education	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85179846132&doi=10.21427%2FEEWB-NV85&partnerID=40&md5=025a4e0842ec621322df21847702063e	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Using GitHub Analytics to Assess the Quality of Collaboration in Software Engineering Teams	10.1109 /FIE61694. 2024.10892887	This research-to-practice full paper investigates using team process analytics from GitHub to support team management. Effective teamwork is essential in higher education learning and workplace success. The role of educators in supporting proper team functioning includes helping students learn how to participate actively and communicate effectively in meetings, delegate work fairly, manage high-quality work throughput, and resolve conflicts if problems arise. Problems often emerge when team members have differing visions or individuals do not contribute equally to the work output. These problems are exacerbated in large classes involving many teams. Detecting these potential issues in teams and helping students work through them is important for team success. In software engineering projects, monitoring individual contributions can begin with mining activities on programming platforms such as GitHub, which makes much of the individual contributions more visible and quantifiable. In this work, we propose a framework for fairly assessing teamwork and present the development of team analytics to assist educators in detecting potential issues in team collaboration. We describe a pilot study involving this tool in the context of a software engineering capstone course with 104 students split into 22 teams managed by 4 teaching assistants. Our results show that the reports offer value in guiding the evaluation process and identifying where problems may be, but do not replace the actual repository analysis where needed. We discuss the potential value of using this tool to improve collaboration. © 2024 IEEE.	Capstone assessment; collaboration analytics; collaboration assessment; GitHub assessments; GitHub metrics; pull request metrics	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-105000774016&doi=10.1109%2FIE61694.2024.10892887&partnerID=40&md5=5cc18842fe6b4031087ad4b810a68568	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem educacao
Generating Team Quality Formula to Predict Product Quality in Software Engineering Project of College Students	10.1109 /ICTS52701. 2021.9607916	In the CHAOS report 2020 released by the Standish Group, 'a good team' is an essential factor in determining the success of a project. Therefore, team quality assessment becomes significant for team management. Furthermore, it has believed that the quality of the product developed represents the quality of the development team. For this reason, it is necessary to measure the quality of the team at any point, so we can take mitigation steps to improve the quality. The study has two aims: (1) to build a team quality measurement model to prove that team quality positively correlates with product quality and (2) to produce a team quality formula to predict product quality. We conducted the study on ten teams with 57 students who attended the Software Development Workshop class. The students applied self-assessment to assess the quality of the team. In addition, software development practitioners carried out product quality assessments. The method used to obtain a relationship between the two is the Pearson correlation. We generated a team quality measurement formula using the Brute Force method. This study proves that the quality of the development team has a positive correlation with the quality of the product developed by 0.87. Meanwhile, the team quality formula can be used as a reference to predict the quality of the product developed © 2021 IEEE.	Capacity building; Product quality; Software development; Team quality; Team quality formula	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85123275703&doi=10.1109%2FICTS52701.2021.9607916&partnerID=40&md5=56bdebd29ed13e5b4b4018dcf10ab93b	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Group Assignments and Support Aimed to Develop Student Teamwork Skills and a Positive Attitude Towards Teamwork in Computer Science Higher Education	10.1145 /3702212. 3702215	The IT industry nowadays puts a lot of focus on teamwork. Therefore, helping Computer Science (CS) Higher Education (HE) degree students develop teamwork skills should be seen as essential for their future employability. One way of doing this is by getting students to practice teamwork through group assignments. However, this poses challenges in ensuring fairness and student equality. Moreover, a negative student attitude towards teamwork can lead to discontent and resistance to contributing to team activities. This paper presents efforts towards developing an approach to group assignments, and associated support, that aim to tackle the above issues. These were applied in an introductory undergraduate second year Software Engineering course in the School of Informatics of the University of Edinburgh. They were evaluated with students using four questionnaires and course feedback. Results were varied and some unexpected. They showcase that, on one hand, bringing teamwork into teaching can enhance students' teamwork skills and improve their attitude towards teamwork. On the other, efforts to offer equal chances of success in the assignment can lead to feelings of inequality and unfairness amongst high achievers, and fear of discussions with peers can lead to unfair marks for students who do not pull their weight. © 2025 Copyright held by the owner/author(s).	assessment fairness; attitude towards teamwork; employability; group assignments; student equality; teamwork skills	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85219167527&doi=10.1145%2F3702212.3702215&partnerID=40&md5=09637a6b21c105d3862424534e98120f	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	chance

Managing Group Projects in Undergraduate Computing	10.1145/3587103.3594163	This panel convenes four educators, each from different institutions and each with experience managing group projects. Their expertise spans topics including: peer assessment and peer evaluation; entrepreneurship; transdisciplinarity; internationalisation; inclusivity; social values; educational technology and tools; feedback and feed-forward; peer rating; free-riders; as well as blended learning; and post-pandemic online discourse. They reflect on the delight of seeing students collaborate to deliver meaningful projects as well as the challenges posed by disengaged students. They also explore a common theme of discordance inherent to teamwork and systems to support student communities. © 2023 Owner/Author.	collaborative learning; curriculum; education management; employability; group; industry; peer; peer assessment; professional skills; project-based learning; software engineering; team	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85166333469&doi=10.1145%2f3587103.3594163&partnerID=40&md5=f60e5bbd8958236c2a151f3f45776c23	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es
Functional Correlations in the Pursuit of Performance Assessment of Classifiers	10.1142/S0218001420510131	In statistical classification and machine learning, as well as in social and other sciences, a number of measures of association have been proposed for assessing and comparing individual classifiers, raters, as well as their groups. In this paper, we introduce, justify, and explore several new measures of association, which we call CO-, ANTI-, and COANTI-correlation coefficients, that we demonstrate to be powerful tools for classifying confusion matrices. We illustrate the performance of these new coefficients using a number of examples, from which we also conclude that the coefficients are new objects in the sense that they differ from those already in the literature. © 2020 World Scientific Publishing Company.	classifier; confusion matrix; Functional correlation; rater; weighted kappa	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85083799930&doi=10.1142%2fS0218001420510131&partnerID=40&md5=eb2142dc1a34d03c1d4e471a6c1d7895	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Gamification Powered by a Large Language Model to Enhance Flipped Classroom Learning in Undergraduate Computer Science	10.34190/ecgbl.18.1.2630	The flipped classroom in computer science has become a popular pedagogy where students complete preparatory reading and videos before class, leaving class time for hands-on practice. In theory, students come to class predisposed with knowledge to complete programming tasks, quizzes, and homework assignments. However, if students do not complete or do not fully understand the preparatory material, those students will not be equipped for class and may also be embarrassed to ask questions during class. In this study, we created a gamified quiz that is powered by a Large Language Model (LLM) that loads in questions from the flipped content transcripts. The game offers students a fun assessment after completing the flipped content that will both motivate them and prepare them for class. The game also provides an anonymous way for students to ask questions as they progress through the game content. Those questions can then be analysed by the instructor and reviewed in class. The study compares in-class quiz scores of a control group versus a group that had access to the gamified quiz in an undergraduate software engineering course over three consecutive course modules. The results obtained from both quantitative and qualitative data are promising, showing an increase in student in-class quiz scores along with positive student engagement with the gamified quiz. Students also reported that the game made them more comfortable with asking questions. Future work would extend this research to more students and over a longer period. The LLM and gamification also have much potential, where games can be created dynamically and be customized and personalized for each student's needs. This work shows an exciting gap in research that could lead to gamified experiences for students in the flipped model that are both relevant and personalized with the use of a LLM, offering the students the greatest chance for success. © 2024 Dechema e.V.. All rights reserved.	Computer Science Education; Engagement; Feedback; Flipped Classroom; Games; Gamification; Gamified Learning; Large Language Models; Satisfaction	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85212953568&doi=10.34190%2fecgbl.18.1.2630&partnerID=40&md5=1cb19aa197c707b3b587122d03ab1f05	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Task Versus Process: A Taxonomy for Group Projects	10.1007/978-3-031-29386-3_14	Group projects appear to be a mandatory requirement of undergraduate degree programmes in software engineering and other, similar courses. But what are these projects for, and what do we expect students to learn from them? Often the group project exists within the curriculum simply because it is required by various authorities and without a clear pedagogic rationale. The language used in module specifications usually refers to employability skills and collaborative working, but often disguises a wide range of different delivery approaches. Assessment regimes may prioritise outputs over the process of producing those outputs. Even the word "process" is ambiguous. Do we mean the systems development process or the group process? If the former, why do we need a group? If the latter, how can this be assessed to the satisfaction of students and external examiners? The "Task Versus Process" taxonomy firstly suggests a model for categorising the aims and objectives of the group project, secondly, evinces an appropriate assessment strategy and finally suggests some approaches that can be taken if staff teams wish to address the "Personal Development" quadrant of the taxonomy. The chapter contextualise the student group project within broader aspects of curriculum design and then attempts to clarify the multifarious and often contradictory objectives proposed for student group projects. Fully appreciating what it is we, as instructors hope to achieve in group projects takes us beyond resigning ourselves to the compulsory inclusion of the project. Projects offer the opportunity to help our students achieve their full potential and to actually deliver the learning outcomes. © Springer Nature Switzerland AG 2018, 2023.	Group project assessment; Learning and teaching strategy; Student group projects	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85122839567&doi=10.1007%2F978-3-031-29386-3_14&partnerID=40&md5=ad9ff971d739b0c8b1366a15f6ca503f	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
20 Years of EPICS at Butler University: Experiences and Lessons Learned	10.1109/FIE58773.2023.10343064	This research-to-practice full paper discusses experiences and lessons learned from our EPICS@BUTLER (Engineering Projects in Community Service at Butler) program. The program, housed within the department of Computer Science and Software Engineering, is part of a college of Liberal Arts and Sciences and serves a diverse population of students with multi-disciplinary backgrounds. The EPICS curriculum is driven by a team-based service-learning pedagogical model. EPICS teams learn how to work together effectively while addressing the immediate IT needs of our non-profit partner clients, navigating their budgetary restrictions, and coping with any lack of existing IT infrastructure. During the 2020/2021 academic year, we launched an empirical study to review and assess EPICS@BUTLER. The study's main goal was to learn from the past 20 years of running the EPICS program by soliciting input from all parties involved. We aimed to improve and expand our service-learning model within an LAS context. More specifically, this study included surveying alumni and current undergraduate students in order to understand the successes and areas of potential improvement within our program. In addition, we conducted one-on-one interviews with our community non-profit partners as well as volunteer team mentors to assess the program's effectiveness and community impact. Based on the empirical data we gathered and analyzed, we discuss how the existing curriculum is effective at providing fulfilling experiences which help our alumni secure jobs after graduation. In addition, we found that the practice of allowing supervised teams to navigate their own EPICS projects helps them improve their professional maturity and interpersonal skills. In summary, this paper discusses an empirical study and aims to leverage the results gathered from our surveys and interviews in order to present a plan for continuous improvement and modernization of our on-going EPICS program. In closing, our paper describes a concise roadmap and offers practical recommendations for implementing a similar EPICS program at other potentially interested academic institutions. © 2023 IEEE.	Course assessment; EPICS; Service-Learning; Software Engineering; Teamwork	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85183026119&doi=10.1109%2FIE58773.2023.10343064&partnerID=40&md5=50099bfd566a1470408485569eab5582	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem avaliar
Organizational Culture from the Focus of Values in Competition: Current and Desired Situation in the University of the Armed Forces ESPE	10.1007/978-3-030-68083-1_4	This work is part of the inter university research project titled "Study of the Organizational Culture; Situation in the Classroom and University Development in Higher Education Institutions of Ecuador". In this specific case, we determine the current and desired cultural typology in the University of the Armed Forces ESPE. The cultural gap is identified, and the cultural characteristics are analyzed according with the methodology of values in competition by Cameron and Quinn. For the effect, the Organizational Culture Assessment Instrument OCAI test is applied in a random manner and given to 450 members of the institution that correspond to 131 professors, 185 students and 134 public servers. The study is complemented with the application of interviews and focal groups. The results divulge that the current dominant culture is hierarchical; meanwhile the desired organizational culture is a clan type. There is evidence that the institution is very controlled and structured, the leadership is considered as an example of guidance and training, the management style offers security and protection of its members, the rules and formal policies provoke unity. © 2021, The Author(s), under exclusive license to Springer Nature Switzerland AG.	Cultural characteristics; Cultural gap; Higher education; OCAI; Organizational culture	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85104855076&doi=10.1007%2F978-3-030-68083-1_4&partnerID=40&md5=b87c7673fc68cde79b935f6ee48a3b32	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Developing a Multiprofessional Mobile App to Enhance Health Habits in Older Adults: User-Centered Approach	10.2196/54214	<p>Background: Although comprehensive lifestyle habits are crucial for healthy aging, their adherence tends to decline as individuals grow older. Sustaining a healthy life over time poses a motivational challenge. Some digital tools, such as smartphone apps aimed at promoting healthy habits, have been used to counteract this decline. However, a more profound investigation is necessary into the diverse experiences of users, particularly when it concerns older adults or those who are unfamiliar with information and communications technologies. Objective: We aimed to develop a mobile app focused on promoting the health of older adults based on the principles of software engineering and a user-centered design. The project respected all ethical guidelines and involved the participation of older adults at various stages of the development of the app. Methods: This study used a mixed methods approach, combining both quantitative and qualitative methodologies for data collection. The study was conducted in Ribeirão Preto, São Paulo, Brazil, and involved 20 older adults of both genders who were aged ≥60 years and enrolled in the Physical Education Program for the Elderly at the University of São Paulo. The research unfolded in multiple phases, encompassing the development and refinement of the app with active engagement from the participants. Results: A total of 20 participants used a mobile health app with an average age of 64.8 (SD 2.7) years. Most participants had a high school education, middle-class status, and varying health literacy (mean score 73.55, SD 26.70). Overall, 90% (18/20) of the participants owned smartphones. However, 20% (4/20) of the participants faced installation challenges and 30% (6/20) struggled with web-based searches. The focus groups assessed app usability and satisfaction. Adjustments increased satisfaction scores significantly (Suitability Assessment of Materials: 34.89% to 70.65%; System Usability Scale: 71.23 to 87.14). Participant feedback emphasized font size, navigation, visual feedback, and personalization, and suggestions included health device integration, social interaction, and in-app communication support. Conclusions: This study contributes to the development of health care technologies tailored to the older adult population, considering their specific needs. It is anticipated that the resulting app will serve as a valuable tool for promoting healthy habits and enhancing the quality of life for older adults. © 2024 JMIR Publications Inc.. All rights reserved.</p>	digital competencies; digital inclusion; digital skills; focus groups; health care; health literacy; health promotion; ICTs; KEYWORDS information and communications technologies; mobile phone; usability; user	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85193017176&doi=10.2196%2f54214&partnerID=40&md5=1fbba712915c677b800376c07f69ec72	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Measure Students' Contribution in Web Programming Projects by Exploring Source Code Repository	10.1109/ICS51289.2020.00099	<p>Large scale software systems are usually developed by multiple teams. Communication and collaboration skills are required as essential skills of qualified developers in the modern environment, in addition to the technical hard skills of software engineering. Therefore, group projects are included in almost courses to train students' professional skills and teamwork abilities. However, in their group projects, most of the students are only required to accomplish functional requirements with limited awareness about the quality of the software. This issue seriously affects the development speed, since it is difficult for team members to read others' code during the development process. Hence, we propose a quality-driven assessment system for group projects with the capability of checking the coding style after each submission and providing immediate feedback to help student teams maintain the code quality for their group projects. Besides, to objectively assess the contribution of all students in group projects, we propose a set of repository mining metrics including two major categories of productivity and quality. A case study about the usage of the system and the proposed contribution evaluation metrics are introduced to illustrate the feasibility of our approach. © 2020 IEEE.</p>	Automation; Code Quality; Continuous Integration; Group Project	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85102200802&doi=10.1109%2fICS51289.2020.00099&partnerID=40&md5=dd381384593b51c17a60c0c51611b3	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
A Chatbot that Uses a Multi-agent Organization to Support Collaborative Learning	10.1007/978-3-030-78645-8_4	<p>This work investigates and apply the use of a multi-agent system to assist in the coordination of group tasks, specifically in educational environments, in which the interaction occurs indirectly, that is, asynchronously. The system has a web interface integrated with a chatbot for more natural interaction. The chatbot communicates with the multi-agent system that is responsible for the organization of the group, that is, it contains information about the tasks and members of the groups, in addition to restrictions that can be imposed according to the organization of the group, and it is also able to return the requested information in natural language through the chatbot. This approach was validated in a practical undergraduate course of software engineering. The students assessed the functionalities and usability of the system while working in groups in order to develop software collaboratively. Our system was used to assist students in a real project. With this assessment, it was found that the system was able to support the development of the group tasks, ensuring quick and consistent responses to the student's request. © 2021, Springer Nature Switzerland AG.</p>	Chatbot; Dialogflow; Group coordination; JaCaMo; Multi-agent system	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85112075007&doi=10.1007%2f978-3-030-78645-8_4&partnerID=40&md5=59b2ae79e511d8863e74d880c0812e9e	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Team performance assessment and improvement in an agile methodology framework	10.1109/CLEI56649.2022.9959959	Improving the performance of work teams is a key issue for any organization because it has a direct impact on the productivity and quality involved in the generation of its products and/or in the provision of the services it offers. The performance of a team can be increased through improvements in the performance of each of its members or the team as a whole. There are several mechanisms to try to achieve performance improvements, however, for a correct orientation of possible actions, it is necessary to evaluate the current performance of the team and each of its members to highlight possible weaknesses or opportunities for improvement. An improvement process is by nature continuous, changes are incorporated gradually and at the same time, the achievements must be reinforced. Agile methods are closely aligned with improvement performance of teams. For instance, Scrum establishes Retrospective Meetings which are exclusively dedicated to continuous improvement of teamwork. This paper proposes a model for assessment and improvement of team performance within an agile methodological framework. In addition, a support tool that implements the model is presented. The model and its tool have been developed and refined through its application for more than a decade in two software engineering subjects. In these subjects, we apply the Project-Based Learning (PBL) teaching method, according to this the students work as a team throughout the subject in a software development project. Although our proposal has been generated in the academic field, we think that it can also be applied and be useful in an industrial context. © 2022 IEEE.	agile methods.; high-performance teams; performance assesment; Teamwork	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85143909893&doi=10.1109%2FCLEI56649.2022.9959959&partnerID=40&md5=0d67351677d4d6d511011d7a2ed4e3b6	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es
Retrospect and Prospect of International Engineering Education Research in the Past Decade	10.1145/3459012.3459024	Object: To understand the progress, hotspots and trends of international engineering education research and development, and provide reference for further research through visual analysis of papers published in 3 engineering education journals of SSCI. Methods: We use the Web of Science database as the search source, select ""Journal of Engineering Education"", ""Journal of Professional Issues in Engineering Education and Practice"", ""International Journal of Engineering Education""for publications, and obtain article type documents published in the above journals from 2010 to 2019. We Use the information visualization analysis software called Citespace to perform statistical analysis, and understand the author groups, publishing institutions, research hotspots, time evolution and frontier fields. Results: A total of 2,323 papers are included in this study, and the number of papers published each year is between 201 and 253. ""International Journal of Engineering Education""is the journal with the most papers, Purdue University is the institution with the most papers, and Borrego, M. is the author who published the most papers. As of September 27, 2020, the average number of paper citations is 6.4, the H-index index is 47, the overall number of citations reached 8941, and a total of 15 papers have been cited more than 80 times; a total of 27 keywords frequency reached 50 times, and the keywords formed 7 clusters. Conclusion: In the past 10 years, international engineering education research has developed well. American universities are more prominent in this field, forming a number of high-level research institutions and core author groups to lead relevant research development; the research hotspots included educational innovation and communication, curriculum design, teaching reform, student motivation survey, Interdisciplinary development, conceptual enlightenment, quality evaluation, etc. are the focus of the industry; assessment tools, gender, sustainability, ethics, computer engineering education, educational technology, virtual reality. © 2021 ACM.	Engineering education; Research papers; Visual analysis	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85111760264&doi=10.1145%2F3459012.3459024&partnerID=40&md5=da6aa4526da223721f1f0a1eb060d1ee	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
A Systematic Mapping of Variables Studied in Research Related to Education in Informatics And Computing	10.16920/jeet/2022/v36i2/22159	Previous theoretical studies (reviews and systematic mappings) have only focused on certain variables of the education of Informatics and Computing such as game-based learning, project-based learning, and problem-based learning. Therefore, the objective of this article was to carry out a systematic mapping (2010-2019) to determine which variables are studied in research related to the education of informatics and computing. We performed a systematic mapping to IEEE Xplore (2010-2019). The protocol corresponds to the PRISMA guidelines for systematic reviews and its contextualization to the performance of systematic mappings. When applying the protocol, 160 articles were finally selected of which 154 are indexed in Scopus (96.25%) and 132 indexed in Scopus and WoS (82.5%). The results highlight that the most studied variables are teaching programming, teaching software engineering, teamwork, collaborative learning, educational technology, assessment, project-based learning, problem-based learning, and game-based learning. There is evidence of a cause-effect relationship (multiple correlations) between the dependent variables: teaching of software engineering and teaching of programming with the independent variables: didactic models based on m-learning, e-learning, and b-learning, project-based learning, problem-based learning, artificial intelligence, and educational technology. It concludes by identifying the principal's studies (higher scientific productivity) and the most studied variables in the didactics of Informatics and Computing. © 2022, Rajarambapu Institute Of Technology. All rights reserved.	computer education; engineering education; Informatics; programming teaching; software engineering teaching; systematic mapping	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85142475839&doi=10.16920%2Fjeet%2F2022%2Fv36i2%2F22159&partnerID=40&md5=638e5896288ef7eb9519af29130485f2	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es

The landscape and gaps in open source fairness toolkits	10.1145/3411764.3445261	With the surge in literature focusing on the assessment and mitigation of unfair outcomes in algorithms, several open source fairness toolkits' recently emerged to make such methods widely accessible. However, little studied are the differences in approach and capabilities of existing fairness toolkits, and their fit-for-purpose in commercial contexts. Towards this, this paper identifies the gaps between the existing open source fairness toolkit capabilities and the industry practitioners' needs. Specifically, we undertake a comparative assessment of the strengths and weaknesses of six prominent open source fairness toolkits, and investigate the current landscape and gaps in fairness toolkits through an exploratory focus group, a semi-structured interview, and an anonymous survey of data science/machine learning (ML) practitioners. We identify several gaps between the toolkits' capabilities and practitioner needs, highlighting areas requiring attention and future directions towards tooling that better support fairness in practice'. © 2021 ACM.		https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85106690246&doi=10.1145%2F3411764.3445261&partnerID=40&md5=5e273f8c5e7fce93bd9df9ede989bd7	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
A strategy to support Engineering Education teaching staff monitoring students' learning process: Metacognitive Challenges	10.5281/zenodo.7062198	It is increasingly required that Engineering Education courses include activities that promote the development of cognitive skills, such as metacognition. However, including such activities is challenging for lecturers, particularly in Distance Learning contexts. It is also complex, when working online, for teaching staff to carry out monitoring of the metacognitive learning processes of students, understand their difficulties, and provide formative feedback. In this work, we present the design and discussion of a pedagogical strategy: Metacognitive Challenges (MC), which allows lecturers to monitor the evolution of students' perceptions regarding their learning process We discuss how lecturers can use MCs for formative assessment and how to weave this intervention with individual students or groups. The Design Science Research methodology was adopted for the design, implementation, and demonstration of MCs, applied in a Software Engineering course within a distance learning Informatics Engineering undergraduate programme. We exemplify how MCs have the potential to support monitoring of students' cognitive and metacognitive processes and offer a set of guidelines on how the teaching staff can use them. In future work, we intend to evaluate the effectiveness of MCs in different teaching contexts, and develop technological solutions that facilitate the monitoring process (reduce the time and effort required for analysis of MC content). © 2022 University of Minho. All rights reserved.	Co-regulation of Learning; Cognitive process monitoring; Metacognition; Self-regulation; Software Engineering Education	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85139847505&doi=10.5281%2Fzenodo.7062198&partnerID=40&md5=e1494832a6348c35b144bfc80a9c9f19	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Digging into group establishment: Intervention design and evaluation	10.1016/j.jss.2021.110974	Previous research has documented challenges in students' group work. An identifiable segment of the previous research that relates to improving students' group work conditions is the study of group formation and self- and peer-assessment. Though studies that primarily focus on how to address the conditions of students' group work and the existing problems can be found, there are not many related to higher education settings. On this ground, the present article advances a qualitative evaluation of the intervention that promotes student groups' self-awareness and thereby self-regulation toward fair group work during a software engineering project. An inductive thematic analysis was applied to the students' written reflections on the intervention. To further understand the results, the concept of "group establishment," referring to destructiveness that complicates individuals' truthful living at the group level, was employed to reflect on the resulting themes. Hoggett (1998) provided this articulation by synthesizing previous results in psychoanalytic theory. Students' experiences with the intervention revealed several value gains, including personally identified benefits as well as open group mood, consolidation of grouping, conceptual learning about group work, and regulation for task allocation. Noted challenges included dishonesty and a personal role conflict, and some students reported minor effects on group performance. Students valued safety in the intervention situation and argued that the intervention was needed from outside the group. A summative review of the students' experiences suggests that the intervention was useful for all groups. The results are discussed from a pedagogic and the aforementioned psychoanalytic perspective, and remarks are made for software engineering education. © 2021	Group establishment; Group work; Intervention; Justice; Software engineering education	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85105693246&doi=10.1016%2Fj.jss.2021.110974&partnerID=40&md5=2992b10c7629112c2537151c31e71678	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Exploring the Assessment List for Trustworthy AI in the Context of Advanced Driver-Assistance Systems	10.1109 /SEthics52569.2021.00009	Artificial Intelligence (AI) is increasingly used in critical applications. Thus, the need for dependable AI systems is rapidly growing. In 2018, the European Commission appointed experts to a High-Level Expert Group on AI (AI-HLEG). AI- HLEG defined Trustworthy AI as 1) lawful, 2) ethical, and 3) robust and specified seven corresponding key requirements. To help development organizations, AI-HLEG recently published the Assessment List for Trustworthy AI (ALTAI). We present an illustrative case study from applying ALTAI to an ongoing development project of an Advanced Driver-Assistance System (ADAS) that relies on Machine Learning (ML). Our experience shows that ALTAI is largely applicable to ADAS development, but specific parts related to human agency and transparency can be disregarded. Moreover, bigger questions related to societal and environmental impact cannot be tackled by an ADAS supplier in isolation. We present how we plan to develop the ADAS to ensure ALTAI-compliance. Finally, we provide three recommendations for the next revision of ALTAI, i.e., life-cycle variants, domainspecific adaptations, and removed redundancy. © 2021 IEEE.	automotive software; ethics; functional safety; machine learning; trustworthy AI	https://www.scopus.com/inward/rec ord.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85113233819&doi=10.1109%2FSEthics52569.2021.00009 &partnerID=40&md5=381ee8f9de4f0758d6a3d1c57c6e76ff	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Entrepreneurially-Minded Program Assessment During Emergency Situations: Using Photovoice to Understand Customer (Engineering Student) Needs	10.52202 /066488-0104	CONTEXT: Innovation, design, and entrepreneurship are economic drivers promoting competition and growth throughout the world, many of which would not exist without well-established continuous improvement and new product development processes. Continuous improvement and new product development processes, such as the lean start-up methodology and design thinking, are well known and thriving in the business world due to the vast amount of empirically-grounded research. Unfortunately, educational institutions and researchers, alike, are lagging when it comes to these processes. Although the quantity of new and transformative degree offerings has increased substantially over the past several decades, limited research has been conducted to document key procedures associated with continuous improvement and the creation of new programs. This problem is only exacerbated when considering the role of innovation during emergency situations. PURPOSE OR GOAL: The purpose of this study is to show one approach (using photovoice) to understand how student voices can be incorporated into the continuous improvement and new program development process, specifically during emergency situations. In contrast to traditional passive data collection methods, such as a survey or focus groups, photovoice is an active data collection method where students engage in the information sharing and interpretation process at a deeper level. Using photovoice, researchers and practitioners, alike, can gain greater insights into the who, what, and how of educational effectiveness. The guiding research question is as follows: What are the factors which can influence the discovery, evaluation, and exploitation of continuous improvement and new program development during emergency situations? APPROACH OR METHODOLOGY/METHODS: This approach uses participatory research, wherein students act as researchers and actively participate in the data collection and analysis process. Under the umbrella of participatory research, the study uses photovoice for collecting qualitative data. The study was implemented in a software engineering course at a university located in the United Kingdom. Students responded to the photovoice prompts by supplying both picture and narrative. The prompts target student perceptions (positive and negative) with respect to blended learning perceptions, technology integration, and career preparedness. The qualitative data was analyzed for themes using NVivo. ACTUAL OR ANTICIPATED OUTCOMES: Analysis of the qualitative data led the researchers to identify three core themes related to the blended learning approach implemented as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic: (1) Institution - macro level, (2) Instruction - mezzo level, and (3) Student - micro level. CONCLUSIONS: The study concludes with recommendations for various higher education benefactors of the user generated data including administration, faculty, marketing, recruitment, advisors, and the students, themselves. It is intended for the overall recommendations to have a direct impact on improving the student experience. Copyright © Lisa Bosman, Usman Naeem, Eranjan Padumadasa, 2021.	emergency situations; Entrepreneurial mindset; program assessment	https://www.scopus.com/inward/rec ord.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85146120205&doi=10.52202%2F066488-0104&partnerID=40&md5=7684b3017aa4a439c8a68a1a6157bd96	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Effects of Group Size, Choice and Membership in Group Assignments Aimed At Developing Student Employability	10.1145/3689535.3689540	Graduate employability is high on the agenda of UK universities. In Computer Science degrees, teamwork is an essential employability skill to develop. Group and authentic assignments can help students develop their teamwork. However, there is no consensus on the best group size, choice and membership for students in such assignments. This poster represents a reflection on experience in trying out different size, choice and membership approaches over four years of running an introductory undergraduate Software Engineering course in the School of Informatics of the University of Edinburgh. Findings revealed the absence of a perfect approach and the need to base decisions on course priorities. © 2024 Owner/Author.	authentic assessment; employability; equality of chances for success; group assignments; teamwork skills	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85211334049&doi=10.1145%2F3689535.3689540&partnerID=40&md5=555a9d20a31d6279dc19f007d7c7b778	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem avaliar
Exploring the Adaptability and Usefulness of Git-Truck for Assessing Software Capstone Project Development	10.1145/3641554.3701798	In software engineering pedagogy, a persistent challenge is the comprehensive assessment of student contributions within software repositories. This study delves into the investigation of the GitTruck tool, initially designed for professional software engineers, and explores its adaptability and effectiveness within an academic setting. We specifically focus on the tool's potential for educators when assessing Capstone software repositories. Our results emphasize that educators found bubble chart visualization and metrics such as "Top Contributor" and "Number of Commits" helpful in understanding group dynamics and contribution. We also discuss the tool's limitations among visual techniques and metrics used. As the educational landscape shifts towards increased virtual and remote modalities, tools like Git-Truck are poised to augment the intricacy and depth of software project evaluations. For those considering adopting or adapting such tools in similar contexts, our study offers the challenges and lessons learned from this experience. © 2025 Copyright held by the owner/author(s).	Capstone Courses; Software Engineering Education; Visualizing Software Projects	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-86000268062&doi=10.1145%2F3641554.3701798&partnerID=40&md5=b26c9ea2dcdf2c6d652f9bbbc0c0c296	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Preliminary Evaluation of a Survey Checklist in the Context of Evidence-based Software Engineering Education	10.5220/0010496204370444	Background: In order to judge evidence it is important to be able to assess study quality. Checklists are means to objectify the assessment. In an earlier study we proposed and evaluated a checklist for surveys, which was assessed by experts. Objective: (1) To assess whether the use of the checklist enables students with limited experience in research to consistently and accurately assess the quality of a research paper. (2) To elicit qualitative feedback to identify improvements to the checklist. Method: The students reviewed a survey in a one-group posttest-only quasi-experiment using the checklist. In total 13 students participated in the context of the course Evidence-based software engineering as part of the study program Information Systems at Flensburg University of Applied Sciences. Results: In total the students achieved 74% percent of agreement among each other. However, the Kappa values indicated mostly a poor level of agreement considering the classification by Fleiss. In addition, the students were quite inaccurate assessing the questions. Though, they performed well on questions for research objectives and the identification of population. Conclusion: Findings indicate that students do not assess reliably. However, further investigations are needed to substantiate the findings. Copyright © 2021 by SCITEPRESS - Science and Technology Publications, Lda. All rights reserved	Checklist; One-group Quasi-experiment; Students; Survey	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85134430768&doi=10.5220%2F0010496204370444&partnerID=40&md5=71f0371e296eba5700476ddbcb6af94	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Introducing low-cost sensors into the classroom settings: Improving the assessment in agile practices with multimodal learning analytics	10.3390/s19153291	Currently, the improvement of core skills appears as one of the most significant educational challenges of this century. However, assessing the development of such skills is still a challenge in real classroom environments. In this context, Multimodal Learning Analysis techniques appear as an attractive alternative to complement the development and evaluation of core skills. This article presents an exploratory study that analyzes the collaboration and communication of students in a Software Engineering course, who perform a learning activity simulating Scrum with Lego® bricks. Data from the Scrum process was captured, and multidirectional microphones were used in the retrospective ceremonies. Social network analysis techniques were applied, and a correlational analysis was carried out with all the registered information. The results obtained allowed the detection of important relationships and characteristics of the collaborative and Non-Collaborative groups, with productivity, effort, and predominant personality styles in the groups. From all the above, we can conclude that the Multimodal Learning Analysis techniques offer considerable feasibilities to support the process of skills development in students. © 2019 by the authors. Licensee MDPI, Basel, Switzerland.	Collaboration; Collocated Collaboration Analytics; Multimodal Learning Analytics; Social Network Analysis	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85070750164&doi=10.3390%2Fs19153291&partnerID=40&md5=4e480101c4e259255ea94fd1e757c18e	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	chance

Evaluating legal implementation readiness decision-making	10.1109/TSE.2014.2383374	Software systems are increasingly regulated. Software engineers therefore must determine which requirements have met or exceeded their legal obligations and which requirements have not. Requirements that have met or exceeded their legal obligations are legally implementation ready, whereas requirements that have not met or exceeded their legal obligations need further refinement. In this paper, we examine how software engineers make these determinations using a multi-case study with three cases. Each case involves assessment of requirements for an electronic health record system that must comply with the US Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA) and is measured against the evaluations of HIPAA compliance subject matter experts. Our first case examines how individual graduate-level software engineering students assess whether the requirements met or exceeded their HIPAA obligations. Our second case replicates the findings from our first case using a different set of participants. Our third case examines how graduate-level software engineering students assess requirements using the Wideband Delphi approach to deriving consensus in groups. Our findings suggest that the average graduate-level software engineering student is ill-prepared to write legally compliant software with any confidence and that domain experts are an absolute necessity. © 2014 IEEE.	Legal Implementation Readiness; Legal Requirements; Regulatory Compliance Software Engineering; Requirements Engineering	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84933047992&doi=10.1109%2FTSE.2014.2383374&partnerID=40&md5=929546ad82a2a8acd471d409a3bb4f66	☐	☑	sem colab
Performance evaluation of university students participating in a simulation game with data envelopment analysis (DEA)		Simulation games have an important role in higher education, because their application allows students to test their theoretical knowledge in a risk free practical environment. The learning by doing concept can also be supported by these methods. Simulation games serve several objectives during the learning process. The multitude of objectives requires sophisticated evaluation methods, which are able to analyse the satisfaction of these targets, and are also able to provide an aggregate performance measure for grading purposes. Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) is able to consider several aspect of simulation game results using sound mathematical methodology which increases the objectivity of the evaluation. Applying DEA for the evaluation of student's performance in a simulation game is a novel area of DEA application. This paper shows how an input oriented constant returns to scale radial model can be used to evaluate the results of student groups in a production simulation game. The paper presents the applied mathematical model, the application environment and summarises the main benefits of this new evaluation tool for grading and assessment purposes. © 2020 SEFI 47th Annual Conference: Varietas Delectat... Complexity is the New Normality, Proceedings. All rights reserved.	DEA; Performance evaluation; Simulation games	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85077823158&partnerID=40&md5=80068c00f2c1971bdecc982e0d06139	☐	☑	sem colab
Massive open online courses in software engineering education	10.1109/FIE.2017.8190588	Despite the popularity of MOOCs in providing opportunities for socialization, collaboration, and professional improvement, there has been little research exploring them in the context of Software Engineering Education (SEE). The purpose of this study is to provide a better understanding of practices and challenges when developing academic software engineering MOOCs. To this end, we research (i) how MOOCs in SEE are designed and (ii) what learning design considerations educators and learning designers have when developing SEE-related MOOCs. To address the first research question, a systematic mapping is performed to outline the current landscape. The second research question is answered by analyzing and reflecting on practical experiences acquired during the design of a MOOC on Agile Software Development. The design of the course was based on the Pedagogical Design Pattern Framework for MOOCs, an approach to design for learning that was defined in our previous studies. For this course, two environments were considered: (a) course-time on the Tim Tec MOOC platform for deeper engagement with active learning activities, such as Project-based learning; (b) a Facebook group as a social and collaborative learning space, including scenarios based on problem-based learning to activate prior knowledge. Some of the pedagogical strategies adopted to motivate self-regulated learning included self-introduction video, diary, diagnostic self-assessments, development of small projects alone and in pairs. Our findings provide evidence that there are still several technological and pedagogical challenges that need to be addressed so as to enhance the MOOCs learning experience for SEE. Technological issues identified include the development of tools and educational games, which should be integrated into MOOCs, and the use of learning analytics to support motivation, user experience, and more active learning in specific topics, such as Project Management, Agile Methods, and Requirements Engineering. In turn, the most significant and needed improvement to the pedagogical aspects is a re-thinking of the virtual moment in the MOOC platform so as to optimize it through activities that promote active learning and contextualized assessments. © 2017 IEEE.	Agile software development; Design patterns; Learning design; Lifelong learning; MOOCs; Software engineering education	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85043269656&doi=10.1109%2FIE.2017.8190588&partnerID=40&md5=a077d176afb086068bac9d27ecd8a10	☐	☑	sem colab

Measurement range increment in a method for evaluating panoramic understanding of programming	10.1109/FIE.2016.7757489	In a prior study we introduced the Programmed Visual Contents Comparison Method (PVCC) for assessment of programming abilities related with Panoramic Understanding of Programming (PUP). With this method, by comparing two or more output pictures produced by programming samples (a question), a student must decide which one of the programs producing them is more difficult to build with programming, or, if the difficulty is similar for all of them. This study reported also the results of a test to evaluate this method's validity performed with groups of students of diverse fields. Validity was verified by comparing the initial programming ability reported by programming professors of these groups with the test results; this confirmed that the PVCC method worked well to find programming abilities related with PUP. In this paper we propose an enhancement to the PVCC Method based on the preparation of New Questions where two or more samples displaying both input data and output pictures are shown. By adding input data to output pictures and focus strictly on the programming processes needed to obtain these pictures from the provided input data, we aim to broaden the range of discernible programming abilities related with PUP. The results of a test performed to verify the suitability of New Questions performed with professors of programming is also reported. © 2016 IEEE.	Computer science education; Graphic design; Programming training; Software engineering; Student assessment	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85006810253&doi=10.1109%2FIEE.2016.7757489&partnerID=40&md5=cf32d72ca4db6fd0c0bf07a58ea029c	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Engaging software engineering students in grading: The effects of peer assessment on self-evaluation, motivation, and study time		Peer assessment is a popular technique for a more fine-grained evaluation of individual students in group projects. Its effect on the evaluation is well studied. However, its effects on the learning abilities of students are often overlooked. In this paper, we explore self-evaluation, motivation, and study time of students in relation to peer assessment, as part of an ongoing project at our local Faculty of Engineering Technology. The aggregated measurements of two years so far show that: (1) students get much better at evaluating their own project on some, but not all, of the evaluation criteria after a peer assessment session, (2) students report in a follow-up survey that they are more motivated to work on their project, and (3) the relation between motivation and time spent on the project increases. These results suggest that peer grading could have positive long-term effects on the reflective, and therefore lifelong learning, skills of students. A better understanding of the evaluation criteria results in more accurate self and peer grades, emphasizing the importance of properly defining and communicating these criteria throughout the semester. © 2020 SEFI 48th Annual Conference Engaging Engineering Education, Proceedings. All rights reserved.	Motivation; Peer assessment; Self-evaluation; Study time	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85107230693&partnerID=40&md5=1fd8f8e8e858c39031e233ebb70a6e60	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
WIP: Teaching a knowledge engineering course using active learning, gamification, and scaffolding		This paper describes the authors' experiences introducing active learning opportunities in a senior level software analysis and design course. The team critically examined the existing artificial intelligence course offered at our institution and created new active learning style instructional materials for selected course topics. We devised delivery strategies that incorporated academic research findings and industry best practices. We focused on problem-based learning strategies for this course, supported by software tools. Based on our assessment data, we believe that students participating in the activities created for this course are better equipped with fundamental theoretical knowledge and valuable hands-on experiences that can measurably increase their ability to contribute to the software industry. Both face to face and online students preferred active learning content delivery to lecture only. Both groups of students felt more engaged with the course materials than they do in traditional lecture courses. © American Society for Engineering Education 2020.		https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85095778628&partnerID=40&md5=34a5d3dfd70d47ed17ce2be3ecb69798	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

<p>IFIP TC3 Open Conference on Computers in Education, OCCE 2018</p>	<p>The proceedings contain 27 papers. The special focus in this conference is on Computers in Education. The topics include: Hanging Pictures or Searching the Web: Informing the Design of a Decision-Making System that Empowers Teachers to Appropriate Educational Resources to Their School's Infrastructure; Designing an Educational Action Task Force for MOOCs and Online Course Production; a Teaching Process Oriented Model for Quality Assurance in Education - Usability and Acceptability; collaboration Platform for Public and Private Actors in Educational Games Development; students' Conducts During a Digital Game-Based Museum School Visit; assessing Social Engagement in a Digital Role-Playing Game: Changes over Time and Gender Differences; a Learning Analytics Approach in Web-Based Multi-user Learning Games; the Role of Audiovisual Translation in Mediating Foreign Language Learning: Activity Theory Perspective; innovation in Language Teaching and Learning: What Do We Need to Make a Massive Open Online Course (MooC) for Language Learning Genuinely Innovative?; Computational Thinking and Problem-Solving in the Context of IEA-ICILS 2018; an Investigation of the Impact of Haptics for Promoting Understanding of Difficult Concepts in Cell Biology; personality-Based Group Formation: A Large-Scale Study on the Role of Skills and Personality in Software Engineering Education; social Networks as Learning Delivery Platforms: Academic Achievement and Attitudes of Students; learning to Share by Reflection-on-Action on an Enterprise Social Media Platform; The Application of Anchoring Vignettes in the Analysis of Self-assessment of ICT Skills: A Pilot Study Among Czech Secondary School Students; student Experiences with a Bring Your Own Laptop e-Exam System in Pre-university College.</p>		<p>https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85069485068&partnerID=40&md5=5d16bc09b39f5456c5cd8b174bab7eca</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<p>sem colab</p>
<p>Annual Conference on Innovation and Technology in Computer Science Education, ITICSE</p>	<p>The proceedings contain 94 papers. The topics discussed include: first year computing students' perceptions of authenticity in assessment; analyzing how interest in learning programming changes during a cs0 course: a qualitative study with Brazilian undergraduates; comparing remote and co-located interaction in free and open source software engineering projects; learning agile with tech startup software engineering projects; student software designs at the undergraduate midpoint; Raspberry Pi as a platform for the internet of things projects: experiences and lessons; an experience-based comparison of unity and unreal for a stand-alone 3d game development course; curriculum mapping as a tool for improving students satisfaction with the choice of courses; when the robot meets the turtle: a gentle introduction to algorithms and functions; GIT: pedagogy, use and administration in undergraduate CS; nailing the TA interview: using a rubric to hire teaching assistants; a comparison of online and hybrid professional development for CS principles teachers; examining a student-generated question activity using random topic assignment; impact of performance level and group composition on student learning during collaborative exams; study habits, exam performance, and confidence: how do workflow practices and self-efficacy ratings align?; application of the Delphi method in computer science principles rubric creation; playfully coding: embedding computer science outreach in schools; and the Solothurn project - bringing computer science education to primary schools in Switzerland.</p>		<p>https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85029505953&partnerID=40&md5=2b4d65a866760a4ad8e2d55e1cd6c215</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<p>sem colab</p>
<p>Early intervention in programming education: Unlocking potential through peer-mentoring and reflective practice</p>	<p>This paper addresses issues associated with retention and progression of learners undertaking introductory programming modules within Further Educations (FE) and Higher Education (HE). Through conducting an Action Research study, this work focuses on a year 1 class group enrolled on a software engineering degree and considers how early intervention group work, with peer mentoring, assessment and reflection, can influence the retention rate and performance of learners considered to be at risk of not progressing to year 2 of the program. © WMSCI 2019 - 23rd World Multi-Conference on Systemics, Cybernetics and Informatics, Proceedings. All rights reserved.</p>	<p>Education; Learning to Program; Software Engineering</p>	<p>https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85074150327&partnerID=40&md5=e6000edc600890b7c072b0af5fc72551</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<p>sem colab</p>

Requirements Assessment in Smart City Districts: A Motivation Concept for Citizens	10.1007/978-3-030-44429-7_20	[Context and motivation] Digitalization is increasingly influencing cities as they evolve into Smart Cities. However, involving citizens in order to develop digital solutions that address real needs of users is a challenging task. In the Smart City project "EnStadt:Pfaff", concepts are to be developed to encourage residents of a city district to participate in the development of a Smart City district by communicating their needs, wishes, and ideas. [Question/problem] In the context of Smart City districts, classic requirements engineering (RE) methods such as interviews can be used, but there is high potential for novel methods, as the residents are concentrated within a very limited physical space and can communicate their needs and wishes through a digital platform as well as through analog communication channels. Our research goal is to investigate such novel methods and their potential for improving Smart City districts with digital solutions. [Principal ideas/results] In this research preview, we describe an initial approach for encouraging a group of citizens (potentially without any software engineering background) to participate in requirements elicitation in the context of Smart Cities. [Contribution] The presented approach consists of nine steps providing guidance for the selection of motivational measures, the reduction of obstacles to participation, and communication of requirements elicitation activities. Furthermore, we present topics for future research. © 2020, Springer Nature Switzerland AG.	Digital platform; Motivation; Requirements engineering; Smart City	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85083955515&doi=10.1007%2F978-3-030-44429-7_20&partnerID=40&md5=adea1690be54fd1d2c1f81af76fe9066	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
A team-approach to putting learner-centered principles to practice in a large course on human-computer interaction	10.1109/FIE.2016.7757576	We present a case study on how a team of instructors put learner-centered principles into practice in a large undergraduate course on Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) that was run in 4 parallel groups of about 50 students. The course stands on the crossroads between software engineering, business, and research in so far as student-teams apply human-centered design techniques to develop mobile apps, test them with real end-users, read research papers and regularly reflect upon their experience. As a proof of the course-concept, selected results from formative and summative assessments are presented. The summative results show that students rated the course as one of the best of the 87 computer science courses run in the summer term of 2015 at the University of Vienna. The primary goal of this paper is to provide instructors intrigued by learner-centered approaches with ideas for their own practice. In particular, this paper is of interest to those who teach Human-Computer Interaction and to those who seek inspiration on mapping their course to the 14 learner-centered principles. © 2016 IEEE.	Formative and summative assessment; Human-computer interaction; Learner-centered principles; Project-based learning; Student-centered learning	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85006825748&doi=10.1109%2FIEE.2016.7757576&partnerID=40&md5=bfce5ad8a1cd3e1eda7bf24dd8345f71	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Poster: Improving formation of student teams: A clustering approach	10.1145/3183440.3195057	Today's courses in engineering and other fields frequently involve projects done by teams of students. An important aspect of these team assignments is the formation of the teams. In some courses, teams select different topics to work on. Ideally team formation would be included with topic selection, so teams could be formed from students interested in the same topics. Intuitive criteria for a team formation algorithm are that students should be assigned to (1) a topic which they have interest and (2) a team of students with similar interests in their topic. We propose an approach to meeting these criteria by mining student preferences for topics with a clustering approach and then matching them in groups to topics that suit their shared interests. Our implementation is based on hierarchical k-means clustering and a weighting formula that favors increasing overall student satisfaction and adding members until the maximum allowable team size is reached. © 2018 Authors.	Bidding; Clustering; MOOCs; Peer assessment system; Student team formation	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85049669548&doi=10.1145%2F3183440.3195057&partnerID=40&md5=99ea490e927e17a0d278c0407a4a1faf	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Evaluating the quality of E-learning material	10.17770 /etr2017vol2.2557	An increasing number of educational institutions in the study process uses one of the e-learning systems. Consequently, more and more students are offered learning materials in electronic format. E-materials in distance learning and e-learning is one of the most important elements, therefore much attention and enough time should be paid for their development. There are a number of studies on e-learning quality, where criteria of quality are discussed in the context of chosen e-learning environment and the process of implementation. This article examines only the quality of ematerial. The aim was to find a way to reduce the effort and time of electronic learning material quality evaluation. The study used content analysis by summarizing the most important factors influencing the quality for teaching materials. Based on the quality criteria mentioned in the literature and personal experience, a criterion, which affects quality of elearning material, were summarized and grouped. The criteria were grouped into four groups resulting from didactic, media, usability and formal quality. Quality evaluation is performed by using one of the methods used in software engineering - checklist. Based on the identified quality criteria a checklist was established. In order to facilitate the evaluation process a web-based tool is offered. The tool includes a defined checklist with assessment rating scale and three levels of impact. Evaluation of material quality is shown in the terms of percentage. After testing the tool, it could be used for course developers, program managers or other persons involved in evaluation process of e-learning resources. © Rezekne Academy of Technologies, Rezekne 2017.	Checklist; Evaluation; Quality indicators; Self-assessment tool	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85028381276&doi=10.17770%2fetr2017vol2.2557&partnerID=40&md5=09e265a08bba87144125c2b30ab78ab4	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Educational use and motivational elements of simulation games for mining engineering students: a phenomenological study	10.1080 /03043797.2019.1666797	This phenomenological study investigates mining engineering students' game playing experiences for educational purposes and seeks to understand the essence of their experiences. In this study, three non-gamer and three-gamer mining engineering students were selected through a criterion sampling method, and then data were collected through in-depth phenomenological interviews and focus group interviews. The study showed that visualisation, learning by doing and motivation were the common themes for the benefits of the use of games in education, whereas addiction, underestimation and time management emerged as the possible problems. Motivational elements were found to be challenge, curiosity, control, information seeking, observation, assessment, hypothesis building and decision making that shaped the participants' experiences. However, games' effect changed based on the personal characteristics and interests of the students. It can be claimed that the findings of this study indicate promising results in the use of games in mining engineering education. © 2019, © 2019 SEFI.	educational use of games; Games; mining engineering education; phenomenological research; simulation games	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85073966371&doi=10.1080%2f03043797.2019.1666797&partnerID=40&md5=6413f3ed4eb817fb5fbcb4e6c2811f5	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

<p>Pedagogical effectiveness of continuous vs. discrete user interaction with computer demonstrations (WIP)</p>	<p>Background Computer demonstrations and simulations are well-researched tools for teaching; resources such as The Guide to Simulation Games for Education and Training have existed for half a century [1] and numerous studies have investigated the value of interactive simulations in the engineering and mathematical academic setting, for example [2]-[5]. The ubiquity of mobile computing devices, the rise of Massive Open Online Courses (MOOC), and changes as textbook publishers embrace electronic media have further spurred the use of simulations as an important method to provide an intuitive, self-guided understanding of quantitative cause-and-effect relationships [6]-[8]. Such simulations may use discrete methods to interact with them, such as setting simulation parameters, pressing a calculate button and observing the results, or they may employ a continuous method of interaction, such as dragging a slider and observing in real-time how the results are affected. Although demonstrations using continuous input methods are considerably more difficult to program, no studies have attempted to quantify the pedagogical benefits, if any, of adopting one manner of user interaction over the other. Methods This Work-In-Progress (WIP) paper describes a set of experiments to test the hypothesis that interactive software demonstrations using continuous input methods are more pedagogically effective than those using discrete input methods. Two different interactive computer demonstrations were created, available at [9], each of which develops student intuition connecting a phasor representation and its time-domain sinusoidal waveform. Both demonstration programs have identical output areas displaying the sinusoid, and identically-appearing input areas showing the phasor. The discrete version requires the user to input the magnitude and angle of the phasor and press a calculate button; the continuous version uses a similar input screen but allows the user to drag a point to establish the phasor magnitude and angle. Although this pilot study examines only a pair of tightly-coupled programs, further work is planned to determine if certain subjects inherently lend themselves better to discrete or continuous input methods. The experiment was conducted in three stages. First, students were randomly selected to be in the A or B teams by alphabetically ordering students in each class and assigning even numbers to continuous and odd numbers to discrete cohorts. Both groups were given ten minutes to read identical tutorials, available at [10], that provide an introduction to the mathematics linking phasors with their time-domain sinusoids. Students were next given instructions to download the phasor application appropriate to their cohort, downloadable at [9], and given a set of identical exercises to complete requiring them to use the software application to determine relationships between various given phasors and their time-domain representations. Last, students were required to close their phasor applications and complete questionnaires [11] which probed their objective understanding of phasors as well as their subjective beliefs about the quality of their understanding of phasors, as well as their rating of the phasor demonstration app as a learning tool. The questionnaire began by requesting their self-assessment of subject mastery, and their subjective determination of the utility of applications such as these in learning causal relationships in engineering. For example, in question 6 of the questionnaire, students were asked How well do you feel you understand the relationship between a phasor and its associated sinusoid? Questions 8-14 were designed to measure students' objective performance in recognizing the equivalence between a phasor and its corresponding time domain signal. The final question asked the students again to provide their subjective determination of the utility of applications such as these for learning causal engineering relationships as compared to traditional methods of instruction. The comparison of the results for the discrete vs. continuous phasor apps were evaluated using the two-tailed student T distribution. Results A total of 91 students were involved in this Work-In-Progress study; 52 in the continuous group and 39 in the discrete group. The actual understanding of the student cohorts, based on scoring of the objective questions, are shown in Figure 2. Figure 2: Comparison of the objectively-scored questions from the two cohorts. The error bars represent the standard error of the mean. In the given sample size, statistical significance at the 0.05 level is not achieved, although it is clearly close. Larger planned studies may, or may not, bridge this gap, clarifying whether or not continuous-style inputs on pedagogical programs improve learning efficacy. Although the objective data do not quite reach significance with this N=91 sample, students' self-assessments of their learning show much stronger differences that reach statistical significance, and curiously they show the opposite of what appears to be the objective truth; the cohort that used the continuous applications believed they understood less than the students that used the discrete applications (Figure 3). This may reflect the Dunner-Kruger paradox that explains the cognitive bias which occurs when low-ability people lack the framework to assess their abilities accurately, and high-ability people overestimate the abilities of others [12],[13]. This relationship is graphically shown in Figure 4, which shows individual students' actual understanding plotted against their subjective self-assessment. Because the underlying data are strongly gridded (there are only a limited number of objective questions, and the self-assessment is a Likert-graded scale with options), the data are shown with numbers representing the count of students with identical scores. Red scores represent those from the discrete group; green from the continuous group. The data points are displayed 1 percentage point higher and lower for red and green, respectively, so their numbers do not collide on the graph. The regression line is plotted for their aggregate and the R2 value calculated, showing a</p>	<p>https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85095740151&partnerID=40&md5=1a5a88f401de2e04217b968c3bc29712</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/></p>	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>	<p>sem es</p>
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A Community-based Computational and Engineering Sciences Initiative toward National Development (COESIND)	10.1109 /FIE43999. 2019.9028640	<p>In this Innovative Practice Full Paper, we propose to establish a community-based learning initiative, which integrates recruitment, advisement, and retention programs with hands-on activities that supplement core curriculum for cohorts of students in the STEM fields - from recruiting through graduation and placement into the workforce. This initiative is designed in three phases: the pilot phase, the alliance phase, and the backbone phase. This project is aimed at the pilot phase; however, its focus does not end when the piloting is over, but rather, it is intended to integrate with other pilot programs into building regional alliances. Through the regional alliances, this proposed pilot initiative is planned to become part of the national backbone program, which aims at producing well-prepared, underrepresented graduates into the STEM-related workforce. Because the percentage of women and minorities (African-American, Hispanics, and Native Americans) in STEM-related workforce is so small, the COESIND program is designed to broaden the participation of these groups. To do so, a community of the eight campuses of Chattahoochee Technical College, the five campuses of Georgia-Perimeter College, the Girls, Inc. of Greater Atlanta, Georgia, Young Women's Christian Association (YWCA) of Greater Atlanta, and three area high schools in Cobb County, all in the metropolitan area of Atlanta, Georgia, will participate in the COESIND program. A Kennesaw State University (KSU) CS mentorship program, The Girls, Inc.'s summer camps have consistently attracted several girls over the years (Google IgniteCS). These institutions, collectively, have a significantly large population of African-American (A-A), Hispanics, and Girls/Women. Faculty from the College of Computing and Software Engineering (CCSE) and College of Engineering at KSU, located in Kennesaw, Georgia, will lead the proposed program. KSU, which recently merged with Southern Polytechnic State University (SPSU), located in Marietta, Georgia, now has a student population of 5,000 in these two Colleges. Moreover, KSU was recently classified as an R2 institution. The University also offers an array of STEM programs and has been ranked 7th among institutions that offer online courses and, at the time the merger, SPSU was ranked among the top three producers of African-American engineering technology graduates in the nation. With its prior implementations of two NSF-LSAMP programs, among other undergraduate-level student training, KSU is qualified to lead such an initiative. Our focus on Computing and Engineering sub-disciplines, among the many STEM-fields, is intentional: To focus on programs and activities where computing and engineering technologies are deployed as tools to solving real-world problems. In this paper, we will describe the motivation of the project and the detailed implementation plan of the pilot phase. The assessment plan along with the measurable outcomes, are summarized in the paper as well. © 2019 IEEE.</p>	community-based learning; hands-on experiences; Internet of Things (IoT); STEM-related workforce; under-representatives	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85082471283&doi=10.1109%2FIE43999.2019.9028640&partnerID=40&md5=1fa4d7784d1fcc00981e263bbb559598	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Blending an Android development course with software engineering concepts	10.1007 /s10639-015-9423-3	<p>The tremendous popularity of mobile computing and Android in particular has attracted millions of developers who see opportunities for building their own start-ups. As a consequence Computer Science students express an increasing interest into the related technology of Java development for Android applications. Android projects are complex by nature and relatively large software products while their development calls for the application of established software engineering practices and tools. However, most software engineering courses focus on 'conventional' software development for desktop or web applications. In this paper we report on the design, implementation and assessment of a novel short course aiming at bridging the gap between software engineering and Android development. The goal is to demonstrate the need for applying software engineering principles on Android development as well as to emphasize that writing software for mobile devices should be regarded as an equally serious programming activity. The proposed course covers design principles, patterns, metrics, refactorings and collaborative software development. The course has been delivered to three groups of undergraduate and postgraduate students at two different institutes. The course has been evaluated: a) by performing a student satisfaction survey, b) through summative assessment of students' performance, c) by investigating whether the proposed course modified the students' career interests and d) by employing assessment by peers based on rubrics. The results indicate that such a short course is capable of increasing student's interest on Android development as well as their awareness of the importance of software engineering concepts on mobile application software development. © 2015, Springer Science+Business Media New York.</p>	Android development; Classroom teaching; Software engineering; Teaching strategies	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84938150267&doi=10.1007%2Fs10639-015-9423-3&partnerID=40&md5=9d5529340cc0e458ea4a8ac8dfc73018	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

<p>A collaborative environment equipped with a tracing system to develop professional skills and encourage participation of learners</p>		<p>This chapter describes a pedagogical environment equipped to track learners' activities. The instructional system is the result of an iterative design. Different cycles of design have produced a collaborative learning methodology and tools to support it. The collaborative environments target vocational training of students who will work on projects in teams (including IT projects where collaboration is essential). The aim is to develop key skills, such as project management, planning, estimation, communication, negotiation, etc. while working the development of expertise in a specific area (database, system, network, software engineering, etc.). The instructional design (ID) methodology that has been applied to design and implement the instructional system is a prototypal approach. Other different ID methods could have been used but the prototypal approach has the advantage to allow an iterative evolution of the system. Successive cycles have allowed the production of an educational method and environment that accompanies it. A generic method emerged, which offers the acquisition of job skills through the ingroup management of a project. The method is hybrid marrying face-to-face sessions with distant work. This method subscribes to the principles of the socio-constructivist theory and offers the characteristics and benefits demonstrated by this theory. The teacher describes awaited activities in a logbook before each face-to-face session. Each group does restitution, under a standardized form, in the team logbook of what has been achieved and scheduled. Tools encourage the restitution and collaboration activities. They are chosen in respect of specific requirements: the tools must be easy to understand, intuitive, provide logging capabilities, provide features for documents sharing, facilitate communication and facilitate feedback from the teacher. The specifications led to use Web 2.0 tools rather than LMS platform. However, the experience showed that traceability of actions ensures better management and assessment. The device has to be improved by adding indicators about the participation of students, the rate of work on activities, the distribution of communications within a group, etc. A tracking tool based on agents has been developed that provides a dashboard for the teacher. Thanks to the dashboard, teachers can observe individual and group activities and detect and awake sleeping learners. Teachers visualize the activity and its distribution among stakeholders. Teachers are thus able to refine their evaluation of work. They can also reactivate the motivation of less active learners. In the same way, a dashboard enables students to understand the nature of their activities and to evaluate their respective participation in the project. This dashboard has a regulatory effect on the activity of the group. This chapter presents the instructional system and the traceability system in place to support and evaluate the learning activities. © 2014 by Nova Science Publishers, Inc. All rights reserved.</p>		<p>https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84953455665&partnerID=40&md5=f734997269d757c1412b222f21f5ec16</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<p>sem es</p>
<p>Activity identification and local linear convergence of forward-backward-type methods</p>	<p>10.1137/16M106340X</p>	<p>In this paper, we consider a class of Forward-Backward (FB) splitting methods that includes several variants (e.g., inertial schemes, FISTA) for minimizing the sum of two proper convex and lower semicontinuous functions, one of which has a Lipschitz continuous gradient, and the other is partly smooth relative to a smooth active manifold M. We propose a unified framework, under which we show that this class of FB-type algorithms (i) correctly identifies the active manifold in a finite number of iterations (finite activity identification), and (ii) then enters a local linear convergence regime, which we characterize precisely in terms of the structure of the underlying active manifold. We also establish and explain why FISTA (with convergent sequences) locally oscillates and can be locally slower than FB. These results may have numerous applications including in signal/image processing, sparse recovery and machine learning. Indeed, the obtained results explain the typical behaviour that has been observed numerically for many problems in these fields such as the Lasso, the group Lasso, the fused Lasso and the nuclear norm minimization to name only a few.</p>	<p>Forward-backward; Inertial methods; ISTA/FISTA; Local linear convergence; Partial smoothness</p>	<p>https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85021155085&doi=10.1137%2F16M106340X&partnerID=40&md5=10a61ba55ac79e789c072d2f9946ee10</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<p>sem colab</p>

An Embedded Systems Course for Engineering Students Using Open-Source Platforms in Wireless Scenarios	10.1109/TE.2016.2526676	This paper presents a case study analyzing the advantages and disadvantages of using project-based learning (PBL) combined with collaborative learning (CL) and industry best practices, integrated with information communication technologies, open-source software, and open-source hardware tools, in a specialized microcontroller and embedded systems engineering Master's course. In addition to addressing industry requirements in both contents and methodology, the course develops capabilities and competencies in problem solving, independent learning, teamwork, and technical knowledge. Since PBL methodology alone does not ensure teamwork, it was complemented with CL. Design review meetings (as described in IEC 61160), deliverables, and organizational resources were also introduced to mirror industry demands. This structure integrated course content and student academic achievement in a simulated industrial environment. The course had students build a modular management system for home appliances, implementing control software on the "Arduino" open-source platform, as well as using wireless communications. The results show that teaching, learning, and student assessment processes can be improved by using PBL with CL. In addition, the introduction of industry practices, such as peer review meetings, brings academia closer to a real-world context. © 1963-2012 IEEE.	Cooperative/collaborative learning; engineering education; IEC 61160; innovation; open-source hardware; open-source software; teaching strategies	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84960172704&doi=10.1109%2FTE.2016.2526676&partnerID=40&md5=74a6594e5cbaa8c6d7eb9e11900f14fc	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	ssem es
Instructional design is to teaching as software engineering is to programming	10.1145/2839509.2844674	This special session will explore practical results from the educational theory of Instructional Design (ID), with particular focus on the widespread similarities between a process for creating successful courses and a process for creating successful software. We present a small set of specific practices that should be easy for CS educators to adopt. In particular, the session will cover the popular Dick & Carey model, meant for beginners to ID. This model helps instructors rigorously define who they will teach to, what they will teach, how they will assess, and (only then) how they will teach. The approach is parallel to Software Engineering techniques such as Test-Driven Development, Requirements Engineering, and Iterative Development. The session will be a blend of presentation, participation, and assessment. Participants will work in small groups both to foster discussion and to provide learning support. The content of the presentation will particularly focus on how the model can be applied practically. It is our hope that attendees, whether new to teaching or experienced, will adopt or be influenced by the model in order to approach their courses with the same rigor they apply to software development.	Dick & Carey; Formal Methods; Instructional Design; Software Engineering; Teaching	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84968586034&doi=10.1145%2F2839509.2844674&partnerID=40&md5=616a4980d2e6bc7f12a209e829ce6859	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
PBL-SEE: An authentic assessment model for PBL-based software engineering education	10.1109/TE.2016.2604227	The problem-based learning (PBL) approach has been successfully applied to teaching software engineering thanks to its principles of group work, learning by solving real problems, and learning environments that match the market realities. However, the lack of well-defined methodologies and processes for implementing the PBL approach represents a major challenge. The approach requires great flexibility and dynamism from all involved, whether in mapping content, in teacher performance, or laying out the process of how learners should go about solving problems. This paper suggests that management processes can help in implementing PBL throughout its life cycle (planning, implementation, monitoring, and enhancement), and proposes an assessment model called PBL-SEE for use in software engineering education (SEE). Two examples of its use are provided. The results show how the model can be applied and how the resulting information can be used to make the PBL initiatives 'authentic,' in that they bring the reality of the labor market to the learning environment, while keeping to PBL principles. © 1963-2012 IEEE.	Bloom's taxonomy; case study; problem solving; problem-based learning (PBL); professional skills; student assessment; teaching evaluations	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85018913386&doi=10.1109%2FTE.2016.2604227&partnerID=40&md5=9c3fd5109a206ca158b126f6ade86d7f	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
R.ECOS - Educational Recommender Ecosystem	10.1109/JSOS.2017.4	This paper presents R.ECOS, an approach from the Software Ecosystems (SECO) perspective to recommend Educational Resources. It defines a platform that allows services integration and other Ecosystems services, with the aim of facilitating the reuse and sharing of solutions in Recommender Systems. The development of the proposal advances on studies of our Research Group, especially in the educational area. An initial assessment of the proposal was made through an application scenario, in which the services of R.ECOS were developed to define groups of users. Additionally, services from third-party were reused. The obtained results in the application scenario point to the viability of our proposal. © 2017 IEEE.	Clustering; Educational Resources; Recommender Systems; Software Ecosystem	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85026376499&doi=10.1109%2FJSOS.2017.4&partnerID=40&md5=4db4b5e51cb996e4265cec37c524f126	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Monitoring of efficiency of feedback systems use on the base of Kherson State University		The article deals with solution of some problems connected to development of feedback services while surveying students on educational environment at a higher education institution. Our research was carried out by the Department of Informatics, Software Engineering and Economic Cybernetics of Kherson State University. During 6 years (2009-2015) in the mentioned above Department, students' survey regarding their satisfaction with an educational process and lecturer' assessment by students' had been carried out. In the process of research, students from the 1st up to the 4th years of study of the Department of Informatics, Software Engineering and Economic Cybernetics were surveyed. All the respondents were divided into two groups: interested and disinterested ones during the survey execution. Introduction of the service ""KSU Feedback"" at Kherson State University on the base of the Department of Informatics, Software Engineering and Economic Cybernetics had a positive impact on creation of an educational environment where higher education institution is a corporation for serving the students. © 2016 by the paper authors.	Feedback; KSU feedback; Quality of education; Services; Social polls; Survey; Training	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84977591939&partnerID=40&md5=7fdf9e56760838e3692e65a3e9d69a9e	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Collaborative and teamwork software development in an undergraduate software engineering course	10.1016/j.jss.2018.07.010	Two key elements of modern software development are collaboration and teamwork. Current methodologies (e.g., agile) and platforms are based on these key elements. This paper describes our experience in stimulating collaboration and teamwork activities of students in the context of a software engineering course at the third year of an undergraduate program in computer science at the University of Milano-Bicocca in Italy. The students were asked to develop a software project in teams of 3 to 5 students for the final exam of the course. The students used GitHub as a collaborative software development platform. In addition, they analyzed the quality of the developed software through SonarQube. The students were also asked to perform project management tasks (e.g., the Gantt) using the Microsoft Project tool. At the end of the course, we gathered the student feedback through a questionnaire on their collaboration and teamwork experience (through GitHub and Microsoft Project tools) and on the use of a software analysis assessment tool, i.e., SonarQube. From their feedback, the students were enthusiastic about working in teams for their project development and about learning how to use tools which are exploited not only in the academic world but also in industry. © 2018	Collaborative software development; GitHub; Microsoft project; Software engineering course; SonarQube; Teamwork	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85049922420&doi=10.1016%2fj.jss.2018.07.010&partnerID=40&md5=0dc5efc11db4722003475830541d308b	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem avaliar
Agile methods as problem-based learning designs: Setting and assessment	10.1145/3284179.3284237	Problem-based learning has been proved as a good method to teach Software Engineering, concretely when project development skills are involved. In those cases, project work departs from some stakeholder requirements that are often ill-defined, and the team progresses by analysis and design identifying the parts that the team can develop and which of them requires further investigation. From a teaching perspective, agile methods like Scrum perfectly fit the problem-based learning model, since sprint results can provide a good indicator of group and individual student progress. In this paper, a case study aimed at introducing learning analytics in an instructional design for Advanced Software Engineering courses using problem-based learning approach is reported. Learning analytics were carried out both from the project work process, adopting some tools of the platform used to manage task and activities (Jira Software), and from the obtained final grade, using Jupyter notebooks. © 2018 Copyright is held by the owner/author(s). Publication rights licensed to ACM.	Agile methods; Jira; Learning analytics; Problem-based learning; Software engineering teaching	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85058546042&doi=10.1145%2f3284179.3284237&partnerID=40&md5=11ba113c990e6354899e9c02ae5dff40	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Enhancing user value of educational technology by three layer assessment	10.1145/3131085.3131105	Teachers and educators are in need for understanding different technology and what is their added value for teaching and learning. This paper is to present an assessment framework that can identify such technology that delivers positive subjective outcomes for the end-users (teacher / learner). The framework consists of three main components: Capability Maturity Model (CMM), Pedagogical Usability and User Experience (UX). To validate the aforementioned approach the research group set up two focus groups. The first group consisted of developers of educational technology. The second group consisted of practitioners. Content analysis method was used to analyze recorded focus group data. Focus groups discussed about whether approach to conduct future assessment of educational technology was valid and suitable. Based on focus group results, the framework stands out as a valid foundation for a holistic assessment of edtech by better understanding the needs of different user stakeholders. © 2017 Association for Computing Machinery.	Capability maturity model; Educational technology; Focus group; Usability; User experience	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85043297747&doi=10.1145%2f3131085.3131105&partnerID=40&md5=1bcbcd8ed0dd9e103cfd9c24c0cb5f2	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Moving from managing enrollment to predicting student success	10.1109/FIE. 2017.8190665	We describe the construction and assessment of a plan to foster student success in Computer Science (CS) in response to continued enrollment growth. We examined cross correlations of grades from student transcripts from the past four years to determine what patterns of grades in early classes were indicative of future success. The resulting statistics and visualizations showed that students generally did better in the first class than subsequent classes, suggesting that C grades in the first class might indicate difficulty. We also examined students enrolled in the pre-capstone software engineering course. The analysis showed that no graduating CS major had received a C in both first two programming courses. We examined the data to be sure that the proposal would not diminish the participation of members of underrepresented groups disproportionately. As a result, the CS faculty approved a change in prerequisite for the third course to require that student receive an A or a B in at least one of the first two courses. GPA data was also analyzed and found to be a poor predictor of success in computer science, demonstrating that our previous approach to limiting enrollment was inferior. This new approach has advantages over the previous GPA-based plan, but enrollment management plans risk making college harder for at risk students to succeed in CS. The biggest limitation of this plan is that it is expected to make only a small change in CS enrollment. © 2017 IEEE.	Computer science; Enrollment management; Retention	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85043300496&doi=10.1109%2FIEE.2017.8190665&partnerID=40&md5=d1abcd3e65f1db91b5e02fbf00552556	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Surprisingly Stochastic: Learning and Application of Emergent Behavior Using Interactive Simulations of Nano-Mechanical Biological Systems		Emergent behavior is pervasive in complex systems, and often produces surprising phenomenon that are challenging to understand and apply usefully, especially with regards to inter-level causalities. Here, we study engineering undergraduates' capacity to understand and solve design problems concerning inter-level causalities in nanomechanical biological systems. To test user understanding and application of inter-level causalities in this system, we developed a GUI bolstered by an agent-based molecular simulation that calculates system performance and renders animations in real-time as users adjust design inputs. We randomly assigned undergraduate engineering students to design-based learning groups with support of either animated simulation rendering or charts. Both groups improved on a set of pre/post design problems. But on assessments of understanding of inter-level causal relationships, only the animation group demonstrated an understanding. Both groups were then presented contrasting animations of continuous and intermittent systems, resulting in about half of participants in each group demonstrating an understanding of inter-level causal behaviors. These findings demonstrate the difficulty in understanding inter-level causal relationships in emergent systems, the usefulness in interactive software tools in overcoming these difficulties, and that understanding of inter-causal relationships may improve performance in design applications. © 2014 Proceedings of the 36th Annual Meeting of the Cognitive Science Society, CogSci 2014. All rights reserved.	Biomedical; Complex Systems Design; Emergence; Engineering; Graphical User Interface; Inter-level Causality; Learning; Multiscale	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85139191817&partnerID=40&md5=697b4f9805064f8f0f4d4b5e85f3cf3b	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es
Let's talk about technology for peace: A systematic assessment of problem-based group collaboration around an interactive tabletop	10.1093 /iwc/iwt061	This work is concerned with the exploration of ideas in the realm of technology for peace, produced by small groups of students working around an interactive tabletop. A collaboration-enforcing tabletop application was used to mediate dialog and collaborative construction of a taxonomy of ideas based on the participants' consensus. The scenarios for discussion concerned the promotion of global peace and the social integration of immigrants in the society. The participants' dialog and interactions were video-recorded and analyzed. The study contributes a systematically developed coding scheme capturing the cognitive and physical elements of problem-based group collaboration around the interactive tabletop. Also, the consistent themes and ideas contributed across the participating groups highlight a number of areas where research could focus in terms of using technology for peace. © 2013 The Author. Published by Oxford University Press on behalf of The British Computer Society. All rights reserved.	collaborative content creation; collaborative learning; empirical studies in HCI; tables and interactive surfaces	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84928314122&doi=10.1093%2Fiwc%2Fiwt061&partnerID=40&md5=4cf3b496357eabfc37e394c958c83336	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es

Mining twitter messages for software evolution	10.1109/ICSE-C.2017.65	Twitter is a widely used social network. Previous research showed that users engage in Twitter to communicate about software applications via short messages, referred to as tweets, and that some of these tweets are relevant for software evolution. However, a manual analysis is impractical due to the large number of tweets - in the range of thousands per day for popular apps. In this work we present ALERTme, an approach to automatically classify, group and rank tweets about software applications. We apply machine learning techniques for automatically classifying tweets requesting improvements, topic modeling for grouping semantically related tweets and a weighted function for ranking tweets according to their relevance for software evolution. We ran our approach on 68,108 tweets from three different software applications and compared the results against practitioners' assessments. Our results are promising and could help incorporate short, informal user feedback with social components into the software evolution process. © 2017 IEEE.	Software evolution; Text mining; User feedback	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85026776112&doi=10.1109%2FICSE-C.2017.65&partnerID=40&md5=ef26524b8614849d477b90c1ca4a0afa	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es
Students' experiences of change in a PBL curriculum		Very few institutions have a problem based learning (PBL) curriculum at an institutional level and there is therefore limited experience with change in systemic PBL models. Aalborg University (AAU) practices an institutional PBL model, and in 2010 a rather comprehensive curriculum restructuring took place at the Faculty of Engineering and Science. The original PBL model assessed some of the courses and projects together, whereas since the reform there is separate assessment of each course and of the project. This article reports the findings from a study of how students have experienced this curriculum change. An explorative mixed method study was used that included qualitative focus group interviews with 10th (final) semester students about their experience of the change. Based on the qualitative study, a questionnaire was sent to all 10th semester students from computer science, software engineering, and architecture and design. The findings indicate that the students always prioritize the projects but with the reforms they experienced a significantly lower degree of integration and coherence of the various elements in a semester. Furthermore, the alignment between project supervision and project exam has increased in the new curriculum as the exams of courses and projects are separated. © 2016 TEMPUS Publications.	Alignment; Curriculum development; Pbl models; Projects	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84959361616&partnerID=40&md5=c6d1f7b66325d7daf6b2ff00567e2128	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Enhancement of working memory using neuro-electrostimulation for accelerated learning	10.1109/SIBIRCON.2017.8109955	The paper describes the results of using the neuro-electrostimulation device for improving the attention and working memory characteristics, which are one of the main parameters of cognition in the learning process. It was shown that the quality of the test for assessment of working memory and attention in the experimental group with the use of neuro-electrostimulation was higher than in the control group. Also it was found that the application of neuro-electrostimulation could be used as a corrective technique for subjects with low initial values of test parameters, which allows increasing the test results for assessing working memory and attention. © 2017 IEEE.	Attention; Cognitive characteristics; Learning ability; Neuro-electrostimulation; Neuroplasticity; Neuroscience of learning; Working memory	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85040525413&doi=10.1109%2FSIBIRCON.2017.8109955&partnerID=40&md5=0f6ba2e1d3d9de9ff20f6b25d07bd851	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
A proposal for technology-based software engineering curriculum development	10.1109/ICEED.2016.7856078	A group of software engineering educators, has embarked on a project to implement and support the creation and adaptation of a common set of teaching material and strategies for software engineering education at the undergraduate level of education. The outcome of this project is a framework, in the form of a repository of best practice software engineering teaching modules, assessment artifacts, and case projects that are founded on a set of program outcomes for undergraduate education in software engineering. The philosophy of the research is that the availability of shared pedagogical material that have been developed in a collaborative manner will advance the learning goals, and promote the adoption of teaching strategies that are in the students' best interest. © 2016 IEEE.	Course; Curriculum; Educational research; Pedagogy; Program outcome; Software engineering	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85015913673&doi=10.1109%2FICEED.2016.7856078&partnerID=40&md5=d666b3435dbca94a86a6c0814272d1c6	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Teaching git on the side - Version control system as a course platform	10.1145/2729094.2742608	The ability to use version control systems is a highly desired skill in the software industry and the need to teach it has been recognized in the literature. Git, and other version control systems, have previously been used by instructors in classrooms to distribute exercises, to facilitate assessment, and as a platform for project collaboration and teamwork. Using version control brings benefits to instructors, e.g. by lowering the need for administrative tasks, as well as to students, e.g. by providing experience with standard software industry tools. We describe how to incrementally present features of Git and incorporate them into the course workflow. We present a case study of running a large (ca. 200 students) course utilizing Git and evaluate the results both from instructor's and learner's point of view. Our evaluation shows, that a distributed version control system can be used successfully to disseminate course materials and facilitate exercise submissions. Copyright 2015 ACM.	Course management; Git; Software engineering; Version control	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84951980839&doi=10.1145%2F2729094.2742608&partnerID=40&md5=3d9d2d88c983ace63c224f728d255dc7	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Implementing a challenge-based approach to teaching selected courses in CS and computational sciences		Challenge Based Instruction/learning (CBI) has been championed as an effective methodology to engage students in their own learning process, allowing them to deal with real-life problems and projects that need to be solved. As The New Media Consortium eloquently puts it, ""[Challenge-based learning] calls for a new way of thinking about the role of the teacher, one in which he or she had to be comfortable as the students struggled and wrestled with a meaningful challenge, letting them choose their own path to understanding."" The approach is even more challenging to implement in the SMT (Science, Mathematics, and Technology) fields at minority-serving institutions requiring trained faculty. This paper describes in detail our efforts to implement CBI in the Computer Science curriculum in general, and Computer Graphics (CG) and Software Engineering (SWE) in particular. The effort is part of an NSF grant awarded to UT Pan Am and UT Brownsville (both are now part of the newly merged university of UT Rio Grande Valley). The CG and SWE courses were selected because of the initial high enrollment but the low retention rate. The paper documents the efforts that have been made in specific areas of the newly implemented courses. These include: 1. The process of identifying course major module objectives and module sub-objectives, in particular, those that are relevant to CBI implementation. 2. Identifying expected difficulties: What are the difficulties that students face when taking the course? 3. Real-world context: Why is the course an important part of the CS curriculum, and where can one find its applications? 4. Knowledge model: What is the conceptual model for the course, including prerequisites, course dependencies, and course level? What concepts and techniques should be considered to enhance understanding of the material? 5. Assessment of learning: How does one change the traditional testing and assessment methods to make sure these include formative assessment (individual and group, in class and outside the class homework) as well as summative assessment? Data analysis and conclusions from the pilot project have been made public to benefit other faculty in CS and other SMT fields nationwide. © American Society for Engineering Education, 2016.	Challenge based instruction/learning (CBI); Computational science; Computer graphics; Engineering; Interdisciplinary studies; SMT (Science mathematics and technology) fields at minority-serving institutions; Software engineering	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84983372830&partnerID=40&md5=a518c56314993a267c3be3a021cfe09	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
A methodology for the classification of quality of requirements using machine learning techniques	10.1016/j.infsof.2015.07.006	Context One of the most important factors in the development of a software project is the quality of their requirements. Erroneous requirements, if not detected early, may cause many serious problems, such as substantial additional costs, failure to meet the expected objectives and delays in delivery dates. For these reasons, great effort must be devoted in requirements engineering to ensure that the project's requirements results are of high quality. One of the aims of this discipline is the automatic processing of requirements for assessing their quality; this aim, however, results in a complex task because the quality of requirements depends mostly on the interpretation of experts and the necessities and demands of the project at hand. Objective The objective of this paper is to assess the quality of requirements automatically, emulating the assessment that a quality expert of a project would assess. Method The proposed methodology is based on the idea of learning based on standard metrics that represent the characteristics that an expert takes into consideration when deciding on the good or bad quality of requirements. Using machine learning techniques, a classifier is trained with requirements earlier classified by the expert, which then is used for classifying newly provided requirements. Results We present two approaches to represent the methodology with two situations of the problem in function of the requirement corpus learning balancing, obtaining different results in the accuracy and the efficiency in order to evaluate both representations. The paper demonstrates the reliability of the methodology by presenting a case study with requirements provided by the Requirements Working Group of the INCOSE organization. Conclusions A methodology that evaluates the quality of requirements written in natural language is presented in order to emulate the quality that the expert would provide for new requirements, with 86.1 of average in the accuracy. © 2015 Elsevier B.V.	Machine learning; Requirements engineering; Requirements quality; Software engineering	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84942019840&doi=10.1016%2Fj.infsof.2015.07.006&partnerID=40&md5=0cb84f8e97c794f55a9c78c45a0dd2f1	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Industry 4.0 Briefcase: An Innovative Engineering Outreach Project for Professions of the Future	10.1007/978-3-030-58802-1_70	This paper presents an engineering outreach project titled "Industry 4.0 Briefcase" that has been developed to introduce the concept of Industry 4.0 to undergraduate students. The project aims to support participants to become aware of Industry 4.0 related topics such as machine learning, data mining, industrial automation, human-machine interface, and product life cycle, and to stimulate the curiosity of them towards these topics. The scope of the project consists of presentations, experimental applications, observations, individual and collaborative studies, assessment and evaluation practices, e-learning applications, and a social program. The project was conducted as a one-week program at a public university in Turkey with the participation of 18 undergraduate 3rd-year students. Participants consist of students from computer engineering and software engineering departments of the engineering faculties and the business department of the faculty of economics and administrative sciences. Thus, participants of the project had the opportunity to exchange information with students and faculty members from different academic backgrounds. The study utilized the mixed methods approach by performing both quantitative and qualitative measurements. To collect data, mini projects and project evaluation forms were used for quantitative measurements and daily virtual classroom sessions and a general evaluation session (focus group interview) were used for qualitative measurements. The success rates of the participants based on the evaluation of the reports they presented were obtained as 91% in data mining, 95% in industrial automation and human-machine interface, and 89% in machine learning course, respectively. It was observed that the overall satisfaction level of the participants from the project activities was over 95%. These findings were also supported by the qualitative findings as the students indicated their overall satisfaction from the organization of the project and stated that working in teams and attending the social program contributed to developing positive relationships with each other and increasing their success. © 2020, Springer Nature Switzerland AG.	Engineering education; Engineering outreach; Industrial automation; Industry 4.0 concepts	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85093115609&doi=10.1007%2F978-3-030-58802-1_70&partnerID=40&md5=a3d29c11d6c170a49c091c35f054f8c6	<input type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab e es
An industry-mentored undergraduate software engineering project	10.1109/FIE.2014.7044180	Software design lifecycle application to a real world project is a critical skill required by the undergraduate computer engineer. Interaction with the local professional software development community is also an equally important opportunity that should be provided. This fosters growth of both technical and soft skills, and exposes the student to standards and working practices in providing quality software solutions for customers. This paper describes the structure of a group-based software development project that integrates industry mentors in the learning and assessment processes. Industry liaisons are given a forum to elucidate some of the industry's requirements of students in terms of knowledge of software design and industrial standards; students gain better understanding of some of the processes which take place in an actual industrial setting; and university curriculum gains industry relevance. The impact of this project is yet to be fully assessed. Assessment can be determined from two aspects: (1) in terms of the benefit to the student (effectiveness of learning objectives achieved, and motivation gained from project based learning and group work) and (2) the impact of providing industry led mentorship. © 2014 IEEE.		https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84938099351&doi=10.1109%2FIE.2014.7044180&partnerID=40&md5=14c4261e0f31cb38ebcb0d96855bacfc	<input type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Investigating the role choice of female students in a software engineering team project	10.1145/3294016.3294028	In 2017 the number of individuals who identify as female in the UK studying a STEM subject (Science, Technology, Engineering and Maths) in further education is 35% where as 94% of their peers who identify as male choose a STEM subject to study. This decreases in higher education with 9% of females compared to 29% of males choosing a STEM subject in 2017 [1]. To address this issue there are many initiatives being set up to recruit females into STEM higher education courses. However there is a lack of research into the experiences of female students once they have started their degree programme in Computer Science. In this study we investigate the roles which undergraduate female students choose in a large software engineering team project to find out if there are barriers that prevent them from taking on technical or programming roles in these projects. We analysed assessment data to determine their previous programming experience and then performed a content analysis of team project deliverables and peer assessment scores. The results show that our female students, despite their strong academic background, tend to pick less technical roles in these projects than male students and are subsequently awarded lower peer review scores by their teammates for their contribution to the group work. These results indicate that teaching interventions may need to take place to make the role choice and peer review processes fairer in such projects. Further investigations are needed to see if there is some form of unconscious bias or imposter syndrome occurring in our software engineering team project module and if this is a common phenomenon in these projects in other HE institutions. © 2019 Association for Computing Machinery.	Fair assessment; Gender; Peer review; Programming; Role choice; Software engineering; STEM; Team project	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85123042555&doi=10.1145%2F3294016.3294028&partnerID=40&md5=9e52cab557e107dc33f00d2bc5c33d33	<input type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Collaborative security risk estimation in agile software development	10.1108/ICS-12-2018-0138	Purpose: Today, agile software development teams in general do not adopt security risk-assessment practices in an ongoing manner to prioritize security work. Protection Poker is a collaborative and lightweight software security risk-estimation technique that is particularly suited for agile teams. Motivated by a desire to understand why security risk assessments have not yet gained widespread adoption in agile development, this study aims to assess to what extent the Protection Poker game would be accepted by agile teams and how it can be successfully integrated into the agile practices. Design/methodology/approach: Protection Poker was studied in capstone projects, in teams doing a graduate software security course and in sessions with industry representatives. Data were collected via questionnaires, observations and group interviews. Findings: Results show that Protection Poker has the potential to be adopted by agile teams. Key benefits include good discussions on security and the development project, along with increased knowledge and awareness. Challenges include ensuring efficient use of time and gaining impact on the end product. Research limitations/implications: Using students allowed easy access to subjects and an ability to collect rich data over time, but at the cost of generalizability to professional settings. Results from interactions with professionals supplement the data from students, showing similarities and differences in their opinions on Protection Poker. Originality/value: The paper proposes ways to tackle the main obstacles to the adoption of the Protection Poker technique, as identified in this study. © 2019, Emerald Publishing Limited.	Agile development; Case study; Protection Poker; Risk assessments; Secure software engineering; Software security	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85067840934&doi=10.1108%2fICS-12-2018-0138&partnerID=40&md5=043b986cdc04a072e290646fd4b3529f	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab		
XPBL: A methodology for managing PBL when teaching computing	10.1109/FIE.2014.7044178	In order to exploit the benefits of PBL and mitigate the risk of failure when implementing it, the NEXT (iNnovative Educational experience in Technology) research group has been working on methods and tools focused on managing the PBL approach as applied to Computing. In this context, this article proposes a teaching and learning methodology based on PBL, called xPBL, consisting of elements that reinforce PBL principles, namely: real and relevant problems; a practical environment; an innovative and flexible curriculum; an authentic assessment process; close monitoring by technical tutors and process tutors, and finally, professional practitioners as teachers and tutors. Based on these elements, the paper describes the design of a PBL approach for a Design course, grounded on acquired knowledge of Design content and past PBL experiences in Software Engineering courses. This approach provides an insightful guide to implementing PBL from xPBL methodology, and provides instruments based on management techniques such as 5W2H (what, why, who, when, where, how and how much) and the production of artifacts to support the conception process of courses based on PBL. © 2014 IEEE.	Design course; Management processes; PBL; Teaching and learning methodology	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84938152545&doi=10.1109%2fFIE.2014.7044178&partnerID=40&md5=5fba6fbad0da564b7a85253e2f1a58fe			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Towards a Clinical Trial Protocol to Evaluate Health Information Systems: Evaluation of a Computerized System for Monitoring Tuberculosis from a Patient Perspective in Brazil	10.1007/s10916-018-0968-8	Assessment of health information systems consider different aspects of the system itself. They focus on the professional who will use the software or on its usability or on the software engineering metrics or on financial and managerial issues. The existent approaches are very resources consuming, disconnected, and not standardized. As the software becomes more critical in the health organizations and in patients, becoming used as a medical device or a medicine, there is an urgency to identify tools and methods that can be applied in the development process. The present work is one of the steps of a broader study to identify standardized protocols to evaluate the health information systems as medicines and medical devices are evaluated by clinical trials. The goal of the present work was to evaluate the effect of the introduction of an information system for monitoring tuberculosis treatment (SISTB) in a Brazilian municipality from the patients' perspective. The Patient Satisfaction Questionnaire and the Hospital Consumer Assessment of Healthcare Providers and Systems were answered by the patients before and after the SISTB introduction, for comparison. Patients from an outpatient clinic, formed the control group, that is, at this site was not implanted the SISTB. Descriptive statistics and mixed effects model were used for data analysis. Eighty-eight interviews were conducted in the study. The questionnaire's results presented better averages after the system introduction but were not considered statistically significant. Therefore, it was not possible to associate system implantation with improved patient satisfaction. The HIS evaluation need be complete, the technical and managerial evaluation, the safety, the impact on the professionals and direct and/or indirect impact on patients are important. Developing the right tools and methods that can evaluate the software in its entirety, from the beginning of the development cycle with a normalized scale, are needed. © 2018, Springer Science+Business Media, LLC, part of Springer Nature.	Health information system evaluation; Patient relationship management; Patient satisfaction; Tuberculosis	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85046691436&doi=10.1007%2fs10916-018-0968-8&partnerID=40&md5=47fd2996ef0f1cea13f3e3381140ab4a					<input type="checkbox"/>

<p>Impact of a computer programming support center on (chemical) engineering students' success and satisfaction</p>	<p>In the chemical/biochemical engineering curriculum at the study institution, 11 required undergraduate courses taught by the Department of Chemical Engineering include a substantial programming component, using Matlab, Python, and/or process simulation software (Aspen Plus™ or SuperPro Designer). In response to demand for increased out-of-class programming support specific to these courses, an expansion of existing support specific to community college transfer students was implemented in January 2020. While the focus of this program was on (bio) chemical engineering students, this support was made available to all engineering students at the study institution. The ongoing goals of this project are as follows: To retain at risk undergraduates in difficult, programming intensive courses, keeping students on track for a 4-year graduation (2-years for transfer students). To increase overall student success and satisfaction in programming intensive courses. In response to an earlier study done on the barriers to success for transfer students in engineering at the study institution [1], a programming crash course in Matlab, piloted in Fall 2017, was developed to address the lack of programming preparation cited by students, and in particular those taking courses in the Department of Chemical Engineering. This crash course has been offered to incoming transfer students in the Fall of their transfer year as an optional 1-credit course for the past three years. Survey results and anecdotal feedback have shown that transfer students find the course to be valuable (course's educational value rated 4.5/5). Additionally, it was found that a number of non-transfer students were interested in the course due to their perceived lack of programming preparation for their junior-level courses. However, despite the interest and positive feedback, students have found it difficult to complete the crash course requirements while also balancing their heavy load of required courses. What had emerged from the three iterations of the programming crash course was that both 4-year and transfer students were eager for on-demand programming support, but hesitant to commit to or persist in a formal course. Additionally, this need for programming support goes beyond the junior-year Fall quarter and transcends the entire (bio)chemical engineering upper-division curriculum. In addition to the survey and anecdotal feedback related to the crash course, students have been demanding additional support on their senior exit surveys for not only their Matlab/Python intensive courses but also for their courses that heavily utilize process simulation software (Aspen Plus™ or SuperPro Designer). In Spring 2017, the junior class at the study institution was also surveyed and their lack of training and support for their programming intensive coursework was also heavily cited. In order to address this need for additional programming support for students, the Department of Chemical Engineering at the study institution established a team of graduate teaching assistants and undergraduate tutors under the direction of a faculty director who were collectively responsible for providing both one-on-one tutoring sessions and small group programming support sessions. In order to assess the goals of this project, a number of direct and indirect assessments were carried out. These included: Direct Assessments (indicates when assessed) Grades in target courses of students who use services vs those that did not (quarterly) Overall average GPA of class in target courses vs previous years (quarterly) Number of students and demographics of students who used services (quarterly) Indirect Assessments (indicates when assessed) Survey of students who use services, to include satisfaction with services, perception of gains in programming skill level, and sense of satisfaction with target courses (quarterly) Comments on senior exit surveys related to programming skills and target courses as compared to previous years (annually) In addition to answering the demand for out-of-class programming support, multiple benefits to both our students associated with this project were anticipated. The first expected benefit was that students would persist in difficult, programming intensive courses instead of dropping or delaying courses thereby delaying their graduation. Secondly, students who took advantage of this support program were expected to see improvement in their performance, particularly in the target (programming intensive) courses. Further, by becoming more adept at using these programming tools, students were expected to have a greater sense of satisfaction with respect to their programming abilities, their performance in these courses, and in their overall college experience. Copyright © American Institute of Chemical Engineers. All rights reserved.</p>		<p>https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85106195263&partnerID=40&md5=b8ce7a884718605b3d77dc2d2a253605</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<p>sem colab</p>
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The education of students about ISO/IEC 29110 software engineering standards and their implementations in very small entities	10.1109/IHTC.2017.8058208	Worldwide, a large majority of organizations developing software are entities having up to 25 people. Since most published software engineering standards had been developed by and for large organizations, most Very Small Entities (VSEs) did not have the expertise to adapt or tailor those software engineering standards to meet their needs. The ISO/IEC 29110 series of standards and guides was specifically developed for VSEs developing software. Many countries that had not participated to international standard development, decided to join the ISO working group mandated to develop the ISO/IEC 29110 series. Since the ISO/IEC 29110 engineering and management guides are easily understandable and freely available, it has greatly helped their adoption. More than 17 countries, such as Colombia, Brazil, Haiti, Jordan, Malaysia, Mexico, Peru and Thailand are teaching ISO/IEC 29110. ISO/IEC 29110 has been used by many students to develop their first products. Many countries have adopted ISO/IEC 29110 as a national standard. A few countries are helping their VSEs in the adoption, implementation and certification activities with government programs. Low cost independent certification and assessment schemes allow VSEs to demonstrate recognition of their competences to local and international customers and partners. © 2017 IEEE.	education; ISO/IEC 29110; management and engineering guide; standard; Very Small Entities	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85022010264&doi=10.1109%2FIHTC.2017.8058208&partnerID=40&md5=cfe9417265fb7ed94a984dc39078f629	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Software factory project for enhancement of student experiential learning	10.33965/celda2019_201911037	Providing opportunities for students to work on real-world software development projects for real customers is critical to prepare students for the IT industry. Such projects help students to understand what they will face in the industry and experience real customer interaction and challenges in collaborative work. To provide this opportunity in an academic environment and enhance the learning and multicultural teamwork experience, the University of Oulu, Finland offers the software factory (SWF) project. This paper presents the design of the SWF course and the learning environment and assessment techniques, and it discusses the importance of reflective learning diaries and serious games. Additionally, this paper examines factors in the SWF learning environment that affect student learning in the SWF course. Survey data were collected from the last six years of SWF projects. The results show that students consider the SWF to be a good collaborative learning environment that helps them achieve academic triumphs and enhances various professional skills. The learning diaries are effective for increasing students' learning experiences as well as providing an opportunity for teaching staff to monitor students' progress and offer better facilitation. These results are helpful for academic institutions and industry when developing such a learning environment. © 2019 16th International Conference on Cognition and Exploratory Learning in Digital Age, CELDA 2019. All rights reserved.	Collaborative Learning; Project-Based Learning; Software Engineering; Software Engineering Curricula; Teamwork	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85078986041&doi=10.33965%2fcelda2019_201911037&partnerID=40&md5=b8eb2fdc965a149c23cedd3e2f07b735	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
XSOF: A generic software teaching and learning model	10.1002/cae.21613	The attitude of software learning by students relies on transforming the Learning Model consistently into Software Development Model. The effort and time taken for development of different phases of software, has few issues, in particular, the principles and practices to be followed in academia. To address these issues, a generic software teaching and learning model called eXtreme Software Teaching (XSOF) is proposed by integrating the essence of the Extreme Programming (XP) method with COSMIC FFP (Common Software Measurement Integration Consortium Full Function Point) Standards. The effectiveness of this proposed model was tested on real time projects assigned to students as a realistic study by selecting them with equal skill and knowledge on programming. They were divided into two groups, such as Pair Programmers and Solo Programmers. The performances of these groups are measured with respect to the trade in person-days using XSOF. The empirical results show that the assessment of person-days are less on pair programming than solo programming and effective programming skill is found with pair programmers. In addition, the robustness of this model are confirmed by the results of another real time project as case study. © 2014 Wiley Periodicals, Inc.	COSMIC FFP; extreme programming; learning; pair programming; software development; solo programming; teaching	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84927616269&doi=10.1002%2fcae.21613&partnerID=40&md5=f8c8fc233e00b3a9eb76ca2407ccc40	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
ITICSE-WGP 2015 - Proceedings of the 2015 ITICSE Conference on Working Group Reports		The proceedings contain 7 papers. The topics discussed include: challenges and recommendations for the design and conduct of global software engineering courses: a systematic review; educational data mining and learning analytics in programming: literature review and case studies; a global snapshot of computer science education in K-12 schools; concepts in K-9 computer science education; new horizons in the assessment of computer science at school and beyond: leveraging on the VIVA platform; multinational perspectives on information technology from academia and industry; and what's in a name? international interpretations of computing education terminology.		https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84964711822&partnerID=40&md5=15e410a83baa5a7e492cd023872df74c	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

12th Joint Conference on Knowledge-Based Software Engineering, JCKBSE 2018		The proceedings contain 26 papers. The special focus in this conference is on Knowledge-Based Software Engineering. The topics include: Bibliometrics EEG metrics associations and connections between learning disabilities and the human brain activity; effectiveness of automated grading tool utilizing similarity for conceptual modeling; generating scenarios with access permission from a conceptual model; a knowledge transfer support system from text-based work reports with domain ontologies; support tool for refining conceptual model in collaborative learning; tool to automatically generate a screen transition model based on a conceptual model; 3D formation control of swarm robots using mobile agents; towards a secure semantic knowledge of healthcare data through structural ontological transformations; group affect recognition: Optimization of automatic classification; analysis of specification in Japanese using natural language processing; an artificial immune system-based approach for the extraction of learning style stereotypes; a sightseeing guidebook automatic generation printing system according to the attribute of tourist (KadaTabi); the development of the system which creates lecture contents by a combination of various units and learning content s; development case of information services to accelerate open innovation and implementation: Through demonstration experiments in Kagawa; automated decision making and personal data protection in intelligent tutoring systems: Design guidelines; authoring technological and platform independent learning material and student's progress profile using web services; computerized adaptive assessment using accumulative learning activities based on revised bloom's taxonomy; deriving successful factors for practical ai system development projects using assurance case; estimation of business rules using associations analysis; notification messages considering human centered design.		https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85051797387&partnerID=40&md5=b3c4bb925e3dbb6fb669f5fb20845703	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Technology enhanced active learning in software engineering	10.5220/0006257602420248	Educating software engineers in software management have long been hard both in academia and in industry. It is extremely difficult to educate software engineering management techniques actively. Historically, we have been quite used to educate in programming in a classroom and in a lab with instructions Teaching any management aspects has been traditionally based on instructions and case studies. We have adopted an active based learning approach to teach final year BSc students in Software Engineering. We let the final year students manage group projects carried out by level 5 students. Mainly, we don't come across a large real-world case study. This work on active learning has changed our way of teaching software engineering and it has made a significant impact on the way the students learning and have been taught traditionally. This research has also proposed an information system model for Technology Enhanced Active Learning and Teaching (ALT) with emphasis on three key principles for teaching Software Engineering: divergent thinking, collaborative learning, and learning through differentiated assessments. More than 90% of students felt they had gained knowledge more quickly with active learning. The ALT model is part of the large scale technology enhanced learning for future learning environments which has been developed adopting most of computer science courses and specialist module. Copyright © 2017 by SCITEPRESS - Science and Technology Publications, Lda. All rights reserved.	Active learning; Collaborative learning; Group project; Project supervision; Software engineering management	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85023772786&doi=10.5220%2f0006257602420248&partnerID=40&md5=5b9769667862d93a25858fd30c676f1e	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem avaliar
Russian grandparenting: Demographic and statistical modelling experience		The demographic situation in Russia has been quite complicated for many years. Its important negative manifestations are low birth rates and low life expectancy at birth. In this situation, studies on the role of older people (primarily grandparents) in the birth, upbringing, and development of grandchildren become especially important. The purpose of our exploratory research is to model the objective and subjective characteristics of Russian grandparents who realize the functions of parental labour in relation to their grandchildren. Statistical modelling of differences between the target group and the alternative group was carried out primarily on the basis of the parametric and nonparametric independent samples tests: t-test, Mann-Whitney U test, median test. Specific features related to age, level of education, social activity and subjective assessments of health of the grandmothers involved in daily childcare were revealed. The model of a typical grandmother actively involved in parental labour was presented. This will be the basis for developing a full-scale survey and determining the best research design. © ECMS Mike Steglich, Christian Mueller, Gaby Neumann, Mathias Walther (Editors).	Independent samples tests; Nonparametric tests; Parental labour; Russian grandparenting; Statistical modelling	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85094976699&partnerID=40&md5=1706a8283b0bb76ff493bb07ba933987	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Using the random forest classifier to assess and predict student learning of Software Engineering Teamwork	10.1109/FIE.2016.7757406	The overall goal of our Software Engineering Teamwork Assessment and Prediction (SETAP) project is to develop effective machine-learning-based methods for assessment and early prediction of student learning effectiveness in software engineering teamwork. Specifically, we use the Random Forest (RF) machine learning (ML) method to predict the effectiveness of software engineering teamwork learning based on data collected during student team project development. These data include over 100 objective and quantitative Team Activity Measures (TAM) obtained from monitoring and measuring activities of student teams during the creation of their final class project in our joint software engineering classes which ran concurrently at San Francisco State University (SFSU), Fulda University (Fulda) and Florida Atlantic University (FAU). In this paper we provide the first RF analysis results done at SFSU on our full data set covering four years of our joint SE classes. These data include 74 student teams with over 380 students, totaling over 30000 discrete data points. These data are grouped into 11 time intervals, each measuring important phases of project development during the class (e.g. early requirement gathering and design, development, testing and delivery). We briefly elaborate on the methods of data collection and describe the data itself. We then show prediction results of the RF analysis applied to this full data set. Results show that we are able to detect student teams who are bound to fail or need attention in early class time with good (about 70%) accuracy. Moreover, the variable importance analysis shows that the features (TAM measures) with high predictive power make intuitive sense, such as late delivery/late responses, time used to help each other, and surprisingly statistics on commit messages to the code repository, etc. In summary, we believe we demonstrate the viability of using ML on objective and quantitative team activity measures to predict student learning of software engineering teamwork, and point to easy-to-measure factors that can be used to guide educators and software engineering managers to implement early intervention for teams bound to fail. Details about the project and the complete ML training database are downloadable from the project web site. © 2016 IEEE.	Assessment; Education; Machine learning; Software engineering teamwork	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85006792140&doi=10.1109%2FIEE.2016.7757406&partnerID=40&md5=625a366937017cf6d4f4012bd8b13ed5	☐	☑	sem avaliar
Collaborative knowledge transfer via Wiki: A project based learning approach in software engineering	10.1109/ICL.2014.7017785	Due to the high complexity and numerous abstract processes in the subject Software Engineering (SWE), both, challenges in teaching and in learning arise. The teaching of Software Engineering is attempted by a new didactic approach to convey a deeper understanding of the complexity and the processes of Software Engineering in the context of the course. The approach complements the classical ex-cathedra lecture with a seminar and a project phase, whereby the direct application of theoretical knowledge is achieved in real-world situations. In addition to the consolidation of factual knowledge, transferable skills, such as presentation, communication and teamwork skills, can be encouraged. The approach focuses on self-studying as well as collaborative learning. The knowledge gained from team working is multiplied by the Wiki and spread over the whole semester. © 2014 IEEE.	collaborative; competencies; course evaluation; knowledge acquisition; knowledge assessment; knowledge platform; knowledge transfer; Moodle; self-studying; Software Engineering; Wiki	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84922932981&doi=10.1109%2FICL.2014.7017785&partnerID=40&md5=7a128f4e3e78d3e67be6592c8835345e	☑	☐	chance
Structured and weighted multi-task low rank tracker	10.1016/j.patcog.2018.04.002	Low rank subspace and multi-task learning have been introduced into object tracking to pursue the accurate representation. However, many existing methods regularize all rank components equally, and shrink with the same threshold. In addition, these methods ignore the discriminative and structured information among tasks during the tracking. In this paper, we propose an online discriminative multi-task tracker with structured and weighted low rank regularization (ODMT-SL). Specifically, the total tracking task is accomplished by the combination of multiple subtasks, and each subtask corresponds to the trace of the image patch from the tracked object. In order to improve the flexibility of multi-task tracker, the weighted nuclear norm is introduced to adaptively assign different tracking importance on different rank components of multiple tasks. The geometric structure relationship among and inside candidates (or training samples) are mined to learn the collaborate representation, according to the discriminative subspace and optimal classifier. They are simultaneously learned and updated by minimizing the developed tracking model. The best candidate is selected by jointly evaluating the normalized metric. The proposed tracker is empirically compared with the state-of-the-art trackers on a large set of public video sequences. Both quantitative and qualitative comparisons demonstrate that the proposed algorithm performs well in terms of effectiveness, accuracy and robustness. © 2018	Group-sparsity regularization; Normalized collaboration metric; Robust multi-subtask learning; Structured and weighted low rank	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85046370733&doi=10.1016%2Fj.patcog.2018.04.002&partnerID=40&md5=a2c197dd6b0ef61cd69cb a8ddcfcdac2	☐	☑	sem colab

Automated formation of peer-learning cohorts using computer-based assessment data: A double-blind study within a software engineering course		An approach is developed to integrate the complementary benefits of digitized assessments and peer learning. The research hypothesis is that each student's assessment data at the fine-grained resolution of correct/incorrect question choice selections can be utilized to partition learners into effective peer learning cohorts. A low overhead approach is explored along with its associated tool, referred to as Automated Peer Learning Cohorts (Auto-PLC). The objective of Auto-PLC is to increase scalability to deliver peer-based learning. First, digitized formative assessments are delivered in a computer-based testing center. This enables automated grading, which frees-up the instructor's and teaching assistants' workloads to become reallocated to recitation sessions for higher-gain learning activities, such as peer-based remediation sessions. Second, within the recitations held following each formative quiz, students are afforded an opportunity to complete a remedial assignment. Auto-graded results of formative assessment submissions undergo Auto-PLC's statistical clustering routines using Excel macros and Python scripts to partition the class into four-person peer learning cohorts having mutually-complementary knowledge gaps and skill efficacies. Within each peer learning cohort, students solve together an assigned remedial problem during the recitation session. Thus, students who have already acquired a particular skill become paired together with students who are still acquiring that same skill, and vice versa. This also aids scalability to large enrollments within Electrical and Computer Engineering (ECE) and Computer Science (CS) courses by maximizing opportunities for students to teach each other the material which they still need to learn. The motivation, design, and outcomes for Auto-PLC are presented within the required undergraduate course COP4331: Processes for Object-Oriented Software Development at a large state university. To evaluate effectiveness, a double-blind IRB-approved study has been conducted in COP4331 involving 206 students. All enrolled participated identically, except for their assignment to either randomly-formed or intelligently-clustered remediation groups. At the end of the semester, all students completed an identical Final Exam to provide a basis by which to compare their relative achievements. The data collected expounds upon the details of Auto-PLC's impact towards achievement on a topic-specific basis. Additionally, learners' perceptions of digitized assessments and participation in recitation-based peer learning cohorts are discussed. © American Society for Engineering Education, 2018.		https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85051185992&partnerID=40&md5=6c17cc264fd6d56840d0004c0d67546a	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sen colab
A project-based learning approach for enhancing learning skills and motivation in software engineering	10.1145/3328778.3366891	Software engineers must be able to manage complex projects, so that skills such as teamwork, leadership or initiative are critical to their successful development. Because of this, it is fundamental that the learning of software engineering as an academic discipline provides solid links between theory and practice. Educational frameworks such as those derived from the European Higher Education Area state that student-centered approaches are a useful tool for achieving these objectives. In this context, we present a project-based learning (PBL) experience report in a software engineering program of a Spanish university. The experience is based on the formation of small heterogeneous teams, which face the initial phases of a software methodology during the development of a project close to a real one. Through a strategy of role rotation and documentation transfer, all students perform different tasks and face different challenges throughout the project. Summative assessment is also adopted, considering not only teacher ratings but also students' peer assessment. The results prove the positive effect of using PBL to improve the training of students in acquiring different skills as future software engineers. © 2020 Copyright held by the owner/author(s). Publication rights licensed to ACM.	Project based learning; Software engineering; Uml	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85081570721&doi=10.1145%2F3328778.3366891&partnerID=40&md5=9bf3bae8a4650620a9c9cc134bacf4c3	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
An investigation of the team knowledge and team performance of the Chinese engineering students in a senior technical module	10.1109/FIE.2014.7044078	Teamwork is a very important attribute for future engineers. China graduates a large number of engineering graduates every year, so it is necessary to investigate the teamwork knowledge and performance level of the Chinese engineering students, and work out a better mechanism of teamwork teaching for them. This work investigates the team knowledge and team performance of the Chinese engineering students in a Year 3 senior technical module - Software Engineering, in which teamwork skills are one of the course objectives. The test results demonstrated that the declarative knowledge of the Year 3 students on team working increased through the years of learning but it was not successfully transferred into action, the skill based outcome. It was found that the participation rate for teamwork training in the technical module was low, and students focused more on the technical production. It was suggested to include the peer rating of team citizenship with a certain percentage (5-10%) in the final coursework mark, and also a certain percentage for individual contribution (5-10%). This will switch the product oriented to both teamwork and product oriented, and the individual contribution assessment will prevent social loafing and hitchhiking. © 2014 IEEE.	Chinese students; Communication Skills; Team Knowledge; Teamwork; technical module	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84938150591&doi=10.1109%2FfIE.2014.7044078&partnerID=40&md5=61ff82be06161704aa5ac509c38960ca	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	chance

Comparative analysis of predictive analytics models in classification problems	10.1109 /APSSSE47353. 2019.00028	<p>Present research is devoted to the comparative analysis of the quality of classification for some methods of descriptive and predictive analytics in the case when most (or all) of independent variables are measured in quality scale with large amount of levels. In this case, some classification methods or their popular realizations calls for conversion of quality variables into systems of dummy variables. If quality scales have large amount of levels which are presented in almost equal proportions in the training set, i.e. it doesn't make sense to enlarge levels, above mentioned requirement will lead to the dramatically rise of problem dimension. As a result, researcher is faced with the curse of dimensionality. It means that, if the problem dimension rise, it'll be necessary to rise the sample size to preserve factors impact estimation accuracy. At the same time, it's not always possible to arrange appropriate growth of the training set volume. In some cases, it's limited by specific properties of the body of interest (system). If such situation appears, it'll be extremely important to evaluate the sensitivity of prediction/classification methods to the curse of dimensionality. Authors of this research focused on the four method of classification, which earn first lines in the lists of the popular methods of business analysis long ago. There are: • Two methods of classification tree building - CART and C4.5 • Logistic regression • Classification on the basis of random forest The first three are descriptive methods, which let's get interpreting (man ready) models, the fourth belongs to predictive analytics. Selection is not random. Descriptive analytics problems extremely important for the process of planning, when it's necessary to get answer on the question 'What will be if...?'. Particularly, one need to get target group description for organization of marketing communication. At the same time, it is quite conceivable that utilization of interpreting (man ready) models involves loss of prediction quality in comparison with methods of predictive analytics. The current research domain is the activity of microfinancing institutions (MFIs). Traditional problem here is the potential client assessment. The main challenge, which arise in the process of above mentioned problem solution, is the constraints on the volume, composition and type of data, which is available for prediction of default or default probability assessment. Thus, it's necessary to evaluate the abilities of classification methods which were designed for work with large amount of data (it means big size of the training set and a lot of variables, from which the most important should be selected). In real practice of microfinancing organization, the most of recorded factors are measured on the qualitative scales with large amount of levels, what is the origin of the above-mentioned problems. The empirical part of the research is grounded on the data of real microfinancing organization. Some hypotheses about the reasons of default were tested as byproduct of this research. © 2019 IEEE.</p>	Descriptive Analytics; Microfinance organization; Predictive Analytics; Social media analysis	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85078131254&doi=10.1109%2fAPSSSE47353.2019.00028&partnerID=40&md5=cb7c172eff2f39a74689e3416f350c3	☐	☑	sem colab
Experience with AOAB methodology in mobile computing module	10.1109 /OSSCOM. 2015.7372683	<p>This paper describes a case study of how Agent Oriented Agile Based (AOAB) development methodology was implemented in mobile computing module to create game as a part of the module assessment requirements. Games can be used in higher education in many ways to increase students participation, enable variation in how lectures are taught and to increase students interest when they create their own game. We provide a new game development methodology and integrated with mobile computing module. The experience described in this paper is based on the feedback from the module staff member, students feedback, final student report and finally module evaluation report by students. The evaluation shows that the students who used AOAB methodology provide a better result rather than groups who used Agile game development methodology in game creation. Finally, we describe the benefit of using game in higher education and how we could enhance students progress in their study. © 2015 IEEE.</p>	Adaptive development model; Agent Oriented Agile Based (AOAB); Agile methodology; Game development methodology; Multi Agent Software Engineering (MaSE); Predictive development model	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84964861366&doi=10.1109%2fOSSCOM.2015.7372683&partnerID=40&md5=933d7ffc7e31a84e87c93b01606d428	☐	☑	sem colab

A serious game to support the ISO 21500 standard education in the context of software project management	10.1016/j.csi.2018.04.012	Context: In recent years the interest in using serious games for software engineering, software process, software project management and software process standards education has increased significantly. The ISO 21500 standard is an international reference standard that provides generic guidance and good practices in project management. Objective: The objective of this work is to identify the state of the art related to the use of serious games for understanding, teaching and supporting education of the standard ISO 21500 with the goal of proposing a simulation-based serious game that supports its management processes in the context of software projects. Method: A multivocal literature review was conducted and a simulation-based serious game, called ProDec, was proposed. In addition, we analyzed the coverage of the management processes, the process and subject groups of the ISO 21500 that ProDec is able to provide, and we conducted an empirical evaluation to assess the educational effectiveness of the game in terms of motivation, user experience, and learning outcomes. Results: As a result, ProDec is able to cover 7 of the 10 subject groups and almost 75% of the project management processes of the ISO 21500 standard. Moreover, all the participants, involved in the empirical evaluation, expressed positive comments that ProDec stimulated their motivation, offered a positive user experience and promoted the learning of the management processes involved in these 7 subject groups. Conclusion: The analysis of the coverage of the ISO 21500 and the outcomes of the educational effectiveness assessment allow us to conclude that ProDec can be a helpful learning resource to be used within the learning/teaching process of the ISO 21500 standard in the context of software projects. © 2018 Elsevier B.V.	Education; Educational effectiveness evaluation; ISO 21500; Multivocal literature review; Serious games; Simulation; Software project management; Standards teaching	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85047054831&doi=10.1016%2fj.csi.2018.04.012&partnerID=40&md5=75a6b7eb4906ec897d9584705148789f	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
A structured hazard analysis and risk assessment method for automotive systems—A descriptive study	10.1016/j.res.2016.09.004	The 2011 release of the first version of the ISO 26262 standard for automotive systems demand the elicitation of safety goals following a rigorous method for hazard and risk analysis. Companies are struggling with the adoption of the standard due to ambiguities, documentation demands and the alignment of the standards demands to existing processes. We previously proposed a structured engineering method to deal with these problems developed in applying action research together with an OEM. In this work, we evaluate how applicable the method is for junior automotive software engineers by a descriptive study. We provided the method to 8 members of the master course Automotive Software Engineering (ASE) at the Technical University Munich. The participants have each been working in the automotive industry for 1–4 years in parallel to their studies. We investigated their application of our method to an electronic steering column lock system. The participants applied our method in a first round alone and afterwards discussed their results in groups. Our data analysis revealed that the participants could apply the method successfully and the hazard analysis and risk assessment achieved a high precision and productivity. Moreover, the precision could be improved significantly during group discussions. © 2016 Elsevier Ltd	Automotive; Empirical study; ISO 26262; Requirements; Safety; Structured method	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84992052014&doi=10.1016%2fj.res.2016.09.004&partnerID=40&md5=9525e38b6afe40f8a4b723daeed28095	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Motivation of computer science students at universities organized around small groups	10.1109/EDUCON.2019.8725059	The academic performance of students is affected by the academic context, their aptitudes and their motivation. The latter is particularly important in Engineering disciplines because the contents to be learnt are especially complex and many students end up having a low performance that leads them to absenteeism and drop out. The European Higher Education Area (EHEA) provides several recommendations related to the academic context (ongoing assessment, mentoring processes and active learning methods among others) that seem to have a positive impact on the students' motivation. However, these cannot always be implemented due to the high number of students per class existing at many Universities. This contribution presents an empirical case study performed with 149 Computer Science students of a University organized around small groups and innovative educational methodologies. The benefits and outcomes of this academic conditions, as well as their impact in the students' motivation, are analyzed and discussed. © 2019 IEEE.	Active learning; Computer science; Engineering; Motivation; Project based learning; Software engineering	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85067426029&doi=10.1109%2fEDUCON.2019.8725059&partnerID=40&md5=a68c5228ab6ce4f9db70d5db45f0ee0d	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

<p>LEOPARD: Identifying Vulnerable Code for Vulnerability Assessment Through Program Metrics</p>	<p>10.1109/ICSE.2019.00024</p>	<p>Identifying potentially vulnerable locations in a code base is critical as a pre-step for effective vulnerability assessment; i.e., it can greatly help security experts put their time and effort to where it is needed most. Metric-based and pattern-based methods have been presented for identifying vulnerable code. The former relies on machine learning and cannot work well due to the severe imbalance between non-vulnerable and vulnerable code or lack of features to characterize vulnerabilities. The latter needs the prior knowledge of known vulnerabilities and can only identify similar but not new types of vulnerabilities. In this paper, we propose and implement a generic, lightweight and extensible framework, LEOPARD, to identify potentially vulnerable functions through program metrics. LEOPARD requires no prior knowledge about known vulnerabilities. It has two steps by combining two sets of systematically derived metrics. First, it uses complexity metrics to group the functions in a target application into a set of bins. Then, it uses vulnerability metrics to rank the functions in each bin and identifies the top ones as potentially vulnerable. Our experimental results on 11 real-world projects have demonstrated that, LEOPARD can cover 74.0% of vulnerable functions by identifying 20% of functions as vulnerable and outperform machine learning-based and static analysis-based techniques. We further propose three applications of LEOPARD for manual code review and fuzzing, through which we discovered 22 new bugs in real applications like PHP, radare2 and FFmpeg, and eight of them are new vulnerabilities. © 2019 IEEE.</p>	<p>Fuzzing; Program Metric; Vulnerability</p>	<p>https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85072277387&doi=10.1109%2FICSE.2019.00024&partnerID=40&md5=ab10dae658886daeef5a190626e3d7dc</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<p>sem colab</p>
<p>Glass: Group learning at significant scale via WiFi-enabled learner design teams in an ECE flipped classroom</p>		<p>The Group Learning At Significant Scale (GLASS) approach is developed to increase the scalability and efficacy of student design teams during group sessions of a Flipped Classroom (FC), as well as conventional modality courses. GLASS utilizes freely-available collaboration tools to facilitate instructional delivery, assessment, and review of teams that leverage campus WiFi connectivity, along with a pedagogical approach using excerpts from actual data sheets and open Internet resources. This immersive collaborative design experience is interwoven on a weekly basis with the technical content provided via video during the preceding week. The instructor manages multiple design teams to conduct a weekly Challenge Problem during inclass time. First, students are randomized by the Learning Management System into small groups. Second, a challenge problem is provided, delivered via WiFi-enabled laptops, tablets, or smart phones, forming virtual design teams, regardless of where students are seated. Third, students utilize their WiFi enabled devices to discuss the challenge question via chatroom-style dialog channels alongside a solution whiteboard and/or figure drawing space, while utilizing open resources on the Internet to postulate a solution. Fourth, once the design team concurs that their results are complete, they submit their answers to the Learning Management System (LMS) for auto-grading and score-recording in the grade book. Credit is earned by correctly answering each designated question sub-part, which provides partial credit. Throughout the team design activity, the instructor monitors the assignment progress online in real-time, including windows for each design team showing a solution draft as it is constructed, and providing feedback via each group's designated chat channel. LMS statistics are available in real-time for the autograded answer of the first design team having a correct solution, dubbed the Pioneer Group, which receives a bonus after its group leader presents their solution to the class. GLASS was piloted within a FC-format ECE course titled Computer Organization, with an enrollment of 116 students, and also trialed within the courses Software Engineering and Healthcare Systems Engineering, having enrollments of 140 students each. Results indicate attainment of learning outcomes while making group sessions significantly more tractable for large enrollment courses and bringing useful insights to the instructor while learning is transpiring. Student perceptions indicated that 71%, 70.1%, and 60.3% of respondents agree or strongly agree that the GLASS tools/procedures were sufficiently easy to learn, that group sessions promoted useful interactions with classmates, and that the collaboration mechanisms enhanced abilities to solve engineering problems, respectively. © American Society for Engineering Education, 2017.</p>		<p>https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85030536051&partnerID=40&md5=4ddff9158496462809433ebacdd94f39</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<p>sem colab</p>

Ranking task activity in teaching software engineering	10.1109/EDUCON.2016.7474678	In this research, we investigate the possibility of applying ranking task activity in teaching and learning software engineering courses. We introduce three types of ranking tasks, conceptual-, contextual- and sequential ranking questions, which cover most core topics such as requirement analysis, architecture design and quality validation in the course. We have also done experiments on a group of students to see if ranking tasks could increase their conceptual knowledge in specific areas. Assessments were given in order to evaluate the effectiveness of this activity, showing an obvious increase in complex conceptual understanding. © 2016 IEEE.	Just-in-time Teaching; Ranking Task; Software Engineering	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84994637538&doi=10.1109%2FEDUCON.2016.7474678&partnerID=40&md5=f4e11512868b682f7a33c464e58c6a8c	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Effects of mastery learning instruction on engineering students' writing skills development and motivation	10.17323/2411-7390-2018-4-4-20-30	This study was aimed to investigate the effects of mastery learning instruction on engineering students' academic writing skills and motivation in an EFL context. The participants were software engineering and computer science first-year students, and they were selected using a multistage sampling technique. Observation, a questionnaire, and pre-and post-tests were employed as data gathering instruments. The research was designed through a time series quasi-experimental research design. The data were analysed through repeated measure ANOVA, independent t-tests, as well as descriptive statistics. The findings indicated that there was a statistical difference between the experimental and the control groups. Hence, students who participated in mastery learning instruction improved their writing skills and achieved better scores in writing skills assessment. Particularly, learners who learned through mastery learning instruction were able to develop paragraphs and essays with clear topic sentences and thesis statements. They also developed paragraphs with proper punctuation and minimized various mechanical errors that were observed during the pre-test. Furthermore, the students who engaged in mastery learning instruction had better levels of motivation. Thus, individualized instruction and continuous feedback helped them improve their engagement in writing activities. Hence, this study calls for more attention to self-paced instruction, regular feedback, assessment, and continuous support in writing classrooms. © 2018 Journal of Language and Education.All right reserved.	Engineering students; Mastery learning instruction; Motivation; Writing skills; Zone of proximity development	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85062595171&doi=10.17323%2F2411-7390-2018-4-4-20-30&partnerID=40&md5=7555aa4c5e5db8370c43032729538f75	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Collaborative and role-play strategies in software engineering learning with web 2.0 tools	10.1002/cae.21557	Software development processes are inherently complex and require the collaboration and coordination of expert teams. The acquisition of both analysis and design competences as well as social skills should thus be the leitmotiv of courses devoted to software engineering learning. However, these aspects are often ignored and excessive importance is attached to the implementation stage. The learning framework described in this article was designed to teach students these competences and skills by means of an immersive learning experience where, working in a team, each student has to play the role of a software developer and address problems linked to requirements specification, design, and the software development process as a whole. Collaborative strategies of this kind have proven to be very successful in active learning processes, to which we have added continuous assessment mechanisms based on rubrics to provide early feedback to students. Additionally, and taking into account the characteristics of the new European Space for Higher Education, we have designed an online personal learning environment (PLE) that facilitates anytime-anywhere communications and provides a suitable social space for the exchange of information, which is crucial to the success of any teamwork effort. More specifically, we propose a learning activity based on Web 2.0 services and adapted to this particular PLE. © 2012 Wiley Periodicals, Inc.	collaborative learning; role-play strategies; software engineering learning; Web 2.0	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84911393796&doi=10.1002%2Fcae.21557&partnerID=40&md5=c2d97fa166b0e28e0ac47a4353842ee5	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem avaliar

Bad blood: Managing toxic relationships through belbin roles for first year software engineering students	10.1145/3162957.3163010	The approach by most universities in pitching team-based projects at senior undergraduate level as a learning and assessment tool can be considerably risky for student success, especially if a student discovers only in their final year of study, that they overestimated the command of their soft skills, potentially leading to them failing the project. This paper reports on an initiative aimed at minimizing this risk by introducing the concept of teamwork earlier in the curriculum, particularly, at first-year level, rather than allowing senior students to be blindsided at the later and (far more) crucial stage. This approach is meant to encourage students to explore interactions with one another, identifying potential shortcomings, and encountering likely sources that often give rise to conflict in team environments. Being the "Rainbow Nation", South Africa can be particularly susceptible to disagreements borne from social differences. Because we are working with first-year students, and because they are typically busy learning to transition from high school to university, the team exercise had to be designed and implemented in such a way as to ensure that opportunities arose, enabling students to question themselves. In addition to having to develop a software solution of their choice, students were introduced to the concept of Belbin roles to better understand how different personalities positively contribute to software development teams and encouraged to assess their own personalities in this regard. Finally, we asked them to write a reflective essay in which they describe their experiences of working in a team. In some essays, reasons for challenges arising were quite detailed while many identified specific soft skills that would need attention to ensure better success on projects in the future. This was in stark contrast to an initial consensus that the students would be able to work in teams without issue. © 2017 Association for Computing Machinery.	Belbin roles; Millennials; Software engineering; Teamwork	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85042115984&doi=10.1145%2F3162957.3163010&partnerID=40&md5=d13959720bc8d79f84ddede3cf91a1a1	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Usability of mobile applications for visually impaired people: An empirical study		Background: The use of mobile devices has increased significantly in recent years becoming the main means of access to communication, learning and other services. However, users with different types of disabilities are marginalized from the benefits of mobile technology. Particularly, people with visual impairment face different challenges given the complexity of its interfaces showing that the development of these applications might not considered this group of users. Aim: From this perspective, the objective of this work is to identify the usability criteria that must be incorporated within mobile applications in order to be used by people with visual disabilities. Method: Through a Systematic Mapping Study (SMS) to investigate the attributes, techniques and tools for the usability evaluation of mobile applications for the visually impaired. Results: After the study, we identified the lack of formal models for assessing the usefulness of mobile applications for visually impaired people, forcing evaluators to use traditional evaluation models and incorporating usability attributes based on their experience. Conclusions: Finally, we conclude that the poor usability of mobile applications for blind people would appear that obeys to the lack of formal usability evaluations models for this kind of applications.	Mobile applications; Systematic mapping study; Usability; Usability assessment tools; Visual impairment	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85032390662&partnerID=40&md5=5b340bf6757ef6efa3dde738cd554d98	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Tech startup learning activities: A formative evaluation	10.1145/3194779.3194781	The Tech Startup model is an approach where students in Software Engineering and Entrepreneurship courses form interdisciplinary teams to create businesses based on software products. The model combines Agile software development with compatible practices from Lean Startup to foster collaboration on real technology startup businesses (tech startups). This paper introduces learning activities for use in the Tech Startup model intended to improve adherence to Agile and Lean Startup methodologies. This study describes a formative evaluation of the learning activities used for: project ideation, project planning, iterative delivery & feedback, and teamwork assessment. The study synthesizes responses to a questionnaire with feedback from three focus groups at the conclusion of an academic term. Based on our findings and observations, we report suggestions for encouraging innovative project ideas from Software Engineering students as well as approaches to holding students accountable for adhering to Agile practices. © 2018 ACM.	Agile; Entrepreneurship; Lean startup; Slicing pie	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85051120049&doi=10.1145%2F3194779.3194781&partnerID=40&md5=03c02b6cfe724a08e8731a8f0c35be1c	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

A grading schema for reinforcing teamwork quality in a capstone course	10.1109/ICSE-Companion. 2019.00112	We teach a capstone course on software engineering where students work in teams during one semester in a real world setting. By the end of each of the three iterations, students get a grade that takes into account several aspects including peer assessment. In the past, students with low commitment used to get only a slightly lower grade because peer assessment's weight was very low. Last semester we added a new grading rule: if the peer assessment is lower than a threshold, then such a grade would be final for the affected student(s). In this work we aim to show the effectiveness of this rule for promoting teamwork quality by recording the progression of peer assessments along the semester. We found that peer assessment decreases and is more disperse in the second iteration, but significantly improves in the third iteration. Our results suggest that the new rule is effective for improving teamwork by making students more responsible for their teammates' grades sooner in the project, when there is still time for improvement. © 2019 IEEE.	Capstone course; Peer assessment	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85071886492&doi=10.1109%2FICSE-Companion.2019.00112&partnerID=40&md5=a1f37761af0081e98d75b7d753ca802f	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
An assessment scheme for student development projects with software industry experience		Numerous attempts were taken to define criteria against which to evaluate and measure software project success. The complexity that surrounds it has been recognized by companies, however the scholarly world is yet to follow. In this article, three dimensions of success have been elicited basing on prior industrial studies: project quality, project efficiency as well as social factors (teamwork quality and learning outcomes). Copyright © 2019 for this paper by its authors.	Academic context; Capstone project; Project efficiency; Project quality; Project success; Software projects evaluation	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85074106638&partnerID=40&md5=b3ee6638091a2b24de61392f6adc8b0a	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es
From Explaining How Random Forest Classifier Predicts Learning of Software Engineering Teamwork to Guidance for Educators	10.1109/FIE.2018.8659102	This Research Full Paper builds on our previous research in Software Engineering (SE) Teamwork Assessment and Prediction project (SETAP) where we used Random Forest (RF) classifier to predict with over 70% accuracy the student learning effectiveness in software engineering teamwork based on 115 objective and quantitative Team Activity Measures (TAM). These TAM measures have been obtained from monitoring and measuring activities of 74 student teams during the creation of their final class project in a joint software engineering classes which ran concurrently at three universities (San Francisco State University, Fulda University and Florida Atlantic University) over the period of four years and, together with team outcomes, have been collected in publicly available SETAP database. In this paper, we provide much deeper analysis of how and why RF made its decisions, namely we address the explainability of our RF classification. We also provide in-depth analysis of differences in grading and behavior of local and global student teams (composed of students from multiple schools). We then use these insights to provide concrete and practical guidance to educators teaching SE teamwork in local and global classroom setting. © 2018 IEEE.	Assessment; Explainability; Global software engineering; Machine Learning; Random Forest; Software engineering teamwork education	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85063478104&doi=10.1109%2FIE.2018.8659102&partnerID=40&md5=70438058c7df20121a5133ba3d83a5d8	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Peer-Formulated Assignment Method for Experimental Projects in CS courses	10.1109/FIE.2018.8658915	New assignment methods are needed for motivating students to carry out experimental projects in computer science (CS) courses. This paper describes a study that uses the peer-formulated assignment method to improve assignment efficiency in CS experimental projects. This method requires each student or group to come up with a problem and then pick another problem from other students to solve. This exchange of problem and solution helps motivate students and leads to their enjoyable learning. Under the guidance of an instructor, students can be inspired with great interest, enhance their practical abilities, and cultivate themselves with an innovative spirit. The role of instructor is not weakened but rather becomes more important. The instructor plays a critical role in assessment. A comprehensive project consists of many design stages, which require the involvement of the instructor. This method has been applied in two CS experimental courses with comprehensive projects, namely, software engineering (SE) and digital system design (DSD). The results show that approximately a 19% improvement in passing rate and a 35% improvement in student perceptions (grade above Good) for SE course. Similar positive results can also be found for DSD course. The survey results also show that most of the students were interested in their assignment, with 81.5% positive and 14.8% no opinion. In conclusion, the peer-formulated assignment method can improve the performance of the students and has achieved a favorable level of acceptance among students. © 2018 IEEE.	Computer science education; Experimental course; Peer-formulated assignments; Undergraduate	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85063470183&doi=10.1109%2FIE.2018.8658915&partnerID=40&md5=73c67ebbf33659fd904243b0758b7a5c	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

<p>The Package Blueprint: Visually analyzing and quantifying packages dependencies</p>	<p>10.1016/j.scico.2014.02.016</p>	<p>Large object-oriented applications are structured over many packages. Packages are important but complex structural entities that are difficult to understand since they act as containers of classes, which can have many dependencies with other classes spread over multiple packages. However to be able to take decisions (e.g. refactoring and/or assessment decisions), maintainers face the challenges of managing (sorting, grouping) the massive amount of dependencies between classes spread over multiple packages. To help maintainers, there is a need for at the same time understanding, and quantifying, dependencies between classes as well as understanding how packages as containers of such classes depend on each other. In this paper, we present a visualization, named Package Blueprint, that reveals in detail package internal structure, as well as the dependencies between an observed package and its neighbors, at both package and class levels. Package blueprint aims at assisting maintainers in understanding package structure and dependencies, in particular when they focus on few packages and want to take refactoring decisions and/or to assess the structure of those packages. A package blueprint is a space filling matrix-based visualization, using two placement strategies that are enclosure and adjacency. Package blueprint is structured around the notion of surfaces that group classes and their dependencies by their packages (i.e., enclosure placement); whilst surfaces are placed next to their parent node which is the package under-analysis (i.e., adjacency placement). We present two views: one stressing how an observed package depends upon the rest of the system and another stressing how the system depends upon that package. To evaluate the contribution of package blueprint for understanding packages we performed an exploratory user study comparing package blueprint with an advanced IDE. The results show that users of package blueprint are faster in analyzing and assessing package structure. The results are proved statically significant and they show that package blueprint considerably improves the experience of standard browser users. © 2014 Elsevier B.V. All rights reserved.</p>	<p>Software comprehension; Software engineering; Software maintenance; Software visualization</p>	<p>https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84900324587&doi=10.1016%2fj.scico.2014.02.016&partnerID=40&md5=6cf9040b1ca8136b366bb05428092383</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<p>sem colab</p>
<p>Designing game-like activities to engage adult learners in higher education</p>	<p>10.1145/3012430.3012603</p>	<p>Both engagement and motivation are important factors in any learning process. Fortunately, there are different approaches worth considering during the design process of learning experiences that could help educators create engagement. One that has shown great potential is the inclusion of game design principles, or game-like experiences, in a curriculum. This paper presents the design and analysis of an e-learning activity within a software engineering course that relies on the application of such an approach as its motivational foundation from a purely educational standpoint (i.e. not as entertainment). The goal was to encourage adult learners to solve non-graded formative activities and to increase their sense of kinship to the class group. After one semester, the results revealed a positive assessment of the experience designed and student engagement. © 2016 ACM.</p>	<p>Adult learners; Elearning; Gamification; Higher education; Software engineering</p>	<p>https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85008156706&doi=10.1145%2f3012430.3012603&partnerID=40&md5=53935d79410163edba2da3ff8763eead</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<p>sem colab</p>
<p>Skill-Based Group Allocation of Students for Project-Based Learning Courses Using Genetic Algorithm: Weightless Penalty Model</p>	<p>10.1109/TALE.2018.8615338</p>	<p>In software engineering courses, project-based learning (PBL) is an essential counterpart for assessment. PBL requires a good spread of students based on their individual skills, this pushes for a successful outcome. Traditionally, the students are assigned to the group randomly by facilitators. In group assignment problem (GAP) students need to be placed in the appropriate groups encapsulating on general and specific criterions where possible to provide diversity. However, the need for a system arises where the assignment of students to groups require not only students to be based on certain criteria but also takes into account specific constraints. Constraints allow taking parameter such as skill preference in an unevenly or limited distributed skill set. For successful completion of projects, there is a need for groups that share same strength. In this paper, a generic method is proposed that uses the genetic algorithm to generate evenly balanced groups. We have employed weightless penalty function to rank the preference of certain constraints based on skills and incur a penalty if they are not satisfied. Since the benchmark datasets are unavailable, data collected from software engineering courses of our University is made available and its utilization with the proposed method is shown. © 2018 IEEE.</p>	<p>genetic algorithm; group assignment problem; penalty function; project-based learning; skill set; weightless</p>	<p>https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85062070327&doi=10.1109%2fTALE.2018.8615338&partnerID=40&md5=3af7aa2b6685f18fd114ee137ed90429</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<p>sem colab</p>

Assessing large-project courses: Model, activities, and lessons learned	10.1145/2732156	In a modern computing curriculum, large-project courses are essential to give students hands-on experience of working in a realistic software engineering project. Assessing such projects is, however, extremely challenging. There are various aspects and trade-offs of assessments that can affect course quality. Individual assessments may fairly grade individuals, but may lose focus of the project as a group activity. Extensive teacher involvement is necessary for objective assessment, but may affect the way that students work. Continuous feedback to students can enhance learning, but may be hard to combine with fair assessment. Most previous work focuses on some specific assessment aspect; in this article, we present an assessment model that consists of a collection of assessment activities, each covering different aspects. We have applied, developed, and improved these activities during a 7yr period. To evaluate the usefulness of the model, we perform questionnaire-based surveys over a 2yr period. Furthermore, we design and execute an experiment that studies to what extent students can perform fair peer assessment and to what degree the assessments of students and teachers agree. We analyze the results, discuss findings, and summarize lessons learned. © 2015 ACM.	Assessment; Project courses; Software engineering	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84954185308&doi=10.1145%2f2732156&partnerID=40&md5=c056198d1d5e084ae1d5e38222bd970a	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Methodology for the creation of interactive MicroWorlds; [Metodología para la creación de micromundos interactivos]	10.17151/kepes.2015.12.11.4	The results of the study on the design and validation of a methodology for the creation of interactive microworlds as learning support for children attending rural telecenters in Manizales (Caldas, Colombia) are presented. The theoretical search was carried out from authors dealing with visual design, educational software engineering, pedagogy and educational information technology. The method implemented was evaluation research with emphasis on educational programs through expert judgment. The data collection techniques were the survey, structured interviews and focus groups. Interdisciplinary assessment, intervention from users and expert judgment are highlighted among the findings which allowed validating a methodology in accordance with the needs of the context.	Educational information technology; Educational software; Interactivity; Interdisciplinary nature; Multimedia teaching	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84950289070&doi=10.17151%2fkepes.2015.12.11.4&partnerID=40&md5=d134eb941ef3fff622f4035bbbc5317c	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
SETAP: Software engineering teamwork assessment and prediction using machine learning	10.1109/FIE.2014.7044199	Effective teaching of teamwork skills in local and globally distributed Software Engineering (SE) teams is recognized as an important part of the education of current and future software engineers. Effective methods for assessment and early prediction of learning effectiveness in SE teamwork are not only a critical part of teaching but also of value in industrial training and project management. This paper presents a novel analytical approach to the assessment and, most importantly, the prediction of learning outcomes in SE teamwork based on data from our joint software engineering class concurrently taught at San Francisco State University (SFSU), Florida Atlantic University (FAU) and Fulda University, Germany (Fulda). Our approach focuses on assessment and prediction of SE teamwork in terms of ability of student teams to apply best SE processes and develop SE products. It differs from existing work in the following aspects: a) it develops and uses only objective and quantitative measures of team activity from multiple sources, such as statistics of student time use, software engineering tool use, and instructor observations; b) it leverages powerful machine learning (ML) techniques applied to team activity measurements to identify quantitative and objective factors which can assess and predict learning of software engineering teamwork skills at the team level. In this paper we provide the following contributions: a) we present in detail for the first time the full team activity measurement data set we developed, consisting of over 40 objective and quantitative measures extracted from student teams working on class projects; b) we present a ML framework which applies the Random Forest (RF) algorithm to the team activity measurements and team outcomes, focusing on predicting teams that are likely to fail; c) we describe in detail our now fully implemented and operational data processing pipeline, consisting of data collection methods from multiple sources, ML training database creation, and ML analysis subsystems; and finally d) we present very preliminary results of ML analysis results based on the data from our joint software engineering classes in Fall 2012, and Spring 2013, with the data from 17 student teams. While our ML training database is currently small, it continuously grows. Our preliminary results, verified with two independent accuracy measures, show that RF is able to predict SE Process and SE Product team performance in intuitively explainable manner. © 2014 IEEE.	Assessment; Education; Machine learning; Software engineering teamwork	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84938124999&doi=10.1109%2fFIE.2014.7044199&partnerID=40&md5=c6b211228a89cf77a956b14304c5a5ea	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem avaliar

Using Learning Analytics to Assess Capstone Project Teams	10.1109/MC.2016.3	Machine-learning-based analytics are an effective tool to help assess student teamwork skills and predict learning outcomes in software engineering courses. © 2016 IEEE.	assessment; Computing Education; machine learning; project management; project-based learning; software engineering; team-based learning	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84962121739&doi=10.1109%2fMC.2016.3&partnerID=40&md5=4ff86ac934efd57042eede b53cf574db	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Authentic individual assessment for team-based software engineering projects	10.1145/3377814.3381702	In order to give students an authentic learning experience and better prepare them for the life-long learning required in contemporary workplaces, educational institutions increasingly use project-based learning in teams. However, this poses the challenge of developing authentic and equitable assessment criteria that reflect individual contributions in a team-work setting without jeopardizing project outcomes. We present a novel and innovative portfolio-based assessment framework that focuses on qualitative outcomes and ensures that the level of achievement reflects a student's competency across each of the defined learning dimensions, including professional behaviour, teamwork, process and relevant contributions towards project deliverables. In this paper, we present the main motivation behind devising and introducing the framework and also reflect on the educational outcomes and challenges of implementing the framework in the context of two final year Software Engineering project units. © 2020 IEEE Computer Society. All rights reserved.		https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85093646829&doi=10.1145%2f3377814.3381702&partnerID=40&md5=6cc9ea6530d4eb5cf7745760d659a6e	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Software engineering personnel training based on CDIO		In view of the traditional educational orientation towards disciplinary knowledge with weaknesses in innovation, practice and teamwork, software engineering personnel training based on CDIO (Conceive, Design, Implement, Operate) was implemented for the software engineering major of the Department of Computer Science at Neijiang Teachers College in Sichuan, China. The reform of the curriculum, teaching, practice environment, and guarantee and assessment systems are described in detail, to provide a reference for engineering education of the software engineering discipline. © 2016 WIETE.		https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84960374823&partnerID=40&md5=204f3d32998be9bac449bea72701d34e	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
A competence graph to derive individual learning paths	10.1145/2787622.2787753	A heterogeneous group of students starts to study informatics each year. Observations show that students need individual support, to create well educated computer scientists. Unfortunately, this does not scale to large student numbers. My goal is to offer individual guidance to students in an introductory informatics class in a form that amortizes the expertise of lecturers and tutors. To that purpose I am developing a competency graph and a body of tagged practice materials. The practice materials facilitate assessment of a student's individual state of competence.	Competencies; Heterogeneity; Higher education; Learning paths; Software engineering education; Teaching methods	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84959278327&doi=10.1145%2f2787622.2787753&partnerID=40&md5=b61914d15e855ca15089212dda167d4f	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

A multi-perspective framework for evaluating software engineering education by assessing students' competencies: SECAT - A software engineering competency assessment tool	10.1109/FIE.2014.7044331	Education invariably aims at developing competencies, technical as well as non-technical ones. As a consequence, there is also a need for methods that can be used to assess the quality of education faithfully. One possible approach is an assessment of whether intended learning outcomes are achieved, i.e. an investigation if the target audience possesses the desired competencies. Assessment of competencies, however, is tricky since competencies are often only vaguely defined. This paper presents SECAT, an approach to assess competencies, and particularly those needed for proper software engineering. To that end, SECAT builds on Rauner's approach for competency assessment in vocational education. Rauner's approach uses nine competency criteria, which are further refined by suitable issues that indicate to which extent a competency is, or should be, present. The main contribution of this paper lies in the adaptation and enhancement of this framework in order to make it useable in software engineering education. Adaptation and enhancements encompass issues such as team and individual assessments, integration of multiple perspectives from various groups of stakeholders, and product- and process-orientation. The paper also presents first insights from using SECAT in a pilot university course in software engineering. © 2014 IEEE.	assessment and evaluation approaches; competence-orientation; didactical approaches; evaluation of didactical approaches; quality of teaching and learning; SECAT; software engineering; software engineering education	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84938152638&doi=10.1109%2FIEE.2014.7044331&partnerID=40&md5=183f6c9f14f932ee917f867b94228b15	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Global minimal diagnosis algorithm for repair incoherent mappings in ontology alignment	10.1109/SNPD.2018.8441046	Incoherent alignment has been a major issue on the ontology matching field. Since 2012, OAEI has its own assessment to evaluate incoherent mapping produced by ontology matching systems. Mapping repair process could automatically resolve the incoherent to coherent situation by removing some unwanted mappings from alignment. Removing unwanted mappings is called diagnosis. Diagnosis process should be done as little as possible to minimize the impact of changes in input alignment. Implementing global minimal technique minimizes the number of removed mappings and total confidence value of removed mappings as well. These both minimal focus will be the evaluator view in this research. Search algorithm has been widely used in solving various path search issues. This research implemented additional procedures into Uniform Cost Search to support minimal diagnosis optimally. The experiments used small-scale ontology with understandable concepts, that was conference track. The results of experiments show that adding reordering priority queue and interaction group procedures meets the objective of two minimal focus. This research improved Uniform Cost Search algorithm to minimally remove unwanted mappings and produce total confidence value of removed mappings. © 2018 IEEE.	incoherent alignment; minimal diagnosis; ontology matching; removed mappings; two minimal focus	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85053551261&doi=10.1109%2FSNPD.2018.8441046&partnerID=40&md5=135cce807d66a6a7cc1852a91ca71cbc	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
The impact of undergraduate mentorship on student satisfaction and engagement, teamwork performance, and team dysfunction in a software engineering group project	10.1145/3328778.3366835	Mentorship schemes in software engineering education usually involve professional software engineers guiding and advising teams of undergraduate students working collaboratively to develop a software system. With or without mentorship, teams run the risk of experiencing team dysfunction: a situation where lack of engagement, internal conflicts, and/or poor team management lead to different assessment outcomes for individual team members and overall frustration and dissatisfaction within the team. The paper describes a mentorship scheme devised as part of a 33 week software engineering group project course, where the mentors were undergraduate students who had recently completed the course successfully and possessed at least a year's experience as professional software engineers. We measure and discuss the impact the scheme had on: (1) student satisfaction and engagement, (2) team performance, and (3) team dysfunction. © 2020 Copyright held by the owner/author(s). Publication rights licensed to ACM.	Mentorship scheme; Software engineering; Teamwork	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85081563461&doi=10.1145%2F3328778.3366835&partnerID=40&md5=4c91a3c718aa72d0ac633272b7a07849	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	chance

A STEM training program to improve middle and high school vex competition outcomes		<p>The VEX Robotics International Competition, presented by the Robotics Engineering and Competition (REC) Foundation, provides an annual engineering challenge in STEM education for middle and high school students. The VEX competition promotes STEM to students and learning communities internationally while aiding the development of such skills as teamwork, leadership, presentation, and communication. This paper presents the development of a one-year afterschool course which provides middle school and high school students who had little to no experience in VEX robotics, with the knowledge and skills necessary to succeed in the VEX Robotics International Competition. This course was designed for students to work with experienced VEX competition team members after-school and weekends during the school year. The veteran team members were individuals who have experience competing on VEX high school and college teams and were able to act as coaches and mentors. The participating students were divided into teams of 10 members for the high school division and 12 members for the middle school division. During summer and winter break, students were given intensive training three days per week, which provided the necessary knowledge and skills to increase their capability in both VEX Robotics and robotics engineering. The training course incorporated the working principles of mobile robots, engineering design, computer aided design (CAD) software, mathematics, physics, computer programming, and technical writing. Throughout the course, students were given the tools and experience necessary to develop their presentation, public speaking, interview, teamwork, leadership, and communication skills. As the students continued their participation in the course, they attended local competitions and tournaments hosted by the VEX REC Foundation. Attending each of the competitions depended upon the completion of the design and implementation of three robots which could achieve the competition tasks efficiently and effectively. Once this requirement was met, students were able to test their newfound skills and knowledge while coaches and mentors evaluated the students' progress. In this paper, the VEX high school and middle school teams, named Overclock, 16099 (A, B, and M) were used to effectively test this new STEM course. The three Overclock teams consisted of a wide range of students from minimal knowledge in VEX robotics to students who had two years of VEX experience. In an overall assessment, it was found that students who participated in the course with minimal knowledge of robots were able to perform significantly better than those who had more than three years of robotics and VEX competition experience but did not participate in the course. Students involved in the program had also shown significant improvement in confidence while they are engaged in public speaking, presentation, hands-on work, or robot competition. Future improvements to the course may include student exposure to additive and subtractive manufacturing, aerial robotics, and an increased variety of electronic devices, such as Arduino and Raspberry Pi. Students who enrolled this course not only learned the knowledge and critical thinking strategies necessary to excel in the STEM field but are also facilitated with the skills necessary to pursue a career in engineering. © American Society for Engineering Education, 2019</p>		https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85078769340&partnerID=40&md5=61cc5ac41bf518c3701508b709a0746b	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Case study of EASYSKILL.CN 3D animation online education platform	10.1145/3362125.3362141	<p>This article studies 3D animation online education on EASYSKILL education platform from the perspectives of teaching resources, project standards, feedback mechanism, assessment mechanism, and effect evaluation. The application effect of project management in learning is studied. The project has achieved satisfactory results in the one-and-a-half-year practice. The project has experienced adjustment and R&D from project idea to later practice. The group is expanded from one member to fifteen members, and the skill sharing platform has also achieved good results. At present, the platform has more than 5,000 online users. By deeply exploring 3D animation online education, the platform gradually develops towards the industrialization and marketization of education, and develops an innovative path for computer animation online education. © 2019 Association for Computing Machinery.</p>	Animation online education; Project-based education; Skill sharing platforms	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85076714604&doi=10.1145%2F3362125.3362141&partnerID=40&md5=0274a5b72421440fef7687bd080a1a20	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

TEAMSCOPE: Measuring software engineering processes with teamwork telemetry	10.1145/3197091.3197107	Project-based learning is an important teaching method in software engineering education. However, it is unclear how student projects can be evaluated objectively and systematically in classrooms. Measurements used in industry, such as quality of the codebase, are not the only expected outcomes in classrooms; informative assessments in project-based learning require more details about how students behave as individuals and as a team. In this paper, we establish the importance of measuring processes in project-based software engineering courses and present metrics mined from software development tools for monitoring and observing processes to facilitate teaching. A case study at a US university confirms that 1) teams with better conformance to software development processes achieve better outcomes, and 2) our approach can be used to design metrics that serve as early detectors of violations to software development processes. Our results suggest that instructors for software engineering courses can use our approach to design process metrics for systematic, targeted, and automatic evaluation of team projects. Furthermore, metrics designed using our approach can be used as building blocks for automated systems, and thus increase the scalability of project-based software engineering courses. © 2018 Copyright held by the owner/author(s).	Project-Based Learning; Software Engineering; Teamwork	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85052022134&doi=10.1145%2F3197091.3197107&partnerID=40&md5=e01e85eb8451e4cad8c072806df18fdc	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Using NVivo to assess a program of goal-corrected empathic attunement skills: a case study in the context of higher education	10.1007/s10209-016-0476-x	This paper focuses on the use of NVivo10 in the process of assessing a developmental program in goal-corrected empathic attunement skills in the context of a psychology master's program course. The authors present the way the software supported this work and discuss how it enabled a process of moving closer to and distancing themselves from the data. The possibility to analyse data in different perspectives—cross-sectional and longitudinal—is also discussed, using qualitative research and analysing different groups of participants (cases) and different years of the program as the project research questions evolved. © 2016, Springer-Verlag Berlin Heidelberg.	Goal-corrected empathic attunement; Higher education; NVivo; Program assessment; Qualitative research	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84975113007&doi=10.1007%2Fs10209-016-0476-x&partnerID=40&md5=d8ffd07fbae8fb8caf6163e7b090d3a	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Online repository for software engineering education		The profession of software engineering is one of the faster growing in the world; in the United States, it is projected that there will be over two million unfilled computer technology positions by the year 2020. Educational institutions are working to address this increasing demand for graduates to fill the personnel vacuum. An approach being pursued by a group of researchers is to develop an open-source Cloud-based repository of teaching artifacts. The repository will be a relational database of searchable case-based material that are tied to related program/course outcomes/topics and structurally attached to assessment material. Other projects have offered similar products and services, but this project focuses on sustainability by designing a dynamic content repository with broad participation.	Curriculum; Education; Repository; Software engineering	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85042192627&partnerID=40&md5=a1168635b60fde3fe9c52d6987cd2f79	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Reverse software engineering: A sophomore-level project in computer systems		On your first day on the job with a new company, you are presented with a challenge. A piece of executable code has been found on an older server, and you must determine what the code is designed to do. In CSI 2334, 'Introduction to Computer Systems (Computer Systems) we introduce to the students a group project simulating such an event. Group projects are used frequently to provide similar learning environments that capitalize on the benefits of peer-to-peer instruction and cooperative learning. The challenge is presented, the students are put on teams, and then the work begins. This paper will document the process taken by the student teams to: φ Determine how to view a binary file. φ Determine what tools are available for use. φ Work with the tools and the executable file to determine whether the file is an old game, a piece of malicious code, or both. φ Once the nature of the binary file is known, students will 1. Modify game play, 2. Quarantine the malicious code, or 3. Both. φ Formulate a final report and presentation to be made to a panel of experts. This paper will document the process conducted by one of the student teams from the Spring 2019 semester, and the methods of assessment used to evaluate each team's results. © American Society for Engineering Education 2020.		https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85095746516&partnerID=40&md5=bd52210e02d182ecbef42e74f75e1aab	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

Teaching and learning software project management: A hands-on approach	10.1109/FIE.2015.7344412	Project management is an essential activity across several areas, including Software Engineering. Through good management it is possible to achieve deadlines, budgets goals and mainly delivering a product that meets customer expectations. Project management activity encompasses: measurement and metrics; estimation; risk analysis; schedules; tracking and control. Considering the importance of managing projects, it is necessary that courses related to Information Technology and Computer Science present to students concepts, techniques and methodology necessary to cover all project management activities. Software project management courses aim at preparing students to apply management techniques required to plan, organize, monitor and control software projects. In a nutshell, software project management focuses on process, problem and people. In this paper we proposed an approach to teaching and learning of software project management using practical activities. The intention of this work is to provide the experience of applying theoretical concepts in practical activities. The teaching and learning approach, applied since 2006 in a Computer Science course, is based on teamwork. Each team is divided into groups assuming different roles of software process development. We have set four groups, each one assuming a different role (manager; software quality assurance; analyst and designer; programmer). The team must be conducted across the software process by its manager. We use four projects, each group is in charge of managing a different project. In this paper we present the proposed approach (based on hands on activities for project management); we summarize the lessons learned by applying the approach since 2006; we present a qualitative analysis from data collect along the application. © 2015 IEEE.	Learning Project Management; Practical Activities; Teaching Methodology; Teamwork	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84960345444&doi=10.1109%2FIEE.2015.7344412&partnerID=40&md5=4e142f13e1e5f995cd453f347856dfd	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem es
Assessing students' IT professional values in a global project setting	10.1145/3231710	This research aimed at evaluating the development and use of low-cost affective domain assessment instruments, culminating with personal and group characterization of representative global information technology (IT) professional values. Values and valuing are a compelling component of Bloom's affective domain of learning for engineering education. In helping students develop professional engineering competencies, it is essential that they develop not just cognitive knowledge of something but also values related to that knowledge and the ability to express these values in professional action. However, even if some professional values are identified, understood, and expressed, assessing students' values and valuing are difficult, and assessment instruments are often difficult to develop, particularly for assessing student learning in the context of a particular course. This exploratory study aimed at examining assessment of dispositional knowledge in the context of global software engineering (GSE). It focused on the development and use of a set of instruments for assessing affective domain student learning of global IT/software engineering (SE) professional values. The project included making explicit the IT professional values of interest among the participating faculty in the form of actionable value statements. Following a process derived from Thurstone scale development, the project included validation of these statements with an expert panel as question roots, followed by the use of these questions to investigate student and alumni receiving, responding, and valuing of these professional values. The effort needed to generate questionnaires suitable for course use was relatively low; these questionnaires were deployed to students and alumni from an open-ended global software engineering project course. Students responding reported significant agreement when receiving these global values, but sent more mixed responses in responding to and valuing them. The effort helped identify several actionable IT professional values worth reinforcing in future course offerings. © 2019 Copyright is held by the owner/author(s)	Affective domain assessment; Dispositional knowledge; Engineering values assessment; Global software engineering	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85059863515&doi=10.1145%2F3231710&partnerID=40&md5=0dafd3592292985a64e564f9e550d521	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

<p>Knowledge transfer: Manageable in crisis?</p>	<p>10.1007/978-3-319-42966-3_5</p>	<p>The chapter discusses crisis-oriented patterns and practices for software development and knowledge transfer. We use a set of models to represent and manage the transfer; these are based on informing science framework and specific learning principles. We use process, data and system perspectives to describe software architecture. Our case studies include knowledge transfer from the Carnegie Mellon University masters' program in software engineering to the Russian Innopolis IT University. The CMU curriculum is integrated with project-based software development; the focus is quality and process improvement. The knowledge transfer requires special instructor training in teaching proficiency. We identified the key factors, which may inhibit technology transfer; these are differences in culture, geography and process maturity. To promote technology transfer in crisis, we suggest using multiple contexts and scaffolding, reducing overall cognitive teaching-and-learning load, establishing efficient feedback and mastering "soft" skills, such as communication, negotiations and time management. We recommend crisis-efficient metacognitive self-directed learning and addressing higher levels of Bloom's taxonomy including justification, analysis and practical application. As a result, the students learn to act as software engineering professionals and experts. Multi-context education includes hands-on learning-by-doing, "wicked" problems and "soft" skills required for crisis agility, which includes self-assessment, self-justification and self-adjustment. We also suggest a model for the knowledge transfer, which includes informing framework of transmitting and receiving sides, and the environment. For crisis, we recommend adding signal amplification, bidirectional feedback and amplitude thresholds. In crisis, successful knowledge transfer requires special training of the receiving side, which involves a number of human-related factors, such as prior knowledge, knowledge organization, feedback, mastery and practice. To ensure the learning quality, adequate bidirectional feedback-driven meta-cognitive cycle organization is very important. Both the students and the faculty should act as software engineering professionals and use their own expert-level judgment. Knowledge transfer should be multi-context and include hands-on project practice. Teamwork, communication and time management are the mission-critical "soft" skills in crisis environments, which are often complex and uncertain. Further, we suggest a high-level design pattern approach in order to model the architectures for systems-of-systems; the model includes five application levels and two data levels. We instantiate this pattern by high-level architecture outlines for systems-of-systems in oil-and-gas and nuclear power industries. © Springer International Publishing Switzerland 2016.</p>	<p>Informing science; Knowledge transfer; System-of-systems; "Soft" skills</p>	<p>https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85007185956&doi=10.1007%2F978-3-319-42966-3_5&partnerID=40&md5=5087ec2cddddd90de53677bd20b361d0c</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<p>sem colab</p>
<p>Meta-heuristic approaches to tackle Skill Based Group allocation of Students in Project Based Learning Courses</p>	<p>10.1109/CEC.2019.8789987</p>	<p>In the arena of software engineering, Project Based Learning (PBL) is one of the fundamental components of practical based assessment. PBL involves team formation where necessary skills are needed to execute the project. Traditionally, the teams were randomly allocated based on individual preferences. To cab on this issue, preference based model needs few refinements such as skills needs to be identified by the facilitator while the students provide the necessary skill data. This way, students get assigned based on their skill rather than just random allocation. In a worst case scenario for random allocation, a team can end up with a very strong team having high skills or vice versa where a team has all of its members with limited skill or few skills are missing. The group created by skill preference would allow each group to more or less have the same strength and nearly all skills would be present in a group. In this paper, a method is extended from its original to cater for other state-of-the-art optimization techniques rather than just genetic algorithm to find a method that can suit small or large dataset. The objective function takes into account the differences between the total skill set of each group with the average total skill set needed for each group and the missing skill penalty of each group is added. Missing skill penalty is incurred due to not satisfying all the constraints such as non-presence of all the skills in a group. The skill rating allows better selection of members in a software engineering course. The results discussed in this paper are from 5 courses of one university. © 2019 IEEE.</p>	<p>firefly algorithm; genetic algorithm; invasive weed optimization; particle swarm optimization; Project Based Learning; skill based</p>	<p>https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85071326830&doi=10.1109%2FCEC.2019.8789987&partnerID=40&md5=2416ee58bb913ccb9c34691c7ef8f6ca</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<p>sem colab</p>

Stochastic Coloured Petri Nets as a modelling language for complex Event Trees	10.1201/b15938-32	This paper is summarizing the outputs of the first stage of the research focused on an evaluation of suitability of Stochastic Coloured Petri Nets (SCPN) for modelling and simulation of complex Event Tree/Fault Tree models. The suggested approach is based on the basic idea to create only one complex Petri Net model of an Event Tree. This model consists of not only the studied Event Tree (ET) but also of all Fault Trees describing Pivotal Events of the ET. SCPN seem to be a very promising platform for this purpose, because they offer coloured tokens and advanced conditioning of a firing of Petri Net transitions (which represent events of trees). These features, together with a suitable software tool, which is able to work with hierarchical nets, brings stochastic Petri Net (PN) model which is easier to read (less arcs and elements than in normal PN model). A SCPN model can be processed only by simulations, not by solving any exact equations. This is caused by a complexity of relations in a model. Using simulations (e.g. Monte-Carlo) has interesting side effect in wider modelling abilities. This paper also presents examples of the usage of the proposed methodology (i.e. Event Tree for a collision between offshore supply vessels and offshore installations) including a confrontation with classical approaches. For the methodology demonstration, the TimeNet software from TU Ilmenau is used. © 2014 Taylor & Francis Group, London..		https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84973442975&doi=10.1201%2fb15938-32&partnerID=40&md5=f2d58fa5ff57f868d77ff9f42c0d4b8d	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
Findings from IAC 2013 Young Professional Workshop: Tools and project organization methodologies that can be implemented into the space sector from other industries		Applied technologies in space sector are performing complicated and challenging projects in comparison other industries. This complexity in the space sector requires new alternatives for business management and project development. Therefore, management strategies in an organization directly affect the project achievements. Project applications, improvement of economic earnings, relations among people in an organization, mentorships, motivation factors and international activities are other significant issues which are really crucial for space sector. To discuss these important issues, we were one of five groups at International Astronautical Congress, Young Professional Workshop in Beijing, 20th September 2013. Our relevant group topic was ""What tools and project organization methodologies have been and can be implemented into the space sector from other industries and the YPs' experience (e.g. software, automotive)?"". As a group we have met several times prior to the workshop. Many ideas are emerged in consequence of meetings. Pre-meeting report helped us to prepare individual materials as members thru the workshop. These different reflections were: (1) agile software and engineering issues, (2) process improvement techniques and learning from manufacturing by multiple copies of the same space platform, (3) social activities of organizations for the internal motivation, (4) TRL improvement, (5) project management and system engineering certification the examples from NASA APPEL and Aerospace Corporation, (6) technology transfer among sectors just as military-space and biology-space, (7) Experience assessment of JAXA, (8) software tools that are being used across industries. During the workshop, we simplified these findings and made the final presentation. In addition, preliminary survey questions are listed and determined after the workshop. Finally, common grounds in our final report are summarized as (1) Software development tools, (2) Process improvement techniques, (3) Project management, system engineering education and certification, (4) Company organization structures and (5) Social Activities to improve sector interest. In the final report, group recommendations are given for the each topic and presented to the IAF YP Committee. Copyright ©2014 by the International Astronautical Federation. All rights reserved.		https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84940196629&partnerID=40&md5=b1ee8d0b9979fab28e9508bf8ea4a05	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab
An Assessment model for large project courses	10.1145/2538862.2538947	Larger project courses, such as capstone projects, are essential in a modern computing curriculum. Assessing such projects is, however, extremely challenging. There are various aspects and trade-offs of assessments that can affect the quality of a project course. Individual assessments can give fair grading of individuals, but may loose focus of the project as a group activity. Extensive teacher involvement is necessary for objective assessment, but may affect the way students are working. Continuous feedback to students can enhance learning, but may be hard to combine with fair assessment. Most previous work is focusing on some specific assessment aspect, whereas we in this paper present an assessment model that consists of a collection of assessment activities, each covering different aspects. We have applied, developed, and improved these activities during a six-year period and evaluated their usefulness by performing a questionnaire-based survey.	Assessment; Project courses; Software engineering	https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84899725619&doi=10.1145%2f2538862.2538947&partnerID=40&md5=12e2b8016625b14cdf565adff2b8022f	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sem colab

